

Cubic-Type Selfie Numbers

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Abstract

By *selfie numbers*, we understand that the numbers represented by their own digits by use of certain operations, such as, *basic operations, factorial, square-root, Fibonacci sequence, Triangular numbers, etc.* In two variables, the *selfie numbers* are obtained by use of *binomial coefficients, S-gonal numbers, centered polygonal numbers, etc.* This paper brings *selfie numbers* in terms of *cubic numbers*. Some *cubic-type patterned selfie numbers* are also studied. The work is up to 5-digits numbers in *digit's order and reverse order of digits*.

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1 Introduction

This subsection brings selfie number using **S-gonal values**. This we have done in separate parts. Before let's see the definition of **S-gonal values**.

1.1 S-gonal Numbers

The general formula for **s-sides of a polygon (s-gonal)** [4, 8] is given by

$$P(n, s) = P_s(n) := \frac{n(n-1)(s-2)}{2} + n, \quad s > 2. \quad (1)$$

See below some particular cases of equation (1):

(i)

$$\text{Triangle (3-gonal): } P_3(n) = T(n) := \frac{n(n+1)}{2} \quad (2)$$

Sequence values: 1, 3, 6, 10, 15,

(ii) *This is also known by triangular numbers.*

$$\text{Square (4-gonal): } P_4(n) = Q(n) := n^2 \quad (3)$$

Sequence values: 1, 4, 9, 16, 25,

This is also known by quadratic function or quadratic numbers.

1.2 S-gonal-Type Selfie Numbers

See below some examples in **digit's order** and **reverse order of digits** of **selfie numbers** in terms of **S-gonal numbers** given in (1):

$4992 := P(4!, 9 + 9 + 2)$	$8967 := 7 \times P(P(6, \sqrt{9}), 8)$
$7744 := (P(7, 7) - 4!)^{\sqrt{4}}$	$9504 := 4! \times P(\sqrt{0! + 5!}, 9)$
$7896 := 7 \times P(8 \times \sqrt{9}, 6)$	$9744 := 4! \times P(4 \times 7, \sqrt{9})$
$65485 := -P(6, 5) + \sqrt{4} \times 8^5$	$49281 := 1 \times 8! + P(29, 4!)$
$65943 := P(6, 5) \times ((\sqrt{9})!^4 - 3)$	$49548 := -8! - P(4!, 5) + 9!/4$
$67977 := (6 + 7) \times (P(9, 7) + 7!)$	$50424 := 4! \times P(-2 + 4!, \sqrt{0! + 5!})$
$72495 := -P(7 + 2, 4) + 9!/5$	$52895 := (5 + P(9, 8))^2 - 5$
$83544 := \sqrt{P(8, 3)} \times (5! - \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{4}}$	$53995 := (5! - P(9, \sqrt{9})) \times 3!! - 5$

The symbol **P** used for **S-gonal numbers** and **P(n, s)** as given in (1). For more details refer author's work [12].

1.3 Triangular Numbers

Triangular numbers are very much famous in the literature of mathematics. The general formula to write these numbers is given by

$$T(n) = 1 + 2 + 3 + \dots = \frac{n+1}{2} = C(n+1, 2).$$

Below are some examples of **Triangular-type selfie numbers** in **digit's order** and in **reverse order of digits** [17]:

$$\begin{aligned}
 1069 &:= T(10) - T(6) + T(T(9)) & 874 &:= T(T(T(4))) - T(T(7) + 8) \\
 1081 &:= T(1 + T(08 + 1)) & 0105 &:= 50 + T(10) \\
 2887 &:= T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(8) + T(8)) + T(7) & 1155 &:= -T(T(5)) + T(51 - 1) \\
 4965 &:= T(-4 + 9) + T(-T(6) + T(T(5))) & 1224 &:= T(T(T(4)) - T(T(2))) - 2 + 1 \\
 4999 &:= 49 + T(99) & 2418 &:= T(81) - T(42) \\
 99545 &:= T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 5 & 99632 &:= 2 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9) \\
 99546 &:= T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 6. & 99633 &:= 3 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9).
 \end{aligned}$$

1.4 Quadratic-Type Selfies

The formula for **quadratic numbers** is given by

$$Q(n) := n^2, n > 0, n \in \mathbb{N}.$$

Below are some examples of selfie numbers with **quadratic-type selfie numbers**. These are in **digit's order** and **inreverse order of digits**:

$$\begin{aligned}
 48 &:= -Q(4) + Q(8) & 49 &:= Q((-9) + Q(4)) \\
 81 &:= Q(8 + 1) & 89 &:= Q(9) + 8 \\
 128 &:= 1 \times 2 \times Q(8) & 224 &:= ((Q(4) - 2) \times Q(Q(2))) \\
 292 &:= Q(Q(Q(2))) + 9 \times Q(2) & 275 &:= Q(5) \times (7 + Q(2)) \\
 322 &:= Q(Q(3) \times 2) - 2 & 736 &:= (Q((Q(6) - Q(3))) + (7)) \\
 1036 &:= 10^3 + Q(6) & 0107 &:= 7 + Q(010) \\
 1125 &:= Q(11 + Q(2)) \times 5 & 0231 &:= -((Q(13) - Q(20))) \\
 1729 &:= 1 \times 7 \times (Q(Q(Q(2))) - 9) & 1257 &:= 7 + Q(Q(5)) \times 2 \times 1 \\
 9843 &:= ((Q((-9) + Q(8))) + Q(Q(4))) \times 3 & 2239 &:= ((-Q(9) + Q((3 \times Q(Q(2)))))) + (Q(Q(2))) \\
 10025 &:= ((100^2) + Q(5)) & 08136 &:= (Q(6) + Q((Q(3) + ((1 + 80)))))) \\
 10384 &:= ((-1) - ((0 - Q(Q(3))) \times (-8))) \times (-Q(4)) & 15323 &:= (Q(Q(Q(3))) + ((Q(Q(Q(2))) + (Q(Q(3)))))) \times (Q(5) + 1)) \\
 99378 &:= (9 \times ((Q(93) + Q(Q(7))) - 8)) & 37293 &:= (-3) + (((Q(Q(9)) - Q(Q(2))) - Q(Q(7))) \times Q(3))
 \end{aligned}$$

There are many ways of representing **selfie numbers**. They can be represented in digit's order, reverse order of digits, increasing and/or decreasing order of digits, etc. These can be obtained by use of basis operations along with **factorial, square-root, Fibonacci sequence, Triangular numbers, binomial coefficients, s-gonal values, centered polygonal numbers**, etc. Below is item-wise details of author's work on **selfie numbers**. These are in **digit's order**, and in **reverse order of digits**:

1. Selfie numbers with **Basic Operations**; [10, 11];
2. Selfie numbers with **Factorial**: [22, 23];
3. Selfie numbers with **Square-root**: [9, 10];
4. Selfie numbers with **Factorial and Square-root**: [9, 10, 11];
5. Selfie numbers with **Fibonacci sequence**: [19, 20];
6. Selfie numbers with **Triangular numbers**: [17];
7. Selfie numbers with **Binomial coefficients**: [18];

8. Selfie numbers with **S-gonal numbers**: [12];
9. Selfie numbers with **Centered Polygonal**: [12];
10. Selfie numbers with **Concatenation-Type**: [13];
11. Selfie numbers with **Quadratic numbers**: [21];

The last section 4 brings the summary of **selfie numbers**.

1.5 Cubic Numbers

Similar to **quadratic-type selfie numbers**, the aim of this work is to bring selfie numbers using **cubic-type selfie numbers**. The work in **digit's order** and also in **reverse order of digits**. The formula for **cubic numbers** is given by

$$C(n) := n^3, n > 0, n \in \mathbb{N}. \quad (4)$$

Remark 1.1. The notation $C(., .)$ in two variables represent **binomial coefficients**, while the $C(.)$ in single variable represent **cubic numbers**.

2 Cubic-Type Selfie Numbers: Digit's Order

This section brings **cubic-type selfie numbers** in digit's order up to 5-digits numbers. It is divided in two subsection. The first one give consecutive and symmetric blocks of 10 or 100 numbers. The section subsection give general values.

2.1 Symmetric and Consecutive

$$250 := 2 \times C(5) + 0$$

$$251 := 2 \times C(5) + 1$$

$$252 := 2 \times C(5) + 2$$

$$253 := 2 \times C(5) + 3$$

$$254 := 2 \times C(5) + 4$$

$$255 := 2 \times C(5) + 5$$

$$256 := 2 \times C(5) + 6$$

$$257 := 2 \times C(5) + 7$$

$$258 := 2 \times C(5) + 8$$

$$259 := 2 \times C(5) + 9$$

$$370 := C(3) + C(7) + 0$$

$$371 := C(3) + C(7) + 1$$

$$372 := C(3) + C(7) + 2$$

$$373 := C(3) + C(7) + 3$$

$$374 := C(3) + C(7) + 4$$

$$375 := C(3) + C(7) + 5$$

$$376 := C(3) + C(7) + 6$$

$$377 := C(3) + C(7) + 7$$

$$378 := C(3) + C(7) + 8$$

$$379 := C(3) + C(7) + 9$$

$$1000 := C(10) + 00$$

$$1001 := C(10) + 01$$

$$1002 := C(10) + 02$$

$$1003 := C(10) + 03$$

$$1004 := C(10) + 04$$

$$1005 := C(10) + 05$$

$$1006 := C(10) + 06$$

$$1007 := C(10) + 07$$

$$1008 := C(10) + 08$$

$$1009 := C(10) + 09$$

$$1010 := C(10) + 10$$

$$1011 := C(10) + 11$$

$$1012 := C(10) + 12$$

$$1013 := C(10) + 13$$

$$1014 := C(10) + 14$$

$$1015 := C(10) + 15$$

$$1016 := C(10) + 16$$

$$1017 := C(10) + 17$$

1018 := C(10) + 18
1019 := C(10) + 19
1020 := C(10) + 20
1021 := C(10) + 21
1022 := C(10) + 22
1023 := C(10) + 23
1024 := C(10) + 24
1025 := C(10) + 25
1026 := C(10) + 26
1027 := C(10) + 27
1028 := C(10) + 28
1029 := C(10) + 29
1030 := C(10) + 30
1031 := C(10) + 31
1032 := C(10) + 32
1033 := C(10) + 33
1034 := C(10) + 34
1035 := C(10) + 35
1036 := C(10) + 36
1037 := C(10) + 37
1038 := C(10) + 38
1039 := C(10) + 39
1040 := C(10) + 40
1041 := C(10) + 41
1042 := C(10) + 42
1043 := C(10) + 43
1044 := C(10) + 44
1045 := C(10) + 45
1046 := C(10) + 46
1047 := C(10) + 47
1048 := C(10) + 48
1049 := C(10) + 49
1050 := C(10) + 00
1051 := C(10) + 51
1052 := C(10) + 52
1053 := C(10) + 53
1054 := C(10) + 54
1055 := C(10) + 55
1056 := C(10) + 56
1057 := C(10) + 57

1058 := C(10) + 58
1059 := C(10) + 59
1060 := C(10) + 60
1061 := C(10) + 61
1062 := C(10) + 62
1063 := C(10) + 63
1064 := C(10) + 64
1065 := C(10) + 65
1066 := C(10) + 66
1067 := C(10) + 67
1068 := C(10) + 68
1069 := C(10) + 69
1070 := C(10) + 70
1071 := C(10) + 71
1072 := C(10) + 72
1073 := C(10) + 73
1074 := C(10) + 74
1075 := C(10) + 75
1076 := C(10) + 76
1077 := C(10) + 77
1078 := C(10) + 78
1079 := C(10) + 79
1080 := C(10) + 80
1081 := C(10) + 81
1082 := C(10) + 82
1083 := C(10) + 83
1084 := C(10) + 84
1085 := C(10) + 85
1086 := C(10) + 86
1087 := C(10) + 87
1088 := C(10) + 88
1089 := C(10) + 89
1090 := C(10) + 90
1091 := C(10) + 91
1092 := C(10) + 92
1093 := C(10) + 93
1094 := C(10) + 94
1095 := C(10) + 95
1096 := C(10) + 96
1097 := C(10) + 97

$$1098 := C(10) + 98$$

$$1099 := C(10) + 99$$

$$2240 := C(C(2)) + C(C(2) + 4) + 0$$

$$2241 := C(C(2)) + C(C(2) + 4) + 1$$

$$2242 := C(C(2)) + C(C(2) + 4) + 2$$

$$2243 := C(C(2)) + C(C(2) + 4) + 3$$

$$2244 := C(C(2)) + C(C(2) + 4) + 4$$

$$2245 := C(C(2)) + C(C(2) + 4) + 5$$

$$2246 := C(C(2)) + C(C(2) + 4) + 6$$

$$2247 := C(C(2)) + C(C(2) + 4) + 7$$

$$2248 := C(C(2)) + C(C(2) + 4) + 8$$

$$2249 := C(C(2)) + C(C(2) + 4) + 9$$

$$2740 := C(2 \times 7) - 4 + 0$$

$$2741 := C(2 \times 7) - 4 + 1$$

$$2742 := C(2 \times 7) - 4 + 2$$

$$2743 := C(2 \times 7) - 4 + 3$$

$$2744 := C(2 \times 7) - 4 + 4$$

$$2745 := C(2 \times 7) - 4 + 5$$

$$2746 := C(2 \times 7) - 4 + 6$$

$$2747 := C(2 \times 7) - 4 + 7$$

$$2748 := C(2 \times 7) - 4 + 8$$

$$2749 := C(2 \times 7) - 4 + 9$$

$$3880 := (-C(3) + C(8)) \times 8 + 0$$

$$3881 := (-C(3) + C(8)) \times 8 + 1$$

$$3882 := (-C(3) + C(8)) \times 8 + 2$$

$$3883 := (-C(3) + C(8)) \times 8 + 3$$

$$3884 := (-C(3) + C(8)) \times 8 + 4$$

$$3885 := (-C(3) + C(8)) \times 8 + 5$$

$$3886 := (-C(3) + C(8)) \times 8 + 6$$

$$3887 := (-C(3) + C(8)) \times 8 + 7$$

$$3888 := (-C(3) + C(8)) \times 8 + 8$$

$$3889 := (-C(3) + C(8)) \times 8 + 9$$

$$4160 := C(4) + C(16) + 0$$

$$4161 := C(4) + C(16) + 1$$

$$4162 := C(4) + C(16) + 2$$

$$4163 := C(4) + C(16) + 3$$

$$4164 := C(4) + C(16) + 4$$

$$4165 := C(4) + C(16) + 5$$

$$4166 := C(4) + C(16) + 6$$

$$4167 := C(4) + C(16) + 7$$

$$4168 := C(4) + C(16) + 8$$

$$4169 := C(4) + C(16) + 9$$

$$7560 := 7 \times 5 \times C(6) + 0$$

$$7561 := 7 \times 5 \times C(6) + 1$$

$$7562 := 7 \times 5 \times C(6) + 2$$

$$7563 := 7 \times 5 \times C(6) + 3$$

$$7564 := 7 \times 5 \times C(6) + 4$$

$$7565 := 7 \times 5 \times C(6) + 5$$

$$7566 := 7 \times 5 \times C(6) + 6$$

$$7567 := 7 \times 5 \times C(6) + 7$$

$$7568 := 7 \times 5 \times C(6) + 8$$

$$7569 := 7 \times 5 \times C(6) + 9$$

$$14750 := (C(1 + 4) - 7) \times C(5) + 0$$

$$14751 := (C(1 + 4) - 7) \times C(5) + 1$$

$$14752 := (C(1 + 4) - 7) \times C(5) + 2$$

$$14753 := (C(1 + 4) - 7) \times C(5) + 3$$

$$14754 := (C(1 + 4) - 7) \times C(5) + 4$$

$$14755 := (C(1 + 4) - 7) \times C(5) + 5$$

$$14756 := (C(1 + 4) - 7) \times C(5) + 6$$

$$14757 := (C(1 + 4) - 7) \times C(5) + 7$$

$$14758 := (C(1 + 4) - 7) \times C(5) + 8$$

$$14759 := (C(1 + 4) - 7) \times C(5) + 9$$

$$15250 := (-1 + C(5) - 2) \times C(5) + 0$$

$$15251 := (-1 + C(5) - 2) \times C(5) + 1$$

$$15252 := (-1 + C(5) - 2) \times C(5) + 2$$

$$15253 := (-1 + C(5) - 2) \times C(5) + 3$$

$$15254 := (-1 + C(5) - 2) \times C(5) + 4$$

$$15255 := (-1 + C(5) - 2) \times C(5) + 5$$

$$15256 := (-1 + C(5) - 2) \times C(5) + 6$$

$$15257 := (-1 + C(5) - 2) \times C(5) + 7$$

$$15258 := (-1 + C(5) - 2) \times C(5) + 8$$

$$15259 := (-1 + C(5) - 2) \times C(5) + 9$$

$$15500 := (-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 00$$

$$15501 := (-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 01$$

$$15502 := (-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 02$$

15503 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 03$
15504 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 04$
15505 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 05$
15506 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 06$
15507 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 07$
15508 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 08$
15509 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 09$
15510 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 10$
15511 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 11$
15512 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 12$
15513 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 13$
15514 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 14$
15515 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 15$
15516 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 16$
15517 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 17$
15518 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 18$
15519 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 19$
15520 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 20$
15521 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 21$
15522 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 22$
15523 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 23$
15524 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 24$
15525 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 25$
15526 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 26$
15527 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 27$
15528 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 28$
15529 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 29$
15530 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 30$
15531 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 31$
15532 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 32$
15533 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 33$
15534 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 34$
15535 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 35$
15536 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 36$
15537 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 37$
15538 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 38$
15539 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 39$
15540 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 40$
15541 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 41$
15542 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 42$

15543 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 43$
15544 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 44$
15545 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 45$
15546 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 46$
15547 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 47$
15548 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 48$
15549 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 49$
15550 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 50$
15551 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 51$
15552 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 52$
15553 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 53$
15554 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 54$
15555 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 55$
15556 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 56$
15557 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 57$
15558 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 58$
15559 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 59$
15560 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 60$
15561 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 61$
15562 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 62$
15563 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 63$
15564 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 64$
15565 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 65$
15566 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 66$
15567 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 67$
15568 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 68$
15569 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 69$
15570 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 70$
15571 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 71$
15572 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 72$
15573 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 73$
15574 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 74$
15575 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 75$
15576 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 76$
15577 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 77$
15578 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 78$
15579 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 79$
15580 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 80$
15581 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 81$
15582 := $(-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 82$

$$\begin{aligned} 15583 &:= (-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 83 \\ 15584 &:= (-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 84 \\ 15585 &:= (-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 85 \\ 15586 &:= (-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 86 \\ 15587 &:= (-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 87 \\ 15588 &:= (-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 88 \\ 15589 &:= (-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 89 \\ 15590 &:= (-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 90 \\ 15591 &:= (-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 91 \\ 15592 &:= (-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 92 \\ 15593 &:= (-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 93 \\ 15594 &:= (-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 94 \\ 15595 &:= (-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 95 \\ 15596 &:= (-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 96 \\ 15597 &:= (-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 97 \\ 15598 &:= (-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 98 \\ 15599 &:= (-1 + C(5)) \times C(5) + 99 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 17360 &:= C(-1^7 + C(3)) - C(6) + 0 \\ 17361 &:= C(-1^7 + C(3)) - C(6) + 1 \\ 17362 &:= C(-1^7 + C(3)) - C(6) + 2 \\ 17363 &:= C(-1^7 + C(3)) - C(6) + 3 \\ 17364 &:= C(-1^7 + C(3)) - C(6) + 4 \\ 17365 &:= C(-1^7 + C(3)) - C(6) + 5 \\ 17366 &:= C(-1^7 + C(3)) - C(6) + 6 \\ 17367 &:= C(-1^7 + C(3)) - C(6) + 7 \\ 17368 &:= C(-1^7 + C(3)) - C(6) + 8 \\ 17369 &:= C(-1^7 + C(3)) - C(6) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 19630 &:= 1 - 9 \times 6 + C(C(3)) + 0 \\ 19631 &:= 1 - 9 \times 6 + C(C(3)) + 1 \\ 19632 &:= 1 - 9 \times 6 + C(C(3)) + 2 \\ 19633 &:= 1 - 9 \times 6 + C(C(3)) + 3 \\ 19634 &:= 1 - 9 \times 6 + C(C(3)) + 4 \\ 19635 &:= 1 - 9 \times 6 + C(C(3)) + 5 \\ 19636 &:= 1 - 9 \times 6 + C(C(3)) + 6 \\ 19637 &:= 1 - 9 \times 6 + C(C(3)) + 7 \\ 19638 &:= 1 - 9 \times 6 + C(C(3)) + 8 \\ 19639 &:= 1 - 9 \times 6 + C(C(3)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 21440 &:= C(2) \times (C(14) - C(4)) + 0 \\ 21441 &:= C(2) \times (C(14) - C(4)) + 1 \\ 21442 &:= C(2) \times (C(14) - C(4)) + 2 \\ 21443 &:= C(2) \times (C(14) - C(4)) + 3 \\ 21444 &:= C(2) \times (C(14) - C(4)) + 4 \\ 21445 &:= C(2) \times (C(14) - C(4)) + 5 \\ 21446 &:= C(2) \times (C(14) - C(4)) + 6 \\ 21447 &:= C(2) \times (C(14) - C(4)) + 7 \\ 21448 &:= C(2) \times (C(14) - C(4)) + 8 \\ 21449 &:= C(2) \times (C(14) - C(4)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 21960 &:= C(2) + C(1 + C(9 - 6)) + 0 \\ 21961 &:= C(2) + C(1 + C(9 - 6)) + 1 \\ 21962 &:= C(2) + C(1 + C(9 - 6)) + 2 \\ 21963 &:= C(2) + C(1 + C(9 - 6)) + 3 \\ 21964 &:= C(2) + C(1 + C(9 - 6)) + 4 \\ 21965 &:= C(2) + C(1 + C(9 - 6)) + 5 \\ 21966 &:= C(2) + C(1 + C(9 - 6)) + 6 \\ 21967 &:= C(2) + C(1 + C(9 - 6)) + 7 \\ 21968 &:= C(2) + C(1 + C(9 - 6)) + 8 \\ 21969 &:= C(2) + C(1 + C(9 - 6)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22440 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 44 + 0 \\ 22441 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 44 + 1 \\ 22442 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 44 + 2 \\ 22443 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 44 + 3 \\ 22444 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 44 + 4 \\ 22445 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 44 + 5 \\ 22446 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 44 + 6 \\ 22447 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 44 + 7 \\ 22448 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 44 + 8 \\ 22449 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 44 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 22950 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 0 \\ 22951 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 1 \\ 22952 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 2 \\ 22953 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 3 \\ 22954 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 4 \\ 22955 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 5 \\ 22956 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 6 \\ 22957 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 7 \\ 22958 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$22959 := (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 9$$

$$23870 := C(2 + C(3)) - C(8) - 7 + 0$$

$$23871 := C(2 + C(3)) - C(8) - 7 + 1$$

$$23872 := C(2 + C(3)) - C(8) - 7 + 2$$

$$23873 := C(2 + C(3)) - C(8) - 7 + 3$$

$$23874 := C(2 + C(3)) - C(8) - 7 + 4$$

$$23875 := C(2 + C(3)) - C(8) - 7 + 5$$

$$23876 := C(2 + C(3)) - C(8) - 7 + 6$$

$$23877 := C(2 + C(3)) - C(8) - 7 + 7$$

$$23878 := C(2 + C(3)) - C(8) - 7 + 8$$

$$23879 := C(2 + C(3)) - C(8) - 7 + 9$$

$$24640 := C(2^4) \times 6 + C(4) + 0$$

$$24641 := C(2^4) \times 6 + C(4) + 1$$

$$24642 := C(2^4) \times 6 + C(4) + 2$$

$$24643 := C(2^4) \times 6 + C(4) + 3$$

$$24644 := C(2^4) \times 6 + C(4) + 4$$

$$24645 := C(2^4) \times 6 + C(4) + 5$$

$$24646 := C(2^4) \times 6 + C(4) + 6$$

$$24647 := C(2^4) \times 6 + C(4) + 7$$

$$24648 := C(2^4) \times 6 + C(4) + 8$$

$$24649 := C(2^4) \times 6 + C(4) + 9$$

$$24840 := C(2 + C(4)) - C(8) - C(C(4)) + 0$$

$$24841 := C(2 + C(4)) - C(8) - C(C(4)) + 1$$

$$24842 := C(2 + C(4)) - C(8) - C(C(4)) + 2$$

$$24843 := C(2 + C(4)) - C(8) - C(C(4)) + 3$$

$$24844 := C(2 + C(4)) - C(8) - C(C(4)) + 4$$

$$24845 := C(2 + C(4)) - C(8) - C(C(4)) + 5$$

$$24846 := C(2 + C(4)) - C(8) - C(C(4)) + 6$$

$$24847 := C(2 + C(4)) - C(8) - C(C(4)) + 7$$

$$24848 := C(2 + C(4)) - C(8) - C(C(4)) + 8$$

$$24849 := C(2 + C(4)) - C(8) - C(C(4)) + 9$$

$$26250 := (2 + C(6) - C(2)) \times C(5) + 0$$

$$26251 := (2 + C(6) - C(2)) \times C(5) + 1$$

$$26252 := (2 + C(6) - C(2)) \times C(5) + 2$$

$$26253 := (2 + C(6) - C(2)) \times C(5) + 3$$

$$26254 := (2 + C(6) - C(2)) \times C(5) + 4$$

$$26255 := (2 + C(6) - C(2)) \times C(5) + 5$$

$$26256 := (2 + C(6) - C(2)) \times C(5) + 6$$

$$26257 := (2 + C(6) - C(2)) \times C(5) + 7$$

$$26258 := (2 + C(6) - C(2)) \times C(5) + 8$$

$$26259 := (2 + C(6) - C(2)) \times C(5) + 9$$

$$26350 := -2 + C(6) \times (-3 + C(5)) + 0$$

$$26351 := -2 + C(6) \times (-3 + C(5)) + 1$$

$$26352 := -2 + C(6) \times (-3 + C(5)) + 2$$

$$26353 := -2 + C(6) \times (-3 + C(5)) + 3$$

$$26354 := -2 + C(6) \times (-3 + C(5)) + 4$$

$$26355 := -2 + C(6) \times (-3 + C(5)) + 5$$

$$26356 := -2 + C(6) \times (-3 + C(5)) + 6$$

$$26357 := -2 + C(6) \times (-3 + C(5)) + 7$$

$$26358 := -2 + C(6) \times (-3 + C(5)) + 8$$

$$26359 := -2 + C(6) \times (-3 + C(5)) + 9$$

$$28560 := (-2 + C(8)) \times 56 + 0$$

$$28561 := (-2 + C(8)) \times 56 + 1$$

$$28562 := (-2 + C(8)) \times 56 + 2$$

$$28563 := (-2 + C(8)) \times 56 + 3$$

$$28564 := (-2 + C(8)) \times 56 + 4$$

$$28565 := (-2 + C(8)) \times 56 + 5$$

$$28566 := (-2 + C(8)) \times 56 + 6$$

$$28567 := (-2 + C(8)) \times 56 + 7$$

$$28568 := (-2 + C(8)) \times 56 + 8$$

$$28569 := (-2 + C(8)) \times 56 + 9$$

$$29160 := C(2 \times 9) \times (-1 + 6) + 0$$

$$29161 := C(2 \times 9) \times (-1 + 6) + 1$$

$$29162 := C(2 \times 9) \times (-1 + 6) + 2$$

$$29163 := C(2 \times 9) \times (-1 + 6) + 3$$

$$29164 := C(2 \times 9) \times (-1 + 6) + 4$$

$$29165 := C(2 \times 9) \times (-1 + 6) + 5$$

$$29166 := C(2 \times 9) \times (-1 + 6) + 6$$

$$29167 := C(2 \times 9) \times (-1 + 6) + 7$$

$$29168 := C(2 \times 9) \times (-1 + 6) + 8$$

$$29169 := C(2 \times 9) \times (-1 + 6) + 9$$

$$31250 := (3 - 1) \times C(25) + 0$$

$$31251 := (3 - 1) \times C(25) + 1$$

$$31252 := (3 - 1) \times C(25) + 2$$

$$\begin{aligned} 31253 &:= (3 - 1) \times C(25) + 3 \\ 31254 &:= (3 - 1) \times C(25) + 4 \\ 31255 &:= (3 - 1) \times C(25) + 5 \\ 31256 &:= (3 - 1) \times C(25) + 6 \\ 31257 &:= (3 - 1) \times C(25) + 7 \\ 31258 &:= (3 - 1) \times C(25) + 8 \\ 31259 &:= (3 - 1) \times C(25) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 31850 &:= C(C(3)) + C(18 + 5) + 0 \\ 31851 &:= C(C(3)) + C(18 + 5) + 1 \\ 31852 &:= C(C(3)) + C(18 + 5) + 2 \\ 31853 &:= C(C(3)) + C(18 + 5) + 3 \\ 31854 &:= C(C(3)) + C(18 + 5) + 4 \\ 31855 &:= C(C(3)) + C(18 + 5) + 5 \\ 31856 &:= C(C(3)) + C(18 + 5) + 6 \\ 31857 &:= C(C(3)) + C(18 + 5) + 7 \\ 31858 &:= C(C(3)) + C(18 + 5) + 8 \\ 31859 &:= C(C(3)) + C(18 + 5) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 32740 &:= C(32) - 7 \times 4 + 0 \\ 32741 &:= C(32) - 7 \times 4 + 1 \\ 32742 &:= C(32) - 7 \times 4 + 2 \\ 32743 &:= C(32) - 7 \times 4 + 3 \\ 32744 &:= C(32) - 7 \times 4 + 4 \\ 32745 &:= C(32) - 7 \times 4 + 5 \\ 32746 &:= C(32) - 7 \times 4 + 6 \\ 32747 &:= C(32) - 7 \times 4 + 7 \\ 32748 &:= C(32) - 7 \times 4 + 8 \\ 32749 &:= C(32) - 7 \times 4 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 32840 &:= C(32) + 8 + C(4) + 0 \\ 32841 &:= C(32) + 8 + C(4) + 1 \\ 32842 &:= C(32) + 8 + C(4) + 2 \\ 32843 &:= C(32) + 8 + C(4) + 3 \\ 32844 &:= C(32) + 8 + C(4) + 4 \\ 32845 &:= C(32) + 8 + C(4) + 5 \\ 32846 &:= C(32) + 8 + C(4) + 6 \\ 32847 &:= C(32) + 8 + C(4) + 7 \\ 32848 &:= C(32) + 8 + C(4) + 8 \\ 32849 &:= C(32) + 8 + C(4) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33280 &:= C(C(3) + 3 + 2) + C(8) + 0 \\ 33281 &:= C(C(3) + 3 + 2) + C(8) + 1 \\ 33282 &:= C(C(3) + 3 + 2) + C(8) + 2 \\ 33283 &:= C(C(3) + 3 + 2) + C(8) + 3 \\ 33284 &:= C(C(3) + 3 + 2) + C(8) + 4 \\ 33285 &:= C(C(3) + 3 + 2) + C(8) + 5 \\ 33286 &:= C(C(3) + 3 + 2) + C(8) + 6 \\ 33287 &:= C(C(3) + 3 + 2) + C(8) + 7 \\ 33288 &:= C(C(3) + 3 + 2) + C(8) + 8 \\ 33289 &:= C(C(3) + 3 + 2) + C(8) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33750 &:= C(3) \times (3 + 7) \times C(5) + 0 \\ 33751 &:= C(3) \times (3 + 7) \times C(5) + 1 \\ 33752 &:= C(3) \times (3 + 7) \times C(5) + 2 \\ 33753 &:= C(3) \times (3 + 7) \times C(5) + 3 \\ 33754 &:= C(3) \times (3 + 7) \times C(5) + 4 \\ 33755 &:= C(3) \times (3 + 7) \times C(5) + 5 \\ 33756 &:= C(3) \times (3 + 7) \times C(5) + 6 \\ 33757 &:= C(3) \times (3 + 7) \times C(5) + 7 \\ 33758 &:= C(3) \times (3 + 7) \times C(5) + 8 \\ 33759 &:= C(3) \times (3 + 7) \times C(5) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34240 &:= (3 + C(4)) \times C(C(2)) - C(4) + 0 \\ 34241 &:= (3 + C(4)) \times C(C(2)) - C(4) + 1 \\ 34242 &:= (3 + C(4)) \times C(C(2)) - C(4) + 2 \\ 34243 &:= (3 + C(4)) \times C(C(2)) - C(4) + 3 \\ 34244 &:= (3 + C(4)) \times C(C(2)) - C(4) + 4 \\ 34245 &:= (3 + C(4)) \times C(C(2)) - C(4) + 5 \\ 34246 &:= (3 + C(4)) \times C(C(2)) - C(4) + 6 \\ 34247 &:= (3 + C(4)) \times C(C(2)) - C(4) + 7 \\ 34248 &:= (3 + C(4)) \times C(C(2)) - C(4) + 8 \\ 34249 &:= (3 + C(4)) \times C(C(2)) - C(4) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 38800 &:= (-C(3) + C(8)) \times 80 + 0 \\ 38801 &:= (-C(3) + C(8)) \times 80 + 1 \\ 38802 &:= (-C(3) + C(8)) \times 80 + 2 \\ 38803 &:= (-C(3) + C(8)) \times 80 + 3 \\ 38804 &:= (-C(3) + C(8)) \times 80 + 4 \\ 38805 &:= (-C(3) + C(8)) \times 80 + 5 \\ 38806 &:= (-C(3) + C(8)) \times 80 + 6 \\ 38807 &:= (-C(3) + C(8)) \times 80 + 7 \\ 38808 &:= (-C(3) + C(8)) \times 80 + 8 \end{aligned}$$

$$38809 := (-C(3) + C(8)) \times 80 + 9$$

$$39280 := (-3 + C(9 + C(2))) \times 8 + 0$$

$$39281 := (-3 + C(9 + C(2))) \times 8 + 1$$

$$39282 := (-3 + C(9 + C(2))) \times 8 + 2$$

$$39283 := (-3 + C(9 + C(2))) \times 8 + 3$$

$$39284 := (-3 + C(9 + C(2))) \times 8 + 4$$

$$39285 := (-3 + C(9 + C(2))) \times 8 + 5$$

$$39286 := (-3 + C(9 + C(2))) \times 8 + 6$$

$$39287 := (-3 + C(9 + C(2))) \times 8 + 7$$

$$39288 := (-3 + C(9 + C(2))) \times 8 + 8$$

$$39289 := (-3 + C(9 + C(2))) \times 8 + 9$$

$$39340 := C(3) + 9 + C(34) + 0$$

$$39341 := C(3) + 9 + C(34) + 1$$

$$39342 := C(3) + 9 + C(34) + 2$$

$$39343 := C(3) + 9 + C(34) + 3$$

$$39344 := C(3) + 9 + C(34) + 4$$

$$39345 := C(3) + 9 + C(34) + 5$$

$$39346 := C(3) + 9 + C(34) + 6$$

$$39347 := C(3) + 9 + C(34) + 7$$

$$39348 := C(3) + 9 + C(34) + 8$$

$$39349 := C(3) + 9 + C(34) + 9$$

$$39430 := 3^9 + C(4) + C(C(3)) + 0$$

$$39431 := 3^9 + C(4) + C(C(3)) + 1$$

$$39432 := 3^9 + C(4) + C(C(3)) + 2$$

$$39433 := 3^9 + C(4) + C(C(3)) + 3$$

$$39434 := 3^9 + C(4) + C(C(3)) + 4$$

$$39435 := 3^9 + C(4) + C(C(3)) + 5$$

$$39436 := 3^9 + C(4) + C(C(3)) + 6$$

$$39437 := 3^9 + C(4) + C(C(3)) + 7$$

$$39438 := 3^9 + C(4) + C(C(3)) + 8$$

$$39439 := 3^9 + C(4) + C(C(3)) + 9$$

$$39630 := C(39) - 6 - C(C(3)) + 0$$

$$39631 := C(39) - 6 - C(C(3)) + 1$$

$$39632 := C(39) - 6 - C(C(3)) + 2$$

$$39633 := C(39) - 6 - C(C(3)) + 3$$

$$39634 := C(39) - 6 - C(C(3)) + 4$$

$$39635 := C(39) - 6 - C(C(3)) + 5$$

$$39636 := C(39) - 6 - C(C(3)) + 6$$

$$39637 := C(39) - 6 - C(C(3)) + 7$$

$$39638 := C(39) - 6 - C(C(3)) + 8$$

$$39639 := C(39) - 6 - C(C(3)) + 9$$

$$42750 := C(42 - 7) - C(5) + 0$$

$$42751 := C(42 - 7) - C(5) + 1$$

$$42752 := C(42 - 7) - C(5) + 2$$

$$42753 := C(42 - 7) - C(5) + 3$$

$$42754 := C(42 - 7) - C(5) + 4$$

$$42755 := C(42 - 7) - C(5) + 5$$

$$42756 := C(42 - 7) - C(5) + 6$$

$$42757 := C(42 - 7) - C(5) + 7$$

$$42758 := C(42 - 7) - C(5) + 8$$

$$42759 := C(42 - 7) - C(5) + 9$$

$$43750 := (4 + 3 + C(7)) \times C(5) + 0$$

$$43751 := (4 + 3 + C(7)) \times C(5) + 1$$

$$43752 := (4 + 3 + C(7)) \times C(5) + 2$$

$$43753 := (4 + 3 + C(7)) \times C(5) + 3$$

$$43754 := (4 + 3 + C(7)) \times C(5) + 4$$

$$43755 := (4 + 3 + C(7)) \times C(5) + 5$$

$$43756 := (4 + 3 + C(7)) \times C(5) + 6$$

$$43757 := (4 + 3 + C(7)) \times C(5) + 7$$

$$43758 := (4 + 3 + C(7)) \times C(5) + 8$$

$$43759 := (4 + 3 + C(7)) \times C(5) + 9$$

$$46640 := (-4 + C(6)) \times (C(6) + 4) + 0$$

$$46641 := (-4 + C(6)) \times (C(6) + 4) + 1$$

$$46642 := (-4 + C(6)) \times (C(6) + 4) + 2$$

$$46643 := (-4 + C(6)) \times (C(6) + 4) + 3$$

$$46644 := (-4 + C(6)) \times (C(6) + 4) + 4$$

$$46645 := (-4 + C(6)) \times (C(6) + 4) + 5$$

$$46646 := (-4 + C(6)) \times (C(6) + 4) + 6$$

$$46647 := (-4 + C(6)) \times (C(6) + 4) + 7$$

$$46648 := (-4 + C(6)) \times (C(6) + 4) + 8$$

$$46649 := (-4 + C(6)) \times (C(6) + 4) + 9$$

$$47520 := -4 + (C(7) - C(5))^2 + 0$$

$$47521 := -4 + (C(7) - C(5))^2 + 1$$

$$\begin{aligned}47522 &:= -4 + (C(7) - C(5))^2 + 2 \\47523 &:= -4 + (C(7) - C(5))^2 + 3 \\47524 &:= -4 + (C(7) - C(5))^2 + 4 \\47525 &:= -4 + (C(7) - C(5))^2 + 5 \\47526 &:= -4 + (C(7) - C(5))^2 + 6 \\47527 &:= -4 + (C(7) - C(5))^2 + 7 \\47528 &:= -4 + (C(7) - C(5))^2 + 8 \\47529 &:= -4 + (C(7) - C(5))^2 + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}49750 &:= (C(4) - 9 + C(7)) \times C(5) + 0 \\49751 &:= (C(4) - 9 + C(7)) \times C(5) + 1 \\49752 &:= (C(4) - 9 + C(7)) \times C(5) + 2 \\49753 &:= (C(4) - 9 + C(7)) \times C(5) + 3 \\49754 &:= (C(4) - 9 + C(7)) \times C(5) + 4 \\49755 &:= (C(4) - 9 + C(7)) \times C(5) + 5 \\49756 &:= (C(4) - 9 + C(7)) \times C(5) + 6 \\49757 &:= (C(4) - 9 + C(7)) \times C(5) + 7 \\49758 &:= (C(4) - 9 + C(7)) \times C(5) + 8 \\49759 &:= (C(4) - 9 + C(7)) \times C(5) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}53250 &:= (C(-5 + C(3)) + 2) \times 5 + 0 \\53251 &:= (C(-5 + C(3)) + 2) \times 5 + 1 \\53252 &:= (C(-5 + C(3)) + 2) \times 5 + 2 \\53253 &:= (C(-5 + C(3)) + 2) \times 5 + 3 \\53254 &:= (C(-5 + C(3)) + 2) \times 5 + 4 \\53255 &:= (C(-5 + C(3)) + 2) \times 5 + 5 \\53256 &:= (C(-5 + C(3)) + 2) \times 5 + 6 \\53257 &:= (C(-5 + C(3)) + 2) \times 5 + 7 \\53258 &:= (C(-5 + C(3)) + 2) \times 5 + 8 \\53259 &:= (C(-5 + C(3)) + 2) \times 5 + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}57230 &:= (C(5) - 7) \times (C(C(2)) - C(3)) + 0 \\57231 &:= (C(5) - 7) \times (C(C(2)) - C(3)) + 1 \\57232 &:= (C(5) - 7) \times (C(C(2)) - C(3)) + 2 \\57233 &:= (C(5) - 7) \times (C(C(2)) - C(3)) + 3 \\57234 &:= (C(5) - 7) \times (C(C(2)) - C(3)) + 4 \\57235 &:= (C(5) - 7) \times (C(C(2)) - C(3)) + 5 \\57236 &:= (C(5) - 7) \times (C(C(2)) - C(3)) + 6 \\57237 &:= (C(5) - 7) \times (C(C(2)) - C(3)) + 7 \\57238 &:= (C(5) - 7) \times (C(C(2)) - C(3)) + 8\end{aligned}$$

$$57239 := (C(5) - 7) \times (C(C(2)) - C(3)) + 9$$

$$\begin{aligned}62250 &:= (-6 - C(2) + C(C(2))) \times C(5) + 0 \\62251 &:= (-6 - C(2) + C(C(2))) \times C(5) + 1 \\62252 &:= (-6 - C(2) + C(C(2))) \times C(5) + 2 \\62253 &:= (-6 - C(2) + C(C(2))) \times C(5) + 3 \\62254 &:= (-6 - C(2) + C(C(2))) \times C(5) + 4 \\62255 &:= (-6 - C(2) + C(C(2))) \times C(5) + 5 \\62256 &:= (-6 - C(2) + C(C(2))) \times C(5) + 6 \\62257 &:= (-6 - C(2) + C(C(2))) \times C(5) + 7 \\62258 &:= (-6 - C(2) + C(C(2))) \times C(5) + 8 \\62259 &:= (-6 - C(2) + C(C(2))) \times C(5) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}64250 &:= (6 - 4 + C(C(2))) \times C(5) + 0 \\64251 &:= (6 - 4 + C(C(2))) \times C(5) + 1 \\64252 &:= (6 - 4 + C(C(2))) \times C(5) + 2 \\64253 &:= (6 - 4 + C(C(2))) \times C(5) + 3 \\64254 &:= (6 - 4 + C(C(2))) \times C(5) + 4 \\64255 &:= (6 - 4 + C(C(2))) \times C(5) + 5 \\64256 &:= (6 - 4 + C(C(2))) \times C(5) + 6 \\64257 &:= (6 - 4 + C(C(2))) \times C(5) + 7 \\64258 &:= (6 - 4 + C(C(2))) \times C(5) + 8 \\64259 &:= (6 - 4 + C(C(2))) \times C(5) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}65320 &:= -C(6) + (C(5) + 3) \times C(C(2)) + 0 \\65321 &:= -C(6) + (C(5) + 3) \times C(C(2)) + 1 \\65322 &:= -C(6) + (C(5) + 3) \times C(C(2)) + 2 \\65323 &:= -C(6) + (C(5) + 3) \times C(C(2)) + 3 \\65324 &:= -C(6) + (C(5) + 3) \times C(C(2)) + 4 \\65325 &:= -C(6) + (C(5) + 3) \times C(C(2)) + 5 \\65326 &:= -C(6) + (C(5) + 3) \times C(C(2)) + 6 \\65327 &:= -C(6) + (C(5) + 3) \times C(C(2)) + 7 \\65328 &:= -C(6) + (C(5) + 3) \times C(C(2)) + 8 \\65329 &:= -C(6) + (C(5) + 3) \times C(C(2)) + 9\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}72360 &:= (C(7) - 2^3) \times C(6) + 0 \\72361 &:= (C(7) - 2^3) \times C(6) + 1 \\72362 &:= (C(7) - 2^3) \times C(6) + 2 \\72363 &:= (C(7) - 2^3) \times C(6) + 3 \\72364 &:= (C(7) - 2^3) \times C(6) + 4 \\72365 &:= (C(7) - 2^3) \times C(6) + 5\end{aligned}$$

$$72366 := (C(7) - 2^3) \times C(6) + 6$$

$$72367 := (C(7) - 2^3) \times C(6) + 7$$

$$72368 := (C(7) - 2^3) \times C(6) + 8$$

$$72369 := (C(7) - 2^3) \times C(6) + 9$$

$$75680 := (C(7) + 5) \times C(6) + C(8) + 0$$

$$75681 := (C(7) + 5) \times C(6) + C(8) + 1$$

$$75682 := (C(7) + 5) \times C(6) + C(8) + 2$$

$$75683 := (C(7) + 5) \times C(6) + C(8) + 3$$

$$75684 := (C(7) + 5) \times C(6) + C(8) + 4$$

$$75685 := (C(7) + 5) \times C(6) + C(8) + 5$$

$$75686 := (C(7) + 5) \times C(6) + C(8) + 6$$

$$75687 := (C(7) + 5) \times C(6) + C(8) + 7$$

$$75688 := (C(7) + 5) \times C(6) + C(8) + 8$$

$$75689 := (C(7) + 5) \times C(6) + C(8) + 9$$

$$87880 := (C(8) - C(7)) \times (8 + C(8)) + 0$$

$$87881 := (C(8) - C(7)) \times (8 + C(8)) + 1$$

$$87882 := (C(8) - C(7)) \times (8 + C(8)) + 2$$

$$87883 := (C(8) - C(7)) \times (8 + C(8)) + 3$$

$$87884 := (C(8) - C(7)) \times (8 + C(8)) + 4$$

$$87885 := (C(8) - C(7)) \times (8 + C(8)) + 5$$

$$87886 := (C(8) - C(7)) \times (8 + C(8)) + 6$$

$$87887 := (C(8) - C(7)) \times (8 + C(8)) + 7$$

$$87888 := (C(8) - C(7)) \times (8 + C(8)) + 8$$

$$87889 := (C(8) - C(7)) \times (8 + C(8)) + 9$$

$$91250 := (C(9) + 1^2) \times C(5) + 0$$

$$91251 := (C(9) + 1^2) \times C(5) + 1$$

$$91252 := (C(9) + 1^2) \times C(5) + 2$$

$$91253 := (C(9) + 1^2) \times C(5) + 3$$

$$91254 := (C(9) + 1^2) \times C(5) + 4$$

$$91255 := (C(9) + 1^2) \times C(5) + 5$$

$$91256 := (C(9) + 1^2) \times C(5) + 6$$

$$91257 := (C(9) + 1^2) \times C(5) + 7$$

$$91258 := (C(9) + 1^2) \times C(5) + 8$$

$$91259 := (C(9) + 1^2) \times C(5) + 9$$

$$93750 := (C(9) + 3 \times 7) \times C(5) + 0$$

$$93751 := (C(9) + 3 \times 7) \times C(5) + 1$$

$$93752 := (C(9) + 3 \times 7) \times C(5) + 2$$

$$93753 := (C(9) + 3 \times 7) \times C(5) + 3$$

$$93754 := (C(9) + 3 \times 7) \times C(5) + 4$$

$$93755 := (C(9) + 3 \times 7) \times C(5) + 5$$

$$93756 := (C(9) + 3 \times 7) \times C(5) + 6$$

$$93757 := (C(9) + 3 \times 7) \times C(5) + 7$$

$$93758 := (C(9) + 3 \times 7) \times C(5) + 8$$

$$93759 := (C(9) + 3 \times 7) \times C(5) + 9$$

$$95320 := 9 \times C(-5 + C(3)) - C(C(2)) + 0$$

$$95321 := 9 \times C(-5 + C(3)) - C(C(2)) + 1$$

$$95322 := 9 \times C(-5 + C(3)) - C(C(2)) + 2$$

$$95323 := 9 \times C(-5 + C(3)) - C(C(2)) + 3$$

$$95324 := 9 \times C(-5 + C(3)) - C(C(2)) + 4$$

$$95325 := 9 \times C(-5 + C(3)) - C(C(2)) + 5$$

$$95326 := 9 \times C(-5 + C(3)) - C(C(2)) + 6$$

$$95327 := 9 \times C(-5 + C(3)) - C(C(2)) + 7$$

$$95328 := 9 \times C(-5 + C(3)) - C(C(2)) + 8$$

$$95329 := 9 \times C(-5 + C(3)) - C(C(2)) + 9$$

$$97250 := (C(9) + 7^2) \times C(5) + 0$$

$$97251 := (C(9) + 7^2) \times C(5) + 1$$

$$97252 := (C(9) + 7^2) \times C(5) + 2$$

$$97253 := (C(9) + 7^2) \times C(5) + 3$$

$$97254 := (C(9) + 7^2) \times C(5) + 4$$

$$97255 := (C(9) + 7^2) \times C(5) + 5$$

$$97256 := (C(9) + 7^2) \times C(5) + 6$$

$$97257 := (C(9) + 7^2) \times C(5) + 7$$

$$97258 := (C(9) + 7^2) \times C(5) + 8$$

$$97259 := (C(9) + 7^2) \times C(5) + 9$$

2.2 General Representations

This section brings **selfie numbers** written in terms of **cubic function** given in (4) in **digit's order**. The whole work is up to 5-digits. The numbers given below contains lot of extra brackets "()" . These can be removed easily after simplifications.

$$\begin{aligned}
 125 &:= C(1^2 \times 5) & 1116 &:= ((1 + C(11)) - C(6)) \\
 135 &:= 1 \times C(3) \times 5 & 1125 &:= ((11 - 2) \times C(5)) \\
 153 &:= 1 + C(5) + C(3) & 1216 &:= (C(((1 + C(2)) + 1)) + C(6)) \\
 163 &:= 1 + 6 \times C(3) & 1229 &:= ((-12) + C(C(2))) + (C(9)) \\
 172 &:= (1 + C(7))/2 & 1238 &:= (C((1 + C(2))) - (3 - C(8))) \\
 216 &:= C((2 - 1) \times 6) & 1239 &:= ((1 + C(C(2))) - (3 - C(9))) \\
 224 &:= C(2) + C(2 + 4) & 1255 &:= ((1 - (-2) \times C(5))) \times 5 \\
 226 &:= C(2) + 2 + C(6) & 1296 &:= (-(((1 + 2) - 9)) \times C(6)) \\
 232 &:= (2 + C(3)) \times C(2) & 1322 &:= (((-1) + C((3 + C(2)))) - C(2)) \\
 235 &:= -C(2) + 3^5 & 1323 &:= -((C(-((1 - 3))) - C((C(2) + 3)))) \\
 243 &:= C(2 + 4) + C(3) & 1325 &:= (((-1) + C((3 + C(2)))) - (5)) \\
 283 &:= 2^8 + C(3) & 1326 &:= ((1 + C((3 + C(2)))) - (6)) \\
 296 &:= 2^9 - C(6) & 1329 &:= ((1 - 3) + C((2 + 9))) \\
 316 &:= -((C(3) - C((1 + 6)))) & 1331 &:= C(((13 - 3) + 1)) \\
 317 &:= -(((C(3) - 1) - C(7))) & 1332 &:= (1 + C(((3 \times 3) + 2))) \\
 324 &:= (C(3) \times (C(2) + (4))) & 1350 &:= (((-1) \times C(3)) \times (-50)) \\
 337 &:= (-((3 + 3)) + C(7)) & 1352 &:= ((1 - C(3)) \times (-52)) \\
 384 &:= ((3 \times C(8))/4) & 1359 &:= (((-1) + C(3)) + C(5)) \times 9 \\
 407 &:= (C(4) + C(07)) & 1371 &:= (((1 + 3) \times C(7)) - 1) \\
 448 &:= -((C(4) - (C(4) \times 8))) & 1372 &:= ((1 + C(3)) \times (7^2)) \\
 512 &:= C(((5 - 1) \times 2)) & 1374 &:= (-((1 - 3)) - (C(7) \times (-4))) \\
 517 &:= (5 + C((1 + 7))) & 1375 &:= (((1 + 3) + 7) \times C(5)) \\
 518 &:= ((5 + 1) + C(8)) & 1387 &:= -((C(13) + (C(8) \times (-7)))) \\
 522 &:= ((5 \times 2) + C(C(2))) & 1394 &:= (((-1) + C(3)) \times C(9)) - C(4) \\
 549 &:= ((C(5) - C(4)) \times 9) & 1456 &:= (C((1 + 4)) + C((5 + 6))) \\
 568 &:= ((5 \times C(6)) - C(8)) & 1459 &:= ((1 + C((4 + 5))) + C(9)) \\
 585 &:= ((C(5) - 8) \times 5) & 1512 &:= (((-1) - C(5)) \times (-12)) \\
 597 &:= -(((C(5) - C(9)) + (7))) & 1532 &:= ((1 - 5) + (3 \times C(C(2)))) \\
 639 &:= ((C(6) \times 3) - 9) & 1533 &:= ((1 - C((5 + 3))) \times (-3)) \\
 655 &:= ((6 + C(5)) \times 5) & 1547 &:= (C((1 + 5)) + C((4 + 7))) \\
 729 &:= (((-7) + C(2)) \times C(9)) & 1576 &:= (C(-((1 - 5))) - (-7) \times C(6)) \\
 739 &:= ((7 + 3) + C(9)) & 1593 &:= ((1 \times 59) \times C(3)) \\
 809 &:= (80 + C(9)) & 1625 &:= ((1 + (6 \times 2)) \times C(5)) \\
 991 &:= (-9) + C((9 + 1)) & 1657 &:= ((16 \times C(5)) - C(7)) \\
 1115 &:= (C(11) - C((1 + 5))) & 1664 &:= (C(((1 \times 6) + 6)) - C(4)) \\
 & & 1672 &:= ((C((1 \times 6)) - (7)) \times C(2))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1674 &:= (C((1+6)) + C((7+4))) \\ 1714 &:= (-1) + (C(7) \times (1+4)) \\ 1715 &:= ((-1) \times C(7)) \times (-1 \times 5)) \\ 1716 &:= (1 + (C(7) \times (-1-6))) \\ 1724 &:= (C(-((1-7) \times 2))) - (4) \\ 1725 &:= (((-1) \times C(7)) - 2) \times (-5) \\ 1727 &:= (-1) + C(((7-2) + 7)) \\ 1728 &:= C((((1+7)/2) + 8)) \\ 1729 &:= (C(((1+7) + 2)) + C(9)) \\ 1734 &:= (-((1-7)) + C((3 \times 4))) \\ 1735 &:= (((-1) - C(7)) - 3) \times (-5) \\ 1752 &:= (((1 + C(7)) - C(5)) \times C(2)) \\ 1875 &:= (((1 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)) \\ 1926 &:= ((1 \times 9) \times (-2) + C(6)) \\ 1962 &:= ((1 \times 9) \times (C(6) + 2)) \\ 2044 &:= ((C(C(2)) \times 04) - (4)) \\ 2048 &:= (((2 \times 0) + 4) \times C(8)) \\ 2125 &:= (((C(2) + 1) + C(2)) \times C(5)) \\ 2169 &:= ((2 + 1) \times (-6) + C(9)) \\ 2176 &:= (-21) + C((7+6)) \\ 2193 &:= ((2 + C((1 \times 9))) \times 3) \\ 2194 &:= (-((2 + 1)) + C((9 + 4))) \\ 2195 &:= (-2) + C(-(((1-9) - 5))) \\ 2197 &:= C(((2 \times (1+9)) - 7)) \\ 2205 &:= (C(2) + C((C(2) - (0-5)))) \\ 2213 &:= ((C(2) + C(2)) + C(13)) \\ 2232 &:= (C((C(2) + (2 \times 3))) - C(C(2))) \\ 2257 &:= (((C(2) + C(C(2))) \times 5) - C(7)) \\ 2259 &:= (((2^{C(2)}) - (5)) \times 9) \\ 2296 &:= (C(2) \times (C(C(2)) + (-9) - C(6))) \\ 2297 &:= (((2^{C(2)}) \times 9) - (7)) \\ 2368 &:= ((C((2^3)) - C(6)) \times 8) \\ 2375 &:= (-((2 - (3 \times 7))) \times C(5)) \\ 2377 &:= ((C(2) \times (-3)) + (C(7) \times 7)) \\ 2385 &:= (((C(2) + C(3)) - C(8)) \times (-5)) \\ 2413 &:= (C((2+4)) + C(13)) \\ 2432 &:= ((2 \times C(4)) \times (C(3) - C(2))) \\ 2435 &:= ((-C(2)) - C((-4) + C(3)))/(-5) \\ 2455 &:= (((C(C(2)) + (4)) \times 5) - (C(5))) \\ 2456 &:= (C(C(2)) - (-((4+5)) \times C(6))) \\ 2464 &:= (-2) \times (C(4) - (6^4)) \\ 2495 &:= ((C(C(2)) - (4+9)) \times 5) \\ 2522 &:= (2 - (-5) \times (C(C(2)) - C(2))) \\ 2525 &:= ((C(C(2)) - (5+2)) \times 5) \\ 2527 &:= (((C(2) + C(5))^2)/7) \\ 2528 &:= (C(2) - (5 \times (C(2) - C(8)))) \\ 2530 &:= ((C(C(2)) \times 5) - (30)) \\ 2533 &:= ((C(C(2)) \times 5) - (3^3)) \\ 2534 &:= ((C(C(2)) - C((-5) + C(3)))/(-4)) \\ 2537 &:= (C((C(2) + (5))) - (3 - C(7))) \\ 2542 &:= (2 + (-5) \times (4 - C(C(2)))) \\ 2544 &:= ((C(C(2)) \times 5) - (4 \times 4)) \\ 2547 &:= (C(C(2)) - (-5) \times (C(4) + C(7))) \\ 2548 &:= (C(2) - (-5) \times (-4) + C(8)) \\ 2555 &:= ((C(C(2)) - (5/5)) \times 5) \\ 2560 &:= (C(C(2)) \times (5 + (6 \times 0))) \\ 2562 &:= (2 + (5 \times C((6+2)))) \\ 2563 &:= ((C(C(2)) \times 5) + (6-3)) \\ 2565 &:= ((C(C(2)) - ((5-6)) \times 5) \\ 2568 &:= ((C(C(2)) \times 5) + C(-((6-8)))) \\ 2583 &:= (C(2) + (5 \times (C(8) + 3))) \\ 2584 &:= -((C(2) \times ((C(5) - C(8)) + C(4)))) \\ 2585 &:= (25 - (C(8) \times (-5))) \\ 2587 &:= -((C(2) - (5 \times (C(8) + (7)))))) \\ 2624 &:= (((C(C(2)) \times 6) - C(C(2))) + C(4)) \\ 2654 &:= (2 \times (C((6+5)) - (4))) \\ 2655 &:= (((C(C(2)) - (6)) \times 5) + (C(5))) \\ 2656 &:= ((2 \times C((6+5))) - (6)) \\ 2672 &:= (C((C(2) + (6))) - 72) \\ 2674 &:= (2 \times (6 + C((7+4)))) \\ 2676 &:= (2 \times ((C(6) + (7)) \times 6)) \\ 2685 &:= ((C(C(2)) \times 6) - ((C(8) - C(5)))) \\ 2693 &:= (C(C(2)) - (6 - (C(9) \times 3))) \\ 2695 &:= ((C(C(2)) + C(-((6-9)))) \times 5) \\ 2699 &:= (C(C(2)) + (-((6-9)) \times C(9))) \\ 2722 &:= (C((2 \times 7)) - (22)) \\ 2724 &:= (((-2) + C(7)) \times C(2)) - (4) \\ 2728 &:= (C((2 \times 7)) - ((2 \times 8))) \\ 2736 &:= (-C(2)) + C(((7-5) + 2)) \\ 2752 &:= (C(2) + C(((7+5) + 2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 2759 &:= ((C(2) + (7)) + C((5 + 9))) \\ 2773 &:= ((2 + C((7 + 7))) + C(3)) \\ 2856 &:= (C(C(2)) + ((C(8) \times 5) - C(6))) \\ 2872 &:= (((2 \times 8) + C(7)) \times C(2)) \\ 2875 &:= (((2 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)) \\ 2912 &:= (C(2) \times ((C(9) - 1)/2)) \\ 2914 &:= (2 - ((C(9) - 1) \times (-4))) \\ 2924 &:= (2 \times ((C(9) \times 2) + (4))) \\ 2944 &:= ((-(2 \times 9)) + C(4)) \times C(4) \\ 2948 &:= ((C(2) + C(9)) \times (-4 - 8)) \\ 2968 &:= (C(C(2)) + ((9 \times C(6)) + C(8))) \\ 2969 &:= (C((C(2) + 9)) - (C(6) \times 9)) \\ 2976 &:= ((C(C(2)) - (9 + 7)) \times 6) \\ 3105 &:= (C(3) \times (-10) + C(5)) \\ 3156 &:= ((-3) + C(15)) - C(6) \\ 3157 &:= (((C(3) + 1) \times C(5)) - C(7)) \\ 3159 &:= (C(3) \times ((1 + C(5)) - 9)) \\ 3259 &:= ((3 + C(C(2))) + C((5 + 9))) \\ 3264 &:= ((3 + (C(2) \times 6)) \times C(4)) \\ 3276 &:= ((C(3) - C(27))/(-6)) \\ 3289 &:= (((3 + 2) \times C(8)) + C(9)) \\ 3329 &:= ((C(C(3)) - C((C(3) - 2))) - (C(9))) \\ 3348 &:= -((C(3) - C(((3 + 4) + 8)))) \\ 3351 &:= (3 + (C(3) \times (C(5) - 1))) \\ 3369 &:= (-((3 + 3)) + C((6 + 9))) \\ 3372 &:= (-3) + C((3 \times (7 - 2))) \\ 3375 &:= C((((3^3) - 7) - 5)) \\ 3448 &:= ((C(3) \times (C(4) + C(4))) - 8) \\ 3472 &:= (((C(3) + C(4)) + C(7)) \times C(2)) \\ 3483 &:= (C(3) \times (4 + C((8 - 3)))) \\ 3527 &:= ((C(3) + C(5)) + C((C(2) + (7)))) \\ 3572 &:= ((C(3) \times (C(5) + (7))) + C(2)) \\ 3577 &:= ((C((3 + 5)) \times 7) - (7)) \\ 3584 &:= ((3 + 5) \times (C(8) - C(4))) \\ 3591 &:= (C(3) \times (C(5) + (9 - 1))) \\ 3592 &:= ((C((3 \times 5)) + C(9)) - C(C(2))) \\ 3625 &:= (((C(3) - (6)) + C(2)) \times C(5)) \\ 3645 &:= (C((36/4)) \times 5) \\ 3648 &:= (3 \times ((C(6) - C(4)) \times 8)) \\ 3715 &:= ((-3) + C(7)) + C(15) \\ 3723 &:= ((3^7) + (C(C(2)) \times 3)) \\ 3744 &:= ((C((3 + 7)) - C(4)) \times 4) \\ 3848 &:= (((C(3) - C(8)) + (4)) \times (-8)) \\ 3875 &:= (((3 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)) \\ 3925 &:= (C((3 + 9)) + C((C(2) + (5)))) \\ 3942 &:= (C(3) \times ((9 + C(4)) \times 2)) \\ 4123 &:= (C((4 + 12)) + C(3)) \\ 4125 &:= ((41 - C(2)) \times C(5)) \\ 4128 &:= ((4 + C(C((1 \times 2)))) \times 8) \\ 4224 &:= ((C(4) \times 2) + C((2^4))) \\ 4225 &:= ((4 + C((C(2) + C(2)))) + (C(5))) \\ 4275 &:= ((C((4 \times 2)) + C(7)) \times 5) \\ 4285 &:= ((C(4) + C((2 \times 8))) + C(5)) \\ 4329 &:= (((-4) - C(3)) + C(C(2))) \times 9) \\ 4368 &:= ((C(4) + C(3)) \times (6 \times 8)) \\ 4392 &:= (((C(4) - 3) \times 9) \times C(2)) \\ 4396 &:= (4 + ((-3) - C(9)) \times (-6)) \\ 4416 &:= (C(4) \times (C(4) - (1 - 6))) \\ 4522 &:= ((C(4) + C((5 + C(2)))) \times 2) \\ 4536 &:= ((C((4 + 5)) + C(3)) \times 6) \\ 4548 &:= (-4) \times (-((5^4)) - C(8)) \\ 4575 &:= ((C(4) - C(5)) \times (-75)) \\ 4589 &:= -((C(4) - ((5 + C(8)) \times 9))) \\ 4608 &:= ((4^6) + C(08)) \\ 4625 &:= ((C(4) - C((6/2))) \times C(5)) \\ 4657 &:= ((C((4 + 6)) \times 5) - C(7)) \\ 4694 &:= -((C(4) + (-6) \times (C(9) + C(4)))) \\ 4697 &:= (((C(4) - (6)) - C(9)) \times (-7)) \\ 4829 &:= ((4 + C((8 \times 2))) + C(9)) \\ 4833 &:= (-C((4 + 8)) - (C(C(3))/(-3))) \\ 4849 &:= (-C(4) + C((C((8/4)) + 9))) \\ 4864 &:= ((4 \times 8) \times (C(6) - C(4))) \\ 4875 &:= (((4 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)) \\ 4889 &:= ((C(4) + C((8 + 8))) + C(9)) \\ 4913 &:= C((((4 + 9) + 1) + 3)) \\ 4917 &:= (4 + C(((9 + 1) + 7))) \\ 4948 &:= (4 \times ((C(9) - (4)) + C(8))) \\ 4964 &:= (-4) \times (-C(9) - C(C((6 - 4)))) \\ 4967 &:= -((C(4) - (9 \times (C(6) + C(7)))) \\ 5125 &:= (C(5) \times (1 + (C(2) \times 5))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 5129 &:= (C((5+1)) + C((C(2)+9))) \\ 5250 &:= -((C(5) \times (C(2) - (50)))) \\ 5322 &:= ((C((-5) + C(3)))/2) - 2 \\ 5324 &:= (C((5 + (3 \times 2))) \times 4) \\ 5376 &:= ((C(5) + 3) \times (7 \times 6)) \\ 5445 &:= ((C(5) - (4)) \times 45) \\ 5488 &:= ((C(5) \times 48) - C(8)) \\ 5490 &:= ((C(5) - C(4)) \times 90) \\ 5621 &:= ((5 + 6) \times (C(C(2)) - 1)) \\ 5626 &:= (((5 + 6) \times C(C(2))) - (6)) \\ 5642 &:= -(((C(5) - C(6)) \times (C(4) - 2))) \\ 5762 &:= ((C(5) \times (7 \times 6)) + C(C(2))) \\ 5819 &:= (-5) + (8 \times (-1) + C(9))) \\ 5824 &:= -(((C(5) - C((8 - 2))) \times C(4))) \\ 5827 &:= (-5) + (8 \times C((2 + 7))) \\ 5829 &:= ((5 - 8) + C((2 \times 9))) \\ 5832 &:= C((((5 + 8) + 3) + 2)) \\ 5837 &:= (5 + C(((8 + 3) + 7))) \\ 5850 &:= ((C(5) - 8) \times 50) \\ 5875 &:= (((5 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)) \\ 5899 &:= (-5) + (8 \times (9 + C(9))) \\ 5945 &:= (((C(5) \times 9) + C(4)) \times 5) \\ 5957 &:= (C(5) + C(-((9 \times (5 - 7)))))) \\ 5974 &:= (((C(5) + C(9)) \times 7) - (4)) \\ 5985 &:= ((5 \times 9) \times (8 + C(5))) \\ 6125 &:= (((6 + 1)^2) \times C(5)) \\ 6264 &:= ((C(6)/(-2)) \times (6 - C(4))) \\ 6344 &:= (C((6 \times 3)) + C((4 + 4))) \\ 6348 &:= ((C((6 \times 3)) + (4)) + C(8)) \\ 6399 &:= ((-((6 \times 3)) + C(9)) \times 9) \\ 6433 &:= (((6 \times C(4)) - C(C(3)))/(-3)) \\ 6453 &:= (((6^4) \times 5) - C(3)) \\ 6456 &:= (-6) \times (4 + (-5) \times C(6))) \\ 6550 &:= ((6 + C(5)) \times 50) \\ 6633 &:= ((-C(6)) - C(C((6 - 3))))/(-3)) \\ 6643 &:= (-C(6)) + C(-((C((6 - 4)) - C(3)))) \\ 6732 &:= ((C(6) - C(7)) + C((C(3) - C(2)))) \\ 6832 &:= ((C(6)/(-8)) + C((C(3) - C(2)))) \\ 6859 &:= C(-(((6 - 8) \times 5) - 9)) \\ 6865 &:= (6 + C(((8 + 6) + 5))) \\ 6875 &:= (((6 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)) \\ 6912 &:= (C((C(6)/9))/(1 \times 2)) \\ 6952 &:= (-C(6)) + ((9 + 5) \times C(C(2))) \\ 6966 &:= (((C(6) + C(9)) + C(6)) \times 6) \\ 7168 &:= (C((7 + 1)) \times (6 + 8)) \\ 7182 &:= (-7) \times ((1 + C(8)) \times (-2)) \\ 7196 &:= ((C(7) + C(19)) - (6)) \\ 7224 &:= ((7 \times 2) \times (C(C(2)) + (4))) \\ 7372 &:= (((-7) + C(3)) \times C(7)) + C(C(2)) \\ 7488 &:= (C(((7 \times 4) - 8)) - C(8)) \\ 7538 &:= ((C(7) \times (-5) + C(3)) - 8) \\ 7546 &:= (((-7) + C(5)) \times C(4)) - (6) \\ 7875 &:= (((7 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)) \\ 7937 &:= (-((7 \times 9)) + C((C(3) - (7)))) \\ 8125 &:= (C((8 + 12)) + C(5)) \\ 8192 &:= (C(8) \times (-((1 - 9) \times 2))) \\ 8224 &:= ((C(8) + 2) \times (2^4)) \\ 8237 &:= ((C(8) \times (-2)) + C((3 \times 7))) \\ 8375 &:= ((C(8) - (3^7)) \times (-5)) \\ 8376 &:= ((8 \times 3) \times (C(7) + (6))) \\ 8675 &:= (((-8) \times C(6)) - (7)) \times (-5) \\ 8875 &:= (((8 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)) \\ 9252 &:= (-9) + C(((C(2) + (5)) + C(2))) \\ 9261 &:= C((9 + ((2 \times 6) \times 1))) \\ 9288 &:= (9 \times ((2 \times C(8)) + 8)) \\ 9317 &:= (C(((9 + 3) - 1)) \times 7) \\ 9396 &:= -((C(9) + (-3) \times C((9 + 6)))) \\ 9425 &:= ((C(9) - (4)) \times (C(2) + (5))) \\ 9477 &:= -((C(9) \times (C(4) - 77))) \\ 9549 &:= (((9 \times C(5)) - C(4)) \times 9) \\ 9639 &:= -((C(9) - (6 \times C((3 + 9)))))) \\ 9657 &:= (9 \times ((C(6) \times 5) - (7))) \\ 9773 &:= (C(C((9 - 7))) + C((7 \times 3))) \\ 9822 &:= ((C((9 + 8)) - 2) \times 2) \\ 9823 &:= ((C((9 + 8)) \times 2) - 3) \\ 9826 &:= (C((9 + 8)) \times (C(2) - (6))) \\ 9832 &:= ((C((9 + 8)) + 3) \times 2) \\ 9872 &:= (((C(9) + C(8)) - (7)) \times C(2)) \\ 9875 &:= (((9 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)) \\ 9928 &:= (C((9 + 9)) + C((2 \times 8))) \end{aligned}$$

- 9945** := $(C(9) + (9 \times (4^5)))$
10125 := $(((10 - 1)^2) \times C(5))$
10220 := $((1 - C(C(02))) \times (-20))$
10245 := $((1 - (C(C(02)) \times (-4))) \times 5)$
10263 := $((C(10) + 2) + C((-6) + C(3)))$
10448 := $(((10^4) - C(4)) + C(8))$
10456 := $((10 \times (4^5)) + C(6))$
10512 := $((10^{5-1}) + C(C(2)))$
10522 := $((-1) - C(05)) + C(22)$
10568 := $((10 - C((5 + 6))) \times (-8))$
10584 := $((-1) - C(05)) \times (-84)$
10639 := $(C(((1 - 06) + C(3))) - 9)$
10647 := $(-1) + C(((0 - 6) + (4 \times 7)))$
10648 := $(C(((1 + 06) + 4)) \times 8)$
10653 := $(-((1 - 06)) + C((-5) + C(3)))$
10657 := $((C(10) \times (6 + 5)) - C(7))$
10658 := $(10 + C(((6 \times 5) - 8))$
10664 := $-((C(10) - ((6^6)/4)))$
10728 := $((C(10) + C(7)) - 2) \times 8$
10744 := $((C(10) + C(7)) \times (4 + 4))$
10875 := $((1 \times 087) \times C(5))$
10928 := $(C(10) + ((-C(9)) - C(C(2))) \times (-8))$
10935 := $((-1) \times C(09)) \times (-3 \times 5)$
11011 := $((1 + C(10)) \times 11)$
11125 := $((1 - (-11) \times C(2))) \times C(5)$
11224 := $(C(C((1 + 1))) + ((C(22) + C(4))))$
11253 := $(-11) - (C(C(2)) \times (5 - C(3)))$
11285 := $((C((11 \times 2)) + C(8)) + C(5))$
11348 := $((-C(11)) + C((C(3) - (4)))) + C(8)$
11375 := $((1 \times 13) \times 7) \times C(5)$
11439 := $((1 + C((-1 \times 4) + C(3))) - C(9))$
11479 := $((C(C((1 + 1))) - C(47))/(-9))$
11584 := $((C(11) + C(5)) \times 8) - C(4)$
11592 := $((-1) - C((1 \times 5))) \times (-92)$
11637 := $((11 \times C(6)) + C((3 \times 7)))$
11648 := $-(((C((1 + 1)) - C(6)) \times (C(4) - 8)))$
11663 := $(-1) - (-16) \times C((6 + 3))$
11683 := $(-C(((1 + 1) \times 6) + 8)) + C(C(3))$
11718 := $((C(11) + C(7)) \times (-1 - 8))$
11773 := $((11 \times C(7)) + C((-7) + C(3)))$
11791 := $((11 \times (C(7) + C(9))) - 1)$
11792 := $(-((1 - 17)) \times (C(9) + C(2)))$
11823 := $((-1) - C(-(1 - 8))) + C(23)$
11875 := $((11 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)$
11889 := $((C(11) \times 8) + C(8)) + C(9)$
11914 := $((C(11) \times 9) - 1) - C(4)$
11915 := $((C(11) \times 9) - C(-(1 - 5)))$
11952 := $((C(11) \times 9) - C((5 - 2)))$
11971 := $((C(11) \times 9) - (7 + 1))$
11978 := $((C(11) \times 9) + ((7 - 8)))$
11979 := $(C(((1 + 1) \times 9) - 7)) \times 9$
12097 := $((1 + C(20)) + C((9 + 7)))$
12123 := $((-1) + C(2)) \times C(12) + C(3)$
12124 := $((-1) + C(2)) \times (C(12) + (4))$
12125 := $((1 + (C(2) \times 12)) \times C(5))$
12158 := $((-1) - C(2)) + C((15 + 8))$
12159 := $((1 + C((C(2) + (15)))) - 9)$
12164 := $(-((1 + 2)) + C(-(1 - (6 \times 4))))$
12167 := $C(((1^2) \times 16) + 7)$
12168 := $(1 + C(((21 - 6) + 8)))$
12169 := $((1 \times 2) + C((-1) + (C(6)/9)))$
12176 := $((1 + C(2)) + C((17 + 6)))$
12194 := $(C((1 + 2)) + C((19 + 4)))$
12223 := $((-1) + C(2)) \times C(2) + C(23)$
12224 := $((1 + 2) \times C((C(2) + C(2)))) - C(4)$
12231 := $(C((1 + 22)) + C((3 + 1)))$
12232 := $((-1) - ((2 - C(C(2))) \times 3)) \times C(2)$
12234 := $((1 + 2) + C(23)) + C(4)$
12246 := $((1 - ((2 - C(C(2))) \times 4)) \times 6)$
12258 := $(C((1 + 2)) \times (C(C(2)) - 58))$
12264 := $((1^2) - C(C(2))) \times (-6 \times 4)$
12282 := $((1 + 2) \times (-2) + C((8 \times 2)))$
12283 := $(1 + ((-2) + C((2 \times 8))) \times 3)$
12284 := $((1 + 2) \times C((2 \times 8))) - (4)$
12285 := $((-1) + C((C(2) + C(2)))) \times (8 - 5)$
12288 := $((1^2) + 2) \times C((8 + 8))$
12289 := $(1 + (C((C(2) \times (-2 - 8))))/9)$
12295 := $((C(12) + 2) + C(9)) \times 5$
12312 := $((1 + C(C(2))) \times (C(3) - (1 + 2)))$
12323 := $((1 + (C(C(2)) \times 3)) \times C(2)) + C(3)$
12328 := $((C((-1) + C(2))) \times 3) + C(C(2)) \times 8$
12339 := $(((-1) + C(C(2))) - C(3)) \times C(3) - C(9)$
12347 := $(-1) - (-((2 + 34) \times C(7)))$
12348 := $(C((-1) + C(2))) \times (3 \times (4 + 8))$

$$\begin{aligned} 12352 &:= (((1 + C(C(2))) \times 3) + (5)) \times C(2) \\ 12364 &:= ((1 + ((C(C(2)) + 3) \times 6)) \times 4) \\ 12365 &:= (-1) + ((2 \times C(C(3))) - (C((6 \times 5)))) \\ 12368 &:= (((-1) + C((C(2) + 3))) + C(6)) \times 8 \\ 12372 &:= (12 \times ((3 \times C(7)) + 2)) \\ 12376 &:= ((C((1 \times 23)) - (7)) + C(6)) \\ 12382 &:= ((-1) + C(23)) + C((8 - 2)) \\ 12383 &:= (C((1 \times 23)) - (-8) \times C(3)) \\ 12384 &:= ((1 + 23) \times (C(8) + (4))) \\ 12393 &:= -(((C(12) - (3 \times C(9))) \times C(3))) \\ 12426 &:= (((1 - C(2)) + C(4)) \times (2 + C(6))) \\ 12473 &:= (-1) - (((2 + C(4)) \times (-7)) \times C(3)) \\ 12474 &:= ((C(((1^2) + C(4))) - (7)) - C(C(4))) \\ 12492 &:= ((-1) + C(24)) - C((9 + 2)) \\ 12529 &:= ((12 + 5) \times (C(2) + C(9))) \\ 12544 &:= ((((-1) + C(2)) + C(5)) + C(4)) \times C(4) \\ 12550 &:= ((1 - (-2) \times C(5)) \times 50) \\ 12625 &:= (((1 - C(2)) - (C(6)/(-2))) \times C(5)) \\ 12636 &:= (C(((1 + C(2)) + (6))) + C((C(3) - (6)))) \\ 12655 &:= ((1 + ((C(C(2)) - (6)) \times 5)) \times 5) \\ 12703 &:= (-1) + ((C(2) + C(70))/C(3)) \\ 12742 &:= -(((C(C((1 + 2))) + C(7)) - C((C(4)/2)))) \\ 12743 &:= (((C(12) + (7)) \times (-4)) + C(C(3))) \\ 12768 &:= ((1 + (C(2) \times 7)) \times (C(6) + 8)) \\ 12799 &:= (-1) - (C(C(2)) \times (-((7 + 9) + 9))) \\ 12823 &:= ((-1) - C((2 + 8))) + C((C(2) \times 3)) \\ 12824 &:= ((-1) \times C((2 + 8))) + C(24) \\ 12825 &:= (((1^2) + C(8)) \times 25) \\ 12832 &:= ((C(C((1 + 2))) + 8) - C((C(3) - C(2)))) \\ 12833 &:= (((1 + C(2)) - C((-8) + C(3))) + C(C(3))) \\ 12855 &:= ((1 + ((2 + C(8)) \times 5)) \times 5) \\ 12864 &:= (((1 - (2 \times 8)) + C(6)) \times C(4)) \\ 12875 &:= (((12 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)) \\ 12896 &:= (C((1 + C(2))) + (C(((8 + 9) + 6)))) \\ 12923 &:= ((C((1 + 2)) + C(9)) + C(23)) \\ 12960 &:= (((1 + C(C(2))) - (C(9))) \times (-60)) \\ 12994 &:= ((1 \times 2) \times ((9 \times C(9)) - C(4))) \\ 12997 &:= (1 - (-((2 \times 9)) \times (C(9) - (7)))) \\ 13084 &:= ((-1) - C(C(3))) - (0 - C((8 \times 4))) \\ 13085 &:= ((-1) \times C(C(3))) + (08^5) \\ 13116 &:= ((C(13) - 11) \times 6) \\ 13122 &:= (((1 \times 3)^{C(1 \times 2)}) \times 2) \\ 13123 &:= ((1 - (3^{C(1 \times 2)})) + C(C(3))) \\ 13157 &:= (((1 + 3) \times C(15)) - C(7)) \\ 13167 &:= (((-1) + C((3 + 1))) \times (C(6) - (7))) \\ 13168 &:= (((C(13) - 1) \times 6) - 8) \\ 13176 &:= ((C(13) - (1^7)) \times 6) \\ 13182 &:= (C(13) \times ((1 \times 8) - 2)) \\ 13196 &:= (C((-1) + C(3)) + ((-1) - C(9)) \times 6) \\ 13232 &:= (1 + (((3 - C(C(2))) \times (-C(3))) - C(C(2)))) \\ 13237 &:= (((1 + C(3)) \times (C(C(2)) - C(3))) - C(7)) \\ 13244 &:= ((C((13 + 2)) - C(4)) \times 4) \\ 13248 &:= (((-1) + C((3 \times 2))) \times C(4)) - C(8) \\ 13249 &:= ((1 + C((3 \times C(2)))) - (C(4) \times 9)) \\ 13256 &:= (((1 + C(3)) \times C(C(2))) + (-5) \times C(6)) \\ 13266 &:= (((C(13) + C(2)) + (6)) \times 6) \\ 13267 &:= -((C((C((1 + 3)) + 2)) - (C(67)))) \\ 13273 &:= (-13) \times (C(2) - (C(7) \times 3)) \\ 13285 &:= ((((-1) + C(3)) \times C(C(2))) - C((8 - 5))) \\ 13310 &:= (C((C(-((1 - 3))) + 3)) \times 10) \\ 13311 &:= (((-1) + C((C(3) - 3))) - C(C((1 + 1)))) \\ 13312 &:= (((-1) + C(3)) \times C(((3 + 1) \times 2)) \\ 13313 &:= ((1 + C((C(3) - 3))) - C(C(-((1 - 3)))) \\ 13326 &:= ((C(13) + (3 \times C(2))) \times 6) \\ 13338 &:= ((-13) \times C(3)) \times (-38) \\ 13339 &:= -((C(C(-((1 - 3)))) - ((C(C(3)) - C((C(3) - 9)))))) \\ 13356 &:= -(((C((1 + C(3))) - C(C(3))) - (5^6))) \\ 13357 &:= ((1 + C((C(3) - 3))) - ((C(5) + C(7)))) \\ 13375 &:= (((-1) + (C(3) \times (-3 - 7))) \times C(5)) \\ 13376 &:= (((1 + 3)^3) \times (-7) + C(6)) \\ 13377 &:= (-(((1 - 3) - 37)) \times C(7)) \\ 13382 &:= (((1 - C(3)) \times (-3) - C(8)) - C(2)) \\ 13385 &:= (((1 - C(3)) \times (-3) - C(8)) - (5)) \\ 13416 &:= (C((-1) + C(3)) - (C(4) + C(16))) \\ 13427 &:= (((-1) - C(C(3))) + C((C(4)/2))) + C(7) \\ 13432 &:= (-((C(13) - (4))) + C((C(3) - 2))) \\ 13446 &:= ((C(13) + 44) \times 6) \\ 13464 &:= ((1 + C((C(3) - (4)))) + (6^4)) \\ 13466 &:= (((-1) + C(3)) - (C(4) \times (6 - C(6)))) \\ 13468 &:= (((-1) - C(C(3))) - (C(4) \times (-6) - C(8))) \\ 13472 &:= (((-1) - C(3)) - (-4) \times C((7 + C(2)))) \\ 13480 &:= (C((-1) + C(3)) - C(-((C(4) - (80)))) \\ 13481 &:= (C(((1 + C(3)) - (4))) - C((8 - 1))) \\ 13484 &:= (C((-1) + C(3)) + ((4 - (8^4)))) \end{aligned}$$

- 13487** := $(-(13) + (4 \times C((8+7))))$
13496 := $(-((1+3)) + (4 \times C((9+6))))$
13500 := $((-1) \times C(3)) \times (-500)$
13504 := $((-1) - C((3 \times 5))) \times (0 - 4)$
13520 := $((1 - C(3)) \times (-520))$
13526 := $(-1) + (C(3) \times ((-5) + C(C(2))) - (6)))$
13529 := $((C(C(-((1-3)))) \times (5^2)) + (C(9)))$
13532 := $((1+3) \times (C((5 \times 3)) + C(2)))$
13536 := $((-1) + (-3) \times C(5)) \times (-36)$
13590 := $(((-1) + C(3)) + C(5)) \times 90$
13625 := $((1 + (3 \times (6^2))) \times C(5))$
13631 := $(-1) - ((3 - C(6)) \times C((3+1)))$
13632 := $(C(-((1-3))) \times ((C(6) - 3) \times C(2)))$
13634 := $(-((1-3)) + ((C(6) - 3) \times C(4)))$
13636 := $((1 + C(3)) + (63 \times C(6)))$
13662 := $((-1) \times C(3)) \times (6 - C((6+2)))$
13663 := $(1 - (C(3) \times (6 - C(C((6/3))))))$
13682 := $((-1) + C(C(3))) + (-6) \times C((8+2)))$
13685 := $((-1) + (C(3) \times 6)) \times 85$
13687 := $((C(13) \times 6) + C(8)) - (7)$
13694 := $(C(C(-((1-3)))) + (6 \times C((9+4))))$
13695 := $((-((1+3)) + C((C(6)/9))) - (C(5)))$
13715 := $((C(-((1-3) \times 7))) - 1) \times 5$
13720 := $((-((1-3)) \times C(7)) \times 20)$
13722 := $((C((-1) + C(3)) - (7)) + 2) \times 2$
13725 := $((1^3) + C((7 \times 2))) \times 5$
13732 := $(-((1-3)) \times (7 + C((C(3) - C(2))))$
13733 := $(-((13 \times 7)) + C((C(3) - 3)))$
13735 := $((C(-((1-3) \times 7))) + 3) \times 5$
13736 := $((C((1 + C(3))) - C((-7) + C(3))) - C(6))$
13742 := $(-1) + (C(3) \times (-((7-4) + C(C(2))))$
13743 := $((C(C(-((1-3)))) - (7-4)) \times C(3))$
13752 := $((1+3) + (C(7) \times 5)) \times C(2)$
13761 := $(1 + (C(-((3-7))) \times (C(6) - 1)))$
13768 := $(C(-((1-3))) \times (-7 - (C(6) \times (-8))))$
13785 := $((13 + (C(7) \times 8)) \times 5)$
13798 := $((1 - C(3)) + C(((7+9) + 8)))$
13812 := $(C(((1 \times 3) \times 8)) - 12)$
13816 := $((-1) + C((3 \times 8))) - (1 + 6)$
13817 := $((-1) + C((3 \times 8))) + ((1 - 7))$
13818 := $((1 + C((3 \times 8))) + ((1 - 8)))$
13821 := $(-((1 \times 3)) + C((8 \times (2 + 1))))$
13822 := $((-1) + C((3 \times 8))) - (2/2)$
13823 := $((1 - C((3 \times 8))) \times (2 - 3))$
13824 := $C(((1^3 \times 8) \times 24))$
13825 := $(1 + C(((38/2) + 5)))$
13826 := $(-((1-3)) + C(((8/2) \times 6)))$
13827 := $((1 \times 3) - (C(8) \times (-27)))$
13828 := $((1+3) + C(((8 \times 2) + 8)))$
13831 := $((-1) + C((3 \times 8))) + C((3 - 1))$
13832 := $((-1) + C((3 \times 8))) + (3^2)$
13833 := $(C(((1 \times 3) \times 8)) + (3 \times 3))$
13834 := $((((1-3) + C(8)) \times C(3)) + C(4))$
13845 := $((1 + C((3 \times 8))) + ((4 \times 5)))$
13848 := $((-((1 \times 3)) - C((8+4))) \times (-8))$
13852 := $((1 + C(3)) + C((8 \times (5 - 2))))$
13867 := $((1 + C((3 \times 8))) + (6 \times 7))$
13869 := $((-1) + ((3 \times C(8)) + (6))) \times 9$
13872 := $((-1) + C((3 \times 8))) + ((7^2))$
13875 := $((13 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)$
13879 := $(1 + (C(3) \times (C(8) - ((7 - 9))))$
13888 := $(C((1 + 3)) + C(((8+8) + 8)))$
13892 := $((C((1 + C(3))) + (8 \times C(9)))/2)$
13955 := $((((1 + 3) \times C(9)) - C(5)) \times 5)$
13958 := $(-1) + ((3 \times 9) \times (5 + C(8)))$
13986 := $((1 \times 3) \times 9) \times (C(8) + (6))$
14079 := $(-1) - (-40) \times (C(7) + 9)$
14125 := $((C((1 + 4)) - 12) \times C(5))$
14162 := $(1 + ((C((4 + 1)) - (6)^2))$
14165 := $((1 + C(4)) \times C((1 \times 6))) + C(5)$
14167 := $(C(((1 \times 4) \times 1) \times 6)) + C(7)$
14168 := $((1 + C((4 - 1))) \times (-6) + C(8))$
14224 := $((14 \times 2) \times (C(C(2)) - (4)))$
14232 := $((C(14) \times (2 + 3)) + C(C(2)))$
14256 := $((-1) + C(4)) - ((2 - 5)) \times C(6)$
14282 := $((C(-((1 - 4))) \times (-2) + C(8)) + C(C(2)))$
14283 := $((1 + (4^2)) + C(8)) \times C(3)$
14287 := $((-1) + (-4) \times (-2) + C(8)) \times (-7)$
14322 := $((-14) + C((3 \times C(2)))) + C(C(2))$
14328 := $((-1) + C((4 \times 3))) \times C(2) + C(8)$
14332 := $((-((1 \times 4)) + C((C(3) - 3))) + C(C(2)))$
14364 := $((C(((1 + 4) \times 3)) + C(6)) \times 4)$
14365 := $((1 + (4^3)) \times (C(6) + (5)))$
14375 := $((C((1 + 4)) - (3 + 7)) \times C(5))$

- 14399** := $(-1) + (C(4) \times (C(-((3-9))) + 9))$
14463 := $(-1) + (C(4) \times (C(4) + (6 \times C(3))))$
14464 := $((14-4) + C(6)) \times C(4)$
14466 := $((-((1-4)) + C(4)) \times C(6)) - (6)$
14495 := $((-1) + (-4) \times (4 - C(9))) \times 5$
14499 := $(C(C(-((1-4)))) - (C(4) \times (9 \times 9)))$
14525 := $((C((1+4)) - (5))^2) + C(5)$
14529 := $((-1) + (-4) \times C(5)) \times (-29)$
14559 := $(-1) - (-4) \times (-5) - (-5) \times C(9))$
14573 := $((1 + C((4+5))) \times (-7)) + C(C(3))$
14581 := $(1 + ((4 \times 5) \times C((8+1))))$
14593 := $(1 + (-4) \times ((-5) \times C(9)) - 3)$
14594 := $(14 + ((-5) \times C(9)) \times (-4))$
14616 := $((-1) + C(4)) \times (C(6) + (16))$
14624 := $((1 + C(4)) \times (C(6) + C(2))) + C(4)$
14625 := $((-1) \times C((4+6))) + C(25)$
14637 := $((-1) + C(4)) \times C(6) + (3 \times C(7))$
14678 := $((-1) + C((4 \times 6))) + C(7) + C(8)$
14685 := $((1 + C(4)) \times (C(6) + 8)) + C(5)$
14688 := $(C(-((1-4))) \times (68 \times 8))$
14689 := $(1 - ((-4) \times C(6)) \times (8+9))$
14695 := $((-1) + (-4) \times (-6 - C(9))) \times 5$
14739 := $(C(((1+47) + 3)))/9$
14765 := $((C(14) - (7)) + C(6)) \times 5$
14768 := $((C((1 \times 4)) + (7)) \times (C(6) - 8))$
14784 := $((1 + (4 \times 7)) \times C(8)) - C(4)$
14796 := $((C(-((1-4))) - (7)) \times C(9)) + C(6)$
14824 := $((C((1+4)) \times 8) + C(24))$
14832 := $-((C(14) - C(((8 \times 3) + 2))))$
14848 := $(1 + ((4 \times 8) - 4)) \times C(8)$
14875 := $((14 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)$
14892 := $((1 \times 4) + 8) \times (C(9) + C(C(2)))$
14893 := $(1 - (-4) \times ((C(8) + C(9)) \times 3))$
14895 := $(C(C(-((1-4)))) - (C((8+9)) - C(5)))$
14923 := $((C(-((1-4))) - (C(9))) + C((-2) + C(3)))$
14935 := $((C(14) - (-9) \times C(3)) \times 5)$
14986 := $(C(C(-((1-4)))) - (C((9+8)) - C(6)))$
15112 := $((-1) + C((5^{1+1}))) - C(C(2))$
15120 := $((-1) - C(5)) \times (-120)$
15125 := $((-1) + C(5)) - (1+2) \times C(5)$
15157 := $((-1) + C(5)) \times C((1 \times 5)) - C(7)$
15192 := $((C(15) + 1) \times (-9))/(-2)$
15227 := $((((-1) + C(5)) - 2)^2) + C(7)$
15238 := $((1 + C(5)) \times C((2+3))) - C(8)$
15246 := $((1 + (5 \times (C(C(2)) - (4)))) \times 6)$
15264 := $((C(-((1-5))) + C(2)) \times (C(6) - (4)))$
15276 := $((C(((1 \times 5)^2)) - C(7)) - (6))$
15281 := $((-1) + C((5^2))) - C((8-1))$
15285 := $(-15) \times ((-2) \times C(8)) + (5)$
15288 := $((-1) + C(5))^2 - (88)$
15309 := $((-((1+5)) + C(3)) \times C(09))$
15330 := $((1 - C((5+3))) \times (-30))$
15336 := $((C((1 \times 5)) - C(3)) - C(3)) \times C(6)$
15365 := $((-1) + (C((5+3)) \times (-6))) \times (-5)$
15367 := $((1 - C(5)) + 3) \times (C(6) - C(7))$
15372 := $((-1) - C(5)) \times (3 - C((7-2)))$
15376 := $((-1) + C(5))^{3-7+6}$
15424 := $((-1) - ((C(5) - (4)) \times (-2))) \times C(4)$
15426 := $((-1) - C(5)) + ((C(4) + C(2)) \times C(6))$
15435 := $((C((1 + (5 \times 4))))/3) \times 5$
15463 := $((1 - C(5)) - (4^6)) + C(C(3))$
15486 := $((1 + (-5) \times (-4 - C(8))) \times 6)$
15492 := $((-1) + C(5)) \times C(-((4-9))) - C(2)$
15495 := $((-1) + C(5)) \times C(-((4-9))) - (5)$
15619 := $(-((1+5)) + C((6+19)))$
15625 := $C(((1+5) - 6) + 25)$
15627 := $((1 + (5^6)) + C(2)) - (7)$
15629 := $(-1) + ((5 \times 6) \times (C(C(2)) + 9))$
15631 := $((1+5) + C(-((6-31)))$
15652 := $((1 \times 5)^6) + C((5-2))$
15653 := $((1 + C(((5 \times 6) - 5))) + C(3))$
15675 := $(-15) \times ((C(6) - (7)) \times (-5))$
15678 := $((-15) + C(6)) \times 78$
15686 := $((1 + (5 \times 6)) \times (C(8) - (6)))$
15723 := $((1 + C(5)) \times C((7-2))) - C(3)$
15736 := $((-((1-5))^7) - (3 \times C(6)))$
15752 := $-(((C((1+5)) - C(7)) - C((5^2))))$
15756 := $((-1) + C(5)) + (7 + (5^6))$
15848 := $(C((-1) + C(-((5-8)))) - (C((4+8))))$
15868 := $((1 + C(5))^{8-6}) - 8$
15872 := $((1 - 5) + 8)^7 - C(C(2))$
15875 := $((C(15) \times (-8)) + C((7 \times 5)))$
15884 := $((-1) \times C(5)) + C((8+8)) \times 4$
15903 := $(-((1-590)) \times C(3))$

$$\begin{aligned} 15936 &:= (C(-((1-5))) \times ((9 \times C(3)) + (6))) \\ 15952 &:= (((1+5) \times C((9+5))) - C(C(2))) \\ 15993 &:= (((1 \times 5) \times (-9) - C(9))) + C(C(3)) \\ 16224 &:= ((-((1-6)) - C(C(2))) \times (C(2) \times (-4))) \\ 16243 &:= (((1-C(6)) \times (2^4)) + C(C(3))) \\ 16253 &:= ((C((1+6)) \times (-2 \times 5)) + C(C(3))) \\ 16259 &:= -((C(-((1-6))) - (2^{5+9}))) \\ 16263 &:= (C(16) + C((26-3))) \\ 16264 &:= ((-1) - (C(6)/(-2))) \times (C(6) - C(4)) \\ 16272 &:= (16 \times ((C(C(2)) - (7)) + C(C(2)))) \\ 16273 &:= -((C(16) - (2 \times C(7)))) + C(C(3)) \\ 16275 &:= (((1-C(6)) - 2) \times (-75)) \\ 16285 &:= (((1+C((6+C(2)))) + C(8)) \times 5) \\ 16315 &:= (((1+6) + C(C(3))) - C(15)) \\ 16355 &:= ((1+C((6+3))) + C((5 \times 5))) \\ 16375 &:= ((-16) \times C(3)) + (7^5) \\ 16379 &:= (((-1) - C(6)) + C(C(3))) - (C(7) \times 9) \\ 16382 &:= (((-((1-6)) + C(3)) \times C(8)) - 2) \\ 16443 &:= ((1 - ((C(6) - C(4)) \times (-4))) \times C(3)) \\ 16444 &:= (((C(16) \times 4) + C(4)) - (4)) \\ 16445 &:= (((C(16) \times 4) - C(4)) + C(5)) \\ 16448 &:= ((C(16) \times 4) + C(-((4-8)))) \\ 16463 &:= (-1) + (6 \times C(-((4 - (6 \times 3)))))) \\ 16464 &:= ((1 \times 6) \times C(((4+6) + 4))) \\ 16465 &:= (1 + (6 \times C(((C(4) + (6))/5)))) \\ 16472 &:= (((-16) + C(4)) \times C(7)) + C(2) \\ 16475 &:= ((C((1 \times 6)) + (4^7)) - C(5)) \\ 16487 &:= (-1) + (-6) \times (-4) + (-8) \times C(7) \\ 16489 &:= (1 + ((C(6) + (-4) \times C(8))) \times (-9)) \\ 16492 &:= ((1 + C(6)) \times (4 + (9 \times C(2)))) \\ 16522 &:= ((-1) + (-6) \times C(5)) \times (-22) \\ 16553 &:= (((1-6) - (5^5)) + C(C(3))) \\ 16558 &:= -(((1-6)^5) + C(C(-((5-8)))))) \\ 16569 &:= (((-1) + C(6)) + (5^6)) + C(9) \\ 16575 &:= ((C((1 \times 6)) + (5)) \times 75) \\ 16625 &:= (-1 + 6)^6 + C(2 \times 5) \\ 16632 &:= ((-((1+6)) \times C(6)) \times (-3) - C(2)) \\ 16655 &:= (((-16) \times C(6)) + C(5)) \times (-5) \\ 16697 &:= (-1 + 6)^6 + C(9) + C(7) \\ 16723 &:= (((-1) \times C(6)) - C((7 \times 2))) + C(C(3)) \\ 16727 &:= (((1-C(6)) + C(7))^2) + C(7) \\ 16752 &:= ((1 + (67 \times C(5))) \times 2) \\ 16758 &:= (((-1) - C(6)) + C(7)) \times (C(5) + 8) \\ 16765 &:= (((-1) - ((C(6) + C(7)) \times (-6))) \times 5) \\ 16784 &:= (((-1) \times C(6)) \times (-78)) - C(4) \\ 16807 &:= ((1 + (6 \times 8)) \times C(07)) \\ 16835 &:= ((1-6) \times (8 - C((3 \times 5)))) \\ 16848 &:= ((C((1+6)) + 8) \times 48) \\ 16863 &:= (((1^6) - C(8)) \times (-6) - C(3)) \\ 16884 &:= ((C(-((1-6))) + C((8+8))) \times 4) \\ 16897 &:= (1 - ((6 \times 8) \times (-9) - C(7))) \\ 16926 &:= ((1 + C(6)) \times ((9 \times C(2)) + (6))) \\ 16939 &:= -((C(-((1-6) - 9)) - (3^9))) \\ 16943 &:= -(((C(-((1-6) - 9)) - (4)) - C(C(3)))) \\ 16956 &:= (C((16+9)) + C((5+6))) \\ 16992 &:= (((1-C(6)) - C(9)) \times (-9 \times 2)) \\ 17123 &:= (((1-7) + 1) \times C(C(2))) + C(C(3)) \\ 17149 &:= (-1) + (C(7) \times (1 + 49)) \\ 17150 &:= (((-1) \times C(7)) \times (-1 \times 50)) \\ 17151 &:= (1 + (C(7) \times (-1 - 51))) \\ 17226 &:= (((1-C(7)) - C(2)) + C(26)) \\ 17231 &:= (((-1) \times C(7)) - 2) + C((C(3) - 1)) \\ 17232 &:= (((-1) - C(7)) + C(((C(2) \times 3) + 2))) \\ 17233 &:= (((-1) \times C(7)) + C((23+3))) \\ 17234 &:= ((1-C(7)) + C(-((C(2) - 34)))) \\ 17250 &:= (((-1) \times C(7)) - 2) \times (-50) \\ 17253 &:= (((C((1+7)) + 2) + C(5)) \times C(3)) \\ 17275 &:= (((1 + (7^2)) \times C(7)) + C(5)) \\ 17280 &:= (C(((1+7) - 2)) \times 80) \\ 17344 &:= ((C((1+7)) \times 34) - C(4)) \\ 17350 &:= (((-1) - C(7)) - 3) \times (-50) \\ 17375 &:= (((-1) + ((-7) + C(3)) \times 7) \times C(5)) \\ 17396 &:= (((-1) \times C(7)) + C(C(3))) - (9 \times C(6)) \\ 17408 &:= (((1-7) + 40) \times C(8)) \\ 17451 &:= (C((-1) + C((7-4)))) + (C(5) \times (-1)) \\ 17485 &:= (((-1) + C(C((7-4)))) - C((8+5))) \\ 17488 &:= (C((-1) + C((7-4)))) - (88) \\ 17492 &:= (-1) + (C(7) \times (49+2)) \\ 17493 &:= (((-1) - ((1-7) \times 4)) \times C(9)) - 3 \\ 17494 &:= (1 + (C(7) \times (C(4) - (9+4)))) \\ 17496 &:= (((1+7) + C(4)) + 9) \times C(6) \\ 17520 &:= (((-1) + (-7) \times C(5)) \times (-20)) \\ 17523 &:= ((C(-((1-7))) \times (-5 \times 2)) + C(C(3))) \\ 17528 &:= (((1-7) + C((5+C(2)))) \times 8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 17529 &:= (((1 + (7^5)) - C(2)) + C(9)) \\ 17539 &:= (((1 \times 7)^5 + 3) + C(9)) \\ 17553 &:= (((-17) \times C(5)) - (5)) + C(C(3))) \\ 17556 &:= (-((1 - (7^5))) - (C(5) \times (-6))) \\ 17558 &:= ((-17) \times C(5)) + C(C(-(5 - 8)))) \\ 17576 &:= C((((1 + 7) + 5) + 7) + 6) \\ 17577 &:= (1 + C((((7 + 5) + 7) + 7)) \\ 17578 &:= ((1 - C(7)) + ((5 \times 7) \times C(8))) \\ 17582 &:= (-((1 - 7) + C((5 + 8) \times 2))) \\ 17584 &:= (((C(17) - 5)) - C(8)) \times 4 \\ 17623 &:= ((((-1) \times C(7)) \times 6) - 2) + C(C(3))) \\ 17625 &:= (((-1) \times C(7)) \times 6) + C(C(-(2 - 5)))) \\ 17631 &:= (((1 - C(7)) \times 6) + C(C((3 \times 1)))) \\ 17632 &:= (((-1) - (C(7) \times 6)) + C(C(3))) + C(2) \\ 17649 &:= ((1 - (-7) \times (C(6) + C(4)))) \times 9 \\ 17664 &:= (((-1) + C(7)) - 66) \times C(4) \\ 17695 &:= (-1) + (-7) \times (C(6) - C((9 + 5)))) \\ 17765 &:= (-17) \times ((7 - C(6)) \times 5) \\ 17766 &:= (((-1) - C((7 + 7))) - C(6)) \times (-6) \\ 17784 &:= ((1 - C(7)) \times (-((7 \times 8) - 4))) \\ 17839 &:= (C((1 \times 7)) + ((8 \times 3) \times C(9))) \\ 17875 &:= (((17 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)) \\ 17885 &:= ((1 - ((-7) \times C(8)) + 8)) \times 5 \\ 17915 &:= ((1 - (7 \times C((9 - 1)))) \times (-5)) \\ 17925 &:= (((-1) - C((7 + 9))) + C(C(2))) \times (-5) \\ 17927 &:= ((C((17 + 9)) + C(2)) + C(7)) \\ 17951 &:= (-1) - ((C(7) + 9) \times (-51)) \\ 18088 &:= (C((18 + 08)) + C(8)) \\ 18223 &:= (((C((1 + 8)) \times (-2)) - 2) + C(C(3))) \\ 18225 &:= (C((18/2)) \times 25) \\ 18235 &:= (((1 + C(8)) + C(2)) \times 35) \\ 18247 &:= ((1 + (C(8)/2)) \times (C(4) + (7))) \\ 18252 &:= ((C(-(1 - 8))) + C(2)) \times 52 \\ 18288 &:= (-18) \times ((C(2) - C(8)) - C(8)) \\ 18324 &:= ((1 + 8) \times ((3 - C(C(2))) \times (-4))) \\ 18352 &:= (((-1) \times C((8 + 3))) + C(C((5 - 2)))) \\ 18363 &:= (((C((1 \times 8)) \times (-3)) + C(6)) + C(C(3))) \\ 18368 &:= (-((1 - 83)) \times (C(6) + 8)) \\ 18375 &:= (((18 + 3) \times 7) \times C(5)) \\ 18378 &:= (-18) \times ((-3) \times C(7)) + 8) \\ 18393 &:= (((-1) + C(8)) \times (C(3) + 9)) - 3 \\ 18396 &:= ((1 - C(8)) \times ((3 - 9) \times 6)) \\ 18426 &:= ((-1) + (C(8) \times (4 + 2))) \times 6 \\ 18431 &:= (-1) + (C(8) \times ((C(4) - C(3)) - 1)) \\ 18433 &:= (1 - (C(8) \times (-((4 \times 3) \times 3)))) \\ 18438 &:= (((-((C((1 + 8)) + (4))) + C(C(3))) - C(8)) \\ 18439 &:= (((1 - C(8)) - (4)) + C(C(3))) - (C(9)) \\ 18479 &:= (((-((1 \times 8)) + C(4)) \times C(7)) - C(9)) \\ 18486 &:= ((1 + 8) \times ((4 \times C(8)) + (6))) \\ 18522 &:= (C(((18 + 5) - 2)) \times 2) \\ 18545 &:= (((C((1 + 8)) \times (-5)) - C(4)) \times (-5)) \\ 18553 &:= (((-((1 + 8)) \times C(5)) - (5)) + C(C(3))) \\ 18558 &:= (((-((1 + 8)) \times C(5)) + C(C(-(5 - 8)))) \\ 18559 &:= ((1 + C(C((8 - 5)))) + (C(5) \times (-9))) \\ 18567 &:= ((1 + 8) \times (5 + (6 \times C(7)))) \\ 18568 &:= (((1 + 85) \times C(6)) - 8) \\ 18576 &:= ((1 \times 8) \times (C(5) + C((7 + 6)))) \\ 18603 &:= (-((18 \times 60)) + C(C(3))) \\ 18625 &:= ((1 - ((C(8) - C(6))/(-2))) \times C(5)) \\ 18649 &:= (1 + ((C(8) + (6)) \times (4 \times 9))) \\ 18661 &:= (-1) + (86 \times (C(6) + 1)) \\ 18683 &:= (((-1) \times C(((8 - 6) + 8))) + C(C(3))) \\ 18793 &:= (1 + (87 \times C((9 - 3)))) \\ 18803 &:= (-((1 \times 880)) + C(C(3))) \\ 18837 &:= (((1 - C(8)) + 8) + C(C(3))) - C(7) \\ 18875 &:= (((18 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)) \\ 18893 &:= (-((1 - 8)) \times (C(8) + (C(9) \times 3))) \\ 18933 &:= (((-18) - C(9)) + C(C(3))) - 3 \\ 18936 &:= (((-18) - C(9)) + C(C(-(3 - 6)))) \\ 18938 &:= (((-((1 \times 8)) - C(9)) + C(C(3))) - 8) \\ 18943 &:= (((1 - 8) - C(9)) - (4)) + C(C(3)) \\ 18947 &:= (((1 - 8) - C(9)) + C(C(-(4 - 7)))) \\ 18948 &:= (((1 + (C(8) \times 9)) \times 4) + C(8)) \\ 18954 &:= (C((18 + 9)) - C((5 + 4))) \\ 18959 &:= ((C((18 + 9)) + (5)) - C(9)) \\ 18962 &:= (((1 \times 8) - C(9)) + C(C((6/2)))) \\ 18963 &:= (((1 + 8) - C(9)) + C(C((6 - 3)))) \\ 19043 &:= (((-1) + 9) \times C(04)) + C(C(3)) \\ 19152 &:= (-19) \times (((-1) - C(5)) \times C(2)) \\ 19172 &:= ((1 + C(C(((9 + 1) - 7)))) - C(C(2))) \\ 19234 &:= (((-((1^9)) - C(C(2))) + C(C(3))) + C(4)) \\ 19239 &:= (((-1) \times C(9)) + (C(C(2)) \times 39)) \\ 19243 &:= (((-((1 - 9)) - C(C(2))) + C(4)) + C(C(3))) \\ 19244 &:= (((-C(19)) - (C(C(2)) \times (-4))) \times (-4)) \\ 19297 &:= (1 + ((9 \times 2) \times (C(9) + C(7)))) \end{aligned}$$

- 19321 := ((-19) + C(C(3))) - C((C(2) - 1)))
19332 := ((-C(((1 + 9) - 3))) + C(C(3))) - C(2))
19335 := (((1 + C(9)) × C(3)) + (-3) × C(5))
19337 := ((C(((1 × 9) × 3)) - 3) - C(7))
19343 := (-(((1 + 9) × 34)) + C(C(3)))
19354 := (-((1 × 9)) + C(C(3))) - (5 × C(4))
19367 := (((1 + C(9)) × C(-(3 - 6))) - C(7))
19368 := ((-19) + C(C(3))) + (C(6) - C(8))
19386 := (((-1) + C((9 × 3))) - C(8)) + C(6)
19388 := ((C((1 × 9)) + C(C(3))) - (C(8) + C(8)))
19396 := -(((C(-(1 - 9))) - C(C(3))) + (-9) - C(6)))
19413 := (-((1 + 9)) × C((4 - 1))) + C(C(3))
19433 := ((C((1 + 9))/(-4)) + C((3³)))
19463 := (((1 - 9) + 4) - C(6)) + C(C(3))
19476 := (((1 × 9) + C(C(-(4 - 7)))) - C(6))
19521 := (((-1) + C(9)) - (5)) × C((2 + 1))
19533 := (-(((1 + 9) × 5) × 3)) + C(C(3))
19539 := ((-19) - C(5)) + (3⁹)
19543 := (((-19) - C(5)) + (4)) + C(C(3))
19547 := (-1) + ((C(9) - (5)) × C(-(4 - 7)))
19553 := (((-1) + C(9)) - C(5)) + (5) + C(C(3))
19554 := (C(C(-(1 - 9) + 5))) - (C(5) + (4))
19558 := (((1⁹) × C(5)) + C(C(-(5 - 8))))
19563 := (((1 + 95) - C(6)) + C(C(3)))
19568 := (((1 + 9) - C(5)) + C((C(6)/8)))
19573 := (((-1) - C(5)) + (7)) + C(C(3))
19585 := (((1 + C(9)) × C(-(5 - 8))) - (C(5)))
19613 := (-(((1 × 9) + 61)) + C(C(3)))
19624 := (C(-(1) + C((9 - 6))) - (C(C(2)) × (-4)))
19627 := (C(C(((1 × 9) - 6))) - (C(2) × 7))
19629 := (C(((1 × 9) - 6)) × (-2) + C(9))
19641 := ((-1) + C(C((9 - 6))) - 41)
19642 := ((1 + C(C((9 - 6))) - 42)
19648 := (((1 - C(9)) × C(6)) + C(4))/(-8)
19653 := (-(((1⁹) × 6) × 5)) + C(C(3))
19656 := (((1 × 96) - 5) × C(6))
19658 := (-((19 + 6)) + C(C(-(5 - 8))))
19663 := ((1 + C(C((9 - 6))) - (-6) + C(3))
19664 := (-19) + C(C(((6 + 6)/4)))
19665 := ((1 × 9) + (C(6) × (C(6) - C(5))))
19668 := ((-1) + C(C((9 - 6))) - (6 + 8))
19669 := ((1 + C(C((9 - 6))) - (6 + 9))
19673 := (-((1 + 9)) + C((6 + (7 × 3))))
19674 := (-((1 × 9)) + C(C(((6 - 7) + 4))))
19675 := ((1 - 9) + C(C((6/(7 - 5))))
19681 := (-1) - ((C((9 × 6))/(-8)) + 1)
19682 := ((C(((1 × 9) × 6)) - 8)/C(2))
19684 := (1 + C(((9 + 6) + 8) + 4))
19685 := (-(((1 - 9) + 6)) + C(C((8 - 5))))
19686 := ((1 + C(C((9 - 6)))) + (8 - 6))
19691 := (-((1 - 9)) + C((C(6)/(9 - 1))))
19692 := ((1 × 9) + C(((6 × 9)/2))
19693 := ((1 + 9) + C(C((6 - (9/3))))
19696 := ((19 - 6) + C(C((9 - 6)))
19710 := ((1 + C(9)) × C(-(7 - 10)))
19722 := (-19) × ((7 + C(C(2))) × (-2))
19723 := (-(((1 - 9) × (7 - 2))) + C(C(3))
19733 := ((C((1 + 9))/(-7) + C(3)) + C(C(3)))
19738 := (((1 × 9) × 7) + C(C(3))) - 8
19743 := (((19 × C(7)) + C(4)) × 3)
19747 := ((1 + (9 × 7)) + C(C(-(4 - 7))))
19766 := (-1) + ((9 × C((7 + 6))) - (6))
19767 := (1 + ((9 × C((7 + 6))) - (7))
19773 := ((1 × 9) × C(-(7 + 7) + C(3)))
19774 := (1 + (9 × C((77 - C(4))))
19834 := (-1) + (((C(9) + 8) × C(3)) - C(4))
19835 := ((C((19 + 8)) + C(3)) + C(5))
19837 := (((1 + C(9)) - 8) × C(3)) + C(7))
19855 := (((-1) - C(5)) × C(8)) - C(5) × 5
19862 := ((C(19) - (C(8) × (-6))) × 2)
19875 := (((19 × 8) + 7) × C(5))
19925 := (-1) + ((9 + C(9)) × C(-(2 - 5)))
19927 := (1 + ((9 + C(9)) × 27))
19968 := (C(-(1 - 9)) × (-9 - (6 × 8)))
20167 := (C(20) + C((16 + 7)))
20193 := ((-2) + C(((0 - 1) + 9))) + C(C(3))
20195 := (C(C(2)) + C(C(((0 - 1) + 9) - 5)))
20196 := ((C(C(2)) + 01) + C(C((9 - 6)))
20203 := ((C(2) + C(C(02))) + C(C(03)))
20223 := (((20 + C(2)) + C(C(2))) + C(C(3))
20224 := (C((20 + C(2))) - C((C(2) + (4))))
20323 := ((20 × 32) + C(C(3)))
20377 := ((C(2) + C(C(03))) + (C(7) + C(7)))
20383 := ((20 × (C(3) + 8)) + C(C(3)))
20391 := ((-20) + C(C(3))) + (C(9) - 1))

- 20393** := ((C(2) + C(C(03))) + (C(9) - C(3)))
20397 := ((-C(2) + C(C(03))) + ((C(9) - (7))))
20453 := ((20 × (4⁵)) - C(3))
 $\mathbf{20455} := ((C(2^{04}) - (5)) \times 5)$
20523 := (((-20) + C(5)) × C(2)) + C(C(3))
20536 := (((C(C(2)) - (0 - C(5))) + C(C(3))) + C(6))
20538 := ((C((2 + 05)) + C(C(3))) + C(8))
20539 := (((2 + C(05)) + C(C(3))) + (C(9)))
20579 := (2 + ((0 - C(57))/(-9)))
20683 := (C((2 + ((0 × 6) + 8))) + C(C(3)))
20736 := (((-2⁰⁷) × C(3)) × (-6))
20762 := ((C((C(2) - (0 - 7))) × 6) + C(C(2)))
20763 := (((-2 - 07) × C(6)) + C(C(3)))
20875 := (((20 × 8) + 7) × C(5))
20932 := (((C(2) + C(09)) + C(C(3))) + C(C(2)))
21105 := (21 × (C(10) + (5)))
21125 := (((2 + 11)²) × C(5))
21139 := (-2) + (((1 + 1) + C(3)) × C(9))
21223 := -((C((C(2) + 1)) - C(((2/2) + C(3))))
21231 := ((C(2) - C((1 + C(2)))) + C((C(3) + 1)))
21244 := (C(C(2)) + ((12⁴) - 4))
21248 := (C(C(2)) + (C(12) × (4 + 8)))
21294 := (2 × (-1) + C(((2 × 9) + 4)))
21296 := (2 × C(-(((1 - 29) + 6))))
21298 := (2 × (1 - (C((2 + 9)) × (-8))))
21315 := (((C(C(2)) × (-1)) + C((C(3) + 1))) - (C(5)))
21322 := (2 × (13 + C(22)))
21367 := -((((C(C(2)) + 1) - C(C(3))) - C((6 + 7))))
21368 := -((((C(C(2)) - C(13)) - C((C(6)/8))))
21370 := -((((C(C(2)) - C((1 + C(3)))) + 70))
21375 := ((C(C(2)) + (-((1 - 3)) - C(7))) × C(5))
21384 := (C(C((2 + 1))) - (C(3) - C((8 + 4))))
21395 := -((((C(C(2)) - C((1 + C(3)))) + (9 × 5)))
21411 := (C(C((2 + 1))) + C((4 + C((1 + 1))))
21413 := -((((C(C(2)) + C(-((1 - 4)))) - C((1 + C(3))))
21422 := (2 × ((-1) + C(4)) + C(22))
21424 := (C(2) × ((C(14) - 2) - C(4)))
21432 := (((-C(2)) + C(((1⁴) + C(3)))) - C(C(2)))
21435 := -((((C(C(2)) - C(((1⁴) + C(3)))) + (5)))
21438 := (((-2) + C(((1⁴) + C(3)))) - C(8))
21439 := ((C(2) × (C(14) + C(3))) - C(9))
21475 := (C(C((2 + 1))) + ((C(4) + C((7 + 5))))
21477 := -((C((2 + 1)) - (C(4) × (-7) + C(7))))
21537 := ((C(-((2 - 15))) + C(C(3))) - C(7))
21576 := (C(2) + (C(-((1 - 5))) × (C(7) - (6))))
21627 := (((C(2) + 1) × C(6)) + C(27))
21643 := (((C(2) - 1) × (C(6) + C(4))) + C(C(3)))
21672 := ((C(C(2)) - C(-((1 - 6)))) × (7 × C(2)))
21683 := (((-2) × C(-((1 - 6)))) × (-8)) + C(C(3))
21724 := ((C(C((2 + 1))) - (7)) - (C(C(2)) × (-4)))
21728 := (((-C(2)) - C(-((1 - 7)))) + (C(28)))
21736 := (((21 + 7)³) - C(6))
21743 := ((C((C(2) + 1)) + C((7 + 4))) + C(C(3)))
21762 := (((C(2) × (-1)) - C(7)) × (-62))
21763 := ((C((21 + 7)) - C(6)) + C(3))
21789 := (C((2 + 1)) × (78 + C(9)))
21824 := (C((2 + 18)) + C(24))
21835 := ((C(2) + C(((1⁸) + C(3)))) - (C(5)))
21853 := (C(C((2 + 1))) + (C((8 + 5)) - C(3)))
21873 := ((C((21 - 8)) - (7)) + C(C(3)))
21875 := (((21 × 8) + 7) × C(5))
21888 := ((C(C(2)) - C(-(((1 - 8) × 8))))/(-8))
21923 := ((C(C(2)) + C(((1 + 9) + 2))) + C(C(3)))
21930 := ((2 + C((1 × 9))) × 30)
21931 := (-21) + C(((9 × 3) + 1))
21933 := ((C(2) + C((1 + (9 × 3)))) - C(3))
21934 := (C(C((2 + 1))) + ((C(9) × 3) + C(4)))
21937 := -((((C(2) - C((1 + (9 × 3)))) + (7)))
21943 := (-((C(2) + 1)) + C(((9) + C(4)) - C(3)))
21944 := (-C(2) + C(-((((1 - 9) × 4) + 4)))
21946 := (C((2 × ((1 + 9) + 4))) - (6))
21951 := (C((2 × ((1 × 9) + 5))) - 1)
21952 := C((((2 - 1) × 9) + 5) × 2)
21954 := (2 + C(((19 + 5) + 4)))
21955 := ((C(2) × (1 + C((9 + 5)))) - (5))
21958 := (-2) + ((1 + C((9 + 5))) × 8)
21973 := ((C(C(2)) - 1) × ((9 + 7) + C(3)))
21995 := (((21 + 9) × C(9)) + C(5))
22024 := (C((C(2) + (20))) + ((C(2) + C(4))))
22033 := (C((C(2) + (20))) - (C(3) × (-3)))
22043 := (C((C(2) + (20))) + ((C(4) + C(3))))
22085 := ((C(2) + C((20 + 8))) + C(5))
22113 := ((C(C(2)) + C((C(2) + 11))) × 3)
22116 := (2 × ((C(C(2)) + (C(11))) × 6))

- 22125** := (((C(2) + C(C(2))) - C((-1) + C(2))) × C(5))
22144 := (((-2) - C((C(2) - 1))) × (-C(4))) + C(4))
22165 := ((C((2 + 2)) + 1) × (C(6) + C(5)))
22168 := (C(2) × (C((2 + 1)) + C((6 + 8))))
22176 := ((C(2) + C((21 + 7))) + C(6))
22184 := -((C(22) + ((-1) - C(8)) × C(4)))
22208 := ((2^{C(2)}) + C((20 + 8)))
22233 := (((2 - C(C(2))) × (-2 + 3)) + C(C(3)))
22243 := ((C(2) × ((2^{C(2)}) + C(4))) + C(C(3)))
22245 := ((-C(22) + C((C(2) × 4))) + C(5))
22253 := ((C(2) + 2) - ((C(C(2)) × (-5)) - C(C(3))))
22256 := (C(2) - ((22 - C(5)) × C(6)))
22272 := ((C(C(2)) × (-((2^{C(2)}) - C(7))))/2)
22275 := (((C(C(2)) + 2) × (-C(2))) - C(7)) × (-5))
22287 := (-C(2) - (((C(2) + C(C(2)))/8) × (-C(7))))
22317 := ((22 + C((C(3) + 1))) + C(7))
22326 := (((C((2 + 2)) - 3)²) × 6)
22337 := -C(C(2)) + C(C(2) + C(3)) - C(C(3)) - C(7)
22355 := ((C((C(2) + C(2))) - (-3) × C(5))) × 5)
22374 := ((22 × 3) × (C(7) - 4))
22375 := (((-2) - C(2)) + (C(3) × 7)) × C(5)
22392 := (C(((2) - C(2)) × (-3)) - (9 × C(C(2))))
22394 := (((C(C(2)) + 2) + C(C(3))) + C((9 + 4)))
22427 := (C(-((2 - (2⁴)))) + C(27))
22457 := ((C(C(2)) + C((C(2) + ((4 × 5)))) - 7)
22462 := ((C(C(2)) - 2) + C((C(4) - ((6²))))
22464 := (((2 + 24) × C(6)) × 4)
22466 := ((C(C(2)) + 2) + C((C(4) - (6 × 6))))
22471 := (C(C(2)) + (((C(2) + C((4 × 7))) - 1)))
22472 := (C(2) + (C(2) × (C(4) + C((7 × 2))))
22473 := (((-2) - C(2)) × (C(4) - C(7))) + C(C(3)))
22489 := (C((2 + 24)) + C((8 + 9)))
22519 := -((C(C(2)) - (((C(C(2)) × 5) - 1) × 9))
22524 := ((C(C(2)) × (-C(2) - (52))) - 4)
22528 := ((2 + ((C(2) × 5) + 2)) × C(8))
22532 := (2 × ((C(C(2)) × (-5) + C(3)) + 2))
22536 := ((2 × (C(C(2)) + C((-5) + C(3)))) + C(6))
22563 := (((C(C(2)) - (2⁵)) × 6) + C(C(3)))
22575 := ((C(C(2)) + (C(2) + C(5))) × (7 × 5))
22590 := (((2^{C(2)}) - 5) × 90)
22599 := ((C(2) + ((2⁵) - 9)) × C(9))
22643 := (((C(2) - C(C(2))) × (-6)) - C(4)) + C(C(3)))
- 22649** := ((C(2) × (C((C(2) + (6))) - 4)) + C(9))
22679 := (-2) - (((2⁶) × C(7)) - C(9))
22681 := (C((2 + 26)) + C((8 + 1)))
22683 := (((2^{C(2)}) + C((6 + 8))) + C(C(3)))
22689 := ((C(2) + C((2 × (6 + 8)))) + C(9))
22697 := (((C(C(2)) - (C(C(2)) × 6)) × (-9)) - C(7))
22757 := ((C(C(2)) + (C((2 × 7)) - 5)) × 7)
22763 := ((C(2) × (C(C(2)) - ((C(7) - C(6)))) + C(C(3)))
22784 := ((C(C(2)) - (2 × 78)) × C(4))
22792 := ((C(C(2)) + (C((2 × 7)))) × (9 - 2))
22807 := (C(C(2)) + ((C(28) + C(07))))
22813 := ((C(C(2)) × (2 + 81)) - C(C(3)))
22815 := (C(22) + C((8 + 15)))
22823 := ((C(22) + 8) + C(23))
22849 := -(((C(22) - C((8 × 4))) - C(9))
22875 := (((22 × 8) + 7) × C(5))
22896 := (2 × (((2 × 8) × C(9)) - C(6)))
22923 := ((C(2) + ((29²))) × C(3))
22929 := (-2) - ((2 × C(9)) - C(29))
22932 := (C((2 + 29)) - C((C(3) - C(2))))
22935 := (((2 - C(C(2))) × (-9)) - 3) × 5)
22942 := (((-2) × C((C(2) + 9))) + C((C(4)/2)))
22944 := (C(2) × (((C(2) - C(9)) + 4) × (-4)))
22968 := (C(2) × ((C(2) + C((9 + 6))) - C(8)))
22976 := (C(2) - (C(2) × ((-9) × C(7)) + C(6)))
22995 := ((C(C(2)) + ((C(2) - 9))) × (9 × 5))
23087 := (2 + (C(3) × (C(08) + C(7))))
23168 := -(((C(C(2)) - C((C(3) + 1))) + (C(6) × (-8))))
23183 := (((-C(2)) - C(C(3))) - 1) + C((8 + C(3)))
23192 := (C((C(2) + C(3))) - C(C(((1⁹) + 2)))
23193 := (C((C(2) + C(3))) - (-1) + C((9 × 3)))
23194 := ((2 - C(C(3))) + C(-((1 - (9 × 4))))
23213 := ((C((C(2) + C(3))) + 21) - C(C(3)))
23243 := ((C(2) × ((-3) + C(C(2))) - C(4)) + C(C(3)))
23247 := ((C(2) + C(C(3))) + ((C(C(2)) - 4) × 7))
23256 := ((C(C(2)) × ((3²) × 5)) + C(6))
23264 := (((2 × C(3)) × 2) × C(6)) - C(4)
23272 := (((2 × C(3))²) - 7) × C(2)
23273 := ((2 × 3) + ((C(C(2)) × 7) + C(C(3))))
23275 := (((C(C(2)) + C(3)) × C(2)) + C(7)) × 5)
23276 := (((2 + C(C(3))) + C((C(2) + 7))) + C(6))
23283 := (C((C(2) + 3)) + ((28³)))

- 23292 := (((C(23) - C(C(2))) - 9) × 2)
23293 := -((C(2) + ((-32) × C(9)) + C(3)))
23324 := ((C(2) × ((C(3) + C(3))²)) - (4))
23325 := ((C((C(2) + C(3))) - C(C(3))) + (C(2) + C(5)))
23326 := (-2) + (((C(3) + C(3)) × 2) × C(6))
23329 := -((2 - 3) + (32 × C(9)))
23332 := ((C(2) + C((3 + 33)))/2)
23336 := (C(2) + (((C(3) × 3) + C(3)) × C(6)))
23344 := ((C(((2 × 3) × 3)) + (4)) × 4)
23352 := ((C(2) × (-3)) × (C(3) - C((5 × 2))))
23374 := (2 × ((C(C(3)) - C((C(3) - (7)))) + (4)))
23375 := (-((2 - ((3³) × 7))) × C(5))
23389 := (C((2 + C(3))) - C((C(3) - ((8 + 9))))))
23392 := (((2 + 3) + C(3)) × (C(9) + 2))
23398 := ((-C(2) + C(C(3))) + (3 × (C(9) + C(8))))
23424 := (2 × (((C(3) - (4)) × C(C(2))) - C(4)))
23452 := ((C(C(2)) + (3 - C(4))) × 52)
23463 := (((2 + 3) - (-4) × C(6))) × C(3))
23465 := (2 - (C(3) × ((-4) × C(6)) - (5)))
23475 := ((-2) + C(3)) × (C(4) - (-7) × C(5)))
23479 := ((C(C(2)) × 3) + ((C((4 × 7)) - 9)))
23483 := ((C(2) × ((C(3) - C(4)) + C(8))) + C(C(3)))
23488 := ((C(C(2)) × 3) - (C((C(4) - 8))/(-8)))
23496 := (C(2) × (C(3) - ((-4) × C(9)) + (6)))
23523 := (((C(C(2)) - (C(3) + (5))) × C(2)) + C(C(3)))
23537 := (((2 + C(35)) - C(C(3))) + C(7))
23544 := ((2 × C(3)) × ((C(5) × 4) - C(4)))
23552 := (C(2) × (((3⁵) + C(5)) × C(2)))
23554 := (2 - (((3⁵) - C(5)) × C(4)))
23563 := ((C((2 × (3 + 5))) - C(6)) + C(C(3)))
23569 := (C((2 + C(3))) + (((C(5) - C(6)) - C(9))))
23579 := (-((C(2) - C(3)) × (C(C(-(5 - 7)))) + (C(9))))
23592 := (C(2) + ((C(3) + (5)) × (C(9) + C(2))))
23594 := ((C(2) + ((3⁵))) × 94)
23611 := (C((-2) + C(3)) - (-6) × C(11))
23617 := -((C(2) + (C((3 × (6 - 1))) × (-7)))
23623 := (-2) - ((C(3) - C(6)) × C((2 + 3)))
23624 := (C(C(2)) - (C(3) × ((C(6) - 2) × (-4))))
23625 := (C((2 + (3 × 6))) + C(25))
23627 := (2 - (C((3 + (6 × 2))) × (-7)))
23633 := (C((2 + C(3))) - (C((6 + 3)) + C(3)))
23639 := (C((2 + C(3))) - ((-6) + C(3)) + C(9))
23652 := (((C(23) - C(6)) - C(5)) × 2)
23654 := (C((2 + C(3))) - (6 + C((5 + 4))))
23657 := (((C(2) × (-3)) + C(6)) × C(5)) - C(7))
23659 := (C((2 + C(3))) - ((6 - 5) + C(9)))
23672 := ((C(C(2)) - (36 × C(7))) × (-2))
23673 := -(((C((-2) + C(3))) + (6)) - C((7 + C(3))))
23680 := ((C((2³)) - C(6)) × 80)
23693 := (C((2 + C(3))) - ((-6) + C(9)) - C(3))
23695 := ((C(C(2)) + C(C(3))) + ((C((6 + 9)) + C(5))))
23723 := (((C((2³)) - (7)) × C(2)) + C(C(3)))
23724 := (C((2 + C(3))) - (C((7 + 2)) - C(4)))
23733 := ((C(C(2)) - ((3 - C(7)) - C(3))) × C(3))
23734 := ((2 × C(3)) + ((C(7) + C(3)) × C(4)))
23744 := (((C(2) × 3) + C(7)) + (4)) × C(4))
23750 := ((C(C(2)) - 37) × 50)
23752 := ((C((C(2) + ((3 × 7)))) - (C(5))) - C(C(2)))
23755 := ((2 × (C(C(3)) + (7))) - C((5 × 5)))
23759 := (C(C(2)) + (C(3) × ((7 + C(5)) + C(9))))
23763 := (-((C(23) + (7))) + C((6 + C(3))))
23765 := ((C(C(2)) - C(3)) × (-76) + C(5))
23769 := ((C(C(2)) × (3 + (7 × 6))) + (C(9)))
23772 := (((C(C(2)) + C(C(3))) - (7)) - (-7) × C(C(2))))
23779 := ((C(C(2)) + C(C(3))) + (7 × C(C(-(7 - 9))))))
23781 := ((2 + C(C(3))) + C(((7 + 8) + 1)))
23784 := ((-2) + C(C(3))) + (7 + (8⁴))
23786 := ((C(C(2)) + C(C(3))) + ((C((7 + 8)) + C(6))))
23788 := ((2 + C(C(3))) - (-7) - C((8 + 8)))
23789 := ((2 + C(C(3))) + ((C((7 + 8)) + C(9))))
23793 := ((C(-(C(2) - C(3))) + (C(7) + C(9))) × 3)
23798 := (C((2 + C(3))) + (-79) - C(8))
23803 := ((C(2) × (3 + C(8))) + C(C(03)))
23813 := (C((2 + C(3))) - ((C(8) + C((1 + 3))))
23814 := (C((2 + C(3))) - ((C(8) - 1) + C(4)))
23822 := ((C(23) - (C(8)/2)) × 2)
23823 := (C((2 + C(3))) - (C(8) + (2 × C(3))))
23824 := (C((C(2) × 3)) + (((8 + 2)⁴))
23826 := ((C((2 + 3)) - C((8 × 2))) × (-6))
23827 := ((-C(2) + C(C(3))) + (8 × (C(C(2)) + (7))))
23843 := ((C(((2³) + 8)) + C(4)) + C(C(3)))
23850 := (((C(2) + C(3)) - C(8)) × (-50))
23852 := (C((2 + C(3))) - (C(8) + ((5²))))
23856 := ((C(2) × 3) × ((8 × C(5)) - (6)))

- 23894** := (((2 × C((3 + 8))) × 9) – C(4))
23895 := (((C(2) – C(3)) – C(8)) × (–(9 × 5)))
23921 := ((C((C(2) + C(3))) + (C(9))) – C(C((2 + 1))))
23923 := (((2 – C(C(3))) + (C(9))) + C((C(2) + C(3))))
23927 := (((C(C(2)) + C((C(3) + 9)))/2) + C(7))
23935 := (((C((-2) + C(3))) – (C(9))) – C(C(3))) × (–5))
23953 := (((C((2 + 3)) + C(9)) × 5) + C(C(3)))
23955 := ((2 + C(C(3))) + ((C(9) + C(5)) × 5))
23956 := (–(2) + ((C(3) – 9) × C((5 + 6))))
23958 := (C((C(2) + 3)) × (–(9) + C(–((5 – 8))))))
23966 := (C((2 + C(3))) + ((9 – C(6)) – C(6)))
23972 := (((C((C(2) + 3)) × 9) + (7)) × 2)
23976 := (((–(2) × C((3 + 9))) × (–7)) – C(6))
23984 := ((–(C(2)) × (C(C(3)) – (C(9)))) + C((–(8) + C(4))))
23992 := –((C(2) + (–(3) × C(((9 + 9) + 2))))))
24064 := –(((C(2) – (C(4) × 06)) × C(4)))
24072 := ((C(C(2)) × (40 + 7)) + C(2))
24125 := ((–(C((2⁴))) – C((1 + C(2)))) × (–5))
24137 := (C(C(2)) – (C(((4 + 1) × 3)) × (–7)))
24167 := ((C(2) + (4 – 1)) × C((6 + 7)))
24176 := ((2⁴) × (–(1) – (–(7) × C(6))))
24192 := (24 × (C((1 + 9)) + C(2)))
24194 := (2 × (C(C(4)) – C(–((1⁹)) + C(4))))
24233 := ((–(2) × (C(4) – C(23))) + C(3))
24253 := –((C(C(2)) + ((–(C(4)) × (C(C(2)) – (C(5)))) + 3))
24256 := ((C(2) × 4) × (C(2) – (C(5) × (–6))))
24258 := (2 – (C(4) × ((C(2) + C(5)) – C(8))))
24276 := ((C(C(2)) + (C(4) + 2)) × (7 × 6))
24283 := (((C((2⁴)) – C(2)) + C(8)) + C(C(3)))
24293 := ((2 + (C((4 × 2)) × 9)) + C(C(3)))
24317 := ((2 × C((-4) + C(3))) – (17))
24318 := (2 × (C((-4) + C(3)) – (1 × 8)))
24320 := ((C(C(2)) – C((4 × 3))) × (–20))
24322 := (((–(C(2)) + C((-4) + C(3))) + 2) × 2)
24323 := ((–(2) – C(4)) + C((32 – 3)))
24325 := (((2 – C((-4) + C(3))) × (–2)) – (5))
24326 := ((2 × C((-4) + C(3))) – (2 + 6))
24327 := ((2 × C(((4 + C(3)) – C(2)))) – (7))
24328 := ((C(C(2)) + C(C(4))) – C(((C(3) × 2) + 8)))
24329 := (((–(2) – C((-4) + C(3))) × (–2)) – 9)
24331 := ((2 × C((-4) + C(3))) – (3 × 1))
24332 := (–(2) – (((–(4) + C(3))³) × (–2)))
24333 := ((2 × C((-4) + C(3))) – (3/3))
24334 := (–((2 – 4) × C(((3³) – 4)))
24335 := ((2 × (C((-4) + C(3))) + 3) – (5))
24341 := ((2 × (4 + C((C(3) – (4)))))) – 1)
24342 := ((2 × C((-4) + C(3))) + (4 × 2))
24346 := (–((2 – 4) × (C((C(3) – (4))) + (6))))
24352 := (C(2) – ((C((-4) + C(3))) + (5)) × (–2))
24354 := ((C(C(2)) – ((C(4) – 3))) × 54)
24356 := (2 × (C((-4) + C(3))) + (5 + 6))
24357 := ((C(2) × (–4)) + C((C(3) – ((5 – 7))))))
24359 := ((C(C(2)) × (C(4) – (3 × 5))) – (C(9)))
24362 := (C((-((2 – 4)) + C(3))) – C((6/2)))
24375 := ((C((2 + 4)) – ((3 × 7))) × C(5))
24376 := –((C(2) + ((C(4) × (–3)) × (C(7) – C(6))))))
24381 := –((C(2) – C((4 + ((3 × 8) + 1))))))
24384 := (((–(2) × C(4)) – 3) + C(8)) × C(4))
24385 := –(((C(2) – (4)) – C(((3 × 8) + 5))))
24387 := (–(2) + C((C(4) + (((3 – 8) × 7))))))
24388 := (C((-((2 – 4)) + C(3))) – (8/8))
24389 := C(–(((2⁴) + ((3 – 8) × 9))))
24391 := (2 + C(((C(4) – C(3)) – (9 – 1))))
24394 := (C((-((2 – 4)) + C(3))) + (9 – 4))
24397 := (C(2) + C(((4 + C(3)) – (9 – 7))))
24429 := ((–(24) + C(4)) + C(29))
24432 := (((C(2) + (4)) × 4) × (–(3) + C(C(2))))
24455 := ((2 + C(4)) + C((4 + (5 × 5))))
24456 := ((C((2⁴)) – ((4 × 5))) × 6)
24462 := (2 × (C(4) + C((46/2))))
24464 := (((C(2) – C((4 × 4))) × (–6)) – C(4))
24472 := (C(24) + C(((4 + 7) × 2)))
24512 := (C(C(2)) – (C((4 × 5)) × (–(1 + 2))))
24514 := (C((24 + 5)) + C((1 + 4)))
24515 := ((C((24 + 5)) + 1) + C(5))
24525 := ((C(2) – C(((4 + 5) + C(2)))) × (–5))
24535 := ((C(C(2)) + (C(4) + C(5))) × 35)
24545 := ((C((C(2) + (4 + 5))) – (4)) × 5)
24552 := (((C(2) – C(4)) + ((5⁵))) × C(2))
24565 := (C(((2 + 4) + 5) + 6)) × 5)
24568 := (C(2) × ((4 – 5) – (–(6) × C(8))))
24573 := ((C(C(2)) × (4 × (5 + 7))) – 3)
24576 := (C((2⁴)) × ((5 + 7) – 6))
24578 := (2 + ((4 × (5 + 7)) × C(8)))

- 24589 := (24 - (-5) × C((8 + 9)))
24596 := ((C((24 + 5)) - 9) + C(6))
24603 := ((C((2⁴)) × 6) + C(03))
24608 := (C(2) × (4 - (-6) × C(08)))
24624 := ((C(2) + (4⁶)) × (2 + 4))
24626 := (2 + ((-((4⁶)) - C(2)) × (-6)))
24629 := ((24 + C(6)) + C(29))
24636 := ((-2) + ((C(4) - C(6)) × C(3))) × (-6)
24657 := (((-((2⁴)) + C(6)) × C(5)) - C(7))
24665 := (((C((2⁴)) - (6)) × 6) + C(5))
24672 := ((C(2) + (4)) × ((6 × C(7)) - 2))
24693 := ((C(((2 × 4) + 6)) × 9) - 3)
24696 := -(((C(2) - C(4)) × ((C(6) + 9) + C(6))))
24712 := (C(2) - (C(4) × (C(7) - C((1 + C(2))))))
24723 := (((C(C(2)) + C(4)) × C(7))/C(2)) + C(3)
24728 := ((C(2) × (4 + C(7))) + C(28))
24747 := (((-2) - C(4)) - (7)) × (4 - C(7))
24749 := (2 + ((-4) + C(7)) × (C(4) + 9))
24759 := ((C((2 + 4)) × (-7) + C(5)) - C(9))
24768 := (C((C(2) × 4)) - C((-7) + (C(6)/8)))
24772 := (((C(C(2)) + (4)) × (7 × 7)) - C(C(2)))
24792 := (((C(2) + (4)) + (C(7) × 9)) × C(2))
24793 := ((C(C(2)) × 47) + ((9³)))
24803 := ((C((C(2) - (4))) × 80) + C(C(3)))
24813 := ((C(C(2)) + ((C(4) + C((8 - 1)))) × C(3))
24816 := (C(2) × (((4 + C(8)) + 1) × 6))
24829 := -((((C(2) + C(4)) - C(8)) - C(29)))
24837 := (C(C(2)) - (C(4) - C((8 + (3 × 7))))))
24862 := (-2) - (48 × (-6) - C(C(2)))
24864 := ((C(2) + (4)) × ((C(8) + (6)) × 4))
24872 := -((C((2 + 4)) + (C(8) × (-7²))))
24875 := (((24 × 8) + 7) × C(5))
24895 := (((-2) - C(4)) - C((8 + 9))) × (-5)
24925 := (((C(2) + C(4)) + C((9 + C(2)))) × 5)
24929 := ((C(2) × ((C(4) - 9)²)) + C(9))
24950 := ((C(C(2)) - (4 + 9)) × 50)
24953 := ((C(C(2)) × 49) - (5 × C(3)))
24965 := ((C(C(2)) + C(4)) + C((-96) + C(5)))
24968 := (C(2) × (49 - (-6) × C(8)))
24976 := -((C(C(2)) - ((C(-((4 - 9))) - (7)) × C(6))))
24982 := -((C(2) - (49 × (C(8) - 2))))
24994 := ((C(C(2)) × 49) - (94))
25024 := (((C(C(2)) × 50) - C(C(2))) - C(4))
25084 := ((C(C(2)) × 50) - (C(8) + (4)))
25088 := (((-((2 - 50)) × C(8)) + C(8))
25137 := (((C(2) + C(5)) × (-1)) × C(3)) × (-7)
25250 := ((C(C(2)) - (5 + 2)) × 50)
25255 := -((C(C(2)) + ((C(52) - C(55))))
25257 := ((C(C(2)) × ((5 × 2) × 5)) - C(7))
25262 := (-2) + (((C(5) - C(2)) × C(6)) - C(2))
25265 := (-2) + (((C(5) - C(2)) × C(6)) - (5))
25267 := (2 + (((C(5) - C(2)) × C(6)) - (7)))
25269 := (-2) - ((C(5) × (C(2) - C(6))) + C(9))
25272 := ((C(2) + C((5 + 2))) × 72)
25277 := (((-C(2)) - ((5 + C(C(2))) × (-7))) × 7)
25284 := (((2 + 5)²) × (C(8) + (4)))
25298 := (((2⁵) + 2) × C(9)) + C(8)
25327 := (C((25 + 3)) + C((C(2) + (7))))
25344 := (((-C(2)) + C(((5 - 3) + C(4)))) - C(C(4)))
25348 := (2 × (((-5) + C((C(3) - (4)))) + C(8)))
25353 := ((C((C(2) + (5))) - C((C(3) - (5)))) × (-3))
25368 := -((C(2) - ((C(5) - 3) × (C(6) - 8))))
25373 := ((C(C(2)) × (C(5) - 37)) - C(C(3)))
25375 := (((2⁵) - 3) × 7) × C(5)
25389 := (C((2 × 5)) + C((38 - 9)))
25392 := (((2 - C(5)) + C(C(3))) + C((9 × 2)))
25398 := (((C(2) - C(5)) + C(C(3))) + (C(9) × 8))
25433 := (((-2) × C(5)) × (4 - C(3))) + C(C(3))
25434 := (((-2) × C(5)) - C(4)) × (-3⁴)
25475 := ((C(2) + (C((5 + 4)) × (-7))) × (-5))
25489 := (((C(C(2)) - (C(5))) × C(4)) - (8 - C(9)))
25497 := (2 - (-5) × (-4) - (C(9) × (-7)))
25507 := (((C(C(2)) + (5)) × 50) - C(7))
25512 := (C(C(2)) + ((5⁵) × C((1 × 2))))
25523 := ((C(2) + C((5 + 5) + C(2))) + C(C(3)))
25528 := ((C(2) × ((5⁵) + 2)) + C(8))
25536 := ((C(2) + C(5)) × ((5 + C(3)) × 6))
25544 := (C(2) × (((5⁵) + 4) + C(4)))
25550 := ((C(C(2)) - (5/5)) × 50)
25552 := (C(C(2)) + (((5⁵) + 5) × C(2)))
25569 := (((-((2 × 5)) + C(5)) × C(6)) + C(9))
25576 := (C(2) × (C((5 + 5)) + C((7 + 6))))
25592 := ((C(C(2)) × (5 + (5 × 9))) - C(2))
25595 := ((C(C(2)) × (5 + (5 × 9))) - (5))

$$\begin{aligned} 25598 &:= (-2) - (-((5 + (5 \times 9))) \times C(8)) \\ 25623 &:= (-2) + (C(5) \times ((C(6) - C(2)) - 3)) \\ 25625 &:= (((2 - 5) + C(6)) - C(2)) \times C(5) \\ 25633 &:= (-C((2^5))) - ((-C(6) + C(C(3))) \times (-3)) \\ 25650 &:= ((C(C(2)) - ((5 - 6))) \times 50) \\ 25657 &:= -(((C((2 \times 5)) - C((6 \times 5))) + C(7))) \\ 25664 &:= ((C(C(2)) \times (56 - 6)) + C(4)) \\ 25725 &:= ((-(2 - 5) \times C(7)) \times 25) \\ 25726 &:= (2 + ((C(5) - 7) \times (2 + C(6)))) \\ 25727 &:= (2 + (-5) \times ((-7) - C(2)) \times C(7))) \\ 25728 &:= (C(2) \times (((-5) + C(7)) \times C(2)) + C(8)) \\ 25729 &:= ((C(2) \times (5^{7-2})) + C(9)) \\ 25732 &:= ((C((2 \times 5)) + C(7)) + C((C(3) + 2))) \\ 25735 &:= ((-2) + ((5 \times C(7)) \times (-3))) \times (-5) \\ 25757 &:= (2^5) + (75 \times C(7)) \\ 25759 &:= -((C(C(2)) - (C(((5 \times 7) - 5)) - C(9)))) \\ 25839 &:= (((2 - C(5)) \times (-8)) \times C(3)) - C(9) \\ 25850 &:= ((2 \times C(5)) + (C(8) \times 50)) \\ 25852 &:= -((C(C(2)) - ((5 - C(8)) \times (-52))) \\ 25863 &:= -((C(C(2)) + (C(5) \times ((8 - C(6)) - 3))) \\ 25865 &:= (C(2) + ((C(5) - 8) \times (C(6) + (5)))) \\ 25875 &:= (((25 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)) \\ 25922 &:= (2 - (-5) \times ((9 \times C(2))^2)) \\ 25935 &:= ((C((2 \times 5)) + C(9)) \times (3 \times 5)) \\ 25984 &:= ((C(2) \times (C((5 + 9)) + C(8))) - C(4)) \\ 25986 &:= (2 + ((C(5) - 9) \times (8 + C(6)))) \\ 25992 &:= (-C(2)) + (-C(5)) \times ((9 - C(9)) + C(C(2)))) \\ 25994 &:= ((-2) \times C(5)) + (C(9) \times (9 \times 4)) \\ 25998 &:= (-2) + (C(5) \times ((-9) + C(9)) - C(8)) \\ 26104 &:= (26 \times (C(10) + (4))) \\ 26113 &:= (((-2) + C(6))^{1+1}) - C(C(3)) \\ 26125 &:= (((2 + C(6)) - 1) - C(2)) \times C(5) \\ 26144 &:= (C(2) + (C(6) \times (C((1 + 4)) - (4)))) \\ 26158 &:= ((C(C(2)) - (61)) \times 58) \\ 26196 &:= ((C(2) + (-6) \times C((1 \times 9)))) \times (-6) \\ 26232 &:= (2 \times (-6) - (-2) \times (3^{C(2)})) \\ 26236 &:= -((C(2) - ((6^2) \times (3^6)))) \\ 26237 &:= (C(C(2)) + (((6 \times C(2)) + C(3)) \times C(7))) \\ 26238 &:= (((-2) + C(6)) \times C((2 + 3))) - C(8) \\ 26244 &:= (((26 - C(2))^4) / 4) \\ 26246 &:= (2 + (C((C(6) / (C(2) - (4)))) / 6)) \\ 26269 &:= ((-2) + C(((6^2) - 6))) - C(9) \\ 26272 &:= -(((C(C(2)) + C(6)) - C(((C(2) + (7)) \times 2)))) \\ 26279 &:= ((C(2) + C(-((6 \times (2 - 7)))) - (C(9))) \\ 26312 &:= ((C(C(2)) - (6)) \times ((C(3) - 1) \times 2)) \\ 26322 &:= (((-2) + C(6)) \times (C((3 + 2)) - 2)) \\ 26329 &:= (((-2) + (6 \times C(3)))^2) + C(9) \\ 26344 &:= (2 \times ((C(6) \times (-3) + C(4)) - (4))) \\ 26346 &:= (((2 \times C(6)) \times (-3) + C(4)) - (6)) \\ 26375 &:= ((2 + ((6^3) - 7)) \times C(5)) \\ 26384 &:= (C(2) \times ((6 \times (C(3) + C(8))) + C(4))) \\ 26424 &:= ((C((26 + 4)) - C(C(2))) - C(4)) \\ 26430 &:= -((C(C(2)) - ((6 - C(4)) + C(30))) \\ 26432 &:= ((C(2) + C(6)) \times (C(4) + (C(3) \times 2))) \\ 26433 &:= (((C(2) - C(6)) + C(43)) / 3) \\ 26482 &:= -((C(C(2)) - (-6) + C(((4 \times 8) - 2)))) \\ 26484 &:= ((C((26 + 4)) - C(8)) - (4)) \\ 26488 &:= (C(((26 - 4) + 8)) - C(8)) \\ 26494 &:= (-((C(C(2)) - (6))) + C(-((C(4) - (94)))) \\ 26496 &:= ((2 \times 64) \times (-9) + C(6)) \\ 26512 &:= -(((C(2) - C(6)) \times C(5)) + C(C((1 \times 2)))) \\ 26521 &:= (((2 + C(6)) \times C(5)) - C((C(2) + 1))) \\ 26523 &:= (((C(2) + C((6 \times 5))) - C(C(2))) + C(3)) \\ 26526 &:= ((((-2) + C(6)) \times C(5)) - C(2)) - C(6) \\ 26529 &:= (((2 + C(6)) \times C(5)) + C(2)) - C(9) \\ 26536 &:= ((C((C(2) + (6 + 5))) + C(C(3))) - (6)) \\ 26546 &:= -((C(C(2)) - ((C((6 \times 5)) + C(4)) - (6))) \\ 26553 &:= ((C(C(2)) - (6 + 5)) \times 53) \\ 26564 &:= (((-2) \times C(6)) + C((5 \times 6))) - (4) \\ 26566 &:= (((-2) - C(6)) + C((5 \times 6))) - C(6) \\ 26596 &:= ((2 + C(6)) \times (C(5) - (9 - 6))) \\ 26621 &:= ((C(26) - C(6)) + C(21)) \\ 26624 &:= ((((-2) + C(6)) - (6)) \times 2) \times C(4) \\ 26625 &:= ((((-2) \times C(6)) + (6)) / (-2)) \times C(5) \\ 26629 &:= (C(C(2)) + (C((6 + 6)) + C(29))) \\ 26643 &:= ((C(2) \times (6 - (C(6) \times (-4)))) + C(C(3))) \\ 26653 &:= (((C(2) + C(6)) \times (-6) + C(5)) - 3) \\ 26654 &:= (C(C(2)) + (6 + (C(6) \times (C(5) - (4)))) \\ 26656 &:= (((2 + 6) + C(6)) \times (C(5) - (6))) \\ 26657 &:= (C(((2 \times 6) - 6) \times 5)) - C(7) \\ 26673 &:= ((C(C(2)) + C(((6 \times 6) + 7))) / 3) \\ 26688 &:= (C(2) \times (C(6) - (-6) \times (8 + C(8)))) \\ 26697 &:= ((C(C(2)) \times 6) - (C((6 + 9)) \times (-7))) \\ 26723 &:= (((-2) + C(6)) \times C((7 - 2))) - C(3) \end{aligned}$$

- 26729** := -((((C(2) - C(6)) × C((7 - 2))) - C(9)))
26733 := (- (267) + C((C(3) + 3)))
26744 := (2 × (((C(6) - (7)) × C(4)) - (4)))
26746 := ((2 × ((C(6) - (7)) × C(4))) - (6))
26752 := (- (2) + ((6 × C(7)) × (5 + C(2))))
26760 := (2 × ((C(6) + (7)) × 60))
26764 := (2 × (6 - ((7 - C(6)) × C(4))))
26768 := (C(2) × (((C(6) + C(7)) × 6) - 8))
26775 := (((C(2) + (6)) + C(7)) × 75)
26782 := ((- (2) - C(6)) + C(((7 + 8) × 2)))
26823 := (((C(2) + (6)) × (C(8) - 2)) + C(C(3)))
26837 := (C(((C(2) - C(6)) / (-8))) + C((3 × 7)))
26875 := (((26 × 8) + 7) × C(5))
26919 := ((C(C(2)) × (6 × 9)) + (- (1) × C(9)))
26924 := (- (C(C(2))) - (C((C(- ((6 - 9))) - C(2)))) × (-4)))
26928 := ((C(2) × (C((6 + 9)) - C(2))) - 8)
26933 := ((2 - 69) + C((C(3) + 3)))
26934 := ((- (2) + C((- ((6 - 9)) + C(3)))) - C(4))
26936 := ((2⁶⁺⁹) - C((3 × 6)))
26944 := ((C(2) + C((6 × (9 - 4)))) - C(4))
26950 := (C((2 × (6 + 9))) - (50))
26952 := ((C(2) × (C((6 + 9)) - (5))) - C(2))
26954 := ((26 × C(9)) + C((5 × 4)))
26955 := ((C(2) × (C((6 + 9)) - (5))) - (5))
26958 := (- (2) - ((C((6 + 9)) - (5)) × (-8)))
26965 := (- ((26 + 9)) + C((6 × 5)))
26968 := (((2 - 6) + C((9 + 6))) × 8)
26973 := (C((C(2) + ((6 + 9) + 7))) - C(3))
26978 := (2 × (C((C(6) / 9)) - ((C(7) - 8))))
26982 := (((2 - C((6 + 9))) × (-8)) - 2)
26984 := ((- (2) + C((6 + 9))) × C((8 / 4)))
26986 := (C((2 × (6 + 9))) - (8 + 6))
26989 := (- (2) + ((C((6 + 9)) × 8) - 9))
26991 := (C((2 × (6 + 9))) - (9 × 1))
26992 := (C((((2 × 6) + 9) + 9)) - C(2))
26995 := (C((((2 × 6) + 9) + 9)) - (5))
26998 := (- (2) + (C((69 - 9)) / 8))
26999 := (C((2 × (6 + 9))) - (9 / 9))
27056 := ((C(2) × 7) + C((05 × 6)))
27064 := (C(((2 - 7) × (0 - 6))) + C(4))
27125 := (C((((2 × 7) + 1) × 2)) + C(5))
27132 := ((C((2 × 7)) - 1) + C((C(3) + 2)))
27133 := (C((2 × 7)) + C((- ((1 - 3)) + C(3))))
27136 := ((2⁷) × (- ((1 + 3)) + C(6)))
27216 := (((2⁷) - 2) × C((1 × 6)))
27231 := ((C(C(2)) × (- (7 - 2))) + (C(31)))
27232 := ((C((C(2) + (7))) + (2 + C(3))) × C(2))
27240 := (((C(C(2)) - C(7)) + C(C(2))) × 40)
27256 := (((2⁷) × 2) + C((5 × 6)))
27262 := (C(C(2)) + (C((7 - 2)) × (C(6) - 2)))
27265 := ((C(2) + (7)) + ((2 + C(6)) × C(5)))
27285 := ((C(C(2)) × (7²)) + C((8 + 5)))
27328 := ((C(2) × 7) × ((- (3) × C(2)) + C(8)))
27334 := (((C(C(2)) - (7)) × (C(3) + C(3))) + C(4))
27335 := - (((C(2) - C(7)) - C(((3 + 3) × 5))))
27339 := ((C(C(2)) + (7 × C(3))) × 39)
27341 := ((- (2) + C(7)) + C((C(3) + (4 - 1))))
27343 := (C((27 + 3)) + C((4 + 3)))
27347 := ((C((27 + 3)) + (4)) + C(7))
27348 := (((C(2) × 7) - 3) × (4 + C(8)))
27352 := (((C(C(2)) + C(7)) × (C(3) + (5))) - C(2))
27355 := (((C(C(2)) + C(7)) × (C(3) + (5))) - (5))
27363 := ((C(C(2)) × ((7 × 3) - 6)) + C(C(3)))
27369 := (((C(C(2)) - C(7)) × (C(3) × 6)) - 9)
27376 := (C(2) × (- (7) + (C(3) × (C(7) - C(6)))))
27378 := ((C(2) + ((7³))) × 78)
27384 := ((C(2) × (- 7)) × ((C(3) - C(8)) - (4)))
27392 := ((2⁷) × ((- (3) + C(9)) - C(C(2))))
27423 := (((C(2) + (7)) × (4 + C(C(2)))) + C(C(3)))
27424 := (((C(C(2)) + C(7)) × (C(4) / 2)) + C(4))
27432 := ((- (C(2)) + C(((7 + 4) + C(3)))) / 2)
27434 := (- (2) + (C((7 + (4 × 3))) × 4))
27440 := ((C((2 × 7)) / 4) × 40)
27442 := (2 + (C(7) × (C(4) + ((4²))))))
27448 := ((C((2 + (7 × 4))) - C(4)) + C(8))
27456 := (C(2) + ((7 × C(4)) + C((5 × 6))))
27485 := (C(2) - ((- (7) - C(4)) × (C(8) - C(5))))
27496 := - ((C(2) × (C(7) - (4 × (C(9) + C(6)))))
27512 := (C(C(2)) + C(((7 × (5 - 1)) + 2)))
27523 := (((C(C(2)) + ((C(7) + C(5)))) × C(2)) + C(C(3)))
27546 := ((C(C(2)) - (7 × C((5 + 4)))) × (- 6))
27549 := (((- ((2 - 7)⁵) - C(4)) × 9)
27561 := ((2 × C(7)) + (C(5) × (C(6) - 1)))
27568 := (((C(2) × 7) + C((5 × 6))) + C(8))
27584 := (((- (2) × C((7 + 5))) × (- 8)) - C(4))

- 27621** := (((2⁷) × C(6)) - C((2 + 1)))
27623 := (((2⁷) × C(6)) + 2) - C(3)
27624 := (((2⁷) × C(6)) - (24))
27629 := (((C(2) + (7)) × C(6)) + C(29))
27634 := (2 × (-7) - (-((6³) × C(4))))
27642 := (((2⁷) × C(6)) - (4 + 2))
27646 := (((2⁷) × C(6)) + ((4 - 6)))
27648 := ((2 + ((7 + 6) × 4)) × C(8))
27653 := (-((2 - 7) + (C(6) × (C(5) + 3))))
27657 := -((C(C(2)) + (C(7) - (C(6) × (C(5) + (7))))))
27662 := (((2⁷) × C(6)) + (6)) + C(2))
27683 := (((2⁷) × C(6)) + 8) + C(3)
27684 := ((2 + 7) × ((6 × C(8)) + (4)))
27729 := (C((2 + ((7 + 7) × 2))) + C(9))
27746 := (2 × ((7 × 7) + C((4 × 6))))
27755 := (C(C(2)) + (-7) + ((C(7) - C(5)) × C(5)))
27776 := ((2⁷) × ((7/7) + C(6)))
27783 := ((-2) × C(7)) - (C(7) × (-83))
27792 := (((C((2 + 7)) - C(7)) × 9) × C(2))
27795 := (-2) - (-7) × (C((7 + 9)) - C(5))
27797 := ((C(-((2 - 7))) - C((7 + 9))) × (-7))
27817 := ((C(C(2)) × ((7 × 8) - 1)) - C(7))
27864 := (((-2) × C((7 + 8))) - C(6)) × (-4)
27875 := (((27 × 8) + 7) × C(5))
27945 := ((2 + C(7)) × (9 × (4 + 5)))
27969 := ((((-2) - C(7)) × C(9)) - C(6)) / (-9))
27973 := ((C(C(2)) × 7) + C(((9 - 7) + C(3))))
27974 := (((C(2) - C(7)) + C(9)) × (7 + C(4)))
28072 := -((C(2) - (80 × (C(7) + C(2))))
28078 := (-2) - (-80) × (C(7) + 8))
28125 := (((2 × 8) - 1)²) × C(5)
28165 := ((C(-((2 - 8))) - 1) × (6 + C(5)))
28203 := (((C(2) + C(8)) + C(20)) + C(C(3)))
28217 := (((C(2) - C(8)) × C(2)) + 1) × (-7))
28232 := (C(2) + (((C(8) - C(2)) / 3)²))
28249 := (((C(C(2)) - (82)) × C(4)) + (C(9)))
28272 := (((2 + C(8)) × C(2)) × 7) - C(C(2))
28323 := (((2 × C(8)) + C(3)) - 2) × C(3)
28324 := (((C(2) + C(8)) + (3^{C(2)})) × 4)
28333 := ((2 + C((8 + 3))) + C((C(3) + 3)))
28334 := (2 × (C((8 × 3)) + C((3 + 4))))
28439 := (C(2) + (((8 + 4) + C(3)) × C(9)))
28448 := ((C(2) - C((8 - 4))) × (4 - C(8)))
28456 := ((28 × (4⁵)) - C(6))
28474 := (-2) - (-84) × (C(7) - (4))
28476 := (((C(2) - C(8)) × (4 - C(7))) / 6)
28477 := (C(2) + ((84 × C(7)) - C(7)))
28512 := (C(-((2 - 8))) × ((C(5) - 1) + C(2)))
28575 := ((-((2⁸)) - C(5)) × (-75))
28576 := ((C(2) × 8) + ((C(5) + (7)) × C(6)))
28593 := ((C((2 + 8)) + (59)) × C(3))
28624 := -((C(2) × ((C(8) + (6)) - C((2⁴))))
28625 := (((2⁸) - C((6/2))) × C(5))
28643 := (((C(C(2)) - (-8) × C(6)) × 4) + C(C(3)))
28648 := (C((2 + 8)) - ((C(6) / (-4)) × C(8)))
28657 := (((2 × 8) + C(6)) × C(5)) - C(7)
28671 := ((C((2 + 8) + 6)) × 7) - 1
28672 := (C((2 × 8)) × ((6 - 7) + C(2)))
28674 := (2 + (((8⁶) × 7) / C(4)))
28688 := ((2 + ((C(8) × 6) + C(8))) × 8)
28704 := (C(2) × ((C(8) × 7) - (0 - 4)))
28721 := ((C((2 × 8)) + (7)) × (C(2) - 1))
28726 := (-2) - ((-8) - C((7 - 2))) × C(6))
28728 := ((C(2) - C(8)) × (-((7²) + 8))
28752 := (C(2) × ((C(8) × 7) + (5 × 2)))
28776 := (C(2) × ((C(8) × 7) + (7 + 6)))
28782 := (((2 + C(8)) × (7 × 8)) - 2)
28784 := (((2 + C(8)) × 7) × C((8/4)))
28791 := ((C(2) × (C(8) + (C(7) × 9))) - 1)
28792 := (C((2 × 8)) + ((C(7) × 9) × C(2)))
28811 := (C(28) + C((8 + 11)))
28819 := ((C(28) + 8) + C(19))
28864 := (C(28) + ((-8) × C(6)) × (-4))
28875 := (((28 × 8) + 7) × C(5))
28952 := ((C(-((2 - 8))) × (9 + C(5))) + C(2))
28963 := -((C(C(2)) + ((C((8 + 9)) × (-6)) + 3)))
28968 := (2 - ((C((8 + 9)) × (-6)) + C(8)))
29115 := (((C(2) × (C(9) - 1)) - 1) × 5)
29120 := (2 × ((C(9) - 1) × 20))
29125 := (((C((2 × 9)) + 1) - C(2)) × 5)
29135 := (((C(2) × (C(9) - 1)) + 3) × 5)
29145 := ((C((2 × 9)) + ((1 - 4))) × 5)
29152 := ((C((2 × 9)) × (1 × 5)) - C(2))
29155 := ((C((2 × 9)) × (1 × 5)) - (5))

$$\begin{aligned} 29158 &:= (-2) - (C(9) \times ((1 \times 5) \times 8))) \\ 29174 &:= ((C(C(2)) - 9) \times ((1 - 7) + C(4))) \\ 29184 &:= ((2^9) \times ((1 - 8) + C(4))) \\ 29234 &:= (2 \times ((C(9) + C((C(2) \times 3))) + C(4))) \\ 29247 &:= (C(C(2)) - ((9 + C((2^4))) \times (-7))) \\ 29248 &:= (C(2) \times (((9 + C(C(2))) - C(4)) \times 8)) \\ 29272 &:= ((C((29 + 2)) - (7)) - C(C(2))) \\ 29275 &:= (((-2) - C(9)) \times C(2)) - (7) \times (-5) \\ 29279 &:= (C((29 + 2)) - C(C(-(7 - 9)))) \\ 29296 &:= (C((C(2) + 9)) + ((C(29) - (6)))) \\ 29302 &:= (C((C(2) + 9)) + C((C(3) + 02))) \\ 29315 &:= ((C((2 \times 9)) + (31)) \times 5) \\ 29316 &:= ((C((C(2) + 9)) - C(3)) \times (1 \times 6)) \\ 29329 &:= (C((C(2) + 9)) + ((C(3) + C(29)))) \\ 29335 &:= (((C(2) + C((-9) + C(3)))) + C(3)) \times 5 \\ 29342 &:= ((C(2) + 9) \times (C((3 \times 4)) - 2)) \\ 29345 &:= (((C((2 \times 9)) - C(3)) + C(4)) \times 5) \\ 29368 &:= (C(2) \times (((-C(9)) + C(C(3)))/6) + C(8))) \\ 29376 &:= (((2 \times C(9)) \times (C(3) - (7))) + C(6)) \\ 29377 &:= -((C(C(2)) - ((C(9) \times (C(3) + (7 + 7)))))) \\ 29425 &:= ((C(C(2)) + ((C(9) - C(4)))) \times 25) \\ 29436 &:= ((C((C(2) + 9)) - (4 + 3)) \times 6) \\ 29437 &:= ((-((2 + 9)) + C((4 + C(3)))) - C(7)) \\ 29439 &:= -(((C(-(2 - 9)) - C((4 + C(3)))) + 9)) \\ 29453 &:= (((C((2 \times 9)) + C(4)) \times 5) - C(3)) \\ 29455 &:= (((C((2 \times 9)) + C(4)) - (5)) \times 5) \\ 29462 &:= (((C((C(2) + 9)) - (4)) \times 6) + C(2)) \\ 29464 &:= (-((2^9) - 4) \times (6 - C(4))) \\ 29466 &:= ((C((C(2) + 9)) + ((4 - 6))) \times 6) \\ 29486 &:= (C(2) - (C((9 + (C(4)/8))) \times (-6))) \\ 29529 &:= ((-((C(2) - C(9))) - (-5) \times C(C(2)))) \times 9 \\ 29535 &:= ((C((2 \times 9)) \times 5) - (-3) \times C(5)) \\ 29547 &:= ((C(C(2)) + ((C(9) \times 5) + C(4))) \times 7) \\ 29568 &:= ((-((2 - 9)) + C(5)) \times (C(6) + 8)) \\ 29573 &:= (C(29) + (C((5 + 7)) \times 3)) \\ 29574 &:= (C(C(2)) - ((C(9) - C(((5 \times 7) - 4)))))) \\ 29625 &:= (((29 + C(6)) - C(2)) \times C(5)) \\ 29641 &:= (-2) + ((C(9) - (6)) \times 41) \\ 29642 &:= (((C(C(2)) + 9) \times (-6)) + C((C(4)/2))) \\ 29645 &:= ((29 + C(6)) \times (-4) + C(5)) \\ 29649 &:= (((C((C(2) + 9)) - C(6)) + C(C(4)))/9) \\ 29672 &:= (C(C(2)) - (C(9) \times (-((6 \times 7) - 2)))) \\ 29686 &:= ((C((C(2) + 9)) \times 6) - (8 - C(6))) \\ 29697 &:= ((C(C(2)) + 9) \times (-6 - (9 \times 7))) \\ 29706 &:= (((C(C(2)) \times 9) + C(7)) \times 06) \\ 29723 &:= ((C(C(2)) \times (9 + (7^2))) + C(3)) \\ 29760 &:= ((C(C(2)) - (9 + 7)) \times 60) \\ 29763 &:= ((-((2 \times 9)) \times C(7)) + C((6 + C(3)))) \\ 29777 &:= (C(((C(C(2)) - (C(9)))/(-7))) - (7 + 7)) \\ 29791 &:= C(((29 - 7) + 9) \times 1) \\ 29792 &:= ((C(((2 \times 9) + 7)) - C(9)) \times 2) \\ 29795 &:= (C(((C(C(2)) - (C(9)))/(-7))) + (9 - 5)) \\ 29799 &:= ((C(2) \times ((9 \times C(7)) + C(9))) - C(9)) \\ 29832 &:= ((((-2) - C(9)) - C(8)) \times (-3)) \times C(2) \\ 29849 &:= (-((C(2) - C(9))) + ((-8) - C(C(4)))/(-9)) \\ 29853 &:= (((2 \times C((9 + 8))) + C(5)) \times 3) \\ 29865 &:= (C(C(2)) - ((C((9 + 8)) \times (-6)) + C(5))) \\ 29875 &:= (((29 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)) \\ 29877 &:= (C(29) - (-8) \times (C(7) + C(7))) \\ 29923 &:= ((C(C(2)) \times ((9 + 9) + 2)) + C(C(3))) \\ 30134 &:= (C((30 + 1)) + C((3 + 4))) \\ 30137 &:= ((C((30 + 1)) + 3) + C(7)) \\ 30272 &:= (((-C(30)) + C(C(2)))/(-7)) \times C(2) \\ 30372 &:= ((C(30) - 3) + C((7 + C(2)))) \\ 30375 &:= (C(30) + C(((3 + 7) + 5))) \\ 30378 &:= ((C(30) + 3) + C((7 + 8))) \\ 30477 &:= (C((C(3) - (0 - 4))) + (C(7) + C(7))) \\ 30493 &:= (C((C(3) - (0 - 4))) + (C(9) - C(3))) \\ 30625 &:= (((C(3) + C(06)) + 2) \times C(5)) \\ 30844 &:= (((-30) + C(8)) \times C(4)) - (4) \\ 30848 &:= ((-30) + C(8)) \times C(-(4 - 8)) \\ 30875 &:= (((30 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)) \\ 30887 &:= ((C(30) + C(8)) + C((8 + 7))) \\ 31034 &:= ((C((C(3) + 10)) - C(C(3))) + C(4)) \\ 31116 &:= ((C(31) + C(11)) - (6)) \\ 31122 &:= (C(31) + C(((1 + 2) + C(2)))) \\ 31123 &:= ((C(31) + 1) + C((C(2) + 3))) \\ 31125 &:= ((C((C(3) - (1 + 1))) \times 2) - (C(5))) \\ 31213 &:= (C((C(3) + 1)) + (21^3)) \\ 31221 &:= (C((C(3) + 1)) + (C(2) + C(21))) \\ 31223 &:= ((C((C(3) - (1 \times 2))) \times 2) - C(3)) \\ 31232 &:= (((-3) \times C(C((1 \times 2)))) + C(32)) \\ 31234 &:= ((3 - 1) - (C(C(2)) \times (3 - C(4)))) \\ 31235 &:= ((3 \times (1 - C(C(2)))) + C((C(3) + (5)))) \end{aligned}$$

- 31242** := ((C((C(3) - (1 × 2))) - (4)) × 2)
31249 := (C(31) - ((2 - 4) × C(9)))
31262 := ((C((C(3) - (1 × 2))) + (6)) × 2)
31265 := ((-31) + C(C(2))) × 65)
31338 := ((C(C(3)) + C(((1 - 1) + C(3)) - 3)) - C(8))
31432 := ((3 × C(((1 + 4) + C(3)))) - C(C(2)))
31449 := ((C(C((3 - 1))) × (C(4) - (4))) + (C(9)))
31464 := (C((C(3) - 1)) + ((C(4) + C((6 × 4))))))
31524 := ((C(31) + (5)) + C((C(2) + (4))))
31577 := (C((C(3) + 1)) - (C(5) × (-77)))
31625 := (-((3 - (16²))) × C(5))
31634 := ((C(C(3)) + (-1) × C(6)) + C((C(3) - (4))))
31723 := (C(C(3)) + ((1 + C(7)) × (C(2) + C(3))))
31742 := ((3 × (1 - C(7))) + C((C(4)/2)))
31744 := ((C((3 + 17)) - C(4)) × 4)
31843 := ((C(C(3)) + ((1 - 8))) + C((-4) + C(3)))
31849 := (C(C(3)) + (-1) + C(((8 × 4) - 9)))
31872 := (C((3 + 1)) × (C(8) - (7 × 2)))
31875 := (((31 × 8) + 7) × C(5))
31937 := ((3 × C((19 + 3))) - (7))
31944 := ((-3) + C((1 × 9))) × 44)
31954 := ((C(3) - 1) × (C(9) - (C(5) × (-4))))
32039 := (C(32) - C(((0 × 3) + 9)))
32044 := (((C(3) + C(20)) × 4) - C(4))
32049 := -(C(3) + ((20 - C(4)) × C(9)))
32125 := (((3 + C(C(2))) - 1)/2) × C(5))
32165 := (C((C(3) + 2)) + ((1 × 6)⁵))
32192 := (C(((3 + 2) - 1)) × (-9) + C(C(2)))
32224 := ((-32) - C(C(2))) + C((C(2) × 4))
32227 := (C((C(3) + C(2))) - C((C(2) + (2 × 7))))
32228 := ((C(32) - C(C(2))) - 28)
32229 := (((-3) - C(C(2))) + C((C(2) + C(2)))) × 9)
32232 := (((-3) × C(2)) - C(C(2))) + C(32)
32235 := ((C((C(3) + C(2))) + C(2)) - C((C(3) - (5))))
32246 := ((C(32) - C(C(2))) - (4 + 6))
32248 := ((C(32) - C((2 × 4))) - 8)
32251 := ((C(32) - C(C(2))) - (5 × 1))
32253 := ((-3) - C(C(2))) + ((2⁵)³)
32255 := ((C(32) - C(C(2))) - (5/5))
32256 := (((3 × C(2))²) × 56)
32259 := ((3 - C(C(2))) + C((C(2) × (-5 - 9))))
32261 := ((C(32) - C(C(2))) + (6 - 1))
32262 := ((C(((3 × C(2)) + C(2))) + (6)) - C(C(2)))
32264 := ((C(32) + C(2)) - C(C((6 - 4))))
32268 := ((C(32) + (2 × 6)) - C(8))
32277 := ((3 + (C(C(2)) × (2 + 7))) × 7)
32283 := ((C(3) - C(C(2))) + C((2⁸⁻³)))
32285 := ((C(3) - C(C(2))) + (2 + (8⁵)))
32292 := (((C((C(3) - 2)) + C(C(2))) + 9) × 2)
32297 := (C(3) + ((-2) - (C(C(2)) × 9)) × (-7))
32336 := ((C(32) - C((3 + 3))) - C(6))
32347 := ((C(32) + C(3)) - (C(4) × 7))
32358 := (C(C(3)) + ((-2) + C(3)) × (-5) + C(8)))
32362 := (C(C(3)) + ((C(23) + C((6 + 2))))))
32368 := (C(C(3)) + (((C(23) + (6)) + C(8))))
32379 := (((C(32) - 3) + C(7)) - C(9))
32384 := (C(32) - 384)
32387 := ((C(32) - 38) - C(7))
32389 := (C((C(3) + 2)) + (C(((3 + 8) + 9))))
32392 := (((C(C(3)) - C((-2) + C(3))) - 9) × C(2))
32421 := ((C(32) - (4)) - C((C(2) - 1)))
32424 := (((3 + C(C(2))) + C(4)) × (-C(2) - C(4)))
32425 := (C(32) - C(((4 - 2) + 5)))
32427 := ((C(32) + (4 - 2)) - C(7))
32429 := ((C(32) + (4)) - C(-((2 - 9))))
32432 := (((C((C(3) - 2)) + (4)) - C(C(3))) × (-C(2)))
32437 := ((C(32) + (4 × 3)) - C(7))
32445 := (((-3) - C(C(2))) × ((-4) - C(4)) + (5))
32448 := (((-3 + 2) × C(4)) + C((4 × 8)))
32451 := (((3 - C(C(2))) × (-C(4))) + (C(5) × (-1)))
32452 := ((C(3) + C((C(2) × 4))) - (C((5 + 2))))
32457 := ((C(3) + C((C(2) × 4))) + (5 - C(7)))
32464 := (C((C(3) × 2)) - C((46 + 4)))
32468 := (((C(32) - (4)) + C(6)) - C(8))
32472 := (((3 + C(C(2))) - C(4)) × 72)
32483 := (C(C(3)) + ((C(2) × (C(4) + (C(8) × 3))))))
32485 := (((3^{C(2)}) - C(-((4 - 8)))) × 5)
32487 := -(C((3²)) - (C(4) × (C(8) + (7))))
32488 := (((C(3) - C((2⁴))) + 8) × (-8))
32514 := (C((C(3) + 2)) - (C(5) × (-1) - C(4)))
32522 := (C(32) - ((C(5) - 2) × 2))
32525 := (C(32) - (((5 - 2)⁵)))
32528 := ((C(C(3)) - (C(25) - C(2))) × 8)
32535 := (C(3) × (((C(2) × 5) × C(3)) + C(5)))

$$\begin{aligned} 32552 &:= (-C((3 \times 2)) + C((5 + C((5 - 2)))))) \\ 32555 &:= (((3^{C(2)}) \times 5) - C(5)) - C(5) \\ 32562 &:= ((C((3 + C(2))) - C(5)) \times C((6/2))) \\ 32567 &:= -((C(C(3)) - ((2 \times C(5)) \times (C(6) - (7)))))) \\ 32572 &:= (-(((C(3) - C((2^5))) - C(7)) - C(C(2)))) \\ 32576 &:= ((3 - C(C(2))) \times (-C(((5 - 7) + 6)))) \\ 32585 &:= ((C(32) - (58)) - C(5)) \\ 32587 &:= ((C(32) - C(5)) - ((8 \times 7))) \\ 32616 &:= (((C(3) - 2) \times 6) + 1) \times C(6) \\ 32624 &:= (C(32) - (6 \times 24)) \\ 32625 &:= (((3^{C(2)}) - ((6^2))) \times 5) \\ 32632 &:= ((C(32) - (C(6) \times 3)) + C(C(2))) \\ 32633 &:= (C(32) - ((6 \times C(3)) - C(3))) \\ 32635 &:= ((C(32) - C((6/3))) - C(5)) \\ 32643 &:= (C(32) - C(((6 - 4) + 3))) \\ 32645 &:= ((C(32) + (6 - 4)) - C(5)) \\ 32649 &:= ((C(32) + (6)) - C(-(4 - 9))) \\ 32655 &:= (((3^{C(2)}) - ((6 \times 5))) \times 5) \\ 32677 &:= (C(32) - ((6 + 7) \times 7)) \\ 32678 &:= (C(32) - (6 \times (7 + 8))) \\ 32681 &:= (C(32) - (6 + 81)) \\ 32685 &:= (((C(32) - C(6)) + 8) + C(5)) \\ 32687 &:= (C(32) + (6 - 87)) \\ 32693 &:= (C(32) - ((C(6) + 9)/3)) \\ 32696 &:= (C(32) - (C(6)/(9 - 6))) \\ 32697 &:= (((C(3) - 2) \times C(6)) - C(9)) \times 7 \\ 32704 &:= (C(32) - C(((7 \times 0) + 4))) \\ 32712 &:= (C(32) - (7 \times C((1 \times 2)))) \\ 32714 &:= ((C(3) \times (-2)) + C(((7 + 1) \times 4))) \\ 32723 &:= ((C(32) - 72) + C(3)) \\ 32728 &:= (C(32) - (((7 - 2) \times 8))) \\ 32729 &:= (C(32) - ((C(7) + C(2))/9)) \\ 32732 &:= (((C(32) - (7)) - C(3)) - 2) \\ 32734 &:= (C((C(3) - (2 - 7))) - 34) \\ 32736 &:= (32 \times ((C(7) \times 3) - (6))) \\ 32739 &:= (((C(32) + (7)) - C(3)) - 9) \\ 32752 &:= ((C(32) - C((7 - 5))) - C(2)) \\ 32753 &:= (C(32) - ((7 + 5) + 3)) \\ 32755 &:= ((C(32) - C((7 - 5))) - (5)) \\ 32756 &:= (C(32) - ((7 - 5) \times 6)) \\ 32758 &:= (C(32) - ((7 - 5) + 8)) \\ 32760 &:= (((C(3) + C(C(2))) + (7)) \times 60) \\ 32761 &:= (C((C(3) - (2 - 7))) - (6 + 1)) \\ 32763 &:= (C(32) - (7 - (6/3))) \\ 32764 &:= (C(32) - ((7 - 6) \times 4)) \\ 32767 &:= (C(32) - ((7 - 6)^7)) \\ 32769 &:= (C(32) + ((7 - 6)^9)) \\ 32775 &:= (C((C(3) - 2)) + (C(7) + (7^5))) \\ 32776 &:= (C(32) + (((7 + 7) - 6))) \\ 32784 &:= (((3^2) + 7) + C((8 \times 4))) \\ 32792 &:= ((3 \times C(2)) + C(((7 + 9) \times 2))) \\ 32793 &:= ((C(32) + ((7 - 9))) + C(3)) \\ 32795 &:= (C(3) + C(((2^7)/(9 - 5)))) \\ 32797 &:= -((C(3) - (C(2) \times (7 + C((9 + 7)))))) \\ 32803 &:= ((C(32) + 8) + C(03)) \\ 32805 &:= ((3^{C(2)}) \times ((8 \times 0) + 5)) \\ 32816 &:= (C(32) + ((8 \times 1) \times 6)) \\ 32817 &:= (C(32) + ((8 - 1) \times 7)) \\ 32822 &:= ((C(3) \times 2) + C(((8^2)/2))) \\ 32823 &:= ((C(32) + (82)) - C(3)) \\ 32824 &:= (C(((3 \times C(2)) + 8)) - ((C(2) - C(4)))) \\ 32825 &:= (((3^{C(2)}) + (8/2)) \times 5) \\ 32826 &:= (C(32) + ((8^2) - 6)) \\ 32827 &:= (3 + (C(2) \times (C((8 \times 2)) + (7)))) \\ 32832 &:= ((C(3) - C(2)) \times C(((8 \times 3)/2))) \\ 32835 &:= ((3 - (C(2) \times (-8))) + C((C(3) + (5)))) \\ 32856 &:= (C(32) + ((8 \times (5 + 6)))) \\ 32859 &:= (-C(3) \times (C(C(2)) + ((-8) \times C(5)) - C(9))) \\ 32862 &:= ((C(32) + (86)) + C(2)) \\ 32875 &:= (((32 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)) \\ 32883 &:= ((C(32) + (88)) + C(3)) \\ 32885 &:= (C((3 + 2)) - (8 - (8^5))) \\ 32886 &:= (C(3) \times ((2 - C(8)) - ((-8) \times C(6)))) \\ 32893 &:= (C(32) + C((8 - (9/3)))) \\ 32921 &:= (C((C(3) + 2)) - (C(9) - C(21))) \\ 32924 &:= ((C(32) + (92)) + C(4)) \\ 32952 &:= (((-3) - C(C(2))) \times (-C((9 - 5)))) - C(2) \\ 32955 &:= (((-3) \times C((2 \times 9) - 5)) \times (-5)) \\ 32976 &:= ((C(32) - C((9 - 7))) + C(6)) \\ 32978 &:= (((C(32) + C(9)) - (7)) - C(8)) \\ 32984 &:= (((3 \times C(2)) \times 9) + C((8 \times 4))) \\ 32993 &:= ((C(32) + 9) + C((9 - 3))) \\ 32995 &:= (C(C(3)) + (C(C(2)) \times (-99) + C(5))) \\ 33124 &:= (((C(3) + C((3 + 1)))^2) \times 4) \end{aligned}$$

- 33125** := (C(C(3)) - ((C(3) - 1) × (C(C(2)) + (5))))
33169 := ((3 + C(31)) + C((6 + 9)))
33222 := ((C(C(3)) - ((3 × 2) × C(C(2)))) × 2)
33237 := (C(C(3)) + (C(3) × (C(C(2)) - (3 + 7))))
33245 := ((33 + C(C(2))) × (-C(4) - C(5)))
33253 := -(((C(3) - C(32)) - C((5 + 3))))
33258 := -((((C(3) - C(32)) - (5)) - C(8)))
33264 := (C(3) × (((3 × 2) × C(6)) - C(4)))
33275 := (C((((3 + 3) × C(2)) + (7)))/5)
33291 := (C(C(3)) - (C(3) × (C(2) - C((9 - 1)))))
33292 := (((3 + C(32)) + 9) + C(C(2)))
33298 := (((C(3) + C(32)) - 9) + C(8))
33327 := ((C((3 + 3)) + C(32)) + C(7))
33345 := (((C(C(3)))/3) - (C(3) × (-4))) × 5)
33372 := (C(C(3)) + ((C(3) × (-3)) × (C(7) - C(C(2)))))
33375 := ((-3) - (C(3) × (-3 + 7))) × C(5)
33385 := (C(C(3)) + ((3 + C((3 × 8))) - C(5)))
33416 := (C(C(3)) - ((C(3) - (C(4) × (-1) + C(6)))))
33443 := ((C(((3 + 3) × 4)) - C(4)) + C(C(3)))
33445 := (((C(C(3)))/3) + ((C(4) + C(4)))) × 5)
33446 := (C(C(3)) - ((-3) + C(4) - C((4 × 6))))
33459 := (C(3) + ((C((3 + C(4))) + (C(5)))/9))
33465 := ((3 - ((C(3) + (4)) × C(6))) × (-5))
33483 := (((-3) + C((3 × 4))) × 8) + C(C(3))
33492 := (3 + (((3 × C(4)) - 9)²)
33497 := (C((3 × 3)) + C((C(4)/9 - 7)))
33499 := ((C(3) + C(34)) - C((9 + 9)))
33507 := (C(C(3)) + C((3 × C(-((5 - 07)))))
33512 := ((C((C(3) - 3)) + (5)) + C(C((1 + 2))))
33513 := ((C((C(3) - 3)) + (5 + 1)) + C(C(3)))
33528 := (33 × ((C(5) + 2) × 8))
33529 := ((C(C(3)) + C(C(3))) + (-5 - C((2 × 9))))
33534 := ((C(C(3)) + C(C(3))) - C(((5 - C(3)) - (4))))
33539 := (((C(C(3)) + C(C(3))) + (5)) - C((C(3) - 9)))
33555 := (((C(C(3)))/3) + (C(5))) × 5 + (C(5))
33556 := ((C(C(3)))/3) - (5 - C((5 × 6)))
33559 := (((C(C(3)))/3) + (5)) × 5 + (C(9))
33561 := ((C(C(3)))/3) - (C((5 × 6)) × (-1))
33563 := ((C((C(3) - 3)) + (56)) + C(C(3)))
33565 := -((C(3) - ((C(3) + C(5)) × (C(6) + (5))))
33576 := (3 × (((C(3) + (5)) × C(7)) + C(6)))
33588 := (C(C(3)) - (C(3) × ((5 - C(8)) - 8)))
33595 := ((-C(3)) + C((C(3) + (5)))) + ((C(9) + C(5)))
33617 := (3 - ((C(3) - C((6 - 1))) × C(7)))
33623 := (((-C(3)) + C((C(3) - (6)))) + C((2 + C(3))))
33625 := (((C(3) × (-3 + 6)) + C(C(2))) × C(5))
33633 := ((C((C(3) - 3)))/(-6)) + (C(33))
33655 := (C((C(3) + 3)) - (C((6 + 5)) × (-5)))
33669 := ((C(C(3)) + (C(3) × 6)) + C((C(6)/9)))
33696 := ((3 + ((C(3) × 6) - 9)) × C(6))
33714 := -((C(C(3)) - ((C(37) + C(14))))
33723 := ((C(3) + C(C(3))) + ((7 + C(C(2))) × C(3)))
33769 := ((3 - (C(37) × (-6)))/9)
33792 := (-((33 × (7 - 9))) × C(C(2)))
33856 := (((-3) + C((C(3) - 8))) + (C((5 × 6))))
33858 := (C(C(3)) - (C(3) × (-((8 + 5)) - C(8))))
33865 := (((3 × 3) + C(8)) × 65)
33872 := ((C(C(3)) - (3 - (-8) × C(7))) × 2)
33875 := (((33 × 8) + 7) × C(5))
33957 := (((C(3) + C(3)) + (9 × 5)) × C(7))
33975 := (C(33) + (-9) × (C(7) - C(5)))
33993 := (C(33) + (-9) × C((9 - 3)))
34125 := (((C(3) + C(4)) × (1 + 2)) × C(5))
34209 := -((C(3) × (C(4) - C((2 + 09))))
34225 := (-C(3) + C(4))² × 25
34227 := (-C(3) + ((C(4) + 2) × (C(C(2)) + (7))))
34229 := ((3 + C((C(4)/2))) + (2 × C(9)))
34235 := (((-3 × 4)) + C(-((C(2) - C(3)))) × 5)
34236 := ((C(3) - C((4 + C(2)))) + C((C(3) + (6))))
34252 := (((3 + C(4)) × C(C(2))) - 52)
34259 := (((3 + C(4)) × C(C(2))) - (5 × 9))
34263 := (C(3) × (((4 + 2) × C(6)) - C(3)))
34265 := ((C((3 + (4²))) - (6)) × 5)
34267 := ((C(3) - C(4)) + (C(C(2)) × 67))
34273 := (((C(3) × 4) - C(2)) × C(7)) - C(3))
34276 := (((3 - C(4)) + C(C(2))) × 76)
34288 := (((3 + C(4)) × C(C(2))) - ((8 + 8)))
34295 := (C((((3 × 4) - 2) + 9)) × 5)
34297 := (((-3) - C(4)) × (-2⁹)) - (7))
34312 := (((3 + C(4)) × C(C((3 - 1)))) + C(2))
34317 := (((-C(3)) - C(C(4))) + C((C(3) + 1)))/(-7))
34327 := (C(3) + (((4 × C(3)) - C(2)) × C(7)))
34331 := (C(3) - (-((C(4) + 3)) × C(C((3 - 1))))
34389 := (((C(C(3)) - C(4)) + C(C(3))) - (C((8 + 9))))
34391 := ((3 + 4) × C((C(3) - (9 + 1))))

- 34432 := ((C((3 × 4)) - C(4)) + C(32))
34447 := (((C(C(3)) + (4/4))/4) × 7)
34477 := -(((C((-3) + C(4))) - C(C(4))) + (C(7) + C(7)))
34488 := ((C((3 × 4)) + C((4 × 8))) - 8)
34489 := -((C((C(3) - 4)) - C(-((4 - 8) × 9))))
34493 := -(((C((C(3) - 4)) - 4) - C((9 + C(3))))
34496 := (C((3 × 4)) + C(-((C(4) - 96))))
34533 := (C((3 × 4)) + ((-5) × C(C(3)))/(-3))
34536 := (3 × C(4) + (53 × C(6)))
34544 := (((C((3 × 4)) × 5) - 4) × 4)
34557 := (-3) + ((4 × 5) × C((5 + 7)))
34574 := (((C(C(3)) - C(C(4))) - 5)/(-7) - C(4))
34575 := ((-3) - (4 × C((5 + 7))) × (-5))
34623 := (((C(3) + 4) × 6)²) + C(3)
34624 := (((C(3) - (4 - 6)) + C(C(2))) × C(4))
34625 := -(((C(3) + ((C(4) - C(6)) × 2)) × C(5)))
34637 := (((C(C(3)) - C(C(4))) + (6/3))/(-7))
34647 := (((3 + C(4)) × C(C((6 - 4)))) + C(7))
34668 := (C(3) × (-4) - ((C(6) × (-6)) + 8))
34698 := (C((C(3) + 4)) - (6 - C((9 + 8))))
34768 := (((C(3) - 4) × 7) × C(6)) - 8
34776 := (C(C(3)) - (C(-((4 - 7))) × (-C(7) + C(6))))
34835 := (((C(3) × 4) + C((-8) + C(3))) × 5)
34845 := (-((3 + 4) + C(8)) × (C(4) + 5))
34853 := ((C(3) + C(4)) × (8 - (C(5) × (-3))))
34875 := (((34 × 8) + 7) × C(5))
34894 := ((34 - C(8)) × (-9 - C(4)))
34922 := -((C((C(3) - 4)) - ((C(9) - C(C(2)))²)))
34937 := (C(-((3 - (4 × 9)))) - (C((3 + 7))))
34944 := (3 × ((C(4) - C((9 × 4)))/(-4))
34965 := (C(3) × (-((4 × 9)) + C((6 + 5))))
34966 := (C(34) + ((C(9) - 6) × (-6)))
34968 := ((C(3) + ((-4) - C(9)) × 6) × (-8))
34973 := -(((C(3) - C(4)) × C(9)) + C((-7) + C(3)))
34986 := (C((3 + 4)) × ((9 + 8) × 6))
34992 := (C(3) × (4 × ((9 + 9)²)))
35138 := -((C(C(3)) + (51 - C(38))))
35152 := -((3 - 5) × C((1 + (5²))))
35183 := (C(C(3)) - (C(5) - C((1 + (8 × 3))))
35189 := -((C(C(3)) - C(-((51 - 89))))
35199 := (C((C(3) + (5 + 1))) + (-9 - C(9)))
35235 := -((3⁵) × ((2 + C(3)) × (-5)))
35242 := (C(C(3)) + (((C((5²)) - C(4)) - 2))
35244 := (C(C(3)) - (-((5²⁺⁴) + C(4)))
35254 := (C(C(3)) + ((C((5²)) - (54)))
35256 := (C(C(3)) - (52 - (5⁶)))
35264 := ((C(3) + C(5)) × (C(C(2)) - (C(6) + C(4))))
35289 := ((C(3) × (5 × (2⁸))) + C(9))
35304 := ((C(C(3)) + C(-((5 - 30)))) - 4)
35308 := (C(C(3)) + C(-((5 × (3 - 08))))
35313 := ((C(C(3)) + 5) + C((C(3) + ((1 - 3))))
35314 := (-((C(C(3)) - (C(5)))) + C(-(((C(3) - 1) - C(4))))
35323 := ((C(C(3)) + (5 × 3)) + C((-2) + C(3)))
35325 := ((-3) + C((5 + C(3)))) + (C(C(2)) × 5)
35328 := (((C(3) × 5) + 3) × (2⁸))
35329 := -(((C(3) - 5) + C(3)) × (C(2) - C(9)))
35338 := (-C(3)) + (-5) × ((C(C(3)))/(-3) - C(8))
35424 := (C(3) × (((-5) × C(4)) - C(2)) × (-4))
35456 := ((-3) - C(5)) × ((C(4) - C(5)) - C(6))
35475 := ((C(3) + (C(5) × (-4))) × (-75))
35512 := (C((C(3) + 5)) + C(((5 + 1) + C(2))))
35524 := (C(C(3)) + ((C((5 × 5)) + C((2 + 4))))
35526 := (C(C(3)) + (((C((5 × 5)) + 2) + C(6)))
35576 := (C((C(3) + 5)) - ((C(5) + C(7)) × (-6)))
35624 := ((3 - C(5)) × ((C(6) - C(C(2))) + 4))
35647 := (C(C(3)) - (-((5⁶) - 4) - C(7))
35655 := (3 × (5 + (C(6) × 55)))
35671 := -((((C(3) - C(5)) - 6) × C(7)) + 1)
35672 := ((C((3 + 5)) + C(6)) × (7²))
35692 := ((C(3) × (C((5 + 6)) - 9)) - 2)
35729 := ((3 + 5) - (-((7²) × C(9)))
35747 := (-3) + (C(5) × ((7 - C(4)) + C(7)))
35785 := -((C(3) + C(5)) + C(-((7 - (8 × 5))))
35825 := (C(C(3)) - ((-5) - C(8)) - C(25))
35839 := ((C(3) - C(5)) + C(((8 × 3) + 9))
35856 := (C(3) × ((5 - 8) + C((5 + 6))))
35875 := (((35 × 8) + 7) × C(5))
35927 := (C((C(3) + 5)) - (-9) × (C(2) + C(7)))
35934 := (-3) + C(((5 × 9) - (3 × 4)))
35936 := (((3 + 5) - 9) + C((C(3) + 6)))
35937 := C((((3⁵) - 9) - 3)/7)
35944 := -((C((C(3) - 5)) - ((C((9 × 4)) - C(4))))
35963 := ((35 - 9) + C((6 + C(3))))
35964 := (C(3) + C((C(5) - ((96 - 4))))

$$\begin{aligned}
 35968 &:= (((3 - C(5)) - (C(9) \times 6)) \times (-8)) \\
 35969 &:= ((C(3) + (5)) + C((9 + (C(6)/9)))) \\
 35983 &:= (-(((C(3) \times (C(5) - C(9))) + 8)) + C(C(3))) \\
 35991 &:= (C(3) \times (((C(5) - C(9)) - C(9)) \times (-1))) \\
 36035 &:= (C((C(3) + (6))) - (C(03) - C(5))) \\
 36056 &:= (C((C(3) + (6))) - ((0 - C(5)) + (6))) \\
 36125 &:= (((3 \times 6) - 1)^2) \times C(5) \\
 36126 &:= (C(3) \times (((C(6) - 1) + C(2)) \times 6)) \\
 36129 &:= (C((C(3) + (6))) + (C(12)/9)) \\
 36141 &:= (C(C(3)) + (6 \times (C(14) - 1))) \\
 36153 &:= (C((C(3) + (6))) + ((1 + 5)^3)) \\
 36162 &:= (C((C(3) + (6))) + ((1 + C(6)) + C(2))) \\
 36224 &:= (((C(3) + C((6/2))) + C(C(2))) \times C(4)) \\
 36233 &:= ((C((C(3) + (6))) + C(C(2))) - (C((3 + 3)))) \\
 36236 &:= (((3 - C(6)) + C(C(2))) + C((C(3) + (6)))) \\
 36244 &:= (((C(3) - (6)) + C(C(2))) \times (C(4) + (4))) \\
 36250 &:= (((-3) + C(6)) + C(C(2))) \times 50 \\
 36253 &:= (C((C(3) + (6))) + ((C((2 + 5)) - C(3)))) \\
 36261 &:= (C(3) \times (((C(6) + C(2)) \times 6) - 1)) \\
 36271 &:= (C((C(3) + (6))) - ((C(2) - C(7)) + 1)) \\
 36272 &:= (C(-((3 - (6^2)))) + ((C(7) - C(2)))) \\
 36274 &:= (C((C(3) + (6))) + ((-2) + C(7)) - (4)) \\
 36275 &:= (C(-((3 - (6^2)))) + ((C(7) - (5)))) \\
 36276 &:= (C((C(3) + (6))) - ((-2) - C(7)) + (6)) \\
 36277 &:= (((-3) + C((6 + 27))) + C(7)) \\
 36279 &:= (((3 \times C((6 \times 2))) \times 7) - 9) \\
 36288 &:= (C(3) \times ((6 \times 28) \times 8)) \\
 36297 &:= (C((C(3) + (6))) + (((C(2) + 9) + C(7)))) \\
 36307 &:= (C((C(3) + (6))) + ((C(3) + C(07)))) \\
 36315 &:= (C((C(3) + (6))) - (3 \times (-1) - C(5))) \\
 36317 &:= -((C(C(3)) - (C(((6) + C(3)) - 1)) \times 7))) \\
 36342 &:= (C(3) \times (((-6) + C(3)) \times C(4)) + 2) \\
 36344 &:= (C((C(3) + (6))) + ((C((3 + 4)) + C(4)))) \\
 36347 &:= (C((C(3) + (6))) - ((-3) - C(4)) - C(7)) \\
 36352 &:= ((36 + 35) \times C(C(2))) \\
 36366 &:= (C((C(3) + (6))) - ((3 - C(6)) - C(6))) \\
 36369 &:= (((C(3) \times 6) + 3) \times C(6)) + C(9) \\
 36375 &:= (((-C(3)) + C(C((6/3)))) \times 75) \\
 36387 &:= (C(3) + ((C(6)/3) \times (C(8) - (7)))) \\
 36396 &:= (C((C(3) + (6))) - ((C(3) \times (-9)) - C(6))) \\
 36423 &:= (((-((C(3) + (C(6) \times (-4)))) + C(C(2))) \times C(3)) \\
 36448 &:= (C((C(3) + (6))) - ((4/4) - C(8))) \\
 36449 &:= (C((C(3) + (6))) + C(-(((4/4) - 9)))) \\
 36450 &:= (C((36/4)) \times 50) \\
 36453 &:= (C((C(3) + (6))) + (4 + C((5 + 3)))) \\
 36458 &:= (C((C(3) + (6))) + ((4 + 5) + C(8))) \\
 36480 &:= (3 \times ((C(6) - C(4)) \times 80)) \\
 36483 &:= (3 \times (-6) + C(((4 - 8) + C(3)))) \\
 36498 &:= (C((C(3) + (6))) - (-49) - C(8)) \\
 36534 &:= (3 \times ((6 + 5) + C((C(3) - (4)))))) \\
 36542 &:= (((C((C(3) - (6))) - (C(5))) \times 4) - 2) \\
 36549 &:= (((C(3) + (6)) \times C(5)) - C(4)) \times 9 \\
 36552 &:= (C((C(3) + (6))) + (5 \times (C(5) - 2))) \\
 36556 &:= (C((C(3) + (6))) + ((5 \times C(5)) - (6))) \\
 36558 &:= (C(C(3)) + (((C(6) \times 5) \times C(5))/8)) \\
 36562 &:= (C((C(3) + (6))) + (5^{6-2})) \\
 36568 &:= (C((C(3) + (6))) + ((C(5) - (6)) + C(8))) \\
 36582 &:= (C((C(3) + (6))) + ((C(5) + C(8)) + C(2))) \\
 36624 &:= (((-3) \times C(6)) - (6)) \times (C(2) - C(4)) \\
 36625 &:= (((-3) - C(6)) + C((6 + 2))) \times C(5) \\
 36638 &:= (C((C(3) + (6))) + ((C(6) - C(3)) + C(8))) \\
 36639 &:= -(((C(3) - C(((6 \times 6) - 3))) - C(9))) \\
 36672 &:= (C((C(3) + (6))) + (6 + C((7 + 2)))) \\
 36675 &:= ((C(C(3)) - ((6 \times 6) \times C(7))) \times 5) \\
 36679 &:= (C((C(3) + (6))) + ((6 + 7) + C(9))) \\
 36693 &:= (((3 \times (C(6) - (6))) + C(9)) \times C(3)) \\
 36728 &:= ((C((3 \times 6)) \times 7) - C((2 \times 8))) \\
 36735 &:= (((-3) - (C(6) \times (7 + C(3)))) \times (-5)) \\
 36739 &:= (C((C(3) + (6))) + (73 + C(9))) \\
 36744 &:= (3 \times ((C(6) \times (-7) + C(4)) - C(4))) \\
 36786 &:= (C((C(3) + (6))) + ((C(7) + C(8)) - (6))) \\
 36792 &:= ((3 + 6) \times (C((7 + 9)) - C(2))) \\
 36828 &:= (C(3) \times ((C((6 + 8))/2) - 8)) \\
 36846 &:= (3 \times (((-6) \times C(8)) \times (-4)) - (6)) \\
 36863 &:= ((3 - C((6 \times 8)))/(-6 - 3)) \\
 36864 &:= ((3 + 6) \times C(((8 - 6)^4))) \\
 36875 &:= (((36 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)) \\
 36882 &:= ((3 + 6) \times (C((8 + 8)) + 2)) \\
 36922 &:= (C((C(3) + (6))) + ((C(9) + (2^{C(2)})))) \\
 36928 &:= (C((C(3) + (6))) - (9 - C((2 + 8)))) \\
 36936 &:= ((3 \times ((6 \times 9) + 3)) \times C(6)) \\
 36937 &:= (C((C(3) + (6))) + C(((9/3) + 7))) \\
 36944 &:= (((C((C(3) - (6))) - 9) \times 4) - C(4)) \\
 36946 &:= (C((C(3) + (6))) - (-9) - C((4 + 6)))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 36962 := ((C(3) × ((C(6) + 9) × 6)) + C(C(2)))
36963 := (((C(3) × 6) + 9) × C(6)) + C(3))
37042 := ((C((3 × 7)) × 04) - 2)
37044 := (C((3 × 7)) × ((0 × 4) + 4))
37084 := ((3 + 70) × (C(8) - (4)))
37146 := ((C(3) × ((C(7) + 1) × 4)) - (6))
37184 := (((C(3) × (C(7) + 1)) + 8) × 4)
37224 := (((3 × C(7)) - C(C(2))) × (C(2) + C(4)))
37233 := (-((3⁷) + (2 × (C(3) + C(C(3)))))
37243 := (((3⁷) × C(2)) + C(4)) + C(C(3))
37244 := (((C(3) × (C(7) + 2)) - (4)) × 4)
37248 := (C((C(3) + (7))) - ((C(2) - (-4) × C(8))))
37252 := ((C(C(3)) - (7)) + C(((C(2) + (5)) × 2)))
37256 := (C((C(3) + (7))) - (2⁵⁺⁶))
37259 := (C(C(3)) + C((7 + ((2 × 5) + 9))))
37263 := (C(C(3)) + ((7 + C(26)) - 3))
37287 := (C(3) × (C(7) - (-2) × (C(8) + (7))))
37324 := ((C((C(3) - (7))) + C((3 + C(2)))) × 4)
37326 := (((-3) + C(7)) - (3^{C(2)})) × (-6)
37341 := (C(3) × (((C(7) + 3) × 4) - 1))
37349 := ((C(3) - (7 + 3)) × C((4 + 9)))
37368 := (C(3) × (((C(7) - C(3)) × 6) - C(8)))
37379 := (3 + (73 × C(C(-(7 - 9))))))
37382 := (((C((3 + 7)) - C(C(3))) - 8) × (-2))
37395 := -(C(3) × (C(7) - C((3 × (9 - 5))))))
37427 := (-((3 × 7)) - ((C(C(4)) - C(2))/(-7)))
37440 := ((C((3 + 7)) - C(4)) × 40)
37448 := ((C(3) × ((C(7) × 4) - (4))) + C(8))
37452 := (((C(3) - (7)) + C(C(4)))/(5 + 2))
37457 := (-((3 + 7)) + ((C(C(4)) + (C(5)))/7))
37519 := ((-3) + C(7)) - (-51) × C(9))
37542 := (((C((3 × 7)) + C(5)) × 4) - 2)
37573 := (C((C(3) + (7))) - ((C((5 + 7)) + 3)))
37576 := (C((C(3) + (7))) - C(-((5 - 7) × 6)))
37584 := (C(3) × ((C(7) + (5)) × (8 - 4)))
37625 := (((3 × C(7)) - C(6)) - C(C(2))) × C(5))
37665 := ((C((3 × 7)) - C((6 + 6))) × 5)
37764 := (C((C(3) + (7))) + (-7) × (C(6) + (4)))
37824 := (((-37) × C(8)) × (-2)) - C(4))
37827 := (((C(C(3)) × (-7)) - 8) + C((C(2) × 7)))
37844 := ((C(3) × ((C(7) + 8) × 4)) - C(4))
37854 := (((C(3) × 7) + C(8)) × 54)
37875 := (((37 × 8) + 7) × C(5))
37884 := ((37 × (C(8) + C(8))) - (4))
37888 := (((3 + 7) + (8 × 8)) × C(8))
37921 := (((C(C(3)) + (7 - C(9))) × 2) - 1)
37935 := ((C(C(3)) + (-7) × C((9 + 3)))) × 5)
37962 := (37 × ((C(9) - C(6)) × 2))
37973 := (C((C(3) + (7))) - C((C((9 - 7)) + 3)))
37984 := (((C(3) × (C(7) + 9)) - 8) × 4)
38125 := ((-38) + C((-1) + C(2))) × C(5))
38126 := (((C(C(3)) - C(8)) × (1 × 2)) - C(6))
38175 := ((3 - C(8)) × (-1 × 75))
38213 := (C((3 × 8)) + C((2 + C((1 × 3))))
38225 := (((C(C(3)) - C(8)) × 2) + (C(2) - C(5)))
38234 := (((C(C(3)) - C(8)) × 2) + (C(3) × (-4)))
38269 := ((C(3) + C(8)) × (2 + 69))
38271 := (((C(C(3)) - C(8)) × 2) - 71)
38275 := -(C(-(3 - 8)) - (C(C(2)) × 75))
38279 := (((C(C(3)) - C(8)) × 2) - ((7 × 9)))
38325 := (((-3) × C(8)) + 3) × (-25))
38328 := (((C(C(3)) - (C(8) + 3)) × 2) - 8)
38342 := ((C(C(3)) - C(8)) × (-((3 - 4) × 2)))
38352 := ((C(C(3)) - ((8³) - 5)) × 2)
38354 := (((C(C(3)) - C(8)) + C(C(3))) + (C(5) × (-4)))
38358 := (((C(C(3)) - 8) + C(C(3))) + (C(5) × (-8)))
38429 := ((C((C(3) - 8)) + C(C(4)))/(-2 - 9))
38452 := (C(C(3)) + (((8 + 4) + C(5))²))
38475 := (((-3) + C(8)) + (4)) × 75)
38479 := (C(38) - ((4⁷) + 9))
38480 := (((C(3) - C(8)) + (4)) × (-80))
38488 := (C(38) + (-4) × C((8 + 8)))
38525 := (((3 × C(8)) + (5)) × 25)
38535 := (((3 × C(8)) × (-5)) - C(3)) × (-5))
38559 := ((-3) × C(8)) + (55 × C(9))
38616 := (((3⁸) - C((6 - 1))) × 6)
38629 := (((3⁸) × 6) - C(2)) - C(9))
38634 := (((C(C(3)) - (C(8) + C(6))) + C(C(3))) - (4))
38639 := (((C(C(3)) + (8 - 6)) + C(C(3))) - (C(9)))
38691 := -(C(3) × (C(8) + ((C(6) × (-9)) - 1)))
38723 := (((C(C(3)) + (8 - C(7))) × 2) + C(3))
38736 := (C(C(3)) + (87 × (3 + C(6))))
38745 := (C(3) × (((-8) - C(7)) + C(4)) × (-5))
38779 := (C(-((3 - 8) × 7)) - C((7 + 9)))

- 38822 := (((C(C(3)) - ((8 + 8))) × 2) - C(C(2)))
38838 := (((C(C(3)) + (-8) - C(8))) + C(C(3))) - 8)
38852 := (((C(C(3)) - C(8)) + C(C((8 - 5)))) - 2)
38862 := ((C(C(3)) + (8 - C(8))) + C(C((6/2))))
38873 := ((38 × (C(8) - (7))) + C(C(3)))
38875 := (((38 × 8) + 7) × C(5))
38912 := ((38 × C((9 - 1))) × 2)
38926 := (((C(C(3)) + (C(8) - C(9))) × 2) - (6))
38927 := ((C(3) × ((8 - C(9)) × (-2))) - (7))
38932 := ((C(C(3)) + ((C(8) - ((9³)))) × 2)
38934 := (((C(C(3)) × 8) - C((9 + 3)))/4)
38942 := (((C(3) × (8 - C(9))) - (4)) × (-2))
38964 := (-3) × (C(8) - (C((9 + 6)) × 4))
39023 := ((C(C(3)) - (C((9 - 02)))) + C(C(3)))
39034 := (-((3 × 90)) + C(34))
39088 := ((C(3) - C((9 + 08))) × (-8))
39123 := (C(C(3)) + (((C(9) - 1) - C(2)) × C(3)))
39132 := ((C(C(3)) - (9 × 13)) × 2)
39184 := ((C(C(3)) - (91)) × (8/4))
39195 := (39 × (C((1 + 9)) + (5)))
39221 := (((C(C(3)) - (9 × C(2))) × 2) - 1)
39223 := (((C(C(3)) - 9) × 2) - (C((2 + 3))))
39225 := (((3⁹) - C(2)) × 2) - C(5)
39232 := ((C((3 + 9)) × 23) - C(C(2)))
39235 := ((3 - 9) + ((2 × C(C(3))) - (C(5))))
39240 := (C((C(3) + (9 - 2))) - C((4 + 0)))
39241 := (((3⁹) × 2) - C((4 + 1)))
39242 := ((-(((3⁹) + 2)) + C(4)) × (-2))
39243 := (C((C(3) + (9 - 2))) - ((C(4) - 3)))
39244 := (C((C(3) + (9 - 2))) + (4 - C(4)))
39245 := (((3⁹) × 2) + 4) - C(5)
39246 := (C((C(3) + (9 - 2))) - ((C(4) - (6))))
39247 := (C((C(3) + (9 - 2))) - ((C(4) - (7))))
39248 := (C((C(3) + (9 - 2))) - ((C(4) - (8))))
39249 := ((C(3) × ((C(9) × 2) - (4))) - 9)
39252 := (C((C(3) + (9 - 2))) - 52)
39259 := (C((C(3) + (9 - 2))) - (5 × 9))
39265 := (((C(C(3)) + 9) × 2) + (6 - C(5)))
39268 := -(((C(3) + 9) - C((26 + 8))))
39272 := (((C(3) × (C(9) - 2)) + (7)) × 2)
39273 := ((-39) + C(2)) + C((7 + C(3)))
39274 := (((C(C(3)) - 9) × 2) - (74))
39277 := (-((3 × 9)) + C((27 + 7)))
39292 := (-((3 + 9)) + C(((C(2) + 9) × 2)))
39293 := ((C(39) - C(-(2 - 9))) - C(C(3)))
39294 := -((C(C(3)) - (-9) × (C(2) - (9⁴))))
39295 := ((C(3) × ((C(9) + 2) + C(9))) - C(5))
39297 := (C(((3 × 9) - 2) + 9)) - (7)
39298 := ((3 - 9) + C((2 × (9 + 8))))
39304 := C(((3 × 9) + 3) + 04))
39307 := (3 + C((9 × 3) + 07))
39312 := (C(3) × ((9³) - 1) × 2)
39316 := ((3 + 9) + C((C(3) + (1 + 6))))
39321 := (-C(3) - ((9 - C(C(3))) × (2 × 1)))
39322 := ((C(3) - 9) + C((32 + 2)))
39325 := (((C(C(3)) - 9) + C(C(3))) - (2⁵))
39327 := ((-39) + C(C(3))) + (C(27))
39329 := (C((C(3) - 9)) + ((C(32) + C(9))))
39330 := (((C(C(3)) - 9) + C(C(3))) - (C((3 + 0))))
39331 := (C(3) + C((9/3) + 31))
39332 := (((C(C(3)) + 9)/3) + C(32))
39333 := (C(C(3)) + (C((9 × 3)) - 33))
39334 := (((3 × 9) + 3) + C(34))
39335 := (((C(C(3)) - 9) + C(C(3))) - (C(3) - (5)))
39336 := (((C(C(3)) - 9) + C(C(3))) - (C(3) - (6)))
39337 := ((C(3) + (9 - 3)) + C((C(3) + (7))))
39338 := (((C(C(3)) - 9) + C(C(3))) - ((C(3) - 8)))
39339 := (((3⁹) - C(3)) + (3⁹))
39351 := (((C(C(3)) - 9) + C(C(3))) - (5 + 1))
39352 := ((C(C(3)) - ((9 + 3) - 5)) × 2)
39353 := (((C(C(3)) + 9) + C(C(3))) - (-5) + C(3))
39356 := (((C(C(3)) - 9) + C(C(3))) + ((5 - 6)))
39357 := (-C(3) + ((-9) - C(C(3))) × (5 - 7))
39360 := (C(C(3)) + ((C((9 × 3)) - (6 + 0)))
39361 := (C(C(3)) + (C((9 × 3)) - (6 - 1)))
39362 := (C(C(3)) + (C((9 × 3)) - (6 - 2)))
39364 := (C(C(3)) + ((C((9 × 3)) - (6 - 4)))
39365 := (C(C(3)) + (C((9 × 3)) - (6 - 5)))
39367 := (C(C(3)) + (C((9 × 3)) - ((6 - 7))))
39368 := (C(C(3)) + (C((9 × 3)) - ((6 - 8))))
39373 := (((3⁹) × 3) + 7) - C(C(3))
39374 := ((-((3 - 9)) + C((C(3) + (7)))) + C(4))
39375 := (((C(3) - 9) + C(3)) × 7) × C(5)
39376 := (((C(C(3)) + 9) + C(C(3))) + (7 - 6))

39384 := ((C(3) - 9) + (C(C(3)) × (8/4)))
39392 := (((C(C(3)) + 9) + C(C(3))) + (9 + C(2)))
39393 := ((C(3) + C((9 × 3))) + C((9 × 3)))
39396 := (3 - (9 × (-3) - (C(9) × 6)))
39420 := (C(3) × ((9 + C(4)) × 20))
39421 := ((C(C(3)) - (9 - C(4))) + C(C((2 + 1))))
39422 := ((C(C(3)) + ((9 × 4) - C(2))) × 2)
39423 := ((C(C(3)) + ((-9) + C(4)) + 2) + C(C(3)))
39429 := (((C(C(3)) + (9 × 4)) × 2) - 9)
39443 := ((C(C(3)) + ((9 + 4) + C(4))) + C(C(3)))
39456 := (3 × ((C((9 + 4)) - (5)) × 6))
39464 := ((((-3) - C(9))/(-4)) × C(6)) - C(4)
39473 := -((C(3) - (C((9 - 4)) × (C(7) - C(3))))))
39474 := (C(C(3)) + ((C(9) + (4)) × C((7 - 4))))
39483 := ((C(C(3)) + (C((9 - 4)) - 8)) + C(C(3)))
39492 := ((-3) + C((9 + 4))) × (9 × 2)
39512 := ((C(C(3)) + (9 + C((5 - 1)))) × 2)
39528 := (C(3) × (952 + C(8)))
39546 := ((C(39)/(-5 + 4)) × (-6))
39547 := (((3 - C(9)) × (-54)) + C(7))
39582 := ((C(3) - 9) × (C((5 + 8)) + 2))
39609 := ((C(3) + (C(9) × 6)) × 09)
39622 := ((C(C(3)) + C(C((9 - 6)))) + (2^{C(2)}))
39628 := ((C(39) - C(C((6/2)))) - 8)
39645 := -(((C(C(3)) - 9) - C(-((6 - 45))))))
39646 := ((C(C(3)) + C(C((9 - 6)))) + (C(4) + C(6)))
39647 := (C((C(3) + ((9 - 6) + 4))) + C(7))
39648 := -((((C(3) - C(9)) - (6)) × (C(4) - 8)))
39653 := (((C(3) × (C(9) + (6))) + C(5)) + C(C(3)))
39662 := (((C(C(3)) + C(C((9 - 6)))) - C(6)) + C(C(2)))
39663 := ((C(C(3)) + (((C(9) - C(6)) - C(6)))) + C(C(3)))
39722 := (((C(C(3)) + (9 - C(7))) + C(C(2))) × 2)
39727 := (((C(C(3)) - (-9 - C(7))) × 2) - C(7))
39736 := ((C(-((3 - 9))) + C((7 + C(3)))) + C(6))
39744 := (C((3 + 9)) × (7 + (4 × 4)))
39747 := (C(C(3)) + ((9 + C(7)) × (C(4) - (7))))
39752 := ((C(C(3)) + (C(9) - C(7))) + C(C((5 - 2))))
39753 := (((C(C(3)) + C(C((9 - 7)))) - (C(5))) + C(C(3)))
39763 := (((C(39) + C(7)) - C(6)) - C(C(3)))
39798 := ((C(3) × (9 - 7)) × (C(9) + 8))
39825 := (C(3) × ((C(9) - (C(8) × 2)) × (-5)))
39834 := (((C(3) - 9) + C(8)) + C(34))

39843 := (C(C(3)) - (-9) × (C(8) + C((4 × 3))))
39852 := -((C(3) × ((C(9) - C((8 + 5))) - C(2)))
39863 := ((C(C(3)) - ((9 - C(8)) + (6))) + C(C(3)))
39869 := ((C(C(3)) - (9 - C(8))) + C(C(-((6 - 9))))
39872 := -((C((C(3) + 9)) - ((C(8) - C(7)) × C(C(2))))))
39875 := (((39 × 8) + 7) × C(5))
39928 := ((-((3 - (9 × 9))) × C(C(2))) - 8)
39942 := (((C(3) × (C(9) + C(9))) + C(4)) + C(C(2)))
40123 := ((40 × (-1) + C(C(2))) + C(C(3)))
40375 := (C(40) - ((C(3) × 7) × C(5)))
40382 := (((-4) + C(C(03))) + C(8)) × 2)
40792 := ((-4) + (07 × C(9))) × C(2)
40875 := (((40 × 8) + 7) × C(5))
41024 := (C(4) - (-10) × C((2⁴)))
41123 := ((C((C((4 - 1)) + 1)) - C(C(2))) + C(C(3)))
41256 := (((C(4) + (1 × 2)) + C(5)) × C(6))
41280 := ((4 + C(C((1 × 2)))) × 80)
41287 := (41 × (C((2 + 8)) + (7)))
41375 := ((-((4 × 1) × 3)) + C(7)) × C(5)
41463 := (((4 - 1) - C((4 × 6))) × (-3))
41466 := (((4 - 1) × C((4 × 6))) - (6))
41472 := ((4 - 1) × C((-((4 - 7)) × C(2))))
41489 := -((C(4) - ((1 + C(4)) - 8) × C(9)))
41536 := (C(4) × ((1⁵) + (3 × C(6))))
41624 := ((41 × C(6)) + C((C(2) × 4)))
41625 := (((C((4 + 1)) + C(6)) - C(2)) × C(5))
41635 := (C(C((4 - 1))) + C(((6 + C(3)) - (5))))
41671 := -((C(41) - C((6 × (7 + 1))))))
41689 := (((C(4) + (16)) × C(8)) + C(9))
41739 := ((-4) - C(17)) + C((C(3) + 9))
41796 := ((C((C(4) - (1⁷))) + (C(9)))/6)
41832 := (((C(4) - 1) × 83) × C(2))
41833 := ((C(4) + C(18)) + C(33))
41875 := ((C((4 + 1)) × (-8)) + C((7 × 5)))
41921 := (C(41) - C((9 + 21)))
41930 := ((C(41) + 9) - C(30))
41976 := ((-4) - (C((1 + 9)) × (-7))) × 6)
41984 := (C(4) × (((-1) + C(9)) - 8) - C(4))
42125 := (((-4 + 2) + C((-1) + C(2))) × C(5))
42235 := ((C(4) × (-2) - C(2)) + C(35))
42237 := ((4 × (C(22) - 3)) - C(7))
42277 := ((4 × (C(22) + (7))) - C(7))

- 42279 := (((4 + C(2)) × C(C(2))) × 7) - (C(9)))
42332 := (((-4) - C(C(2))) - C(3)) + C((C(3) + C(2))))
42336 := ((C(4) - C(2)) × (C(3) + ((3⁶))))
42358 := (C(((4 × 2) + C(3))) - (5 + C(8)))
42363 := (-C((4 × 2))) + C((C(3) + C((6/3))))
42368 := (C(4) × (((-2) + C(3)) × 6) + C(8))
42375 := ((-4) × C((2 + 3))) + C((7 × 5))
42376 := (4 × C(((2 + C(3)) - (7)))) - C(6)
42394 := (((-C(4)) + C(C(2))) + 3) × 94
42423 := (((C(4) - C(C(2))) - (4)) + C((C(2) + C(3))))
42427 := ((C(4) - C(C(2))) + (C((42 - 7))))
42432 := (C(4) × ((-2) - C(4)) + C((3²)))
42494 := -(((C(4) + 2) + ((C(4) - C(9)) × C(4))))
42523 := (((-42) + C(5)) × C(C(2))) + C(3)
42532 := (-C(((4 - 2) + 5))) + C((C(3) + C(2)))
42533 := (((-4) × (C(2) - C((-5) + C(3)))) - C(3))
42536 := ((-4) × ((C(2) - C((-5) + C(3)))) + (6))
42552 := ((C(4) × ((C(2) + C(5)) × 5)) - C(2))
42555 := ((C(4) × ((C(2) + C(5)) × 5)) - (5))
42584 := ((-4) + ((C(C(2)) - (5)) × 84))
42591 := (4 × C((C(2) + (5 + 9)))) - 1
42592 := (((4 - 2)⁵) × C((9 + 2)))
42623 := (-((42 × 6)) + C((C(2) + C(3))))
42624 := ((C(((4²) + 6)) + C(2)) × 4)
42625 := (C((4 + 26)) + C(25))
42657 := (((-4 - 2) - C(6)) + C((5 × 7)))
42672 := ((-42) × ((C(6) - C(7)) × C(2)))
42675 := (((4²) - C(6)) + C((7 × 5)))
42683 := (((C(4)/2) × (-6)) + C((8 + C(3))))
42691 := (((C(C(4)) + 2)/6) - (C((9 + 1))))
42747 := ((C(4) × (-2)) + C(((7 × 4) + 7)))
42776 := ((C(C(4)) + (-2) × C((7 + 7)))/6)
42803 := (-((C(4) + C(2))) + C((8 + C(03))))
42811 := (-C(4)) + C((C(2) + C((-8 - 11))))
42813 := (-((C(4) - 2)) + C((8 + C((1 × 3))))
42833 := ((-42) + C((8 + (3³))))
42835 := (-((4 × (2 + 8))) + C(35))
42843 := ((C(4)/(-2)) + C(((8 × 4) + 3)))
42857 := ((C((-4) - (C(2) × (-8))))/5) - C(7)
42863 := (((-4) - C(2)) + C((8 + C((6 - 3))))
42869 := ((-4 + 2)) + C((8 + C((-6 - 9))))
42871 := ((-4) + C(((28 + 7) × 1)))
42872 := (((C(4) × (-2)) × (8 - C(7))) - C(2))
42875 := C((((4 × 2) - 8) + 7) × 5)
42879 := (4 + C(-((28 - (7 × 9))))
42883 := (((4²) - 8) + C((8 + C(3))))
42931 := ((C(4) - C(2)) + C(((9 + C(3)) - 1)))
42932 := ((C(4) + ((2 - 9))) + C((C(3) + C(2))))
42938 := (((C(4) + C(2)) - 9) + C((C(3) + 8)))
42939 := (C(4) + C(((29 - 3) + 9)))
42941 := ((C(4) + 2) + C(((9 × 4) - 1)))
42944 := (((4 + 2) + C(9)) - C(4)) × C(4)
42945 := -(((C(4) + 2) - (C(9) × (C(4) - (5))))
42947 := ((C(4) + C(2)) + C(((9 - 4) × 7)))
42957 := ((C(4) + ((2 × 9))) + C((5 × 7)))
42966 := ((C(4) - 2) × (C(9) - (6 × 6)))
42983 := (((4 + C(2)) × 9) + C((8 + C(3))))
43125 := ((C((4 + 3)) + (1 × 2)) × C(5))
43136 := (C(4) × ((C(3) - 1) + (3 × C(6))))
43154 := ((C((4 + 3)) × (1 + C(5))) - C(4))
43157 := -(((C(4) - 3) - ((1 + C(5)) × C(7))))
43168 := (((-C(4)) + C(C((3 + 1))))/6) - C(8)
43217 := (C(((C(4) - C(3)) - 2)) - (1 - C(7)))
43218 := (C((4 + 3)) + C((C((2 + 1)) + 8)))
43245 := (((4 + C(3))²) × 45)
43258 := (((-4) + C((C(3) + C(2)))) - ((C(5) - C(8))))
43264 := (((C(4) × 3) + C(2)) × C(6)) + C(4)
43276 := ((C(4) + C((C(3) + C(2)))) + (C(7) - (6)))
43290 := (((-4) - C(3)) + C(C(2))) × 90
43296 := (((-C(4) - 3) + C(C(2))) × 96)
43325 := ((C((4 × 3)) × (C(3) - 2)) + C(5))
43345 := (C(4) + (C(3) × (C((3 × 4)) - C(5))))
43375 := ((4 + C(((3 - 3) + 7))) × C(5))
43388 := (((4 - 3) + C((C(3) + 8))) + C(8))
43392 := (C(4) × (339 × 2))
43416 := (((C(4) + 3) × (4 - 1)) × C(6))
43452 := ((-4) × (-((C(3) + C(4)) × C(5))) + C(C(2)))
43557 := ((-4) + ((-((3 - 5) + C(5)) × C(7)))
43569 := (((C(4) - C(3)) × C(5)) + C(6)) × 9
43592 := (((-4) + C(35)) + C(9)) - C(2)
43595 := (((-4) + C(35)) + C(9)) - (5)
43597 := ((C(((4 + 3) × 5)) + C(9)) - (7))
43599 := (((4 + C(35)) - 9) + C(9))
43615 := (C((4 + C(3))) + C(-((6 × (1 - 5))))

43634 := ((C(43) - C((6 + C(3)))) + C(4))
43656 := ((C(C(4)) - ((-3) + C(6)) - (5)))/6
43680 := ((C(4) + C(3)) × (6 × 80))
43686 := ((C(C(4)) - (36 - 8))/6)
43712 := (C(4) × (-3) + (C(7) × (1 × 2)))
43725 := (((-4) + C((3 × 7))) - C(C(2))) × 5
43732 := (((4 - (3⁷)) - C(C(3))) × (-2))
43776 := ((C(C(4)) + C(C((3 - (7/7)))))/6)
43872 := ((4 × C(38)) - C((7 × C(2))))
43875 := (((43 × 8) + 7) × C(5))
43904 := (((-43) + C(9)) × C(04))
43912 := (((-4) - C((3 × 9) + 1)) × (-2))
43928 := -(((C(4) × (C(3) - C(9))) + C((2 + 8))))
43952 := (((C(4) - 3) × C(9)) - (5)) - C(C(2)))
43956 := (((4 × 3) × C(9)) × 5) + C(6)
43957 := (((C(4) - 3) × C(9)) - C(C(-(5 - 7))))
43981 := ((C(4) - 3) × (C(9) - (8 × 1)))
44093 := ((C(4) × (-40) + C(9)) - 3)
44192 := (((4 - C(4)) × (1 - C(9))) + C(C(2)))
44199 := -(((C(4) × (C((4 - 1)) - C(9))) + C(9)))
44217 := (((4/4) + C(2)) × C(17))
44247 := (((4 + C((4 × 2)))/4) × C(7))
44253 := (-((C(4) - C(((4 × 2) × 5)))) - C(C(3)))
44263 := ((4 - (C((4²)) × (-6))) + C(C(3)))
44268 := (C(4) + (((C(C(4)) + C(2))/6) + C(8)))
44325 := (((4 + 4) - C(C(3))) + C((C(2) × 5)))
44385 := (((C(4) + (4)) - C(C(3))) + C((8 × 5)))
44416 := ((C(4) + C(4)) × (4 + C((1 + 6))))
44469 := (((-C(4)) + C(-((4/4) - 6))) × C(9))
44492 := (((4 - C(4)) × (-4) - C(9)) + C(C(2)))
44532 := (C(-(4 - 45)) - C((C(3) + 2)))
44533 := (C(4) - ((C(4) - C(5)) × C((3 × 3))))
44573 := (-4) - ((C(4) - (5 × C(7))) × C(3))
44657 := (((4 - C(4)) × (-6)) × C(5)) - C(7)
44671 := (((C(4) + C(4)) × (6 + C(7))) - 1)
44672 := (-((4 × 4)) × ((-6) - C(7)) × C(2))
44696 := (-((4 × 4)) + ((C(6) - 9) × C(6)))
44738 := (((4 - C((C(4) + 7)))) + 3)/(-8)
44773 := (((C(4) + C(4)) × (C(7) + 7)) - C(3))
44853 := (((C(C(4))/4) + (-8) × C(5)) - C(C(3)))
44857 := ((C(4) × ((C(4) + C(8)) + C(5))) - 7)
44875 := (((44 × 8) + 7) × C(5))

44924 := (((-4) + C((4 × 9))) - C((C(2) + (4))))
44928 := ((C(4) + C(4)) × (C((9 - 2)) + 8))
44931 := (4 + ((C(4) × (C(9) - C(3))) - 1))
44932 := (-4) + ((C(4) × (C(9) - C(3))) + C(2))
44942 := (-((4⁴)) + (C(9) × (C(4) - 2)))
45125 := (((4 × 5) - 1)²) × C(5)
45136 := ((C(4) × (C(51) + C(C(3))))/C(6))
45194 := -((((C(4) - C(5)) - 1) × C(9)) + (4))
45198 := ((4 × ((C(5) - 1) × C(9)))/8)
45220 := ((C(4) + C((5 + C(2)))) × 20)
45225 := (45 × (C((C(2) + 2)) + (5)))
45276 := (((-((4 × 5) + 2)) × C(7)) × (-6))
45357 := -((C((4 × (5 + 3))) - (5⁷)))
45360 := ((C((4 + 5)) + C(3)) × 60)
45375 := ((4 - C(5)) × (-375))
45395 := ((C(-(C(4) - C(5))) + ((3 - 9)))/5)
45479 := ((C(4) × (C((5 + 4)) - 7)) - C(9))
45562 := ((C(45) + ((5 - 6)))/2)
45564 := (((-4) × C(5)) × (C(5) - C(6))) + C(4)
45568 := ((C(4) - ((5 - (5 × 6)))) × C(8))
45592 := (((C(4) - 5) + C((5 × 9)))/2)
45625 := (((C(4) + 5) - C(6)) + C(C(2))) × C(5)
45626 := (((-((4⁵)) + C((6²))) - 6))
45631 := (C(C(4)) - ((5 + 6) × C(C((3 × 1))))
45696 := (-4) × ((C(5) - 6) × (-96))
45727 := (((C(45) + C(7))/2) - 7)
45738 := (((-4) + C(5)) × ((C(7) + C(3)) + 8))
45750 := ((C(4) - C(5)) × (-750))
45752 := (((-((4 - 5)) + C(7)) × (C(5) + C(2)))
45783 := (((4 + C(5)) × C(7)) + (C(8) × 3))
45799 := ((C(4) × ((5 - 7) + C(9))) - C(9))
45824 := (((4 × C(5)) + C((8 - 2))) × C(4))
45832 := (((C(45) + C(8)) + C(3))/2)
45843 := (((C(C(4)) - (5 × 8))/4) - C(C(3)))
45853 := ((4^{5×8/5}) - C(C(3)))
45875 := (((45 × 8) + 7) × C(5))
45929 := ((C((45 - 9)) + 2) - C(9))
45933 := -((((C(4) - C(5)) × ((C(9) + C(3)) - 3)))
45936 := (((4 + 5) - C(9)) + C(36))
45945 := ((C(4) - (C(5) × (-9) - C(4))) × 5)
45955 := (((4⁵) × 9) × 5) - C(5)
46072 := (C(C(4)) - (C(60) + 72))

- 46144 := (C(C(4)) - C((6 × (14 - 4))))
46161 := -((C(4) - ((C(6) - 1) × (C(6) - 1))))
46199 := ((C(4) × (-((6 + 1) + C(9))) - 9)
46208 := ((C(4) + C((6²))) - C(08))
46216 := ((4 - C(6)) × (-2) - C((1 × 6)))
46224 := (((-4) + C(6)) + 2) × C((2 + 4))
46228 := (4 - (-((C(6) - 2)) × C(-((2 - 8))))))
46271 := ((C(4) × (-6) + C((2 + 7)))) - 1)
46272 := (C(4) × (-6 - (27²)))
46296 := (((4 + 6) × C(C(2))) × 9) + C(6))
46305 := (C(((4 × 6) - 3)) × 05)
46317 := ((4 + C((6³⁻¹))) - C(7))
46325 := (((-4) + C((-6) + C(3))) + C(2)) × 5)
46345 := (((4 + C((-6) + C(3))) + (4)) × 5)
46349 := -((((C(4) + C(6)) + C(3)) - C((4 × 9))))
46360 := (C(C(4)) - (-((6³) + C(60)))
46364 := (((4 - C(6)) × (-3) - C(6)) - C(4))
46368 := -((((C(4) + C(6)) - C(36)) + 8))
46369 := (C(4) - (-63) × (6 + C(9)))
46375 := ((C(4) + 6) + (C(3 × 7)) × 5)
46384 := ((C((C(4) + 6))) - (C(C(3)) × 8))/4)
46394 := -((((C(4) + 6) + ((3 - C(9)) × C(4))))
46436 := ((-4) - C(6) + C((4 × (3 + 6))))
46457 := (((C(4) × 6) × (-4) + C(5)) - 7)
46497 := (((C(4) - C(6)) + C((4 × 9)) - 7)
46522 := (C(C(4)) + (-6) × C((5²) + C(2))))
46524 := (-4) - (-((C(6) - C(5)) × C(C(2))) + C(4))
46528 := (((C(4) × (C(6) - C(5))) - C(2)) × 8)
46535 := ((4 + C((6⁵⁻³))) - C(5))
46536 := (-((4 × 6) × 5) + C(36))
46539 := ((C(-((4 - 6))) - C(5)) + C((C(3) + 9)))
46552 := (((C(4) × (C(6) - C(5))) - 5) × C(2))
46557 := ((4 + (C((6 + 5)) × (-5))) × (-7))
46562 := -((((C(4) + ((6 × 5))) - C((6²))))
46565 := (((4 + C(6)) - 5) × C(6)) + C(5)
46568 := (-((4 × 6)) - ((C(5) - C(6)) × C(8)))
46572 := (((-4) - (C(6) × (C(5) - C(7)))) - C(C(2)))
46576 := -((C(C(-((4 - 6)))) + ((C(5) - C(7)) × C(6))))
46584 := (-4) + (((C(6) - C(5)) × C(8)) - 4))
46586 := ((C(4) × ((C(6) - C(5)) × 8)) - 6)
46588 := (4 + (((C(6) - C(5)) × C(8)) - 8))
46591 := ((C(4) × (-((6 - 5) + C(9))) - 1)
46592 := (C(4) × (((6 - 5) + C(9)) - 2))
46593 := (-((C(4) - (6 - 5))) + C((9 + C(3))))
46595 := ((C(4) × ((6 - 5) + C(9))) - C(5))
46598 := (((C(C(4)) + 6)/5) - (C(9) × 8))
46623 := (-((4 - ((6⁶) - 2))) - C(3))
46624 := -((((C(4) - (6⁶)) - (C(2) × 4)))
46625 := (-((4 - (6⁶))) - C(-((2 - 5))))
46639 := (C(4) + ((C(6) × (C(6) + 3)) - C(9)))
46662 := ((4 + ((6⁶) - 6)) + C(2))
46664 := (C(-((4 - 6))) + C((6⁶⁻⁴)))
46668 := ((4 + (6⁶)) + C(-((6 - 8))))
46683 := (C((4 × ((6/6) + 8))) + C(3))
46693 := (C(4) + (((6⁶) - (9 × 3))))
46712 := ((C(4) + (6⁷⁻¹)) - C(2))
46715 := (C(4) + (((6⁷⁻¹) - 5)))
46762 := ((C(4) + (6 × 7)) + C((6²)))
46766 := -((C(4) + ((C(6) + 7)) × (6 - C(6))))
46782 := (46 × (-7) + (C(8) × 2))
46784 := ((((-4) + C(6)) + 7) + C(8)) × C(4))
46835 := ((C(4) × (C(6) + C(8))) + ((3⁵)))
46844 := (((4 + C(6)) + C(8)) × C(4)) - 4)
46845 := ((C(4) + C((6^{8/4}))) + C(5))
46848 := ((((-4) + C(6)) + C(8)) × C(4)) + C(8))
46875 := (((46 × 8) + 7) × C(5))
46876 := (4 + ((C(6) + (8 - 7)) × C(6)))
46879 := (4 - (C((68 + 7))/(-9)))
46892 := ((4 - C(6)) + (C(8) × 92))
46896 := ((4 × 6) - ((C(8) - C(9)) × C(6)))
46912 := (C(4) × ((6 + C(9)) - (1 × 2)))
46915 := ((C(4) × (6 + C(9))) + (-1) × C(5))
46927 := (-4) - ((C(69) + C(2))/(-7))
46928 := (C(4) + ((C(6) × (C(9) - C(C(2)))) - 8))
46933 := (((C(4) + C(6)) + C((9 + C(3)))) - 3)
46936 := ((C(4) + C(6)) + ((9 - 3)⁶)
46939 := (C(4) - (C(((C(6) + 9)/3))/(-9)))
46948 := (((-4) - C(6)) + C((9 × 4))) + C(8))
46970 := (((C(4) - 6) - C(9)) × (-70))
46976 := (C(4) × ((6 + C(9)) - (7 - 6)))
46984 := ((C(4) × (6 + C(9))) + (8 - C(4)))
46995 := ((C(4) × (6 + C(9))) - (9 × 5))
47097 := ((C(4) × (7 + C(09))) - 7))

- 47125 := ((-((C(4) + 71)) + C(C(2))) × C(5))
47168 := (C(-((4 × (7 - 16)))) + C(8))
47232 := (C(4) × ((7 + 2) + C((3²))))
47239 := (((C(4) + (7)) + C(C(2))) + C((C(3) + 9)))
47296 := (-4) × (C(7) - C((29 - 6)))
47323 := ((C(4) × 7) - (-3) × C((-2) + C(3)))
47365 := (((4 - C((7 × 3))) - C(6)) × (-5))
47389 := (4 - (-((73 - 8)) × C(9)))
47417 := ((C(4) × 741) - (7))
47424 := ((C(4) × 742) - C(4))
47449 := (C((C(4) - ((7 × 4)))) + (C(4) + C(9)))
47533 := ((4 × ((7⁵) - 3)) - C(C(3)))
47537 := ((C((C(4) - (7))) + (C(5))) - (C(C(3)) × 7))
47539 := ((4 + C(7)) × (C(5) + (3 + 9)))
47552 := (-C(4)) - (-(((C(7) - C(5)) - C(5)) × C(C(2))))
47573 := ((4 × ((7⁵) + 7)) - C(C(3)))
47625 := (((-4) - C(7)) + C(6)) + C(C(2)) × C(5)
47656 := (C((4 × 7)) + ((-6) + C(5)) × C(6))
47665 := -(((C(4) + (7)) - (C(6) × (C(6) + (5))))))
47677 := (((C(4) + 76) × C(7)) - C(7))
47712 := ((C(C(4)) + ((C(7) - C(71)))) / (-2))
47744 := (((-4) + C(7)) + C(7)) + C(4) × C(4)
47775 := (((-4) × C(7)) + (7)) × (-7 × 5))
47843 := (((C(4) × 7) - 8) × C(4)) + C(C(3))
47875 := ((47 × 8) + 7) × C(5)
47884 := (4 - ((C(7) + C(8)) × (8 - C(4))))
47916 := (C((4 + ((7 × 9) - 1))) / 6)
47924 := (((C((4 + 7)) × 9) + 2) × 4)
47933 := ((C(4) × ((-7) + C(9)) + C(3)) - 3)
47936 := (C(4) × ((-7) + C(9)) + C(-((3 - 6))))
47943 := ((C((4 + 7)) × (9 × 4)) + C(3))
47956 := -((C(4) + (C(7) × ((-9) - C(5)) - (6))))
48064 := (C(4) - ((C(80) × (-6)) / C(4)))
48128 := (((48 - 1) × 2) × C(8))
48237 := (((4 × 8) + C(-((C(2) - C(3)))))) × 7)
48256 := (C(4) × (-8) + ((-2) - C(5)) × (-6))
48328 := -((C(4) - (8 × ((3^{C(2)}) - C(8))))
48375 := (((4 × (8 + 3)) + C(7)) × C(5))
48384 := (C((4 + 8)) × ((3 × 8) + 4))
48388 := (-4) - ((C(8) - (3⁸)) × 8)
48392 := ((C(4) + (C(8) × (C(3) + C(9)))) / C(2))
48448 := (C(4) + (84 × (C(4) + C(8))))
48594 := (-4) - ((C(8) + (5)) × (-94))
48640 := (((C(C(4)) + C(8)) / (-C(6))) × (-40))
48672 := ((48 × 6) × (-C(7)) + C(C(2)))
48676 := ((-4) + C(8)) + ((C(6) + (7)) × C(6))
48689 := (((C(C(4)) + C(8)) / 6) + (C((8 + 9))))
48768 := (48 × ((C(7) - C(6)) × 8))
48839 := (-4) - (-(((8 × 8) + 3)) × C(9))
48843 := (C(((C(4) + 8) / 8)) × (C(4) + 3))
48875 := (((48 × 8) + 7) × C(5))
48934 := (-((C((4 + 8)) - 9)) + C(-((C(3) - C(4))))
49152 := ((C(4) × (91 + 5)) × C(2))
49216 := (C(4) × (C(9) + (C(2) × (-1 - 6))))
49233 := (((4⁹⁻²) + C(3)) × 3)
49234 := ((C((49 - C(2))) - C(C(3))) - (4))
49243 := (-4) + (C((9 + 2)) × (C(4) - C(3)))
49272 := ((C(4) × (C(9) - 2)) + C((7 × 2)))
49275 := (((C(4) - C(9)) + C(2)) × (-75))
49298 := (4 + ((9 - C(C(2))) × (-98))
49348 := ((-((C(4) + C(9))) + C(-((C(3) - C(4)))))) - C(8))
49375 := (((49 + 3) + C(7)) × C(5))
49392 := (-4) × ((-9) - C(3)) × C((9 - 2))
49397 := (-4) + (9 × (C((C(3) - 9)) - C(7)))
49419 := ((C(4) × (C(9) - C(4))) + C(19))
49432 := (-((4 - 9⁴)) + C((C(3) + C(2))))
49444 := -((C(4) - ((C(9) × (C(4) + (4))) - C(4))))
49536 := (C(4) × ((9 × 5) + (3⁶)))
49544 := -(((C(C(4)) + C((9 + 5))) - C((C(4) + (4))))))
49572 := ((C(4) + (9 - 5)) × C((7 + 2)))
49625 := -((C((C(4) - 9)) - C(((6 × 2) × 5)))
49656 := (-4) × (((9 × C(6)) + C(5)) × (-6))
49697 := -((C(4) - ((C(9) - C(6)) × 97))
49724 := (C(4) + ((97 × C(C(2))) - (4)))
49725 := (-C(4)) - ((-97) × C(C(2))) - (C(5)))
49728 := (((C(4) × (-97)) - C(2)) × (-8))
49734 := (((C(4) × (-9)) - C(7)) + C(-((C(3) - C(4))))
49735 := (((4 - C(9)) × (-7³)) / 5)
49739 := ((-4) + (9 × C(7))) + C((C(3) + 9))
49785 := (-4) + ((97 × C(8)) + C(5))
49792 := (C(4) × (C(9) + (7 × (9 - 2))))
49844 := ((-4) - C(9)) × ((-8) - C(4)) + (4))
49848 := (C(4) + (-98) × (4 - C(8)))
49875 := ((C(4) - C(9)) × (-((8 + 7) × 5)))

- 49896** := $((-(498) + C(9)) \times C(6))$
49928 := $((4 - C(9)) + C((9 + 28)))$
49937 := $((4 + 9) - C(9)) + C(37)$
50653 := $C(((5 + ((0 \times 6) + 5)) + C(3)))$
50688 := $-(((C(5) - C(06)) - 8) \times C(8))$
50875 := $((50 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)$
51102 := $(51 \times (C(10) + 2))$
51255 := $(51 \times (C((2 \times 5)) + (5)))$
51408 := $((C(5) + 1) \times 408)$
51479 := $((C(5) \times ((-1) + C(4)) + C(7))) + C(9)$
51488 := $(-C(5) + (-1 + 4)^8) \times 8$
51743 := $(C(((5 - 1) \times 7)) + C((4 + C(3))))$
51759 := $(-(((5 - 1) - 75)) \times C(9))$
51858 := $-(((C(5) + (1 + 8)) \times (C(5) - C(8))))$
51875 := $((51 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)$
52135 := $(((-5) + C(21)) - C(C(3))) \times (-5)$
52136 := $-((C((5 + 2)) \times (C((1 + 3)) - C(6))))$
52225 := $((-5) - ((C(C(2)) - 2) \times C(C(2)))) / (-5)$
52238 := $((C(5) \times (-2)) - (C(2) \times (-3^8)))$
52266 := $((((C(5) \times 2) - C(2)) \times C(6)) - (6))$
52299 := $((5 - (C(2) \times (-2) + C(9))) \times (-9))$
52324 := $((-(C(5) + 2) + C(C(3))) + C((C(2) \times 4)))$
52336 := $(C((5 \times C(2))) - ((C(3) + C(3)) \times C(6)))$
52353 := $((-5) - (C(2) \times (-3^5))) \times C(3)$
52363 := $-((C(5) - (C(2) \times (3^{C(6/3)}))))$
52364 := $((C(5) \times 2) - 3) \times (C(6) - (4))$
52416 := $((C(5) - C(2)) \times C(4)) \times (1 + 6)$
52425 := $((C((5 - 2)) - C(C(4))) - C(2)) / (-5)$
52437 := $((C(5) - C(2)) \times C(4)) + 3 \times 7$
52438 := $(((-5) + C((C(2) \times 4))) + C(C(3))) - 8$
52445 := $((((5 - 2)^4) + C(C(4))) / 5)$
52459 := $-((C((5 + C(2))) - ((C(4) \times (C(5) + C(9))))))$
52465 := $(-5) \times ((C((C(2) + 4))) \times (-6) - (C(5)))$
52479 := $((((-5) - C(2)) - (4)) \times C(7)) \times (-9)$
52483 := $(-5) - (C(((2) + C(4)) - 8)) / (-3)$
52493 := $(5 + ((C(2) + C(4)) \times (9^3)))$
52528 := $(5 + (-2 + 5)^{C(2)}) \times 8$
52533 := $(5 - (C(2) \times (-5) + (C(C(3)) / (-3))))$
52603 := $-((C(5) + (C(26) \times (0 - 3))))$
52625 := $(C(5) \times (((C(2) - C(6)) \times (-2)) + (5)))$
52632 := $((-C(5) + C(C(2))) \times ((C(6) \times 3) - C(C(2))))$
52634 := $((C((5 + C(2))) - C(6)) + C(-((C(3) - C(4))))$
52648 := $((C((5 + 2)) \times (C(6) - C(4))) + C(8))$
52656 := $((C((5 \times 2)) + (6^5)) \times 6)$
52697 := $((5 + ((C(C(2)) - (6)) \times C(9))) / 7)$
52713 := $((5 - C((27 - 1))) \times (-3))$
52728 := $((5 \times (C((C(2) + (7 \times 2)))) - C(8))$
52733 := $(5 + (C(-((C(2) - (7)) - C(3)))) \times 3)$
52743 := $(((-5) - C(-((2 - (7 \times 4)))))) \times (-3)$
52762 := $((C(5) \times (-2)) \times (7 - C(6))) + C(C(2))$
52853 := $(C(5) + (C((2 \times (8 + 5)))) \times 3)$
52875 := $((52 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)$
52992 := $((((5 + 2) + C(9)) \times 9) \times C(2))$
52997 := $(5 + ((C(2) \times 9) \times (C(9) + (7))))$
53103 := $((-C(5) - C((C(3) - 1))) \times (0 - 3))$
53133 := $((5 \times C(3)) + C((-1 + C(3)))) \times 3$
53163 := $((5 \times 31) \times C(6)) + C(C(3))$
53195 := $((C((-5) + C(3))) - (1 \times 9)) \times 5$
53225 := $(-(5 \times 3) - (C(22) \times (-5)))$
53232 := $(5 \times C((C(3) - (2 + 3)))) - C(2)$
53235 := $((C((-5) + C(3))) + ((2 - 3))) \times 5$
53240 := $(C((5 + (3 \times 2))) \times 40)$
53248 := $(5 \times C(32)) - C(48)$
53295 := $((C((-5) + C(3))) + (2 + 9)) \times 5$
53325 := $-(((C((-5) + C(3))) + C(3)) - C((C(2) \times 5)))$
53352 := $((C(5) + C(3)) \times C(3)) \times (5 + C(2))$
53396 := $((C((5 + C(3))) + C(C(3))) + ((C(9) + C(6))))$
53443 := $-((C(5) - ((C(3) + 4)) \times C((4 \times 3))))$
53475 := $((C((-5) + C(3))) + 47) \times 5$
53488 := $((C(5) + (3^{C(4)/8})) \times 8)$
53545 := $(((-C(5)) - C((C(3) - 5))) + C(4)) \times (-5)$
53564 := $((5 + (3^5)) \times C(6)) - (4)$
53565 := $(5 \times (C((C(3) - 5))) + (65))$
53625 := $((C(5) \times (-3)) - ((C(6) \times (-2)) \times C(5)))$
53649 := $((C(5) + C((3 \times 6))) + (4)) \times 9$
53657 := $((5 - 3) \times C((6 \times 5))) - C(7)$
53752 := $((C((5 \times 3) + 7)) \times 5) + C(C(2))$
53760 := $((C(5) + 3) \times (7 \times 60))$
53768 := $((-C(5)) - C(C(3))) + (C((7 \times 6)) - C(8))$
53785 := $(-5) \times ((-(3 \times 7)) \times C(8) - (5))$
53824 := $((5 + (3 \times 8))^2) \times C(4)$
53848 := $((C(5) - C(3)) + 8) \times (-4) + C(8)$
53853 := $((5 \times C((C(3) - 8))) - (C(5))) + C(C(3))$
53875 := $((53 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)$

- 53928 := -((((C(5) - C(3)) + 9) × (C(2) - C(8))))
53973 := ((C((5 × 3)) × (9 + 7)) - C(3))
54143 := (-C((5 + 4))) + C(((1 + C(4)) - C(3)))
54189 := (((C(5) + C(4)) + C(18)) × 9)
54216 := (((C(5) × (4 - 2)) + 1) × C(6))
54243 := (((5 × 4) × C((C(2) + (4)))) + C(C(3)))
54272 := (((C(5) - (4)) - C(2)) - (7)) × C(C(2)))
54273 := (-(((C(5) - C(42)) + (7))) - C(C(3)))
54275 := (-C(5)) - (-C(4) × (C(C(2)) + ((C(7) - (5))))))
54277 := (5 - (-C(4) × (C(C(2)) - (7 - C(7))))))
54329 := (5 - ((-4) × C(3)) × (C(C(2)) - 9))
54375 := (C(5) + (((C(4) + C(3)) + C(7)) × C(5)))
54450 := ((C(5) - (4)) × 450)
54500 := -(C(5) × (C(4) - (500)))
54537 := (((C(5) - C(4)) + C(5)) - C(3)) × C(7)
54625 := (C(5) × (((-4) × C(6)) / (-2)) + (5))
54648 := ((5 + C(4)) × ((C(6) + C(4)) + C(8)))
54656 := (C((5 × 4)) + ((6⁵) × 6))
54662 := ((C((5 × 4)) + (6)) + C((6²)))
54665 := ((-((5⁴)) - C(6)) × (-65))
54675 := (C((54/6)) × 75)
54725 := ((5 + C((4 × 7))) + C((2⁵)))
54743 := (-((C(5) + (4))) + C(((7 + 4) + C(3))))
54747 := (-C(5)) + C(((4 + C((7 - 4))) + (7)))
54781 := (C(5) + (C(4) × ((C(7) + C(8)) - 1)))
54784 := (((5 - 4) + C(7)) + C(8)) × C(4)
54832 := ((-5) + C(((C(4) / (-8)) + C(3)))) × C(2)
54852 := (-((5 × 4)) + C(((8 × 5) - 2)))
54867 := (-5) + C(((4 - 8) + (6 × 7)))
54872 := C((((5 × 4) - 8) + 7) × 2)
54875 := (C(5) × (4 + (87 × 5)))
54900 := ((C(5) - C(4)) × 900)
54925 := (C(((54 + 9) + 2)) / 5)
54945 := (((5 × C((4 + 9))) + (4)) × 5)
54966 := ((C(5) × ((C(4) + 9) × 6)) + C(6))
54997 := (C(5) + C(((4 × 9) + 9) - 7))
55245 := (((5 × C((5 + C(2)))) + C(4)) × 5)
55286 := (-((5 + 5)) - (-((2⁸)) × C(6)))
55323 := ((C(-((5 - 53))) / 2) + C(3))
55488 := ((C((5 + 5)) × (C(4) - 8)) - C(8))
55523 := (((C(5) - (55)) × C(C(2))) + C(C(3)))
55566 := (C((((5 + 5) + 5) + 6)) × 6)
55621 := (55 - (-6) × C(21))
55625 := (-5) × (((C(5) - C(6)) + 2) × C(5))
55744 := (((-5) - (C(5) × (-7))) × C(4)) + C(4)
55832 := (((5 - C(5)) - C((-8) + C(3))) × (-C(2)))
55836 := ((C(((5 × 5) + 8)) + C(C(3))) + C(6))
55872 := ((C(5) + C(((C(5) + 8) / 7))) × C(2))
55875 := (((55 × 8) + 7) × C(5))
55907 := ((C(5) × (5 × 90)) - C(7))
55933 := (-(((5⁵) - 9)) + (3 × C(C(3))))
55973 := ((C(-((5 × (5 - 9)))) × 7) - C(3))
56175 := (((C(5) × (-6)) + 1) × (-75))
56223 := ((-C(5) × (62 - C(C(2)))) - C(3))
56224 := (56 × (C((C(2) + 2)) + (4)))
56316 := ((C(5) + C((-6) + C(3))) × (1 × 6))
56376 := -((((C(5) - C((6 + 3))) + C(7)) × C(6)))
56462 := -((((C(5) - (6 × C(4))) × (C(6) + 2)))
56544 := (((-5) - C(6)) - C((-5) + C(4))) + C(C(4))
56625 := ((-((C(5) - 66)) + C(C(2))) × C(5))
56644 := (((C(5) - (6))⁶⁻⁴) × 4)
56673 := ((5 + (-6) × (-6) - C(7))) × C(3)
56683 := ((-C(5) × (C(6) - C(C(-((6 - 8)))))) + C(C(3)))
56722 := ((C(5) - ((-6) + C(7))²) / (-2))
56742 := ((C(5) × (6 - (-7) × C(4))) - C(2))
56745 := (-5) - ((-6) + (-7) × C(4)) × C(5))
56775 := (((C(5) × 6) + (7)) × 75)
56826 := (((C(5) - (6 + 8)) × C(C(2))) - (6))
56832 := (((C(5) + C(6)) - 8) / 3) × C(C(2))
56835 := (((C(5) - C(6)) + C(8)) × C(3)) × 5)
56844 := ((C(5) - ((C(6) + 8) × C(4))) × (-4))
56875 := (((56 × 8) + 7) × C(5))
57122 := (((-5) + C(7))^{1×2}) / 2)
57143 := ((-5) + C(71)) - C((C(4) + 3))
57168 := (((C((5 × 7)) + 1) / (-6)) × (-8))
57285 := (57 × (C((2 + 8)) + (5)))
57293 := ((-C(5) × (7 - C(C(2)))) - C((-9) + C(3)))
57295 := ((5 × 7) × (C(C(2)) - (-9) × C(5)))
57321 := (-C((5 + 7)) - (-3) × C(C((2 + 1))))
57331 := ((-5) × C(7)) + (3 × (C(C(3)) - 1))
57332 := ((-5) × C(7)) - ((-3) × C(C(3)) + 2))
57334 := (((-5) × C(7)) - C(C(3))) - (C(C(3)) × (-4))
57344 := ((-C((5 × 7) - 3)) + C(C(4))) / 4
57367 := ((C((5 + 7)) × (C(3) + (6))) + C(7))

$$\begin{aligned} 57375 &:= (((-5) - C(7))/(-3) + C(7)) \times C(5) \\ 57564 &:= ((C(5) + C(7)) \times (C(5) - (6 - 4))) \\ 57568 &:= (((C(5) + (7)) + C(5)) \times (C(6) + 8)) \\ 57625 &:= (C(5) \times ((7 \times 6) \times C(2)) + C(5)) \\ 57637 &:= (C(5) - (-7) \times (C(6) + C((C(3) - (7)))))) \\ 57687 &:= (((C(5) - (7 + 6)) \times C(8)) + C(7)) \\ 57833 &:= (-((C((5 + 7)) - C(8))) + (3 \times C(C(3)))) \\ 57844 &:= ((C(5) - ((-7) \times C(8)) \times 4) \times 4) \\ 57875 &:= (((57 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)) \\ 57876 &:= (C(5) - (((C(7) - C(8)) \times C(7)) + C(6))) \\ 57948 &:= ((C(5) + (7)) \times ((-9) - C(4)) + C(8)) \\ 58083 &:= ((-((5 - 80)) \times C(8)) + C(C(3))) \\ 58157 &:= (((C(5) + C((8 - 1))) \times C(5)) - C(7)) \\ 58195 &:= -(((C(5) + C((8 + 1))) - (9^5))) \\ 58239 &:= ((-5) \times C((8 - 2))) + C(39) \\ 58243 &:= (-C(5)) + ((C(8) - C(-((C(2) - C(4)))))/(-3)) \\ 58293 &:= (((5 \times 8) \times 2) \times C(9)) - C(3) \\ 58295 &:= (-5) \times ((-((8 \times 2)) \times C(9)) + (5)) \\ 58319 &:= (C(((5 + 8) \times 3)) - C((1 + 9))) \\ 58339 &:= (-5) + (((-8) - C(C(3))) \times (-3)) - (C(9))) \\ 58344 &:= ((5 - C((8 + 3))) \times (-44)) \\ 58368 &:= (((5 \times 8) \times 3) - 6) \times C(8) \\ 58375 &:= ((C(5) \times (C((8 - 3)) + C(7))) - C(5)) \\ 58383 &:= ((-5) - (C(8) \times 38)) \times (-3) \\ 58393 &:= (-5) + (((C(8) + C(C(3))) - (C(9))) \times 3) \\ 58398 &:= (-((5 - 8)) \times (C(C(3)) - (C(9) - C(8)))) \\ 58437 &:= ((C(5) - C(8)) \times ((C(4) \times 3) - C(7))) \\ 58466 &:= ((C(5) \times (C(8) - 46)) + C(6)) \\ 58500 &:= ((C(5) - 8) \times 500) \\ 58532 &:= (-5) - ((C(C((8 - 5))) \times (-3)) + C(C(2))) \\ 58564 &:= (((C(5) - 8) + C(5))^{6-4}) \\ 58596 &:= (((-5) + C(8)) \times (C(5) - 9)) - C(6) \\ 58625 &:= ((C((5 + 8)) - C((6 \times 2))) \times C(5)) \\ 58647 &:= ((C(5) + ((8 \times 6))) \times (-4) + C(7)) \\ 58733 &:= ((C(-((5 - 8))) - C(7)) + (3 \times C(C(3)))) \\ 58824 &:= -(((C(5) - C(8)) \times (C((8 - 2)) - C(4))) \\ 58833 &:= (-C((5 + (8/8)))) + (3 \times C(C(3))) \\ 58875 &:= (((58 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)) \\ 58916 &:= -(((C(5) + 8) - (9^{-1+6}))) \\ 58926 &:= ((-5) + (C((8 + 9)) \times 2)) \times 6 \\ 58932 &:= -((C(5) - ((8 + (9^{3+2})))))) \\ 59049 &:= (-((5 - 90) + 4)) \times C(9) \\ 59167 &:= (C(5) + ((9^{-1+6}) - (7))) \\ 59174 &:= (C(5) + (9^{17+4})) \\ 59176 &:= (((C(5) - 9) \times C((1 + 7))) - C(6)) \\ 59185 &:= (-((C(5) + 9)) + C(-((1 - (8 \times 5)))))) \\ 59224 &:= ((-((C(5) - 9)) \times (2 - C(C(2)))) + C(4)) \\ 59276 &:= ((C(5) - 9) \times (C(C(2)) - (7 - 6))) \\ 59285 &:= (((C(5) - 9) \times (-2) + C(8)) + C(5)) \\ 59292 &:= (((-5) - C(9)) + 2) \times (-9^2) \\ 59293 &:= ((-C(5)) \times (-9) - C(C(2))) - C((-9) + C(3)) \\ 59296 &:= (((C(5) - 9) \times C(C(2))) - (96)) \\ 59307 &:= ((-5) + C((9 + 30))) - (7) \\ 59314 &:= (-5) + C(((9 + C(3)) - ((1 - 4)))) \\ 59319 &:= C((((5 \times 9) + 3) \times 1) - 9) \\ 59324 &:= (5 + C(-((9 - (3 \times (2^4)))))) \\ 59332 &:= ((C(5) - C((93/3))) \times (-2)) \\ 59333 &:= (5 + ((-93) - C(C(3))) \times (-3)) \\ 59373 &:= ((5 + ((C(9) \times 3) + (7))) \times C(3)) \\ 59387 &:= (-((5 - (9 \times (3^8)))) + C(7)) \\ 59392 &:= ((C(5) - 9) \times C(-((3 - 9) - 2))) \\ 59433 &:= (((C(-((5 - 9))) + C(4)) + C(C(3))) \times 3) \\ 59435 &:= ((C(5) - 9) + C((4 + 35))) \\ 59437 &:= ((C(5) + C((9 \times 4) + 3)) - (7)) \\ 59439 &:= ((-5) + C((9 - 4))) + C(39) \\ 59444 &:= (C(5) + C(-((9 - 4) - 44))) \\ 59450 &:= (((C(5) \times 9) + C(4)) \times 50) \\ 59464 &:= ((-5) \times ((9 - C(4)) \times C(6))) + C(4) \\ 59517 &:= ((C(5) + (9^5)) + C((1 \times 7))) \\ 59539 &:= ((C(5) + (95)) + C(39)) \\ 59554 &:= ((5 + (9^5)) - (C(5) \times (-4))) \\ 59562 &:= (-((5 - ((9^5) + 6))) + C(C(2))) \\ 59564 &:= (((5 + C(9)) - (5^6)) \times (-4)) \\ 59582 &:= (C((-((5 - 9)) + C(-((5 - 8)))))) \times 2) \\ 59583 &:= ((-((5 - (9^5))) + C(8)) + C(3)) \\ 59616 &:= (((59 + C(6)) + 1) \times C(6)) \\ 59624 &:= (-((C(5) - 9)) \times ((-6) - C(C(2))) + (4))) \\ 59625 &:= ((C(5) \times (-9)) \times ((-6) \times C(2)) - (5)) \\ 59633 &:= -((C(-((5 - 9))) - ((C(6) + C(C(3))) \times 3))) \\ 59648 &:= (((-5) + C(9)) + C(6)) \times C(4) - C(8) \\ 59657 &:= ((-5) + C((9 + (6 \times 5)))) + C(7) \\ 59848 &:= (((C(5) - 9) \times (C(8) + (4))) - 8) \\ 59875 &:= (((59 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)) \\ 59895 &:= ((C(5) + C(9)) - ((8 - (9^5)))) \end{aligned}$$

- 59968 := (C(-(5-9))) × ((C(9) + C(6)) - 8))
60835 := (C(-(60-83))) × 5)
60875 := (((60 × 8) + 7) × C(5))
61233 := (((C(6) + C(C(1 × 2)))) + C(C(3))) × 3)
61236 := (-6) × ((C(12) - C(3)) × (-6))
61344 := (C(6) × ((1 + C(3)) + (4⁴)))
61397 := (((C(6) - 1) - C(3)) - 9) × C(7))
61533 := ((C(6) × (1 - (C(5) × (-3)))) - C(C(3)))
61625 := ((61 + (C(6) × 2)) × C(5))
61865 := -(C((6 + 1)) - (8 × (6⁵)))
61875 := (((61 × 8) + 7) × C(5))
61929 := (C(6) + ((C(19) - 2) × 9))
61952 := ((C(6) - ((1 × 95))) × C(C(2)))
62125 := (((-6) + C(C(2))) - (1 + C(2))) × C(5))
62208 := ((6²) × C((20 - 8)))
62238 := ((6 - C(C(2))) × (2 - C(-(3 - 8))))
62243 := ((C((6²)) - C((2⁴))) + C(C(3)))
62244 := ((C((C(6/2)) - 2)) - C(4)) × 4)
62272 := (-C((6 × 2))) + C((C(2) × (7 - 2)))
62304 := ((C(6) - (C(C(2)) × (-30))) × 4)
62336 := (((-6) + C((C(2) + C(3)))) + C(C(3))) - C(6))
62375 := (((-6) + C((2³))) - 7) × C(5))
62389 := (((C(6) + C(C(2))) - C(3)) × 89)
62391 := ((6 × C(C(2))) - (C(39) × (-1)))
62424 := (C(6) + (C((C(2) + C(4)))/(2 + 4)))
62426 := ((C(6) + 2) + (C((C(4) + C(2)))/6))
62435 := (-C(62)) + C(((C(4) × 3) - C(5)))
62452 := ((-6) × C(2)) + (4 × C((5²)))
62456 := ((C(6) - C((2 × 4))) × (5 - C(6)))
62458 := (-6) - (2 × ((C(4) - C(5)) × C(8)))
62464 := (C((6 + 2)) × ((C(4) - (6) + C(4)))
62494 := (-6) - (C(((2⁴) + 9)) × (-4))
62502 := (((6 - 2) + C(50))/2)
62521 := (((6 - C(C(2))) × (-C(5))) - C((C(2) + 1)))
62522 := (-C((6 × 2))) + (-C(5)) × (-2 - C(C(2)))
62524 := ((6 + C(25)) × (C(2) - (4)))
62529 := (((6 - C(C(2))) × (-C(5))) + (C(2) - C(9)))
62534 := (6 - ((C(C(2)) × (-C(5) - 3)) - C(4)))
62558 := (C(C((6/2))) + C(-(5 - (5 × 8))))
62564 := (C((6 - 2)) + ((5⁶) × 4))
62587 := ((C(62) - C(5)) - C((8 × 7)))
62634 := (-6) × (C((2 × 6)) - C((C(3) - (4))))
62694 := ((C(6) × ((-2) × C(6)) - C(9))/(-4))
62712 := (C(62) - C((7 × C((1 × 2))))
62726 := ((6 + C(C(2))) + (C(72)/6))
62736 := (-6) × ((C(C(2)) × (7 - C(3))) - C(6))
62767 := ((((-C(6)) + C(C(2))) - 7) × C(6)) + C(7))
62784 := (-6) × (C(C(2)) - (C(7) × (8 × 4)))
62856 := (C(6) × (285 + 6))
62875 := (((62 × 8) + 7) × C(5))
62964 := (((C(6) × (-2)) + C(9)) × (C(6) - (4)))
62985 := (((6 × 2) + C(9)) × 85)
63125 := ((C(C((6/3))) - (-1 + C(2))) × C(5))
63159 := ((6 × C((C(3) - (1 × 5)))) - (C(9)))
63238 := ((6 × (C(C(3)) + 2)) - C(38))
63243 := (((-6) × (3 - C(24))) - C(C(3)))
63261 := ((C(6) - 3) × (C(C(2)) - (C(6) - 1)))
63284 := -(C(6) - (C((3 + 2)) × (C(8) - (4))))
63288 := (C(6) × ((-3) - C(-(2 - 8))) + C(8))
63293 := (((6 + C((C(3) + C(2)))) + (C(9))) + C(C(3)))
63325 := (((C(6) × (-3)) - C(3)) + C((C(2) × 5)))
63352 := ((C(6) × (-3)) + C(((C(3) + 5) + C(2))))
63358 := (((-6) × (3 - C((C(3) - 5)))) - C(8))
63364 := ((C(-(6/3)) + C(3)) + C(6)) × 4)
63423 := (C((6 + 3)) × (C(4) + (23)))
63424 := ((C((6 + 34)) - C(C(2))) - C(4))
63425 := (((6 + C((C(3) - 4))) + C(C(2))) × 5)
63484 := ((C((6 + 34)) - C(8)) - (4))
63488 := (((6 + C(3)) × 4) - 8) × C(8))
63504 := (6 × (C((C(3) - 5)) + (0 - C(4))))
63538 := (((-6) × (-C(3)) - C((-5) + C(3)))) - C(8))
63564 := (6 × (C((C(3) - 5)) - (C(6)/4)))
63625 := (((-6) - 3) + C((6 + 2))) × C(5))
63657 := (C(((6/3) + 6) × 5)) - C(7))
63744 := ((C(((6 - 3) + 7)) - (4)) × C(4))
63782 := (-C(6)) - ((C((C(3) - 7))) × (-8) + 2))
63784 := -(C(6) - C(((3 + 7) × (8 - 4))))
63822 := (-6) × ((3 + 8) - C(22))
63824 := ((6 × C(((3 × 8) - 2))) - C(4))
63838 := (((-6) × C(3)) + C(((8 - 3) × 8)))
63841 := (C(6) + ((-3) + C(8)) × C((4 + 1)))
63855 := ((6 + C(3)) × ((C(8) - C(5)) × 5))
63856 := (((C(6)/3) + C((8 × 5))) - C(6))
63875 := (((63 × 8) + 7) × C(5))
63881 := (6 - (C(-(3 - 8)) × (-C(8) - 1)))

- 63884 := (((-6) × C((3+8))) × (-8)) - (4))
63888 := (6 × C(((38-8)-8)))
63928 := ((-C(6)) × (C(-(3-9))) - C(C(2)))) - 8)
63936 := ((C(C((6/3))) - C((9-3)))) × C(6))
63958 := (((-6) - C(3)) - 9) + C((5 × 8))
63973 := (C((6 + ((3 × 9) + 7))) - C(3))
63990 := ((-((6 × 3)) + C(9)) × 90)
63994 := (-6) + C((((3 × 9) + 9) + 4))
64002 := ((-6) + C(40)) + C(02))
64003 := ((6 + C(40)) - 03)
64006 := (6 + C((40 + (0 × 6))))
64021 := ((-6) + C(40)) + C((2 + 1))
64022 := (((6 + C(40)) + C(2)) + C(2))
64023 := (((-6) + C(40)) + 2) + C(3))
64033 := ((6 + C(40)) + ((3³)))
64043 := (((6 + C(40)) + C(4)) - C(3))
64049 := (((-6) + C(40)) + C(4)) - 9)
64058 := ((-6) + C(4)) + C((05 × 8))
64064 := (C(((6 + 40) - 6)) + C(4))
64125 := -(((C(6) - C(((4-1)²))) × C(5)))
64127 := ((-C(6)) + C(((4+1) × C(2)))) + C(7))
64152 := (C(6) - (C(4) × (1 - C((5 × 2))))))
64211 := (6 + ((4^{C(2)}) - C(11)))
64216 := (C(6) + C(-(((4 × 2) × (1 - 6))))))
64220 := ((C(6) + (4)) + C((2 × 20)))
64233 := (((C(6) × (-4 × 2)) - C(C(3))) × (-3))
64242 := (-(((6⁴) - 2)) + (4^{C(2)}))
64243 := ((C(6) + C((C(4) - (24)))) + C(3))
64248 := ((-((6⁴)) + C(2)) + (4⁸))
64272 := (-6) × (-C(4)) - C((C(2) + (7 × 2))))
64289 := (-6) + (((4^{C(2)}) - C(8)) - C(9))
64294 := (C(6) - ((C(C(4)) - C((2 × 9)))/(-4)))
64337 := ((-6) + C((43 - 3))) + C(7))
64357 := (C(6) - (((C(4) × (-3)) + (5)) × C(7)))
64384 := ((6 × C(4)) + C(-(3 × 8) + C(4)))
64385 := ((6 + 4) - ((-3) - C(8)) × C(5))
64405 := (((C(6) + C(4)) + C(40)) + C(5))
64407 := ((64 + C(40)) + C(7))
64441 := (((-6) - C(4)) × C(4)) + C(41))
64448 := ((C(((6 + 4) × 4)) - C(4)) + C(8))
64456 := ((C(64)/4) + (-5) × C(6))
64457 := ((C(6) × ((4 - C(4)) × (-5))) - C(7))
64482 := (((-C(6)) + C(C(4)))/4) - (C((8 + 2))))
64511 := ((C(C((6 - 4))) × (C(5) + 1)) - 1)
64512 := (64 × ((C(5) + 1) × C(2)))
64518 := (6 - (C(4) × ((C(5) + 1) × (-8))))
64522 := (6 + (4 × ((C(5) + 2)²)))
64524 := ((6 × 4) + (C(5) × (C(C(2)) + (4))))
64547 := -(((C(6) + C(4)) - ((C(5) + C(4)) × C(7))))
64582 := (((6 + C(4)) + C((5 × 8))) + C(C(2)))
64657 := ((C((6 + 4)) × 65) - C(7))
64729 := (C((C((6 - 4)) × (7 - 2))) + (C(9)))
64763 := (-64) + (C(7) × (C(6) - C(3)))
64768 := (((6 - 4)⁷) × (-6) + C(8))
64773 := ((C(6)/(-4)) - (-7) × C((7 × 3)))
64808 := -(((C(6) - (4⁸)) + C(08)))
64827 := (((C((6 + 4)) + C(8))/C(2)) × C(7))
64842 := (((C(6) - C(C(4))) + C(8))/(-4)) - C(C(2)))
64857 := (((C(6) × 4) + C((8 × 5))) - (7))
64864 := ((C(6) × ((4 + C(8)) - C(6))) + C(4))
64872 := (-C(6)) - (C(4) × (-((C(8) - (7)))) - C(C(2))))
64875 := (((64 × 8) + 7) × C(5))
64923 := ((C((-6) + C(4)) - C((9 - 2)))/3)
64977 := -((C(6) - ((4^{C(9-7)}) - C(7))))
65016 := (((6 × 50) + 1) × C(6))
65119 := (-6) - (-C(5)) × (C(C((1 + 1))) + 9))
65178 := -((C(6) + ((C(5) + 1) × (-7) - C(8))))
65187 := (-((6 - ((5 - 1)⁸))) - C(7))
65232 := ((C((6 × 5)) - C((2 × C(3))))/(-2))
65268 := (6 - ((-C(5)) × (C(C(2)) + (6))) - C(8))
65284 := -((C(6) - (C(5) × ((C(2) + C(8)) + (4))))))
65342 := -(((C(6) + (5)) - C(3)) - (4^{C(2)})))
65344 := (((6 × (C(5) + 3)) - C(C(4)))/(-4))
65358 := ((C((6 + 5)) + C(3)) + C((5 × 8)))
65384 := -((C(6) - (((C(5) + 3) × C(8)) + C(4))))
65394 := (-C(6)) + (5 × (C(C(3)) - (9⁴)))
65417 := ((6 - C(5)) + (4¹⁺⁷))
65433 := (((6 × C(5)) × (C(4) - 3)) + C(C(3)))
65442 := ((-((6 × 5)) - C(4)) + (4^{C(2)}))
65444 := -((C(6) - C(5)) + ((4 - C(C(4)))/(-4)))
65445 := -(((C(6) - C(5)) - (C(4) × (4⁵))))
65469 := (-6) - (-5) × (C((4 × 6)) - C(9))
65500 := ((6 + C(5)) × 500)

- 65528 := $(-6 + 5 + 5)^{C(2)} - 8$
65532 := $(6 + ((5 - C((5 + C(3)))) \times (-2)))$
65542 := $(6 + (((5 - 5) + 4)^{C(2)}))$
65583 := $(((-6) - C(5)) + (5 \times C(8))) \times C(3)$
65694 := $-((C(6) - ((5 \times 6) \times C((9 + 4))))$
65728 := $((C(6) + C(((5 + 7) + C(2)))) \times 8)$
65744 := $((C(6) - C(-((5 - 7)))) + (C(C(4))/4))$
65745 := $((C(6) + C(-((5 - 74))))/5)$
65748 := $(((-6) - C(5)) + C(7)) + (4^8)$
65752 := $(C(6) + (C(-((5 - 7)^5)) \times 2))$
65772 := $((C(6) \times ((-5) - C(7)) \times (-7))/C(2))$
65832 := $(-C(6) + (((C(5) - C(8))/(-3)) \times C(C(2))))$
65869 := $(-6) + (C(5) \times (C(8) + ((6 + 9))))$
65875 := $((65 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)$
65918 := $((C(6) - C(5)) \times (C(9) + 1)) - C(8)$
65928 := $(-6) \times ((C(5) \times (-92)) + C(8))$
65946 := $(-6) \times ((-5) \times C((9 + 4))) - (6))$
65952 := $((C(6) - C(5)) \times C(9)) + C(5) - C(C(2))$
66043 := $((C(6) - C(60)) + C(C(4))) + C(C(3))$
66096 := $(C(6) \times ((60 - 9) \times 6))$
66123 := $((C(6) \times (C(6) - (1^2))) + C(C(3)))$
66240 := $((C((6 + 6)) + C(C(2))) + C(40))$
66312 := $((6^6) - C(3)) + C(C((1 + 2)))$
66313 := $((6^6) + C(C(3))) - (-1) + C(3))$
66331 := $((6^6) + C(C(3))) - C((3 - 1))$
66333 := $((6^6) + C(C(3))) - (3 + 3)$
66336 := $((6^6) + C(C(3))) + ((3 - 6))$
66343 := $((6 \times 6)^3 + 4) + C(C(3))$
66352 := $((6^6) + C(C(3))) + (5 + C(2))$
66373 := $((6^6) + C(C(3))) + (7 + C(3))$
66394 := $((6^6) + C(C(3))) - (9 - C(4))$
66403 := $((6^6) + C(4)) + C(C(03))$
66448 := $((6 \times (C(6) - C(4))) + (4^8))$
66528 := $(C(6) \times ((6 + 5) \times 28))$
66542 := $(-6) + ((6 + C(5)) \times (-4) + C(C(2))))$
66744 := $(C(6) + (C(6) \times (7 \times 44)))$
66856 := $(-C(6) + (C(C(-((6 - 8)))) \times (C(5) + (6))))$
66875 := $((66 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)$
67048 := $((C(6) \times 7) + (04^8))$
67193 := $(C(((6 \times 7) - 1)) - C((9 + 3)))$
67229 := $(C((6 \times 7)) - C((C(2) + (2 + 9))))$
67240 := $((C(6) \times (7 + C(2))) + C(40))$
67266 := $((-((C(6) - (7))) + C(C(2))) \times (C(6) + (6)))$
67375 := $((C(6) + C(7)) - C(3)) + (7) \times C(5)$
67392 := $(C(6) \times ((C(7) - 39) + C(2)))$
67532 := $((C((6 \times 7)) + (5)) - (3^{C(2)}))$
67544 := $((C(6) \times (-7) + (5 \times C(4))) - C(4))$
67547 := $(-(((6 - (7^5)) \times 4) + C(7))$
67582 := $(6 + (((7 + C(5)) \times C(8)) - C(2)))$
67584 := $((C(6) - C(7)) - (5)) \times (-8) \times C(4)$
67585 := $(6 + (((7 + C(5)) \times C(8)) - (5)))$
67594 := $((6 \times C(7)) + (C(C(-((5 - 9))))/4))$
67645 := $(6 - ((C(7) + C(6)) \times (4 - C(5))))$
67683 := $((6 \times C((-7) + (C(6)/8))) + C(C(3)))$
67875 := $((67 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)$
67914 := $((6 + C(7)) + C(9)) \times (-1) + C(4))$
67928 := $(C(6) + (((7 + C(9))^2)/8))$
67995 := $((C(6) \times (-7 \times 9)) + 9) \times (-5)$
68125 := $((6 + C(8)) + C((1 + 2))) \times C(5)$
68256 := $((C(6)/(-8)) + C((2 + 5))) \times C(6)$
68257 := $((C(6) + ((8 - 25))) \times C(7))$
68315 := $((6 - C(8)) \times C(3)) - 1) \times (-5)$
68323 := $((68 + C(3)) \times C(C(2))) + C(C(3))$
68345 := $((C(68) - C((3 + C(4)))) \times 5)$
68375 := $((68 \times 3) + C(7)) \times C(5)$
68392 := $(-C(6) - (-((C((8 - 3)) + 9)) \times C(C(2))))$
68448 := $((C(6) + C(8)) \times 4) + (4^8)$
68596 := $(-6) + ((C(8) \times (C(5) + 9)) - (6))$
68599 := $((C(C(-((6 - 8)))) \times (C(5) + 9)) - 9)$
68625 := $((C(6) - C(8)) + C(((6^2) + 5)))$
68634 := $(-6) \times ((C(8) + C(6)) - C((C(3) - (4))))$
68644 := $((6 + C(8)) \times 6) + (C(C(4))/4)$
68698 := $((6 + 8) \times (-6) + C((9 + 8)))$
68768 := $((C(6)/(-8)) + C(7)) \times C(6) + C(8)$
68782 := $((6 + 8) \times C((7 + 8) + 2))$
68875 := $((68 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)$
68894 := $((6 + C(8)) \times (8 + C((9 - 4))))$
68921 := $C((((6 \times 8) - 9) + 2) \times 1)$
68927 := $(6 + C(((8 + 9) \times 2) + 7))$
68935 := $((6 + 8) + C(((9 + C(3)) + (5))))$
68948 := $((C(6)/8) + C((9 + (4 \times 8))))$
68957 := $(6 + ((C(8) \times (9 + C(5))) + C(7)))$
68959 := $((C(6) - C(8)) + (95 \times C(9)))$

$$\begin{aligned} 68968 &:= ((C(6) - C(8)) \times ((-9) - C(6)) - 8)) \\ 69115 &:= ((C((C(6)/9)) - 1) \times (1 \times 5)) \\ 69125 &:= ((C((C(6)/9)) + (1^2)) \times 5) \\ 69135 &:= (((C((C(6)/9)) \times (-1)) - 3) \times (-5)) \\ 69145 &:= ((C((C(6)/9)) + (1 + 4)) \times 5) \\ 69216 &:= (-6) \times ((C(9) - C(2)) \times (-16)) \\ 69235 &:= ((C((C(6)/9)) + 23) \times 5) \\ 69255 &:= ((C(6) - C(9)) \times (-((2 \times 5) - C(5))) \\ 69279 &:= ((C(6) - (-C(9)) \times (C(C(2)) + C(7))))/9) \\ 69345 &:= ((C(6) - 9) \times ((-3) - C(4)) \times (-5)) \\ 69375 &:= (((6 + 9) \times 37) \times C(5)) \\ 69418 &:= ((-((6 + 9)) + C(41)) + C(8)) \\ 69434 &:= (-((C(6) - C(9))) + C(((C(4) - C(3)) + (4)))) \\ 69465 &:= ((-69) - C((4 \times 6))) \times (-5) \\ 69475 &:= ((C((C(6)/9)) + (C(4) + (7))) \times 5) \\ 69552 &:= (C(6) \times ((C((9 - 5)) \times 5) + 2)) \\ 69598 &:= -((C(6) + ((9 + C(5)) \times (-9) - C(8)))) \\ 69660 &:= (((C(6) + C(9)) + C(6)) \times 60) \\ 69776 &:= -(((C(6) + C((9 + 7))) - C((7 \times 6)))) \\ 69792 &:= ((6 \times (9 + 7)) \times (C(9) - 2)) \\ 69848 &:= (C(6) + (((9 \times 8) + C(4)) \times C(8))) \\ 69875 &:= ((C((6 + 9)) \times 8) + C((7 \times 5))) \\ 69912 &:= ((-6) + C((9 + 9))) \times 12) \\ 69944 &:= ((C(C(-((6 - 9)))) - C((9 + 4))) \times 4) \\ 69963 &:= (6 - ((C(9) \times (-96)) + C(3))) \\ 69969 &:= (-6) - ((C(9) \times (-96)) + 9) \\ 69972 &:= (-6) \times ((C(9) \times (-9 + 7)) + 2) \\ 69977 &:= (((6 \times C(9)) \times (9 + 7)) - (7)) \\ 69982 &:= ((-6) \times ((C(9) + C(9)) \times (-8))) - 2) \\ 69984 &:= (C(6) \times ((9 \times 9) \times (8 - 4))) \\ 69993 &:= (((69 \times C(9)) + 9) + C(C(3))) \\ 70343 &:= ((7 + C(C(03))) + C((C(4) - C(3)))) \\ 70835 &:= ((C(7) + C((08 \times 3))) \times 5) \\ 70875 &:= (((70 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)) \\ 71136 &:= (-((C(7) - 1)) \times (C(-((1 - 3))) - C(6))) \\ 71168 &:= ((-((7 \times 11)) + C(6)) \times C(8)) \\ 71284 &:= (71 \times (C((2 + 8)) + (4))) \\ 71328 &:= (((C(7) \times (-1) + C(3))) - 2) \times 8) \\ 71344 &:= (C(7) \times ((13 \times 4) \times 4)) \\ 71362 &:= (-C((7 + 1))) + (C((C(3) + (6))) \times 2) \\ 71496 &:= ((C(7) + (((1 - 4) - 9))) \times C(6)) \\ 71498 &:= (-7) \times ((-14) \times C(9)) - 8) \\ 71595 &:= ((-C(71)) - C(-((5 - 9))))/(-5) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 71625 &:= (((C(71) + C(6)) - 2)/5) \\ 71687 &:= (C(7) - (((-1) \times C(6)) + 8) \times C(7)) \\ 71820 &:= (-7) \times ((1 + C(8)) \times (-20)) \\ 71874 &:= (C((-7) + ((1 - C(8))/(-7))))/4) \\ 71875 &:= (((71 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)) \\ 71928 &:= ((C(7) - (1 + 9)) \times C(-(2 - 8))) \\ 72063 &:= ((-7) - C(20)) \times (-6 + 3) \\ 72135 &:= (-7) \times (C((C(2) - 1)) - C((C(3) - (5)))) \\ 72233 &:= (C(7) + (2 \times (C(2) + C(33)))) \\ 72235 &:= (((C(7) - C(2)) \times C((2 \times 3))) - C(5)) \\ 72261 &:= (((C(7) - C(2)) - 2) \times (C(6) + 1)) \\ 72296 &:= (C(((7^2) - C(2))) + C((9 + 6))) \\ 72333 &:= (((C(7) - C(2)) \times C((3 + 3))) - C(3)) \\ 72373 &:= -((C(7) \times (C(2) - ((3 \times 73)))) \\ 72424 &:= (((C(7) - C(2)) \times C((4 + 2))) + C(4)) \\ 72441 &:= ((7 \times C(C(2))) - ((C(4) - C(41)))) \\ 72485 &:= (C(72) - C((C(4) + (8 - 5)))) \\ 72568 &:= (((-7) + C((2 + 5))) \times C(6)) - 8) \\ 72576 &:= (((7^{-2+5}) - (7)) \times C(6)) \\ 72625 &:= (((7 + C(C(2))) + 62) \times C(5)) \\ 72633 &:= ((C(7) - 2) \times ((6^3) - 3)) \\ 72657 &:= -(((C(7) + C(2)) + (C(6) \times (5 - C(7)))) \\ 72666 &:= (((C(7) + 2) \times (C(6) - (6))) + C(6)) \\ 72667 &:= -((C((7 - 2)) - (C(6) \times (-6) + C(7)))) \\ 72675 &:= (C(7) - ((2 - C(6)) \times (C(7) - (5)))) \\ 72687 &:= -((C(7) + ((-2) - C(6)) \times (-8) + C(7)))) \\ 72716 &:= (C(7) \times ((2 + C((7 - 1))) - (6))) \\ 72759 &:= -(((C(7) \times ((C(2) - C(7)) + C(5))) - C(9))) \\ 72875 &:= (((72 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)) \\ 72966 &:= ((C(((7 \times 2) + 9)) - (6)) \times 6) \\ 73125 &:= ((73 + C(C((1 \times 2)))) \times C(5)) \\ 73144 &:= ((-7) \times C((C(3) - ((1 - 4)))) + C(C(4))) \\ 73164 &:= (((C(7) - 3) \times (-1) + C(6)) + C(4)) \\ 73174 &:= (7 - (-3) \times C((1 + (7 \times 4)))) \\ 73261 &:= (C((7 \times 3)) + C((C(2) \times (6 - 1)))) \\ 73359 &:= (C((7 \times ((3/3) + 5))) - C(9)) \\ 73376 &:= -((C((7 - 3)) + ((3 - C(7)) \times C(6))) \\ 73576 &:= -((C(C((7 + 3)/5))) - (C((7 \times 6)))) \\ 73608 &:= ((C((7 \times 3)) - (60)) \times 8) \\ 73612 &:= (((C(7) - 3) \times (C(6) - 1)) + C(C(2))) \\ 73622 &:= ((-7) - C(C(3))) + (C((6^2)) \times 2) \\ 73629 &:= (-((7 - (3 \times (6^2)))) \times C(9)) \end{aligned}$$

- 73634 := (((C(7) + 3) × (C(6) - 3)) - C(4))
73656 := ((C(7) - ((3 - 6) + 5)) × C(6))
73683 := ((-((7³)) - (-6) × C(8))) × C(3))
73736 := -((C((7 + 3)) - ((C(7) + 3) × C(6))))
73742 := -(((C(7) + 3) - C((7 × (4 + 2))))))
73745 := (C(7) × ((-((3 × 7)) + C(4)) × 5))
73766 := -((((C(7) - C(3)) - C((7 × 6))) + (6)))
73772 := (-((C(7) - C(3))) + C(-((7 - (7²))))))
73783 := (C(7) - (((3 - C(7)) × 8) × C(3)))
73866 := (((C((7 × 3)) × 8) - C(6)) - (6))
73875 := (((73 × 8) + 7) × C(5))
73928 := (((C((-7) + C(3))) + (C(9))) + C(C(2))) × 8)
73953 := (C(-((7 × (3 - 9)))) - (5 × C(3)))
73968 := ((C((7 × 3)) - ((9 + 6))) × 8)
73985 := (((-((7 × 3)) × C(9)) + C(8)) × (-5))
73994 := (C(-((7 × (3 - 9)))) - (94))
74024 := (C((7 × (4 + 02))) - C(4))
74088 := C((7 × ((40 + 8)/8)))
74125 := ((C(7) + (C((4 + 1)) × 2)) × C(5))
74142 := (C((7 - 4)) × (C(14) + 2))
74169 := (((C(7) - (4 - 1)) × C(6)) + C(9))
74215 := ((C(7) + C(42)) - C((1 + 5)))
74216 := (((C(7) + C(42)) + 1) - C(6))
74245 := -((((C(7) - C(42)) + (-4) × C(5))))
74252 := (-((((C(7) - C(42)) + (5))) + C(C(2))))
74257 := (-((C(7) - C(42))) + C(C(-((5 - 7))))))
74262 := ((C(7) × ((4 - 2) + C(6))) - C(C(2)))
74277 := (C((7 - 4)) × (C((2 × 7)) + (7)))
74298 := (((-7) + C(42)) + C(9)) - C(8)
74367 := ((C(7) - (4³)) + C((6 × 7)))
74375 := (((C(7) - C(4)) - C(3)) + C(7)) × C(5))
74397 := ((-7) + C(43)) + (C(9) × (-7))
74427 := ((C(7) - (4)) + C(((4 + 2) × 7)))
74431 := (C(7) + C(((44 - 3) + 1)))
74435 := ((C(7) + (4)) + C(((C(4) - C(3)) + (5))))
74487 := (-7) × ((C(44)/(-8)) + (7))
74522 := (7 × (C(((4 × 5) + 2)) - 2))
74528 := ((7 × C(((4 × 5) + 2))) - 8)
74536 := (7 × C(((4⁵⁻³) + 6)))
74563 := ((C((7 + 4)) × 56) + C(3))
74643 := ((7 - (4⁶)) - (-4) × C(C(3)))
74644 := (((C(7) - (4)) × (C(6) + (4))) + C(4))
74697 := -((C(7) - ((C(4) + (6)) × (C(9) + C(7))))))
74736 := (((7⁴)/7) + 3) × C(6))
74752 := (((7 + C(4)) + 75) × C(C(2)))
74763 := (((C(7) - ((4 - 7))) × C(6)) + C(3))
74875 := (((74 × 8) + 7) × C(5))
74888 := (((C(7) - (4)) + C(8)) × 88)
74948 := ((C(7) × ((C(4) - 9) × 4)) - C(8))
74952 := ((C(7) + (4)) × C(((9 - 5) + 2)))
75117 := (((C(7) - C(5)) + 1) × C((1 × 7)))
75159 := (((C(7) + (5)) × C((1 + 5))) - 9)
75164 := (((C(7) + (5)) × C((1 × 6))) - (4))
75175 := (7 + (C((5 + 1)) × (C(7) + (5))))
75223 := (-C((7 × 5)) - ((2 - C(2)) × C(C(3))))
75274 := (((C(7) - C(5)) × (2 + C(7))) + C(4))
75375 := (75 × (C((3 + 7)) + (5)))
75395 := (((7⁵) - C((3 + 9))) × 5)
75456 := ((C(C((7 - 5))) + C(4)) × (C(5) + (6)))
75558 := (-7) + (5 × (C((5 × 5)) - C(8)))
75565 := ((C(C((7 - 5))) - (5⁶)) × (-5))
75625 := ((C(7) - ((C(5) + (6)) × (-2))) × C(5))
75643 := (C((7 × 5)) + C(((C(6) × 4)/C(3))))
75676 := ((C(7) × (5 + C(6))) - (C(7) - C(6)))
75712 := ((C(7) - (5)) × (C((7 - 1)) + C(2)))
75722 := (((C(7) - C(5)) × (C(7) + 2)) + C(C(2)))
75735 := (((C(7) - C(5)) + C(7)) × C(3)) × 5)
75789 := (-7) × (((-5) × C(7)) + C(8)) × 9)
75803 := (C(7) × (5 - (-8) × C(03)))
75816 := (C((7 + 5)) + C(((8 - 1) × 6)))
75867 := (((7 × C(5)) - C(8)) × (C(6) - (7)))
75875 := (((75 × 8) + 7) × C(5))
75934 := ((-7) + C(5)) + ((-C(9)) + C(C(3))) × 4)
76146 := (C(7) × (C(6) + ((1⁴) × 6)))
76173 := (((7 + C(6)) - 1) × C(7)) + C(3))
76285 := (C((7 + 6)) + C((2 + (8 × 5))))
76489 := (C(7) × (6 - ((C(4) × 8) - C(9))))
76492 := ((C((7 × 6)) - (-4) × C(9)) - C(C(2)))
76532 := ((C(7) × (C(6) + (5))) + C((3²)))
76584 := (C((7 × 6)) + ((5 × C(8)) - C(4)))
76711 := (((7 + C(6)) × (C(7) + 1)) - 1)
76712 := ((7 + C(6)) × (C(7) + (1²)))
76715 := ((-7) + (C(6) × (-71))) × (-5)
76816 := ((C(7) × (C(6) + 8)) - (16))

$$\begin{aligned} 76822 &:= ((C(7) \times (C(6) + 8)) + (-2) - C(2)) \\ 76824 &:= (((7 \times C((6 + 8))) - 2) \times 4) \\ 76825 &:= (-7) + ((C(6) + 8) \times C((2 + 5))) \\ 76827 &:= ((C(7) \times (C(6) + 8)) + ((2 - 7))) \\ 76832 &:= (C((7 \times 6)) + C((8 + (3 \times 2)))) \\ 76833 &:= ((C(7) \times (C(6) + 8)) + (3/3)) \\ 76848 &:= (((-C(7)) + C((C(6)/8))) \times 4) - C(8) \\ 76874 &:= (-7) \times (-6) + (((-8) \times C(7)) \times 4) \\ 76875 &:= (((76 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)) \\ 76925 &:= ((C(7) \times (C(6) + 9)) + (-2) \times C(5)) \\ 76957 &:= ((C(7) \times (C(6) + 9)) + (C(5) - C(7))) \\ 77168 &:= (-7) + (C(7) \times ((1 + C(6)) + 8)) \\ 77175 &:= (C(7) \times ((C(7) + (1 \times 7)) - C(5))) \\ 77264 &:= (((C(7) + (7)) + C(2)) \times C(6)) - C(4) \\ 77324 &:= (((C(7) + (7)) - C(C(3))) + 2) \times (-4) \\ 77362 &:= (((-C((7 + 7))) - C((C(3) + (6)))) \times (-2)) \\ 77364 &:= (((7 - C(7)) + C(C(3))) - (6)) \times 4) \\ 77374 &:= ((7 + 7) - ((C(C(3)) - C(7)) \times (-4))) \\ 77437 &:= (77 - (-4) \times (C(C(3)) - C(7))) \\ 77463 &:= -((C((7 \times 7)) - ((C(4) - (6))^3)) \\ 77518 &:= (C(7) \times ((C(7) - C(5)) + (1 \times 8))) \\ 77566 &:= (((-7) - C(7)) \times (-5) - C(6)) + C(6) \\ 77648 &:= (((C(7) + (7)) \times C(6)) - (-4) \times C(8)) \\ 77653 &:= (C((((7 + 7) + C(6))/5)) - C(C(3))) \\ 77672 &:= (-7) \times (((-7) \times C(6)) \times 7) - C(C(2))) \\ 77673 &:= (C(7) + ((-7) + C(6)) \times (C(7) + C(3))) \\ 77679 &:= (((-7) + C(7)) \times C(6)) - (-7) \times C(9)) \\ 77875 &:= (((77 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)) \\ 77952 &:= (((-7) + C(7)) \times ((9 - C(5)) \times (-2))) \\ 78125 &:= (C((7 + ((8 + 1) \times 2))) \times 5) \\ 78262 &:= ((C(7) + ((8 \times 2))) \times (C(6) + 2)) \\ 78273 &:= (-((C(7) - 8)) + (2 \times C((7 + C(3)))) \\ 78436 &:= -((((C(7) + C(8)) - C(43)) + C(6))) \\ 78445 &:= ((C(-((7 - (8 \times 4)))) + C(4)) \times 5) \\ 78525 &:= (((7 \times 8) \times 5)^2) + C(5) \\ 78543 &:= (((-7) \times C((8 - 5))) - (-4) \times C(C(3))) \\ 78622 &:= (((C(7) + 8) \times (C(6) + C(2))) - 2) \\ 78624 &:= ((C(7) + 8) \times (C(6) + (2 \times 4))) \\ 78634 &:= (-((7 \times (8 + 6))) - (C(C(3)) \times (-4))) \\ 78652 &:= (-((C(7) - C(((8 \times 6) - 5)))) - C(C(2))) \\ 78679 &:= (C(7) + (C(8) \times (C(6) - ((7 \times 9)))) \\ 78732 &:= (C(((((-7) + C(8)) - C(7))/3))/2) \\ 78733 &:= (-((7 - 8)) - (-((7 - 3) \times C(C(3)))) \\ 78836 &:= ((C(78) - (C(8) \times 3))/6) \\ 78848 &:= (((7 \times 88)/4) \times C(8)) \\ 78875 &:= (((78 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)) \\ 78993 &:= ((C(((C(7) + 8)/9)) - 9) + C(C(3))) \\ 79216 &:= ((C(7) + (9 \times C(C(2)))) \times 16) \\ 79233 &:= (C(7) \times ((9 - 2) \times 33)) \\ 79244 &:= ((C(7) + (C(9) \times 2)) \times 44) \\ 79247 &:= (-7) \times ((C(9) \times (-2^4)) + C(7)) \\ 79375 &:= (C(((7 + 9) + C(3))) - (7 + C(5))) \\ 79437 &:= (((-7) \times 9) + C(43)) - (7) \\ 79443 &:= (-((7 + 9) \times 4) + C(43)) \\ 79454 &:= (-7) - (C(9) \times (-45) - C(4)) \\ 79468 &:= ((7 + C(9)) + (4 \times C((C(6)/8))) \\ 79473 &:= (((-7) + C((9 \times 4) + 7)) - C(3)) \\ 79483 &:= (C((7 + (9 \times 4))) - ((8 \times 3))) \\ 79494 &:= (C((7 + (9 \times 4))) - (9 + 4)) \\ 79507 &:= C(-(((C(7) - C(9)) + C(((5 \times 0) + 7)))) \\ 79522 &:= ((7 + C(((9 \times 5) - 2))) + C(2)) \\ 79523 &:= ((7 + 9) + C(((5 \times C(2)) + 3))) \\ 79524 &:= (((7 + 9) + C(5))^2) \times 4) \\ 79576 &:= (C(7) \times ((C((9 - 5)) \times 7) - C(6))) \\ 79586 &:= (79 + C(-((5 - (8 \times 6)))) \\ 79643 &:= (((C(7) + 9) - C(6)) + C(43)) \\ 79723 &:= (C(-(((C(7) - C(9)) + C(7)))) + (C((2 \times 3)))) \\ 79725 &:= ((C(7) + C((C(9) - (C(7) \times 2)))) - (C(5))) \\ 79859 &:= ((C(7) + 9) + C(((C(8) - C(5))/9))) \\ 79875 &:= (((79 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)) \\ 80875 &:= (((80 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)) \\ 81243 &:= ((8 + C(12)) + C(43)) \\ 81648 &:= (81 \times (C((6 + 4)) + 8)) \\ 81875 &:= (((81 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)) \\ 81920 &:= (C(8) \times (-((1 - 9) \times 20))) \\ 82125 &:= ((C((8 + 2)) - C((-1) + C(2))) \times C(5)) \\ 82432 &:= -((C(8) - (C(24) \times (3 \times 2)))) \\ 82472 &:= ((C(8) - (24)) \times (-C(7)) + C(C(2))) \\ 82568 &:= (-C(8)) - (((C(C(2)) - (C(5))) \times (-C(6))) + C(8)) \\ 82593 &:= (C((8 + 25)) + C((9 + C(3)))) \\ 82649 &:= ((C(8) \times ((C(2) + C(6)) - C(4))) + C(9)) \\ 82693 &:= (-8) - (((C(C(2)) \times (-6)) + 9) \times C(3)) \\ 82755 &:= (((C(8)/(-2)) + (7^5)) \times 5) \\ 82837 &:= (-C(8)) + ((C(-((2 - 8))) + C(3)) \times C(7)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 82875 &:= (((82 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)) \\ 82896 &:= ((-8) + C((C(-((2 - 8)))/9))) \times 6) \\ 82936 &:= (-8) + ((-((2^9)) \times C(3)) \times (-6)) \\ 82944 &:= (((C((8 - 2))/9)^4)/4) \\ 83125 &:= (((C((8 + 3)) - 1)/2) \times C(5)) \\ 83166 &:= (((C((8 \times 3)) + 1) \times 6) + C(6)) \\ 83267 &:= (C(8) - (C(3) \times ((C(C(2)) \times (-6)) + (7)))) \\ 83287 &:= ((C((8 \times 3)) \times (-2 - 8)) + C(7)) \\ 83346 &:= (((C((8 \times 3)) + 3) + C(4)) \times 6) \\ 83349 &:= (C((8 + ((3 \times 3) + 4))) \times 9) \\ 83368 &:= (-8) + ((C(C(3)) - C((C(3) - (6)))) \times 8) \\ 83373 &:= ((8 + (3 \times C((3 \times 7)))) \times 3) \\ 83376 &:= ((8 \times C((3^3))) - C((7 \times 6))) \\ 83528 &:= (8 \times ((C(3) \times (-C(5)) + C(C(2)))) - 8) \\ 83563 &:= (-8) - ((C((C(3) - (5))) \times (-6)) - C(C(3))) \\ 83564 &:= (C(8) - ((C(C(3)) - (-5) \times C(6)) \times (-4))) \\ 83586 &:= (((-8) \times C(3)) \times (C(5) - C(8)) - (6)) \\ 83618 &:= (C(8) + ((C(3) \times 6) \times (1 + C(8)))) \\ 83683 &:= (C(((8 + 3) - 6) \times 8)) + C(C(3)) \\ 83685 &:= ((8 + C(C(3))) + (-6) + C((8 \times 5))) \\ 83750 &:= ((C(8) - (3^7)) \times (-50)) \\ 83789 &:= (C(8) + ((C((3 \times 7)) - 8) \times 9)) \\ 83853 &:= (-C((8 + 3))) - (-8) \times C((-5) + C(3)) \\ 83875 &:= (((83 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)) \\ 83959 &:= ((C(8) \times (39 + C(5))) - 9) \\ 84125 &:= (((8 - C(4)) + C((1 + C(2)))) \times C(5)) \\ 84375 &:= (C((C(8) - 437))/5) \\ 84456 &:= (((8 \times C(4)) + (4)) - C(5)) \times C(6) \\ 84463 &:= ((8 + C(44)) - C((6 + 3))) \\ 84469 &:= (((8 + C(44)) + (6)) - C(9)) \\ 84472 &:= ((-8) + C(C(4))) - ((4 + C(7)) \times C(C(2))) \\ 84495 &:= (C((-8) + C(4)) - (-4) + C((9 \times 5))) \\ 84544 &:= (((C(8)/(-4)) \times 5) + C(44)) \\ 84666 &:= (((8 + (C(4) \times 6)) \times C(6)) - (6)) \\ 84668 &:= -(((C(8) + (4)) - C(((6 \times 6) + 8))) \\ 84671 &:= (((8 - C(4)) \times C(6)) \times (-7)) - 1) \\ 84672 &:= ((-8) \times C(4)) + C(((6 \times 7) + 2)) \\ 84683 &:= (-((C(8) \times (C(4) - C(6)))) + C((-8) + C(3))) \\ 84721 &:= ((C(84) + C(7))/(C(2) - 1)) \\ 84736 &:= (8 \times (C((4 + 7)) + C((C(3) - (6)))))) \\ 84744 &:= (8 + ((C(4) \times (-7)) + C(44))) \\ 84875 &:= (((84 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)) \\ 84892 &:= ((C((-8) + C(4))) - (8 \times C(9)))/2) \\ 84928 &:= (C((8 + (4 \times 9))) - (2^8)) \\ 84964 &:= ((C((8 + (4 \times 9))) - C(6)) - (4)) \\ 84967 &:= (C(8) + ((C(4) - C(9)) \times (C(6) - C(7)))) \\ 84992 &:= (C(8) \times (4 + ((9 \times 9) \times 2))) \\ 85136 &:= (8 \times (C((-5) + C((1 \times 3)))) - (6)) \\ 85144 &:= (-((8 \times 5)) + C((1 \times 44))) \\ 85173 &:= ((-8) + C((51 - 7))) - 3) \\ 85176 &:= ((-8) + C(5)) \times (C((1 + 7)) + C(6)) \\ 85177 &:= ((8 \times C((5 + 17))) - (7)) \\ 85182 &:= (C(((C(8) - C(5)) - C(-((1 - 8)))))) - 2) \\ 85184 &:= C((((8 - 5) \times 1) + 8) \times 4) \\ 85192 &:= (8 + C(((51 - 9) + 2))) \\ 85222 &:= ((8 \times (5 + C(22))) - 2) \\ 85223 &:= (((8^5) + 2) \times 2) + C(C(3)) \\ 85224 &:= ((C(8) \times (5 + C(22)))/C(4)) \\ 85244 &:= ((8 + 52) + C(44)) \\ 85245 &:= (C(-((8 - 52))) - (C(4) - C(5))) \\ 85248 &:= (C(-((8 - 52))) + C(-((4 - 8)))) \\ 85249 &:= -((C(8) - ((C(5) - C(2)) \times (4 + C(9)))))) \\ 85293 &:= (((8 + C((5 + 2))) \times C(9))/3) \\ 85312 &:= (-8) + (5 \times (C((C(3) - 1)) - C(C(2)))) \\ 85317 &:= ((8 + C(5)) + C((C(3) + (17)))) \\ 85325 &:= ((8 \times (C((-5) + C(3)) + 2)) + (C(5))) \\ 85332 &:= ((8 + 5) \times (3 + (3^{C(2)}))) \\ 85339 &:= (C(((8 \times 5) + 3)) + C((C(3) - 9))) \\ 85344 &:= (((8 + C(5)) + C(3)) + C(44)) \\ 85366 &:= (-((8^5)) - ((C(C(3)) + (6)) \times (-6))) \\ 85373 &:= ((8 \times C((-5) + C(3))) + (7 \times C(3))) \\ 85464 &:= ((C(((8 \times 5) + 4)) + C(6)) + C(4)) \\ 85527 &:= (C(((C(8) - C(5)) - C((5 + 2)))) + C(7)) \\ 85568 &:= (((C(8) - C(5)) - (5)) \times (C(6) + 8)) \\ 85625 &:= (((C(8) + C(5)) + (6 \times C(2))) \times C(5)) \\ 85672 &:= (8 \times (C(5) - (C(6) \times (-7^2)))) \\ 85683 &:= (((C(8) - (5))^{-6+8})/3) \\ 85688 &:= (((-8) + C(5)) \times (C(6) + C(8))) + C(8) \\ 85723 &:= ((C(8) + C(-((5 - (7^2)))))) + C(3) \\ 85727 &:= (((8 - C((5 \times 7))) \times (-2)) - (7)) \\ 85742 &:= (((-8) + C((5 \times 7))) + (4)) \times 2) \\ 85745 &:= (((-8) \times C((5 \times 7)))/(-4)) - (5) \\ 85752 &:= (-8) + ((-5) - C((7 \times 5))) \times (-2) \\ 85772 &:= (8 - ((C((5 \times 7)) + (7)) \times (-2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}85782 &:= (((8 + C((5 \times 7))) + 8) \times 2) \\85875 &:= (((85 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)) \\85948 &:= (C(C((8 - 5))) + (C(9) + (4^8))) \\85952 &:= (C((8 \times 5)) + C(((9 + 5) \times 2))) \\86044 &:= (860 + C(44)) \\86203 &:= (C((8 \times 6)) - C((2 + C(03)))) \\86239 &:= -((C(8) + ((6 - C((2 + 3))) \times C(9)))) \\86247 &:= -((C(((8 - 8) + C(6))/C(2))) - C(47))) \\86272 &:= (((C(8) \times 6) - C((C(2) \times 7)))/(-2)) \\86344 &:= (C(8) + ((C(6) \times 3) + C(44))) \\86357 &:= ((C((8 + 6)) \times 3) + (5^7)) \\86375 &:= (((C(8) + C(6)) - 37) \times C(5)) \\86442 &:= ((-86) + C(C(4))) - C((C(4) - C(2))) \\86523 &:= (8 - (-65) \times C((C(2) + 3))) \\86526 &:= (-((C(8) - 6))) \times ((C(5) - C(C(2))) + C(6)) \\86528 &:= ((8^6) - C(((5 + 2) \times 8))) \\86632 &:= ((C(8) + C(6)) \times (-6) + C((3 + 2))) \\86750 &:= (((-8) \times C(6)) - 7) \times (-50) \\86779 &:= (((C(8) - 6)) \times C(7))/(-7 - 9)) \\86784 &:= ((C(8) \times (-678))/(-4)) \\86813 &:= (((-8) + C(6)) \times C(8)) - C(C((1 \times 3))) \\86875 &:= ((8 + 687) \times C(5)) \\86932 &:= ((C((8 \times 6)) + C(9)) - C((C(3) + 2))) \\86967 &:= (C((8 \times 6)) - (C((9 + 6)) \times 7)) \\87204 &:= ((C(8) - C(7)) \times (C(C(2)) + 04)) \\87249 &:= (((-((C((8 \times 7)) + C(2))) + C(C(4))) + (C(9))) \\87288 &:= (((C((8 \times 7))/2) - C(8)) - 8) \\87336 &:= (((C(8) + C(C((7 - 3))))/3) - C(6)) \\87424 &:= (((-8) - ((C(7) \times (-4)) - 2)) \times C(4)) \\87439 &:= (((C(8) + 7)) + (C(C(4)) \times 3))/9) \\87464 &:= -((C(8) - (((C(7) + C(4)) \times C(6)) + C(4))) \\87493 &:= (((-8) + C(7)) + (4^9))/3) \\87552 &:= (C(8) \times ((C(7) - (5/5))/2)) \\87625 &:= ((C(8) + (7 \times C((6/2)))) \times C(5)) \\87648 &:= (8 + ((C(76) + C(C(4)))/8)) \\87711 &:= ((C(8) + 7) \times (-C(7)) + C(C((1 + 1)))) \\87723 &:= (((C(8) + (7/7))^2)/3) \\87744 &:= (((-8) \times C((7 + 7))) \times (-4)) - C(4) \\87799 &:= ((C((8 \times 7))/(-7 - 9)) - 9) \\87812 &:= ((8 + C((7 \times 8)))/(1 \times 2)) \\87864 &:= (8 \times (7 - (C((8 + 6)) \times (-4)))) \\87875 &:= (((87 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}87928 &:= (8 \times (C(7) - (C((9 + 2)) \times (-8)))) \\87992 &:= (((8 + 7) \times C((9 + 9))) + C(C(2))) \\88387 &:= ((C(8) + (8 + 3)) \times (C(8) - C(7))) \\88464 &:= (((-C(88)) - C(C(4))) \times (-6))/C(4) \\88568 &:= (-8) + (C(8) \times (C(5) + ((6 \times 8)))) \\88576 &:= (C(8) \times (-((8 + (5 \times 7))) + C(6))) \\88725 &:= ((C(8) \times (C(8) - C(7))) + C((C(2) + (5)))) \\88726 &:= (((-8 \times 8) - C(7)) \times (-2 - C(6))) \\88768 &:= (C(88) - C((76 + 8))) \\88875 &:= (((8 \times 88) + 7) \times C(5)) \\89125 &:= (((-8) + C(9)) - C((1 \times 2))) \times C(5) \\89341 &:= (((8 + C(9)) + C(C(3))) + C(41)) \\89344 &:= ((C(8) \times ((C(9) - C(3)) - 4))/4) \\89352 &:= (((C(8) + 9) + C((C(3) - 5))) \times C(2)) \\89373 &:= (C(((8 \times 9)/3) + 7)) \times 3) \\89381 &:= (8 - (C(93)/(-8 + 1))) \\89549 &:= (((-8) + C(9)) \times C(5)) - (C(4) \times 9) \\89625 &:= (((-8) + C(9)) - (6 - 2)) \times C(5) \\89738 &:= (-C(8)) + ((C(9) - 7) \times C(-((3 - 8)))) \\89765 &:= (((C(8) - 97) \times C(6)) + C(5)) \\89792 &:= ((C(8) \times 9) + C((C(7) + 9)/C(2))) \\89856 &:= (((C(8) \times 9) \times (-8) + C(5))/6) \\89875 &:= (((89 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)) \\89928 &:= ((8 \times 9) \times ((C(9) + C(2)) + C(8))) \\90125 &:= ((C(9) - C((0 \times 1) + 2)) \times C(5)) \\90396 &:= -((C(9) - C((039 + 6)))) \\90549 &:= (C((9 \times 05)) - (C(4) \times 9)) \\90625 &:= ((C(9) - (06 - 2)) \times C(5)) \\90782 &:= ((C(90) - (C(7) \times 8))/C(2)) \\90875 &:= (((90 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)) \\91125 &:= C(((9 + 11) + 25)) \\91134 &:= (9 + C((11 + 34))) \\91145 &:= ((9 + 11) + C(45)) \\91359 &:= ((9 \times (-1) + C(3)) + C((5 \times 9))) \\91395 &:= (((9 + 1) \times C(3)) + C((9 \times 5))) \\91445 &:= (C((9 \times (1 + 4))) + (C(4) \times 5)) \\91512 &:= (((C(9) - 1) \times C(5)) + C(C((1 \times 2)))) \\91525 &:= ((C(9) + C((1 + (5^2)))) \times 5) \\91625 &:= ((C(9) + ((1 \times 6) - 2)) \times C(5)) \\91657 &:= (((C(9) + (1 + 6)) \times C(5)) - C(7)) \\91729 &:= (((C(9) - 1) \times C((7 - 2))) + C(9)) \\91845 &:= (((-9) + C((1 + 8))) + C(45)) \\91852 &:= ((C(9) + C(((1 + 8) \times 5))) - 2)\end{aligned}$$

- 91853 := ((C(9) - 1) + C(-((8 - 53))))
91854 := (C(9) + C((1 + ((8 × 5) + 4))))
91855 := ((C(9) + 1) + C(((8 × 5) + 5)))
91875 := (((91 × 8) + 7) × C(5))
91945 := ((91 + C(9)) + C(45))
92045 := (920 + C(45))
92088 := (9 × ((20 × C(8)) - 8))
92125 := ((C(9) + C(2)) × 125)
92205 := (9 × ((C(C(2)) × 20) + (5)))
92279 := (((C(9) - C(2)) × (2⁷)) - 9)
92288 := ((C(9) - C(2)) × ((2 × 8) × 8))
92344 := ((C((9 + 2)) + C(3)) × (C(4) + (4)))
92376 := (((9 × C(C(2))) × (C(3) - (7))) + C(6))
92453 := ((C((9 + 2)) + C(45)) - 3)
92475 := (9 × (((C(C(2)) × 4) + (7)) × 5))
92527 := ((C(9) × (2 + C(5))) - (C(2) × 7))
92573 := ((C(9) × (2 + C(5))) - (7 + 3))
92575 := ((C(9) × (2 + C(5))) - C((7 - 5)))
92582 := ((C(9) × (2 + C(5))) - (8/C(2)))
92583 := (C(9) × (-2) + ((C(5) - C(8))/(-3)))
92591 := (9 + (((2 + C(5)) × C(9)) - 1))
92592 := ((9 - C(-((2 - 59)))))/(-2))
92593 := (-C(9) - (2 × (-5) - C((9 + C(3)))))
92596 := ((C(9) - C(2)) + (C(5) × (C(9) + (6))))
92610 := (C((9 + (2 × 6))) × 10)
92625 := (((C(9) + C(2)) + (6 - 2)) × C(5))
92648 := ((9 × C(26)) - (4⁸))
92662 := (((C(9) - C(C(2))) + C(6)) × (C(6) - 2))
92672 := (-((C((9 + 2)) + (C(6) × (-7)))) × C(C(2)))
92837 := ((C(9) + 2) × ((-8) × C(3)) + C(7))
92875 := (((92 × 8) + 7) × C(5))
93042 := (((-C(9)) + C(C(3))) - (0 - C(42)))
93125 := ((C(9) + ((3 + 1)²)) × C(5))
93170 := (C(((9 + 3) - 1)) × 70)
93184 := (((-((9³) - 1)) × C(8))/(-4))
93238 := (((9 - 3) × C((-2) + C(3))) - C(8))
93244 := ((C((9 + C(3))) × 2) + (-4 - C(4)))
93248 := ((C((9 + C(3))) × 2) - C(-((4 - 8))))
93256 := ((C((9 + C(3))) × 2) - (56))
93285 := ((C((9 + C(3))) × 2) - C((8 - 5)))
93294 := ((9 - C(3)) + (2 × C((9 × 4))))
93311 := ((C((9 + C(3))) × (3 - 1)) - 1)
93312 := ((9 × (3 + 3)) × C(12))
93322 := ((C((9 + C(3))) + (3 + 2)) × 2)
93339 := ((C((9 + C(3))) + C(3)) + C((C(3) + 9)))
93375 := ((C(9) - ((3 - (3 × 7)))) × C(5))
93382 := ((C((9 + C(3))) + (C(3) + 8)) × 2)
93464 := -((C(((9 + C(3)) + (4))) - C((C(6)/4))))
93465 := (93 × (C((4 + 6)) + (5)))
93479 := -((C(9) - ((C(3) - (4)) × C((7 + 9))))))
93526 := ((C(9) × (3 + C(5))) - (2 - C(6)))
93528 := ((C(9) × (3 + C(5))) + C(-((2 - 8))))
93529 := (((C(9) × (3 + C(5))) - C(C(2))) + (C(9)))
93537 := ((9 + C(35)) + C(37))
93548 := (((C(9) + 3) × C(5)) - (-4 × C(8)))
93552 := ((C((9 + C(3))) - (5 - C(5))) × 2)
93562 := ((C((9 + C(3))) + (C(5))) × (-6 + C(2)))
93625 := ((C(9) + ((3 × 6) + 2)) × C(5))
93654 := ((C(9) - 3) × (65 + C(4)))
93685 := (C((9 + 36)) - (C(8) × (-5)))
93734 := ((9 × (C(C(3)) - C((7 × 3)))) - C(4))
93761 := (((-9) + C(C(3))) + ((C((7 × 6)) - 1)))
93771 := (C((9 × 3)) + C((7 × (7 - 1))))
93794 := (((-9) × C(3)) × (C(7) - C(9))) - (4))
93824 := (((-((C(9) + 3) × C(8))) - C(C(2)))/(-4))
93875 := (((93 × 8) + 7) × C(5))
93952 := -((C(((9 × 3) + 9)) - C(52)))
94041 := (C(9) × (4 + C((04 + 1))))
94125 := ((C(9) + ((4 - 1) × C(2))) × C(5))
94157 := (((C(9) + C((4 - 1))) × C(5)) - C(7))
94176 := (((94 - 1) + C(7)) × C(6))
94262 := ((C(((9 - 4)²)) × 6) + C(C(2)))
94326 := ((9 × C(4)) - (C((C(3) - 2)) × (-6)))
94427 := ((C(9) × ((C(4) + C(4)) + 2)) - C(7))
94436 := (((-9) + C(44)) + C((C(3) - (6))))
94438 := -(((C((-9) + C(4))) - C(C(4))) + C((3 + 8)))
94553 := ((C(9) × (4 + C(5))) + C((5 + 3)))
94558 := ((C(9) × (4 + C(5))) + (5 + C(8)))
94625 := (((C(9) + C(4)) - ((6²))) × C(5))
94824 := (((-9) - C(4)) + C(8)) × C((2 + 4))
94875 := (((94 × 8) + 7) × C(5))
94968 := ((9 - ((C(4) - 9) × C(6))) × (-8))
95125 := (((C(9) + (5)) + C((1 + 2))) × C(5))
95221 := (C((9 × 5)) + C((C(2) × (2 × 1))))

- 95232 := (((C((9 - 5)) - 2) × 3) × C(C(2)))
95247 := (9 × (((-5) × C(C(2))) × (-4)) + C(7))
95263 := ((C(95) - C(2))/(6 + 3))
95297 := -((C(9) - ((C(5) + C(2)) × (C(9) - (7))))))
95365 := (((C(9) - C(5)) - C(C(3))) + (6)) × (-5))
95368 := (((9 + C(5)) - 3) × (C(6) + C(8)))
95375 := (C((9 × 5)) + ((C(3) + (7)) × C(5)))
95384 := ((9 × C((-5) + C(3))) - (C(8) - C(4)))
95395 := (((C(9) - C(5)) - (3⁹)) × (-5))
95424 := ((-9) - (C(5) × (-4) - C(2))) × C(4)
95472 := (9 × ((-5) + C((4 + 7))) × C(2))
95490 := ((9 × C(5)) - C(4)) × 90
95499 := ((95 + (4 × 9)) × C(9))
95625 := (C((9 × 5)) - ((6²) × C(5)))
95627 := ((C(9) × (C(5) + (6))) + (2⁷))
95697 := (((9 × 5) × 6) + 9) × C(7)
95774 := ((C((C(9 - 5)) + (7))) + (7)) - C(C(4))
95787 := (9 × (-5) + C(((7 + 8) + 7)))
95823 := (-9) - (C((58 + C(2)))/(-3))
95832 := (9 × C(((5 + 8) + (3²))))
95835 := (((-((9 - 5)) - C(8)) + C(C(3))) × 5)
95838 := (-9) + ((-5) × (C(8) - C(C(3)))) - 8))
95875 := ((95 × 8) + 7) × C(5)
95877 := (9 × (5 + C(((8 + 7) + 7))))
96125 := ((C(9) + ((6 - 1) × C(2))) × C(5))
96159 := ((C(9) - (6)) × ((-1) + C(5)) + 9))
96192 := (96 × (C((1 + 9)) + 2))
96224 := ((C(9) × (6 × 22)) - (4))
96228 := (C(9) × ((62 × 2) + 8))
96256 := (C(((9 × 6) - C(2))) + (-5) × C(6))
96285 := ((C(9) + (6)) × ((2⁸) - C(5)))
96354 := (9 × ((-6) + C((C(3) - (5)))) + C(4))
96435 := (((-9) × (C(6) + (4))) - (C(C(3)) × (-5)))
96462 := ((9 - C(6)) × (46 - C(C(2))))
96625 := (((C(9) + (6 × 6)) + C(2)) × C(5))
96634 := -(((C(-((9 - 66))) - C(C(3))) - C(C(4))))
96643 := (-(((C(9) + C(6)) × C(6))) + C((C(4) + 3)))
96759 := (-9) - ((C(6) × (-7)) × C(-((5 - 9))))
96768 := ((C((9 - 6)) × 7) × C(C(-((6 - 8))))
96783 := ((9 + 6) - (-7) × C((8 × 3)))
96822 := ((C(((9 × 6) - 8)) - 2) - C(C(2)))
96823 := -(((C(9) - C(6)) - (8 × C(23))))
96824 := (C(((9 × 6) - 8)) - C((2 × 4)))
96875 := (((96 × 8) + 7) × C(5))
96957 := (C(9) × (((C(6)/9) - (5)) × 7))
97125 := ((C(9) + ((7 - 1) × C(2))) × C(5))
97152 := ((C(9) + (7)) × ((-1) + C(5)) + C(2))
97173 := (((9 × C(7)) + C((1 + 7))) × C(3))
97327 := (-9) + C((73 - 27))
97328 := (C(((9 + 7) × 3) - 2)) - 8
97333 := (C(((9 + 7) + 3) + C(3))) - 3
97335 := (((C(9) - (7)) × C(3)) - C(3)) × 5
97336 := C((9 + 73) - 36))
97338 := ((9 - 7) + C((C(3) + C(3)) - 8))
97343 := (-((C(9) + C(7))) + ((C(C(3)) × 4) + C(C(3))))
97345 := (9 + C(((7 + 34) + 5)))
97416 := (((C(9) - C(7)) + C(4)) + 1) × C(6)
97433 := (97 + C((43 + 3)))
97462 := (-(((C(9) - C(7)) - C(46))) + C(C(2)))
97469 := (C(9) - (-7) × (-4) + C((C(6)/9)))
97479 := (((-9) - C(7)) × (C(4) - C(7))) - C(9)
97524 := (-((9 × 7)) × ((-C(5) + C(C(2))) × (-4)))
97532 := (C(9) - (-7) × (5 + C((3 × C(2))))))
97534 := (((C(9) - (7)) × 5) × C(3)) + C(4)
97572 := ((9 × 7) + C(5)) × (7 + C(C(2)))
97625 := -(((C(9) + ((-7) × C(6)) + 2)) × C(5))
97678 := ((C(9) × ((7 - C(6)) + C(7))) - 8)
97686 := (((-((C(9) + C(7))) × C((C(6)/8))) / (-C(6)))
97735 := (-((C(9) - ((7 × 7)))) - (C(C(3)) × (-5)))
97746 := (-9) + (C(7) × ((C(7) - C(4)) + (6)))
97764 := (9 + (C(7) × ((C(7) + (6)) - C(4))))
97846 := (((-((9 - 7)) + C(8)) + C(46))
97875 := (((97 × 8) + 7) × C(5))
98125 := ((C(9) + ((8 - 1) × C(2))) × C(5))
98146 := ((C(9) + (81)) + C(46))
98220 := ((C((9 + 8)) - 2) × 20)
98232 := (((-9) + (C((8 × 2)) × 3)) × C(2))
98235 := (((9 × 8)/2) - C(C(3))) × (-5))
98253 := (((9 + 8) - C((2⁵))) × (-3))
98297 := ((C((98 - 2))/9) - (7))
98304 := (((9 × C(8))/3) × C(04))
98313 := (9 - ((C(8) × (-3)) × C((1 + 3))))
98320 := ((C((9 + 8)) + 3) × 20)
98334 := (((C(9) + C(8)) - C(3)) × (3⁴))

$$\begin{aligned}
 98343 &:= (-(9 \times 8) + ((C(C(3)) \times 4) + C(C(3)))) \\
 98345 &:= (9 + (8 \times (C((C(3) - (4))) + (C(5)))) \\
 98355 &:= (((-(9 + 8) + C(C(3))) + (5)) \times 5) \\
 98358 &:= (-9) + (((8 - C(C(3))) \times (-5)) - 8) \\
 98375 &:= (((-(9 - 8) + C(C(3))) - (7)) \times 5) \\
 98384 &:= ((C((9 + 8)) + C(C(3))) \times (8 - 4)) \\
 98425 &:= ((C(C(-((9 - 8) - 4)))) + 2) \times 5) \\
 98435 &:= (((-(9 - 8) \times 4) - C(C(3))) \times (-5)) \\
 98496 &:= (9 \times (((-C(8)) - C(C(4))) \times (-9))/C(6)) \\
 98513 &:= (98 + (5 \times C(C((1 \times 3)))) \\
 98523 &:= (98 + (-5) \times (-2) - C(C(3)))) \\
 98533 &:= (-(9 + 8) + (-5) \times (-C(3)) - C(C(3)))) \\
 98545 &:= (((9 \times C((8 + 5))) - C(4)) \times 5) \\
 98623 &:= (C((9 \times 8)) - C((62 + 3))) \\
 98632 &:= (((9 + 8) \times C((6 \times 3))) - C(C(2))) \\
 98637 &:= ((C((9 + 8)) - C(6)) \times (3 \times 7)) \\
 98784 &:= (((9 \times 8) \times C(7)) \times (8 - 4))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 98793 &:= (9 + ((-8) \times C(7)) \times (-9) - C(3))) \\
 98875 &:= (((98 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5)) \\
 98944 &:= (((C(9) + C((8 + 9))) \times C(4)) - C(C(4))) \\
 98954 &:= (C((9 + 8)) + (C(9) \times (C(5) + (4)))) \\
 99125 &:= ((C(9) + ((9 - 1)^2)) \times C(5)) \\
 99127 &:= (((9 + 9) - 1)^2) \times C(7)) \\
 99135 &:= (-9) + (C(9) \times (1 + (C(3) \times 5))) \\
 99144 &:= (C((9 + 9)) \times (1 + (4 \times 4))) \\
 99153 &:= (9 + (C(9) \times (1 + (5 \times C(3)))) \\
 99535 &:= (((-99) - C(5)) - C(C(3))) \times (-5)) \\
 99549 &:= (-(9 \times 9) \times ((C(5) \times (-4)) - C(9))) \\
 99584 &:= (((9 \times (-9) + C(5))) + C(8)) \times C(4)) \\
 99594 &:= (C(9) + ((9 \times 5) \times C((9 + 4)))) \\
 99864 &:= ((C(9) - (9 \times 8)) \times (C(6) - C(4))) \\
 99873 &:= (C(9) \times (9 + (C(8)/(7 - 3))) \\
 99875 &:= (((99 \times 8) + 7) \times C(5))
 \end{aligned}$$

2.3 Pattern in Cubic-Type Selfies

In 1966, Madachy [8] pp. 174-175, gave an idea of **number patterns** writing as:

$$\begin{array}{lll}
 3^4 \times 425 := 34425 & 31^2 \times 325 := 312325 & 73 \times 9 \times 42 := 73942 \\
 3^4 \times 4250 := 344250 & 31^2 \times 3250 := 3123250 & 73 \times 9 \times 420 := 739420 \\
 3^4 \times 42500 := 3442500 & 31^2 \times 32500 := 31232500 & 73 \times 9 \times 4200 := 7394200
 \end{array}$$

Based on the same idea as above, there are some **Cubic-type selfie numbers**, those can be extended in patterned form just multiplying successively by 10. See below the examples:

$$\begin{array}{ll}
 135 := 1 \times C(3) \times 5 & 655 := (6 + C(5)) \times 5 \\
 1350 := 1 \times C(3) \times 50 & 6550 := (6 + C(5)) \times 50 \\
 13500 := 1 \times C(3) \times 500 & 65500 := (6 + C(5)) \times 500 \\
 \\
 549 := (C(5) - C(4)) \times 9 & 1022 := (-1 + C(C(02))) \times 2 \\
 5490 := (C(5) - C(4)) \times 90 & 10220 := (-1 + C(C(02))) \times 20 \\
 54900 := (C(5) - C(4)) \times 900 & 102200 := (-1 + C(C(02))) \times 200 \\
 \\
 585 := (C(5) - 8) \times 5 & 1255 := (1 + 2 \times C(5)) \times 5 \\
 5850 := (C(5) - 8) \times 50 & 12550 := (1 + 2 \times C(5)) \times 50 \\
 58500 := (C(5) - 8) \times 500 & 125500 := (1 + 2 \times C(5)) \times 500
 \end{array}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1296 &:= (-1 - C(C(2)) + C(9)) \times 6 \\12960 &:= (-1 - C(C(2)) + C(9)) \times 60 \\129600 &:= (-1 - C(C(2)) + C(9)) \times 600\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1331 &:= C(C(-1 + 3) + 3) \times 1 \\13310 &:= C(C(-1 + 3) + 3) \times 10 \\133100 &:= C(C(-1 + 3) + 3) \times 100\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1352 &:= (-1 + C(3)) \times 52 \\13520 &:= (-1 + C(3)) \times 520 \\135200 &:= (-1 + C(3)) \times 5200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1359 &:= (-1 + C(3) + C(5)) \times 9 \\13590 &:= (-1 + C(3) + C(5)) \times 90 \\135900 &:= (-1 + C(3) + C(5)) \times 900\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1372 &:= (-1 + 3) \times C(7) \times 2 \\13720 &:= (-1 + 3) \times C(7) \times 20 \\137200 &:= (-1 + 3) \times C(7) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1512 &:= (1 + C(5)) \times 12 \\15120 &:= (1 + C(5)) \times 120 \\151200 &:= (1 + C(5)) \times 1200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1533 &:= (-1 + C(5 + 3)) \times 3 \\15330 &:= (-1 + C(5 + 3)) \times 30 \\153300 &:= (-1 + C(5 + 3)) \times 300\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1715 &:= 1 \times C(7) \times 1 \times 5 \\17150 &:= 1 \times C(7) \times 1 \times 50 \\171500 &:= 1 \times C(7) \times 1 \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1725 &:= (1 \times C(7) + 2) \times 5 \\17250 &:= (1 \times C(7) + 2) \times 50 \\172500 &:= (1 \times C(7) + 2) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1728 &:= C(1 + 7 - 2) \times 8 \\17280 &:= C(1 + 7 - 2) \times 80 \\172800 &:= C(1 + 7 - 2) \times 800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1735 &:= (1 + C(7) + 3) \times 5 \\17350 &:= (1 + C(7) + 3) \times 50 \\173500 &:= (1 + C(7) + 3) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}1752 &:= (1 + 7 \times C(5)) \times 2 \\17520 &:= (1 + 7 \times C(5)) \times 20 \\175200 &:= (1 + 7 \times C(5)) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}2193 &:= (2 + C(1 \times 9)) \times 3 \\21930 &:= (2 + C(1 \times 9)) \times 30 \\219300 &:= (2 + C(1 \times 9)) \times 300\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}2259 &:= (2^{C(2)} - 5) \times 9 \\22590 &:= (2^{C(2)} - 5) \times 90 \\225900 &:= (2^{C(2)} - 5) \times 900\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}2368 &:= (C(2^3) - C(6)) \times 8 \\23680 &:= (C(2^3) - C(6)) \times 80 \\236800 &:= (C(2^3) - C(6)) \times 800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}2375 &:= (C(C(2)) - 37) \times 5 \\23750 &:= (C(C(2)) - 37) \times 50 \\237500 &:= (C(C(2)) - 37) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}2385 &:= (-C(2) - C(3) + C(8)) \times 5 \\23850 &:= (-C(2) - C(3) + C(8)) \times 50 \\238500 &:= (-C(2) - C(3) + C(8)) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}2432 &:= (-C(C(2)) + C(4 \times 3)) \times 2 \\24320 &:= (-C(C(2)) + C(4 \times 3)) \times 20 \\243200 &:= (-C(C(2)) + C(4 \times 3)) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}2495 &:= (C(C(2)) - 4 - 9) \times 5 \\24950 &:= (C(C(2)) - 4 - 9) \times 50 \\249500 &:= (C(C(2)) - 4 - 9) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}2525 &:= (C(C(2)) - 5 - 2) \times 5 \\25250 &:= (C(C(2)) - 5 - 2) \times 50 \\252500 &:= (C(C(2)) - 5 - 2) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}2555 &:= (C(C(2)) - 5/5) \times 5 \\25550 &:= (C(C(2)) - 5/5) \times 50 \\255500 &:= (C(C(2)) - 5/5) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}2565 &:= (C(C(2)) - 5 + 6) \times 5 \\25650 &:= (C(C(2)) - 5 + 6) \times 50 \\256500 &:= (C(C(2)) - 5 + 6) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}2676 &:= 2 \times (C(6) + 7) \times 6 \\26760 &:= 2 \times (C(6) + 7) \times 60 \\267600 &:= 2 \times (C(6) + 7) \times 600\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}2724 &:= (C(C(2)) - C(7) + C(C(2))) \times 4 \\27240 &:= (C(C(2)) - C(7) + C(C(2))) \times 40 \\272400 &:= (C(C(2)) - C(7) + C(C(2))) \times 400\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}2744 &:= C(2 \times 7)/4 \times 4 \\27440 &:= C(2 \times 7)/4 \times 40 \\274400 &:= C(2 \times 7)/4 \times 400\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}2912 &:= 2 \times (C(9) - 1) \times 2 \\29120 &:= 2 \times (C(9) - 1) \times 20 \\291200 &:= 2 \times (C(9) - 1) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}2914 &:= 2 + (C(9) - 1) \times 4 \\29140 &:= 2 + (C(9) - 1) \times 40 \\291400 &:= 2 + (C(9) - 1) \times 400\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}2976 &:= (C(C(2)) - 9 - 7) \times 6 \\29760 &:= (C(C(2)) - 9 - 7) \times 60 \\297600 &:= (C(C(2)) - 9 - 7) \times 600\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}3276 &:= (C(3) + C(C(2)) + 7) \times 6 \\32760 &:= (C(3) + C(C(2)) + 7) \times 60 \\327600 &:= (C(3) + C(C(2)) + 7) \times 600\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}3625 &:= (-3 + C(6) + C(C(2))) \times 5 \\36250 &:= (-3 + C(6) + C(C(2))) \times 50 \\362500 &:= (-3 + C(6) + C(C(2))) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}3645 &:= C(36/4) \times 5 \\36450 &:= C(36/4) \times 50 \\364500 &:= C(36/4) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}3648 &:= 3 \times (C(6) - C(4)) \times 8 \\36480 &:= 3 \times (C(6) - C(4)) \times 80 \\364800 &:= 3 \times (C(6) - C(4)) \times 800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}3744 &:= (C(3 + 7) - C(4)) \times 4 \\37440 &:= (C(3 + 7) - C(4)) \times 40 \\374400 &:= (C(3 + 7) - C(4)) \times 400\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}3848 &:= (-C(3) + C(8) - 4) \times 8 \\38480 &:= (-C(3) + C(8) - 4) \times 80 \\384800 &:= (-C(3) + C(8) - 4) \times 800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}3942 &:= C(3) \times (9 + C(4)) \times 2 \\39420 &:= C(3) \times (9 + C(4)) \times 20 \\394200 &:= C(3) \times (9 + C(4)) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}4128 &:= (4 \times 1 + C(C(2))) \times 8 \\41280 &:= (4 \times 1 + C(C(2))) \times 80 \\412800 &:= (4 \times 1 + C(C(2))) \times 800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}4275 &:= (C(4 \times 2) + C(7)) \times 5 \\42750 &:= (C(4 \times 2) + C(7)) \times 50 \\427500 &:= (C(4 \times 2) + C(7)) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}4329 &:= (-4 - C(3) + C(C(2))) \times 9 \\43290 &:= (-4 - C(3) + C(C(2))) \times 90 \\432900 &:= (-4 - C(3) + C(C(2))) \times 900\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}4368 &:= (C(4) + C(3)) \times 6 \times 8 \\43680 &:= (C(4) + C(3)) \times 6 \times 80 \\436800 &:= (C(4) + C(3)) \times 6 \times 800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}4522 &:= (C(4) + C(5 + C(2))) \times 2 \\45220 &:= (C(4) + C(5 + C(2))) \times 20 \\452200 &:= (C(4) + C(5 + C(2))) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}4536 &:= (C(4+5) + C(3)) \times 6 \\45360 &:= (C(4+5) + C(3)) \times 60 \\453600 &:= (C(4+5) + C(3)) \times 600\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}4575 &:= (-C(4) + C(5)) \times 75 \\45750 &:= (-C(4) + C(5)) \times 750 \\457500 &:= (-C(4) + C(5)) \times 7500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}4697 &:= (-C(4) + 6 + C(9)) \times 7 \\46970 &:= (-C(4) + 6 + C(9)) \times 70 \\469700 &:= (-C(4) + 6 + C(9)) \times 700\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}4864 &:= (C(C(4)) + C(8))/C(6) \times 4 \\48640 &:= (C(C(4)) + C(8))/C(6) \times 40 \\486400 &:= (C(C(4)) + C(8))/C(6) \times 400\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}5324 &:= C(5 + 3 \times 2) \times 4 \\53240 &:= C(5 + 3 \times 2) \times 40 \\532400 &:= C(5 + 3 \times 2) \times 400\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}5376 &:= (C(5) + 3) \times 7 \times 6 \\53760 &:= (C(5) + 3) \times 7 \times 60 \\537600 &:= (C(5) + 3) \times 7 \times 600\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}5445 &:= (C(5) - 4) \times 45 \\54450 &:= (C(5) - 4) \times 450 \\544500 &:= (C(5) - 4) \times 4500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}5945 &:= (C(5) \times 9 + C(4)) \times 5 \\59450 &:= (C(5) \times 9 + C(4)) \times 50 \\594500 &:= (C(5) \times 9 + C(4)) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}6399 &:= (-6 \times 3 + C(9)) \times 9 \\63990 &:= (-6 \times 3 + C(9)) \times 90 \\639900 &:= (-6 \times 3 + C(9)) \times 900\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}6966 &:= (C(6) + C(9) + C(6)) \times 6 \\69660 &:= (C(6) + C(9) + C(6)) \times 60 \\696600 &:= (C(6) + C(9) + C(6)) \times 600\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}7168 &:= C(7+1) \times (6+8) \\71680 &:= C(7+1) \times (60+80) \\716800 &:= C(7+1) \times (600+800)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}7182 &:= 7 \times (1 + C(8)) \times 2 \\71820 &:= 7 \times (1 + C(8)) \times 20 \\718200 &:= 7 \times (1 + C(8)) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}8192 &:= C(8) \times (-1+9) \times 2 \\81920 &:= C(8) \times (-1+9) \times 20 \\819200 &:= C(8) \times (-1+9) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}8375 &:= (-C(8) + 3^7) \times 5 \\83750 &:= (-C(8) + 3^7) \times 50 \\837500 &:= (-C(8) + 3^7) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}8675 &:= (8 \times C(6) + 7) \times 5 \\86750 &:= (8 \times C(6) + 7) \times 50 \\867500 &:= (8 \times C(6) + 7) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}9261 &:= C(9 + 2 \times 6) \times 1 \\92610 &:= C(9 + 2 \times 6) \times 10 \\926100 &:= C(9 + 2 \times 6) \times 100\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}9317 &:= C(9 + 3 - 1) \times 7 \\93170 &:= C(9 + 3 - 1) \times 70 \\931700 &:= C(9 + 3 - 1) \times 700\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}9549 &:= (9 \times C(5) - C(4)) \times 9 \\95490 &:= (9 \times C(5) - C(4)) \times 90 \\954900 &:= (9 \times C(5) - C(4)) \times 900\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}9822 &:= (C(9+8) - 2) \times 2 \\98220 &:= (C(9+8) - 2) \times 20 \\982200 &:= (C(9+8) - 2) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}9832 &:= (C(9+8) + 3) \times 2 \\98320 &:= (C(9+8) + 3) \times 20 \\983200 &:= (C(9+8) + 3) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}10245 &:= (1 + C(C(02)) \times 4) \times 5 \\102450 &:= (1 + C(C(02)) \times 4) \times 50 \\1024500 &:= (1 + C(C(02)) \times 4) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}10568 &:= (-10 + C(5 + 6)) \times 8 \\105680 &:= (-10 + C(5 + 6)) \times 80 \\1056800 &:= (-10 + C(5 + 6)) \times 800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}10584 &:= (1 + C(05)) \times 84 \\105840 &:= (1 + C(05)) \times 840 \\1058400 &:= (1 + C(05)) \times 8400\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}10648 &:= C(1 + 06 + 4) \times 8 \\106480 &:= C(1 + 06 + 4) \times 80 \\1064800 &:= C(1 + 06 + 4) \times 800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}10728 &:= (C(10) + C(7) - 2) \times 8 \\107280 &:= (C(10) + C(7) - 2) \times 80 \\1072800 &:= (C(10) + C(7) - 2) \times 800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}10935 &:= 1 \times C(09) \times 3 \times 5 \\109350 &:= 1 \times C(09) \times 3 \times 50 \\1093500 &:= 1 \times C(09) \times 3 \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}11011 &:= (1 + C(10)) \times 11 \\110110 &:= (1 + C(10)) \times 110 \\1101100 &:= (1 + C(10)) \times 1100\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}11592 &:= (1 \times 1 + C(5)) \times 92 \\115920 &:= (1 \times 1 + C(5)) \times 920 \\1159200 &:= (1 \times 1 + C(5)) \times 9200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}11718 &:= (C(11) + C(7)) \times (-1 + 8) \\117180 &:= (C(11) + C(7)) \times (-10 + 80) \\1171800 &:= (C(11) + C(7)) \times (-100 + 800)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}11979 &:= C((1 + 1) \times 9 - 7) \times 9 \\119790 &:= C((1 + 1) \times 9 - 7) \times 90 \\1197900 &:= C((1 + 1) \times 9 - 7) \times 900\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}12246 &:= (1 + (-2 + C(C(2)))) \times 4 \times 6 \\122460 &:= (1 + (-2 + C(C(2)))) \times 4 \times 60 \\1224600 &:= (1 + (-2 + C(C(2)))) \times 4 \times 600\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}12264 &:= (-1^2 + C(C(2))) \times 6 \times 4 \\122640 &:= (-1^2 + C(C(2))) \times 6 \times 40 \\1226400 &:= (-1^2 + C(C(2))) \times 6 \times 400\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}12285 &:= (-1 + C(C(2) + C(2))) \times (8 - 5) \\122850 &:= (-1 + C(C(2) + C(2))) \times (80 - 50) \\1228500 &:= (-1 + C(C(2) + C(2))) \times (800 - 500)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}12295 &:= (C(12) + 2 + C(9)) \times 5 \\122950 &:= (C(12) + 2 + C(9)) \times 50 \\1229500 &:= (C(12) + 2 + C(9)) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}12328 &:= (C(-1 + C(2)) \times 3 + C(C(2))) \times 8 \\123280 &:= (C(-1 + C(2)) \times 3 + C(C(2))) \times 80 \\1232800 &:= (C(-1 + C(2)) \times 3 + C(C(2))) \times 800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}12364 &:= (1 + (C(C(2)) + 3) \times 6) \times 4 \\123640 &:= (1 + (C(C(2)) + 3) \times 6) \times 40 \\1236400 &:= (1 + (C(C(2)) + 3) \times 6) \times 400\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}12368 &:= (-1 + C(C(2) + 3) + C(6)) \times 8 \\123680 &:= (-1 + C(C(2) + 3) + C(6)) \times 80 \\1236800 &:= (-1 + C(C(2) + 3) + C(6)) \times 800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}12655 &:= (1 + (C(C(2)) - 6) \times 5) \times 5 \\126550 &:= (1 + (C(C(2)) - 6) \times 5) \times 50 \\1265500 &:= (1 + (C(C(2)) - 6) \times 5) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}12825 &:= (1^2 + C(8)) \times 25 \\128250 &:= (1^2 + C(8)) \times 250 \\1282500 &:= (1^2 + C(8)) \times 2500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}12855 &:= (1 + (2 + C(8)) \times 5) \times 5 \\128550 &:= (1 + (2 + C(8)) \times 5) \times 50 \\1285500 &:= (1 + (2 + C(8)) \times 5) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 13116 &:= (C(13) - 11) \times 6 & 13715 &:= (C((-1 + 3) \times 7) - 1) \times 5 \\ 131160 &:= (C(13) - 11) \times 60 & 137150 &:= (C((-1 + 3) \times 7) - 1) \times 50 \\ 1311600 &:= (C(13) - 11) \times 600 & 1371500 &:= (C((-1 + 3) \times 7) - 1) \times 500 \\ \\ 13122 &:= (1 \times 3^{C(1 \times 2)}) \times 2 & 13722 &:= (C(-1 + C(3) - 7) + 2) \times 2 \\ 131220 &:= (1 \times 3^{C(1 \times 2)}) \times 20 & 137220 &:= (C(-1 + C(3) - 7) + 2) \times 20 \\ 1312200 &:= (1 \times 3^{C(1 \times 2)}) \times 200 & 1372200 &:= (C(-1 + C(3) - 7) + 2) \times 200 \\ \\ 13176 &:= (C(13) - 1^7) \times 6 & 13725 &:= (1^3 + C(7 \times 2)) \times 5 \\ 131760 &:= (C(13) - 1^7) \times 60 & 137250 &:= (1^3 + C(7 \times 2)) \times 50 \\ 1317600 &:= (C(13) - 1^7) \times 600 & 1372500 &:= (1^3 + C(7 \times 2)) \times 500 \\ \\ 13244 &:= (C(13 + 2) - C(4)) \times 4 & 13735 &:= (C((-1 + 3) \times 7) + 3) \times 5 \\ 132440 &:= (C(13 + 2) - C(4)) \times 40 & 137350 &:= (C((-1 + 3) \times 7) + 3) \times 50 \\ 1324400 &:= (C(13 + 2) - C(4)) \times 400 & 1373500 &:= (C((-1 + 3) \times 7) + 3) \times 500 \\ \\ 13266 &:= (C(13) + C(2) + 6) \times 6 & 13785 &:= (13 + C(7) \times 8) \times 5 \\ 132660 &:= (C(13) + C(2) + 6) \times 60 & 137850 &:= (13 + C(7) \times 8) \times 50 \\ 1326600 &:= (C(13) + C(2) + 6) \times 600 & 1378500 &:= (13 + C(7) \times 8) \times 500 \\ \\ 13326 &:= (C(13) + 3 \times C(2)) \times 6 & 13823 &:= (1 - C(3 \times 8)) \times (2 - 3) \\ 133260 &:= (C(13) + 3 \times C(2)) \times 60 & 138230 &:= (1 - C(3 \times 8)) \times (20 - 30) \\ 1332600 &:= (C(13) + 3 \times C(2)) \times 600 & 1382300 &:= (1 - C(3 \times 8)) \times (200 - 300) \\ \\ 13338 &:= 13 \times C(3) \times 38 & 13869 &:= (-1 + 3 \times C(8) + 6) \times 9 \\ 133380 &:= 13 \times C(3) \times 380 & 138690 &:= (-1 + 3 \times C(8) + 6) \times 90 \\ 1333800 &:= 13 \times C(3) \times 3800 & 1386900 &:= (-1 + 3 \times C(8) + 6) \times 900 \\ \\ 13446 &:= (C(13) + 44) \times 6 & 14287 &:= (1 + 4 \times (-2 + C(8))) \times 7 \\ 134460 &:= (C(13) + 44) \times 60 & 142870 &:= (1 + 4 \times (-2 + C(8))) \times 70 \\ 1344600 &:= (C(13) + 44) \times 600 & 1428700 &:= (1 + 4 \times (-2 + C(8))) \times 700 \\ \\ 13504 &:= (1 + C(3 \times 5)) \times 04 & 14495 &:= (-1 + 4 \times (-4 + C(9))) \times 5 \\ 135040 &:= (1 + C(3 \times 5)) \times 040 & 144950 &:= (-1 + 4 \times (-4 + C(9))) \times 50 \\ 1350400 &:= (1 + C(3 \times 5)) \times 0400 & 1449500 &:= (-1 + 4 \times (-4 + C(9))) \times 500 \\ \\ 13685 &:= (-1 + C(3) \times 6) \times 85 & 14529 &:= (1 + 4 \times C(5)) \times 29 \\ 136850 &:= (-1 + C(3) \times 6) \times 850 & 145290 &:= (1 + 4 \times C(5)) \times 290 \\ 1368500 &:= (-1 + C(3) \times 6) \times 8500 & 1452900 &:= (1 + 4 \times C(5)) \times 2900 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}14688 &:= C(-1 + 4) \times 68 \times 8 \\146880 &:= C(-1 + 4) \times 68 \times 80 \\1468800 &:= C(-1 + 4) \times 68 \times 800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}14695 &:= (-1 + 4 \times (6 + C(9))) \times 5 \\146950 &:= (-1 + 4 \times (6 + C(9))) \times 50 \\1469500 &:= (-1 + 4 \times (6 + C(9))) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}14765 &:= (C(14) - 7 + C(6)) \times 5 \\147650 &:= (C(14) - 7 + C(6)) \times 50 \\1476500 &:= (C(14) - 7 + C(6)) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}14935 &:= (C(14) + 9 \times C(3)) \times 5 \\149350 &:= (C(14) + 9 \times C(3)) \times 50 \\1493500 &:= (C(14) + 9 \times C(3)) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}15246 &:= (1 + 5 \times (C(C(2)) - 4)) \times 6 \\152460 &:= (1 + 5 \times (C(C(2)) - 4)) \times 60 \\1524600 &:= (1 + 5 \times (C(C(2)) - 4)) \times 600\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}15365 &:= (1 + C(5 + 3) \times 6) \times 5 \\153650 &:= (1 + C(5 + 3) \times 6) \times 50 \\1536500 &:= (1 + C(5 + 3) \times 6) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}15435 &:= C(1 + 5 \times 4) / 3 \times 5 \\154350 &:= C(1 + 5 \times 4) / 3 \times 50 \\1543500 &:= C(1 + 5 \times 4) / 3 \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}15486 &:= (1 + 5 \times (4 + C(8))) \times 6 \\154860 &:= (1 + 5 \times (4 + C(8))) \times 60 \\1548600 &:= (1 + 5 \times (4 + C(8))) \times 600\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}15678 &:= (-15 + C(6)) \times 78 \\156780 &:= (-15 + C(6)) \times 780 \\1567800 &:= (-15 + C(6)) \times 7800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}16224 &:= (1 - 6 + C(C(2))) \times C(2) \times 4 \\162240 &:= (1 - 6 + C(C(2))) \times C(2) \times 40 \\1622400 &:= (1 - 6 + C(C(2))) \times C(2) \times 400\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}16275 &:= (-1 + C(6) + 2) \times 75 \\162750 &:= (-1 + C(6) + 2) \times 750 \\1627500 &:= (-1 + C(6) + 2) \times 7500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}16285 &:= (1 + C(6 + C(2)) + C(8)) \times 5 \\162850 &:= (1 + C(6 + C(2)) + C(8)) \times 50 \\1628500 &:= (1 + C(6 + C(2)) + C(8)) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}16522 &:= (1 + 6 \times C(5)) \times 22 \\165220 &:= (1 + 6 \times C(5)) \times 220 \\1652200 &:= (1 + 6 \times C(5)) \times 2200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}16575 &:= (1 \times C(6) + 5) \times 75 \\165750 &:= (1 \times C(6) + 5) \times 750 \\1657500 &:= (1 \times C(6) + 5) \times 7500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}16655 &:= (16 \times C(6) - C(5)) \times 5 \\166550 &:= (16 \times C(6) - C(5)) \times 50 \\1665500 &:= (16 \times C(6) - C(5)) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}16752 &:= (1 + 67 \times C(5)) \times 2 \\167520 &:= (1 + 67 \times C(5)) \times 20 \\1675200 &:= (1 + 67 \times C(5)) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}16765 &:= (-1 + (C(6) + C(7)) \times 6) \times 5 \\167650 &:= (-1 + (C(6) + C(7)) \times 6) \times 50 \\1676500 &:= (-1 + (C(6) + C(7)) \times 6) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}16848 &:= (C(1 + 6) + 8) \times 48 \\168480 &:= (C(1 + 6) + 8) \times 480 \\1684800 &:= (C(1 + 6) + 8) \times 4800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}16884 &:= (C(-1 + 6) + C(8 + 8)) \times 4 \\168840 &:= (C(-1 + 6) + C(8 + 8)) \times 40 \\1688400 &:= (C(-1 + 6) + C(8 + 8)) \times 400\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}16992 &:= (-1 + C(6) + C(9)) \times 9 \times 2 \\169920 &:= (-1 + C(6) + C(9)) \times 9 \times 20 \\1699200 &:= (-1 + C(6) + C(9)) \times 9 \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}17528 &:= (1 - 7 + C(5 + C(2))) \times 8 \\175280 &:= (1 - 7 + C(5 + C(2))) \times 80 \\1752800 &:= (1 - 7 + C(5 + C(2))) \times 800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}17584 &:= (C(17) - 5 - C(8)) \times 4 \\175840 &:= (C(17) - 5 - C(8)) \times 40 \\1758400 &:= (C(17) - 5 - C(8)) \times 400\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}17649 &:= (1 + 7 \times (C(6) + C(4))) \times 9 \\176490 &:= (1 + 7 \times (C(6) + C(4))) \times 90 \\1764900 &:= (1 + 7 \times (C(6) + C(4))) \times 900\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}17765 &:= 17 \times (-7 + C(6)) \times 5 \\177650 &:= 17 \times (-7 + C(6)) \times 50 \\1776500 &:= 17 \times (-7 + C(6)) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}17766 &:= (1 + C(7 + 7) + C(6)) \times 6 \\177660 &:= (1 + C(7 + 7) + C(6)) \times 60 \\1776600 &:= (1 + C(7 + 7) + C(6)) \times 600\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}17885 &:= (1 + 7 \times C(8) - 8) \times 5 \\178850 &:= (1 + 7 \times C(8) - 8) \times 50 \\1788500 &:= (1 + 7 \times C(8) - 8) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}17915 &:= (-1 + 7 \times C(9 - 1)) \times 5 \\179150 &:= (-1 + 7 \times C(9 - 1)) \times 50 \\1791500 &:= (-1 + 7 \times C(9 - 1)) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}17925 &:= (1 + C(7 + 9) - C(C(2))) \times 5 \\179250 &:= (1 + C(7 + 9) - C(C(2))) \times 50 \\1792500 &:= (1 + C(7 + 9) - C(C(2))) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}18225 &:= C(18/2) \times 25 \\182250 &:= C(18/2) \times 250 \\1822500 &:= C(18/2) \times 2500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}18235 &:= (1 + C(8) + C(2)) \times 35 \\182350 &:= (1 + C(8) + C(2)) \times 350 \\1823500 &:= (1 + C(8) + C(2)) \times 3500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}18252 &:= (C(-1 + 8) + C(2)) \times 52 \\182520 &:= (C(-1 + 8) + C(2)) \times 520 \\1825200 &:= (C(-1 + 8) + C(2)) \times 5200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}18324 &:= (1 + 8) \times (-3 + C(C(2))) \times 4 \\183240 &:= (1 + 8) \times (-3 + C(C(2))) \times 40 \\1832400 &:= (1 + 8) \times (-3 + C(C(2))) \times 400\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}18396 &:= (1 - C(8)) \times (3 - 9) \times 6 \\183960 &:= (1 - C(8)) \times (3 - 9) \times 60 \\1839600 &:= (1 - C(8)) \times (3 - 9) \times 600\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}18426 &:= (-1 + C(8) \times (4 + 2)) \times 6 \\184260 &:= (-1 + C(8) \times (4 + 2)) \times 60 \\1842600 &:= (-1 + C(8) \times (4 + 2)) \times 600\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}18431 &:= -1 + C(8) \times (C(4) - C(3)) \\18522 &:= C(18 + 5 - 2) \times 2 \\185220 &:= C(18 + 5 - 2) \times 20 \\1852200 &:= C(18 + 5 - 2) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}18545 &:= (C(1 + 8) \times 5 + C(4)) \times 5 \\185450 &:= (C(1 + 8) \times 5 + C(4)) \times 50 \\1854500 &:= (C(1 + 8) \times 5 + C(4)) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}19244 &:= (C(19) - C(C(2)) \times 4) \times 4 \\192440 &:= (C(19) - C(C(2)) \times 4) \times 40 \\1924400 &:= (C(19) - C(C(2)) \times 4) \times 400\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}19722 &:= 19 \times (7 + C(C(2))) \times 2 \\197220 &:= 19 \times (7 + C(C(2))) \times 20 \\1972200 &:= 19 \times (7 + C(C(2))) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}19743 &:= (19 \times C(7) + C(4)) \times 3 \\197430 &:= (19 \times C(7) + C(4)) \times 30 \\1974300 &:= (19 \times C(7) + C(4)) \times 300\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}19862 &:= (C(19) + C(8) \times 6) \times 2 \\198620 &:= (C(19) + C(8) \times 6) \times 20 \\1986200 &:= (C(19) + C(8) \times 6) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$20455 := (C(2^{04}) - 5) \times 5$$

$$204550 := (C(2^{04}) - 5) \times 50$$

$$2045500 := (C(2^{04}) - 5) \times 500$$

$$20736 := 2^{07} \times C(3) \times 6$$

$$207360 := 2^{07} \times C(3) \times 60$$

$$2073600 := 2^{07} \times C(3) \times 600$$

$$21762 := (C(2) \times 1 + C(7)) \times 62$$

$$217620 := (C(2) \times 1 + C(7)) \times 620$$

$$2176200 := (C(2) \times 1 + C(7)) \times 6200$$

$$22113 := (C(C(2)) + C(C(2) + 11)) \times 3$$

$$221130 := (C(C(2)) + C(C(2) + 11)) \times 30$$

$$2211300 := (C(C(2)) + C(C(2) + 11)) \times 300$$

$$22116 := 2 \times (C(C(2)) + C(11)) \times 6$$

$$221160 := 2 \times (C(C(2)) + C(11)) \times 60$$

$$2211600 := 2 \times (C(C(2)) + C(11)) \times 600$$

$$22275 := ((C(C(2)) + 2) \times C(2) + C(7)) \times 5$$

$$222750 := ((C(C(2)) + 2) \times C(2) + C(7)) \times 50$$

$$2227500 := ((C(C(2)) + 2) \times C(2) + C(7)) \times 500$$

$$22326 := (C(2 + 2) - 3)^2 \times 6$$

$$223260 := (C(2 + 2) - 3)^2 \times 60$$

$$2232600 := (C(2 + 2) - 3)^2 \times 600$$

$$22355 := (C(C(2) + C(2)) + 3 \times C(5)) \times 5$$

$$223550 := (C(C(2) + C(2)) + 3 \times C(5)) \times 50$$

$$2235500 := (C(C(2) + C(2)) + 3 \times C(5)) \times 500$$

$$22464 := (2 + 24) \times C(6) \times 4$$

$$224640 := (2 + 24) \times C(6) \times 40$$

$$2246400 := (2 + 24) \times C(6) \times 400$$

$$22575 := (C(C(2)) + C(2) + C(5)) \times 7 \times 5$$

$$225750 := (C(C(2)) + C(2) + C(5)) \times 7 \times 50$$

$$2257500 := (C(C(2)) + C(2) + C(5)) \times 7 \times 500$$

$$22792 := (C(C(2)) + C(2 \times 7)) \times (9 - 2)$$

$$227920 := (C(C(2)) + C(2 \times 7)) \times (90 - 20)$$

$$2279200 := (C(C(2)) + C(2 \times 7)) \times (900 - 200)$$

$$22935 := ((-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 - 3) \times 5$$

$$229350 := ((-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 - 3) \times 50$$

$$2293500 := ((-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 - 3) \times 500$$

$$22944 := C(2) \times (-C(2) + C(9) - 4) \times 4$$

$$229440 := C(2) \times (-C(2) + C(9) - 4) \times 40$$

$$2294400 := C(2) \times (-C(2) + C(9) - 4) \times 400$$

$$22995 := (C(C(2)) + C(2) - 9) \times 9 \times 5$$

$$229950 := (C(C(2)) + C(2) - 9) \times 9 \times 50$$

$$2299500 := (C(C(2)) + C(2) - 9) \times 9 \times 500$$

$$23275 := ((C(C(2)) + C(3)) \times C(2) + C(7)) \times 5$$

$$232750 := ((C(C(2)) + C(3)) \times C(2) + C(7)) \times 50$$

$$2327500 := ((C(C(2)) + C(3)) \times C(2) + C(7)) \times 500$$

$$23292 := (C(23) - C(C(2)) - 9) \times 2$$

$$232920 := (C(23) - C(C(2)) - 9) \times 20$$

$$2329200 := (C(23) - C(C(2)) - 9) \times 200$$

$$23344 := (C(2 \times 3 \times 3) + 4) \times 4$$

$$233440 := (C(2 \times 3 \times 3) + 4) \times 40$$

$$2334400 := (C(2 \times 3 \times 3) + 4) \times 400$$

$$23452 := (C(C(2)) + 3 - C(4)) \times 52$$

$$234520 := (C(C(2)) + 3 - C(4)) \times 520$$

$$2345200 := (C(C(2)) + 3 - C(4)) \times 5200$$

$$23594 := (C(2) + 3^5) \times 94$$

$$235940 := (C(2) + 3^5) \times 940$$

$$2359400 := (C(2) + 3^5) \times 9400$$

$$23652 := (C(23) - C(6) - C(5)) \times 2$$

$$236520 := (C(23) - C(6) - C(5)) \times 20$$

$$2365200 := (C(23) - C(6) - C(5)) \times 200$$

$$23672 := (-C(C(2)) + 36 \times C(7)) \times 2$$

$$236720 := (-C(C(2)) + 36 \times C(7)) \times 20$$

$$2367200 := (-C(C(2)) + 36 \times C(7)) \times 200$$

$$23793 := (C(-C(2) + C(3)) + C(7) + C(9)) \times 3$$

$$237930 := (C(-C(2) + C(3)) + C(7) + C(9)) \times 30$$

$$2379300 := (C(-C(2) + C(3)) + C(7) + C(9)) \times 300$$

$$23822 := (C(23) - C(8)/2) \times 2$$

$$238220 := (C(23) - C(8)/2) \times 20$$

$$2382200 := (C(23) - C(8)/2) \times 200$$

$$23826 := (-C(2 + 3) + C(8 \times 2)) \times 6$$

$$238260 := (-C(2 + 3) + C(8 \times 2)) \times 60$$

$$2382600 := (-C(2 + 3) + C(8 \times 2)) \times 600$$

$$23972 := (C(C(2) + 3) \times 9 + 7) \times 2$$

$$239720 := (C(C(2) + 3) \times 9 + 7) \times 20$$

$$2397200 := (C(C(2) + 3) \times 9 + 7) \times 200$$

$$24125 := (C(2^4) + C(1 + C(2))) \times 5$$

$$241250 := (C(2^4) + C(1 + C(2))) \times 50$$

$$2412500 := (C(2^4) + C(1 + C(2))) \times 500$$

$$24276 := (C(C(2)) + C(4) + 2) \times 7 \times 6$$

$$242760 := (C(C(2)) + C(4) + 2) \times 7 \times 60$$

$$2427600 := (C(C(2)) + C(4) + 2) \times 7 \times 600$$

$$24322 := (-C(2) + C(-4 + C(3)) + 2) \times 2$$

$$243220 := (-C(2) + C(-4 + C(3)) + 2) \times 20$$

$$2432200 := (-C(2) + C(-4 + C(3)) + 2) \times 200$$

$$24354 := (C(C(2)) - C(4) + 3) \times 54$$

$$243540 := (C(C(2)) - C(4) + 3) \times 540$$

$$2435400 := (C(C(2)) - C(4) + 3) \times 5400$$

$$24456 := (C(2^4) - 4 \times 5) \times 6$$

$$244560 := (C(2^4) - 4 \times 5) \times 60$$

$$2445600 := (C(2^4) - 4 \times 5) \times 600$$

$$24535 := (C(C(2)) + C(4) + C(5)) \times 35$$

$$245350 := (C(C(2)) + C(4) + C(5)) \times 350$$

$$2453500 := (C(C(2)) + C(4) + C(5)) \times 3500$$

$$24545 := (C(C(2) + 4 + 5) - 4) \times 5$$

$$245450 := (C(C(2) + 4 + 5) - 4) \times 50$$

$$2454500 := (C(C(2) + 4 + 5) - 4) \times 500$$

$$24565 := C(2 + 4 + 5 + 6) \times 5$$

$$245650 := C(2 + 4 + 5 + 6) \times 50$$

$$2456500 := C(2 + 4 + 5 + 6) \times 500$$

$$24624 := (C(2) + 4^6) \times (2 + 4)$$

$$246240 := (C(2) + 4^6) \times (20 + 40)$$

$$2462400 := (C(2) + 4^6) \times (200 + 400)$$

$$24636 := (2 - C(4) + C(6) \times C(3)) \times 6$$

$$246360 := (2 - C(4) + C(6) \times C(3)) \times 60$$

$$2463600 := (2 - C(4) + C(6) \times C(3)) \times 600$$

$$24816 := C(2) \times (4 + C(8) + 1) \times 6$$

$$248160 := C(2) \times (4 + C(8) + 1) \times 60$$

$$2481600 := C(2) \times (4 + C(8) + 1) \times 600$$

$$24895 := (2 + C(4) + C(8 + 9)) \times 5$$

$$248950 := (2 + C(4) + C(8 + 9)) \times 50$$

$$2489500 := (2 + C(4) + C(8 + 9)) \times 500$$

$$24925 := (C(2) + C(4) + C(9 + C(2))) \times 5$$

$$249250 := (C(2) + C(4) + C(9 + C(2))) \times 50$$

$$2492500 := (C(2) + C(4) + C(9 + C(2))) \times 500$$

$$25137 := (C(2) + C(5)) \times 1 \times C(3) \times 7$$

$$251370 := (C(2) + C(5)) \times 1 \times C(3) \times 70$$

$$2513700 := (C(2) + C(5)) \times 1 \times C(3) \times 700$$

$$25272 := (C(2) + C(5 + 2)) \times 72$$

$$252720 := (C(2) + C(5 + 2)) \times 720$$

$$2527200 := (C(2) + C(5 + 2)) \times 7200$$

$$2655300 := (C(C(2)) - 6 - 5) \times 5300$$

$$25277 := (-C(2) + (5 + C(C(2)))) \times 7 \times 7$$

$$26775 := (C(2) + 6 + C(7)) \times 75$$

$$252770 := (-C(2) + (5 + C(C(2)))) \times 7 \times 70$$

$$267750 := (C(2) + 6 + C(7)) \times 750$$

$$2527700 := (-C(2) + (5 + C(C(2)))) \times 7 \times 700$$

$$2677500 := (C(2) + 6 + C(7)) \times 7500$$

$$25353 := (-C(C(2) + 5) + C(C(3) - 5)) \times 3$$

$$26968 := (2 - 6 + C(9 + 6)) \times 8$$

$$253530 := (-C(C(2) + 5) + C(C(3) - 5)) \times 30$$

$$269680 := (2 - 6 + C(9 + 6)) \times 80$$

$$2535300 := (-C(C(2) + 5) + C(C(3) - 5)) \times 300$$

$$2696800 := (2 - 6 + C(9 + 6)) \times 800$$

$$25475 := (-C(2) + C(5 + 4) \times 7) \times 5$$

$$27339 := (C(C(2)) + 7 \times C(3)) \times 39$$

$$254750 := (-C(2) + C(5 + 4) \times 7) \times 50$$

$$273390 := (C(C(2)) + 7 \times C(3)) \times 390$$

$$2547500 := (-C(2) + C(5 + 4) \times 7) \times 500$$

$$2733900 := (C(C(2)) + 7 \times C(3)) \times 3900$$

$$25536 := (C(2) + C(5)) \times (5 + C(3)) \times 6$$

$$27378 := (C(2) + 7^3) \times 78$$

$$255360 := (C(2) + C(5)) \times (5 + C(3)) \times 60$$

$$273780 := (C(2) + 7^3) \times 780$$

$$2553600 := (C(2) + C(5)) \times (5 + C(3)) \times 600$$

$$2737800 := (C(2) + 7^3) \times 7800$$

$$25725 := (-2 + 5) \times C(7) \times 25$$

$$27546 := (-C(C(2)) + 7 \times C(5 + 4)) \times 6$$

$$257250 := (-2 + 5) \times C(7) \times 250$$

$$275460 := (-C(C(2)) + 7 \times C(5 + 4)) \times 60$$

$$2572500 := (-2 + 5) \times C(7) \times 2500$$

$$2754600 := (-C(C(2)) + 7 \times C(5 + 4)) \times 600$$

$$25735 := (2 + 5 \times C(7) \times 3) \times 5$$

$$27549 := ((-2 + 7)^5 - C(4)) \times 9$$

$$257350 := (2 + 5 \times C(7) \times 3) \times 50$$

$$275490 := ((-2 + 7)^5 - C(4)) \times 90$$

$$2573500 := (2 + 5 \times C(7) \times 3) \times 500$$

$$2754900 := ((-2 + 7)^5 - C(4)) \times 900$$

$$25935 := (C(2 \times 5) + C(9)) \times 3 \times 5$$

$$27864 := (2 \times C(7 + 8) + C(6)) \times 4$$

$$259350 := (C(2 \times 5) + C(9)) \times 3 \times 50$$

$$278640 := (2 \times C(7 + 8) + C(6)) \times 40$$

$$2593500 := (C(2 \times 5) + C(9)) \times 3 \times 500$$

$$2786400 := (2 \times C(7 + 8) + C(6)) \times 400$$

$$26158 := (C(C(2)) - 61) \times 58$$

$$27945 := (2 + C(7)) \times 9 \times (4 + 5)$$

$$261580 := (C(C(2)) - 61) \times 580$$

$$279450 := (2 + C(7)) \times 9 \times (40 + 50)$$

$$2615800 := (C(C(2)) - 61) \times 5800$$

$$2794500 := (2 + C(7)) \times 9 \times (400 + 500)$$

$$26196 := (-C(2) + 6 \times C(1 \times 9)) \times 6$$

$$28217 := ((-C(2) + C(8)) \times C(2) - 1) \times 7$$

$$261960 := (-C(2) + 6 \times C(1 \times 9)) \times 60$$

$$282170 := ((-C(2) + C(8)) \times C(2) - 1) \times 70$$

$$2619600 := (-C(2) + 6 \times C(1 \times 9)) \times 600$$

$$2821700 := ((-C(2) + C(8)) \times C(2) - 1) \times 700$$

$$26553 := (C(C(2)) - 6 - 5) \times 53$$

$$28324 := (C(2) + C(8) + 3^{C(2)}) \times 4$$

$$265530 := (C(C(2)) - 6 - 5) \times 530$$

$$283240 := (C(2) + C(8) + 3^{C(2)}) \times 40$$

$$2832400 := (C(2) + C(8) + 3^{C(2)}) \times 400$$

$$28575 := (2^8 + C(5)) \times 75$$

$$285750 := (2^8 + C(5)) \times 750$$

$$2857500 := (2^8 + C(5)) \times 7500$$

$$28688 := (2 + C(8) \times 6 + C(8)) \times 8$$

$$286880 := (2 + C(8) \times 6 + C(8)) \times 80$$

$$2868800 := (2 + C(8) \times 6 + C(8)) \times 800$$

$$29115 := (C(2) \times (C(9) - 1) - 1) \times 5$$

$$291150 := (C(2) \times (C(9) - 1) - 1) \times 50$$

$$2911500 := (C(2) \times (C(9) - 1) - 1) \times 500$$

$$29125 := (C(2 \times 9) + 1 - C(2)) \times 5$$

$$291250 := (C(2 \times 9) + 1 - C(2)) \times 50$$

$$2912500 := (C(2 \times 9) + 1 - C(2)) \times 500$$

$$29135 := (C(2) \times (C(9) - 1) + 3) \times 5$$

$$291350 := (C(2) \times (C(9) - 1) + 3) \times 50$$

$$2913500 := (C(2) \times (C(9) - 1) + 3) \times 500$$

$$29145 := (C(2 \times 9) + 1 - 4) \times 5$$

$$291450 := (C(2 \times 9) + 1 - 4) \times 50$$

$$2914500 := (C(2 \times 9) + 1 - 4) \times 500$$

$$29248 := C(2) \times (9 + C(C(2)) - C(4)) \times 8$$

$$292480 := C(2) \times (9 + C(C(2)) - C(4)) \times 80$$

$$2924800 := C(2) \times (9 + C(C(2)) - C(4)) \times 800$$

$$29275 := ((2 + C(9)) \times C(2) + 7) \times 5$$

$$292750 := ((2 + C(9)) \times C(2) + 7) \times 50$$

$$2927500 := ((2 + C(9)) \times C(2) + 7) \times 500$$

$$29315 := (C(2 \times 9) + 31) \times 5$$

$$293150 := (C(2 \times 9) + 31) \times 50$$

$$2931500 := (C(2 \times 9) + 31) \times 500$$

$$29316 := (C(C(2) + 9) - C(3)) \times 1 \times 6$$

$$293160 := (C(C(2) + 9) - C(3)) \times 1 \times 60$$

$$2931600 := (C(C(2) + 9) - C(3)) \times 1 \times 600$$

$$29335 := (C(2) + C(-9 + C(3)) + C(3)) \times 5$$

$$293350 := (C(2) + C(-9 + C(3)) + C(3)) \times 50$$

$$2933500 := (C(2) + C(-9 + C(3)) + C(3)) \times 500$$

$$29345 := (C(2 \times 9) - C(3) + C(4)) \times 5$$

$$293450 := (C(2 \times 9) - C(3) + C(4)) \times 50$$

$$2934500 := (C(2 \times 9) - C(3) + C(4)) \times 500$$

$$29425 := (C(C(2)) + C(9) - C(4)) \times 25$$

$$294250 := (C(C(2)) + C(9) - C(4)) \times 250$$

$$2942500 := (C(C(2)) + C(9) - C(4)) \times 2500$$

$$29436 := (C(C(2) + 9) - 4 - 3) \times 6$$

$$294360 := (C(C(2) + 9) - 4 - 3) \times 60$$

$$2943600 := (C(C(2) + 9) - 4 - 3) \times 600$$

$$29455 := (C(2 \times 9) + C(4) - 5) \times 5$$

$$294550 := (C(2 \times 9) + C(4) - 5) \times 50$$

$$2945500 := (C(2 \times 9) + C(4) - 5) \times 500$$

$$29466 := (C(C(2) + 9) + 4 - 6) \times 6$$

$$294660 := (C(C(2) + 9) + 4 - 6) \times 60$$

$$2946600 := (C(C(2) + 9) + 4 - 6) \times 600$$

$$29547 := (C(C(2)) + C(9) \times 5 + C(4)) \times 7$$

$$295470 := (C(C(2)) + C(9) \times 5 + C(4)) \times 70$$

$$2954700 := (C(C(2)) + C(9) \times 5 + C(4)) \times 700$$

$$29573 := C(29) + C(5 + 7) \times 3$$

$$29641 := (-2 + C(9) - 6) \times 41$$

$$296410 := (-2 + C(9) - 6) \times 410$$

$$2964100 := (-2 + C(9) - 6) \times 4100$$

$$29706 := (C(C(2)) \times 9 + C(7)) \times 06$$

$$297060 := (C(C(2)) \times 9 + C(7)) \times 060$$

$$2970600 := (C(C(2)) \times 9 + C(7)) \times 0600$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29791 &:= C(29 - 7 + 9) \times 1 \\ 297910 &:= C(29 - 7 + 9) \times 10 \\ 2979100 &:= C(29 - 7 + 9) \times 100 \\ \\ 29853 &:= (2 \times C(9 + 8) + C(5)) \times 3 \\ 298530 &:= (2 \times C(9 + 8) + C(5)) \times 30 \\ 2985300 &:= (2 \times C(9 + 8) + C(5)) \times 300 \\ \\ 31242 &:= (C(C(3) - 1 \times 2) - 4) \times 2 \\ 312420 &:= (C(C(3) - 1 \times 2) - 4) \times 20 \\ 3124200 &:= (C(C(3) - 1 \times 2) - 4) \times 200 \\ \\ 31262 &:= (C(C(3) - 1 \times 2) + 6) \times 2 \\ 312620 &:= (C(C(3) - 1 \times 2) + 6) \times 20 \\ 3126200 &:= (C(C(3) - 1 \times 2) + 6) \times 200 \\ \\ 31265 &:= (-31 + C(C(2))) \times 65 \\ 312650 &:= (-31 + C(C(2))) \times 650 \\ 3126500 &:= (-31 + C(C(2))) \times 6500 \\ \\ 31744 &:= (C(3 + 17) - C(4)) \times 4 \\ 317440 &:= (C(3 + 17) - C(4)) \times 40 \\ 3174400 &:= (C(3 + 17) - C(4)) \times 400 \\ \\ 31944 &:= (-3 + C(1 \times 9)) \times 44 \\ 319440 &:= (-3 + C(1 \times 9)) \times 440 \\ 3194400 &:= (-3 + C(1 \times 9)) \times 4400 \\ \\ 32256 &:= (3 \times C(2))^2 \times 56 \\ 322560 &:= (3 \times C(2))^2 \times 560 \\ 3225600 &:= (3 \times C(2))^2 \times 5600 \\ \\ 32277 &:= (3 + C(C(2)) \times (2 + 7)) \times 7 \\ 322770 &:= (3 + C(C(2)) \times (2 + 7)) \times 70 \\ 3227700 &:= (3 + C(C(2)) \times (2 + 7)) \times 700 \\ \\ 32292 &:= (C(C(3) - 2) + C(C(2)) + 9) \times 2 \\ 322920 &:= (C(C(3) - 2) + C(C(2)) + 9) \times 20 \\ 3229200 &:= (C(C(3) - 2) + C(C(2)) + 9) \times 200 \\ \\ 32451 &:= ((-3 + C(C(2))) \times C(4) - C(5)) \times 1 \\ 324510 &:= ((-3 + C(C(2))) \times C(4) - C(5)) \times 10 \\ 3245100 &:= ((-3 + C(C(2))) \times C(4) - C(5)) \times 100 \\ \\ 32472 &:= (3 + C(C(2)) - C(4)) \times 72 \\ 324720 &:= (3 + C(C(2)) - C(4)) \times 720 \\ 3247200 &:= (3 + C(C(2)) - C(4)) \times 7200 \\ \\ 32485 &:= (3^{C(2)} - C(-4 + 8)) \times 5 \\ 324850 &:= (3^{C(2)} - C(-4 + 8)) \times 50 \\ 3248500 &:= (3^{C(2)} - C(-4 + 8)) \times 500 \\ \\ 32488 &:= (-C(3) + C(2^4) - 8) \times 8 \\ 324880 &:= (-C(3) + C(2^4) - 8) \times 80 \\ 3248800 &:= (-C(3) + C(2^4) - 8) \times 800 \\ \\ 32528 &:= (C(C(3)) - C(25) + C(2)) \times 8 \\ 325280 &:= (C(C(3)) - C(25) + C(2)) \times 80 \\ 3252800 &:= (C(C(3)) - C(25) + C(2)) \times 800 \\ \\ 32625 &:= (3^{C(2)} - 6^2) \times 5 \\ 326250 &:= (3^{C(2)} - 6^2) \times 50 \\ 3262500 &:= (3^{C(2)} - 6^2) \times 500 \\ \\ 32655 &:= (3^{C(2)} - 6 \times 5) \times 5 \\ 326550 &:= (3^{C(2)} - 6 \times 5) \times 50 \\ 3265500 &:= (3^{C(2)} - 6 \times 5) \times 500 \\ \\ 32697 &:= ((C(3) - 2) \times C(6) - C(9)) \times 7 \\ 326970 &:= ((C(3) - 2) \times C(6) - C(9)) \times 70 \\ 3269700 &:= ((C(3) - 2) \times C(6) - C(9)) \times 700 \\ \\ 32825 &:= (3^{C(2)} + 8/2) \times 5 \\ 328250 &:= (3^{C(2)} + 8/2) \times 50 \\ 3282500 &:= (3^{C(2)} + 8/2) \times 500 \\ \\ 32955 &:= 3 \times C(2 \times 9 - 5) \times 5 \\ 329550 &:= 3 \times C(2 \times 9 - 5) \times 50 \end{aligned}$$

$$3295500 := 3 \times C(2 \times 9 - 5) \times 500$$

$$33124 := (C(3) + C(3 + 1))^2 \times 4$$

$$331240 := (C(3) + C(3 + 1))^2 \times 40$$

$$3312400 := (C(3) + C(3 + 1))^2 \times 400$$

$$33222 := (C(C(3)) - 3 \times 2 \times C(C(2))) \times 2$$

$$332220 := (C(C(3)) - 3 \times 2 \times C(C(2))) \times 20$$

$$3322200 := (C(C(3)) - 3 \times 2 \times C(C(2))) \times 200$$

$$33345 := (C(C(3))/3 + C(3) \times 4) \times 5$$

$$333450 := (C(C(3))/3 + C(3) \times 4) \times 50$$

$$3334500 := (C(C(3))/3 + C(3) \times 4) \times 500$$

$$33445 := (C(C(3))/3 + C(4) + C(4)) \times 5$$

$$334450 := (C(C(3))/3 + C(4) + C(4)) \times 50$$

$$3344500 := (C(C(3))/3 + C(4) + C(4)) \times 500$$

$$33465 := (-3 + (C(3) + 4) \times C(6)) \times 5$$

$$334650 := (-3 + (C(3) + 4) \times C(6)) \times 50$$

$$3346500 := (-3 + (C(3) + 4) \times C(6)) \times 500$$

$$33528 := 33 \times (C(5) + 2) \times 8$$

$$335280 := 33 \times (C(5) + 2) \times 80$$

$$3352800 := 33 \times (C(5) + 2) \times 800$$

$$33561 := C(C(3))/3 + C(5 \times 6) \times 1$$

$$335610 := C(C(3))/3 + C(5 \times 6) \times 10$$

$$3356100 := C(C(3))/3 + C(5 \times 6) \times 100$$

$$33655 := C(C(3) + 3) + C(6 + 5) \times 5$$

$$33865 := (3 \times 3 + C(8)) \times 65$$

$$338650 := (3 \times 3 + C(8)) \times 650$$

$$3386500 := (3 \times 3 + C(8)) \times 6500$$

$$33872 := (C(C(3)) - 3 - 8 \times C(7)) \times 2$$

$$338720 := (C(C(3)) - 3 - 8 \times C(7)) \times 20$$

$$3387200 := (C(C(3)) - 3 - 8 \times C(7)) \times 200$$

$$34225 := (-C(3) + C(4))^2 \times 25$$

$$342250 := (-C(3) + C(4))^2 \times 250$$

$$3422500 := (-C(3) + C(4))^2 \times 2500$$

$$34235 := (-3 \times 4 + C(-C(2) + C(3))) \times 5$$

$$342350 := (-3 \times 4 + C(-C(2) + C(3))) \times 50$$

$$3423500 := (-3 \times 4 + C(-C(2) + C(3))) \times 500$$

$$34265 := (C(3 + 4^2) - 6) \times 5$$

$$342650 := (C(3 + 4^2) - 6) \times 50$$

$$3426500 := (C(3 + 4^2) - 6) \times 500$$

$$34276 := (3 - C(4) + C(C(2))) \times 76$$

$$342760 := (3 - C(4) + C(C(2))) \times 760$$

$$3427600 := (3 - C(4) + C(C(2))) \times 7600$$

$$34295 := C(3 \times 4 - 2 + 9) \times 5$$

$$342950 := C(3 \times 4 - 2 + 9) \times 50$$

$$3429500 := C(3 \times 4 - 2 + 9) \times 500$$

$$34447 := (C(C(3)) + 4/4)/4 \times 7$$

$$344470 := (C(C(3)) + 4/4)/4 \times 70$$

$$3444700 := (C(C(3)) + 4/4)/4 \times 700$$

$$34544 := (C(3 \times 4) \times 5 - 4) \times 4$$

$$345440 := (C(3 \times 4) \times 5 - 4) \times 40$$

$$3454400 := (C(3 \times 4) \times 5 - 4) \times 400$$

$$34575 := (3 + 4 \times C(5 + 7)) \times 5$$

$$345750 := (3 + 4 \times C(5 + 7)) \times 50$$

$$3457500 := (3 + 4 \times C(5 + 7)) \times 500$$

$$34835 := (C(3) \times 4 + C(-8 + C(3))) \times 5$$

$$348350 := (C(3) \times 4 + C(-8 + C(3))) \times 50$$

$$3483500 := (C(3) \times 4 + C(-8 + C(3))) \times 500$$

$$34968 := (-C(3) + (4 + C(9)) \times 6) \times 8$$

$$349680 := (-C(3) + (4 + C(9)) \times 6) \times 80$$

$$3496800 := (-C(3) + (4 + C(9)) \times 6) \times 800$$

$$34986 := C(3 + 4) \times (9 + 8) \times 6$$

$$\begin{aligned} 349860 &:= C(3+4) \times (9+8) \times 60 \\ 3498600 &:= C(3+4) \times (9+8) \times 600 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 35235 &:= 3^5 \times (2+C(3)) \times 5 \\ 352350 &:= 3^5 \times (2+C(3)) \times 50 \\ 3523500 &:= 3^5 \times (2+C(3)) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 35424 &:= C(3) \times (5 \times C(4) + C(2)) \times 4 \\ 354240 &:= C(3) \times (5 \times C(4) + C(2)) \times 40 \\ 3542400 &:= C(3) \times (5 \times C(4) + C(2)) \times 400 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 35475 &:= (-C(3) + C(5) \times 4) \times 75 \\ 354750 &:= (-C(3) + C(5) \times 4) \times 750 \\ 3547500 &:= (-C(3) + C(5) \times 4) \times 7500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 35655 &:= 3 \times (5 + C(6)) \times 55 \\ 356550 &:= 3 \times (5 + C(6)) \times 550 \\ 3565500 &:= 3 \times (5 + C(6)) \times 5500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 35968 &:= (-3 + C(5) + C(9) \times 6) \times 8 \\ 359680 &:= (-3 + C(5) + C(9) \times 6) \times 80 \\ 3596800 &:= (-3 + C(5) + C(9) \times 6) \times 800 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 35991 &:= C(3) \times (-C(5) + C(9) + C(9)) \times 1 \\ 359910 &:= C(3) \times (-C(5) + C(9) + C(9)) \times 10 \\ 3599100 &:= C(3) \times (-C(5) + C(9) + C(9)) \times 100 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 36126 &:= C(3) \times (C(6) - 1 + C(2)) \times 6 \\ 361260 &:= C(3) \times (C(6) - 1 + C(2)) \times 60 \\ 3612600 &:= C(3) \times (C(6) - 1 + C(2)) \times 600 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 36375 &:= (-C(3) + C(C(6/3))) \times 75 \\ 363750 &:= (-C(3) + C(C(6/3))) \times 750 \\ 3637500 &:= (-C(3) + C(C(6/3))) \times 7500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 36549 &:= ((C(3) + 6) \times C(5) - C(4)) \times 9 \\ 365490 &:= ((C(3) + 6) \times C(5) - C(4)) \times 90 \\ 3654900 &:= ((C(3) + 6) \times C(5) - C(4)) \times 900 \end{aligned}$$

$$36675 := (C(C(3)) - 6 \times 6 \times C(7)) \times 5$$

$$\begin{aligned} 366750 &:= (C(C(3)) - 6 \times 6 \times C(7)) \times 50 \\ 3667500 &:= (C(C(3)) - 6 \times 6 \times C(7)) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 36735 &:= (3 + C(6) \times (7 + C(3))) \times 5 \\ 367350 &:= (3 + C(6) \times (7 + C(3))) \times 50 \\ 3673500 &:= (3 + C(6) \times (7 + C(3))) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 37184 &:= (C(3) \times (C(7) + 1) + 8) \times 4 \\ 371840 &:= (C(3) \times (C(7) + 1) + 8) \times 40 \\ 3718400 &:= (C(3) \times (C(7) + 1) + 8) \times 400 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 37244 &:= (C(3) \times (C(7) + 2) - 4) \times 4 \\ 372440 &:= (C(3) \times (C(7) + 2) - 4) \times 40 \\ 3724400 &:= (C(3) \times (C(7) + 2) - 4) \times 400 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 37324 &:= (C(C(3) - 7) + C(3 + C(2))) \times 4 \\ 373240 &:= (C(C(3) - 7) + C(3 + C(2))) \times 40 \\ 3732400 &:= (C(C(3) - 7) + C(3 + C(2))) \times 400 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 37326 &:= (3 - C(7) + 3^{C(2)}) \times 6 \\ 373260 &:= (3 - C(7) + 3^{C(2)}) \times 60 \\ 3732600 &:= (3 - C(7) + 3^{C(2)}) \times 600 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 37382 &:= (-C(3+7) + C(C(3)) + 8) \times 2 \\ 373820 &:= (-C(3+7) + C(C(3)) + 8) \times 20 \\ 3738200 &:= (-C(3+7) + C(C(3)) + 8) \times 200 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 37584 &:= C(3) \times (C(7) + 5) \times (8 - 4) \\ 375840 &:= C(3) \times (C(7) + 5) \times (80 - 40) \\ 3758400 &:= C(3) \times (C(7) + 5) \times (800 - 400) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 37665 &:= (C(3 \times 7) - C(6 + 6)) \times 5 \\ 376650 &:= (C(3 \times 7) - C(6 + 6)) \times 50 \\ 3766500 &:= (C(3 \times 7) - C(6 + 6)) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 37854 &:= (C(3) \times 7 + C(8)) \times 54 \\ 378540 &:= (C(3) \times 7 + C(8)) \times 540 \\ 3785400 &:= (C(3) \times 7 + C(8)) \times 5400 \end{aligned}$$

$$37962 := 37 \times (C(9) - C(6)) \times 2$$

$$\begin{aligned}379620 &:= 37 \times (C(9) - C(6)) \times 20 \\3796200 &:= 37 \times (C(9) - C(6)) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}37984 &:= (C(3) \times (C(7) + 9) - 8) \times 4 \\379840 &:= (C(3) \times (C(7) + 9) - 8) \times 40 \\3798400 &:= (C(3) \times (C(7) + 9) - 8) \times 400\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}38269 &:= (C(3) + C(8)) \times (2 + 69) \\382690 &:= (C(3) + C(8)) \times (20 + 690) \\3826900 &:= (C(3) + C(8)) \times (200 + 6900)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}38342 &:= (C(C(3)) - C(8)) \times (-3 + 4) \times 2 \\383420 &:= (C(C(3)) - C(8)) \times (-3 + 4) \times 20 \\3834200 &:= (C(C(3)) - C(8)) \times (-3 + 4) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}38352 &:= (C(C(3)) - 8^3 + 5) \times 2 \\383520 &:= (C(C(3)) - 8^3 + 5) \times 20 \\3835200 &:= (C(C(3)) - 8^3 + 5) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}38475 &:= (-3 + C(8) + 4) \times 75 \\384750 &:= (-3 + C(8) + 4) \times 750 \\3847500 &:= (-3 + C(8) + 4) \times 7500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}38525 &:= (3 \times C(8) + 5) \times 25 \\385250 &:= (3 \times C(8) + 5) \times 250 \\3852500 &:= (3 \times C(8) + 5) \times 2500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}38535 &:= (3 \times C(8) \times 5 + C(3)) \times 5 \\385350 &:= (3 \times C(8) \times 5 + C(3)) \times 50 \\3853500 &:= (3 \times C(8) \times 5 + C(3)) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}38616 &:= (3^8 - C(6 - 1)) \times 6 \\386160 &:= (3^8 - C(6 - 1)) \times 60 \\3861600 &:= (3^8 - C(6 - 1)) \times 600\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}38745 &:= C(3) \times (8 + C(7) - C(4)) \times 5 \\387450 &:= C(3) \times (8 + C(7) - C(4)) \times 50 \\3874500 &:= C(3) \times (8 + C(7) - C(4)) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$38912 := 38 \times C(9 - 1) \times 2$$

$$\begin{aligned}389120 &:= 38 \times C(9 - 1) \times 20 \\3891200 &:= 38 \times C(9 - 1) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}38932 &:= (C(C(3)) + C(8) - 9^3) \times 2 \\389320 &:= (C(C(3)) + C(8) - 9^3) \times 20 \\3893200 &:= (C(C(3)) + C(8) - 9^3) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}38942 &:= (C(3) \times (-8 + C(9)) + 4) \times 2 \\389420 &:= (C(3) \times (-8 + C(9)) + 4) \times 20 \\3894200 &:= (C(3) \times (-8 + C(9)) + 4) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}39088 &:= (-C(3) + C(9 + 08)) \times 8 \\390880 &:= (-C(3) + C(9 + 08)) \times 80 \\3908800 &:= (-C(3) + C(9 + 08)) \times 800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}39132 &:= (C(C(3)) - 9 \times 13) \times 2 \\391320 &:= (C(C(3)) - 9 \times 13) \times 20 \\3913200 &:= (C(C(3)) - 9 \times 13) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}39242 &:= (3^9 + 2 - C(4)) \times 2 \\392420 &:= (3^9 + 2 - C(4)) \times 20 \\3924200 &:= (3^9 + 2 - C(4)) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}39272 &:= (C(3) \times (C(9) - 2) + 7) \times 2 \\392720 &:= (C(3) \times (C(9) - 2) + 7) \times 20 \\3927200 &:= (C(3) \times (C(9) - 2) + 7) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}39312 &:= C(3) \times (9^3 - 1) \times 2 \\393120 &:= C(3) \times (9^3 - 1) \times 20 \\3931200 &:= C(3) \times (9^3 - 1) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}39352 &:= (C(C(3)) - 9 - 3 + 5) \times 2 \\393520 &:= (C(C(3)) - 9 - 3 + 5) \times 20 \\3935200 &:= (C(C(3)) - 9 - 3 + 5) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}39422 &:= (C(C(3)) + 9 \times 4 - C(2)) \times 2 \\394220 &:= (C(C(3)) + 9 \times 4 - C(2)) \times 20 \\3942200 &:= (C(C(3)) + 9 \times 4 - C(2)) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39456 &:= 3 \times (C(9+4) - 5) \times 6 \\ 394560 &:= 3 \times (C(9+4) - 5) \times 60 \\ 3945600 &:= 3 \times (C(9+4) - 5) \times 600 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39492 &:= (-3 + C(9+4)) \times 9 \times 2 \\ 394920 &:= (-3 + C(9+4)) \times 9 \times 20 \\ 3949200 &:= (-3 + C(9+4)) \times 9 \times 200 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39512 &:= (C(C(3)) + 9 + C(5-1)) \times 2 \\ 395120 &:= (C(C(3)) + 9 + C(5-1)) \times 20 \\ 3951200 &:= (C(C(3)) + 9 + C(5-1)) \times 200 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39546 &:= C(39)/(5+4) \times 6 \\ 395460 &:= C(39)/(5+4) \times 60 \\ 3954600 &:= C(39)/(5+4) \times 600 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39609 &:= (C(3) + C(9) \times 6) \times 09 \\ 396090 &:= (C(3) + C(9) \times 6) \times 090 \\ 3960900 &:= (C(3) + C(9) \times 6) \times 0900 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39722 &:= (C(C(3)) + 9 - C(7) + C(C(2))) \times 2 \\ 397220 &:= (C(C(3)) + 9 - C(7) + C(C(2))) \times 20 \\ 3972200 &:= (C(C(3)) + 9 - C(7) + C(C(2))) \times 200 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39825 &:= C(3) \times (-C(9) + C(8) \times 2) \times 5 \\ 398250 &:= C(3) \times (-C(9) + C(8) \times 2) \times 50 \\ 3982500 &:= C(3) \times (-C(9) + C(8) \times 2) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 40382 &:= (-4 + C(C(03)) + C(8)) \times 2 \\ 403820 &:= (-4 + C(C(03)) + C(8)) \times 20 \\ 4038200 &:= (-4 + C(C(03)) + C(8)) \times 200 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 41463 &:= (-4 + 1 + C(4 \times 6)) \times 3 \\ 414630 &:= (-4 + 1 + C(4 \times 6)) \times 30 \\ 4146300 &:= (-4 + 1 + C(4 \times 6)) \times 300 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 41976 &:= (-4 + C(1+9) \times 7) \times 6 \\ 419760 &:= (-4 + C(1+9) \times 7) \times 60 \\ 4197600 &:= (-4 + C(1+9) \times 7) \times 600 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 42394 &:= (-C(4) + C(C(2)) + 3) \times 94 \\ 423940 &:= (-C(4) + C(C(2)) + 3) \times 940 \\ 4239400 &:= (-C(4) + C(C(2)) + 3) \times 9400 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 42624 &:= (C(4^2 + 6) + C(2)) \times 4 \\ 426240 &:= (C(4^2 + 6) + C(2)) \times 40 \\ 4262400 &:= (C(4^2 + 6) + C(2)) \times 400 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 42871 &:= (-4 + C(28+7)) \times 1 \\ 428710 &:= (-4 + C(28+7)) \times 10 \\ 4287100 &:= (-4 + C(28+7)) \times 100 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 43245 &:= (4 + C(3))^2 \times 45 \\ 432450 &:= (4 + C(3))^2 \times 450 \\ 4324500 &:= (4 + C(3))^2 \times 4500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 43296 &:= (-C(4) + 3 + C(C(2))) \times 96 \\ 432960 &:= (-C(4) + 3 + C(C(2))) \times 960 \\ 4329600 &:= (-C(4) + 3 + C(C(2))) \times 9600 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 43392 &:= C(4) \times 339 \times 2 \\ 433920 &:= C(4) \times 339 \times 20 \\ 4339200 &:= C(4) \times 339 \times 200 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 43569 &:= ((C(4) - C(3)) \times C(5) + C(6)) \times 9 \\ 435690 &:= ((C(4) - C(3)) \times C(5) + C(6)) \times 90 \\ 4356900 &:= ((C(4) - C(3)) \times C(5) + C(6)) \times 900 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 43725 &:= (-4 + C(3 \times 7) - C(C(2))) \times 5 \\ 437250 &:= (-4 + C(3 \times 7) - C(C(2))) \times 50 \\ 4372500 &:= (-4 + C(3 \times 7) - C(C(2))) \times 500 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 43732 &:= (-4 + 3^7 + C(C(3))) \times 2 \\ 437320 &:= (-4 + 3^7 + C(C(3))) \times 20 \\ 4373200 &:= (-4 + 3^7 + C(C(3))) \times 200 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 43912 &:= (4 + C(3 \times 9 + 1)) \times 2 \\ 439120 &:= (4 + C(3 \times 9 + 1)) \times 20 \\ 4391200 &:= (4 + C(3 \times 9 + 1)) \times 200 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}45276 &:= (4 \times 5 + 2) \times C(7) \times 6 \\452760 &:= (4 \times 5 + 2) \times C(7) \times 60 \\4527600 &:= (4 \times 5 + 2) \times C(7) \times 600\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}45375 &:= (-4 + C(5)) \times 375 \\453750 &:= (-4 + C(5)) \times 3750 \\4537500 &:= (-4 + C(5)) \times 37500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}45945 &:= (C(4) + C(5) \times (9 + C(4))) \times 5 \\459450 &:= (C(4) + C(5) \times (9 + C(4))) \times 50 \\4594500 &:= (C(4) + C(5) \times (9 + C(4))) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}46305 &:= C(4 \times 6 - 3) \times 05 \\463050 &:= C(4 \times 6 - 3) \times 050 \\4630500 &:= C(4 \times 6 - 3) \times 0500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}46325 &:= (-4 + C(-6 + C(3)) + C(2)) \times 5 \\463250 &:= (-4 + C(-6 + C(3)) + C(2)) \times 50 \\4632500 &:= (-4 + C(-6 + C(3)) + C(2)) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}46345 &:= (4 + C(-6 + C(3)) + 4) \times 5 \\463450 &:= (4 + C(-6 + C(3)) + 4) \times 50 \\4634500 &:= (4 + C(-6 + C(3)) + 4) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}46557 &:= (-4 + C(6 + 5) \times 5) \times 7 \\465570 &:= (-4 + C(6 + 5) \times 5) \times 70 \\4655700 &:= (-4 + C(6 + 5) \times 5) \times 700\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}47365 &:= (-4 + C(7 \times 3) + C(6)) \times 5 \\473650 &:= (-4 + C(7 \times 3) + C(6)) \times 50 \\4736500 &:= (-4 + C(7 \times 3) + C(6)) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}47775 &:= (4 \times C(7) - 7) \times 7 \times 5 \\477750 &:= (4 \times C(7) - 7) \times 7 \times 50 \\4777500 &:= (4 \times C(7) - 7) \times 7 \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}47924 &:= (C(4 + 7) \times 9 + 2) \times 4 \\479240 &:= (C(4 + 7) \times 9 + 2) \times 40 \\4792400 &:= (C(4 + 7) \times 9 + 2) \times 400\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}48237 &:= (4 \times 8 + C(-C(2) + C(3))) \times 7 \\482370 &:= (4 \times 8 + C(-C(2) + C(3))) \times 70 \\4823700 &:= (4 \times 8 + C(-C(2) + C(3))) \times 700\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}48768 &:= 48 \times (C(7) - C(6)) \times 8 \\487680 &:= 48 \times (C(7) - C(6)) \times 80 \\4876800 &:= 48 \times (C(7) - C(6)) \times 800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}49233 &:= (4^{9-2} + C(3)) \times 3 \\492330 &:= (4^{9-2} + C(3)) \times 30 \\4923300 &:= (4^{9-2} + C(3)) \times 300\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}49275 &:= (-C(4) + C(9) - C(2)) \times 75 \\492750 &:= (-C(4) + C(9) - C(2)) \times 750 \\4927500 &:= (-C(4) + C(9) - C(2)) \times 7500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}49656 &:= 4 \times (9 \times C(6) + C(5)) \times 6 \\496560 &:= 4 \times (9 \times C(6) + C(5)) \times 60 \\4965600 &:= 4 \times (9 \times C(6) + C(5)) \times 600\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}49728 &:= (C(4) \times 97 + C(2)) \times 8 \\497280 &:= (C(4) \times 97 + C(2)) \times 80 \\4972800 &:= (C(4) \times 97 + C(2)) \times 800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}51408 &:= (C(5) + 1) \times 408 \\514080 &:= (C(5) + 1) \times 4080 \\5140800 &:= (C(5) + 1) \times 40800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}51488 &:= (-C(5) + (-1 + 4)^8) \times 8 \\514880 &:= (-C(5) + (-1 + 4)^8) \times 80 \\5148800 &:= (-C(5) + (-1 + 4)^8) \times 800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}52135 &:= (5 - C(21) + C(C(3))) \times 5 \\521350 &:= (5 - C(21) + C(C(3))) \times 50 \\5213500 &:= (5 - C(21) + C(C(3))) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}52299 &:= (-5 + C(2) \times (-2 + C(9))) \times 9 \\522990 &:= (-5 + C(2) \times (-2 + C(9))) \times 90 \\5229900 &:= (-5 + C(2) \times (-2 + C(9))) \times 900\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}52416 &:= (C(5) - C(2)) \times C(4) \times (1 + 6) \\524160 &:= (C(5) - C(2)) \times C(4) \times (10 + 60) \\5241600 &:= (C(5) - C(2)) \times C(4) \times (100 + 600)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}52437 &:= ((C(5) - C(2)) \times C(4) + 3) \times 7 \\524370 &:= ((C(5) - C(2)) \times C(4) + 3) \times 70 \\5243700 &:= ((C(5) - C(2)) \times C(4) + 3) \times 700\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}52479 &:= (5 + C(2) + 4) \times C(7) \times 9 \\524790 &:= (5 + C(2) + 4) \times C(7) \times 90 \\5247900 &:= (5 + C(2) + 4) \times C(7) \times 900\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}52528 &:= (5 + (-2 + 5)^{C(2)}) \times 8 \\525280 &:= (5 + (-2 + 5)^{C(2)}) \times 80 \\5252800 &:= (5 + (-2 + 5)^{C(2)}) \times 800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}52656 &:= (C(5 \times 2) + 6^5) \times 6 \\526560 &:= (C(5 \times 2) + 6^5) \times 60 \\5265600 &:= (C(5 \times 2) + 6^5) \times 600\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}52713 &:= (-5 + C(27 - 1)) \times 3 \\527130 &:= (-5 + C(27 - 1)) \times 30 \\5271300 &:= (-5 + C(27 - 1)) \times 300\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}52743 &:= (5 + C(-2 + 7 \times 4)) \times 3 \\527430 &:= (5 + C(-2 + 7 \times 4)) \times 30 \\5274300 &:= (5 + C(-2 + 7 \times 4)) \times 300\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}53103 &:= (C(5) + C(C(3) - 1)) \times 03 \\531030 &:= (C(5) + C(C(3) - 1)) \times 030 \\5310300 &:= (C(5) + C(C(3) - 1)) \times 0300\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}53133 &:= (5 \times C(3) + C(-1 + C(3))) \times 3 \\531330 &:= (5 \times C(3) + C(-1 + C(3))) \times 30 \\5313300 &:= (5 \times C(3) + C(-1 + C(3))) \times 300\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}53195 &:= (C(-5 + C(3)) - 1 \times 9) \times 5 \\531950 &:= (C(-5 + C(3)) - 1 \times 9) \times 50 \\5319500 &:= (C(-5 + C(3)) - 1 \times 9) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}53235 &:= (C(-5 + C(3)) + 2 - 3) \times 5 \\532350 &:= (C(-5 + C(3)) + 2 - 3) \times 50 \\5323500 &:= (C(-5 + C(3)) + 2 - 3) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}53295 &:= (C(-5 + C(3)) + 2 + 9) \times 5 \\532950 &:= (C(-5 + C(3)) + 2 + 9) \times 50 \\5329500 &:= (C(-5 + C(3)) + 2 + 9) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}53475 &:= (C(-5 + C(3)) + 47) \times 5 \\534750 &:= (C(-5 + C(3)) + 47) \times 50 \\5347500 &:= (C(-5 + C(3)) + 47) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}53488 &:= (C(5) + 3^{C(4)/8}) \times 8 \\534880 &:= (C(5) + 3^{C(4)/8}) \times 80 \\5348800 &:= (C(5) + 3^{C(4)/8}) \times 800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}53649 &:= (C(5) + C(3 \times 6) + 4) \times 9 \\536490 &:= (C(5) + C(3 \times 6) + 4) \times 90 \\5364900 &:= (C(5) + C(3 \times 6) + 4) \times 900\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}54189 &:= (C(5) + C(4) + C(18)) \times 9 \\541890 &:= (C(5) + C(4) + C(18)) \times 90 \\5418900 &:= (C(5) + C(4) + C(18)) \times 900\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}54665 &:= (5^4 + C(6)) \times 65 \\546650 &:= (5^4 + C(6)) \times 650 \\5466500 &:= (5^4 + C(6)) \times 6500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}54675 &:= C(54/6) \times 75 \\546750 &:= C(54/6) \times 750 \\5467500 &:= C(54/6) \times 7500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}54945 &:= (5 \times C(4 + 9) + 4) \times 5 \\549450 &:= (5 \times C(4 + 9) + 4) \times 50 \\5494500 &:= (5 \times C(4 + 9) + 4) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}55245 &:= (5 \times C(5 + C(2)) + C(4)) \times 5 \\552450 &:= (5 \times C(5 + C(2)) + C(4)) \times 50 \\5524500 &:= (5 \times C(5 + C(2)) + C(4)) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}55566 &:= C(5 + 5 + 5 + 6) \times 6 \\555660 &:= C(5 + 5 + 5 + 6) \times 60 \\5556600 &:= C(5 + 5 + 5 + 6) \times 600\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}56175 &:= (C(5) \times 6 - 1) \times 75 \\561750 &:= (C(5) \times 6 - 1) \times 750 \\5617500 &:= (C(5) \times 6 - 1) \times 7500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}56316 &:= (C(5) + C(-6 + C(3))) \times 1 \times 6 \\563160 &:= (C(5) + C(-6 + C(3))) \times 1 \times 60 \\5631600 &:= (C(5) + C(-6 + C(3))) \times 1 \times 600\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}56644 &:= (C(5) - 6)^{6-4} \times 4 \\566440 &:= (C(5) - 6)^{6-4} \times 40 \\5664400 &:= (C(5) - 6)^{6-4} \times 400\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}56775 &:= (C(5) \times 6 + 7) \times 75 \\567750 &:= (C(5) \times 6 + 7) \times 750 \\5677500 &:= (C(5) \times 6 + 7) \times 7500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}56835 &:= (C(5) - C(6) + C(8)) \times C(3) \times 5 \\568350 &:= (C(5) - C(6) + C(8)) \times C(3) \times 50 \\5683500 &:= (C(5) - C(6) + C(8)) \times C(3) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}56844 &:= (-C(5) + (C(6) + 8) \times C(4)) \times 4 \\568440 &:= (-C(5) + (C(6) + 8) \times C(4)) \times 40 \\5684400 &:= (-C(5) + (C(6) + 8) \times C(4)) \times 400\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}57168 &:= (C(5 \times 7) + 1)/6 \times 8 \\571680 &:= (C(5 \times 7) + 1)/6 \times 80 \\5716800 &:= (C(5 \times 7) + 1)/6 \times 800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}57844 &:= (C(5) + 7 \times C(8) \times 4) \times 4 \\578440 &:= (C(5) + 7 \times C(8) \times 4) \times 40 \\5784400 &:= (C(5) + 7 \times C(8) \times 4) \times 400\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}58344 &:= (-5 + C(8 + 3)) \times 44 \\583440 &:= (-5 + C(8 + 3)) \times 440 \\5834400 &:= (-5 + C(8 + 3)) \times 4400\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}58383 &:= (5 + C(8) \times 38) \times 3 \\583830 &:= (5 + C(8) \times 38) \times 30 \\5838300 &:= (5 + C(8) \times 38) \times 300\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}58926 &:= (-5 + C(8 + 9) \times 2) \times 6 \\589260 &:= (-5 + C(8 + 9) \times 2) \times 60 \\5892600 &:= (-5 + C(8 + 9) \times 2) \times 600\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}59332 &:= (-C(5) + C(93/3)) \times 2 \\593320 &:= (-C(5) + C(93/3)) \times 20 \\5933200 &:= (-C(5) + C(93/3)) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}59433 &:= (C(-5 + 9) + C(4) + C(C(3))) \times 3 \\594330 &:= (C(-5 + 9) + C(4) + C(C(3))) \times 30 \\5943300 &:= (C(-5 + 9) + C(4) + C(C(3))) \times 300\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}59564 &:= (-5 - C(9) + 5^6) \times 4 \\595640 &:= (-5 - C(9) + 5^6) \times 40 \\5956400 &:= (-5 - C(9) + 5^6) \times 400\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}59582 &:= C(-5 + 9 + C(-5 + 8)) \times 2 \\595820 &:= C(-5 + 9 + C(-5 + 8)) \times 20 \\5958200 &:= C(-5 + 9 + C(-5 + 8)) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}59633 &:= (-C(-5 + 9) + C(6) + C(C(3))) \times 3 \\596330 &:= (-C(-5 + 9) + C(6) + C(C(3))) \times 30 \\5963300 &:= (-C(-5 + 9) + C(6) + C(C(3))) \times 300\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}60835 &:= C(-60 + 83) \times 5 \\608350 &:= C(-60 + 83) \times 50 \\6083500 &:= C(-60 + 83) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}62304 &:= (C(6) + C(C(2)) \times 30) \times 4 \\623040 &:= (C(6) + C(C(2)) \times 30) \times 40 \\6230400 &:= (C(6) + C(C(2)) \times 30) \times 400\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}62389 &:= (C(6) + C(C(2)) - C(3)) \times 89 \\623890 &:= (C(6) + C(C(2)) - C(3)) \times 890 \\6238900 &:= (C(6) + C(C(2)) - C(3)) \times 8900\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}62391 &:= (6 \times C(C(2)) + C(39)) \times 1 \\623910 &:= (6 \times C(C(2)) + C(39)) \times 10 \\6239100 &:= (6 \times C(C(2)) + C(39)) \times 100\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}62985 &:= (6 \times 2 + C(9)) \times 85 \\629850 &:= (6 \times 2 + C(9)) \times 850 \\6298500 &:= (6 \times 2 + C(9)) \times 8500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}63855 &:= (6 + C(3)) \times (C(8) - C(5)) \times 5 \\638550 &:= (6 + C(3)) \times (C(8) - C(5)) \times 50 \\6385500 &:= (6 + C(3)) \times (C(8) - C(5)) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}64233 &:= (C(6) \times 4 \times 2 + C(C(3))) \times 3 \\642330 &:= (C(6) \times 4 \times 2 + C(C(3))) \times 30 \\6423300 &:= (C(6) \times 4 \times 2 + C(C(3))) \times 300\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}65728 &:= (C(6) + C(5 + 7 + C(2))) \times 8 \\657280 &:= (C(6) + C(5 + 7 + C(2))) \times 80 \\6572800 &:= (C(6) + C(5 + 7 + C(2))) \times 800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}66096 &:= C(6) \times (60 - 9) \times 6 \\660960 &:= C(6) \times (60 - 9) \times 60 \\6609600 &:= C(6) \times (60 - 9) \times 600\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}66528 &:= C(6) \times (6 + 5) \times 28 \\665280 &:= C(6) \times (6 + 5) \times 280 \\6652800 &:= C(6) \times (6 + 5) \times 2800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}67995 &:= (C(6) \times 7 \times 9 - 9) \times 5 \\679950 &:= (C(6) \times 7 \times 9 - 9) \times 50 \\6799500 &:= (C(6) \times 7 \times 9 - 9) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}68315 &:= ((-6 + C(8)) \times C(3) + 1) \times 5 \\683150 &:= ((-6 + C(8)) \times C(3) + 1) \times 50 \\6831500 &:= ((-6 + C(8)) \times C(3) + 1) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}68345 &:= (C(68) - C(3 + C(4))) \times 5 \\683450 &:= (C(68) - C(3 + C(4))) \times 50 \\6834500 &:= (C(68) - C(3 + C(4))) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}68921 &:= C(6 \times 8 - 9 + 2) \times 1 \\689210 &:= C(6 \times 8 - 9 + 2) \times 10 \\6892100 &:= C(6 \times 8 - 9 + 2) \times 100\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}69115 &:= (C(C(6)/9) - 1) \times 1 \times 5 \\691150 &:= (C(C(6)/9) - 1) \times 1 \times 50 \\6911500 &:= (C(C(6)/9) - 1) \times 1 \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}69125 &:= (C(C(6)/9) + 1^2) \times 5 \\691250 &:= (C(C(6)/9) + 1^2) \times 50 \\6912500 &:= (C(C(6)/9) + 1^2) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}69135 &:= (C(C(6)/9) \times 1 + 3) \times 5 \\691350 &:= (C(C(6)/9) \times 1 + 3) \times 50 \\6913500 &:= (C(C(6)/9) \times 1 + 3) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}69145 &:= (C(C(6)/9) + 1 + 4) \times 5 \\691450 &:= (C(C(6)/9) + 1 + 4) \times 50 \\6914500 &:= (C(C(6)/9) + 1 + 4) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}69216 &:= 6 \times (C(9) - C(2)) \times 16 \\692160 &:= 6 \times (C(9) - C(2)) \times 160 \\6921600 &:= 6 \times (C(9) - C(2)) \times 1600\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}69235 &:= (C(C(6)/9) + 23) \times 5 \\692350 &:= (C(C(6)/9) + 23) \times 50 \\6923500 &:= (C(C(6)/9) + 23) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}69345 &:= (C(6) - 9) \times (3 + C(4)) \times 5 \\693450 &:= (C(6) - 9) \times (3 + C(4)) \times 50 \\6934500 &:= (C(6) - 9) \times (3 + C(4)) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}69465 &:= (69 + C(4 \times 6)) \times 5 \\694650 &:= (69 + C(4 \times 6)) \times 50 \\6946500 &:= (69 + C(4 \times 6)) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}69475 &:= (C(C(6)/9) + C(4) + 7) \times 5 \\694750 &:= (C(C(6)/9) + C(4) + 7) \times 50 \\6947500 &:= (C(C(6)/9) + C(4) + 7) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}69912 &:= (-6 + C(9 + 9)) \times 12 \\699120 &:= (-6 + C(9 + 9)) \times 120 \\6991200 &:= (-6 + C(9 + 9)) \times 1200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}69984 &:= (C(6) \times ((9 \times 9) \times (8 - 4))) \\699840 &:= C(6) \times 9 \times 9 \times (80 - 40) \\6998400 &:= C(6) \times 9 \times 9 \times (800 - 400)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}71344 &:= C(7) \times 13 \times 4 \times 4 \\713440 &:= C(7) \times 13 \times 4 \times 40 \\7134400 &:= C(7) \times 13 \times 4 \times 400\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}72966 &:= (C(7 \times 2 + 9) - 6) \times 6 \\729660 &:= (C(7 \times 2 + 9) - 6) \times 60 \\7296600 &:= (C(7 \times 2 + 9) - 6) \times 600\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}73608 &:= (C(7 \times 3) - 60) \times 8 \\736080 &:= (C(7 \times 3) - 60) \times 80 \\7360800 &:= (C(7 \times 3) - 60) \times 800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}73928 &:= (C(-7 + C(3)) + C(9) + C(C(2))) \times 8 \\739280 &:= (C(-7 + C(3)) + C(9) + C(C(2))) \times 80 \\7392800 &:= (C(-7 + C(3)) + C(9) + C(C(2))) \times 800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}73968 &:= (C(7 \times 3) - 9 - 6) \times 8 \\739680 &:= (C(7 \times 3) - 9 - 6) \times 80 \\7396800 &:= (C(7 \times 3) - 9 - 6) \times 800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}73985 &:= (7 \times 3 \times C(9) - C(8)) \times 5 \\739850 &:= (7 \times 3 \times C(9) - C(8)) \times 50 \\7398500 &:= (7 \times 3 \times C(9) - C(8)) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}74888 &:= (C(7) - 4 + C(8)) \times 88 \\748880 &:= (C(7) - 4 + C(8)) \times 880 \\7488800 &:= (C(7) - 4 + C(8)) \times 8800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}75395 &:= (7^5 - C(3 + 9)) \times 5 \\753950 &:= (7^5 - C(3 + 9)) \times 50 \\7539500 &:= (7^5 - C(3 + 9)) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}75565 &:= (-C(C(7 - 5)) + 5^6) \times 5 \\755650 &:= (-C(C(7 - 5)) + 5^6) \times 50 \\7556500 &:= (-C(C(7 - 5)) + 5^6) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}75735 &:= (C(7) - C(5) + C(7)) \times C(3) \times 5 \\757350 &:= (C(7) - C(5) + C(7)) \times C(3) \times 50 \\7573500 &:= (C(7) - C(5) + C(7)) \times C(3) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}75789 &:= 7 \times (5 \times C(7) - C(8)) \times 9 \\757890 &:= 7 \times (5 \times C(7) - C(8)) \times 90 \\7578900 &:= 7 \times (5 \times C(7) - C(8)) \times 900\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}76715 &:= (7 + C(6) \times 71) \times 5 \\767150 &:= (7 + C(6) \times 71) \times 50 \\7671500 &:= (7 + C(6) \times 71) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}76824 &:= (7 \times C(6 + 8) - 2) \times 4 \\768240 &:= (7 \times C(6 + 8) - 2) \times 40 \\7682400 &:= (7 \times C(6 + 8) - 2) \times 400\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}77324 &:= (-C(7) - 7 + C(C(3)) - 2) \times 4 \\773240 &:= (-C(7) - 7 + C(C(3)) - 2) \times 40 \\7732400 &:= (-C(7) - 7 + C(C(3)) - 2) \times 400\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}77362 &:= (C(7 + 7) + C(C(3) + 6)) \times 2 \\773620 &:= (C(7 + 7) + C(C(3) + 6)) \times 20 \\7736200 &:= (C(7 + 7) + C(C(3) + 6)) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}77364 &:= (7 - C(7) + C(C(3)) - 6) \times 4 \\773640 &:= (7 - C(7) + C(C(3)) - 6) \times 40 \\7736400 &:= (7 - C(7) + C(C(3)) - 6) \times 400\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}77952 &:= (-7 + C(7)) \times (-9 + C(5)) \times 2 \\779520 &:= (-7 + C(7)) \times (-9 + C(5)) \times 20 \\7795200 &:= (-7 + C(7)) \times (-9 + C(5)) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}78125 &:= C(7 + (8 + 1) \times 2) \times 5 \\781250 &:= C(7 + (8 + 1) \times 2) \times 50 \\7812500 &:= C(7 + (8 + 1) \times 2) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}79216 &:= (C(7) + 9 \times C(C(2))) \times 16 \\792160 &:= (C(7) + 9 \times C(C(2))) \times 160 \\7921600 &:= (C(7) + 9 \times C(C(2))) \times 1600\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}79233 &:= C(7) \times (9 - 2) \times 33 \\792330 &:= C(7) \times (9 - 2) \times 330 \\7923300 &:= C(7) \times (9 - 2) \times 3300\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}79244 &:= (C(7) + C(9) \times 2) \times 44 \\792440 &:= (C(7) + C(9) \times 2) \times 440 \\7924400 &:= (C(7) + C(9) \times 2) \times 4400\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}79524 &:= (7 + 9 + C(5))^2 \times 4 \\795240 &:= (7 + 9 + C(5))^2 \times 40 \\7952400 &:= (7 + 9 + C(5))^2 \times 400\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}82755 &:= (-C(8)/2 + 7^5) \times 5 \\827550 &:= (-C(8)/2 + 7^5) \times 50 \\8275500 &:= (-C(8)/2 + 7^5) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}82896 &:= (-8 + C(C(-2 + 8)/9)) \times 6 \\828960 &:= (-8 + C(C(-2 + 8)/9)) \times 60 \\8289600 &:= (-8 + C(C(-2 + 8)/9)) \times 600\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}83346 &:= (C(8 \times 3) + 3 + C(4)) \times 6 \\833460 &:= (C(8 \times 3) + 3 + C(4)) \times 60 \\8334600 &:= (C(8 \times 3) + 3 + C(4)) \times 600\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}83349 &:= C(8 + 3 \times 3 + 4) \times 9 \\833490 &:= C(8 + 3 \times 3 + 4) \times 90 \\8334900 &:= C(8 + 3 \times 3 + 4) \times 900\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}83373 &:= (8 + 3 \times C(3 \times 7)) \times 3 \\833730 &:= (8 + 3 \times C(3 \times 7)) \times 30 \\8337300 &:= (8 + 3 \times C(3 \times 7)) \times 300\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}85742 &:= (-8 + C(5 \times 7) + 4) \times 2 \\857420 &:= (-8 + C(5 \times 7) + 4) \times 20 \\8574200 &:= (-8 + C(5 \times 7) + 4) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}85782 &:= (8 + C(5 \times 7) + 8) \times 2 \\857820 &:= (8 + C(5 \times 7) + 8) \times 20 \\8578200 &:= (8 + C(5 \times 7) + 8) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}89373 &:= C(8 \times 9/3 + 7) \times 3 \\893730 &:= C(8 \times 9/3 + 7) \times 30 \\8937300 &:= C(8 \times 9/3 + 7) \times 300\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}91525 &:= (C(9) + C(1 + 5^2)) \times 5 \\915250 &:= (C(9) + C(1 + 5^2)) \times 50 \\9152500 &:= (C(9) + C(1 + 5^2)) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}92125 &:= (C(9) + C(2)) \times 125 \\921250 &:= (C(9) + C(2)) \times 1250 \\9212500 &:= (C(9) + C(2)) \times 12500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}92288 &:= (C(9) - C(2)) \times 2 \times 8 \times 8 \\922880 &:= (C(9) - C(2)) \times 2 \times 8 \times 80 \\9228800 &:= (C(9) - C(2)) \times 2 \times 8 \times 800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}92475 &:= 9 \times (C(C(2)) \times 4 + 7) \times 5 \\924750 &:= 9 \times (C(C(2)) \times 4 + 7) \times 50 \\9247500 &:= 9 \times (C(C(2)) \times 4 + 7) \times 500\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}93322 &:= (C(9 + C(3)) + 3 + 2) \times 2 \\933220 &:= (C(9 + C(3)) + 3 + 2) \times 20 \\9332200 &:= (C(9 + C(3)) + 3 + 2) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}93382 &:= (C(9 + C(3)) + C(3) + 8) \times 2 \\933820 &:= (C(9 + C(3)) + C(3) + 8) \times 20 \\9338200 &:= (C(9 + C(3)) + C(3) + 8) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}93552 &:= (C(9 + C(3)) - 5 + C(5)) \times 2 \\935520 &:= (C(9 + C(3)) - 5 + C(5)) \times 20 \\9355200 &:= (C(9 + C(3)) - 5 + C(5)) \times 200\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}94968 &:= (-9 + (C(4) - 9) \times C(6)) \times 8 \\949680 &:= (-9 + (C(4) - 9) \times C(6)) \times 80 \\9496800 &:= (-9 + (C(4) - 9) \times C(6)) \times 800\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 95395 &:= (-C(9) + C(5) + 3^9) \times 5 \\
 953950 &:= (-C(9) + C(5) + 3^9) \times 50 \\
 9539500 &:= (-C(9) + C(5) + 3^9) \times 500 \\
 \\
 96957 &:= C(9) \times (C(6)/9 - 5) \times 7 \\
 969570 &:= C(9) \times (C(6)/9 - 5) \times 70 \\
 9695700 &:= C(9) \times (C(6)/9 - 5) \times 700 \\
 \\
 97335 &:= ((C(9) - 7) \times C(3) - C(3)) \times 5 \\
 973350 &:= ((C(9) - 7) \times C(3) - C(3)) \times 50 \\
 9733500 &:= ((C(9) - 7) \times C(3) - C(3)) \times 500 \\
 \\
 97524 &:= 9 \times 7 \times (-C(5) + C(C(2))) \times 4 \\
 975240 &:= 9 \times 7 \times (-C(5) + C(C(2))) \times 40 \\
 9752400 &:= 9 \times 7 \times (-C(5) + C(C(2))) \times 400 \\
 \\
 98235 &:= (-9 \times 8/2 + C(C(3))) \times 5 \\
 982350 &:= (-9 \times 8/2 + C(C(3))) \times 50 \\
 9823500 &:= (-9 \times 8/2 + C(C(3))) \times 500 \\
 \\
 98253 &:= (-9 - 8 + C(2^5)) \times 3 \\
 982530 &:= (-9 - 8 + C(2^5)) \times 30 \\
 9825300 &:= (-9 - 8 + C(2^5)) \times 300 \\
 \\
 98355 &:= (-9 - 8 + C(C(3)) + 5) \times 5 \\
 983550 &:= (-9 - 8 + C(C(3)) + 5) \times 50 \\
 9835500 &:= (-9 - 8 + C(C(3)) + 5) \times 500 \\
 \\
 98375 &:= (-9 + 8 + C(C(3)) - 7) \times 5 \\
 983750 &:= (-9 + 8 + C(C(3)) - 7) \times 50 \\
 9837500 &:= (-9 + 8 + C(C(3)) - 7) \times 500 \\
 \\
 98384 &:= (C(9 + 8) + C(C(3))) \times (8 - 4) \\
 983840 &:= (C(9 + 8) + C(C(3))) \times (80 - 40) \\
 9838400 &:= (C(9 + 8) + C(C(3))) \times (800 - 400) \\
 \\
 98425 &:= (C(C(-9 + 8 + 4)) + 2) \times 5 \\
 984250 &:= (C(C(-9 + 8 + 4)) + 2) \times 50 \\
 9842500 &:= (C(C(-9 + 8 + 4)) + 2) \times 500 \\
 \\
 98435 &:= ((9 - 8) \times 4 + C(C(3))) \times 5 \\
 984350 &:= ((9 - 8) \times 4 + C(C(3))) \times 50 \\
 9843500 &:= ((9 - 8) \times 4 + C(C(3))) \times 500 \\
 \\
 98545 &:= (9 \times C(8 + 5) - C(4)) \times 5 \\
 985450 &:= (9 \times C(8 + 5) - C(4)) \times 50 \\
 9854500 &:= (9 \times C(8 + 5) - C(4)) \times 500 \\
 \\
 98784 &:= 9 \times 8 \times C(7) \times (8 - 4) \\
 987840 &:= 9 \times 8 \times C(7) \times (80 - 40) \\
 9878400 &:= 9 \times 8 \times C(7) \times (800 - 400) \\
 \\
 99535 &:= (99 + C(5) + C(C(3))) \times 5 \\
 995350 &:= (99 + C(5) + C(C(3))) \times 50 \\
 9953500 &:= (99 + C(5) + C(C(3))) \times 500
 \end{aligned}$$

3 Cubic-Type Selfie Numbers: Reverse Order of Digits

This section brings **cubic-type selfie numbers** in reverse order of digits up to 5-digits numbers. It is divided in three subsection. The first one give consecutive and symmetric blocks of 10. The second subsection brings symmetric and nonconsecutive blocks, and the third subsection give the general values.

3.1 Symmetric and Consecutive

$$\begin{aligned}
 250 &:= 0 + C(5) \times 2 & 253 &:= 3 + C(5) \times 2 \\
 251 &:= 1 + C(5) \times 2 & 254 &:= 4 + C(5) \times 2 \\
 252 &:= 2 + C(5) \times 2 & 255 &:= 5 + C(5) \times 2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$256 := 6 + C(5) \times 2$$

$$257 := 7 + C(5) \times 2$$

$$258 := 8 + C(5) \times 2$$

$$259 := 9 + C(5) \times 2$$

$$370 := 0 + C(7) + C(3)$$

$$371 := 1 + C(7) + C(3)$$

$$372 := 2 + C(7) + C(3)$$

$$373 := 3 + C(7) + C(3)$$

$$374 := 4 + C(7) + C(3)$$

$$375 := 5 + C(7) + C(3)$$

$$376 := 6 + C(7) + C(3)$$

$$377 := 7 + C(7) + C(3)$$

$$378 := 8 + C(7) + C(3)$$

$$379 := 9 + C(7) + C(3)$$

$$2240 := 0 + C(4 + C(2)) + C(C(2))$$

$$2241 := 1 + C(4 + C(2)) + C(C(2))$$

$$2242 := 2 + C(4 + C(2)) + C(C(2))$$

$$2243 := 3 + C(4 + C(2)) + C(C(2))$$

$$2244 := 4 + C(4 + C(2)) + C(C(2))$$

$$2245 := 5 + C(4 + C(2)) + C(C(2))$$

$$2246 := 6 + C(4 + C(2)) + C(C(2))$$

$$2247 := 7 + C(4 + C(2)) + C(C(2))$$

$$2248 := 8 + C(4 + C(2)) + C(C(2))$$

$$2249 := 9 + C(4 + C(2)) + C(C(2))$$

$$2740 := 0 - 4 + C(7 \times 2)$$

$$2741 := 1 - 4 + C(7 \times 2)$$

$$2742 := 2 - 4 + C(7 \times 2)$$

$$2743 := 3 - 4 + C(7 \times 2)$$

$$2744 := 4 - 4 + C(7 \times 2)$$

$$2745 := 5 - 4 + C(7 \times 2)$$

$$2746 := 6 - 4 + C(7 \times 2)$$

$$2747 := 7 - 4 + C(7 \times 2)$$

$$2748 := 8 - 4 + C(7 \times 2)$$

$$2749 := 9 - 4 + C(7 \times 2)$$

$$3880 := 0 + 8 \times (C(8) - C(3))$$

$$3881 := 1 + 8 \times (C(8) - C(3))$$

$$3882 := 2 + 8 \times (C(8) - C(3))$$

$$3883 := 3 + 8 \times (C(8) - C(3))$$

$$3884 := 4 + 8 \times (C(8) - C(3))$$

$$3885 := 5 + 8 \times (C(8) - C(3))$$

$$3886 := 6 + 8 \times (C(8) - C(3))$$

$$3887 := 7 + 8 \times (C(8) - C(3))$$

$$3888 := 8 + 8 \times (C(8) - C(3))$$

$$3889 := 9 + 8 \times (C(8) - C(3))$$

$$7560 := 0 + C(6) \times 5 \times 7$$

$$7561 := 1 + C(6) \times 5 \times 7$$

$$7562 := 2 + C(6) \times 5 \times 7$$

$$7563 := 3 + C(6) \times 5 \times 7$$

$$7564 := 4 + C(6) \times 5 \times 7$$

$$7565 := 5 + C(6) \times 5 \times 7$$

$$7566 := 6 + C(6) \times 5 \times 7$$

$$7567 := 7 + C(6) \times 5 \times 7$$

$$7568 := 8 + C(6) \times 5 \times 7$$

$$7569 := 9 + C(6) \times 5 \times 7$$

$$01000 := 0 + C(0010)$$

$$01001 := 1 + C(0010)$$

$$01002 := 2 + C(0010)$$

$$01003 := 3 + C(0010)$$

$$01004 := 4 + C(0010)$$

$$01005 := 5 + C(0010)$$

$$01006 := 6 + C(0010)$$

$$01007 := 7 + C(0010)$$

$$01008 := 8 + C(0010)$$

$$01009 := 9 + C(0010)$$

$$01020 := 0 + 20 + C(10)$$

$$01021 := 1 + 20 + C(10)$$

$$01022 := 2 + 20 + C(10)$$

$$01023 := 3 + 20 + C(10)$$

$$01024 := 4 + 20 + C(10)$$

$$01025 := 5 + 20 + C(10)$$

$$01026 := 6 + 20 + C(10)$$

$$01027 := 7 + 20 + C(10)$$

$$01028 := 8 + 20 + C(10)$$

$$01029 := 9 + 20 + C(10)$$

$$01031 := 1 + 30 + C(10)$$

$$01032 := 2 + 30 + C(10)$$

$$01033 := 3 + 30 + C(10)$$

$$01034 := 4 + 30 + C(10)$$

$$01035 := 5 + 30 + C(10)$$

$$01036 := 6 + 30 + C(10)$$

$$01037 := 7 + 30 + C(10)$$

$$01038 := 8 + 30 + C(10)$$

$$01039 := 9 + 30 + C(10)$$

$$01041 := 1 + 40 + C(10)$$

$$01042 := 2 + 40 + C(10)$$

$$01043 := 3 + 40 + C(10)$$

$$01044 := 4 + 40 + C(10)$$

$$01045 := 5 + 40 + C(10)$$

$$01046 := 6 + 40 + C(10)$$

$$01047 := 7 + 40 + C(10)$$

$$01048 := 8 + 40 + C(10)$$

$$01049 := 9 + 40 + C(10)$$

$$01051 := 1 + 50 + C(10)$$

$$01052 := 2 + 50 + C(10)$$

$$01053 := 3 + 50 + C(10)$$

$$01054 := 4 + 50 + C(10)$$

$$01055 := 5 + 50 + C(10)$$

$$01056 := 6 + 50 + C(10)$$

$$01057 := 7 + 50 + C(10)$$

$$01058 := 8 + 50 + C(10)$$

$$01059 := 9 + 50 + C(10)$$

$$01061 := 1 + 60 + C(10)$$

$$01062 := 2 + 60 + C(10)$$

$$01063 := 3 + 60 + C(10)$$

$$01064 := 4 + 60 + C(10)$$

$$01065 := 5 + 60 + C(10)$$

$$01066 := 6 + 60 + C(10)$$

$$01067 := 7 + 60 + C(10)$$

$$01068 := 8 + 60 + C(10)$$

$$01069 := 9 + 60 + C(10)$$

$$01071 := 1 + 70 + C(10)$$

$$01072 := 2 + 70 + C(10)$$

$$01073 := 3 + 70 + C(10)$$

$$01074 := 4 + 70 + C(10)$$

$$01075 := 5 + 70 + C(10)$$

$$01076 := 6 + 70 + C(10)$$

$$01077 := 7 + 70 + C(10)$$

$$01078 := 8 + 70 + C(10)$$

$$01079 := 9 + 70 + C(10)$$

$$01081 := 1 + 80 + C(10)$$

$$01082 := 2 + 80 + C(10)$$

$$01083 := 3 + 80 + C(10)$$

$$01084 := 4 + 80 + C(10)$$

$$01085 := 5 + 80 + C(10)$$

$$01086 := 6 + 80 + C(10)$$

$$01087 := 7 + 80 + C(10)$$

$$01088 := 8 + 80 + C(10)$$

$$01089 := 9 + 80 + C(10)$$

$$01091 := 1 + 90 + C(10)$$

$$01092 := 2 + 90 + C(10)$$

$$01093 := 3 + 90 + C(10)$$

$$01094 := 4 + 90 + C(10)$$

$$01095 := 5 + 90 + C(10)$$

$$01096 := 6 + 90 + C(10)$$

$$01097 := 7 + 90 + C(10)$$

$$01098 := 8 + 90 + C(10)$$

$$01099 := 9 + 90 + C(10)$$

$$01250 := 0 + C(5) \times 2 + C(10)$$

$$01251 := 1 + C(5) \times 2 + C(10)$$

$$01252 := 2 + C(5) \times 2 + C(10)$$

$$01253 := 3 + C(5) \times 2 + C(10)$$

$$01254 := 4 + C(5) \times 2 + C(10)$$

$$01255 := 5 + C(5) \times 2 + C(10)$$

$$01256 := 6 + C(5) \times 2 + C(10)$$

$$01257 := 7 + C(5) \times 2 + C(10)$$

$$01258 := 8 + C(5) \times 2 + C(10)$$

$$01259 := 9 + C(5) \times 2 + C(10)$$

$$01350 := (0 - ((5 \times C(3)) \times (-10)))$$

$$01351 := (1 - ((5 \times C(3)) \times (-10)))$$

$$01352 := (2 - ((5 \times C(3)) \times (-10)))$$

$$\begin{aligned}01354 &:= (4 - ((5 \times C(3)) \times (-10))) \\01355 &:= (5 - ((5 \times C(3)) \times (-10))) \\01356 &:= (6 - ((5 \times C(3)) \times (-10))) \\01357 &:= (7 - ((5 \times C(3)) \times (-10))) \\01358 &:= (8 - ((5 \times C(3)) \times (-10))) \\01359 &:= (9 - ((5 \times C(3)) \times (-10)))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}01370 &:= 0 + C(7) + C(3) + C(10) \\01371 &:= 1 + C(7) + C(3) + C(10) \\01372 &:= 2 + C(7) + C(3) + C(10) \\01373 &:= 3 + C(7) + C(3) + C(10) \\01374 &:= 4 + C(7) + C(3) + C(10) \\01375 &:= 5 + C(7) + C(3) + C(10) \\01376 &:= 6 + C(7) + C(3) + C(10) \\01377 &:= 7 + C(7) + C(3) + C(10) \\01378 &:= 8 + C(7) + C(3) + C(10) \\01379 &:= 9 + C(7) + C(3) + C(10)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}02250 &:= 0 + C(5) \times (-2 + 20) \\02251 &:= 1 + C(5) \times (-2 + 20) \\02252 &:= 2 + C(5) \times (-2 + 20) \\02253 &:= 3 + C(5) \times (-2 + 20) \\02254 &:= 4 + C(5) \times (-2 + 20) \\02255 &:= 5 + C(5) \times (-2 + 20) \\02256 &:= 6 + C(5) \times (-2 + 20) \\02257 &:= 7 + C(5) \times (-2 + 20) \\02258 &:= 8 + C(5) \times (-2 + 20) \\02259 &:= 9 + C(5) \times (-2 + 20)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}02500 &:= 0 + C(05) \times 20 \\02501 &:= 1 + C(05) \times 20 \\02502 &:= 2 + C(05) \times 20 \\02503 &:= 3 + C(05) \times 20 \\02504 &:= 4 + C(05) \times 20 \\02505 &:= 5 + C(05) \times 20 \\02506 &:= 6 + C(05) \times 20 \\02507 &:= 7 + C(05) \times 20 \\02508 &:= 8 + C(05) \times 20 \\02509 &:= 9 + C(05) \times 20\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}02580 &:= 0 + C(8) \times 5 + 20 \\02581 &:= 1 + C(8) \times 5 + 20 \\02582 &:= 2 + C(8) \times 5 + 20 \\02583 &:= 3 + C(8) \times 5 + 20 \\02584 &:= 4 + C(8) \times 5 + 20 \\02585 &:= 5 + C(8) \times 5 + 20 \\02586 &:= 6 + C(8) \times 5 + 20 \\02588 &:= 8 + C(8) \times 5 + 20 \\02589 &:= 9 + C(8) \times 5 + 20 \\02597 &:= 7 + C(8) \times 5 + 20\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}13480 &:= 0 - 8^4 + C(C(3) - 1) \\13481 &:= 1 - 8^4 + C(C(3) - 1) \\13482 &:= 2 - 8^4 + C(C(3) - 1) \\13483 &:= 3 - 8^4 + C(C(3) - 1) \\13484 &:= 4 - 8^4 + C(C(3) - 1) \\13485 &:= 5 - 8^4 + C(C(3) - 1) \\13486 &:= 6 - 8^4 + C(C(3) - 1) \\13487 &:= 7 - 8^4 + C(C(3) - 1) \\13488 &:= 8 - 8^4 + C(C(3) - 1) \\13489 &:= 9 - 8^4 + C(C(3) - 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}14750 &:= 0 + (C(5) - 7) \times C(4 + 1) \\14751 &:= 1 + (C(5) - 7) \times C(4 + 1) \\14752 &:= 2 + (C(5) - 7) \times C(4 + 1) \\14753 &:= 3 + (C(5) - 7) \times C(4 + 1) \\14754 &:= 4 + (C(5) - 7) \times C(4 + 1) \\14755 &:= 5 + (C(5) - 7) \times C(4 + 1) \\14756 &:= 6 + (C(5) - 7) \times C(4 + 1) \\14757 &:= 7 + (C(5) - 7) \times C(4 + 1) \\14758 &:= 8 + (C(5) - 7) \times C(4 + 1) \\14759 &:= 9 + (C(5) - 7) \times C(4 + 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}15250 &:= 0 + C(5) \times (-2 + C(5) - 1) \\15251 &:= 1 + C(5) \times (-2 + C(5) - 1) \\15252 &:= 2 + C(5) \times (-2 + C(5) - 1) \\15253 &:= 3 + C(5) \times (-2 + C(5) - 1) \\15254 &:= 4 + C(5) \times (-2 + C(5) - 1) \\15255 &:= 5 + C(5) \times (-2 + C(5) - 1) \\15256 &:= 6 + C(5) \times (-2 + C(5) - 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}15257 &:= 7 + C(5) \times (-2 + C(5) - 1) \\15258 &:= 8 + C(5) \times (-2 + C(5) - 1) \\15259 &:= 9 + C(5) \times (-2 + C(5) - 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}15500 &:= 0 + C(05) \times (C(5) - 1) \\15501 &:= 1 + C(05) \times (C(5) - 1) \\15502 &:= 2 + C(05) \times (C(5) - 1) \\15503 &:= 3 + C(05) \times (C(5) - 1) \\15504 &:= 4 + C(05) \times (C(5) - 1) \\15505 &:= 5 + C(05) \times (C(5) - 1) \\15506 &:= 6 + C(05) \times (C(5) - 1) \\15507 &:= 7 + C(05) \times (C(5) - 1) \\15508 &:= 8 + C(05) \times (C(5) - 1) \\15509 &:= 9 + C(05) \times (C(5) - 1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}19630 &:= 0 + C(C(3)) - 6 \times 9 + 1 \\19631 &:= 1 + C(C(3)) - 6 \times 9 + 1 \\19632 &:= 2 + C(C(3)) - 6 \times 9 + 1 \\19633 &:= 3 + C(C(3)) - 6 \times 9 + 1 \\19634 &:= 4 + C(C(3)) - 6 \times 9 + 1 \\19635 &:= 5 + C(C(3)) - 6 \times 9 + 1 \\19636 &:= 6 + C(C(3)) - 6 \times 9 + 1 \\19637 &:= 7 + C(C(3)) - 6 \times 9 + 1 \\19638 &:= 8 + C(C(3)) - 6 \times 9 + 1 \\19639 &:= 9 + C(C(3)) - 6 \times 9 + 1\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}21960 &:= 0 + C(C(-6 + 9) + 1) + C(2) \\21961 &:= 1 + C(C(-6 + 9) + 1) + C(2) \\21962 &:= 2 + C(C(-6 + 9) + 1) + C(2) \\21963 &:= 3 + C(C(-6 + 9) + 1) + C(2) \\21964 &:= 4 + C(C(-6 + 9) + 1) + C(2) \\21965 &:= 5 + C(C(-6 + 9) + 1) + C(2) \\21966 &:= 6 + C(C(-6 + 9) + 1) + C(2) \\21967 &:= 7 + C(C(-6 + 9) + 1) + C(2) \\21968 &:= 8 + C(C(-6 + 9) + 1) + C(2) \\21969 &:= 9 + C(C(-6 + 9) + 1) + C(2)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}22440 &:= 0 + 44 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\22441 &:= 1 + 44 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\22442 &:= 2 + 44 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\22443 &:= 3 + 44 \times (-2 + C(C(2)))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}22444 &:= 4 + 44 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\22445 &:= 5 + 44 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\22446 &:= 6 + 44 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\22447 &:= 7 + 44 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\22448 &:= 8 + 44 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\22449 &:= 9 + 44 \times (-2 + C(C(2)))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}22950 &:= 0 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\22951 &:= 1 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\22952 &:= 2 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\22953 &:= 3 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\22954 &:= 4 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\22955 &:= 5 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\22956 &:= 6 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\22957 &:= 7 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\22958 &:= 8 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\22959 &:= 9 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2)))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}23870 &:= 0 - 7 - C(8) + C(C(3) + 2) \\23871 &:= 1 - 7 - C(8) + C(C(3) + 2) \\23872 &:= 2 - 7 - C(8) + C(C(3) + 2) \\23873 &:= 3 - 7 - C(8) + C(C(3) + 2) \\23874 &:= 4 - 7 - C(8) + C(C(3) + 2) \\23875 &:= 5 - 7 - C(8) + C(C(3) + 2) \\23876 &:= 6 - 7 - C(8) + C(C(3) + 2) \\23877 &:= 7 - 7 - C(8) + C(C(3) + 2) \\23878 &:= 8 - 7 - C(8) + C(C(3) + 2) \\23879 &:= 9 - 7 - C(8) + C(C(3) + 2)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}24640 &:= 0 + C(4) + 6 \times C(4^2) \\24641 &:= 1 + C(4) + 6 \times C(4^2) \\24642 &:= 2 + C(4) + 6 \times C(4^2) \\24643 &:= 3 + C(4) + 6 \times C(4^2) \\24644 &:= 4 + C(4) + 6 \times C(4^2) \\24645 &:= 5 + C(4) + 6 \times C(4^2) \\24646 &:= 6 + C(4) + 6 \times C(4^2) \\24647 &:= 7 + C(4) + 6 \times C(4^2) \\24648 &:= 8 + C(4) + 6 \times C(4^2) \\24649 &:= 9 + C(4) + 6 \times C(4^2)\end{aligned}$$

$$24840 := 0 - C(C(4)) - C(8) + C(C(4) + 2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24841 &:= 1 - C(C(4)) - C(8) + C(C(4) + 2) \\ 24842 &:= 2 - C(C(4)) - C(8) + C(C(4) + 2) \\ 24843 &:= 3 - C(C(4)) - C(8) + C(C(4) + 2) \\ 24844 &:= 4 - C(C(4)) - C(8) + C(C(4) + 2) \\ 24845 &:= 5 - C(C(4)) - C(8) + C(C(4) + 2) \\ 24846 &:= 6 - C(C(4)) - C(8) + C(C(4) + 2) \\ 24847 &:= 7 - C(C(4)) - C(8) + C(C(4) + 2) \\ 24848 &:= 8 - C(C(4)) - C(8) + C(C(4) + 2) \\ 24849 &:= 9 - C(C(4)) - C(8) + C(C(4) + 2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26250 &:= 0 + C(5) \times (2 + C(6) - C(2)) \\ 26251 &:= 1 + C(5) \times (2 + C(6) - C(2)) \\ 26252 &:= 2 + C(5) \times (2 + C(6) - C(2)) \\ 26253 &:= 3 + C(5) \times (2 + C(6) - C(2)) \\ 26254 &:= 4 + C(5) \times (2 + C(6) - C(2)) \\ 26255 &:= 5 + C(5) \times (2 + C(6) - C(2)) \\ 26256 &:= 6 + C(5) \times (2 + C(6) - C(2)) \\ 26257 &:= 7 + C(5) \times (2 + C(6) - C(2)) \\ 26258 &:= 8 + C(5) \times (2 + C(6) - C(2)) \\ 26259 &:= 9 + C(5) \times (2 + C(6) - C(2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26350 &:= 0 + (C(5) - 3) \times C(6) - 2 \\ 26351 &:= 1 + (C(5) - 3) \times C(6) - 2 \\ 26352 &:= 2 + (C(5) - 3) \times C(6) - 2 \\ 26353 &:= 3 + (C(5) - 3) \times C(6) - 2 \\ 26354 &:= 4 + (C(5) - 3) \times C(6) - 2 \\ 26355 &:= 5 + (C(5) - 3) \times C(6) - 2 \\ 26356 &:= 6 + (C(5) - 3) \times C(6) - 2 \\ 26357 &:= 7 + (C(5) - 3) \times C(6) - 2 \\ 26358 &:= 8 + (C(5) - 3) \times C(6) - 2 \\ 26359 &:= 9 + (C(5) - 3) \times C(6) - 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 29160 &:= 0 + (6 - 1) \times C(9 \times 2) \\ 29161 &:= 1 + (6 - 1) \times C(9 \times 2) \\ 29162 &:= 2 + (6 - 1) \times C(9 \times 2) \\ 29163 &:= 3 + (6 - 1) \times C(9 \times 2) \\ 29164 &:= 4 + (6 - 1) \times C(9 \times 2) \\ 29165 &:= 5 + (6 - 1) \times C(9 \times 2) \\ 29166 &:= 6 + (6 - 1) \times C(9 \times 2) \\ 29167 &:= 7 + (6 - 1) \times C(9 \times 2) \\ 29168 &:= 8 + (6 - 1) \times C(9 \times 2) \end{aligned}$$

$$29169 := 9 + (6 - 1) \times C(9 \times 2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 31250 &:= 0 + C(5^2) \times (-1 + 3) \\ 31251 &:= 1 + C(5^2) \times (-1 + 3) \\ 31252 &:= 2 + C(5^2) \times (-1 + 3) \\ 31253 &:= 3 + C(5^2) \times (-1 + 3) \\ 31254 &:= 4 + C(5^2) \times (-1 + 3) \\ 31255 &:= 5 + C(5^2) \times (-1 + 3) \\ 31256 &:= 6 + C(5^2) \times (-1 + 3) \\ 31257 &:= 7 + C(5^2) \times (-1 + 3) \\ 31258 &:= 8 + C(5^2) \times (-1 + 3) \\ 31259 &:= 9 + C(5^2) \times (-1 + 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33280 &:= 0 + C(8) + C(2 + 3 + C(3)) \\ 33281 &:= 1 + C(8) + C(2 + 3 + C(3)) \\ 33282 &:= 2 + C(8) + C(2 + 3 + C(3)) \\ 33283 &:= 3 + C(8) + C(2 + 3 + C(3)) \\ 33284 &:= 4 + C(8) + C(2 + 3 + C(3)) \\ 33285 &:= 5 + C(8) + C(2 + 3 + C(3)) \\ 33286 &:= 6 + C(8) + C(2 + 3 + C(3)) \\ 33287 &:= 7 + C(8) + C(2 + 3 + C(3)) \\ 33288 &:= 8 + C(8) + C(2 + 3 + C(3)) \\ 33289 &:= 9 + C(8) + C(2 + 3 + C(3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33750 &:= 0 + C(5) \times (7 + 3) \times C(3) \\ 33751 &:= 1 + C(5) \times (7 + 3) \times C(3) \\ 33752 &:= 2 + C(5) \times (7 + 3) \times C(3) \\ 33753 &:= 3 + C(5) \times (7 + 3) \times C(3) \\ 33754 &:= 4 + C(5) \times (7 + 3) \times C(3) \\ 33755 &:= 5 + C(5) \times (7 + 3) \times C(3) \\ 33756 &:= 6 + C(5) \times (7 + 3) \times C(3) \\ 33757 &:= 7 + C(5) \times (7 + 3) \times C(3) \\ 33758 &:= 8 + C(5) \times (7 + 3) \times C(3) \\ 33759 &:= 9 + C(5) \times (7 + 3) \times C(3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34240 &:= 0 - C(4) + C(C(2)) \times (C(4) + 3) \\ 34241 &:= 1 - C(4) + C(C(2)) \times (C(4) + 3) \\ 34242 &:= 2 - C(4) + C(C(2)) \times (C(4) + 3) \\ 34243 &:= 3 - C(4) + C(C(2)) \times (C(4) + 3) \\ 34244 &:= 4 - C(4) + C(C(2)) \times (C(4) + 3) \\ 34245 &:= 5 - C(4) + C(C(2)) \times (C(4) + 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}34246 &:= 6 - C(4) + C(C(2)) \times (C(4) + 3) \\34247 &:= 7 - C(4) + C(C(2)) \times (C(4) + 3) \\34248 &:= 8 - C(4) + C(C(2)) \times (C(4) + 3) \\34249 &:= 9 - C(4) + C(C(2)) \times (C(4) + 3)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}39280 &:= 0 + 8 \times (C(C(2)) + 9) - 3 \\39281 &:= 1 + 8 \times (C(C(2)) + 9) - 3 \\39282 &:= 2 + 8 \times (C(C(2)) + 9) - 3 \\39283 &:= 3 + 8 \times (C(C(2)) + 9) - 3 \\39284 &:= 4 + 8 \times (C(C(2)) + 9) - 3 \\39285 &:= 5 + 8 \times (C(C(2)) + 9) - 3 \\39286 &:= 6 + 8 \times (C(C(2)) + 9) - 3 \\39287 &:= 7 + 8 \times (C(C(2)) + 9) - 3 \\39288 &:= 8 + 8 \times (C(C(2)) + 9) - 3 \\39289 &:= 9 + 8 \times (C(C(2)) + 9) - 3\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}39330 &:= 0 + C(C(3)) + C(C(3)) - 9 - C(3) \\39331 &:= 1 + C(C(3)) + C(C(3)) - 9 - C(3) \\39332 &:= 2 + C(C(3)) + C(C(3)) - 9 - C(3) \\39333 &:= 3 + C(C(3)) + C(C(3)) - 9 - C(3) \\39334 &:= 4 + C(C(3)) + C(C(3)) - 9 - C(3) \\39335 &:= 5 + C(C(3)) + C(C(3)) - 9 - C(3) \\39336 &:= 6 + C(C(3)) + C(C(3)) - 9 - C(3) \\39337 &:= 7 + C(C(3)) + C(C(3)) - 9 - C(3) \\39338 &:= 8 + C(C(3)) + C(C(3)) - 9 - C(3) \\39339 &:= 9 + C(C(3)) + C(C(3)) - 9 - C(3)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}39430 &:= 0 + C(C(3)) + C(4) + C(9 \times 3) \\39431 &:= 1 + C(C(3)) + C(4) + C(9 \times 3) \\39432 &:= 2 + C(C(3)) + C(4) + C(9 \times 3) \\39433 &:= 3 + C(C(3)) + C(4) + C(9 \times 3) \\39434 &:= 4 + C(C(3)) + C(4) + C(9 \times 3) \\39435 &:= 5 + C(C(3)) + C(4) + C(9 \times 3) \\39436 &:= 6 + C(C(3)) + C(4) + C(9 \times 3) \\39437 &:= 7 + C(C(3)) + C(4) + C(9 \times 3) \\39438 &:= 8 + C(C(3)) + C(4) + C(9 \times 3) \\39439 &:= 9 + C(C(3)) + C(4) + C(9 \times 3)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}43750 &:= 0 + C(5) \times (C(7) + 3 + 4) \\43751 &:= 1 + C(5) \times (C(7) + 3 + 4) \\43752 &:= 2 + C(5) \times (C(7) + 3 + 4)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}43753 &:= 3 + C(5) \times (C(7) + 3 + 4) \\43754 &:= 4 + C(5) \times (C(7) + 3 + 4) \\43755 &:= 5 + C(5) \times (C(7) + 3 + 4) \\43756 &:= 6 + C(5) \times (C(7) + 3 + 4) \\43757 &:= 7 + C(5) \times (C(7) + 3 + 4) \\43758 &:= 8 + C(5) \times (C(7) + 3 + 4) \\43759 &:= 9 + C(5) \times (C(7) + 3 + 4)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}46640 &:= 0 + (4 + C(6)) \times (C(6) - 4) \\46641 &:= 1 + (4 + C(6)) \times (C(6) - 4) \\46642 &:= 2 + (4 + C(6)) \times (C(6) - 4) \\46643 &:= 3 + (4 + C(6)) \times (C(6) - 4) \\46644 &:= 4 + (4 + C(6)) \times (C(6) - 4) \\46645 &:= 5 + (4 + C(6)) \times (C(6) - 4) \\46646 &:= 6 + (4 + C(6)) \times (C(6) - 4) \\46647 &:= 7 + (4 + C(6)) \times (C(6) - 4) \\46648 &:= 8 + (4 + C(6)) \times (C(6) - 4) \\46649 &:= 9 + (4 + C(6)) \times (C(6) - 4)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}49750 &:= 0 + C(5) \times (C(7) - 9 + C(4)) \\49751 &:= 1 + C(5) \times (C(7) - 9 + C(4)) \\49752 &:= 2 + C(5) \times (C(7) - 9 + C(4)) \\49753 &:= 3 + C(5) \times (C(7) - 9 + C(4)) \\49754 &:= 4 + C(5) \times (C(7) - 9 + C(4)) \\49755 &:= 5 + C(5) \times (C(7) - 9 + C(4)) \\49756 &:= 6 + C(5) \times (C(7) - 9 + C(4)) \\49757 &:= 7 + C(5) \times (C(7) - 9 + C(4)) \\49758 &:= 8 + C(5) \times (C(7) - 9 + C(4)) \\49759 &:= 9 + C(5) \times (C(7) - 9 + C(4))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}52340 &:= 0 - 4 \times (C(C(3)) - C(2^5)) \\52341 &:= 1 - 4 \times (C(C(3)) - C(2^5)) \\52342 &:= 2 - 4 \times (C(C(3)) - C(2^5)) \\52343 &:= 3 - 4 \times (C(C(3)) - C(2^5)) \\52344 &:= 4 - 4 \times (C(C(3)) - C(2^5)) \\52345 &:= 5 - 4 \times (C(C(3)) - C(2^5)) \\52346 &:= 6 - 4 \times (C(C(3)) - C(2^5)) \\52347 &:= 7 - 4 \times (C(C(3)) - C(2^5)) \\52348 &:= 8 - 4 \times (C(C(3)) - C(2^5)) \\52349 &:= 9 - 4 \times (C(C(3)) - C(2^5))\end{aligned}$$

$$53240 := 0 + C((C(4) + 2)/3) \times 5$$

$$53241 := 1 + C((C(4) + 2)/3) \times 5$$

$$53242 := 2 + C((C(4) + 2)/3) \times 5$$

$$53243 := 3 + C((C(4) + 2)/3) \times 5$$

$$53244 := 4 + C((C(4) + 2)/3) \times 5$$

$$53245 := 5 + C((C(4) + 2)/3) \times 5$$

$$53246 := 6 + C((C(4) + 2)/3) \times 5$$

$$53247 := 7 + C((C(4) + 2)/3) \times 5$$

$$53248 := 8 + C((C(4) + 2)/3) \times 5$$

$$53249 := 9 + C((C(4) + 2)/3) \times 5$$

$$53250 := 0 + 5 \times (2 + C(C(3) - 5))$$

$$53251 := 1 + 5 \times (2 + C(C(3) - 5))$$

$$53252 := 2 + 5 \times (2 + C(C(3) - 5))$$

$$53253 := 3 + 5 \times (2 + C(C(3) - 5))$$

$$53254 := 4 + 5 \times (2 + C(C(3) - 5))$$

$$53255 := 5 + 5 \times (2 + C(C(3) - 5))$$

$$53256 := 6 + 5 \times (2 + C(C(3) - 5))$$

$$53257 := 7 + 5 \times (2 + C(C(3) - 5))$$

$$53258 := 8 + 5 \times (2 + C(C(3) - 5))$$

$$53259 := 9 + 5 \times (2 + C(C(3) - 5))$$

$$53460 := 0 + (C(6) + 4) \times 3^5$$

$$53461 := 1 + (C(6) + 4) \times 3^5$$

$$53462 := 2 + (C(6) + 4) \times 3^5$$

$$53463 := 3 + (C(6) + 4) \times 3^5$$

$$53464 := 4 + (C(6) + 4) \times 3^5$$

$$53465 := 5 + (C(6) + 4) \times 3^5$$

$$53466 := 6 + (C(6) + 4) \times 3^5$$

$$53467 := 7 + (C(6) + 4) \times 3^5$$

$$53468 := 8 + (C(6) + 4) \times 3^5$$

$$53469 := 9 + (C(6) + 4) \times 3^5$$

$$57230 := 0 + (C(3) - C(C(2))) \times (7 - C(5))$$

$$57231 := 1 + (C(3) - C(C(2))) \times (7 - C(5))$$

$$57232 := 2 + (C(3) - C(C(2))) \times (7 - C(5))$$

$$57233 := 3 + (C(3) - C(C(2))) \times (7 - C(5))$$

$$57234 := 4 + (C(3) - C(C(2))) \times (7 - C(5))$$

$$57235 := 5 + (C(3) - C(C(2))) \times (7 - C(5))$$

$$57236 := 6 + (C(3) - C(C(2))) \times (7 - C(5))$$

$$57237 := 7 + (C(3) - C(C(2))) \times (7 - C(5))$$

$$57238 := 8 + (C(3) - C(C(2))) \times (7 - C(5))$$

$$57239 := 9 + (C(3) - C(C(2))) \times (7 - C(5))$$

$$61440 := 0 + C(C(4))/4 - C(16)$$

$$61441 := 1 + C(C(4))/4 - C(16)$$

$$61442 := 2 + C(C(4))/4 - C(16)$$

$$61443 := 3 + C(C(4))/4 - C(16)$$

$$61444 := 4 + C(C(4))/4 - C(16)$$

$$61445 := 5 + C(C(4))/4 - C(16)$$

$$61446 := 6 + C(C(4))/4 - C(16)$$

$$61447 := 7 + C(C(4))/4 - C(16)$$

$$61448 := 8 + C(C(4))/4 - C(16)$$

$$61449 := 9 + C(C(4))/4 - C(16)$$

$$62250 := 0 + C(5) \times (C(C(2)) - C(2) - 6)$$

$$62251 := 1 + C(5) \times (C(C(2)) - C(2) - 6)$$

$$62252 := 2 + C(5) \times (C(C(2)) - C(2) - 6)$$

$$62253 := 3 + C(5) \times (C(C(2)) - C(2) - 6)$$

$$62254 := 4 + C(5) \times (C(C(2)) - C(2) - 6)$$

$$62255 := 5 + C(5) \times (C(C(2)) - C(2) - 6)$$

$$62256 := 6 + C(5) \times (C(C(2)) - C(2) - 6)$$

$$62257 := 7 + C(5) \times (C(C(2)) - C(2) - 6)$$

$$62258 := 8 + C(5) \times (C(C(2)) - C(2) - 6)$$

$$62259 := 9 + C(5) \times (C(C(2)) - C(2) - 6)$$

$$62720 := 0 + C(C(2)) + C(72)/6$$

$$62721 := 1 + C(C(2)) + C(72)/6$$

$$62722 := 2 + C(C(2)) + C(72)/6$$

$$62723 := 3 + C(C(2)) + C(72)/6$$

$$62724 := 4 + C(C(2)) + C(72)/6$$

$$62725 := 5 + C(C(2)) + C(72)/6$$

$$62726 := 6 + C(C(2)) + C(72)/6$$

$$62727 := 7 + C(C(2)) + C(72)/6$$

$$62728 := 8 + C(C(2)) + C(72)/6$$

$$62729 := 9 + C(C(2)) + C(72)/6$$

$$63250 := 0 + C(5) \times (C(2^3) - 6)$$

$$63251 := 1 + C(5) \times (C(2^3) - 6)$$

$$63252 := 2 + C(5) \times (C(2^3) - 6)$$

$$63253 := 3 + C(5) \times (C(2^3) - 6)$$

$$\begin{aligned}63254 &:= 4 + C(5) \times (C(2^3) - 6) \\63255 &:= 5 + C(5) \times (C(2^3) - 6) \\63256 &:= 6 + C(5) \times (C(2^3) - 6) \\63257 &:= 7 + C(5) \times (C(2^3) - 6) \\63258 &:= 8 + C(5) \times (C(2^3) - 6) \\63259 &:= 9 + C(5) \times (C(2^3) - 6)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}64250 &:= 0 + C(5) \times (C(C(2)) - 4 + 6) \\64251 &:= 1 + C(5) \times (C(C(2)) - 4 + 6) \\64252 &:= 2 + C(5) \times (C(C(2)) - 4 + 6) \\64253 &:= 3 + C(5) \times (C(C(2)) - 4 + 6) \\64254 &:= 4 + C(5) \times (C(C(2)) - 4 + 6) \\64255 &:= 5 + C(5) \times (C(C(2)) - 4 + 6) \\64256 &:= 6 + C(5) \times (C(C(2)) - 4 + 6) \\64257 &:= 7 + C(5) \times (C(C(2)) - 4 + 6) \\64258 &:= 8 + C(5) \times (C(C(2)) - 4 + 6) \\64259 &:= 9 + C(5) \times (C(C(2)) - 4 + 6)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}65320 &:= 0 + C(C(2)) \times (3 + C(5)) - C(6) \\65321 &:= 1 + C(C(2)) \times (3 + C(5)) - C(6) \\65322 &:= 2 + C(C(2)) \times (3 + C(5)) - C(6) \\65323 &:= 3 + C(C(2)) \times (3 + C(5)) - C(6) \\65324 &:= 4 + C(C(2)) \times (3 + C(5)) - C(6) \\65325 &:= 5 + C(C(2)) \times (3 + C(5)) - C(6) \\65326 &:= 6 + C(C(2)) \times (3 + C(5)) - C(6) \\65327 &:= 7 + C(C(2)) \times (3 + C(5)) - C(6) \\65328 &:= 8 + C(C(2)) \times (3 + C(5)) - C(6) \\65329 &:= 9 + C(C(2)) \times (3 + C(5)) - C(6)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}72360 &:= 0 - 6^3 \times (C(2) - C(7)) \\72361 &:= 1 - 6^3 \times (C(2) - C(7)) \\72362 &:= 2 - 6^3 \times (C(2) - C(7)) \\72363 &:= 3 - 6^3 \times (C(2) - C(7)) \\72364 &:= 4 - 6^3 \times (C(2) - C(7)) \\72365 &:= 5 - 6^3 \times (C(2) - C(7)) \\72366 &:= 6 - 6^3 \times (C(2) - C(7)) \\72367 &:= 7 - 6^3 \times (C(2) - C(7)) \\72368 &:= 8 - 6^3 \times (C(2) - C(7)) \\72369 &:= 9 - 6^3 \times (C(2) - C(7))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}75680 &:= 0 + C(8) + C(6) \times (5 + C(7)) \\75681 &:= 1 + C(8) + C(6) \times (5 + C(7)) \\75682 &:= 2 + C(8) + C(6) \times (5 + C(7)) \\75683 &:= 3 + C(8) + C(6) \times (5 + C(7)) \\75684 &:= 4 + C(8) + C(6) \times (5 + C(7)) \\75685 &:= 5 + C(8) + C(6) \times (5 + C(7)) \\75686 &:= 6 + C(8) + C(6) \times (5 + C(7)) \\75687 &:= 7 + C(8) + C(6) \times (5 + C(7)) \\75688 &:= 8 + C(8) + C(6) \times (5 + C(7)) \\75689 &:= 9 + C(8) + C(6) \times (5 + C(7))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}79850 &:= 0 - C((C(5) - C(8))/9) + C(7) \\79851 &:= 2 - C((C(5) - C(8))/9) + C(7) \\79852 &:= 3 - C((C(5) - C(8))/9) + C(7) \\79853 &:= 4 - C((C(5) - C(8))/9) + C(7) \\79854 &:= 5 - C((C(5) - C(8))/9) + C(7) \\79855 &:= 6 - C((C(5) - C(8))/9) + C(7) \\79856 &:= 7 - C((C(5) - C(8))/9) + C(7) \\79857 &:= 8 - C((C(5) - C(8))/9) + C(7) \\79858 &:= 9 - C((C(5) - C(8))/9) + C(7) \\79859 &:= 0 - C((C(5) - C(8))/9) + C(7)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}87880 &:= 0 - (8 + C(8)) \times (C(7) - C(8)) \\87881 &:= 1 - (8 + C(8)) \times (C(7) - C(8)) \\87882 &:= 2 - (8 + C(8)) \times (C(7) - C(8)) \\87883 &:= 3 - (8 + C(8)) \times (C(7) - C(8)) \\87884 &:= 4 - (8 + C(8)) \times (C(7) - C(8)) \\87885 &:= 5 - (8 + C(8)) \times (C(7) - C(8)) \\87886 &:= 6 - (8 + C(8)) \times (C(7) - C(8)) \\87887 &:= 7 - (8 + C(8)) \times (C(7) - C(8)) \\87888 &:= 8 - (8 + C(8)) \times (C(7) - C(8)) \\87889 &:= 9 - (8 + C(8)) \times (C(7) - C(8))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}91250 &:= 0 + C(5) \times (2 - 1 + C(9)) \\91251 &:= 1 + C(5) \times (2 - 1 + C(9)) \\91252 &:= 2 + C(5) \times (2 - 1 + C(9)) \\91253 &:= 3 + C(5) \times (2 - 1 + C(9)) \\91254 &:= 4 + C(5) \times (2 - 1 + C(9)) \\91255 &:= 5 + C(5) \times (2 - 1 + C(9)) \\91256 &:= 6 + C(5) \times (2 - 1 + C(9)) \\91257 &:= 7 + C(5) \times (2 - 1 + C(9))\end{aligned}$$

$$91258 := 8 + C(5) \times (2 - 1 + C(9))$$

$$91259 := 9 + C(5) \times (2 - 1 + C(9))$$

$$93750 := 0 + C(5) \times (7 \times 3 + C(9))$$

$$93751 := 1 + C(5) \times (7 \times 3 + C(9))$$

$$93752 := 2 + C(5) \times (7 \times 3 + C(9))$$

$$93753 := 3 + C(5) \times (7 \times 3 + C(9))$$

$$93754 := 4 + C(5) \times (7 \times 3 + C(9))$$

$$93755 := 5 + C(5) \times (7 \times 3 + C(9))$$

$$93756 := 6 + C(5) \times (7 \times 3 + C(9))$$

$$93757 := 7 + C(5) \times (7 \times 3 + C(9))$$

$$93758 := 8 + C(5) \times (7 \times 3 + C(9))$$

$$93759 := 9 + C(5) \times (7 \times 3 + C(9))$$

$$95320 := 0 - C(C(2)) + C(C(3) - 5) \times 9$$

$$95321 := 1 - C(C(2)) + C(C(3) - 5) \times 9$$

$$95322 := 2 - C(C(2)) + C(C(3) - 5) \times 9$$

$$95323 := 3 - C(C(2)) + C(C(3) - 5) \times 9$$

$$95324 := 4 - C(C(2)) + C(C(3) - 5) \times 9$$

$$95325 := 5 - C(C(2)) + C(C(3) - 5) \times 9$$

$$95326 := 6 - C(C(2)) + C(C(3) - 5) \times 9$$

$$95327 := 7 - C(C(2)) + C(C(3) - 5) \times 9$$

$$95328 := 8 - C(C(2)) + C(C(3) - 5) \times 9$$

$$95329 := 9 - C(C(2)) + C(C(3) - 5) \times 9$$

$$97340 := 0 + 4 + C(37 + 9)$$

$$97341 := 1 + 4 + C(37 + 9)$$

$$97342 := 2 + 4 + C(37 + 9)$$

$$97343 := 3 + 4 + C(37 + 9)$$

$$97344 := 4 + 4 + C(37 + 9)$$

$$97345 := 5 + 4 + C(37 + 9)$$

$$97346 := 6 + 4 + C(37 + 9)$$

$$97347 := 7 + 4 + C(37 + 9)$$

$$97348 := 8 + 4 + C(37 + 9)$$

$$97349 := 9 + 4 + C(37 + 9)$$

3.2 Symmetric and Nonconsecutive

$$01101 := 101 + C(10)$$

$$01111 := 111 + C(10)$$

$$01121 := 121 + C(10)$$

$$01131 := 131 + C(10)$$

$$01141 := 141 + C(10)$$

$$01151 := 151 + C(10)$$

$$01161 := 161 + C(10)$$

$$01171 := 171 + C(10)$$

$$01181 := 181 + C(10)$$

$$01191 := 191 + C(10)$$

$$01202 := 202 + C(10)$$

$$01212 := 212 + C(10)$$

$$01222 := 222 + C(10)$$

$$01232 := 232 + C(10)$$

$$01242 := 242 + C(10)$$

$$01252 := 252 + C(10)$$

$$01262 := 262 + C(10)$$

$$01272 := 272 + C(10)$$

$$01282 := 282 + C(10)$$

$$01292 := 292 + C(10)$$

$$01303 := 303 + C(10)$$

$$01313 := 313 + C(10)$$

$$01323 := 323 + C(10)$$

$$01333 := 333 + C(10)$$

$$01343 := 343 + C(10)$$

$$01353 := 353 + C(10)$$

$$01363 := 363 + C(10)$$

$$01373 := 373 + C(10)$$

$$01383 := 383 + C(10)$$

$$01393 := 393 + C(10)$$

$$01404 := 404 + C(10)$$

$$01414 := 414 + C(10)$$

$$01424 := 424 + C(10)$$

$$01434 := 434 + C(10)$$

$$01444 := 444 + C(10)$$

$$01454 := 454 + C(10)$$

$$01464 := 464 + C(10)$$

$$01474 := 474 + C(10)$$

01484 := 484 + C(10)
01494 := 494 + C(10)
01505 := 505 + C(10)
01515 := 515 + C(10)
01525 := 525 + C(10)
01535 := 535 + C(10)
01545 := 545 + C(10)
01555 := 555 + C(10)
01565 := 565 + C(10)
01575 := 575 + C(10)
01585 := 585 + C(10)
01595 := 595 + C(10)
01606 := 606 + C(10)
01616 := 616 + C(10)
01626 := 626 + C(10)
01636 := 636 + C(10)
01646 := 646 + C(10)
01656 := 656 + C(10)
01666 := 666 + C(10)
01676 := 676 + C(10)
01686 := 686 + C(10)
01696 := 696 + C(10)
01707 := 707 + C(10)
01717 := 717 + C(10)
01727 := 727 + C(10)
01737 := 737 + C(10)
01747 := 747 + C(10)
01757 := 757 + C(10)
01767 := 767 + C(10)
01777 := 777 + C(10)
01787 := 787 + C(10)
01797 := 797 + C(10)
01808 := 808 + C(10)
01818 := 818 + C(10)
01828 := 828 + C(10)
01838 := 838 + C(10)
01848 := 848 + C(10)
01858 := 858 + C(10)
01868 := 868 + C(10)
01878 := 878 + C(10)

01888 := 888 + C(10)
01898 := 898 + C(10)
01909 := 909 + C(10)
01919 := 919 + C(10)
01929 := 929 + C(10)
01939 := 939 + C(10)
01949 := 949 + C(10)
01959 := 959 + C(10)
01969 := 969 + C(10)
01979 := 979 + C(10)
01989 := 989 + C(10)
01999 := 999 + C(10)

02500 := 00 + C(5) × 20
02511 := 11 + C(5) × 20
02522 := 22 + C(5) × 20
02533 := 33 + C(5) × 20
02544 := 44 + C(5) × 20
02555 := 55 + C(5) × 20
02566 := 66 + C(5) × 20
02577 := 77 + C(5) × 20
02588 := 88 + C(5) × 20
02599 := 99 + C(5) × 20

15500 := 00 + C(5) × (C(5) - 1)
15511 := 11 + C(5) × (C(5) - 1)
15522 := 22 + C(5) × (C(5) - 1)
15533 := 33 + C(5) × (C(5) - 1)
15544 := 44 + C(5) × (C(5) - 1)
15555 := 55 + C(5) × (C(5) - 1)
15566 := 66 + C(5) × (C(5) - 1)
15577 := 77 + C(5) × (C(5) - 1)
15588 := 88 + C(5) × (C(5) - 1)
15599 := 99 + C(5) × (C(5) - 1)

2704 := -40 + C(7 × 2)
2713 := -31 + C(7 × 2)
2722 := -22 + C(7 × 2)
2731 := -13 + C(7 × 2)

36007 := 70 + C(06 + C(3))
36018 := 81 + C(06 + C(3))
36029 := 92 + C(06 + C(3))

$$\begin{aligned} 97340 &:= 04 + C(37 + 9) \\ 97351 &:= 15 + C(37 + 9) \\ 97362 &:= 26 + C(37 + 9) \\ 97373 &:= 37 + C(37 + 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 97384 &:= 48 + C(37 + 9) \\ 97395 &:= 59 + C(37 + 9) \end{aligned}$$

3.3 General Representations

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** written in terms of **cubic function** given in (4) in **reverse order of digits**. The whole work is up to 5-digits. The numbers given below contains lot of extra brackets " $()$ ". These can be removed easily after simplifications.

$$\begin{aligned} 135 &:= (5 \times C((3 \times 1))) & 0285 &:= (C(5) + (8 \times 20)) \\ 163 &:= ((C(3) \times 6) + 1) & 0326 &:= ((-C(6)) + C(C(2))) + (30)) \\ 224 &:= (C((4 + 2)) + C(2)) & 0347 &:= (C(7) + (4 + (3 \times 0))) \\ 226 &:= ((C(6) + 2) + C(2)) & 0367 &:= (C(7) - ((6 - 30))) \\ 232 &:= ((2 + C(3)) \times C(2)) & 0395 &:= (C(5) + (9 \times 30)) \\ 243 &:= (C(3) + C((4 + 2))) & 0562 &:= (C((2 + 6)) + (50)) \\ 283 &:= (C(3) + (C(8)/2)) & 0568 &:= (C(8) + (6 + 50)) \\ 316 &:= (C((6 + 1)) - C(3)) & 0729 &:= C((9 + ((2^7) \times 0))) \\ 317 &:= ((C(7) + 1) - C(3)) & 0809 &:= (C(9) - (0 - 80)) \\ 324 &:= ((4 + C(2)) \times C(3)) & 0864 &:= (4 \times C((6 + (8 \times 0)))) \\ 337 &:= (C(7) - (3 + 3)) & 0875 &:= (C(5) \times (7 + (8 \times 0))) \\ 407 &:= (C(7) + C(04)) & & \\ 448 &:= ((8 \times C(4)) - C(4)) & 1022 &:= (2 \times (C(C(2)) - 01)) \\ 458 &:= (C(8) - (54)) & 1115 &:= -((C((5 + 1)) - C(11))) \\ 512 &:= C(((2 + 1) + 5)) & 1116 &:= -(((C(6) - 1) - C(11))) \\ 517 &:= (C((7 + 1)) + (5)) & 1125 &:= (C(5) \times (-2 - 11)) \\ 518 &:= (C(8) + (1 + 5)) & 1216 &:= (C(6) + C(((1 + C(2)) + 1))) \\ 522 &:= (C(C(2)) + (2 \times 5)) & 1238 &:= ((C(8) - 3) + C((C(2) + 1))) \\ 549 &:= (-9) \times (C(4) - C(5)) & 1239 &:= (((C(9) - 3) + C(C(2))) + 1) \\ 568 &:= -((C(8) - (C(6) \times 5))) & 1255 &:= (-5) \times ((C(5) \times (-2)) - 1) \\ 585 &:= ((C(5) - 8) \times 5) & 1285 &:= (-5) \times ((C(8)/(-2)) - 1) \\ 597 &:= ((-7) + C(9)) - C(5) & 1296 &:= (C(6) \times ((9 - 2) - 1)) \\ 639 &:= (-9) + (3 \times C(6)) & 1322 &:= ((-C(2)) + C((C(2) + 3))) - 1) \\ 655 &:= (5 \times (C(5) + (6))) & 1323 &:= (C((3 + C(2))) - C((3 - 1))) \\ 729 &:= (C(9) \times (C(2) - (7))) & 1325 &:= ((-5) + C((C(2) + 3))) - 1) \\ 736 &:= (C((6 + 3)) + (7)) & 1326 &:= ((-6) + C((C(2) + 3))) + 1) \\ 739 &:= (C(9) + (3 + 7)) & 1329 &:= (C((9 + 2)) - (3 - 1)) \\ 991 &:= (C((1 + 9)) - 9) & 1331 &:= C(((13 - 3) + 1)) \\ & & 1332 &:= (C(((2^3) + 3)) + 1) \\ 0235 &:= (5 \times (C(3) + (20))) & 1359 &:= (9 \times ((C(5) + C(3)) - 1)) \\ 0263 &:= ((C(3) + C(6)) + (20)) & & \end{aligned}$$

- 1371** := $(-1) - (C(7) \times (-(3+1)))$
1372 := $((2 \times C(7)) \times (3-1))$
1374 := $((4 \times C(7)) + (3-1))$
1375 := $(C(5) \times ((7+3)+1))$
1394 := $-((C(4) + (C(9) \times (-(3-1))))))$
1456 := $(C((6+5)) + C((4+1)))$
1459 := $((C(9) + C((5+4))) + 1)$
1499 := $((C(9) + C(9)) + 41)$
1512 := $((C(2) - 1) \times C((5+1)))$
1532 := $((C(C(2)) \times 3) - (5-1))$
1533 := $(3 \times (C((3+5)) - 1))$
1547 := $(C((7+4)) + C((5+1)))$
1576 := $((C(6) \times 7) + C((5-1)))$
1625 := $(C(5) \times ((2 \times 6) + 1))$
1647 := $(C((7-4)) \times 61)$
1664 := $((C(4) - C((6+6))) \times (-1))$
1672 := $(C(2) \times (-7) + C((6 \times 1)))$
1674 := $(C((4+7)) + C((6+1)))$
1714 := $((4+1) \times C(7) - 1)$
1715 := $(5 \times C(((1+7)-1)))$
1716 := $((6-1) \times C(7) + 1)$
1721 := $(C(12) - (7 \times 1))$
1724 := $(-4) + C((2 \times (7-1)))$
1725 := $(-5) \times (-2) - C((7 \times 1))$
1727 := $(C(((7-2)+7)) - 1)$
1728 := $C(((8/2)+7)+1)$
1729 := $(C(9) + C(((2+7)+1)))$
1734 := $(C((4 \times 3)) + (7-1))$
1735 := $(-5) \times ((-3) - C(7) - 1)$
1752 := $(2 \times ((C(5) \times 7) + 1))$
1863 := $(C(3) \times (68+1))$
1875 := $(C(5) \times ((7+8) \times 1))$
1926 := $((C(6) - 2) \times (9 \times 1))$
1962 := $((-2) - C(6)) \times (-9 \times 1)$
1967 := $((C(7) \times 6) - (91))$
2044 := $(-4) + (4 \times C(C(02)))$
2125 := $(C(5) \times ((C(2) + 1) + C(2)))$
2163 := $((C(C(3)) - C(6)) / (1 + C(2)))$
2169 := $((C(9) - (6)) \times (1+2))$
2185 := $(C((5+8)) - 12)$
2193 := $(3 \times (C(9) + (1 \times 2)))$
2194 := $(C((4+9)) - (1+2))$
2195 := $(C(((5+9)-1)) - 2)$
2197 := $C((((7+9)-1)-2))$
2205 := $(C((5+C(02))) + C(2))$
2213 := $(-((C(3) - C(12))) + C(C(2)))$
2232 := $(C((C(2) + (3 \times 2))) - C(C(2)))$
2257 := $(-C(7) - (-5) \times (C(2) + C(C(2))))$
2259 := $(9 \times (-5) + (2^{C(2)}))$
2276 := $((6 \times 7)^2 + C(C(2)))$
2296 := $((-((C(6) + 9)) + C(C(2))) \times C(2))$
2297 := $(-7) - (-9) \times (2^{C(2)})$
2335 := $(-C(5) + ((3 - C(C(3))) / (-C(2))))$
2345 := $(-5) \times (43 - C(C(2)))$
2347 := $((7^4) - (C(3) \times 2))$
2368 := $((C(8) - (6^3)) \times C(2))$
2375 := $(C(5) \times ((7 \times 3) - 2))$
2377 := $((C(7) \times 7) - (3 \times C(2)))$
2385 := $(5 \times ((C(8) - C(3)) - C(2)))$
2432 := $((C(2) - C(3)) \times C(4) \times (-2))$
2448 := $(C(8) + ((44^2)))$
2453 := $((C(C(3)) + (5 - C(4))) / C(2))$
2455 := $(-C(5) - (-5) \times (4 + C(C(2))))$
2456 := $((6^5) / 4 + C(C(2)))$
2464 := $((C(4) - (6^4)) \times (-2))$
2495 := $(-5) \times ((9+4) - C(C(2)))$
2502 := $(20 \times C(5) + 2)$
2522 := $((C(2) - C(C(2))) \times (-5) + 2)$
2525 := $(-5) \times ((2+5) - C(C(2)))$
2527 := $((7 - C(C(2))) \times (-5) + 2)$
2528 := $((C(8) - C(2)) \times 5 + C(2))$
2533 := $(-((3^3)) - (-5) \times C(C(2)))$
2537 := $((C(7) - 3) + C((5 + C(2))))$
2542 := $((C(C(2)) - (4)) \times 5 + 2)$
2544 := $(-((4 \times 4)) - (-5) \times C(C(2)))$
2547 := $((C(7) + C(4)) \times 5 + C(C(2)))$
2548 := $((C(8) - (4)) \times 5 + C(2))$
2555 := $(-5) \times ((5/5) - C(C(2)))$
2561 := $((1^6) - (-5) \times C(C(2)))$

$$\begin{aligned} 2562 &:= ((C((2+6)) \times 5) + 2) \\ 2563 &:= (-((3-6) - (-5) \times C(C(2)))) \\ 2565 &:= (-5) \times (-((6-5) - C(C(2)))) \\ 2568 &:= ((C(C((8-6))) \times 5) + C(2)) \\ 2583 &:= (((3+C(8)) \times 5) + C(2)) \\ 2584 &:= -((((C(4) - C(8)) + C(5)) \times C(2))) \\ 2585 &:= ((5 \times C(8)) + ((5^2))) \\ 2587 &:= (((7+C(8)) \times 5) - C(2)) \\ 2624 &:= (C(4) - ((C(C(2)) \times (-6)) + C(C(2)))) \\ 2647 &:= (C(7) + (C(4) \times (6^2))) \\ 2654 &:= ((4 - C((5+6))) \times (-2)) \\ 2655 &:= (C(5) + (-5) \times (6 - C(C(2)))) \\ 2656 &:= (-6) + (C((5+6)) \times 2) \\ 2674 &:= ((C((4+7)) + (6)) \times 2) \\ 2676 &:= ((C(6) + (7)) \times (6 \times 2)) \\ 2685 &:= ((C(5) - (C(8) \times (-6))) - C(C(2))) \\ 2693 &:= (((3 \times C(9)) - (6)) + C(C(2))) \\ 2695 &:= (-5) \times (-C((9-6)) - C(C(2))) \\ 2699 &:= ((C(9) \times (9-6)) + C(C(2))) \\ 2724 &:= (-4) + ((-2) + C(7)) \times C(2) \\ 2728 &:= (-((8 \times 2)) + C((7 \times 2))) \\ 2736 &:= (C(((6/3) \times 7)) - C(2)) \\ 2752 &:= (C(2) + C(((5+7) + 2))) \\ 2759 &:= ((C((9+5)) + (7)) + C(2)) \\ 2773 &:= ((C(3) + C((7+7))) + 2) \\ 2784 &:= ((C(4) \times 87)/2) \\ 2826 &:= (C((6+C(2))) + (82)) \\ 2852 &:= -((C(C(2)) - ((58^2)))) \\ 2856 &:= (-((C(6) - (5 \times C(8)))) + C(C(2))) \\ 2872 &:= (((C(2) + C(7)) + 8) \times C(2)) \\ 2875 &:= (C(5) \times (7 + (8 \times 2))) \\ 2912 &:= (C(2) \times ((-1) + C(9))/2) \\ 2914 &:= ((4 \times C((1 \times 9))) - 2) \\ 2924 &:= (((-4) + C(2)) \times C(9)) + C(2) \\ 2944 &:= (C(4) \times (C(4) - ((9 \times 2)))) \\ 2948 &:= ((8-4) \times (C(9) + C(2))) \\ 2968 &:= ((C(8) + (C(6) \times 9)) + C(C(2))) \\ 2969 &:= (((-9) \times C(6)) + C((9+C(2)))) \\ 2976 &:= (-6) \times ((7+9) - C(C(2))) \\ 3015 &:= ((-5) - C(10)) \times (-3) \\ 3157 &:= -((C(7) + (C(5) \times (-1) - C(3)))) \\ 3159 &:= (((-9) + C(5)) + 1) \times C(3) \\ 3259 &:= ((C((9+5)) + C(C(2))) + 3) \\ 3264 &:= (C(4) \times ((6 \times C(2)) + 3)) \\ 3276 &:= (-6) \times ((-7) - C(C(2))) - C(3) \\ 3289 &:= (C(9) + (C(8) \times (2+3))) \\ 3321 &:= (123 \times C(3)) \\ 3329 &:= ((-C(9)) - C((-2) + C(3))) + C(C(3)) \\ 3348 &:= (C(((8+4) + 3)) - C(3)) \\ 3351 &:= (((-1) + C(5)) \times C(3)) + 3 \\ 3369 &:= (C((9+6)) - (3+3)) \\ 3372 &:= (((C(2) + (7))^3) - 3) \\ 3448 &:= (-8) + ((C(4) + C(4)) \times C(3)) \\ 3472 &:= (C(2) \times ((C(7) + C(4)) + C(3))) \\ 3483 &:= ((C((3 \times 8))/4) + C(3)) \\ 3527 &:= (C((7+C(2))) + (C(5) + C(3))) \\ 3572 &:= (C(2) + ((7+C(5)) \times C(3))) \\ 3577 &:= (-7) + (7 \times C((5+3))) \\ 3584 &:= ((C(4) - C(8)) \times (-5+3)) \\ 3591 &:= ((-((1-9)) + C(5)) \times C(3)) \\ 3592 &:= -((C(C(2)) - (C(9) + C((5 \times 3)))) \\ 3625 &:= (C(5) \times (26+3)) \\ 3645 &:= ((C(5) + (4+6)) \times C(3)) \\ 3648 &:= (8 \times ((C(4) - C(6)) \times (-3))) \\ 3653 &:= (((C(C(3)) \times 5) + C(6))/C(3)) \\ 3685 &:= (-5) \times (-8) - C((6+3)) \\ 3744 &:= (-4) \times (C(4) - C((7+3))) \\ 3848 &:= (8 \times ((-4) + C(8)) - C(3)) \\ 3875 &:= (C(5) \times (7 + (8 \times 3))) \\ 3925 &:= (C((5+C(2))) + C((9+3))) \\ 3942 &:= (2 \times ((C(4) + 9) \times C(3))) \\ 4123 &:= (C(3) + C((2+14))) \\ 4128 &:= (8 \times (C(C(2)) + (1 \times 4))) \\ 4161 &:= ((C(16) + 1) + C(4)) \\ 4224 &:= ((C(4) \times 2) + C((2^4))) \\ 4225 &:= ((C(5) + C((C(2) + C(2)))) + (4)) \\ 4275 &:= (5 \times (C(7) + C((2 \times 4)))) \\ 4285 &:= ((C(5) + C((8 \times 2))) + C(4)) \\ 4288 &:= (8 \times (C(8) + (24))) \\ 4329 &:= (9 \times (C(C(2)) - (C(3) + (4)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 4368 &:= ((8 \times 6) \times (C(3) + C(4))) & 5829 &:= (C((9 \times 2)) - (8 - 5)) \\ 4392 &:= ((C(2) \times 9) \times (-3) + C(4)) & 5832 &:= C(((2 + 3) + 8) + 5) \\ 4396 &:= ((6 \times (C(9) + 3)) + (4)) & 5837 &:= (C(((7 + 3) + 8)) + (5)) \\ 4416 &:= (((6 - 1) + C(4)) \times C(4)) & 5875 &:= (C(5) \times (7 + (8 \times 5))) \\ 4522 &:= (2 \times (C((C(2) + (5)))) + C(4)) & 5899 &:= (((9 + C(9)) \times 8) - (5)) \\ 4528 &:= (8 \times (C(C(2)) + 54)) & 5945 &:= (5 \times (C(4) - (-9) \times C(5))) \\ 4536 &:= (6 \times (C(3) + C((5 + 4)))) & 5957 &:= (C(((7 - 5) \times 9)) + C(5)) \\ 4589 &:= ((9 \times (C(8) + (5))) - C(4)) & 5974 &:= (-4) - (-7) \times (C(9) + C(5))) \\ 4612 &:= (C(C(2)) + (C(16) + (4))) & 5985 &:= ((C(5) + 8) \times (9 \times 5)) \\ 4657 &:= -((C(7) + (-5) \times C((6 + 4)))) & 6012 &:= ((-2) - C(10)) \times (-6) \\ 4694 &:= (((C(4) + C(9)) \times 6) - C(4)) & 6264 &:= (((C(4) - (6))/2) \times C(6)) \\ 4697 &:= (7 \times ((C(9) + (6)) - C(4))) & 6344 &:= (C((4 + 4)) + C((3 \times 6))) \\ 4829 &:= ((C(9) + C((2 \times 8))) + (4)) & 6348 &:= ((C(8) + (4)) + C((3 \times 6))) \\ 4833 &:= ((C(C(3))/3) - C((8 + 4))) & 6399 &:= (9 \times (C(9) - ((3 \times 6)))) \\ 4837 &:= (((-C(7)) + C(C(3))) + 8)/4 & 6453 &:= -((C(C(3)) - (((C(5) - (4)) \times C(6)))) \\ 4849 &:= (C((9 + (C(4)/8))) - C(4)) & 6456 &:= (((C(6) \times 5) - (4)) \times 6) \\ 4864 &:= ((C(4) - C(6)) \times (-8 \times 4)) & 6552 &:= ((C(2) - C(5)) \times (-56)) \\ 4875 &:= (C(5) \times (7 + (8 \times 4))) & 6643 &:= (C(-((C(3) - 46))) - C(6)) \\ 4889 &:= ((C(9) + C((8 + 8))) + C(4)) & 6732 &:= (C(-((C(2) - C(3)))) - ((C(7) - C(6)))) \\ 4913 &:= C(((3 + 1) + 9) + 4) & 6783 &:= (C((C(3) - 8)) - (76)) \\ 4917 &:= (C(((7 + 1) + 9)) + (4)) & 6853 &:= (C(((C(3) + C(5))/8)) - (6)) \\ 4941 &:= (C(14) + C((9 + 4))) & 6859 &:= C((9 + (5 \times (8 - 6)))) \\ 4948 &:= (((C(8) - (4)) + C(9)) \times 4) & 6865 &:= (C(((5 + 6) + 8)) + (6)) \\ 4964 &:= ((C(C(-((4 - 6)))) + (C(9))) \times 4) & 6875 &:= (C(5) \times (7 + (8 \times 6))) \\ 4967 &:= (((C(7) + C(6)) \times 9) - C(4)) & 6952 &:= ((C(C(2)) \times (5 + 9)) - C(6)) \\ 5125 &:= (((5 \times C(2)) + 1) \times C(5)) & 6966 &:= (((C(6) + C(6)) + C(9)) \times 6) \\ 5129 &:= (C((9 + C(2))) + (C((1 + 5)))) & 7168 &:= (C(8) \times ((6 + 1) + 7)) \\ 5242 &:= -((C(2) - (42 \times C(5)))) & 7182 &:= (2 \times ((C(8) + 1) \times 7)) \\ 5245 &:= ((C(5) \times 42) - (5)) & 7224 &:= ((4 + C(C(2))) \times (2 \times 7)) \\ 5324 &:= (4 \times C(((2 \times 3) + 5))) & 7372 &:= (C(C(2)) + ((-7) + C(3)) \times C(7)) \\ 5376 &:= ((6 \times 7) \times (3 + C(5))) & 7488 &:= (-C(8) + C(-((8 - (4 \times 7)))) \\ 5445 &:= ((C(5) - (4)) \times 45) & 7538 &:= (-8) + ((C(3) - (5)) \times C(7)) \\ 5621 &:= ((1 - C(C(2))) \times (-6 + 5)) & 7546 &:= (-6) + (C(4) \times (C(5) - (7))) \\ 5626 &:= (-6) - (C(C(2)) \times (-6 + 5)) & 7875 &:= (C(5) \times ((7 \times 8) + 7)) \\ 5632 &:= (C(2^3)) \times (6 + 5) & 7937 &:= (C((-7) + C(3)) - ((9 \times 7))) \\ 5642 &:= ((-2) + C(4)) \times (C(6) - C(5)) & 8125 &:= (C(5) + C((2 + 18))) \\ 5762 &:= (C(C(2)) - (-((6 \times 7)) \times C(5)) & 8216 &:= (C(6) + C((12 + 8))) \\ 5819 &:= (((C(9) - 1) \times 8) - (5)) & 8224 &:= ((4^2) \times (2 + C(8))) \\ 5824 &:= ((-C(4)) + C(C(2))) \times (8 + 5) & 8237 &:= (C((7 \times 3)) - (2 \times C(8))) \\ 5827 &:= ((C((7 + 2)) \times 8) - (5)) & 8376 &:= ((-6) - C(7)) \times (-3 \times 8) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 8583 &:= ((C((C(3) + 8))/5) + 8) \\ 8675 &:= (-5) \times (-7) + (C(6) \times (-8))) \\ 8712 &:= (C(2) - (-17) \times C(8)) \\ 8875 &:= (C(5) \times (7 + (8 \times 8))) \\ 8936 &:= ((C(6) \times 39) + C(8)) \\ 9252 &:= (C(((C(2) + 5)) + C(2))) - 9) \\ 9261 &:= C(((1 \times 6) \times 2) + 9) \\ 9288 &:= (((C(8) + C(8)) + C(2)) \times 9) \\ 9317 &:= (7 \times C(-((1 - 3) - 9))) \\ 9396 &:= ((C((6 + 9)) \times 3) - C(9)) \\ 9425 &:= ((5 + C(2)) \times (-4) + C(9)) \\ 9477 &:= ((77 - C(4)) \times C(9)) \\ 9549 &:= (-9) \times (C(4) + (C(5) \times (-9))) \\ 9625 &:= (C(5) \times (C(2) + 69)) \\ 9639 &:= ((C((9 + 3)) \times 6) - C(9)) \\ 9657 &:= ((7 + (-5) \times C(6)) \times (-9)) \\ 9773 &:= (C((3 \times 7)) + C(C(-((7 - 9)))))) \\ 9822 &:= (2 \times (-2) + C((8 + 9))) \\ 9823 &:= (-3) + (2 \times C((8 + 9))) \\ 9826 &:= ((-6) + C(2)) \times C((8 + 9)) \\ 9832 &:= (2 \times (3 + C((8 + 9)))) \\ 9872 &:= (C(2) \times ((-7) + C(8)) + C(9)) \\ 9875 &:= (C(5) \times (7 + (8 \times 9))) \\ 9928 &:= (C((8 \times 2)) + C((9 + 9))) \\ \\ 00157 &:= -((C(7) - ((5 \times 100))) \\ 00248 &:= ((C(8) - C(4)) - 200) \\ 00347 &:= (C(7) + (4 + (3 \times 00))) \\ 00475 &:= ((C(5) \times 7) - (400)) \\ 00729 &:= C((9 + ((2^7) \times 00))) \\ 00864 &:= (4 \times C((6 + (8 \times 00)))) \\ 00875 &:= (C(5) \times (7 + (8 \times 00))) \\ 01125 &:= (C(5) \times (-((2 - 1) - 10))) \\ 01126 &:= ((6 \times 21) + C(10)) \\ 01135 &:= ((5 \times C(3)) + C((1 \times 10))) \\ 01142 &:= (C(C(2)) + ((C(4) - 1) \times 10)) \\ 01152 &:= (C(C(2)) + (C((5 - 1)) \times 10)) \\ 01153 &:= ((3 \times 51) + C(10)) \\ 01163 &:= (((C(3) \times 6) + 1) + C(10)) \\ 01224 &:= ((C((4 + 2)) + C(2)) + C(10)) \\ 01226 &:= (((C(6) + 2) + C(2)) + C(10)) \\ 01229 &:= ((C(9) + C(C(2))) - (2 + 10)) \\ \\ 01236 &:= (6 \times (C((3 \times 2)) - 10)) \\ 01243 &:= ((C(3) + C((4 + 2))) + C(10)) \\ 01283 &:= (C(3) - ((C(8)/(-2)) - C(10))) \\ 01289 &:= (((9 + 8)^2) + C(10)) \\ 01321 &:= (C((C((1 \times 2)) + 3)) - 10) \\ 01324 &:= (((4 + C(2)) \times C(3)) + C(10)) \\ 01335 &:= (-5) \times (3 - (C(3) \times 10)) \\ 01337 &:= ((C(7) - (3 + 3)) + C(10)) \\ 01338 &:= (C((8 + 3)) - ((3 - 10))) \\ 01341 &:= (C((14 - 3)) + 10) \\ 01344 &:= (C(4) \times ((4 + C(3)) - 10)) \\ 01367 &:= (C(7) + ((6/3)^{10})) \\ 01375 &:= (C(5) \times ((7 \times 3) - 10)) \\ 01385 &:= ((C(5) \times (8 + 3)) + 10) \\ 01387 &:= ((7 \times C(8)) - C((3 + 10))) \\ 01407 &:= ((C(7) + C(04)) + C(10)) \\ 01448 &:= (((8 \times C(4)) - C(4)) + C(10)) \\ 01458 &:= ((C(8) - (54)) + C(10)) \\ 01488 &:= -((C(8) + (-((8/4)) \times C(10)))) \\ 01522 &:= (C(C(2)) + ((2 \times 5) + C(10))) \\ 01549 &:= ((-9) \times (C(4) - C(5))) + C(10) \\ 01568 &:= -((C(8) - ((C(6) \times 5) + C(10)))) \\ 01585 &:= (((5 + C(8)) \times 5) - C(10)) \\ 01593 &:= (C(3) \times (9 + (5 \times 10))) \\ 01596 &:= (-6) \times ((C(9) + 5) - C(10)) \\ 01597 &:= (((-7) + C(9)) - C(5)) + C(10) \\ 01628 &:= -((C(8) - ((2 - C(6)) \times (-10)))) \\ 01639 &:= (-9) + ((3 \times C(6)) + C(10)) \\ 01645 &:= (C(5) + ((C(4) - C(6)) \times (-10))) \\ 01648 &:= (C((8/4)) \times (C(6) - 10)) \\ 01655 &:= (5 \times (C((5 + 6)) - C(10))) \\ 01657 &:= -((C(7) - (C(5) \times (6 + 10)))) \\ 01664 &:= (C(4) \times ((6 \times 6) - 10)) \\ 01668 &:= ((8 \times C(6)) - (6 \times 10)) \\ 01675 &:= ((5 \times (C(7) - (6))) - 10) \\ 01688 &:= ((8 \times 86) + C(10)) \\ 01705 &:= ((5 \times C(07)) - 10) \\ 01736 &:= ((C((6 + 3)) + (7)) + C(10)) \\ 01738 &:= (C(((8 - 3) + 7)) + 10) \\ 01739 &:= ((C(9) + C((3 + 7))) + 10) \\ 01744 &:= (((4 + 4) \times C(7)) - C(10)) \\ 01745 &:= (-5) \times ((4 - C(7)) - 10) \end{aligned}$$

- 01764** := $(-4) \times ((C(6) + C(7)) - C(10))$
01874 := $((4 \times C(7)) + C(8)) - 10$
01924 := $((-4) \times (-2) - C(9)) - C(10)$
01928 := $(8 \times (C(C(2)) + (C(9) - C(10))))$
01943 := $(C(3) - ((-4) \times C(9)) + C(10))$
01944 := $((C((C(4) - 4)) \times 9) / C(10))$
01973 := $-((C(3) + ((7 - 9) \times C(10))))$
02157 := $-((C(7) - (C(5) \times (1 \times 20))))$
02176 := $(C((6 + 7)) - (1 + 20))$
02177 := $(C(((7 + 7) - 1)) - (20))$
02263 := $-(((C(C(3)) + 6) - C((C(2) + (20))))))$
02269 := $-((C(C((9 - 6))) - C((C(2) + (20))))))$
02357 := $-((C(7) - ((5 \times C(3)) \times 20))$
02389 := $(C(9) + (83 \times 20))$
02455 := $-((C(5) - ((C(5) + 4) \times 20))$
02492 := $-((C(2) - (C((9 - 4) \times 20))$
02495 := $(-5) + (C((9 - 4) \times 20))$
02512 := $-((C(2) + ((-1) - C(5)) \times 20))$
02515 := $(-5) - ((-1) - C(5)) \times 20$
02545 := $(C(5) + ((4 - C(5)) \times (-20))$
02568 := $(8 \times ((C(6) + C(5)) - (20))$
02576 := $(C(6) - ((7 - C(5)) \times 20))$
02737 := $(-7) + C((C(3) + ((7 - 20))))$
02744 := $C(((4/4) - 7) + 20)$
02764 := $(-(4^6) - (C(7) \times (-20))$
02788 := $((8 \times (8 + C(7))) - (20))$
02852 := $(C(C(2)) + ((C(5) - 8) \times 20))$
02857 := $-((C(7) + (C((5 \times 8)) / (-20))))$
02935 := $((5 \times 3) \times C(9)) - C(20)$
02943 := $(C(3) + (4 \times C((9 + (2 \times 0))))$
03226 := $((C((6 + C(2))) + C(C(2))) - (30))$
03268 := $(86 \times (C(2) + (30)))$
03286 := $((C((6 + 8)) + C(C(2))) + (30))$
03426 := $((C(6) \times 2^4) - (30))$
03453 := $((C(3) \times (C(5) + 4)) - (30))$
03458 := $((8 + C(5)) \times (-4 - 30))$
03469 := $((C((9 + 6)) + C(4)) + (30))$
03486 := $((6 \times (C(8) + C(4))) + (30))$
03526 := $-(((C(6) + C(2)) - (C(5) \times 30)))$
03557 := $-((C(7) + ((5 + C(5)) \times (-30))))$
03562 := $-((C(2) + ((6 - C(5)) \times 30))$
03565 := $(-5) - ((6 - C(5)) \times 30)$
03723 := $(-C(3) - (C(-(2 - 7))) \times (-30))$
03756 := $(C(6) - ((C(5) - 7) \times (-30))$
03928 := $(8 \times (C(C(2)) + ((9 - 30))))$
03963 := $((C((C(3) + 6)) / 9) - (30))$
04113 := $(3 \times (C(11) + 40))$
04125 := $-((C(5) \times (C(2) - (1 + 40))))$
04394 := $(C((4 + 9)) + C(-(C(3) - 40)))$
04396 := $((6 \times (C(9) - 3)) + 40)$
04537 := $-((C(7) - ((3 - C(5)) \times (-40))))$
04575 := $(-5) \times ((-7) \times C(5) - 40)$
04762 := $((C(2) + 6) \times C(7) - 40)$
04855 := $-((C((5 \times 5)) + (C(8) \times (-40))))$
04864 := $((C(4) - C(6)) \times (8 - 40))$
04873 := $((C((C(3) + 7)) / 8) - 40)$
04875 := $(C(5) \times ((7 - 8) + 40))$
04913 := $C(((3 \times 19) - 40))$
04924 := $((4 \times (C(C(2)) + (C(9)))) - 40)$
04953 := $(C(((3 + 5) + 9)) + 40)$
05184 := $(C(4) \times (81 + (5 \times 0)))$
05244 := $((C(C(4)) + ((C(4) - C(2)))) / 50)$
05395 := $(5 \times (C(9) + (350)))$
05424 := $(-C(4) + (2 \times C((C(4) - 50))))$
05521 := $-((C((1 + C(2))) + (C(5) \times (-50))))$
05529 := $-(((C(9) - C(2)) + (C(5) \times (-50))))$
05697 := $((-7) \times C(9) + (C(6) \times 50))$
05789 := $((C(9) \times 8) + ((7 - 50)))$
05882 := $(C(((2 + 8) + 8)) + (50))$
06292 := $((2 + 9) \times (C(C(2)) + (60)))$
06384 := $(-4) \times ((C(8) \times (-3)) - (60))$
06655 := $(5 \times C(((5 + 6) + (6 \times 0))))$
06919 := $(C(((9 + 1) + 9)) + (60))$
06952 := $-((C(2) - ((C(5) - 9) \times 60))$
06955 := $(-5) + ((C(5) - 9) \times 60)$
07192 := $(C(2) \times (C(9) + 170))$
07435 := $-((C(5) + (C(3) \times (-4 \times 70))))$
07657 := $-((C(7) + (C(5) \times (6 - 70))))$
07894 := $(C(4) + (9 \times 870))$
08064 := $(C(4) + C(-(60 - 80)))$
08352 := $(C(C(2)) - ((C(5) - C(3)) \times (-80)))$
08545 := $((5 + C(4)) \times C(5) - (80))$
08575 := $((5 \times C(7)) \times (5 + (8 \times 0)))$
08658 := $((8 - C(5)) \times (6 - 80))$
09263 := $(C((C(3) - 6)) + (2 + (9 \times 0)))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 09351 &:= (C(-((1+5)) + C(3))) + (90)) \\
 09387 &:= (((C(7) + 8) \times C(3)) - (90)) \\
 09863 &:= (C((C(3) - (6))) + (C(8) + (90))) \\
 \\
 10125 &:= (C(5) \times ((C(2) \times 10) + 1)) \\
 10221 &:= (((1 - C(C(2))) \times (-20)) + 1) \\
 10245 &:= (-5) \times ((-4) \times C(C(2))) - 01)) \\
 10248 &:= (8 \times ((C(4) \times 20) + 1)) \\
 10522 &:= ((C(22) - C(5)) - 01) \\
 10639 &:= (-9) + C((C(3) - (6 - 01))) \\
 10647 &:= (C(((7 \times 4) - 6)) - 01) \\
 10648 &:= (8 \times C(((4 + 6) + 01))) \\
 10653 &:= (C((C(3) - (5))) + (6 - 01)) \\
 10875 &:= (C(5) \times ((7 + 80) \times 1)) \\
 10935 &:= ((5 \times 3) \times C((9 \times 01))) \\
 11011 &:= (1 + C(10)) \times 11 \\
 11025 &:= ((C(5) - (20))^{1+1}) \\
 11125 &:= (C(5) \times ((C(2) \times 11) + 1)) \\
 11224 &:= ((C(4) + C(C(2))) + C((2 \times 11))) \\
 11235 &:= (((C(5) + C(C(3)))/2) + (C(11))) \\
 11253 &:= (((C(3) - (5)) \times C(C(2))) - 11) \\
 11264 &:= (((4 \times 6) - 2) \times C(C((1 + 1)))) \\
 11285 &:= ((C(5) + C(8)) + C((2 \times 11))) \\
 11348 &:= ((C(8) + C((-4) + C(3))) - (C(11))) \\
 11392 &:= (C(2) \times (93 + C(11))) \\
 11439 &:= ((-C(9)) + C((C(3) - (4)))) + (1 \times 1)) \\
 11584 &:= -(C(4) + (-8) \times (C(5) + C(11))) \\
 11637 &:= (C((7 \times 3)) + (C(6) \times 11)) \\
 11648 &:= ((-8) + C(4)) \times (C(6) - C((1 + 1))) \\
 11663 &:= ((C(3) \times (C(6) + C(6))) - (1 \times 1)) \\
 11664 &:= (C(((4 \times 6) - 6)) \times (1 + 1)) \\
 11683 &:= (C(C(3)) - (C((8 + (6 \times (1 + 1)))))) \\
 11718 &:= ((8 - 1) \times (C(7) + C(11))) \\
 11773 &:= (C((C(3) - (7))) + (C(7) \times 11)) \\
 11791 &:= (-1) - ((C(9) + C(7)) \times (-11)) \\
 11875 &:= (C(5) \times (7 + (8 \times 11))) \\
 11889 &:= ((C(9) + C(8)) + (8 \times C(11))) \\
 11914 &:= -(((C(4) + 1) + (-9) \times C(11))) \\
 11915 &:= -(C((5 - 1)) + (-9) \times C(11)) \\
 11952 &:= -(C(-(2 - 5)) - (9 \times C(11))) \\
 11971 &:= (-((1 + 7)) - (-9) \times C(11)) \\
 11978 &:= (-((8 - 7)) - (-9) \times C(11)) \\
 11979 &:= (9 \times C(-(7 - (9 \times (1 + 1))))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 12125 &:= (C(5) \times ((C(2) \times 12) + 1)) \\
 12146 &:= (C(((6 \times 4) - 1)) - (21)) \\
 12164 &:= (C(((4 \times 6) - 1)) - (2 + 1)) \\
 12167 &:= C((((7 - 6) + 1) + 21)) \\
 12168 &:= (C((((8 + 6) + 1) + C(2))) + 1) \\
 12223 &:= ((((-3) \times C(C(2))) + C(2)) \times (-C(2))) - 1) \\
 12224 &:= (-C(4)) + (C(C(2)) \times (C(2) \times (2 + 1))) \\
 12231 &:= (C((1 + 3)) + C((2 + 21))) \\
 12232 &:= ((C(23) + C((2 + 2))) + 1) \\
 12234 &:= ((C(4) + 3) + C((2 + 21))) \\
 12246 &:= (-6) \times ((-4) \times C(C(2))) + (C(2) - 1)) \\
 12264 &:= ((-((4^6)) + C(2)) \times (-2 + 1)) \\
 12282 &:= ((-2) + C((8 \times 2))) \times (2 + 1) \\
 12283 &:= ((3 \times (C((8 \times 2)) - 2)) + 1) \\
 12284 &:= (-4) - (C((8 \times 2)) \times (-2 + 1)) \\
 12285 &:= (-((5 - 8)) \times (C((C(2) + C(2))) - 1)) \\
 12296 &:= (((C(6)/9) \times C(C(2))) + C((2 \times 1))) \\
 12312 &:= ((C(C(2)) + 1) \times (3 + 21)) \\
 12323 &:= (C(3) + (C(2) \times ((3 \times C(C(2))) + 1))) \\
 12328 &:= (8 \times (C(C(2)) + (3 \times C((C(2) - 1)))))) \\
 12339 &:= (-C(9)) - (C(3) \times ((C(3) - C(C(2))) + 1)) \\
 12347 &:= ((C(7) \times (4 + 32)) - 1) \\
 12348 &:= (C(84)/(C(3) + (21))) \\
 12352 &:= (C(2) \times (5 + (3 \times (C(C(2)) + 1)))) \\
 12364 &:= (-4) \times ((-6) \times (3 + C(C(2)))) - 1) \\
 12365 &:= (-C((5 \times 6)) - ((C(C(3)) \times (-2)) + 1)) \\
 12368 &:= (8 \times ((C(6) + C((3 + C(2)))) - 1)) \\
 12375 &:= (C(5) \times (((7 + 3)^2) - 1)) \\
 12376 &:= ((C(6) - (7)) + C(((3 \times C(2)) - 1))) \\
 12383 &:= ((C(3) \times 8) + C(((3 \times C(2)) - 1))) \\
 12384 &:= ((4 + C(8)) \times (3 + 21)) \\
 12385 &:= (((C(5) - C(8)) \times (-32)) + 1) \\
 12392 &:= (((C(2) + 9) \times C((3^2))) - 1) \\
 12393 &:= (C(C(3)) + (C(9) \times (-((3^2) + 1)))) \\
 12426 &:= ((C(6) + 2) \times ((C(4) - C(2)) + 1)) \\
 12467 &:= ((-((C(7) - (6))) + C(C(4)))/21) \\
 12473 &:= (((C(3) \times 7) \times (C(4) + 2)) - 1) \\
 12474 &:= -(((C(C(4)) + (7)) - C((C(4) + (2 - 1)))))) \\
 12501 &:= (((10^5)/C(2)) + 1) \\
 12544 &:= (C(4) \times (((C(4) + C(5)) + C(2)) - 1)) \\
 12625 &:= -(C(5) \times (C(2) - ((C(6)/2) + 1))) \\
 12636 &:= (C(((6 + 3) + 6)) + C(21))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}12655 &:= (-5) \times ((-5) \times (-6) + C(C(2))) - 1) \\12691 &:= (C(19) + C((6 \times (2 + 1)))) \\12742 &:= ((C((C(2) \times 4)) - C(7)) - C(C((2 + 1)))) \\12743 &:= ((C(3) \times 472) - 1) \\12768 &:= ((-8) - C(6)) \times ((-7) \times C(2)) - 1) \\12799 &:= (((9 + 9) + 7) \times C(C(2))) - 1) \\12823 &:= (C((3 \times C(2))) - ((C((8 + 2)) + 1))) \\12825 &:= ((5^2) \times (C(8) + (2 - 1))) \\12832 &:= ((C(2) + C(C(3))) - C((-8) + C((2 + 1)))) \\12833 &:= ((C(C(3)) - C((C(3) - 8))) + (C(2) + 1)) \\12855 &:= (-5) \times ((-5) \times (C(8) + 2)) - 1) \\12864 &:= (C(4) \times (C(6) - ((8 \times 2) - 1))) \\12896 &:= (C(((6 + 9) + 8)) + C((C(2) + 1))) \\12994 &:= ((C(4) - (9 \times C(9))) \times (-2 \times 1)) \\12997 &:= (((7 - C(9)) \times (-9 \times 2)) + 1) \\13084 &:= ((C((4 \times 8)) - C(C(03))) - 1) \\13122 &:= (2 \times ((2 + 1)^{C(3-1)})) \\13123 &:= (((3^{C(2)}) \times (-1 - 3)) + 1) \\13125 &:= (C(5) \times ((C(2) \times 13) + 1)) \\13167 &:= ((7 - C(6)) \times (1 - C((3 + 1)))) \\13168 &:= (8 \times ((61 \times C(3)) - 1)) \\13182 &:= (-((2 - 8)) \times C((13 \times 1))) \\13196 &:= ((-6) \times (C(9) + 1)) + C((C(3) - 1)) \\13225 &:= (((C(5) - C(2)) - 2)^{3-1}) \\13232 &:= (-2) - ((3 - C(C(2))) \times (C(3) - 1)) \\13237 &:= (-C(7)) - ((C(3) - C(C(2))) \times (C(3) + 1)) \\13244 &:= ((-4) - C(4)) - (C(C(2)) \times (-C(3) - 1)) \\13248 &:= ((C(8) + C(4)) \times (23 \times 1)) \\13249 &:= (((-9) \times C(4)) \times (-23)) + 1) \\13256 &:= ((C(6) \times (-5)) - (C(C(2)) \times (-C(3) + 1))) \\13273 &:= (((C((C(3) + 7))) + C(C(2)))/3) + 1) \\13285 &:= -((C(-((5 - 8))) + (C(C(2)) \times (-C(3) - 1)))) \\13311 &:= (-1) + ((-1) + C(3)) \times C(C((3 - 1))) \\13312 &:= (C(2) \times ((-1) + C(3)) \times C((3 + 1))) \\13313 &:= -(((C(C((3 - 1))) - C((C(3) - 3))) - 1)) \\13338 &:= ((C(8) + (3/3)) \times (C(3) - 1)) \\13339 &:= -(((C((-9) + C(3))) - C(C(3))) + C(C((3 - 1)))) \\13357 &:= ((-((C(7) + C(5))) + C((C(3) - 3))) + 1) \\13375 &:= (C(5) \times (((7 - 3) \times C(3)) - 1)) \\13376 &:= ((C(6) - 7) \times C(-((C(3) - 31)))) \\13377 &:= (C(7) \times ((7 + 33) - 1)) \\13382 &:= -((C(2) - ((C(8) + 3) \times (C(3) - 1))))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}13385 &:= (-5) + ((C(8) + 3) \times (C(3) - 1)) \\13392 &:= ((-2) \times C((9 - 3))) \times (-31) \\13427 &:= (((C(7) + C((C(2) \times 4))) - C(C(3))) - 1) \\13466 &:= (((C(6) - 6) \times C(4)) + C(3)) - 1) \\13468 &:= (((C(8) + 6) \times C(4)) - C(C(3))) - 1) \\13469 &:= ((C((9 + 6)) \times 4) - 31) \\13472 &:= ((C((C(2) + 7))) \times 4) - (C(3) + 1) \\13496 &:= ((C((6 + 9)) \times 4) - (3 + 1)) \\13504 &:= (-4) \times ((0 - C((5 \times 3))) - 1) \\13526 &:= (((C(6)/2) \times C(5)) + C(3)) - 1) \\13529 &:= (C(9) - (C(C(2)) \times (-5^{3-1}))) \\13532 &:= ((C(2) + C((3 \times 5))) \times (3 + 1)) \\13557 &:= ((7^5) - (C(5) \times (C(3) - 1))) \\13564 &:= (C(4) - (C((6 \times 5))/(-3 - 1))) \\13567 &:= ((C(7) \times (-6)) + C((5^{3-1}))) \\13625 &:= (C(5) \times ((-2) - C(6))/(-3 - 1)) \\13631 &:= (-1) - ((3 - C(6)) \times C((3 + 1))) \\13632 &:= (C(2) \times ((-3) + C(6)) \times C((3 - 1))) \\13634 &:= ((C(4) \times (-3) + C(6)) + (3 - 1)) \\13636 &:= (((63 \times C(6)) + C(3)) + 1) \\13638 &:= (C((8 \times 3)) - (6 \times 31)) \\13657 &:= (-7) \times ((5^6) - C((C(3) - 1))) \\13662 &:= ((C((2 + 6)) - 6) \times C((3 \times 1))) \\13663 &:= ((C(3) \times (-6) + C(C((6/3)))) + 1) \\13682 &:= (((C((2 + 8)) \times (-6)) + C(C(3))) - 1) \\13694 &:= ((C((4 + 9)) \times 6) + C(C((3 - 1))) \\13715 &:= (-5) \times (1 - C((7 \times (3 - 1)))) \\13722 &:= (2 \times (2 + C((-7) + C(3)) - 1)) \\13732 &:= ((C(-((C(2) - C(3)))) + 7) \times (3 - 1)) \\13735 &:= (-5) \times (-3 - C((7 \times (3 - 1)))) \\13736 &:= ((-C(6)) - C((C(3) - 7))) + C((C(3) + 1)) \\13742 &:= (((C(C(2)) + (4 - 7)) \times C(3)) - 1) \\13743 &:= (-((3^4)) + C(-((7 - 31))) \\13752 &:= (C(2) \times ((5 \times C(7)) + (3 + 1))) \\13761 &:= (((-1) + C(6)) \times C((7 - 3))) + 1) \\13768 &:= (((8 \times C(6)) - 7) \times C((3 - 1))) \\13793 &:= (C((3 \times C(9 - 7))) - 31) \\13796 &:= (C((C(6)/9)) - (7 \times (3 + 1))) \\13798 &:= ((C(((8 + 9) + 7)) - C(3)) + 1) \\13816 &:= (C((6 + 18)) - C((3 - 1))) \\13817 &:= (-7) + C(((1 - 8) + 31)) \\13818 &:= ((-((8 - 1)) + C((8 \times 3))) + 1)\end{aligned}$$

- 13821 := $(-(1+2) + C((8 \times 3) \times 1))$
13822 := $(-2) + C(((28-3)-1))$
13826 := $((-6) + C(2)) + C(((8 \times 3) \times 1))$
13828 := $(8/2) + C(((8 \times 3) \times 1))$
13831 := $((-1) + C((3 \times 8))) + C((3-1))$
13832 := $(C(2) + (((3 \times 8)^3) \times 1))$
13833 := $(3 \times 3) + C(((8 \times 3) \times 1))$
13834 := $(C(4) + (C(3) \times (C(8) - (3-1))))$
13842 := $((C(24) - 8) + C(3)) - 1$
13845 := $((5 \times 4) + C((8 \times 3))) + 1$
13848 := $(8 \times (C((4+8)) + (3 \times 1)))$
13851 := $((1^5) + C(8)) \times C((3 \times 1))$
13852 := $((C(((2^5) - 8)) + C(3)) + 1)$
13867 := $((7 \times 6) + C((8 \times 3))) + 1$
13869 := $(9 \times (6 + ((C(8) \times 3) - 1)))$
13875 := $(-5) \times ((C(7) \times (-8)) - (31))$
13879 := $((9-7) + C(8)) \times C(3) + 1$
13888 := $(8 \times 8) + C(((8 \times 3) \times 1))$
13896 := $(C((C(6)/9)) + (8 + C((3+1))))$
13955 := $(-5) \times (C(5) + (C(9) \times (-3+1)))$
13958 := $((C(8) + 5) \times (9 \times 3)) - 1$
13986 := $((6 + C(8)) \times ((9 \times 3) \times 1))$
14125 := $(C(5) \times ((C(2) \times 14) + 1))$
14165 := $(C(5) - (C(6) \times (-1) - C((4 \times 1))))$
14167 := $(C(7) + C(((6 \times 1) \times 4) \times 1))$
14168 := $((C(8) - 6) \times (1 + C((4-1))))$
14227 := $((C(7) + (2+2)) \times 41)$
14256 := $(C(6) \times ((5^2) + 41))$
14282 := $(C(C(2)) + (((C(8) - 2) \times C((4-1))))$
14283 := $(C(3) \times (C(8) + ((2^4) + 1)))$
14287 := $(-7) \times (((C(8) - 2) \times (-4)) - 1)$
14297 := $-((C(7) - (((9+2)^4) - 1)))$
14328 := $(C(8) + (C(2) \times (C((3 \times 4) - 1)))$
14332 := $((C(C(2)) + C((C(3) - 3))) - (4 \times 1))$
14336 := $(C(C((6/3))) + C((C(3) - (4-1))))$
14364 := $(4 \times (C(6) + C((3 \times (4+1))))$
14365 := $((5 + (6^3)) \times (C(4) + 1))$
14375 := $((C(5) - (7+3)) \times C((4+1)))$
14399 := $((9 + C((9-3))) \times C(4)) - 1$
14463 := $((C(3) \times 6) + C(4)) \times C(4) - 1$
14466 := $(-6) + (C(6) \times (C(4) + (4-1)))$
14495 := $(-5) \times (((C(9) - 4) \times (-4)) + 1)$
14499 := $((-((9 \times 9)) \times C(4)) + C(C((4-1))))$
14553 := $(C(C(3)) + (-5 - (C(5) \times 41)))$
14558 := $(C(C((8-5))) - (C(5) \times 41))$
14559 := $((C(9) \times 5) - 5) \times 4 - 1$
14573 := $(C(C(3)) + (-7) \times (C((5+4)) + 1))$
14581 := $((C((1+8)) \times (5 \times 4)) + 1)$
14593 := $((-3 - (C(9) \times 5)) \times (-4)) + 1$
14616 := $((C(6) + 16) \times (C(4) - 1))$
14624 := $(C(4) + ((C(2) + C(6)) \times (C(4) + 1)))$
14625 := $(C((5^2)) - C(((6+4) \times 1)))$
14637 := $((C(7) \times 3) + (C(6) \times (C(4) - 1)))$
14642 := $((C(2 + C(4))/6)^4) + 1$
14671 := $(-17) \times ((C(6) \times (-4)) + 1)$
14678 := $((C(8) + C(7)) + C((6 \times 4))) - 1$
14685 := $(C(5) - ((-8) - C(6)) \times (C(4) + 1))$
14689 := $((9+8) \times C(6)) \times 4 + 1$
14695 := $(-5) \times (((C(9) + 6) \times (-4)) + 1)$
14768 := $((8 - C(6)) \times (-7 - C((4 \times 1))))$
14771 := $((-C(17)) + C(C((7-4)))) + 1$
14784 := $-((C(4) + (C(8) \times (-((7 \times 4) + 1))))$
14791 := $((-1) + C(9)) + (C(7) \times 41)$
14796 := $(C(6) - (C(9) \times (7 - C((4-1))))$
14848 := $(C(8) \times ((4 \times 8) - 4) + 1)$
14875 := $(C(5) \times (78 + 41))$
14892 := $((C(C(2)) + (C(9))) \times ((8+4) \times 1))$
14893 := $((3 \times ((C(9) + C(8)) \times 4)) + 1)$
14895 := $((C(5) - C((9+8))) + C(C((4-1))))$
14923 := $(C((C(3) - 2)) - (C(9) - C((4-1))))$
14986 := $((C(6) - C((8+9))) + C(C((4-1))))$
15093 := $(C(C(3)) - (90 \times 51))$
15125 := $(C(5) \times ((C(2) \times 15) + 1))$
15157 := $((C(7) - ((C(5) - 1) \times C(5))) \times (-1))$
15238 := $-((C(8) - (C((3+2)) \times (C(5) + 1)))$
15246 := $(-6) \times (((-4) + C(C(2))) \times (-5)) - 1)$
15264 := $((-4) + C(6)) \times (C(2) + C((5-1)))$
15276 := $((-6) - C(7)) + C((25 \times 1))$
15281 := $-((C(-((1-8))) - (C(25) - 1)))$
15309 := $(C(9) \times (C(03) - (5+1)))$
15336 := $((C(6) - 3)/3) \times C((5+1))$
15365 := $(-5) \times ((-6) \times C((3+5))) - 1$
15366 := $(-6) \times ((C(C((6/3))) \times (-5)) - 1)$
15367 := $((C(7) - C(6)) \times ((-3) + C(5)) - 1)$

$$\begin{aligned} 15372 &:= ((C(-(2-7))) - 3) \times (C(5) + 1) \\ 15376 &:= -(((C(6) - C(7)) + 3) \times (C(5) - 1))) \\ 15424 &:= (C(4) \times ((2 \times (-4) + C(5))) - 1) \\ 15426 &:= ((C(6) \times (C(2) + C(4))) - (C(5) + 1)) \\ 15433 &:= (C(C(3)) + (-34) \times C((5 \times 1))) \\ 15434 &:= ((C((4+3)) \times 45) - 1) \\ 15472 &:= -((C(C(2)) + (-74) \times C((5+1)))) \\ 15473 &:= (((C(C(3)) - C(7)) \times (-4))/(-5)) + 1) \\ 15486 &:= (-6) \times (((C(8) + 4) \times (-5)) - 1) \\ 15488 &:= (C(88)/(45 - 1)) \\ 15492 &:= -((C(2) - (C((9-4)) \times (C(5) - 1)))) \\ 15495 &:= (-5) + (C((9-4)) \times (C(5) - 1)) \\ 15525 &:= ((5^2) + (C(5) \times (C(5) - 1))) \\ 15526 &:= -(((C(6) + C(2)) - (C(5) \times (C(5) + 1)))) \\ 15533 &:= (33 + (C(5) \times (C(5) - 1))) \\ 15534 &:= (((C(4) + C(3)) - C((5 \times 5))) \times (-1)) \\ 15543 &:= ((-(3^4) + C((5 \times 5))) - 1) \\ 15544 &:= (44 + (C(5) \times (C(5) - 1))) \\ 15551 &:= (((-1) + C(5)) \times C(5)) + (51) \\ 15552 &:= ((-(2-5)^5) \times C((5-1))) \\ 15555 &:= (55 + (C(5) \times (C(5) - 1))) \\ 15561 &:= (C(-(((1-6) \times 5))) - C((5-1))) \\ 15566 &:= (66 + (C(5) \times (C(5) - 1))) \\ 15577 &:= ((-(7 \times 7) + C((5 \times 5))) + 1) \\ 15588 &:= (88 + (C(5) \times (C(5) - 1))) \\ 15599 &:= (99 + (C(5) \times (C(5) - 1))) \\ 15617 &:= ((-7) + C(-(((1-6) \times 5)))) - 1) \\ 15618 &:= ((-8) + C(-(((1-6) \times 5)))) + 1) \\ 15619 &:= (C((9+16)) - (5+1)) \\ 15621 &:= (C(-((1-26))) - (5-1)) \\ 15623 &:= (C((C(3) - 2)) - ((6-5) + 1)) \\ 15624 &:= (C(((4+26) - 5)) - 1) \\ 15626 &:= (C((((6^2) - 6) - 5)) + 1) \\ 15629 &:= (((-9) - C(C(2))) \times (-6 \times 5)) - 1) \\ 15653 &:= ((C(3) + C((5 \times 6) - 5)) + 1) \\ 15686 &:= ((6 - C(8)) \times -((6 \times 5) + 1)) \\ 15723 &:= (-C(3)) - (C(-((2-7))) \times (-C(5) + 1))) \\ 15748 &:= -(((C(8) - (4^7)) + C(5)) - 1) \\ 15752 &:= ((C(25) + C(7)) - C((5+1))) \\ 15782 &:= ((-2) \times C(8)) + ((7^5) - 1) \\ 15848 &:= (-C((8+4))) + C((C((8-5)) - 1)) \\ 15875 &:= (C(5) \times (-((7-8)) + C(5) + 1)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 15884 &:= (-4) \times ((C(8) \times (-8)) + C((5 \times 1))) \\ 15936 &:= ((6 - (C(3) \times (-9))) \times C((5-1))) \\ 15952 &:= -((C(C(2)) - (C((5+9)) \times (5+1))) \\ 15993 &:= (C(C(3)) - ((9 + C(9)) \times (5 \times 1))) \\ 16125 &:= (C(5) \times ((2^{1+6}) + 1)) \\ 16138 &:= ((C(8) + C((31-6))) + 1) \\ 16224 &:= ((C(4)/2) \times (C(C(2)) - (6-1))) \\ 16243 &:= (C(C(3)) - ((4^2) \times (C(6) - 1))) \\ 16253 &:= (C(C(3)) - ((5 \times 2) \times C((6+1)))) \\ 16255 &:= (-5) \times ((C(5) \times (-26)) - 1) \\ 16275 &:= ((-5) \times (-7 - C(2))) \times (C(6) + 1) \\ 16285 &:= (-5) \times ((-C(8)) - C((C(2) + (6)))) - 1) \\ 16355 &:= (C((5 \times 5)) + (((3^6) + 1))) \\ 16369 &:= ((-C((9+6))) + C(C(3))) + (61) \\ 16375 &:= (C(5) \times (((C(7) + 3) - C(6)) + 1)) \\ 16379 &:= (((-9) \times C(7)) + C(C(3))) - (C(6) + 1) \\ 16382 &:= (-2) + (C(8) \times (C(3) + (6-1))) \\ 16395 &:= (-5) \times ((9 - C(C(3)))/(6 \times 1)) \\ 16441 &:= (((C(14) - 4) \times 6) + 1) \\ 16443 &:= (C(3) \times ((-4) \times (C(4) - C(6))) + 1) \\ 16444 &:= (C(4) - (4 - (4^{6+1}))) \\ 16445 &:= ((C(5) - C(4)) + (4^{6+1})) \\ 16448 &:= (C((8-4)) + (4^{6+1})) \\ 16463 &:= ((C(((3 \times 6) - 4)) \times 6) - 1) \\ 16464 &:= (C(((4+6) + 4)) \times (6 \times 1)) \\ 16465 &:= ((C((56/4)) \times 6) + 1) \\ 16487 &:= (((C(7) \times 8) + 4) \times 6) - 1) \\ 16489 &:= ((9 \times ((C(8) \times 4) - C(6))) + 1) \\ 16492 &:= (((C(2) \times 9) + 4) \times (C(6) + 1)) \\ 16522 &:= (-22) \times ((C(5) \times (-6)) - 1) \\ 16553 &:= (C(C(3)) - (((5^5) + 6) - 1)) \\ 16557 &:= (((7^5) - C(5)) - C((6-1))) \\ 16558 &:= (C(C((8-5))) - (5^{6-1})) \\ 16569 &:= ((C(9) + C(6)) + ((5^6) - 1)) \\ 16592 &:= (((-((2-9))^5) - C(6)) + 1) \\ 16625 &:= (C(5) \times ((2 \times 66) + 1)) \\ 16632 &:= (((C(2) + 3) \times C(6)) \times (6+1)) \\ 16653 &:= (3 \times ((C(5) - C(6)) \times (-61))) \\ 16723 &:= (C(C(3)) - (C((2 \times 7)) + C((6 \times 1)))) \\ 16727 &:= (C(7) + (2^{7+6+1})) \\ 16729 &:= (C(9) - (-((2^7)) \times C((6-1))) \end{aligned}$$

- 16758 := ((8 + C(5)) × ((C(7) - C(6)) - 1))
16765 := (-5) × (((C(6) + C(7)) × (-6)) + 1))
16773 := -((C(3) + (7 - (7⁶⁻¹))))
16835 := ((C((5 × 3)) - 8) × (6 - 1))
16863 := ((C(3) + (6)) × (C(C((8 - 6)))) - 1))
16875 := (5 × C(((7 × (8 - 6)) + 1)))
16884 := (-4) × ((C(8) × (-8)) - C((6 - 1)))
16896 := (C((C(6)/9)) + (C(8) × (6 × 1)))
16897 := (((C(7) + 9) × (8 × 6)) + 1)
16926 := ((6 + (C(2) × 9)) × (C(6) + 1))
16939 := (C((9 × 3)) - C(((9 + 6) - 1)))
16943 := (C(C(3)) - (-4) + C(((9 + 6) - 1)))
16992 := ((2 × 9) × ((C(9) + C(6)) - 1))
17123 := (C(C(3)) + (C(C(2)) × ((1 - 7) + 1)))
17125 := (C(5) × ((C(2) × 17) + 1))
17149 := (((9 + 41) × C(7)) - 1)
17151 := ((-((1 - 51)) × C(7)) + 1)
17231 := (C((-1) + C(3)) + (-2) - C((7 × 1)))
17232 := (C(((C(2) × 3) + 2)) - (C(7) + 1))
17233 := (C((C(3) - (3 - 2))) - C((7 × 1)))
17253 := (C(3) × ((5 × (2⁷)) - 1))
17375 := (C(5) × (((-7) + C(3)) × 7) - 1))
17396 := (((C(6) × (-9)) + C(C(3))) - C((7 × 1)))
17448 := ((C(8)/(-4)) + C((C(-((4 - 7))) - 1)))
17451 := ((-1) × C(5)) + C((C(-((4 - 7))) - 1)))
17465 := ((5 × C(6)) + ((4⁷) + 1))
17478 := ((C(8) + (7⁴)) × (7 - 1))
17479 := (-97) + C((C(-((4 - 7))) - 1))
17485 := ((-C((5 + 8))) + C(C(-((4 - 7)))) - 1)
17488 := (-88) + C((C(-((4 - 7))) - 1))
17493 := (-3) - (C(9) × (-4 × (7 - 1)))
17494 := (((C(4) - (9 + 4)) × C(7)) + 1)
17496 := ((6 × C(9)) × (-((4 - 7) - 1))
17497 := (-79) + C((C(-((4 - 7))) - 1))
17523 := (C(C(3)) - ((2 × 5) × C((7 - 1)))
17528 := (8 × (C((C(2) + (5))) - (7 - 1))
17557 := ((7⁵) + (C(5) × (7 - 1))
17568 := (8 × (C(((C(6) - C(5))/7)) - 1))
17569 := ((9 × C(6)) + (5⁷⁻¹))
17575 := (C(((57 + C(5))/7)) - 1)
17576 := C((((6 + 7) + 5) + 7) + 1))
17577 := (C((((7 + 7) + 5) + 7) + 1))
17578 := (((C(8) × (7 × 5)) - C(7)) + 1)
17582 := (C((2 × (8 + 5))) + (7 - 1))
17623 := (C(C(3)) - (2 + (6 × C((7 × 1))))
17625 := (C(C((5 - 2))) - (6 × C((7 × 1)))
17626 := (C(C((6/2))) - ((6 × C(7)) - 1))
17631 := (C(C((1 × 3))) - (6 × (C(7) - 1))
17632 := ((C(2) + C(C(3))) - ((6 × C(7)) + 1))
17649 := (9 × (((C(4) + C(6)) × 7) + 1))
17664 := (C(4) × ((-66) + C(7)) - 1))
17695 := (((C((5 + 9)) - C(6)) × 7) - 1)
17739 := (9 × ((3⁷) - C((7 - 1)))
17766 := (6 × ((C(6) + C((7 + 7))) + 1))
17784 := (-((4 - (8 × 7))) × (C(7) - 1))
17839 := ((C(9) × (3 × 8)) + C((7 × 1)))
17885 := (-5) × (8 - ((C(8) × 7) + 1))
17915 := (-5) × ((C(-((1 - 9))) × (-7)) + 1))
17962 := ((C(26) + C(9)) - C((7 × 1))
18063 := (C(3) × (-60) + C((8 + 1)))
18125 := (C(5) × ((C(2) × 18) + 1))
18223 := (C(C(3)) + (-2) + (-2) × C((8 + 1)))
18225 := ((5²) × C(((2 + 8) - 1))
18247 := ((-7) - C(4)) × (-((2⁸) + 1))
18262 := (C(26) + (2 × C((8 - 1)))
18324 := (-4) × ((C(C(2)) - 3) × (-8 + 1))
18352 := (C(C(-((2 - 5)))) + (C((3 + 8)) × (-1))
18353 := (C(C(3)) - ((C((-5) + C(3)))/8) - 1))
18363 := (C(C(3)) - ((C(6) - (3 × C(8))) × (-1))
18375 := (C(5) × ((7 × 3) × (8 - 1))
18393 := (-3) + ((9 + C(3)) × (C(8) - 1))
18396 := ((6 × (9 - 3)) × (C(8) - 1))
18423 := ((3²) × ((4 × C(8)) - 1))
18426 := (-6) × ((-((2 + 4)) × C(8)) + 1))
18431 := (((-1) - C(3)) + C(4)) × C(8) - 1)
18432 := (C((2³)) × (4 × (8 + 1))
18433 := (((3 × 3) × 4) × C(8)) + 1)
18438 := ((-C(8) + C(C(3))) - (4 + C((8 + 1)))
18439 := ((-C(9) + C(C(3))) - ((4 + C(8)) - 1))
18468 := (((8 + C(6)) + (4)) × 81)
18479 := ((C(9) - ((7⁴) × 8)) × (-1))
18486 := ((6 - (C(8) × (-4))) × (8 + 1))
18522 := (2 × C(-((2 - 5) × (8 - 1))))
18545 := (5 × (C(4) + (5 × C((8 + 1))))

- 18549 := ((C(9) + (-4) × C(5)) × 81)
18553 := (C(C(3)) - (5 + (C(5) × (8 + 1))))
18558 := (C(C((8 - 5))) - (C(5) × (8 + 1)))
18559 := (((-9) × C(5)) + C(C(-(5 - 8)))) + 1)
18567 := (((C(7) × (-6)) - (5)) × (-8 + 1))
18568 := (-8) + (C(6) × (5 + 81))
18576 := ((C((6 + 7)) + C(5)) × (8 × 1))
18649 := (((9 × 4) × (6 + C(8))) + 1)
18656 := ((C(6) × 5) + C(((C(6)/8) - 1)))
18682 := ((-C((2 + 8))) + C((C(6)/8))) - 1)
18683 := (C(C(3)) - C(((8 - 6) + 8) × 1))
18724 := ((C(C(4)) - C(2))/(7 + 8) - 1)
18773 := (C(C(3)) - (C(7) + ((7 × 81))))
18837 := ((-C(7)) + C(C(3))) + ((8 - C(8)) + 1)
18893 := (((3 × C(9)) + C(8)) × (8 - 1))
18938 := ((-8) + C(C(3))) - (C(9) + (8 × 1))
18943 := (C(C(3)) - ((4 + C(9)) + (8 - 1)))
18947 := (C(C((7 - 4))) - (C(9) + (8 - 1)))
18948 := (C(8) + (-4) × ((-9) × C(8)) - 1))
18962 := ((26 × C(9)) + (8 × 1))
18963 := (C(C(3)) - (((C(6) - 9) + C(8)) + 1))
19043 := (C(C(3)) - (C(4) × (09 + 1)))
19125 := (C(5) × ((C(2) × 19) + 1))
19172 := ((C(27) + 1) - C((9 - 1)))
19224 := (C((4 + 2)) × (-2 - 91))
19234 := ((C(4) + C(C(3))) - ((2⁹) + 1))
19243 := (C(C(3)) + (((C(4) + C(2)) - C((9 - 1))))))
19262 := -(((C(C(2)) - C(C((6/2)))) - (91)))
19297 := (((C(7) + C(9)) × (2 × 9)) + 1)
19332 := ((-C(2)) + C(C(3))) - C(-((3 - 9) - 1)))
19335 := ((C(5) × (-3)) + (C(3) × (C(9) + 1)))
19337 := ((C(7) + (3 - (3⁹))) × (-1))
19354 := (((C(4) × (-5)) + C(C(3))) - (9 × 1))
19367 := -((C(7) - (C((6 - 3)) × (C(9) + 1))))
19368 := (((-8) - C(6)) + C(C(3))) - (91)
19375 := (C(5) × (C((7 - 3)) + (91)))
19383 := (((C(3) × 8) - 3) × 91)
19386 := ((C(6) - C(8)) + (((3⁹) - 1))
19388 := ((-((C(8) + C(8))) + C(C(3))) - (C(9) × (-1)))
19396 := (((C(6) + 9) + C(C(3))) - C((9 - 1)))
19413 := (C(C(3)) - (C(-((1 - 4))) × (9 + 1)))
19453 := (C(C(3)) - (((C(5) × (-4)) + C(9)) + 1))
19463 := (C(C(3)) - (C(6) - (((4 - 9) + 1))))
19476 := (((-C(6)) + C(C((7 - 4)))) + (9 × 1))
19521 := (C((1 + 2)) × ((-5) + C(9)) - 1)
19533 := (C(C(3)) - ((3 × 5) × (9 + 1)))
19539 := (9 × ((3 × (-5) + C(9))) - 1)
19547 := ((C((7 - 4)) × (-5) + C(9))) - 1)
19553 := (C(C(3)) - (C(5) - (((5 - 9) - 1))))
19554 := (((-4) - C(5)) + C(C(-(((5 - 9) + 1))))))
19558 := (C(C((8 - 5))) - C(-(((5 - 9) - 1))))
19563 := (C(C(3)) - (C(6) - ((5 + 91))))
19573 := (C(C(3)) - ((-7) + C(5)) - (9 - 1))
19583 := (C(C(3)) - (((-8) × C(5))/(-9 + 1)))
19584 := ((C(4) + C(8)) × (C(5) - (91)))
19585 := -((C(5) - (C((8 - 5)) × (C(9) + 1))))
19586 := (((-6) + C(C((8 - 5)))) - (91))
19613 := (C(C(3)) - ((1 × 69) + 1))
19614 := (C(C((4 - 1))) - (69 × 1))
19623 := (C(C(3)) + ((C(2) - (69 - 1))))
19624 := ((C(4)/(-2)) + (C(6) × 91))
19627 := (((-7) × C(2)) + C((C(6)/(9 - 1))))
19629 := (((C(9) - 2) × C(6))/(9 - 1))
19643 := (C(C(3)) - (C(4) - (C(6)/(9 × 1))))
19644 := (-4) + (C(4) × (C(6) + (91)))
19646 := (-((6 + 4)) + (C(6) × 91))
19648 := (C((8 - 4)) × (C(6) + (91)))
19651 := (-((1 × 5)) + (C(6) × 91))
19652 := (((-2⁵) + C(C(-(6 - 9)))) + 1)
19653 := (C(C(3)) - (5 + ((C(6)/9) + 1)))
19655 := (-((5/5)) + (C(6) × 91))
19656 := (C(6) × (-((5 - 6) × 91)))
19658 := (C(C((8 - 5))) - ((C(6)/9) + 1))
19661 := (-((1 - 6)) + (C(6) × 91))
19663 := (C(C(3)) - (((6 + 6) + 9) - 1))
19664 := (C(-((4 - 6))) + (C(6) × 91))
19665 := (((C(5) - C(6)) × C(6)) - 9) × (-1)
19668 := (((-8 + 6) + C(C(-(6 - 9)))) - 1)
19669 := (C(C((9 - 6))) - ((6 + 9) - 1))
19673 := (C(((3 × 7) + 6)) - (9 + 1))
19674 := (C(C(((4 - 7) + 6))) - (9 × 1))
19675 := -((C(-((5 - 7))) - C((C(6)/(9 - 1))))))
19681 := (((-1⁸) + C(C(-(6 - 9)))) - 1)
19682 := ((C(2)/(-8)) + C((C(6)/(9 - 1))))

- 19683 := C((((3 + 8) + 6) + 9) + 1))
19684 := (C((((4 + 8) + 6) + 9)) + 1)
19685 := (C(C(-(5 - 8)))) - (((6 - 9) + 1)))
19686 := (C((C(6)/8)) - (((6 - 9) × 1)))
19691 := (-((1 - 9)) + C((C(6)/(9 - 1))))
19692 := (C(2) + (((9 - 6)⁹) + 1))
19693 := (C((3⁹⁻⁶)) + (9 + 1))
19723 := (C(C(3)) - (((2 - 7) × (9 - 1))))
19738 := ((-8) + C(C(3))) + ((7 × 9) × 1))
19739 := (C((9 × 3)) + (7 × (9 - 1)))
19743 := (C(C(3)) + (4 × ((7 + 9) - 1)))
19747 := (C(C((7 - 4))) + ((7 × 9) + 1))
19752 := (2 × ((C(5) × 79) + 1))
19763 := (C(C(-(3 - 6)))) + (79 + 1))
19766 := (-6) - ((C((6 + 7)) × (-9)) + 1))
19767 := (-7) - ((C((6 + 7)) × (-9)) - 1))
19773 := (C(C(3)) - (((7/7) - 91)))
19774 := (C(C((4 - (7/7)))) + (91))
19834 := -((C(4) - ((C(3) × (8 + C(9))) - 1)))
19837 := (C(7) + (C(3) × ((-8) + C(9)) + 1)))
19855 := (-5) × (C(5) - C(((8 + 9) - 1)))
19872 := (27 × ((8 + C(9)) - 1))
19875 := -((C(5) × ((C(7) - C(8)) + (9 + 1))))
19925 := ((C((5 - 2)) × (9 + C(9))) - 1)
19926 := (C((6/2)) × (9 + C((9 × 1))))
19928 := ((C(82) - C((9 × 9))) + 1)
19968 := (((8 × 6) - 9) × C((9 - 1)))
20083 := (C(C(3)) + ((800/2)))
20163 := (C(C(3)) + ((6 × 10) × C(2)))
20164 := (-C(4) + C(6) - 10)²
20183 := (C(C(3)) + (C(8) - (10 + 2)))
20185 := (C(C(-(5 - 8)))) - (10 - C(C(2))))
20193 := (C(C(3)) + (C((9 - 1)) - 02))
20195 := (C(C(-(5 - 9) + 1))) + C(C(02)))
20196 := (-((C(6) - C(9))) + C(C((1 + 02))))
20203 := ((C(C(3)) + C(02)) + C(C(02)))
20223 := ((C(C(3)) + C(C(2))) + (20 + C(2)))
20224 := -((C((4 + C(2))) - C((20 + C(2))))))
20377 := (((C(7) + C(7)) + C(C(3))) + C(02))
20393 := (C(C(3)) + ((C(9) - C(3)) + C(02)))
20397 := (((-7) + C(9)) + C(C(3))) - C(02))
20424 := (-C(4)) + ((C(C(2)) × 40) + C(2))
20443 := ((C(3) - C(4)) + (40 × C(C(2))))
20448 := (-((8 × 4)) + (40 × C(C(2))))
20453 := -((C(3) - (5 × C((4⁰²))))))
20455 := (-5) × (5 - C((4⁰²)))
20467 := (-((7 + 6)) + (40 × C(C(2))))
20481 := (-1) - ((C(8) × (-40)) - 2))
20484 := (-4) - ((C(8) × (-40)) - C(2))
20536 := (((C(6) + C(C(3))) + (C(5))) + C(C(02)))
20538 := ((C(8) + C(C(3))) + (C((5 + 02))))
20539 := ((C(9) + C(C(3))) + ((C(5) + 02)))
20683 := (C(C(3)) + C((8 + ((6 × 0) + 2))))
20762 := (C(C(2)) + (6 × C((7 + C(02))))))
20763 := (C(C(3)) - (C(6) × (-7 - 02)))
20774 := (47 × (-70) + C(C(2)))
20875 := (C(5) × (7 + (80 × 2)))
20932 := ((C(C(2)) + C(C(3))) + ((C(9) + C(02))))
21025 := ((C(5) + (20))^{1×2})
21125 := (C(5) × ((2 + 11)²))
21139 := ((C(9) × (C(3) + (1 + 1))) - 2)
21184 := (C(4) × (C((8 - 1)) - 12))
21223 := (C((C(3) + (2/2))) - C((1 + C(2))))
21231 := ((C((1 + C(3))) + C(2)) - C((1 + C(2))))
21246 := (-C(6)) - (42 × (1 - C(C(2))))
21248 := (C(8) - ((-4) - C(2)) × C(12))
21263 := (-3) - (-62) × C((-1) + C(2))
21267 := ((C(7) × 62) + (1²))
21294 := ((C((4 + (9 × 2))) - 1) × 2)
21296 := (C(((C(6)/9) - 2)) × (1 × 2))
21298 := (((8 × C((9 + 2))) + 1) × 2)
21315 := ((-C(5)) + C((1 + C(3)))) - C(C((1 × 2)))
21323 := (C(3) + (C((23 - 1)) × 2))
21367 := (((C((7 + 6)) + C(C(3))) - 1) - C(C(2)))
21375 := (C(5) × (((7³) - 1)/2))
21384 := ((C((4 + 8)) + C(C(3))) - C((1 + 2)))
21393 := (C(C(3)) + ((9 - C(3)) + C(12)))
21395 := ((-((5 × 9)) + C((C(3) + 1))) - C(C(2)))
21396 := ((-((6 + 9)) + C(C(3))) + C(12))
21411 := (C((C((1 + 1)) + (4))) + C(C((1 + 2))))
21413 := (((-C(3)) + C((1 + C((4 - 1)))))) - C(C(2))
21422 := (((C(22) + C(4)) - 1) × 2)
21423 := (C(C(3)) + (((C(2) + (4)) + C(12))))
21435 := ((5 - C((34 + 1)))/(-2))

- 21439 := ((C(((−9) − C(3)) + C(4))) − 1) − C(C(2)))
21445 := (5 × (C(4) + ((C(4) + 1)²)))
21475 := ((C((5 + 7)) + C(4)) + C(C((1 + 2))))
21477 := (((−7) + C(7)) × C(4) − C((1 + 2)))
21483 := (C(C(3)) + ((8 + C(4)) + C(12)))
21533 := (C(C(3)) + ((−3) + C(5)) + C(12)))
21535 := (5 × (C(C(3)) − (((C(5) − 1)²))))
21536 := (C(C((6 − 3))) + ((C(5) + C(12))))
21537 := (((−C(7)) + C(C(3))) + C((5 + C((1 × 2))))))
21576 := (((−6) + C(7)) × C((5 − 1))) + C(2))
21627 := (((7 + 2) × C(6)) + C(C((1 + 2))))
21643 := (C(C(3)) + ((C(4) + C(6)) × (−1) + C(2)))
21672 := ((C(C(2)) + C((7 + 6))) × C((1 × 2)))
21683 := (C(C(3)) + ((−8) × C((6 − 1))) × (−2)))
21724 := (((4 × C(C(2))) − (7)) + C(C((1 + 2))))
21736 := (−C(6)) + C(((C(3) − 7)) + C((1 × 2))))
21743 := ((C(C(3)) + C((4 + 7))) + C((1 + C(2))))
21782 := (((C(28) + C(7)) − 1) − C(C(2)))
21824 := (C(4) × (−2) + C(((8 + 1) − 2)))
21825 := (((C(5) − C(28)) × (−1)) − 2)
21843 := (−3) − ((C(C(4)) + 8)/(−12)))
21846 := ((C(64) + 8)/12)
21853 := (C(C(3)) + (C((5 + 8)) − C((1 + 2))))
21864 := ((C(C(4)) + ((C(6) + 8)))/12)
21875 := (C(5) × ((−7) − C((8 − 1)))/(−2)))
21888 := ((C(8) + C((8 × 8)))/12)
21896 := ((C(6) × (98 + 1)) + C(C(2)))
21923 := −(((C(3) − C((29 − 1))) + 2))
21924 := (42 × ((9 + 1) + C(C(2))))
21931 := (C((1 + C(3))) − (9 + 12))
21932 := (C((2 + C(3))) − ((C(9) + C(12))))
21933 := −(((C(3) − C(((3 × 9) + 1))) − C(2)))
21934 := ((C(4) + C(C(3))) + (C(9) × (1 + 2)))
21937 := (((−7) + C(((3 × 9) + 1))) − C(2))
21943 := (C(−(((C(3) − C(4)) + 9))) − (1 + C(2)))
21944 := ((C(4) + C((4 + 9))) + C(C((1 + 2))))
21946 := (−6) + C((((4 + 9) + 1) × 2))
21947 := (C((7 × 4)) − ((9 + 1)/2))
21951 := (−1) + C((((5 + 9) × 1) × 2))
21954 := (((4 × C((5 + 9))) + 1) × 2)
21955 := (−5) + ((C((5 + 9)) + 1) × C(2))
21958 := ((8 × (C((5 + 9)) + 1)) − 2)
21973 := ((C(3) + ((7 + 9))) × (−1) + C(C(2)))
22024 := ((C(4) + C((20 + C(2)))) + C(2))
22113 := (C(3) × (C(−((1 − 12))) − C(C(2))))
22116 := (−6) × ((C(11) + C(C(2))) × (−2))
22125 := (−C(5)) × ((C((C(2) − 1)) − C(C(2))) − C(2))
22144 := (C(4) − (−C(4)) × (C((−1) + C(2))) + 2))
22165 := ((C(5) + C(6)) × (1 + C((2 + 2))))
22168 := ((C((8 + 6)) + C((1 + 2))) × C(2))
22184 := ((C(4) × (C(8) + 1)) − C(22))
22233 := (C(C(3)) + ((3 + 2) × (C(C(2)) − 2)))
22243 := (C(C(3)) + ((C(4) + (2^{C(2)})) × C(2)))
22245 := ((C(5) + C((C(4)/2))) − C(22))
22253 := (C(C(3)) + ((5 × C(C(2))) + (C(2) + 2)))
22256 := ((C(6) × (C(5) − (22))) + C(2))
22272 := ((C(C(2)) × (C(7) − (2^{C(2)})))/2)
22275 := (−5) × (−C(7) − ((C(C(2)) + 2) × C(2)))
22287 := ((C(7) × ((C(8) + C(2))/C(2))) − C(2))
22313 := (C((C(3) + 1)) + ((C(3) − C(2))²))
22317 := ((C(7) + C((1 + C(3)))) + 22)
22337 := (((−C(7)) − C(C(3))) + C((C(3) + C(2)))) − C(C(2)))
22355 := (−5) × ((C(5) × (−3)) − C((C(2) + C(2))))
22374 := ((4 − C(7)) × (−3 × 22))
22375 := (C(5) × (((7 × C(3)) − C(2)) − 2))
22392 := ((C(C(2)) × (−9)) + (C((32 − 2))))
22394 := (((C((4 + 9)) + C(C(3))) + 2) + C(C(2)))
22416 := (((−6) + C(14)) × C(2)) + C(C(2))
22427 := (C((7 × 2)) + C(C(((4 + 2)/2)))
22435 := (5 × (((3 + C(4))²) − 2))
22453 := (C(C(3)) + (−5) × (−(42) − C(C(2))))
22457 := (((−7) + C(((5 × 4) + C(2)))) + C(C(2)))
22462 := (((C((C(2) + 6))) + C(4)) × C(2)) − 2)
22464 := ((−4) × C(6)) × (−(4 + 22))
22466 := (−6) − (((C(6) − 4))²)/(−2))
22468 := ((−8) + ((C(6) − 4))²)/2)
22471 := (((−1) + C((7 × 4))) + C(2)) + C(C(2))
22472 := (((C((2 × 7)) + C(4)) × C(2)) + C(2))
22473 := (C(C(3)) + ((C(7) − C(4)) × (C(2) + 2)))
22489 := (C((9 + 8)) + C((4 + 22)))
22519 := ((9 × (−1) − (−5) × C(C(2)))) − C(C(2))
22524 := (−4) − (C(C(2)) × (−52) + C(2))
22532 := (((C(C(2)) × (C(3) − 5)) + 2) × 2)
22536 := (C(6) − ((C((C(3) − 5)) + C(C(2))) × (−2)))

- 22563 := ((C(C(3)) - C(6)) - ((-C(5)) + C(C(2))) × (-C(2)))
22564 := (C(4) + (((6 × (5²))²)))
22575 := ((5 × 7) × ((C(5) + C(2)) + C(C(2))))
22599 := ((C(9) - C((9 × 5)))/(-2 + 2))
22624 := (-((C(4) - C(2))) × ((C(6)/2) - C(C(2))))
22643 := ((C(C(3)) - C(4)) - (-6) × (C(C(2)) - C(2)))
22649 := (C(9) - ((-4) + C((6 + C(2)))) × (-C(2)))
22679 := ((C(9) + C((7 × (6 - 2)))) - 2)
22681 := (C((1 + 8)) + C((6 + 22)))
22682 := (((C(28) + C(6)) + C(C(2))) + 2)
22683 := (C(C(3)) + ((C((8 + 6)) + (2^{C(2)}))))
22689 := ((C(9) + 8) + C((6 + 22)))
22697 := (-C(7)) + ((9 + (6²)) × C(C(2)))
22729 := (-C((9 × 2))) + ((-C(7)) + C(C(2)))²)
22763 := (C(C(3)) + (((C(6) - C(7)) + C(C(2))) × C(2)))
22784 := (4 × (C(8) + (7²)))
22792 := (-((2 - 9)) × (C((7 × 2)) + C(C(2))))
22813 := -((C(C(3)) + (-((1 + 82)) × C(C(2))))))
22814 := (((4 × C(18)) - C(C(2))) - 2)
22815 := (C((5 + 18)) + C(22))
22849 := ((C(9) + C((4 × 8))) - C(22))
22875 := (C(5) × (7 + (8 × 22)))
22896 := (((C((6 + 9)) - C(8)) × C(2)) - C(2))
22923 := (C(3) × ((29²) + C(2)))
22932 := -((C(-((C(2) - C(3)))) - (C((9 + 22))))))
22935 := (-5) × (3 - (9 × (C(C(2)) - 2)))
22942 := (C((C(2) × 4)) + (C((9 + C(2))) × (-2)))
22944 := (-4) × (((4 - C(9)) + C(2)) × C(2))
22968 := -((((C(8) - C((6 + 9))) - C(2)) × C(2)))
22976 := -((((C(6) - (C(7) × 9)) × C(2)) - C(2)))
22995 := ((5 × 9) × ((-9) + C(C(2))) + C(2))
23087 := (((C(7) + C(8)) × C(03)) + 2)
23104 := ((C((4 + 01)) + C(3))²)
23125 := (-C(5)) × ((C((C(2) - 1)) + C(3))/(-2))
23134 := (43 × ((-1) + C(3)) + C(C(2)))
23143 := (C((C(3) - 4)) + (C((1 + C(3)))/2))
23168 := (((8 × C(6)) + C((1 + C(3)))) - C(C(2)))
23183 := (((C((C(3) + 8)) - 1) - C(C(3))) - C(2))
23193 := (-((3⁹) - 1)) + C((C(3) + C(2)))
23194 := ((C(((4 × 9) - 1)) - C(C(3))) + 2)
23243 := (C(C(3)) + (((-C(4)) + C(C(2))) - 3) × C(2))
23247 := ((-7) × (4 - C(C(2)))) + (C(C(3)) + C(2))
23256 := (C(6) + ((-5) × C(C(2))) × (-3²))
23264 := -((C(4) - (((6²)³)/2))
23272 := (C(2) × (-7) + ((2 × C(3))²))
23273 := (C(C(3)) + ((7 × C(C(2))) + (3 × 2)))
23275 := (((5 × 7)²) × (C(3) - C(2)))
23276 := (((C(6) + C((7 + C(2)))) + C(C(3))) + 2)
23283 := -((C(3) + ((C(8) - C(23)) × 2)))
23292 := ((C(C(2)) + (9 - C(23))) × (-2))
23293 := ((C((C(3) + 9))/2) - (C(3) + C(2)))
23324 := (-4) + (C(2) × ((C(3) + C(3))²))
23325 := (((C(5) + C(2)) - C(C(3))) + C((C(3) + C(2))))
23332 := ((C(2) + C((3 + 33)))/2)
23336 := ((C(6) × ((C(3) × 3) + C(3))) + C(2))
23344 := (-4) × (-4 - C(((3 × 3) × 2)))
23352 := (((C((2 × 5)) - C(3)) × 3) × C(2))
23364 := (4 × (C((6 × 3)) + (3²)))
23374 := (((4 - C((-7) + C(3))) + C(C(3))) × 2)
23375 := (C(5) × ((7 × (3³) - 2))
23389 := -((C((-((9 + 8)) + C(3))) - C((C(3) + 2))))
23398 := (((C(8) + C(9)) × 3) + C(C(3))) - C(2))
23424 := ((C(4) + (C(C(2)) × (4 - C(3)))) × (-2))
23436 := ((C(6) + C(((3 × 4) × 3)))/2)
23456 := (-((6⁵)) - (-((C(4) - 3)) × C(C(2))))
23463 := (C(3) × ((C(6) × 4) + (3 + 2)))
23465 := (((5 - (C(6) × (-4))) × C(3)) + 2)
23475 := (((C(5) × 7) + C(4)) × (C(3) - 2))
23479 := ((-9) + C((7 × 4))) + (3 × C(C(2)))
23483 := (C(C(3)) + (((C(8) - C(4)) + C(3)) × C(2)))
23488 := ((C(((8 + 8) + 4)) × 3) - C(C(2)))
23496 := ((((-6) - C(9)) × (-4)) - 3) × C(2))
23512 := -(((C(21) - 5)) - C(32))
23523 := (C(C(3)) + ((C(C(2)) - (5 + C(3))) × C(2)))
23537 := (((C(7) + C(35)) - C(C(3))) + 2)
23544 := ((C(4) + 45) × C((3 × 2)))
23552 := (C(C(2)) × (55 - (3²)))
23557 := ((7⁵) + (C((5 × 3)) × 2))
23563 := (C(C(3)) - ((C(6) - C(((5 + 3) × 2))))))
23569 := -(((C(9) + C(6)) - C(5))) + C((C(3) + 2))
23579 := ((-C(9)) - C(C((7 - 5)))) × (-C(3) - C(2))
23592 := (((C(2) + C(9)) × (5 + C(3))) + C(2))
23611 := ((C(11) × 6) + C((C(3) - 2)))
23617 := ((7 × C(-((1 - 6) × 3))) - C(2))

- 23623 := ((C((3 + 2)) × (C(6) - C(3))) - 2)
23624 := ((-4) × ((2 - C(6)) × C(3))) + C(C(2))
23625 := ((5 + 2) × C((6 + (3²))))
23627 := ((7 × C((2 × 6) + 3))) + 2
23633 := (-((C(3) + ((3⁶)))) + C((C(3) + 2)))
23639 := (-(((C(9) + C(3)) - (6))) + C((C(3) + 2)))
23652 := (C(C(-(2 - 5)))) + ((63²))
23654 := (-((C((4 + 5)) + (6))) + C((C(3) + 2)))
23657 := -(C(7) + (C(5) × (-6 × 32)))
23659 := (-((C(9) - ((5 - 6)))) + C((C(3) + 2)))
23667 := (-7) × (-6 - C((6 + (3²))))
23672 := -(((C(C(2)) - (C((7 × 6)/3)) + C(C(2))))
23673 := ((C((C(3) + (7))) - (6)) - C((C(3) - 2)))
23693 := (((C(3) - C(9)) + (6)) + C((C(3) + 2)))
23695 := (((C(5) + C(9 + 6))) + C(C(3))) + C(C(2))
23716 := (((C(6) × (-1)) + C(7)) + C(3))²
23723 := ((C(3) × (C(2) - C(7))) + C(32))
23724 := ((C(4) - C((2 + 7))) + C((C(3) + 2)))
23733 := (((-3) × C((3 × 7))) - C(C(3)))/(-2)
23734 := ((C(4) × (C(3) + C(7))) + (C(3) × 2))
23744 := (C(4) × ((-4) + C(7)) + 32)
23748 := ((8⁴) - (C((7 + C(3)))/(-2)))
23752 := -(((C(C(2)) + (C(5))) - C(((7 × 3) + C(2))))
23755 := (-C((5 × 5))) + ((-7) - C(C(3))) × (-2))
23759 := (((C(9) + C(5)) + (7)) × C(3)) + C(C(2))
23763 := (C(C(3)) + (-6) × ((C(7) - 3) × (-2)))
23764 := (((4⁶) - 7) + C(C(3))) - C(2)
23765 := ((56 - 7) × (-C(3)) + C(C(2)))
23769 := (C(9) + (((6 × 7) + 3) × C(C(2))))
23772 := (((C(C(2)) × 7) - (7)) + C(C(3))) + C(C(2))
23779 := (((C(C(9 - 7))) × 7) + C(C(3))) + C(C(2))
23781 := ((C(((1 + 8) + 7)) + C(C(3))) + 2)
23786 := (((C(6) + C((8 + 7))) + C(C(3))) + C(C(2)))
23788 := (((C((8 + 8)) + (7)) + C(C(3))) + 2)
23789 := (((C(9) + C((8 + 7))) + C(C(3))) + 2)
23793 := (3 × ((C(9) + C(7)) + C((C(3) - C(2))))
23803 := (C(C(3)) + ((C(08) + 3) × C(2)))
23807 := ((-70) - C(8)) + C((C(3) + 2))
23813 := (-((C((3 + 1)) + C(8))) + C((C(3) + 2)))
23814 := (-(((C(4) - 1) + C(8))) + C((C(3) + 2)))
23816 := ((-61) - C(8)) + C((C(3) + 2))
23823 := (C((C(3) + 2)) - (C(8) + (C(3) × 2)))
23824 := ((C(C(4)) + C(2)) - C((8 + (C(3) × 2))))
23825 := ((-52) - C(8)) + C((C(3) + 2))
23826 := (6 × (C((2 × 8)) - C((3 + 2))))
23827 := (((7 + C(C(2))) × 8) + C(C(3))) - C(2)
23834 := ((-43) - C(8)) + C((C(3) + 2))
23843 := (C(C(3)) + (C(4) + ((8³) × C(2))))
23852 := ((-25) - C(8)) + C((C(3) + 2))
23856 := ((-6) - (C(5) × (-8))) × (3 × C(2))
23861 := ((-16) - C(8)) + C((C(3) + 2))
23894 := -(C(4) + ((9 × C((8 + 3))) × (-2)))
23895 := ((5 × 9) × ((C(8) + C(3)) - C(2)))
23921 := -(((C(C((1 + 2))) - (C(9))) - C((C(3) + C(2))))
23923 := (((C((C(3) + C(2))) + (C(9))) - C(C(3))) + 2)
23927 := (C(7) - ((C(2) + C(9)) × (-32)))
23935 := (5 × ((C(C(3)) + (C(9))) - C((C(3) - 2))))
23953 := (C(C(3)) - ((C(5) + C(9)) × (-3 + 2)))
23955 := ((5 × (C(5) + C(9))) + C(C(3))) + 2
23956 := ((C((6 + 5)) × (-9) + C(3)) - 2)
23958 := ((C((8 - 5)) - 9) × C((3 + C(2))))
23966 := ((C(66)/(9 + 3)) + C(2))
23972 := (2 × (7 - (-9) × C((3 + C(2))))
23976 := (C(6) × (79 + 32))
23984 := (C((C(4) - 8)) - ((-C(9)) + C(C(3))) × C(2))
23992 := ((C(((2 + 9) + 9)) × 3) - C(2))
24064 := (C(4) × ((6 × C(04)) - C(2)))
24125 := (5 × (C((C(2) + 1)) + C((4²))))
24137 := ((7 × C((3 × (1 + 4)))) + C(C(2)))
24139 := ((C(9) × 3) + C((14 × 2)))
24149 := (C((9 + 4)) + C((14 × 2)))
24157 := -((C(7) + (C(5) × (-14²))))
24167 := (C((7 + 6)) × (-((1 - 4) + C(2)))
24176 := (((C(6) × (-7)) + 1) × (-4²))
24184 := ((C((4 + 8)) × 14) - C(2))
24192 := ((C(C(2)) + (C((9 + 1)))) × (4²))
24194 := ((-((4⁹)) + C((-1) + C(4))) × (-2))
24253 := (-3) + (((-C(5)) + C(C(2))) × C(4)) - C(C(2)))
24256 := (C((6 × 5)) - C(((2⁴) - 2))
24258 := (((C(8) - C(5)) - C(2)) × C(4)) + 2
24264 := ((C(C(4)) - (C(62) + C(4))) + C(C(2)))
24276 := ((6 × 7) × (C(C(2)) + (C(4) + 2)))
24283 := (C(C(3)) + (((C(8) - C(2)) + C((4²))))
24293 := (C(C(3)) + ((9 × C((2 × 4))) + 2))

$$\begin{aligned} 24318 &:= ((8 - C((C((1 \times 3) - (4)))) \times (-2)) \\ 24322 &:= (((2 - C(23)) + (4)) \times (-2)) \\ 24323 &:= ((C((32 - 3)) - C(4)) - 2) \\ 24325 &:= (C((5 + (C(2) \times 3))) - C((-4) + C(2))) \\ 24326 &:= ((-((6 - 2)) + C((C(3) - (4)))) \times 2) \\ 24327 &:= (-7) - (C(23) \times (-4 - 2)) \\ 24328 &:= (-8) - ((-2) \times C((C(3) - (4)))) - 2) \\ 24329 &:= (-9) - ((-2) - C((C(3) - (4)))) \times 2) \\ 24331 &:= (-((1 \times 3)) - (C((C(3) - (4))) \times (-2))) \\ 24332 &:= ((C(23) + ((3 - 4))) \times 2) \\ 24333 &:= (-((3/3)) - (C((C(3) - (4))) \times (-2))) \\ 24334 &:= (((-4) + C(3))^3) \times (4 - 2) \\ 24335 &:= (-5) - ((-3) - C((C(3) - (4)))) \times 2) \\ 24341 &:= (-1) - ((-4) - C((C(3) - (4)))) \times 2) \\ 24342 &:= ((2 \times C((-4) + C(3))) + (4 \times 2)) \\ 24346 &:= ((-6) - C((-4) + C(3))) \times (-4 - 2) \\ 24352 &:= (C(2) + ((-5) - C((C(3) - (4)))) \times (-2)) \\ 24354 &:= ((4 \times 5) - (C((C(3) - (4))) \times (-2))) \\ 24356 &:= (((6 + 5) + C((C(3) - (4)))) \times 2) \\ 24357 &:= (C(((7 - 5) + C(3))) - (C(4)/2)) \\ 24359 &:= (-C(9)) - (-((53 - 4)) \times C(C(2))) \\ 24362 &:= (((C(2) + (6)) + C((C(3) - (4)))) \times 2) \\ 24375 &:= (C(5) \times ((7 \times C(3)) + (4 + 2))) \\ 24376 &:= (((C(6) - C(7)) \times (-3)) \times C(4)) - C(2) \\ 24381 &:= (C((1 + ((8 \times 3) + 4))) - C(2)) \\ 24384 &:= ((-4) + C(8)) \times (3 \times (4^2)) \\ 24385 &:= ((C((5 + (8 \times 3))) + (4)) - C(2)) \\ 24387 &:= (C(((7 \times 8) - C(3))) - (4 - 2)) \\ 24388 &:= (-((8/8)) + C((C(3) + (4 - 2)))) \\ 24389 &:= C(((9 \times (8 - 3)) - (4^2))) \\ 24391 &:= (C(((1 \times 93) - C(4))) + 2) \\ 24392 &:= (C(29) - (((3 - 4) - 2))) \\ 24394 &:= (-((4 - 9)) + C((C(3) + (4 - 2)))) \\ 24397 &:= (C(((7 \times 9) - 34)) + C(2)) \\ 24423 &:= (C((C(3) + 2)) + ((C(4) + (4))/2)) \\ 24432 &:= ((C(C(2)) - 3) \times (C(4) - ((4^2)))) \\ 24453 &:= (C((-35) + C(4)) + C((-4) + C(2))) \\ 24455 &:= ((C(((5 \times 5) + 4)) + C(4)) + 2) \\ 24456 &:= (-6) \times ((5 \times 4) - C((4^2))) \\ 24464 &:= -((C(4) + (-6) \times (C((4 \times 4)) - C(2)))) \\ 24472 &:= (C(2) \times (C((7 + 4)) + C((4 + C(2)))) \\ 24512 &:= (((2 + 1) \times C((5 \times 4))) + C(C(2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24525 &:= (-5) \times (C(2) - C(((5 + 4) + C(2)))) \\ 24545 &:= (-5) \times (4 - C(((5 + 4) + C(2)))) \\ 24552 &:= (((C(2) + ((5^5))) - C(4)) \times C(2)) \\ 24557 &:= ((7^5) + (C(5) \times (C(4) - 2))) \\ 24565 &:= (5 \times C(((6 + 5) + 4) + 2)) \\ 24568 &:= (((C(8) \times 6) - (5 - 4)) \times C(2)) \\ 24571 &:= ((C(17) \times 5) + (4 + 2)) \\ 24573 &:= (((C((C(3) + (7))) \times 5) + C(4))/C(2)) \\ 24576 &:= (6 \times C(((7 - 5) \times 4) \times 2)) \\ 24578 &:= ((C(8) \times ((7 + 5) \times 4)) + 2) \\ 24589 &:= (((C(9) - 8) \times C(5)) - (4^{C(2)})) \\ 24596 &:= (C(C(-((6 - 9)))) + C(((5 + 4) + C(2)))) \\ 24603 &:= (C(3) - ((0 - 6) \times C((4^2)))) \\ 24608 &:= (((C(8) \times 06) + (4)) \times C(2)) \\ 24624 &:= (((C(C(4)) + C(C(2))) \times 6)/C((-4) + C(2))) \\ 24632 &:= (((C(2) - C(3)) \times (-6^4)) + C(2)) \\ 24635 &:= (5 \times (C(3) + ((6 + C(4))^2)) \\ 24636 &:= (6 \times ((C(3) \times (C(6) - C(4))) + 2)) \\ 24657 &:= -((C(7) - (C(5) \times (C(6) - ((4^2)))))) \\ 24665 &:= (C(5) - (-6) \times (-6) + C((4^2))) \\ 24672 &:= ((-2) + (C(7) \times 6)) \times (4 + C(2)) \\ 24693 &:= (-3) - (-9) \times C((6 + (4 \times 2))) \\ 24696 &:= (((C(6) + 9) + C(6)) \times (C(4) - C(2))) \\ 24712 &:= (((C((C(2) + 1)) - C(7)) \times C(4)) + C(2)) \\ 24732 &:= ((C(2) + C(C(3))) + ((7 + C(4))^2)) \\ 24747 &:= ((C(7) - (4)) \times ((7 + C(4)) + 2)) \\ 24749 &:= (((9 + C(4)) \times (C(7) - (4))) + 2) \\ 24759 &:= -((C(9) - ((C(5) - (7)) \times C((4 + 2)))))) \\ 24772 &:= -((C(C(2)) + ((7 \times 7) \times (-4) - C(C(2)))))) \\ 24792 &:= (C(2) \times ((9 \times C(7)) + (4)) + C(2)) \\ 24813 &:= (C(3) \times ((C(-((1 - 8))) + C(4)) + C(C(2)))) \\ 24816 &:= (-6) \times (((-1) - C(8)) - (4)) \times C(2) \\ 24837 &:= ((C(((7 \times 3) + 8)) - C(4)) + C(C(2))) \\ 24862 &:= (((C(C(2)) - C(6)) \times 84) - 2) \\ 24864 &:= ((-4) \times (6 + C(8))) \times (-4 - C(2)) \\ 24875 &:= (C(5) \times (C(7) - ((8 + 4)^2))) \\ 24894 &:= ((49 \times (C(8) - (4))) + 2) \\ 24895 &:= (5 \times ((C((9 + 8)) + C(4)) + 2)) \\ 24897 &:= -((((C(7) - C(9)) \times (C(8) + (4)))/C(2))) \\ 24925 &:= (5 \times (C((C(2) + 9)) + ((C(4) + C(2)))) \\ 24929 &:= (C(9) + (C(2) \times ((-9) + C(4))^2)) \\ 24964 &:= (4 \times (((6 + 9) + C(4))^2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 24965 &:= ((C((5 + (C(6)/9))) + C(4)) + C(C(2))) \\ 24976 &:= ((C(6) \times (-7) + C((9 - 4))) - C(C(2))) \\ 25002 &:= ((200 \times C(5)) + 2) \\ 25137 &:= (C((7 \times 3)) + ((1 + C(5))^2)) \\ 25255 &:= ((C(55) - C(C(2))) - (C(52))) \\ 25257 &:= -((C(7) - (((5 \times (2^5))^2))) \\ 25262 &:= (-2) - ((C(6) \times (C(2) - C(5))) + C(2)) \\ 25264 &:= ((C((C(4) - C((6/2)))) - (C(5)))/2) \\ 25265 &:= (-5) - ((C(6) \times (C(2) - C(5))) + 2) \\ 25267 &:= (-7) - ((C(6) \times (C(2) - C(5))) - 2) \\ 25269 &:= -((C(9) - (((C(6) - C(2)) \times C(5)) - 2)) \\ 25272 &:= (-27) \times ((C(2) - C(5)) \times C(2)) \\ 25277 &:= (-7) \times ((-7) \times C(C(2))) - C((5 - 2))) \\ 25284 &:= ((4 + C(8)) \times ((2 + 5)^2)) \\ 25298 &:= (C(8) + (C(9) \times ((2^5) + 2))) \\ 25324 &:= ((C((C((-4) + C(2))) - C(3))) - (5))/2) \\ 25327 &:= (C((7 + C(2))) + C((3 + (5^2)))) \\ 25334 &:= ((C((C(4) - C(3))) + (3 \times 5))/2) \\ 25344 &:= -(((C(C(4)) - C((C(4) - ((3 - 5)))))) + C(2)) \\ 25348 &:= (((C(8) + C((-4) + C(3)))) - (5)) \times 2) \\ 25353 &:= (3 \times (C((-5) + C(3))) - C((5 + C(2)))) \\ 25368 &:= (((8 - C(6)) \times (3 - C(5))) - C(2)) \\ 25375 &:= (C(5) \times (7 + ((C(3) - C(5)) \times (-2)))) \\ 25389 &:= ((C(9) - (8^3)) \times (C(5) - C(2))) \\ 25392 &:= ((C(29) + 3) + C((5 \times 2))) \\ 25398 &:= (((8 \times C(9)) + C(C(3))) - ((C(5) - C(2)))) \\ 25433 &:= (C(C(3)) - (((C(3) - 4) \times C(5)) \times (-2))) \\ 25443 &:= (C(C(3)) - (C(4) \times (-45 \times 2))) \\ 25475 &:= (-5) \times ((-7) \times C((4 + 5))) + C(2)) \\ 25489 &:= ((C(9) - 8) + (C(4) \times (-C(5)) + C(C(2)))) \\ 25497 &:= ((((-7) \times C(9)) + 4) \times (-5)) + 2) \\ 25512 &:= (C(C(2)) + (((1 \times 5)^5) \times C(2))) \\ 25523 &:= ((C(C(3)) + C(2)) + C(((5 + 5) + C(2)))) \\ 25528 &:= (C(8) + (C(2) \times ((5^5) + 2))) \\ 25536 &:= ((6 \times (C(3) + 5)) \times (C(5) + C(2))) \\ 25544 &:= ((C(4) + ((4 + (5^5)))) \times C(2)) \\ 25552 &:= (C(C(2)) + (((5^5) + 5) \times C(2))) \\ 25569 &:= (C(9) + (C(6) \times (C(5) - (5 \times 2)))) \\ 25573 &:= -((C(3) - (((7 \times 5) + C(5))^2)) \\ 25576 &:= ((C((6 + 7)) + C((5 + 5))) \times C(2)) \\ 25592 &:= ((C(C(2)) \times ((9 \times 5) + 5)) - C(2)) \\ 25595 &:= (-5) + (((9 \times 5) + 5) \times C(C(2))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25598 &:= ((C(8) \times ((9 \times 5) + 5)) - 2) \\ 25623 &:= ((((-3) - C(2)) + C(6)) \times C(5)) - 2) \\ 25624 &:= ((C((C(4) + 2))/(6 + 5)) - C(C(2))) \\ 25625 &:= (C(5) \times (((2 + C(6)) - (5)) - C(2))) \\ 25627 &:= ((7^2) \times ((6 + 5) + C(C(2)))) \\ 25629 &:= ((C(92) - C((C(6) - C(5)))) + C(C(2))) \\ 25657 &:= -(((C(7) - C((5 \times 6))) + C((5 \times 2))) \\ 25717 &:= ((C(7) \times (1 \times 75)) - C(2)) \\ 25725 &:= (((5 - 2) \times C(7)) \times (5^2)) \\ 25726 &:= (((C(6) + 2) \times (-7) + C(5)) + 2) \\ 25727 &:= (((7 + C(2)) \times C(7)) \times 5) + 2) \\ 25728 &:= ((C(8) + (C(2) \times (C(7) - (5)))) \times C(2)) \\ 25729 &:= (C(9) + ((-((2 - 7)^5) \times C(2))) \\ 25732 &:= (C((2 + C(3))) + ((C(7) + C((5 \times 2)))) \\ 25735 &:= (-5) \times (((3 \times C(7)) \times (-5)) - 2) \\ 25759 &:= -((C(9) - C(((5 \times 7) - 5))) - C(C(2))) \\ 25792 &:= ((C(C(2)) - (9 + 7)) \times 52) \\ 25839 &:= -((C(9) - ((C(3) \times 8) \times (C(5) - 2))) \\ 25852 &:= -((C(C(2)) - ((5 - C(8)) \times (-52))) \\ 25857 &:= -((7 - 58) \times (-5) + C(C(2))) \\ 25863 &:= (((3 + C(6)) - 8) \times C(5)) - C(C(2)) \\ 25865 &:= (((-5) - C(6)) \times (8 - C(5))) + C(2) \\ 25875 &:= (C(5) \times (7 + (8 \times (5^2)))) \\ 25921 &:= (((C((1 + 2)) + 9) + C(5))^2) \\ 25935 &:= ((5 \times 3) \times (C(9) + C((5 \times 2)))) \\ 25947 &:= ((C(7) - C(4)) \times (95 - 2)) \\ 25948 &:= ((C(8) - (4 + 9)) \times 52) \\ 25973 &:= ((37 \times C(9)) - C((5 \times 2))) \\ 25984 &:= ((C(4) - C(8)) \times ((9 - C(5))/2)) \\ 25986 &:= (((C(6) + 8) \times (-9) + C(5)) + 2) \\ 25992 &:= (((C(C(2)) + (9 - C(9))) \times (-C(5))) - C(2)) \\ 25994 &:= (((-4) \times C(9)) \times (-9)) + (C(5) \times (-2)) \\ 25998 &:= -((((C(8) + 9) - C(9)) \times C(5)) + 2) \\ 26083 &:= (C(C(3)) + ((80^{-6+C(2)})) \\ 26112 &:= (C(C(2)) \times (-11 - 62)) \\ 26113 &:= -((C(C(3)) - ((-((1 + 1)) + C(6))^2)) \\ 26125 &:= (C(5) \times (((2 - 1) + C(6)) - C(2))) \\ 26136 &:= (((C(6) + C(3)) - 1) \times C(6))/2) \\ 26144 &:= (((-4) + C((4 + 1))) \times C(6)) + C(2) \\ 26196 &:= (-6) \times ((C(9) \times (-1 \times 6)) + C(2)) \\ 26199 &:= (-9) + ((C(9) - 1) \times (6^2)) \\ 26232 &:= (((-2) \times (3^{C(2)})) + (6)) \times (-2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26233 &:= (-3 - ((C((C(3) \times 2))/(-6)) + C(2))) \\ 26236 &:= (((6 \times C(3))^2 - (6 + 2)) \\ 26237 &:= (-7) + ((3^{C(2)}) \times (6 - 2)) \\ 26238 &:= -((C(8) - (C((3 + 2)) \times (C(6) - 2)))) \\ 26242 &:= ((C((-2) + C(4)) - C(2))/6) - 2 \\ 26246 &:= ((C((C(6)/(-4) + C(2)))/6) + 2) \\ 26269 &:= -(((C(9) - C((6^2) - 6))) + 2) \\ 26272 &:= ((C((C(2) + 7)) \times 2) - C(6)) - C(C(2))) \\ 26279 &:= -(((C(9) - C((7 - 2) \times 6))) - C(2)) \\ 26288 &:= ((88 - C(C(2))) \times (-62)) \\ 26312 &:= ((2 \times (-1) + C(3)) \times (-6) + C(C(2))) \\ 26322 &:= ((-2) + C((2 + 3))) \times (C(6) - 2) \\ 26326 &:= ((-C(6)) + C(-((C(2) - C(3)))) + (C(C((6/2)))) \\ 26329 &:= (C(9) + ((-2) + (C(3) \times 6))^2) \\ 26344 &:= ((4 - ((C(4) - 3) \times C(6))) \times (-2)) \\ 26346 &:= (-6) + (((C(4) - 3) \times C(6)) \times 2) \\ 26364 &:= (C(((4 + 6) + 3)) \times (6 \times 2)) \\ 26372 &:= ((2^7) + ((C(3) \times 6)^2)) \\ 26384 &:= ((C(4) + ((C(8) + C(3)) \times 6)) \times C(2)) \\ 26424 &:= (-((C(4) - C((24 + 6)))) - C(C(2))) \\ 26432 &:= (((2 \times C(3)) + C(4)) \times (C(6) + C(2))) \\ 26433 &:= ((C((C(3) + 3))/4) + C(C((6/2)))) \\ 26482 &:= ((C(-((2 - (8 \times 4)))) - (6)) - C(C(2))) \\ 26488 &:= -((C(8) - C((8 + ((4 \times 6) - 2)))) \\ 26494 &:= ((C(4) \times (9 \times 46)) - 2) \\ 26496 &:= ((C(6) - 9) \times (C(4) + C((6 - 2)))) \\ 26512 &:= (C(C(2)) + (C((1 \times 5)) \times (C(6) - C(2)))) \\ 26521 &:= -((C((1 + C(2))) - (C(5) \times (C(6) + 2)))) \\ 26523 &:= ((C(3) - C(C(2))) + (C((5 \times 6)) + C(2))) \\ 26526 &:= (((C(6) - 2) \times C(5)) - C(6)) - C(2) \\ 26529 &:= -(((C(9) - C(2)) - (C(5) \times (C(6) + 2)))) \\ 26536 &:= ((-6) + C(C(3))) + C(((5 + 6) + C(2))) \\ 26542 &:= (C((24 - 5)) + C(C((6/2)))) \\ 26546 &:= (((-6) + C(4)) + C((5 \times 6))) - C(C(2)) \\ 26557 &:= (-(((7^5) \times 5)) + C((6 \times C(2)))) \\ 26563 &:= (((-3) + C(6)) \times C(5)) - (62) \\ 26564 &:= (((-4) + C(6)) \times C(5)) + C((6 - 2)) \\ 26566 &:= -(((C(6) + C(6)) - C((5 \times 6))) + 2) \\ 26587 &:= (C(7) + ((C((8 - 5)) \times 6)^2)) \\ 26596 &:= (((6 - 9) + C(5)) \times (C(6) + 2)) \\ 26624 &:= ((C(4) - (2 \times 6)) \times C((6 + 2))) \\ 26625 &:= (C(5) \times (((-2) \times C(6)) + (6))/(-2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 26643 &:= (C(C(3)) + (((4 \times C(6)) + (6)) \times C(2))) \\ 26653 &:= (-3) + ((C(5) - (6)) \times (C(6) + C(2))) \\ 26654 &:= ((((-4) + C(5)) \times C(6)) + (6)) + C(C(2)) \\ 26656 &:= ((6 - C(5)) \times ((-6) - C(6)) - 2) \\ 26657 &:= -((C(7) - ((5 \times 6)^{6/2})) \\ 26676 &:= -(((C((6 \times 7)) - C(66))/C(2))) \\ 26688 &:= ((((-8) - C(8)) \times (-6)) + C(6)) \times C(2) \\ 26697 &:= ((7 \times C((9 + 6))) - (-6 \times C(C(2)))) \\ 26723 &:= (-C(3) - (C(-((2 - 7))) \times (-C(6) - 2))) \\ 26729 &:= (C(9) - (C(-((2 - 7))) \times (-C(6) - C(2)))) \\ 26733 &:= (3 \times ((C(3) \times (C(7) + (6))) - C(C(2)))) \\ 26744 &:= (((C(4) + C(4)) \times (-7) + C(6))) - C(2) \\ 26746 &:= (-6) + (C(4) \times ((7 - C(6)) \times (-2))) \\ 26752 &:= (((C(2) + 5) \times C(7)) \times 6) - 2 \\ 26764 &:= ((C(4) \times (C(6) - 7)) + (6)) \times 2 \\ 26765 &:= ((C((5 \times 6)) - C(7)) - (C(6)/(-2))) \\ 26768 &:= (8 \times (((C(6) + C(7)) \times 6) - C(2))) \\ 26782 &:= ((C((2 \times (8 + 7))) - C(6)) - 2) \\ 26823 &:= (C(C(3)) + ((2 - C(8)) \times (-6) - C(2))) \\ 26837 &:= (C((7 \times 3)) + C((-8 + C(6))/C(2))) \\ 26863 &:= (C(C(3)) - (C(6) - (86^2))) \\ 26875 &:= (C(5) \times ((-((7 - 8)) + C(6)) - 2)) \\ 26919 &:= (-C(9)) + (((1 \times 9) \times 6) \times C(C(2))) \\ 26924 &:= (((-4) + C(C(2))) \times (-9 - 62)) \\ 26928 &:= (-8) - ((C(2) - C((9 + 6))) \times C(2)) \\ 26934 &:= (((-C(4)) + C((C(3) + (9 - 6)))) - 2) \\ 26936 &:= (C((6/3)) \times (C((9 + 6)) - C(2))) \\ 26944 &:= -(((C(4) - C(((4 \times 9) - 6))) - C(2))) \\ 26946 &:= ((C(6)/(-4)) + C(((9 + 6) \times 2))) \\ 26952 &:= ((C(2) \times (-5) + C((9 + 6)))) - C(2) \\ 26954 &:= ((C((4 \times 5)) - C(9)) + C(C((6/2)))) \\ 26955 &:= (-5) - ((5 - C((9 + 6))) \times C(2)) \\ 26958 &:= ((8 \times (-5) + C((9 + 6)))) - 2 \\ 26965 &:= ((C((5 \times 6)) - C((9 - 6))) - C(2)) \\ 26968 &:= (8 \times (C((6 + 9)) - (6 - 2))) \\ 26982 &:= (-2) + (8 \times (C((9 + 6)) - 2)) \\ 26984 &:= ((C(4)/8) \times (C((9 + 6)) - 2)) \\ 26986 &:= -((6 + 8) + C(((9 + 6) \times 2))) \\ 26989 &:= (-9) - ((-8) \times C((9 + 6))) + 2) \\ 26991 &:= -((1 \times 9) + C(((9 + 6) \times 2))) \\ 26992 &:= (C(((2 \times (9 + 9)) - 6)) - C(2)) \\ 26995 &:= (-5) + C(((9 + 9) + (6 \times 2))) \end{aligned}$$

- 26999 := $(-(9/9) + C((9+6) \times 2))$
 27048 := $((C(8) + 40) \times 7^2)$
 27056 := $(C((6 \times 5)) + (07 \times C(2)))$
 27064 := $(C(4) + C((6 \times (07 - 2))))$
 27088 := $-(C(8) + (-80) \times (C(7) + 2))$
 27097 := $(C(7) \times ((-90) - C(7)) + C(C(2)))$
 27125 := $(C(5) + C((21 + 7) + 2))$
 27132 := $(C((2 + C(3))) + (-1) + C((7 \times 2)))$
 27133 := $(C((C(3) + (3 - 1))) + C((7 \times 2)))$
 27136 := $((C(6) \times ((3 - 1)^7)) - C(C(2)))$
 27145 := $(-5) \times ((-4) - C(17)) - C(C(2))$
 27156 := $(-6) \times (-((C(5) + C(17))) + C(C(2)))$
 27216 := $(C(6) \times (((1 \times 2)^7) - 2))$
 27225 := $((C(5) + (C(2) \times (-2 - 7)))^2)$
 27232 := $((2 + C(3)) + C((C(2) + (7)))) \times C(2)$
 27235 := $(-C(5)) - (32 \times (-C(7)) - C(C(2)))$
 27244 := $((44 + C(C(2))) \times 7^2)$
 27256 := $(C((6 \times 5)) + (2^7) \times 2)$
 27262 := $(C(C(2)) + ((C(6) - 2) \times C((7 - 2))))$
 27264 := $(C(4) \times ((62 \times 7) - C(2)))$
 27265 := $((C(5) \times (C(6) + 2)) + (7 + C(2)))$
 27285 := $((C(5) - C((8 \times 2))) \times (-7)) - C(C(2))$
 27328 := $((C(8) - (C(2) \times 3)) \times (7 \times C(2)))$
 27334 := $(C(4) - ((C(3) + C(3)) \times (7 - C(C(2))))$
 27335 := $((C((5 \times (3 + 3))) + C(7)) - C(2))$
 27341 := $(C(-((1 - 4)) + C(3))) + ((C(7) - 2))$
 27342 := $((2 - C(4)) \times (-((3 \times 7)^2))$
 27348 := $((C(8) + (4)) \times (-3) + (7 \times C(2)))$
 27352 := $(-C(2)) - ((5 + C(3)) \times (-C(7)) - C(C(2)))$
 27355 := $(-5) - ((5 + C(3)) \times (-C(7)) - C(C(2)))$
 27363 := $(C(C(3)) + (C(C((6/3))) \times (7 + C(2))))$
 27369 := $(-9) - ((6 \times C(3)) \times (C(7) - C(C(2))))$
 27376 := $-((((C(6) - C(7)) \times C(3)) + (7)) \times C(2))$
 27384 := $((((-4) - C(8)) + C(3)) \times (-7)) \times C(2)$
 27423 := $(C(C(3)) + ((C(C(2)) + (4)) \times (7 + C(2))))$
 27424 := $(C(4) - ((C(2) \times 4) \times (-C(7)) - C(C(2))))$
 27432 := $((-C(2)) + C((C(3) + (4 + 7))))/2$
 27433 := $(-3) - (C((C(3) + (4 + 7)))/(-2))$
 27434 := $((4 \times C(((3 \times 4) + 7))) - 2)$
 27436 := $(C(-(((6 + 3) - 47)))/2)$
 27442 := $((2^4 + C(4)) \times C(7)) + 2$
 27448 := $((C(8) - C(4)) + C(((4 \times 7) + 2)))$
 27456 := $(C((6 \times 5)) - ((C(4) \times (-7)) - C(2)))$
 27465 := $((C((5 \times 6)) - 47) + C(C(2)))$
 27485 := $-((((C(5) - C(8)) \times (C(4) + (7))) - C(2)))$
 27496 := $((((C(6) + C(9)) \times 4) - C(7)) \times C(2))$
 27512 := $(C(C(2)) + C(((1 + 5) \times (7 - 2))))$
 27523 := $(C(C(3)) + ((C(C(2)) + ((C(5) + C(7)))) \times C(2)))$
 27546 := $(-6) \times ((C((4 + 5)) \times (-7)) + C(C(2)))$
 27549 := $(-9) \times (C(4) - (5^{7-2}))$
 27556 := $((6 + C(5)) + (5 \times 7))^2$
 27561 := $(((-1) + C(6)) \times C(5)) + (C(7) \times 2)$
 27568 := $((C(8) + C((6 \times 5))) + (7 \times C(2)))$
 27584 := $-((C(4) - (C(8) \times (5 + 7^2))))$
 27634 := $((4^3 \times C(6)) - (7)) \times 2$
 27642 := $(C(2) + ((C((4 \times 6)) - (7)) \times 2))$
 27644 := $(-4) + (C(4) \times (6 \times 72))$
 27646 := $(((-6) - C((4 \times 6))) + (7)) \times (-2)$
 27648 := $(C(8) \times ((4 \times (6 + 7)) + 2))$
 27653 := $((3 + C(5)) \times C(6)) + (7 - 2)$
 27657 := $((7 + C(5)) \times C(6)) - C(7) - C(C(2))$
 27662 := $((-((2^6)) \times C(6)) - (7)) \times (-2)$
 27664 := $(-C(46)) + C(((6 \times 7) + C(2)))$
 27683 := $(C(C(3)) - ((C(8) + (C(6) \times (-7))) \times C(2)))$
 27684 := $((-4) + (C(8) \times (-6))) \times (-7 + 2)$
 27688 := $(8 \times (86 + C((7 + C(2))))$
 27729 := $(C(9) + C((2 + ((7 + 7) \times 2))))$
 27746 := $((C((6 \times 4)) + ((7 \times 7))) \times 2)$
 27755 := $(-((C(5) \times (C(5) - C(7))) + (7))) + C(C(2))$
 27768 := $((C(8) \times 6) + (C(7) \times 72))$
 27791 := $(-1) + ((C(9) - C(7)) \times 72)$
 27792 := $(C(2) + ((C(9) + C((7 + 7))) \times C(2)))$
 27795 := $((C(5) - C((9 + 7))) \times (-7)) - 2$
 27797 := $((7 - C(9)) \times 77)/(-2)$
 27816 := $(61 \times (C(8) - (7 \times C(2))))$
 27817 := $(-C(7) + (-((1 - (8 \times 7))) \times C(C(2))))$
 27857 := $(-7) + ((C(5) - C(8)) \times (-72))$
 27864 := $((4 \times C(6)) + C(((8 + 7) \times 2)))$
 27866 := $((C(6) \times (C(6) - (87))) + 2)$
 27875 := $((C(5) \times 7) + C(((8 + 7) \times 2)))$
 27936 := $((C(6)/3) \times ((C(9) - C(7)) + 2))$
 27945 := $((5 + 4) \times 9) \times (C(7) + 2)$
 27963 := $(C(C(3)) + ((C(6)/9) \times (C(7) + 2)))$
 27973 := $(C((C(3) - ((7 - 9)))) - (-7) \times C(C(2)))$

- 27974 := ((C(4) + (7)) × ((C(9) - C(7)) + C(2)))
28032 := ((C(2) + C(30)) + (C(8) × 2))
28123 := (-3) + (C((C(2) - 1)) × 82))
28125 := (C(5) × ((C(2) + 1) + C((8 - 2))))
28126 := (C(((6 + 2) - 1)) × 82)
28128 := ((82 × C(-((1 - 8)))) + 2)
28165 := ((C(5) + (6)) × (-1) + C((8 - 2)))
28217 := (-7) × (1 + ((C(2) - C(8)) × C(2)))
28249 := (C(9) + (C(4) × (C(C(2)) - (82))))
28272 := (((C(2) × 7) × (2 + C(8))) - C(C(2)))
28297 := (((C(7) × (9²)) + C(8)) + 2)
28323 := (C(3) × ((-2) + C(3)) + (C(8) × 2))
28324 := (-4) × (-((C(2) + (3⁸))) - C(C(2)))
28333 := (C((C(3) + 3)) + ((C((3 + 8)) + 2)))
28334 := ((C((4 + 3)) + C((3 × 8))) × 2)
28371 := (-1) + ((C(7) + 3) × 82))
28387 := ((C(7) × 83) - (82))
28439 := ((C(9) × (C(3) + (4 + 8))) + C(2))
28448 := ((8 - C(4)) × ((-4) - C(8)) + C(2))
28485 := ((C(58) + C((4 × 8)))/C(2))
28512 := (((C(2) - 1) + C(5)) × C((8 - 2)))
28513 := (C((C(3) + 1)) + (-((5 - 8)^{C(2)}))
28576 := ((C(6) × (7 + C(5))) + ((8²)))
28618 := ((C((8 - 1)) + (6)) × 82)
28624 := (((C((4²)) - (6)) - C(8)) × C(2))
28643 := (C(C(3)) + (-4) × ((C(6) × (-8)) - C(C(2))))
28648 := (((C(8)/4) × C(6)) + C((8 + 2)))
28653 := -((C(3) + ((-56) × C(8)) - C(2)))
28657 := (-7) + ((56 × C(8)) - C(2))
28671 := (-1) + (7 × C(((6 + 8) + 2)))
28672 := ((C(2) - (7 - 6)) × C((8 × 2)))
28688 := (8 × (((C(8) × 6) + C(8)) + 2))
28704 := ((4 + (07 × C(8))) × C(2))
28721 := ((-1) + C(2)) × (7 + C((8 × 2)))
28726 := (((-C(6)) - C((C(2) + (7)))) × (-8)) - 2)
28728 := ((C(8) - C(2)) × (-7 - (8²)))
28736 := (C((6/3)) × ((7 × C(8)) + C(2)))
28748 := ((84 × C(7)) - (8²))
28752 := (((2 × 5) - (-7) × C(8)) × C(2))
28759 := (-((9⁵)) + (C((7 × 8))/2))
28776 := (((6 + 7) - (-7) × C(8)) × C(2))
28781 := (-1) - ((-8) - C(7)) × 82))
28782 := (((2 + C(8)) × (7 × 8)) - 2)
28784 := (((C(4)/8) × 7) × (C(8) + 2))
28791 := (-1) - (((-9) × C(7)) - C(8)) × C(2))
28792 := (((C(2) × 9) × C(7)) + C((8 × 2)))
28864 := (((-4) × C(6)) + C(8)) × (-82))
28875 := (C(5) × ((7 + 8) + C((8 - 2))))
28904 := ((40 × C(9)) - (C(8)/2))
28952 := (C(2) + ((C(5) + 9) × C((8 - 2))))
28963 := (((-3) - (-6) × C((9 + 8))) - C(C(2)))
28968 := -((C(8) + ((-6) × C((9 + 8))) - 2))
28986 := (6 × (C((8 + 9)) - (82)))
29014 := (((C(C(4)) - C(10))/9) - 2)
29115 := (-5) × (1 + ((1 - C(9)) × C(2)))
29125 := (-5) × ((C(2) - 1) - C((9 × 2)))
29134 := (((C(4) + C(31)) - C(9)) + C(2))
29135 := (-5) × (-3) + ((1 - C(9)) × C(2))
29145 := (-5) × ((4 - 1) - C((9 × 2)))
29152 := (((C(2) × 5) × C((1 × 9))) - C(2))
29155 := (-5) - (-5) × C(((1 × 9) × 2))
29157 := (C((7 × 5)) + (C(19) × (-2)))
29158 := (((8 × 5) × C((1 × 9))) - 2)
29174 := ((C(4) - (7 - 1)) × (-9) + C(C(2)))
29182 := ((C(C(2)) × ((C(8) + 1)/9)) - 2)
29184 := (C(4) × (((C(8) + 1)/9) × C(2)))
29234 := (((-C(4)) - C((3 × C(2)))) - (C(9))) × (-2))
29241 := (((C(-((1 - 4))) - C(2)) × 9)²)
29245 := (C(5) - (((C(C(4)) + C(2))/(-9)) + C(2)))
29247 := ((7 × (C((4²)) + 9)) + C(C(2)))
29248 := (8 × (((-C(4)) + C(C(2))) + 9) × C(2))
29272 := -((C(C(2)) + (7 - C((29 + 2))))
29275 := (-5) × (-7) - ((2 + C(9)) × C(2))
29279 := (C(((9 - 7) + 29)) - C(C(2)))
29302 := (C((2 + C(03))) + C((9 + C(2))))
29316 := (-6) × (C((1 × 3)) - C((9 + C(2))))
29317 := -((C(7) - ((-1) - C(39))/(-2)))
29326 := (62 × (-39) + C(C(2)))
29335 := (-5) × ((-C(3)) - C((C(3) - 9))) - C(2))
29342 := (((-2) + C((4 × 3))) × (9 + C(2)))
29345 := (5 × ((C(4) - C(3)) + C((9 × 2))))
29375 := (C(5) × ((C(7) - C(3)) - ((9²))))
29376 := (C(6) + (((-7) + C(3)) × C(9)) × 2)
29377 := (((7 + 7) + C(3)) × C(9)) - C(C(2))

- 29412 := (2 × ((-1) + C(49))/C(2))
29425 := ((5²) × (-((C(4) - C(9))) + C(C(2))))
29433 := (((-3) × (C(C(3)) - C(4))) - 9)/(-2)
29436 := (-6) × ((3 + 4) - C((9 + C(2))))
29437 := ((-C(7)) + C((C(3) + (4)))) - (9 + 2)
29439 := ((-9) + C((C(3) + (4)))) - C((9 - 2))
29453 := -((C(3) + (-5) × (C(4) + C((9 × 2))))))
29455 := (-5) × ((5 - C(4)) - C((9 × 2)))
29462 := (C(2) - (-6) × (-4) + C((9 + C(2))))
29466 := (-6) × ((6 - 4) - C((9 + C(2))))
29469 := (-9) + (6 × C(-((C(4) - (9²))))))
29475 := (-5) × (-7) - (C(4) × 92))
29486 := ((6 × C((C(8/4) + 9))) + C(2))
29496 := (((69 × C(4)) - C(9)) × C(2))
29498 := (-((8 - 94)) × C((9 - 2)))
29526 := ((6 + C(C(2))) × (59 - 2))
29527 := (C(7) - (C(C(2)) × (-59 - 2)))
29529 := (9 × ((C(C(2)) × 5) + ((C(9) - C(2))))))
29535 := ((C(5) × 3) - (-5) × C((9 × 2)))
29547 := (-7) × (-((C(4) - (-5) × C(9))) - C(C(2)))
29568 := ((8 + C(6)) × (C(5) + (9 - 2)))
29574 := ((C(-((4 - (7 × 5)))) - (C(9))) + C(C(2)))
29584 := (((C(4) - 8) + C(5)) - 9)²
29585 := (-5) × (-85) - C((9 × 2)))
29594 := ((-49) × (C(5) - C(9))) - 2
29642 := (C((C(2) × 4)) - (-6) × (-9) - C(C(2))))
29672 := ((-((2 - (7 × 6))) × C(9)) + C(C(2)))
29686 := ((C(6) - 8) + (6 × C((9 + C(2))))))
29697 := (((7 × 9) - 6) × (9 + C(C(2))))
29706 := (-6) × ((0 - C(7)) - (9 × C(C(2))))
29729 := ((9 + (2⁷)) × (C(9) - C(C(2))))
29763 := (C((C(3) + (6))) - (C(7) × (9 × 2)))
29783 := (C((C(3) - ((8/(7 - 9)))))) - C(2)
29791 := C(-(((1⁹) - ((7 + 9) × 2)))
29792 := ((C(((2 × 9) + 7)) - C(9)) × 2)
29793 := (C((39 - C(-((7 - 9)))))) + 2
29798 := (C(((C(8) - C(9))/(-7))) + (9 - 2))
29799 := -((C(9) + (((-9) × C(7)) - C(9)) × C(2)))
29832 := ((C(2) × 3) × ((C(8) + C(9)) + 2))
29849 := (C(9) + (((C(C(4)) + 8)/9) - C(2)))
29852 := (C((2⁵)) + ((8 × C(9))/(-2)))
29853 := (3 × (C(5) + (C((8 + 9)) × 2)))
29865 := (-((C(5) + (-6) × C((8 + 9)))) + C(C(2)))
29875 := (5 × (C(7) + (C(8) × (9 + 2))))
29923 := (C(C(3)) - (C(C(2)) × (-((9 + 9) + 2)))
30134 := (C((4 + C(3))) + (C((10 - 3))))
30137 := ((C(7) + C(31)) + 03)
30267 := (((-7) × C(6)) × (-20)) + C(3)
30331 := (C(-((C(-((1 - 3))) - (30)))) + C(C(3)))
30372 := (C((C(2) + (7))) + ((C(30) - 3)))
30375 := ((C(5) + C((7 + 3))) × C(03))
30378 := ((C((8 + 7)) + C(30)) + 3)
30477 := ((C(7) + C(7)) + C((4 + C(03))))
30493 := (-((C(3) - C(9))) + C((4 + C(03))))
30625 := (C(5) × ((2 + C(6)) + C(03)))
30875 := (C(5) × (7 + (80 × 3)))
31125 := (-C(5)) - (-2) × C((-((1 + 1)) + C(3)))
31168 := ((C(8) × 61) - C((1 + 3)))
31213 := (C((C(3) + 1)) + (21³))
31223 := ((C((C(3) - 2)) × 2) - C((1 × 3)))
31227 := ((C(7) + (C(C(2)) × (-21))) × (-3))
31232 := (C(C(2)) × (-3) + C(((2 - 1) + 3)))
31234 := (((C(4) - 3) × C(C(2))) - ((1 - 3)))
31235 := (C((5 + C(3))) - ((C(C(2)) - 1) × 3))
31239 := (((-9) + C(C(3))) - C(21)) × 3
31242 := (2 × (-4) + C((-2) + C((1 × 3))))
31245 := (((C(5) - C(4)) × C(C(2))) + 13)
31262 := (2 × (6 + C((-2) + C((1 × 3))))))
31265 := (((5 + C(6))²) - C((-1) + C(3)))
31293 := ((C(C(3)) - (-9) + C(21)) × 3)
31338 := ((-C(8)) + C(C(3))) + C((C(3) - (1 + 3)))
31349 := ((C(9) × 43) - ((1 - 3)))
31424 := (C(4) × (C(C(2)) - ((C(4) - 1)/3)))
31432 := -((C(C(2)) + (-3) × C((-((4 + 1)) + C(3))))))
31449 := (C(9) + ((C(4) - 4) × C(C(-((1 - 3))))))
31464 := ((C(4) + C((6 × 4))) + C((-1) + C(3)))
31559 := (((95 × C(5)) + 1) + C(C(3)))
31577 := ((77 × C(5)) + C((1 + C(3))))
31625 := (C(5) × ((2 × C((6 - 1))) + 3))
31634 := ((C((-4) + C(3)) - C(6)) + C(C((1 × 3))))
31723 := (((C(3) + C(2)) × (C(7) + 1)) + C(C(3)))
31742 := (C((C(2) × 4)) - ((C(7) - 1) × 3))
31744 := (-4) × (C(4) - C((7 + 13)))
31746 := (-6) × ((C(4) + C(7)) × (-13))

- 31782 := (2 × (C(8) + (7 × C(13))))
31843 := ((C((C(3) - (4))) - (8 - 1)) + C(C(3)))
31849 := ((C(-(9 - (4 × 8)))) - 1) + C(C(3)))
31851 := ((C((15 + 8)) + 1) + C(C(3)))
31872 := ((-(2 × 7) + C(8)) × C((1 + 3)))
31937 := (-7) - (-3) × C((9 + 13)))
31942 := ((C((2 + C(4)))/9) + ((1 - 3)))
31944 := ((C(44)/(9 - 1)) × 3)
31954 := (((4 × C(5)) + C(9)) × (-1) + C(3))
32024 := (4 × (C(20) + (2 × 3)))
32039 := -(C(9) - ((30 + 2)³))
32192 := ((C(C(2)) - 9) × C(((1²) + 3)))
32227 := (((7 × 2) × C(2))²) + C(C(3))
32229 := (9 × ((C((C(2) + C(2))) - C(C(2))) - 3))
32232 := -(C(C(2)) - ((C(32) - (C(2) × 3))))
32235 := -(((C((-5) + C(3))) - C(2)) - C((C(2) + C(3))))
32248 := ((C((8 × 4)) - C(2)) - C((2³)))
32252 := (2 × (((C(5) + 2)²) - 3))
32256 := (C(((6 × 5) + 2)) - C((2³)))
32258 := (((8⁵) + 2) - C((2³)))
32259 := ((9 × (5 + 2)) × C(C(2))) + 3
32262 := (2 × ((-6) + C(C(2))) + C((-2) + C(3)))
32277 := (-7) × ((-(7 + 2)) × C(C(2))) - 3
32279 := (((9 × 7) × C(C(2))) + 23)
32283 := ((C(3) - C(8)) + C((2²⁺³)))
32284 := (-4) × (C((8 × 2)) - C(23))
32292 := (2 × ((9 + C(C(2))) + C((-2) + C(3))))
32297 := ((-7) × ((-9) × C(C(2))) - 2) + C(3)
32347 := (((-7) × C(4)) + C(32)) + C(3)
32348 := ((C(8) + (-4) × C((C(3) + 2)))/(-3))
32358 := (((C(8) - (5)) × (C(3) - 2)) + C(C(3)))
32362 := ((C(C(2)) + C(C((6 - 3)))) + C(23))
32368 := (((C(8) + (6)) + C(C(3))) + C(23))
32379 := -(((C(9) - C(7)) - C(32)) + 3)
32384 := (C(4) × ((8³) - (2 × 3)))
32389 := (C(((9 + 8) + 3)) + C((2 + C(3))))
32392 := (C(2) × ((-9) + C(C(3))) - C((-2) + C(3)))
32424 := (-((C(4) - C(2))) × ((-C(4) - C(C(2))) - 3))
32425 := -(C((5 + 2)) - C((4 × 2³)))
32427 := -(((C(7) - 2) - C((4 × 2³))))
32432 := (C(2) × ((C(C(3)) - (4)) - C((-2) + C(3))))
32444 := ((4 - C((4 + 42)))/(-3))
32445 := (((-5) × C(4)) + C((C(4)/2))) - 3
32448 := ((-8) - C((4 + 42)))/(-3)
32451 := ((-1) × C(5)) + (C(4) × (C(C(2)) - 3))
32452 := ((-(((C(2) - C(5)) + (4))²) + C(C(3)))
32457 := ((-(C(7) - (5))) + C((C(4)/2))) + C(3)
32464 := (((C(46) + C(4)) - C(2))/3)
32472 := (((C(C(2)) - C(7)) × (-C(4))) - C(2)) × (-3)
32479 := (-97) + (C(4) × (C(C(2)) - 3))
32483 := (C(C(3)) - (C(8) × ((4 - 2) - C(3))))
32488 := (8 × (((C(8) - (4)) × C(2)) - 3))
32497 := (-79) + (C(4) × (C(C(2)) - 3))
32514 := (((C(4) + 1) × C(5)) + C((2 + C(3))))
32528 := (8 × ((C(2) - C((5²))) + C(C(3))))
32535 := ((5 × ((3⁵) - 2)) × C(3))
32552 := (C((2⁵)) - C(((5 - 2) + 3)))
32557 := (((7⁵) + C(5)) + C((-2) + C(3)))
32562 := ((C(C(2)) + ((C(6) - C(5)))) × (2 × C(3)))
32567 := ((((-7) + C(6)) × C(5)) × 2) - C(C(3))
32576 := (C(((6 - 7) + 5)) × (C(C(2)) - 3))
32616 := (C(6) × (1 + (-6) × (2 - C(3))))
32624 := (C((C(4)/2)) - ((6 × C(2)) × 3))
32625 := (C(5) × ((C(2) × (6²)) - C(3)))
32643 := ((C(C(3)) + (-4) × C(6)) + C((C(2) × 3)))
32697 := (-7) × (C(9) + (C(6) × (2 - C(3))))
32704 := (-C(4)) + C(((07 - 2) + C(3)))
32714 := (C((4 × (1 + 7))) - (2 × C(3)))
32723 := ((C(32) - 72) + C(3))
32741 := (((1 × 4)⁷) × 2) - C(3)
32742 := (C((C(2) × 4)) - ((7 - C(2)) + C(3)))
32744 := (C((4 + (4 × 7))) - (C(2) × 3))
32745 := (C((5 + C(-(4 - 7)))) - 23)
32749 := (((9⁴) - 7) × C(2)) - C(C(3))
32752 := (C((2⁵)) + ((7 - 23)))
32753 := (C((C(3) + (5))) - ((7 - 2) × 3))
32759 := (-9) + C((5 + ((7 + 2) × 3)))
32761 := (-((1 + 6)) + C(((7 - 2) + C(3))))
32762 := (C(((C(2) + C(6))/7)) - (2 × 3))
32764 := (-4) + C((((6 + 7) - C(2)) + C(3)))
32765 := (C(((5 + 6) - 7) × C(2))) - 3
32767 := (-((7 - 6)) + C(((7 - 2) + C(3))))
32784 := (C((4 × 8)) - ((7 - 23)))
32792 := (C((2 × (9 + 7))) + (C(2) × 3))

- 32793** := ((C((39 - 7)) - 2) + C(3))
32794 := (((C(C(4)) - C((9 - 7)))/C(2)) + C(3))
32795 := (((-(5 - 9))⁷ × 2) + C(3))
32797 := (((7 + C((9 + 7))) × C(2)) - C(3))
32822 := (C(((2 + 2) × 8)) + (2 × C(3)))
32823 := ((C(32) + (82)) - C(3))
32824 := ((C(4) - C(2)) + (8²⁺³))
32827 := (((7 + C((2 × 8))) × C(2)) + 3)
32832 := (((C(2) - C(3)) × (-8)) × C((2 × 3)))
32844 := ((C(4) + (4)) × ((C(8) - 2) - C(3)))
32853 := (C((C(3) + (5))) + (82 + 3))
32859 := (((C(C((9 - 5))) + C(8))/C(2)) + C(3))
32875 := (C(5) × (-7) - ((8 + 2) × C(3)))
32885 := (C(5) - (8 - (8²⁺³)))
32886 := (((C(6) × 8) - C(8)) + 2) × C(3))
32952 := (-C(2)) + (C(-((5 - 9))) × (C(C(2)) + 3))
32955 := ((5 × C(-((5 - (9 × 2)))))) × 3)
32958 := (((8⁵) + C(9)) - C(C(2))) - C(3))
32984 := (C((4 × 8)) + C((9 × 2)/3))
32995 := (((C(5) - 99) × C(C(2))) + C(C(3)))
33055 := (-5) × (-50) + (C(C(3))/(-3))
33125 := ((5 + C(C(2))) × (-1) + C(3)) + C(C(3))
33165 := (-5) × ((C(6) + C(C((1 × 3))))/(-3))
33222 := (2 × ((C(C(2)) × (-2 × 3)) + C(C(3))))
33234 := (((C(43) + C(C(2))) + C(C(3)))/3)
33237 := (((-(7 + 3)) + C(C(2))) × C(3)) + C(C(3))
33245 := ((C(5) - C(4)) × (C(C(2)) + 33))
33253 := (C((C(3) + (5))) + ((C((2³)) - C(3))))
33256 := ((65 × C(C(2))) - (C(3) - 3))
33264 := ((C((4 + 6)) + C(2)) × 33)
33291 := (((-(1 - 9)) - C(C(2))) × (-C(3))) + C(C(3))
33345 := (-5) × ((-4) × C(3)) + (C(C(3))/(-3))
33372 := (((C(C(2)) + C(7)) × (-3)) + (C(33)))
33375 := (C(5) × ((7 + 3) × C(3)) - 3)
33385 := (((C(5) - C((8 × 3)))) + C(C(3))) + 3)
33416 := (((C(6) - 1) × C(4)) - C(3)) + C(C(3))
33443 := (C(C(3)) - (C(4) - C((4 × (3 + 3))))
33445 := (-5) × (-((C(4) + C(4))) + (C(C(3))/(-3)))
33446 := (((C((6 × 4)) - C(4)) + C(C(3))) + 3)
33453 := ((C(C(3)) - 54) + C((C(3) - 3)))
33464 := ((C((4 × 6)) - 43) + C(C(3)))
33465 := (-5) × ((C(6) × (-4) - C(3)) + 3)
33483 := (C(C(3)) - (-8) × (C((4 × 3)) - 3))
33497 := (C((C(-((7 - 9))) × 4)) + (C((3 × 3))))
33507 := (C((C((7 - 05)) × 3)) + C(C(3)))
33512 := ((C(C((2 + 1))) + (5)) + C((C(3) - 3)))
33513 := ((C(C(3)) + (1 + 5)) + C((C(3) - 3)))
33528 := (8 × ((-2) - C(5)) × (-33))
33529 := (((C((9 × 2)) + (5))) + C(C(3))) + C(C(3))
33534 := -(((C((-4) + C(3)) - (5))) - C(C(3))) - C(C(3))
33539 := -(((C((-9) + C(3)) - (5)) - C(C(3))) - C(C(3)))
33555 := (C(5) + (-5) × (-C(5)) + (C(C(3))/(-3)))
33556 := ((C((6 × 5)) - (5)) - (C(C(3))/(-3)))
33559 := (C(9) + (-5) × (-5) + (C(C(3))/(-3)))
33561 := (C(((1 × 6) × 5)) - (C(C(3))/(-3)))
33565 := ((5 + C(6)) × (C(5) + C(3))) - C(3)
33576 := ((C(6) - (C(7) × (-5) - C(3))) × 3)
33588 := (((C(8) + (8 - 5)) × C(3)) + C(C(3)))
33595 := (((C(5) + C(9)) + C((5 + C(3)))) - C(3))
33615 := ((516 × C(3)) + C(C(3)))
33617 := ((C(7) × (C(-((1 - 6))) - C(3))) + 3)
33623 := ((C((C(3) + 2)) + C((-6) + C(3))) - C(3))
33625 := (C(5) × (C(C(2)) - (C(6) + ((3³))))
33633 := ((C((C(3) - 3))/(-6)) + (C(33)))
33655 := ((5 × C((5 + 6))) + C((C(3) + 3)))
33669 := (((C(9) + (6))) - C(C((6/3)))) × (-C(3))
33696 := (-6) × (((9 - C(6)) × C(3)) - C(3))
33723 := (C(3) + (((C(C(2)) + (7)) × C(3)) + C(C(3))))
33792 := (C(C(2)) × ((9 - 7) × 33))
33856 := ((C((6 × 5)) + C((-8) + C(3))) - 3)
33858 := (((C(8) + (5 + 8)) × C(3)) + C(C(3)))
33872 := (2 × (((C(7) × (-8)) + C(C(3))) - 3))
33875 := (C(5) × (7 + (8 × 33)))
33957 := (C(7) × ((5 × 9) + C(3)) + C(3))
33975 := (((C(5) - C(7)) × 9) + C(33))
33993 := ((C(-((3 - 9))) × (-9)) + (C(33)))
34125 := (C(5) × ((C((2 + 1)) + C(4)) × 3))
34209 := ((C((9 + 02)) - C(4)) × C(3))
34227 := (((7 + C(C(2))) × (2 + C(4))) - C(3))
34229 := (((C(9) × 2) + C((C(2) × 4))) + 3)
34235 := (5 × (C((C(3) - C(2))) - (4 × 3)))
34236 := ((C((6 + C(3))) - C((C(2) + (4)))) + C(3))
34237 := (73 × (C(C(2)) - 43))
34239 := ((C(9) + C(C(3))) + (C(24) + 3))
34259 := (-((9 × 5)) + (C(C(2)) × (C(4) + 3)))

- 34263 := (C(3) × ((C(6) × (2 + 4)) - C(3)))
34265 := (-5) × (6 - C((2⁴) + 3)))
34273 := -((C(3) + (C(7) × (C(2) + (-4) × C(3))))))
34288 := (-((8 + 8)) + (C(C(2)) × (C(4) + 3)))
34295 := (5 × C(((9 × 2) + 4) - 3))
34312 := (C(2) + (C(C(-((1 - 3)))) × (C(4) + 3)))
34322 := ((-2) + ((C(2) + 3)⁴)) + C(C(3)))
34324 := (((4 × 2) + 3)⁴) + C(C(3))
34327 := ((C(7) × ((-2) + C(3)) × 4) + C(3))
34331 := ((C(C(-((1 - 3)))) × (3 + C(4))) + C(3))
34356 := (((C(6) × 53) + (4)) × 3)
34389 := (((-C((9 + 8))) + C(C(3))) - C(4)) + C(C(3)))
34391 := (C((-((1 + 9)) + C(3))) × (4 + 3))
34425 := (-5) × ((C((C(2) + 4))) × (-4)) + C(3))
34432 := (((C(C(2)) + C(3)) × C(4)) - ((4³)))
34477 := ((-((C(7) + C(7))) + C(C(4))) - C((C(4) - 3)))
34488 := ((-8) + C((8 × 4))) + C((4 × 3))
34489 := (C((9 × (8 - 4))) - C((-4) + C(3)))
34493 := ((C((C(3) + 9)) + (4)) - C((-4) + C(3)))
34523 := ((C(3) + C((2⁵))) + C((4 × 3)))
34533 := (((C(C(3)))/(-3)) × (-5)) + C((4 × 3))
34544 := (-4) × (4 + (-5) × C((4 × 3)))
34557 := ((C((7 + 5)) × (5 × 4)) - 3)
34575 := (-5) × ((C((7 + 5)) × (-4)) - 3)
34624 := (C(4) × (C(C(2)) + ((6 - 4) + C(3))))
34625 := (C(5) × ((2 × (C(6) - C(4))) - C(3)))
34647 := (C(7) + (C(C(-((4 - 6)))) × (C(4) + 3)))
34657 := -((C(7) - (C(5) × (C(6) + (4³))))))
34658 := ((8⁵) - ((-6) - C(4)) × C(3))
34668 := ((-8) - ((C(6) × (-6)) + (4))) × C(3))
34698 := ((C((8 + 9)) - (6)) + C((4 + C(3))))
34712 := ((C(2) + C(17)) + C((4 + C(3))))
34768 := (-8) + ((C(6) × (-7)) × (4 - C(3)))
34776 := (((C(6) + C(7)) × C((7 - 4))) + C(C(3)))
34835 := (5 × (C((C(3) - 8)) - (-4) × C(3)))
34845 := ((5 + C(4)) × (C(8) - (4 + 3)))
34853 := (((3 × C(5)) + 8) × (C(4) + C(3)))
34875 := (C((5 × 7)) - C((8 + (4 × 3))))
34896 := (((C((6 × 9)) - 8) - C(C(4)))/(-3))
34937 := -((C((7 + 3)) - C(((9 × 4) - 3)))
34944 := (((C(4) - C((4 × 9)))/(-4)) × 3)
34965 := ((C((5 + 6)) - (9 × 4)) × C(3))
34968 := (8 × ((6 × (C(9) + (4))) - C(3)))
34973 := (C((C(3) - (7))) + (C(9) × (C(4) - C(3))))
34986 := ((6 × (8 + 9)) × C((4 + 3)))
34992 := ((C((2 × (9 + 9)))/4) × 3)
35038 := (((C(8) × 30) - (5)) + C(C(3)))
35125 := ((C(52)/(-1 - 5)) - C(3))
35152 := (C((25 + 1)) × (5 - 3))
35183 := ((C(38) - (1 + 5)) - C(C(3)))
35199 := ((-9) - C(9)) + C(((1 + 5) + C(3)))
35236 := (((C(6)/(-3)) + C(25)) + C(C(3)))
35242 := (((-2) - C(4)) + C(25)) + C(C(3))
35264 := ((-((C(4) + C(6))) + C(C(2))) × (C(5) + C(3)))
35289 := (C(9) + (((C(8)/2) × 5) × C(3)))
35296 := ((69 × C(C(2))) - (5 + C(3)))
35308 := (C(((8 - 03) × 5)) + C(C(3)))
35313 := ((C((C(3) + ((1 - 3)))) + (5)) + C(C(3)))
35314 := ((C((41 - 3)) + C(5)) - C(C(3)))
35323 := ((C(C(3)) + C((-2) + C(3))) + (5 × 3))
35325 := (((5 × C(C(2))) - 3) + C((5 + C(3))))
35328 := (C(8) × ((2 × C(3)) + (5 × 3)))
35329 := ((C(9) - C(2)) × ((C(3) - (5)) + C(3)))
35338 := (((C(8) - (C(C(3)))/(-3)) × 5) - C(3))
35344 := ((-4) - (C(4) × (-3)))⁵⁻³
35423 := (((C(C(3)) - C(2)) × 4)/5) + C(C(3))
35424 := (4 × ((C(2) + (C(4) × 5)) × C(3)))
35456 := (((C(6) + C(5)) - C(4)) × (C(5) + 3))
35478 := (((-8) - C(7)) × (-45)) + C(C(3))
35512 := (C((C(2) + (1 + 5))) + C((5 + C(3))))
35524 := ((C((4 + 2)) + C((5 × 5))) + C(C(3)))
35526 := (((C(6) + 2) + C((5 × 5))) + C(C(3)))
35576 := ((6 × (C(7) + C(5))) + C((5 + C(3))))
35624 := (((-4) + C(C(2))) - C(6)) × (C(5) - 3))
35649 := (9 × ((4⁶) - (5 × C(3))))
35655 := (((55 × C(6)) + (5)) × 3)
35657 := -((C(7) - ((C(5) × (6⁵))/C(3))))
35671 := (-1) + (C(7) × ((6 + C(5)) - C(3)))
35692 := (-2) + ((-9) + C((6 + 5))) × C(3))
35721 := ((C((1 + 2)) × 7)⁵⁻³)
35736 := ((C(63)/7) + (5 × 3))
35747 := (((7 - C(4)) + C(7)) × C(5)) - 3)
35762 := -(((C(C(2)) + ((C(6) - (7⁵)))) - C(C(3))))
35776 := ((C(6) + C(7)) × C(((7 + 5)/3)))

- 35785 := ((C(((5 × 8) - 7)) - C(5)) - C(3))
35825 := (((C((5²)) + C(8)) + (5)) + C(C(3)))
35839 := ((C((9 + (3 × 8))) - C(5)) + C(3))
35856 := ((C((6 + 5)) - (8 - 5)) × C(3))
35927 := (((C(7) + C(2)) × 9) + C((5 + C(3))))
35934 := (C(-(((4 × 3) - (9 × 5)))) - 3)
35936 := (C((6 + C(3))) - ((9 - 5) - 3))
35937 := C((((7 - 3) + 95)/3))
35944 := (-((C(4) - C((4 × 9)))) - C((-5) + C(3)))
35964 := (C((4 + ((C(6)/9) + (5)))) + C(3))
35968 := (8 × (((6 × C(9)) + C(5)) - 3))
35969 := (C((9 + (C(6)/9))) + (5 + C(3)))
35983 := (C(C(3)) - (8 - ((C(9) - C(5)) × C(3))))
35991 := (((C((1 × 9)) + C(9)) - C(5)) × C(3))
36035 := ((C(5) - C(3)) + C((06 + C(3))))
36056 := ((-6) + C(5)) + C((06 + C(3)))
36126 := (((C(6) + C(2)) - 1) × 6) × C(3))
36141 := (((C(14) - 1) × 6) + C(C(3)))
36147 := ((C(7) × (C(4) - (16))) + C(C(3)))
36153 := (C((C(3) + (5 + 1))) + ((6³)))
36162 := (((C(2) + C(6)) + 1) + C((6 + C(3))))
36224 := (C(4) × (C(C(2)) + (2 × C((6 - 3)))))
36233 := ((-C((3 + 3))) + C(C(2))) + C((6 + C(3)))
36236 := ((-((C(6) - 3)) + C(C(2))) + C((6 + C(3))))
36244 := ((C(4) + (4)) × (C(C(2)) + (-6) + C(3)))
36253 := (-((C(3) - C((5 + 2)))) + C((6 + C(3))))
36261 := ((-1) + ((C(6) + C(2)) × 6)) × C(3))
36271 := (((-1) + C(7)) - C(2)) + C((6 + C(3)))
36274 := (((-4) + C(7)) - 2) + C((6 + C(3)))
36276 := (((-6) + C(7)) + 2) + C((6 + C(3)))
36277 := ((C(7) + C((7 + 26))) - 3)
36279 := (-9) + ((-7) × C((2 × 6))) × (-3))
36281 := ((-1) + C(8)) × (C(2) + (63))
36284 := (-4) - (((C(8) - C(2)) × C(6))/(-3))
36286 := ((-6) + ((C(8) - C(2)) × C(6)))/3)
36288 := (((C(8) - 8) × C(2)) × (6 + 3))
36297 := (((C(7) + 9) + C(2)) + C((6 + C(3))))
36307 := ((C(7) + C(03)) + C((6 + C(3))))
36315 := (((C(5) + 1) × 3) + C((6 + C(3))))
36317 := ((7 × C(((1) + C(3)) - (6)))) - C(C(3)))
36342 := ((2 + (C(4) × (C(3) - (6)))) × C(3))
36344 := ((C(4) + C((4 + 3))) + C((6 + C(3))))
36347 := (((C(7) + C(4)) + 3) + C((6 + C(3))))
36352 := (C(C(2)) × ((5 + 3) + 63))
36366 := (((C(6) + C(6)) - 3) + C((6 + C(3))))
36369 := (C(9) + (C(6) × ((C(3) × 6) + 3)))
36396 := ((C(6) - (-9) × C(3))) + C((6 + C(3)))
36423 := (((-C(3)) + C(C(2))) - (-4) × C(6)) × C(3))
36448 := ((C(8) - (4/4)) + C((6 + C(3))))
36449 := (C((9 - (4/4))) + C((6 + C(3))))
36453 := ((C((3 + 5)) + (4)) + C((6 + C(3))))
36458 := ((C(8) + (5 + 4)) + C((6 + C(3))))
36483 := ((C((C(3) - (8 - 4))) - (6)) × 3)
36534 := ((C((-4) + C(3))) + (5 + 6)) × 3)
36542 := (-2) + (-4) × (C(5) - C((-6) + C(3))))
36544 := (C(4) × ((C(4) - (5)) + C(C((6/3)))))
36549 := (-9) × (C(4) + (C(5) × (-6) - C(3)))
36552 := (((2 - C(5)) × (-5)) + C((6 + C(3))))
36556 := ((-6) - (-5) × C(5)) + C((6 + C(3)))
36568 := (((C(8) - (6)) + C(5)) + C((6 + C(3))))
36582 := (((C(2) + C(8)) + C(5)) + C((6 + C(3))))
36624 := ((C(4) - C(2)) × (6 + (C(6) × 3)))
36625 := (C(5) × (266 + C(3)))
36638 := (((C(8) - C(3)) + C(6)) + C((6 + C(3))))
36639 := ((C(9) - C(3)) + C(((6 × 6) - 3)))
36648 := (((C(8) - (4)) × C(6)) + C(6))/3)
36657 := (-C(7)) + (-C(5)) × (C(6) - C(C((6/3))))
36672 := ((C((2 + 7)) + (6)) + C((6 + C(3))))
36675 := (-5) × ((C(7) × (6 × 6)) - C(C(3)))
36679 := ((C(9) + (7 + 6)) + C((6 + C(3))))
36693 := ((C(3) + C(9)) + C(((6 × 6) - 3)))
36723 := (((C((C(3) + C(2)))/(-7)) × (-6)) - C(3))
36728 := -((C((8 × 2)) + (-7) × C((6 × 3))))
36735 := (5 × (((C(3) + (7)) × C(6)) + 3))
36744 := ((C(4) - ((C(4) - (7)) × C(6))) × (-3))
36753 := (((C(35)/(-7)) × (-6)) + 3)
36786 := (((-6) + C(8)) + C(7)) + C((6 + C(3)))
36792 := ((C(2) - C((9 + 7))) × (-6 + 3))
36825 := (((C(5) - C(2)) - C((8 × 6)))/(-3))
36842 := (((2 + C(4)) - C((8 × 6)))/(-3))
36844 := (((4 - C(4)) + C((8 × 6)))/3)
36846 := (((6 × 4) × C(8)) - (6)) × 3)
36855 := (-5) × ((C(5) - 8) × (-63))
36861 := (-1) + ((-6) + C((8 × 6)))/3)
36862 := (-2) + (C((6 × 8))/(6 - 3))

36863 := ((3 - C((6 × 8)))/(-6 - 3))
36865 := (-((5 - 6) + (C((8 × 6))/3))
36866 := ((6 + C((6 × 8)))/(6 - 3))
36869 := (((9 + 6) + C((8 × 6)))/3)
36871 := ((1 × 7) + (C((8 × 6))/3))
36872 := (C(C(2)) + (((-7) + C(8)) × C(6))/3))
36882 := ((2 + C((8 + 8))) × (6 + 3))
36883 := ((C(3) - 8) + (C((8 × 6))/3))
36922 := (((2^{C(2)}) + C(9)) + C((6 + C(3))))
36928 := ((C((8 + 2)) - 9) + C((6 + C(3))))
36936 := (C(6) × (3 × ((9 × 6) + 3)))
36937 := (C((7 + (C(3)/9))) + C((6 + C(3))))
36944 := (-C(4) + (-4) × (9 - C((-6) + C(3))))
36946 := (((C(6) + C(4)) + C(9)) + C((6 + C(3))))
36962 := (C(C(2)) + (((C(6) + 9) × 6) × C(3)))
36963 := (((C(3) × 6) + 9) × C(6)) + C(3))
37042 := (-2) + (4 × C((07 × 3)))
37044 := (4 × C(((4 × 0) + 7) × 3))
37084 := ((-4) + C(8)) × 073
37124 := (4 × ((C(21) - 7) + C(3)))
37146 := (-6) - (-4) × ((1 + C(7)) × C(3))
37159 := (((C(9) × 51) + 7) - C(3))
37179 := (C(9) × ((7 + 17) + C(3)))
37184 := (-4) × (-8) + ((-1) - C(7)) × C(3))
37186 := (((C(6) × 81) + 7) + C(C(3)))
37222 := (-C(2)) + ((2 - C(C(2))) × (-73))
37224 := (-((C(4) + C(2))) × (C(C(2)) - (C(7) × 3)))
37225 := (-5) + ((2 - C(C(2))) × (-73))
37234 := (((C(4) × 3)²) + C(7)) + C(3))
37244 := (-4) × (4 - ((2 + C(7)) × C(3)))
37248 := (((C(8) × (-4)) - C(2)) + C((7 + C(3))))
37251 := ((-1) × C(5)) + (C(C(2)) × 73)
37252 := ((C(((C(2) + 5) × 2) - 7)) + C(C(3)))
37259 := (C((9 + ((5 × 2) + 7))) + C(C(3)))
37262 := ((C(26) + C(27)) + 3)
37279 := (-97) + (C(C(2)) × 73)
37287 := (((7 + C(8)) × 2) + C(7)) × C(3))
37288 := (-88) + (C(C(2)) × 73)
37297 := (-79) + (C(C(2)) × 73)
37324 := (4 × (C((C(2) + 3)) + C((-7) + C(3))))
37341 := ((-1) - (-4) × (3 + C(7))) × C(3))
37349 := (C((9 + 4)) × (C(3) - (7 + 3)))

37368 := -(((C(8) - (-6) × (C(3) - C(7)))) × C(3))
37372 := ((C(C(2)) × 73) - (7 - 3))
37376 := (C(C(((6 - 7) + 3))) × 73)
37382 := (2 × ((8 + C(C(3))) - (C((7 + 3))))))
37395 := ((C(-((5 - 9) × 3)) - C(7)) × C(3))
37413 := (((C(C((3 + 1))) - C(4))/7) - C(3))
37416 := (-6) + (((1 - C(C(4)))/(-7)) - C(3))
37421 := (((C((1 × 2)) - C(C(4)))/(-7)) - C(3))
37422 := (((2/2) - C(C(4)))/(-7)) - C(3))
37423 := (((-((3 × 2)) - C(C(4)))/(-7)) - C(3))
37426 := (((C((6/2)) + C(C(4)))/7) - C(3))
37427 := (C(7) + ((C(C(2)) - 4) × 73))
37437 := (((C((7 - 3)) - C(C(4)))/(-7)) - 3)
37448 := (C(8) - ((4 + (-4) × C(7))) × C(3))
37457 := (-7) + (((-C(5) - C(C(4)))/(-7)) - 3))
37471 := ((((-1) + C(7)) + C(C(4)))/7) - C(3))
37475 := (((C(-((5 - 7))) - C(C(4)))/(-7)) + C(3))
37476 := (((-((6 - 7)) - C(C(4)))/(-7)) + C(3))
37483 := (((C(3) × (-8)) - C(C(4)))/(-7)) + 3)
37494 := (((C(C(4)) + (C((9 - 4))))/7) + C(3))
37542 := (-2) - (-4) × (C(5) + C((7 × 3)))
37573 := (C((C(3) + 7)) - ((C((5 + 7)) + 3)))
37576 := (-C((6 × (7 - 5))) + C((7 + C(3))))
37584 := (-((4 - 8)) × ((5 + C(7)) × C(3)))
37596 := ((-6) + C(9)) × (C(5) - 73)
37602 := ((C((20 + 6)) + C(7)) + C(C(3)))
37625 := (-C(5)) × (C(C(2)) + ((C(6) - (C(7) × 3))))
37665 := (-5) × (C((6 + 6)) - C((7 × 3)))
37764 := (((-4) - C(6)) × 7) + C((7 + C(3)))
37824 := ((-C(4) + C(C(2))) + (C(8) × 73))
37827 := ((C((7 × C(2))) - 8) - (7 × C(C(3))))
37844 := -((C(4) + (-4) × ((8 + C(7)) × C(3))))
37863 := ((36 × (C(8) - 7)) + C(C(3)))
37884 := ((-4) + C(8)) + (C(8) × 73)
37888 := (C(8) × ((8/8) + 73))
37921 := (-1) + (2 × (-((C(9) - 7))) + C(C(3))))
37935 := (-5) × ((C((3 + 9)) × 7) - C(C(3)))
37973 := (C((C(3) + 7)) - C((C((9 - 7)) + 3)))
37984 := (-4) × (8 + ((-9) - C(7)) × C(3))
38037 := ((C(-((7 - 30))) + C(8)) × 3)
38126 := (-C(6) - (2 × (C((1 × 8)) - C(C(3))))))
38177 := ((C(7) × 71) + C((8 × 3)))
38213 := (C((31 - 2)) + C((8 × 3)))

$$\begin{aligned} 38225 &:= (-((C(5) - C(2))) - (2 \times (C(8) - C(C(3)))))) \\ 38234 &:= ((-4) \times C(3)) - (2 \times (C(8) - C(C(3)))) \\ 38269 &:= (9 + 62) \times (C(8) + C(3)) \\ 38279 &:= (-((9 \times 7)) - (2 \times (C(8) - C(C(3)))))) \\ 38325 &:= ((5^2) \times ((3 \times C(8)) - 3)) \\ 38326 &:= (((-6) \times ((-C(2) + C(C(3))) - C(8)))/(-3)) \\ 38328 &:= (-8) + (2 \times (C(C(3)) - (C(8) + 3))) \\ 38336 &:= ((6/3) \times (C(C(3)) - (C(8) + 3))) \\ 38337 &:= (((-C(7)) + C(C(3))) - (3^8)) \times 3 \\ 38342 &:= (((-C((2 \times 4))) + C(C(3))) - C(8)) + C(C(3)) \\ 38348 &:= ((8/4) \times (C(C(3)) - ((C(8) - 3)))) \\ 38352 &:= (2 \times ((5 + C(C(3))) - (8^3))) \\ 38354 &:= ((((-4) \times C(5)) + C(C(3))) - C(8)) + C(C(3)) \\ 38358 &:= ((((-8) \times C(5)) + C(C(3))) - 8) + C(C(3)) \\ 38376 &:= ((C(6) \times ((7 \times 3) + C(8)))/3) \\ 38488 &:= (8 \times ((C(8) \times (-4)) + C((-8) + C(3)))) \\ 38525 &:= (C(5) - ((-25) \times C(8)) \times 3) \\ 38535 &:= (-5) \times (((3 \times 5) \times C(8)) - C(3)) \\ 38559 &:= ((C(9) \times 55) - (C(8) \times 3)) \\ 38629 &:= (((C(9) \times 26) - 8) + C(C(3))) \\ 38634 &:= (((-4) + C(C(3))) - (C(6) + C(8))) + C(C(3)) \\ 38639 &:= (((-C(9)) + C(C(3))) - ((6 - 8))) + C(C(3)) \\ 38677 &:= (-7) - ((-76) \times (C(8) - 3)) \\ 38691 &:= ((1 + ((9 \times C(6)) - C(8))) \times C(3)) \\ 38718 &:= (-81) \times ((7 - C(8)) + C(3)) \\ 38723 &:= (C(3) + (2 \times (-((C(7) - 8)) + C(C(3)))))) \\ 38742 &:= (2 \times (-((4 \times 78)) + C(C(3)))) \\ 38745 &:= (-5) \times (((C(4) - C(7)) - 8) \times C(3)) \\ 38779 &:= -((C((9 + 7)) - C((7 \times (8 - 3)))))) \\ 38808 &:= ((80 - 8) \times (C(8) + C(3))) \\ 38822 &:= -((C(C(2)) - (2 \times (-((8 + 8)) + C(C(3)))))) \\ 38838 &:= (((-8) + C(C(3))) + (-8 - C(8))) + C(C(3)) \\ 38844 &:= ((-44) + C(8)) \times 83 \\ 38852 &:= (((-2) + C(C(-((5 - 8)))))) - (C(8) - C(C(3)))) \\ 38862 &:= (((C(2) + C((C(6)/8))) - C(8)) + C(C(3))) \\ 38875 &:= (C(5) \times (C(7) - (8 + (8 \times 3)))) \\ 38912 &:= (C(C(2)) \times (1 + ((9 \times 8) + 3))) \\ 38926 &:= (-6) + (2 \times (-((C(9) - C(8))) + C(C(3)))) \\ 38927 &:= (-7) - ((-2) \times ((C(9) - 8) \times C(3))) \\ 38932 &:= (2 \times (C(C(3)) - ((C(9) - (8^3)))))) \\ 38942 &:= (2 \times (4 + ((C(9) - 8) \times C(3)))) \\ 38964 &:= (((-4) \times C((6 + 9))) + C(8)) \times (-3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39023 &:= ((C(C(3)) - C(-((2 - 09)))) + C(C(3))) \\ 39088 &:= (8 \times (C((8 + 09)) - C(3))) \\ 39123 &:= (C(C(3)) - (((C(2) + 1) - C(9)) \times C(3))) \\ 39221 &:= (-1) + (2 \times ((C(2) \times (-9)) + C(C(3)))) \\ 39223 &:= (-C((3 + 2))) + (2 \times (-9) + C(C(3))) \\ 39225 &:= -((C(5) + (2 \times (C(2) - C((9 \times 3)))))) \\ 39235 &:= (-C(5)) + ((C(C(3)) \times 2) - (9 - 3)) \\ 39241 &:= -((C((1 + 4)) + (-2) \times C((9 \times 3)))) \\ 39242 &:= (-2) \times ((C(4) - 2) - C((9 \times 3))) \\ 39243 &:= ((3 - C(4)) + C((-((2 - 9)) + C(3))) \\ 39244 &:= ((4 - C(4)) + C((-((2 - 9)) + C(3))) \\ 39245 &:= -(((C(5) - 4) + (-2) \times C((9 \times 3)))) \\ 39246 &:= ((6 - C(4)) + C((-((2 - 9)) + C(3))) \\ 39247 &:= ((7 - C(4)) + C((-((2 - 9)) + C(3))) \\ 39248 &:= ((8 - C(4)) + C((-((2 - 9)) + C(3))) \\ 39249 &:= (-9) - ((4 - (2 \times C(9))) \times C(3)) \\ 39259 &:= (-((9 \times 5)) + C((-((2 - 9)) + C(3))) \\ 39265 &:= -((C(5) - 6)) + (2 \times (9 + C(C(3)))) \\ 39272 &:= (2 \times (7 - ((2 - C(9)) \times C(3))) \\ 39292 &:= (C(((C(2) + 9) \times 2)) - (9 + 3)) \\ 39293 &:= ((C(39) - C(-((2 - 9)))) - C(C(3))) \\ 39295 &:= -((C(5) - (((C(9) + 2) + C(9)) \times C(3)))) \\ 39297 &:= (-7) + C(((9 - 2) + (9 \times 3))) \\ 39298 &:= (C(((8 + 9) \times 2)) - (9 - 3)) \\ 39306 &:= ((-60) + C(C(3))) + (C((9 \times 3))) \\ 39307 &:= (C((7 - ((0 - 3) \times 9))) + 3) \\ 39312 &:= (2 \times ((-1) \times C(3)) + C((9 \times 3))) \\ 39315 &:= ((-51) + C(C(3))) + (C((9 \times 3))) \\ 39316 &:= (C(((6 + 1) + C(3))) + (9 + 3)) \\ 39321 &:= (((1 \times 2) \times (C(C(3)) - 9)) - C(3)) \\ 39322 &:= (-C(2)) + ((2 \times C(C(3))) - (9 + C(3))) \\ 39324 &:= ((-42) + C(C(3))) + (C((9 \times 3))) \\ 39325 &:= (-5) + ((2 \times C(C(3))) - (9 + C(3))) \\ 39328 &:= (8 \times (C(((2^3) + 9)) + 3)) \\ 39342 &:= (2 \times (-((4 \times 3)) + C((9 \times 3)))) \\ 39343 &:= ((C(34) + C(3)) + (9 + 3)) \\ 39347 &:= (((-((7 \times 4)) + C(C(3))) + 9) + C(C(3))) \\ 39348 &:= (((8/4) \times C(C(3))) - (-9) + C(3)) \\ 39351 &:= ((-15) + C(C(3))) + (C((9 \times 3))) \\ 39352 &:= (2 \times ((5 + C(C(3))) - (9 + 3))) \\ 39353 &:= (((C(C(3)) + 5) + C(C(3))) - (-9) + C(3)) \\ 39357 &:= (((7 - 5) \times (C(C(3)) + 9)) - C(3)) \\ 39358 &:= (-8) - (-((5 - 3) \times C((9 \times 3)))) \end{aligned}$$

- 39361** := $((1 - 6) + C(C(3))) + (C((9 \times 3)))$
39362 := $(2 \times (-(6/3) + C((9 \times 3))))$
39364 := $((4 - 6) + C(C(3))) + (C((9 \times 3)))$
39365 := $((5 - 6) + C(C(3))) + (C((9 \times 3)))$
39367 := $((7 - 6) + C(C(3))) + (C((9 \times 3)))$
39368 := $((8 - 6) + C(C(3))) + (C((9 \times 3)))$
39372 := $((C(27) + C(C(3))) + (9 - 3))$
39373 := $(C(C(3)) + (7 + ((3 \times 9)^3)))$
39374 := $((C(4) + C((7 + C(3)))) + (9 - 3))$
39375 := $((C(5) \times 7) \times ((C(3) - 9) + C(3)))$
39376 := $((-(6 - 7) + C(C(3))) + 9) + C(C(3))$
39378 := $((C(8) - (7)) \times 39) + C(C(3))$
39392 := $((C(2) + 9) + C(C(3))) + 9) + C(C(3))$
39393 := $((C(3) + C((9 \times 3))) + C((9 \times 3)))$
39396 := $(((-6) \times C(9) - 3) \times (-9)) + 3$
39397 := $(C((7 + (9 \times 3))) + (93))$
39412 := $(2 \times ((14 + 9) + C(C(3))))$
39421 := $((C(C((1 + 2))) + ((C(4) - 9))) + C(C(3)))$
39422 := $(2 \times (-(C(2) - (4 \times 9))) + C(C(3)))$
39423 := $((C(C(3)) + (C(2) + (49))) + C(C(3)))$
39429 := $(-9) + (2 \times ((4 \times 9) + C(C(3))))$
39443 := $((C(C(3)) + (C(4) + (4 + 9))) + C(C(3)))$
39456 := $(-6) \times ((-5) + C((4 + 9))) \times (-3))$
39459 := $((C(9) \times 54) + (93))$
39464 := $-((C(4) + ((C(6)/(-4)) \times (C(9) + 3)))$
39473 := $((-(C(3) - C(7))) \times C(-(4 - 9))) - C(3))$
39474 := $((C(-(4 - 7))) \times (4 + C(9))) + C(C(3))$
39483 := $((C(C(3)) - 8) + C(-(4 - 9))) + C(C(3))$
39492 := $(2 \times ((9 \times C((4 + 9))) - C(3)))$
39512 := $(2 \times ((C(-(1 - 5))) + 9) + C(C(3)))$
39528 := $((8 + C((C(2) + (5)))) \times 9) + C(C(3))$
39546 := $(C((C((6 - 4) + (5))) \times (-9) + C(3)))$
39577 := $(-(C(7) + (C(7) \times (-59)))) + C(C(3))$
39582 := $((-2) + C((8 + 5))) - C(9)) \times C(3)$
39608 := $(C(80) + (C((6 \times 9)) \times (-3)))$
39609 := $(9 \times ((06 \times C(9)) + C(3)))$
39622 := $((2^{C(2)} + C(C(-(6 - 9)))) + C(C(3)))$
39625 := $(C(5) \times ((C(2) + C(6)) + (93)))$
39628 := $((-8) + C(((C(2) \times 6) - 9))) - C(C(3))$
39636 := $(C(((6 + C(3)) + (6))) - (C((9 \times 3))))$
39646 := $((C(6) + C(4)) + C(C(-(6 - 9)))) + C(C(3))$
39647 := $(C(7) + C(((46 - 9) - 3)))$
39648 := $((8 - C(4)) \times ((-6) - C(9)) + C(3))$
39653 := $(C(C(3)) + (C(5) - ((-6) - C(9)) \times C(3)))$
39662 := $((C(C(2)) - C(6)) + C(C(-(6 - 9)))) + C(C(3))$
39663 := $((C(C(3)) - ((C(6) + C(6)) - C(9))) + C(C(3)))$
39722 := $(2 \times ((C(C(2)) - ((C(7) - 9))) + C(C(3))))$
39727 := $(-C(7)) + (2 \times ((C(7) + 9) + C(C(3))))$
39736 := $((C(6) + C((C(3) + (7)))) + (C((9 - 3))))$
39741 := $((1 + C((C(4) + (7))))/9) - C(3)$
39744 := $((4 \times 4) + 7) \times C((9 + 3))$
39747 := $((-7) + C(4)) \times (C(7) + 9) + C(C(3))$
39748 := $(-C(8)) + ((C((C(4) - (7)))/9) + C(C(3)))$
39752 := $(C(C(-(2 - 5))) - ((C(7) - C(9)) - C(C(3))))$
39753 := $((C(C(3)) - (C(5))) + C(C(-(7 - 9)))) + C(C(3))$
39798 := $((-8) - C(9)) \times (7 - 9) \times C(3)$
39825 := $(-5) \times (((-2) \times C(8)) + C(9)) \times C(3))$
39843 := $((C(34) + C(8)) + ((9 \times 3)))$
39852 := $((C(2) + C((5 + 8))) - C(9)) \times C(3)$
39863 := $((C(C(3)) - ((6 - C(8)) + 9)) + C(C(3)))$
39869 := $((C(C((9 - 6))) + ((C(8) - 9))) + C(C(3)))$
39872 := $((C(C(2)) \times (-C(7) - C(8))) - C((9 + C(3))))$
39875 := $(C(5) \times (C(7) - ((8 \times 9)/3)))$
39928 := $(-8) + (C(C(2)) \times ((9 \times 9) - 3))$
39936 := $(C(C((6/3))) \times ((9 \times 9) - 3))$
39942 := $(C(C(2)) + ((C(4) + ((C(9) + C(9)) \times C(3))))$
40328 := $((C(8) \times 2) + C((30 + 4)))$
40382 := $(2 \times ((C(8) + C(C(3))) - 04))$
40792 := $(C(2) \times ((C(9) \times 7) + (0 - 4)))$
40875 := $(C(5) \times (7 + (80 \times 4)))$
40888 := $(-8) - ((C(8) \times (-80)) + C(4))$
41123 := $((C(C(3)) - C(C(2))) + C((1 + C(-(1 - 4))))))$
41125 := $(C(5) \times (C((C(2) - 1)) - 14))$
41229 := $((9^2) \times (C(C(2)) + ((1 - 4))))$
41256 := $(C(6) \times ((C(5) + 2) + C((1 \times 4))))$
41375 := $(C(5) \times (C(7) - ((3 \times 1) \times 4)))$
41463 := $((-3) + C((6 \times 4))) \times (-1 - 4))$
41466 := $(-6) - (C((6 \times 4)) \times (1 - 4))$
41489 := $((C(9) \times ((-8) + C(4)) + 1)) - C(4)$
41536 := $((C(6) \times 3) \times C((5 - 1))) + C(4)$
41593 := $((-3) + C((-9) + C((5 - 1))))/4$
41595 := $((5 + C((-9) + C((5 - 1))))/4$
41625 := $((C(5) - C(2)) + C(6)) \times C((1 + 4))$
41635 := $(C((-5) + C(3)) + (6)) + C(C(-(1 - 4)))$
41683 := $(C(C(3)) + (8 \times (6 + C(14))))$

- 41875 := (C(5) × (C(7) - (8 × (1⁴))))
41976 := (-6) × ((-7) × C((9 + 1))) + (4))
41984 := (C(4) × (((-8) + C(9)) - 1) - C(4))
42125 := (((C(5) - 2) × C((-1) + C(2)))) - C(4))
42237 := -(C(7) + ((3 - C(22)) × 4))
42277 := -(C(7) - ((-7) - C(22)) × (-4))
42279 := (-C(9)) + ((-7) × C(C(2))) × (-C(2) + (4)))
42327 := ((C(7) + C(C(2))) + (3 × C(24)))
42332 := (((C(C(2) + C(3))) - C(3)) - C(C(2))) - (4))
42336 := (C(6) × (((C(3) - 3) × C(2)) + (4)))
42346 := (((-6) + C(4)) × C((3²))) + C(4))
42358 := (-((C(8) + (5))) + C((C(3) + (2 × 4))))
42363 := (C((C(3) + C((6/3)))) - C((2 × 4)))
42368 := ((C(8) + (6 × (C(3) - 2))) × C(4))
42375 := (C(5) × (C(7) - ((3 - 2) × 4)))
42376 := (-C(6)) + (C(((7) + C(3)) + 2) × 4))
42423 := (((C(C(3) + C(2))) - (4)) - C(C(2))) + C(4))
42432 := ((C(C(2)) × ((3⁴) + 2)) - C(4))
42464 := (C(46) - C((42 - 4)))
42494 := ((C(4) × (C(9) - C(4))) - (2 + C(4)))
42496 := (C((C(6)/9)) + ((-C(4)) + C(C(2))) × C(4))
42532 := (C((C(2) + C(3))) - C((5 - 2) + 4))
42533 := (-C(3)) + ((C((C(3) - (5))) - C(2)) × 4))
42536 := (((-6) + C((C(3) - (5)))) - C(2)) × 4
42543 := (C(C(3)) - (-45) × (C(C(2)) - (4)))
42552 := -(C(2) - (5 × ((C(5) + C(2)) × C(4))))
42555 := (-5) + (5 × ((C(5) + C(2)) × C(4)))
42591 := (-1) + (C(((9 + 5) + C(2))) × 4))
42592 := (C(((29 - 5) - 2)) × 4)
42599 := -(C(9) - ((C(9) - (52)) × C(4)))
42624 := ((C(((4²) + 6)) + C(2)) × 4)
42625 := (C((5²)) + C((6 + 24)))
42632 := (C(C(2)) - (-3) × (C(6) + C(24)))
42653 := ((C(35) - C(6)) - (2 + 4))
42657 := ((C((7 × 5)) - C(6)) + ((2 - 4)))
42672 := (((2 × 7) × 6) × (C(C(2)) - (4)))
42675 := ((C((5 × 7)) - C(6)) + ((2⁴)))
42683 := (C((C(3) + 8)) - (C(6) - (24)))
42688 := -(C(8) - (((-8) + C(6))²) - C(4))
42694 := (((C(4) + C(9)) × C(6)) - C(C(2)))/4
42723 := (C(C(3)) + (C(C(2)) × ((7²) - 4)))
42743 := ((C(34) + C((7 + C(2)))) + C(4))
42747 := (C(((7 × 4) + 7)) - (2 × C(4)))
42752 := (((2 × (-5) + C(7))) - C(2)) × C(4))
42752 := (((2 × (-5) + C(7))) - C(2)) × C(4))
42803 := (C((C(3) + 08)) - ((C(2) + C(4))))
42807 := (((C(70) - C(8))/C(2)) - (4))
42811 := (C(-((1 - (18 × 2)))) - C(4))
42813 := (C((C(3) + (1 × 8))) + (2 - C(4)))
42843 := (C((3 + (4 × 8))) - (C(2) × 4))
42844 := (((C(44) + C(8))/2) - (4))
42857 := ((C((7 × 5)) - (82)) + C(4))
42863 := (C((C(3) + C(-((6 - 8)))))) - (C(2) + (4))
42869 := (C((C((9 - 6)) + 8)) - (2 + 4))
42871 := (C(((((-1) - C(7))/(-8)) - C(2))) - (4))
42872 := -(C(2) - (((C(7) - 8) × 2) × C(4)))
42875 := C((((5 × 7) × 8)/2)/4)
42878 := (((8 - C(7)) × C(8)) + C(2))/(-4)
42883 := (C((C(3) + 8)) + ((8/2) + 4))
42931 := (C(((7) + C(3)) + 9) - ((C(2) - C(4))))
42932 := (C((C(2) + C(3))) + (-((9 - 2) + C(4)))
42938 := (C((8 + C(3))) + ((-9) + C(2)) + C(4))
42939 := (C(((9/3) × 9) + C(2)) + C(4))
42941 := (C(-((1 - (4 × 9)))) + (2 + C(4)))
42944 := (((4 - C(4)) + C(9)) + 2) × C(4))
42945 := ((((-5) + C(4)) × C(9)) - 2) - C(4))
42947 := (C(-((7 × (4 - 9)))) + ((C(2) + C(4))))
42957 := ((C((7 × 5)) + ((9 × 2))) + C(4))
42966 := ((-((6 × 6)) + C(9)) × (-2) + C(4))
42983 := (C((C(3) + 8)) + (9 × (C(2) + (4))))
42995 := ((59 × C(9)) - ((2⁴)))
43125 := ((C(5) × 2) + C((1 + 34)))
43136 := (((C(6) × 3) - 1) + C(3)) × C(4))
43154 := -(C(4) - ((C(5) + 1) × C((3 + 4))))
43157 := ((C(7) × (C(5) + 1)) + (3 - C(4)))
43204 := (((40²) × C(3)) + (4))
43217 := ((C(7) - 1) + C(((7) - C(3)) + C(4)))
43218 := (C((8 - 1)) + C(((7) - C(3)) + C(4)))
43258 := (((C(8) - C(5)) + C((C(2) + C(3)))) - (4))
43264 := (C(4) × (((C(6) + C(2)) × 3) + (4)))
43276 := (((-6) + C(7)) + C((C(2) + C(3)))) + C(4))
43325 := (C(5) + ((-2) + C(3)) × C((3 × 4)))
43345 := -(C(5) - C((4 × 3)) × C(3)) - C(4))
43375 := (C(5) × (C(7) + ((3 - 3) + 4)))

$$\begin{aligned}43388 &:= ((C(8) + C((8 + C(3)))) - ((3 - 4))) \\43392 &:= (((C(C(2)) - C(9))) \times (-3)) + C(3) \times C(4) \\43397 &:= ((C((7 + 9)) - 3) + C(34)) \\43416 &:= ((C(6) \times (-1 - 4)) \times (3 + C(4))) \\43452 &:= ((C(C(2)) - ((C(5) \times (C(4) + C(3)))))) \times (-4) \\43464 &:= (((4^6) + C(4)) + C(34)) \\43472 &:= ((C((C(2) \times 7)) - C((4 \times 3)))/4) \\43524 &:= (((C((C(4)/2)) - C(5)))/(-3)) \times (-4) \\43527 &:= ((C(7) \times (2 + C(5))) - 34) \\43557 &:= ((C(7) \times (C(5) + (5 - 3))) - (4)) \\43569 &:= (9 \times (C(6) - (C(5) \times (C(3) - C(4)))))) \\43584 &:= (((4 \times C(8)) - (5))/3) \times C(4) \\43597 &:= ((-7) + C(9)) + C((5 \times (3 + 4))) \\43615 &:= (C(((5 - 1) \times 6)) + C((C(3) + (4)))) \\43616 &:= ((C(6) + C(16)) + C(34)) \\43624 &:= (((C(C(4)) + 2)/6) + (-3 - C(4))) \\43634 &:= ((C(43) - C((6 + C(3)))) + C(4)) \\43712 &:= (((2 \times C((1 \times 7))) - 3) \times C(4)) \\43725 &:= (-5) \times (C(C(2)) - ((C((7 \times 3)) - (4)))) \\43732 &:= (2 \times (((3^7) + C(C(3))) - (4))) \\43742 &:= (2 \times (C((4 \times 7)) - ((3^4)))) \\43749 &:= ((-((9^4)) - C(7)) + C(-((C(3) - C(4)))))) \\43875 &:= (C(5) \times (C(7) - ((8 \times (3 - 4)))))) \\43904 &:= (((-40) + C(9)) - 3) \times C(4) \\43912 &:= (2 \times (C((1 + (9 \times 3))) + (4))) \\43921 &:= (((1 + C(C(2))) \times 9) + C(34)) \\43923 &:= (3 \times ((C(2) + (9/3))^4)) \\43928 &:= -((C((8 + 2)) - ((C(9) - C(3)) \times C(4)))) \\43937 &:= (-C(7)) + (((C(C(3)) \times 9) - C(3))/4) \\43948 &:= (((C(8) + (4)) \times 9) + C(34)) \\43952 &:= -((C(C(2)) - (-5) + (C(9) \times (-3) + C(4)))))) \\43956 &:= (C(6) + ((-5) \times C(9)) \times (-3 \times 4)) \\43957 &:= -((C(C((7 - 5))) + (C(9) \times (3 - C(4)))))) \\43981 &:= ((-((1 \times 8)) + C(9)) \times (-3) + C(4)) \\44096 &:= ((690 \times C(4)) - C(4)) \\44192 &:= (C(C(2)) + ((C(9) - 1) \times (C(4) - (4)))) \\44199 &:= (-C(9)) + ((C(9) - C(-((1 - 4)))) \times C(4)) \\44226 &:= (((-C(6)) \times C(C(2))) + C((2 + C(4))))/4) \\44247 &:= (C(7) \times ((C(4) \times 2) + (4/4))) \\44253 &:= -((C(C(3)) - (C(((5 \times 2) \times 4)) - C(4)))) \\44263 &:= (C(C(3)) + ((6 \times C((2^4))) + (4))) \\44265 &:= (((-5) + C(6))^2) - (4^4)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}44288 &:= (C(8) + ((C(8) - C(-((C(2) - C(4)))))/(-4))) \\44325 &:= ((C((5 \times C(2))) - C(C(3))) + (4 + 4)) \\44378 &:= (C(87) - C(((3^4) + 4))) \\44385 &:= ((C((5 \times 8)) - C(C(3))) - (-4 - C(4))) \\44416 &:= ((C((6 + 1)) + (4)) \times (C(4) + C(4))) \\44469 &:= (C(9) \times (C((6 - (4/4))) - C(4))) \\44492 &:= (C(C(2)) + ((C(9) + (4)) \times (C(4) - (4)))) \\44533 &:= ((C((3 \times 3)) \times (C(5) - C(4))) + C(4)) \\44573 &:= ((C(3) \times ((C(7) \times 5) - C(4))) - (4)) \\44657 &:= -((C(7) + ((C(5) \times (-6)) \times (C(4) - (4)))))) \\44671 &:= (-1) + ((C(7) + (6)) \times (C(4) + C(4))) \\44672 &:= (C(2) \times ((C(7) + (6)) \times (4 \times 4))) \\44682 &:= (-C((2 \times 8)) - (C((-6) + C(4)))/(-4)) \\44696 &:= (((C(6) - 9) \times C(6)) - ((4 \times 4))) \\44773 &:= -((C(3) - ((C(7) + (7)) \times (C(4) + C(4)))))) \\44853 &:= -(((C(C(3)) - (C(5) \times (-8))) - (C(C(4))/4))) \\44857 &:= (-7) + (((C(5) + C(8)) + C(4)) \times C(4)) \\44875 &:= (C(5) \times (7 + (8 \times 44))) \\44924 &:= -((C((4 + C(2))) - ((C((9 \times 4)) - (4)))))) \\44928 &:= ((8 + C(-((2 - 9)))) \times (C(4) + C(4))) \\44931 &:= (-1) - (((C(3) - C(9)) \times C(4)) - (4)) \\44932 &:= (C(2) - (((C(3) - C(9)) \times C(4)) + (4))) \\44942 &:= (((-2) + C(4)) \times C(9)) - (4^4) \\44952 &:= ((C(C(2)) + (C(5) \times (-94))) \times (-4)) \\45184 &:= (C(4) \times (81 + (5^4))) \\45194 &:= (-4) - (C(9) \times ((-1) - C(5)) + C(4)) \\45264 &:= (((-4) + C(6))^2) + (5 \times C(4)) \\45276 &:= ((6 \times C(7)) \times (2 + (5 \times 4))) \\45343 &:= (C((C(3) + (4))) + ((3^5) \times C(4))) \\45375 &:= (C(5) \times ((7^3) + (5 \times 4))) \\45479 &:= (((C(9) - (7)) \times C(4)) - C((5 + 4))) \\45564 &:= (C(4) - (((C(6) - C(5)) \times C(5)) \times (-4))) \\45568 &:= (C(8) \times ((6 \times 5) - 5) + C(4)) \\45576 &:= -((C(6) \times (C(7) - (554)))) \\45625 &:= (C(5) \times (C(C(2)) - ((C(6) - (5)) - C(4)))) \\45631 &:= (((-1) \times C(C(3))) \times (6 + 5)) + C(C(4)) \\45632 &:= ((C(C(2)) \times (-36) + C(5)) + C(4)) \\45738 &:= (((8 + C(3)) + C(7)) \times (C(5) - (4))) \\45752 &:= ((C(2) + C(5)) \times (C(7) + (5 - 4))) \\45783 &:= ((3 \times C(8)) + (C(7) \times (C(5) + (4)))) \\45799 &:= -((C(9) - ((C(9) - (7 - 5)) \times C(4)))) \\45824 &:= (C(4) \times (C(-((2 - 8))) - (C(5) \times (-4))))\end{aligned}$$

- 45843 := -((C(C(3)) - ((C(C(4)) - (8 × 5))/4)))
45875 := (C(5) × ((C(7) - (8 × 5)) + C(4)))
45926 := ((C((6²)) - C(9)) - (5 - 4))
45927 := (C((7 + 2)) × (9 + 54))
45933 := (((C(3) - 3) + C(9)) × (C(5) - C(4)))
45936 := ((63 × C(9)) + (5 + 4))
45945 := (5 × (((C(4) + 9) × C(5)) + C(4)))
46144 := (C(C(4)) - (C(((4 × 16) - 4))))
46161 := (((1 - C(6)) × (1 - C(6))) - C(4))
46199 := (-9) + ((C(9) - (1 + 6)) × C(4))
46216 := ((C(6) + (1 × 2)) × (C(6) - (4)))
46224 := (C((4 + 2)) × ((2 + C(6)) - (4)))
46228 := (((C((8 - 2)) - 2) × C(6)) + (4))
46266 := ((-6) + C((6²))) - (6 × C(4))
46271 := (-1) + ((C((7 + 2)) - (6)) × C(4))
46272 := (((27²) - 6) × C(4))
46278 := (((C(8) + C(7)) + 2) × C(6))/4
46296 := (C(6) + ((9 × C(C(2))) × (6 + 4)))
46305 := (5 × C(((0 - 3) + (6 × 4))))
46306 := (-((C(60) - (C(3) × 6))) + C(C(4)))
46317 := (((C(7) × (-1)) + C(36)) + (4))
46319 := (-91) × (3 - C(C((6 - 4))))
46325 := (-5) × ((-C(2)) - C((C(3) - (6)))) + (4)))
46345 := (-5) × ((-4) - C((C(3) - (6)))) - (4)))
46349 := (((C((9 × 4)) - C(3)) - C(6)) - C(4))
46364 := ((4 - C(6)) × (-3) - C(6)) - C(4))
46368 := (((-8) - C(6)) + C(36)) - C(4))
46375 := (C(5) × (7 + 364))
46394 := ((C(4) × (C(9) - 3)) - (6 + C(4)))
46436 := ((C(((6 + 3) × 4)) - C(6)) - (4))
46457 := (-7) + (((C(5) - (4)) × 6) × C(4))
46479 := (((-C(9)) - C((-7) + C(4))) + (6))/(-4))
46497 := (((-7) + C((9 × 4))) - C(6)) + C(4))
46522 := ((C((C(2) + (25))) × (-6)) + C(C(4)))
46524 := (-4) - ((C(C(2)) × (C(5) - C(6))) + C(4))
46528 := (-8) × (C(2) + ((C(5) - C(6)) × C(4)))
46539 := (C((9 + C(3))) - (C(5) - C((6 - 4))))
46552 := (C(2) × (-5) - ((C(5) - C(6)) × C(4)))
46557 := (-7) × ((-5) × C((5 + 6))) + (4))
46565 := (C(5) + (C(6) × ((-5) + C(6)) + (4)))
46568 := ((C(8) × (C(6) - C(5))) - (6 × 4))
46572 := -((C(C(2)) - (((C(7) - C(5)) × C(6)) - (4))))
46576 := ((C(6) × (C(7) - C(5))) - C(C((6 - 4))))
46584 := (-4) - ((C(8) × (C(5) - C(6))) + (4))
46586 := (-((6 - (8⁵))) + C((6 × 4)))
46588 := ((C(8) × (85 + 6)) - (4))
46591 := (-1) + ((C(9) + ((5 - 6))) × C(4))
46592 := (((-2) + C(9)) - ((5 - 6))) × C(4))
46593 := (C((C(3) + 9)) - ((5 - 6) + C(4)))
46595 := -((C(5) - ((C(9) - ((5 - 6))) × C(4))))
46598 := (C((-89) + C(5))) + (6 - C(4))
46623 := -((C(3) + ((2 - ((6⁶) - 4))))
46624 := ((C(4)/(-2)) + C((6⁶⁻⁴)))
46625 := -((C((5 - 2)) - (((6⁶) - 4))))
46626 := (C((6²)) - (6 + (6 × 4)))
46629 := ((C((9 × C(2))) - C(6))/C((6 - 4)))
46631 := ((-1) + C(36)) - ((6 × 4))
46638 := ((-8) + C(36)) - ((6 + 4))
46639 := ((-9) + C(36)) - C((6 - 4))
46652 := (C(((2 + 5) × 6) - 6)) - (4))
46655 := (-((5/5)) + C((6⁶⁻⁴)))
46662 := (C(2) + (((6⁶) - 6) + 4))
46664 := (C(-((4 - 6))) + C((6⁶⁻⁴)))
46668 := (C((8 - 6)) + ((6⁶) + 4))
46683 := (C(3) + C(((8 + (6/6)) × 4)))
46693 := (-(((3 × 9) - (6⁶))) + C(4))
46696 := (((C(6)/(-9)) + (6⁶)) + C(4))
46697 := -((C(7) + ((C(9) + (6)) × (-64))))
46712 := -C(2) + (-1 + 7)⁶ + C(4)
46715 := -5 + (-1 + 7)⁶ + C(4)
46726 := (C((6²)) + ((7 × (6 + 4))))
46766 := (((6 - C(6)) × (-7) - C(6)) - C(4))
46784 := ((((-4) + C(8)) + (7)) + C(6)) × C(4))
46844 := (-4) - (((-4) - C(8)) - C(6)) × C(4))
46848 := ((C(8) - ((4 - 8))) + C(6)) × C(4))
46866 := ((-6) - C((6 × 8))) + C((C(6)/4))
46872 := -((C(((C(2) × 7) - 8)) - C((C(6)/4))))
46875 := (C(5) × (C(7) + (8 + (6 × 4))))
46876 := (((C(6) - ((7 - 8))) × C(6)) + (4))
46896 := ((C(6) × (C(9) - C(8))) + (6 × 4))
46912 := (((-2) + C((1 × 9))) + (6)) × C(4))
46915 := ((C(5) × (-1)) + ((C(9) + (6)) × C(4)))
46926 := ((-C(6)) × (C(C(2)) - (C(9)))) + (C(6)/4))

- 46928 := $(-8) + (((C(C(2)) - C(9))) \times (-C(6))) + C(4))$
46933 := $((-3) + C((C(3) + 9))) + (C(6) + C(4))$
46936 := $((6^{-3+9}) + C(6)) + C(4)$
46948 := $((C(8) + C((4 \times 9))) - C(6)) - (4)$
46976 := $((((6 - 7) + C(9)) + (6)) \times C(4))$
46984 := $-(((C(4) - 8) - ((C(9) + (6)) \times C(4))))$
46995 := $(-(5 \times 9)) + ((C(9) + (6)) \times C(4))$
47063 := $((C(36) + C(07)) + C(4))$
47097 := $(-7) + ((C(9) - (0 - 7)) \times C(4))$
47168 := $(C(8) + C((6^{(1+7)/4}))$
47225 := $(-(5^2)) \times (C(C(2)) - ((7^4)))$
47232 := $((2 + C((3^2))) + (7)) \times C(4)$
47239 := $((C((9 + C(3))) + C(C(2))) - (-7 - C(4)))$
47278 := $(-C((8 + 7))) + C((-27) + C(4))$
47296 := $((C(((6 + 9) + C(2))) - C(7)) \times 4)$
47323 := $(C(3) - ((C(23) - C(7)) \times (-4)))$
47328 := $(((-8) - C(23)) + C(7)) \times (-4)$
47365 := $(5 \times ((C(6) + C((3 \times 7))) - (4)))$
47449 := $((C(9) + C(4)) + C((C(4) - ((7 \times 4))))$
47537 := $(((-7) \times C(C(3))) + (C(5))) + C((-7) + C(4))$
47539 := $((9 + 3) + C(5)) \times (C(7) + (4))$
47552 := $((C(C(2)) \times (-((C(5) + C(5)) - C(7)))) - C(4))$
47573 := $-((C(C(3)) - ((7^5) + 7) \times 4))$
47625 := $(C(5) \times ((-26) + C(7)) + C(4))$
47656 := $(((-6) + C(5)) \times C(6)) + C((7 \times 4))$
47665 := $((((5 + C(6)) \times C(6)) - (7)) - C(4))$
47744 := $((((C(4) - 4) + C(7)) + C(7)) \times C(4))$
47775 := $((5 \times 7) \times (-7 - (C(7) \times (-4))))$
47843 := $(C(C(3)) + (C(4) \times (-8) - (-7) \times C(4)))$
47849 := $((94 \times C(8)) - C(7)) + C(4)$
47884 := $((C(4) - 8) \times (C(8) + C(7))) + (4)$
47924 := $(-4) \times (-2 - (9 \times C((7 + 4))))$
47933 := $(-3) + (((C(3) + C(9)) - (7)) \times C(4))$
47936 := $((C((6 - 3)) + C(9)) - (7)) \times C(4)$
47943 := $(C(3) - (-((4 \times 9)) \times C((7 + 4))))$
47956 := $((((6 + C(5)) + 9) \times C(7)) - C(4))$
48125 := $(C(5) \times (C(C(2)) - (-1 - (C(8)/(-4))))$
48237 := $(7 \times (C((C(3) - C(2))) + (8 \times 4)))$
48256 := $((6 \times (C(5) + 2)) - 8) \times C(4)$
48265 := $((((5 + C(6))^2) - C(8)) - C(4))$
48328 := $((-8) \times (C(C(2)) - (3^8))) - C(4)$
48359 := $((-95) \times (3 - C(8))) + (4)$
48375 := $(C(5) \times (C(7) + ((3 + 8) \times 4)))$
48384 := $(C((4 + 8)) \times ((3 \times 8) + 4))$
48388 := $((-8) \times (C(8) - (3^8))) - (4)$
48392 := $(C(2) + ((C(9) + C(3)) \times C((8 - 4))))$
48448 := $((84 \times (C(4) + C(8))) + C(4))$
48464 := $(C(4) + ((C(6) + (4))^{8/4}))$
48497 := $(-7) - (-94 \times (C(8) + (4)))$
48522 := $-((2^{C(2)}) - (C(58)/4))$
48525 := $(-C(5) + ((C(C(2)) - (C(58)))/(-4)))$
48528 := $((C((8 + 2)) - C(58))/(-4))$
48536 := $(C(6) - ((-((3^5)) - C(8)) \times C(4)))$
48546 := $-((C(6) + ((C(4) - C(58))/4)))$
48561 := $((-1) - C(6)) + (C(58)/4)$
48573 := $(C(3) \times ((C(7) \times 5) + (84)))$
48642 := $(-C(2) + ((C((C(4) - (6))) - C(8))/4))$
48645 := $(-5) + ((C((C(4) - (6))) - C(8))/4)$
48648 := $(((-C(8)) + C((C(4) - (6)))) - 8)/4$
48664 := $((C(46)/(-6 - 8)) - (4))$
48672 := $((C(C(2)) - C(7)) \times ((C(6) + 8) + C(4)))$
48676 := $((((C(6) + (7)) \times C(6)) + C(8)) - (4))$
48764 := $((C((C(4) - (6))) - (7 \times 8))/4)$
48792 := $((C(29) + (7)) \times (8/4))$
48839 := $((C(9) \times (3 + (8 \times 8))) - (4))$
48875 := $(C(5) \times ((C(7) - ((8 + 8))) + C(4)))$
48922 := $(2 \times ((C(29) + 8) + C(4)))$
48934 := $(C((C(4) - C(3))) + (9 - C((8 + 4))))$
48936 := $-((C(6) - (((3 + 9) \times (8^4))))$
49152 := $((((C(2) \times 5) - 1) + C(9)) \times C(4))$
49216 := $((((6 - 1) \times C(2)) + C(9)) \times C(4))$
49243 := $-(((C(3) - C(4)) \times C((2 + 9))) + (4))$
49272 := $(C((2 \times 7)) + ((-2) + C(9)) \times C(4))$
49275 := $-(((C(5) - C((7 \times 2))) - C((9 \times 4))))$
49344 := $((C(4) \times (43 + C(9))) - C(4))$
49348 := $((-C(8) + C((C(4) - C(3)))) - (C(9) + C(4)))$
49375 := $(C(5) \times ((C(7) - (3 + 9)) + C(4)))$
49392 := $((2 \times 9) \times C((C(3) - (9 + 4))))$
49397 := $((C(7) - C((-9) + C(3))) \times (-9)) - (4)$
49432 := $(C((C(2) + C(3))) - (4 - (9^4)))$
49444 := $-((C(4) - (((C(4) + (4)) \times C(9)) - C(4))))$
49536 := $((C((6 + 3)) + (5 \times 9)) \times C(4))$
49538 := $((C(8) + (3 \times 5)) \times 94)$
49544 := $((C((C(4) + (4))) - C((5 + 9))) - C(C(4)))$

- 49572 := (C((2+7)) × (-(5-9)) + C(4))
49625 := -((C((5×2)) - ((6+9)⁴))
49656 := (-6) × ((C(5) + (C(6) × 9)) × (-4))
49728 := (8 × ((-2) - C(7)) + (9⁴))
49734 := (C((C(4) - C(3))) - ((C(7) - (-9) × C(4))))
49735 := -((((C(5) - C(37)) + C(9)) + C(4)))
49739 := (C((9 + C(3))) + ((C(7) × 9) - (4)))
49744 := (-((4 + 4)) × (C(7) - (9⁴)))
49792 := ((-((2 - 9) × 7) + C(9)) × C(4))
49844 := ((C(4) + (4)) × ((8 + C(9)) - (4)))
49875 := ((5 × (7 + 8)) × (C(9) - C(4)))
49928 := ((C((8 + 29)) - C(9)) + (4))
50653 := C((C(3) + (5 + ((6 × 0) + 5))))
50688 := (C(8) × ((8 + C(6)) - C(05)))
50875 := (C(5) × (7 + (80 × 5)))
51365 := (-C(56) + C(-((C((3 + 1)) - C(5))))
51479 := (C(9) + (((C(7) + C(4)) - 1) × C(5)))
51743 := (C((C(3) + (4))) + C(-((7 × (1 - 5))))
51754 := ((C((4 + 5)) × 71) - (5))
51759 := (C(9) × ((5 × 71)/5))
51786 := ((-68) - C(7)) × (-1) - C(5))
51858 := ((C(8) - C(5)) × ((8 + 1) + C(5)))
51875 := (-C(5)) × (-((C(7) + 8)) - C(-((1 - 5))))
52114 := (C(41) - ((-1) + C(2))⁵)
52122 := (((2 - C(C(2))) × (1 - C(C(2))))/5)
52136 := ((C(6) - C((3 + 1))) × C((2 + 5)))
52222 := (-2) + (((C(C(2)) - 2) × C(C(2)))/5)
52224 := ((C(C(4)) - (2^{C(2)+2}))/5)
52225 := ((-5) - ((C(C(2)) - 2) × C(C(2))))/(-5))
52232 := (C(2) × ((3^{C(2)}) - (2⁵)))
52238 := ((8 × (3^{C(2)})) + (-2) × C(5))
52266 := (-6) - (C(6) × (C(2) + (-2) × C(5)))
52299 := (((9 × C(9)) - C(2)) × C(2)) - C(5))
52316 := (((C(6) + 13)²) - C(5))
52324 := ((C((C(4)/2)) + C(C(3))) + (-2) - C(5))
52326 := (C(C((6/2))) + (C(32) - C(5)))
52336 := (-((C(6) × (C(3) + C(3)))) + C((C(2) × 5)))
52339 := (((9 - C(C(3)))/(-3)) × C(2)) - (C(5))
52353 := (C(C(3)) - ((C(5) - C(3)) - C((2⁵))))
52363 := ((C((3 × 6)) × (3²)) - C(5))
52364 := ((4 - C(6)) × (3 + (-2) × C(5)))
52384 := -((C(4) - (8 × ((3^{C(2)}) - (5))))
52416 := ((-((6 + 1)) × C(4)) × (C(2) - C(5)))
52422 := (-C(2)) - (((-2) + C(C(4))) + C(2))/(-5))
52423 := ((-((C(3) + 2)) + C(C((-4) + C(2))))/5)
52424 := ((C(C(4)) - (C(2) + ((4²))))/5)
52425 := (((C((5 - 2)) - C(C(4))) - C(2))/(-5))
52426 := (((6 × 2) - C(C(4))) + 2)/(-5)
52427 := (((7 - C(2)) + C(C(4))) - C(2))/5)
52428 := (((C((8²)) + (4)) - C(2))/5)
52429 := (((-((9 - 2)) + C(C(4))) + C(2))/5)
52431 := (((1 × 3) + C(C(4))) + C(2))/5)
52432 := (((2³) + C(C(4))) + C(2))/5)
52434 := ((C(C(4)) + (34 - C(2)))/5)
52437 := (-7) × (-3) + (C(4) × (C(2) - C(5)))
52438 := (((-8) + C(C(3))) + C((C(4)/2))) - (5))
52441 := (((-1) + C(C(4))) + ((C(4) - 2))/5)
52442 := ((2 + C(C(4))) + C((-4) + C(2)))/5)
52443 := ((C(3) + C(44)) - C((2⁵)))
52444 := ((C(C(4)) + ((C(4) + (4)) + C(2)))/5)
52445 := (5 - ((C(C(4)) + ((C(4) - C(2))))/(-5))
52446 := (((C((C(6)/4)) + C(C(4)))/C(2)) - (5))
52447 := (C(C((7 - 4))) - (4 - C((2⁵))))
52448 := (8 - ((C(C(4)) + ((C(4) - C(2))))/(-5))
52449 := (9 - ((C(C(4)) + ((C(4) - C(2))))/(-5))
52451 := (C(C(-((1⁵) - 4))) + C((2⁵)))
52459 := (((C(9) + C(5)) × C(4)) - C((C(2) + (5))))
52465 := (-5) × ((-((6⁴) × C(2)) - C(5))
52466 := (-6) - ((-C(6)) - C(C((-4) + C(2))))/5)
52479 := ((9 × C(7)) × ((4 + C(2)) + (5)))
52489 := ((9 × (8⁴)) + C(25))
52491 := (((1 + (9⁴)) × C(2)) - (5))
52493 := (((C(3) × 9) × C((4 + 2))) + (5))
52523 := (((3^{C(2)}) + (5)) × C(2)) - (5))
52528 := 8 × ((-2 + 5)^{C(2)} + 5)
52533 := (((C(C(3)))/3) + (5)) × C(2) + (5))
52625 := (C(5) × (((C(2) - C(6)) × (-2)) + (5)))
52632 := -((((C(C(2)) - (3 × C(6))) × (C(C(2)) - (C(5))))
52634 := ((C((C(4) - C(3))) - C(6)) + C((C(2) + (5))))
52648 := (C(8) - ((C(4) - C(6)) × C((2 + 5))))
52728 := (-C(8)) + (C((C(2) + (7 × 2))) × 5)
52733 := ((3 × C(((C(3) + (7)) - C(2)))) + (5))
52743 := (3 × (C(((4 × 7) - 2)) + (5)))

$$\begin{aligned} 52762 &:= (C(C(2)) + (((C(6) - (7)) \times 2) \times C(5))) \\ 52853 &:= ((3 \times C(((5 + 8) \times 2))) + C(5)) \\ 52875 &:= (C(5) \times (C(7) + (((8 \times 2) \times 5))) \\ 52973 &:= -((C(3) - ((C(7) + ((9^2))) \times C(5))) \\ 52992 &:= ((C(2) \times 9) \times (C(9) + (2 + 5))) \\ 52997 &:= ((((-7) - C(9)) \times (-9)) \times C(2)) + (5)) \\ 53103 &:= (3 \times (C(((0 - 1) + C(3))) + (C(5)))) \\ 53133 &:= (3 \times (C((C(3) - 1)) + (C(3) \times 5))) \\ 53136 &:= (C(6) \times (3 + ((1 \times 3)^5))) \\ 53195 &:= (-5) \times (9 - C((C((1 \times 3)) - (5)))) \\ 53213 &:= (-C(3)) - (C(-((1 - 23))) \times (-5)) \\ 53215 &:= ((-5) + C(-((1 - 23))) \times 5) \\ 53225 &:= ((5 \times C(22)) - (3 \times 5)) \\ 53232 &:= (-C(2)) - (-((3 + 2) \times C((C(3) - (5)))))) \\ 53235 &:= ((C((-5) + C(3))) + ((2 - 3)) \times 5) \\ 53295 &:= (-5) \times (-((9 + 2) - C((C(3) - (5)))))) \\ 53325 &:= ((C((5 \times C(2))) - C(3)) - C((C(3) - (5)))) \\ 53352 &:= (((C(2) - C(5)) \times (-3)) \times (C(3) + C(5))) \\ 53396 &:= (((C(6) + C(9)) + C(C(3))) + C((C(3) + (5)))) \\ 53413 &:= (31 \times (C((4 \times 3) - (5))) \\ 53443 &:= (((C(3) + (4)) \times C((4 \times 3))) - C(5)) \\ 53523 &:= (C(-((3 - 25))) + (C(35))) \\ 53545 &:= (((-((C(5) - C(4))) - C((-5) + C(3)))) \times (-5)) \\ 53564 &:= (-4) - (C(6) \times (-5 + (3^5))) \\ 53565 &:= (-5) \times (-65 - C((C(3) - (5)))) \\ 53625 &:= ((5 + C(2)) \times ((6 + C(3)) \times C(5))) \\ 53649 &:= (9 \times ((4 + C((6 \times 3))) + C(5))) \\ 53657 &:= -((C(7) + (C((5 \times 6)) \times (3 - 5)))) \\ 53752 &:= (C(C(2)) + (5 \times C((7 + (3 \times 5)))) \\ 53762 &:= (((C(26) + C(7)) \times 3) + (5)) \\ 53768 &:= (((-((C(8) - C((6 \times 7)))) - C(C(3))) - (C(5))) \\ 53785 &:= (-5) \times ((C(8) \times (-7 \times 3)) - (5)) \\ 53848 &:= ((C(8) - (4)) \times ((8 - C(3)) + C(5))) \\ 53853 &:= (C(C(3)) + ((5 \times C((-8) + C(3)))) - (C(5))) \\ 53875 &:= (((5 + C(7)) + (83)) \times C(5)) \\ 53928 &:= ((C(8) - C(2)) \times ((9 - C(3)) + C(5))) \\ 53946 &:= ((C(((C(6)/4) + 9)) + C(C(3)))/5) \\ 53973 &:= -((C(3) + (-((7 + 9)) \times C((3 \times 5)))) \\ 54143 &:= (C(-((3 - 41))) - (C((4 + 5)))) \\ 54157 &:= (C((7 + 5)) + ((1 + C(C(4)))/5)) \\ 54193 &:= (((-3) - C(9)) + (C((1 + C(4)))/5)) \\ 54216 &:= (C(6) + ((C(12)/4) \times C(5))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54243 &:= (C(C(3)) + (C((4 + C(2))) \times (4 \times 5))) \\ 54272 &:= (C(C(2)) \times (((-7) - C(2)) - (4)) + C(5)) \\ 54275 &:= ((((-5) + C(7)) + C(C(2))) \times C(4)) - (C(5)) \\ 54277 &:= ((((-7) + C(7)) + C(C(2))) \times C(4)) + (5)) \\ 54289 &:= (((9 + C(8))^2) + (4))/5) \\ 54329 &:= (((9 - C(C(2))) \times (C(3) \times (-4))) + (5)) \\ 54343 &:= ((C(C(3)) \times 4) - (C((34 - 5)))) \\ 54375 &:= (C(5) + (((C(7) + C(3)) + C(4)) \times C(5))) \\ 54537 &:= -((C(7) \times (((C(3) - C(5)) + C(4)) - C(5)))) \\ 54624 &:= (((4 \times C((C(2) + (6)))) + C(C(4)))/5) \\ 54625 &:= (C(5) \times ((C((2 \times 6))/4) + (5))) \\ 54648 &:= (((C(8) + C(4)) + C(6)) \times (C(4) + (5))) \\ 54656 &:= (((6^5) \times 6) + C((4 \times 5))) \\ 54683 &:= ((C(38) - 64) - C(5)) \\ 54723 &:= (-C(3)) - ((C(C(2)) - (74)) \times (-C(5))) \\ 54743 &:= (C((C(3) + (4 + 7))) - (4 + C(5))) \\ 54744 &:= (-((C(4) + C(4))) + C(-((7 - 45)))) \\ 54747 &:= (C(((7 + 4) + C((7 - 4)))) - (C(5))) \\ 54781 &:= ((((-1) + C(8)) + C(7)) \times C(4)) + C(5)) \\ 54784 &:= (C(4) \times ((C(8) + C(7)) - ((4 - 5)))) \\ 54803 &:= ((C((30 + 8)) - C(4)) - (5)) \\ 54832 &:= (C(2) \times (C((C(3) - C((8/4)))) - (5))) \\ 54852 &:= (C(-((2 - (5 \times 8)))) - (4 \times 5)) \\ 54866 &:= (-6) + C(((6 + ((8/4)^5))) \\ 54867 &:= (C(((7 \times 6) - 8) + 4)) - (5)) \\ 54872 &:= (C(2 \times (((7 \times 8)/4) + 5))) \\ 54875 &:= (((5 \times C(7)) \times (8 \times 4)) - (5)) \\ 54877 &:= (C(((((-7) + C(7))/8) - (4))) + (5)) \\ 54914 &:= ((C((C(4) + 1)) + (9 - C(4)))/5) \\ 54917 &:= (C(((C(7) - 1)/9)) + 45) \\ 54925 &:= (C(((52 + 9) + 4))/5) \\ 54931 &:= (C(-((1 - 39))) + ((C(4) - (5)))) \\ 54933 &:= (C(C(3)) + ((3 \times 94) \times C(5))) \\ 54945 &:= (((5 \times C((4 + 9))) + (4)) \times 5) \\ 54966 &:= (C(6) - (-6) \times ((9 + C(4)) \times C(5))) \\ 54997 &:= (C(-(((7 - 9) - (9 \times 4)))) + (C(5))) \\ 55146 &:= (C(6) - ((C((C(4) + 1)))/(-5)) - (5)) \\ 55245 &:= (-5) \times (-C(4) - (C((C(2) + (5))) \times 5)) \\ 55279 &:= ((C(9) \times (-((7^2)) + C(5))) - C(5)) \\ 55286 &:= ((C((6 \times 8))/2) - (5 + 5)) \\ 55412 &:= (C(C(2)) - ((C((1 + C(4))) - (C(5)))/(-5))) \\ 55488 &:= -((C(8) + ((8 - C(4)) \times C((5 + 5)))) \end{aligned}$$

- 55523 := (C(C(3)) - (C(C(2)) × (55 - C(5))))
55562 := (C(C(2)) - ((C(65)/(-5)) - C(5)))
55566 := (6 × C(((6 + 5) + 5) + 5))
55625 := ((C(5) + ((2⁶) × 5)) × C(5))
55654 := (C((4 + 5)) + (C(65)/5))
55657 := -((C(7) - (56 × C((5 + 5))))))
55659 := ((C(9) + (5)) + (C(65)/5))
55744 := (C(4) + (C(4) × ((7 × C(5)) - (5))))
55832 := (C(2) × (C((C(3) - 8)) - (5 - C(5))))
55836 := ((C(6) + C(C(3))) + C((8 + (5 × 5))))
55875 := (C(5) × (7 + (8 × 55)))
55912 := (C(2) × ((C(19) + (5)) + C(5)))
55933 := ((3 × C(C(3))) + ((9 - (5⁵))))
55973 := -((C(3) + (-7) × C(((9 - 5) × 5))))
56203 := (C((30 + C(2))) + C((6 + 5)))
56224 := (C((42 - 2)) - (6⁵))
56257 := ((C(7) × (-52) + C(6)) + (5))
56316 := (-6) × ((-1) × C((C(3) - (6)))) - (C(5)))
56376 := -((C(6) × ((C(7) - ((3⁶))) + C(5))))
56462 := ((-2) - C(6)) × ((C(4) × (-6)) + C(5))
56544 := ((C(C(4)) - C((C(4) - (5)))) - ((C(6) + (5))))
56625 := (((-C(5)) + C(C(2))) + (66)) × C(5))
56673 := (C(3) × (((C(7) + (6)) × 6) + (5)))
56683 := (C(C(3)) + ((C(C((8 - 6))) - C(6)) × C(5)))
56742 := -((C(2) + (((C(4) × (-7)) - (6)) × C(5))))
56745 := (-5) - (((C(4) × (-7)) - (6)) × C(5))
56826 := (-6) + (C(C(2)) × (-((8 + 6)) + C(5)))
56832 := (C((2³)) × (-((8 + 6)) + C(5)))
56835 := ((5 × C(3)) × ((C(8) - C(6)) + C(5)))
56844 := (-4) × ((C(4) × (-8) - C(6)) + C(5))
56875 := ((-57) + C(C((8 - 6)))) × C(5)
57122 := ((C(C(2)) - C((C(2) - 1))) × (C(7) - (5)))
57276 := (((C(6) - ((7²))) × C(7)) - (5))
57293 := -((C((C(3) - 9)) + ((C(C(2)) - (7)) × (-C(5))))))
57295 := (((C(5) × (-9)) - C(C(2))) × (-7 × 5))
57321 := (((1 + 2) × C(C(3))) - (C((7 + 5))))
57331 := (((1 - C(C(3))) × (-3)) - (C(7) × 5))
57332 := (-2) - ((-3) × C(C(3))) + (C(7) × 5))
57334 := (((4 × C(C(3))) - C(C(3))) - (C(7) × 5))
57344 := ((4 - (-4) × C(3)) × C(C((7 - 5))))
57367 := (C(7) - ((-6) - C(3)) × C((7 + 5)))
57375 := ((((-5) - C(7))/(-3)) + C(7)) × C(5)
57456 := ((-C(6)) + C(((5 - 4) + (7))))/5
57564 := (((4 - 6) + C(5)) × (C(7) + C(5)))
57568 := ((8 + C(6)) × ((C(5) + (7)) + C(5)))
57625 := (C(5) × ((C(2) × (6 × 7)) + C(5)))
57627 := (((C(7) + C(C(2))) × (-6) + C(7))/5)
57637 := (((C((-7) + C(3))) + C(6)) × 7) + (C(5)))
57687 := (C(7) + (C(8) × (-((6 + 7)) + C(5))))
57793 := (C(39) + (-7) × (C(7) - C(5)))
57833 := ((3 × C(C(3))) + (C(8) - C((7 + 5))))
57844 := (-4) × (((-4) × C(8)) × 7) - C(5))
57875 := (((57 × 8) + 7) × C(5))
57876 := -((C(6) + (((C(7) - C(8)) × C(7)) - C(5))))
57932 := -((C(C(2)) - (C(39) + (-7) × C(5))))
57948 := (((C(8) - C(4)) - 9) × (7 + C(5)))
58126 := ((6 × C(21)) - (C(8) × (-5)))
58157 := (-C(7)) + ((-C(5)) - C(-((1 - 8)))) × (-C(5)))
58195 := -(((C(5) + C(9)) - ((1 + 8)⁵))
58293 := -((C(3) - (C(9) × ((2 × 8) × 5))))
58295 := (-5) × ((C(9) × (-2 × 8)) + (5))
58319 := -((C((9 + 1)) - C((3 × (8 + 5))))
58339 := (-C(9)) - ((-3) × (C(C(3)) + 8)) + (5))
58344 := (44 × (C((3 + 8)) - (5)))
58354 := (C(45) - (3 + (8⁵)))
58368 := (C(8) × (6 × ((3 × 8) - 5)))
58372 := (C((C(2) + (7))) + ((C(38) + C(5))))
58375 := (((C(5) + C(7)) × C(-((3 - 8)))) - (C(5)))
58383 := (3 × ((C(8) × 38) + (5)))
58393 := ((3 × ((-C(9)) + C(C(3))) + C(8)) - (5))
58398 := (((C(8) - C(9)) + C(C(3))) × (8 - 5))
58437 := ((C(7) + (-3) × C(4)) × (C(8) - C(5)))
58532 := -((C(C(2)) - ((C(C(3)) × (-5 - 8)) - (5))))
58596 := -((C(6) - ((-9) + C(5)) × (C(8) - (5))))
58625 := (C(5) × (((C(2) × (-6)) + C(8)) + (5)))
58647 := ((C(7) - (4)) × ((6 × 8) + C(5)))
58674 := -((4 - 7) × (C((C(6)/8)) - (C(5))))
58733 := ((3 × C(C(3))) - (C(7) - C((8 - 5))))
58824 := ((-C(4) + C(-((2 - 8)))) × (C(8) - C(5)))
58833 := ((3 × C(C(3))) - C(((8/8) + 5)))
58926 := (-6) × ((-2) × C((9 + 8))) + (5))
58931 := (((-1) + C(39)) - C(8)) + C(5)
58944 := -((C(4) × (C(4) - 985)))
58984 := (((C((4 × 8)) × 9) + 8)/5)

- 59057 := (C((7 - 5)) + (09⁵))
59113 := (C((3 + 1)) + ((1 × 9)⁵))
59114 := (C(4) + (1 + ((1 × 9)⁵)))
59133 := ((3 × (C(3) + 1)) + (9⁵))
59167 := ((-7) + C((6 - 1))) + (9⁵)
59174 := (-4 + 7)¹⁺⁹ + C(5)
59176 := (((C(6) - C(7)) × (-1)) + (9⁵))
59182 := (C(2) + ((C(81)/9) + C(5)))
59183 := (((3⁸) + 1) × 9) + C(5)
59185 := ((C((5 × 8) - 1)) - 9) - C(5)
59193 := ((C(39) - (1⁹)) - C(5))
59194 := (C(((49 - 1) - 9)) - C(5))
59217 := ((-((C(7) + 1)) + C(C(2))) + (9⁵))
59218 := ((C(8) - C((-1) + C(2))) + (9⁵))
59224 := (C(4) - ((2 - C(C(2))) × (-9) + C(5)))
59236 := ((C(6) - C(3)) - (2 - (9⁵)))
59237 := (((-7) - (3^{C(2)})) × (-9)) + C(5)
59239 := (((C(9) - C(3)) - C(C(2))) + (9⁵))
59243 := ((3 × C(4)) + (2 + (9⁵)))
59274 := (C((47 - C(2))) - (9 × 5))
59275 := -((((C(5) - C(7)) - C(2)) - (9⁵)))
59276 := (((6 - 7) + C(C(2))) × (-9) + C(5))
59285 := (C(5) + ((C(8) - 2) × (-9) + C(5)))
59293 := (((C(3) + C(9)) - C(C(2))) + (9⁵))
59307 := ((-7) + C(039)) - (5)
59312 := ((-2) + C((1 × 39))) - (5)
59314 := (C((C((4 - 1)) + (3 + 9))) - (5))
59317 := ((-7) + C((1 × 39))) + (5)
59319 := C(9 - (((1 × 3) - 9) × 5))
59321 := ((-((1 + 2)) + C(39)) + (5))
59323 := ((-((3 - 2)) + C(39)) + (5))
59324 := (C((((4²) × 3) - 9)) + (5))
59326 := (((-6) + C(2)) + C(39)) + (5)
59328 := (((8/2) + C(39)) + (5))
59332 := (((2³) + C(39)) + (5))
59333 := (((3 × 3) + C(39)) + (5))
59338 := (((8 × 3) + C(39)) - (5))
59341 := (C(-((1 - 4))) + ((C(39) - (5))))
59346 := (((C(6) - C(4)) + C(39)) - C(5))
59359 := (((9 × 5) + C(39)) - (5))
59362 := (((C(2) × 6) + C(39)) - (5))
59372 := (C(C(2)) + ((-7) × C(3)) + (9⁵))
59373 := (C(3) × (7 + ((3 × C(9)) + (5))))
59386 := (-6) - ((8³) × (9 - C(5)))
59387 := (C(7) - ((8 - 3) - (9⁵)))
59388 := (((8 × 8) + C(39)) + (5))
59433 := (((3 + 3) × C(4)) + (9⁵))
59435 := ((C((5 + 34)) - 9) + C(5))
59437 := ((-7) + C((3 + (4 × 9)))) + C(5)
59444 := (C(((4 + 44) - 9)) + C(5))
59453 := ((C((35 + 4)) + 9) + C(5))
59464 := (C(4) + (C(6) × ((C(4) - 9) × 5)))
59493 := ((C(39) + (49)) + C(5))
59497 := (C(C(-((7 - 9)))) - (C(4) - (9⁵)))
59517 := ((C(7) + C((1 × 5))) + (9⁵))
59554 := ((4 × C(5)) + (5 + (9⁵)))
59561 := (C(C(((1 + 6) - 5))) + (9⁵))
59562 := (C(C(2)) + ((6 - 5) + (9⁵)))
59582 := (2 × C((C((8 - 5)) + (9 - 5)))
59583 := ((C(3) + C(8)) - ((5 - (9⁵))))
59588 := ((C(8) + C((8 - 5))) + (9⁵))
59624 := (((-4) + C(C(2))) + (6)) × (-9) + C(5))
59625 := (C(5) × ((2 × C(6)) + (9 × 5)))
59633 := ((3 × (C(C(3)) + C(6))) - (C((9 - 5))))
59648 := -((C(8) - (C(4) × ((C(6) + C(9)) - (5))))))
59652 := (C(C(2)) - (((C(5) - C(6)) - (9⁵))))
59657 := ((C(7) + C(((5 × 6) + 9))) - (5))
59659 := ((C(9) - C(5)) + (6 + (9⁵)))
59727 := (((C(7) - C(2)) + C(7)) + (9⁵))
59735 := (((5 - 3) × C(7)) + (9⁵))
59762 := (C(C(2)) + ((6 × 79) × C(5)))
59778 := (C((8 + (7/7))) + (9⁵))
59779 := (C(9) + (((7/7) + (9⁵))))
59787 := ((C(7) + C(((8 - C(7))/(-9)))) + (C(5)))
59838 := ((-83) × (8 - C(9))) - (5)
59848 := (-8) + ((4 + C(8)) × (-9) + C(5))
59895 := ((C(5) + C(9)) - ((8 - (9⁵))))
59932 := -((C(C(2)) - (C(39) - (-9) × C(5))))
59968 := (((-8) + C(6)) + C(9)) × C((9 - 5))
59986 := (((C(6) - 8) + C(9)) + (9⁵))
60472 := -((C(2) + (-((7 × 40)) × C(6))))
60475 := (-5) - (-((7 × 40)) × C(6))

- 60875 := (C(5) × (7 + (80 × 6)))
61233 := (3 × ((C(C(3)) + C(C(2))) - (-1) × C(6)))
61236 := (((-C(6)) + C(C(3))) - C(21)) × 6
61344 := (((4⁴) + C(3)) + 1) × C(6)
61395 := (-5) × (9 + (-3) × C(16)))
61397 := (C(7) × (((-9) - C(3)) - 1) + C(6)))
61479 := (-C(9)) - (C(((7 + C(4)) + 1)/(-6)))
61533 := -(C(C(3)) + (((-3) × C(5)) - 1) × C(6)))
61776 := (C(6) × (C(7) - ((C(7) - 1)/6)))
61952 := (C(C(2)) × (C(5) - (9 + 1) - 6))
61958 := ((85 × C(9)) - (1 + 6))
62125 := (-C(5)) × ((21 - C(C(2))) - (6))
62144 := (-C(4)) - (C((C(4) + C((1 × 2))))/(-6))
62199 := (-9) + (((-C(9)) × C(C((1 × 2))))/(-6))
62208 := (C((8 + C((02 + 2))))/6)
62238 := ((C((8 - 3)) - 2) × (C(C(2)) - (6)))
62272 := (C((C(2) × (7 - 2))) - C((2 × 6)))
62284 := ((C((48 + 2))/2) - C(6))
62292 := (((-C(2)) + C((9 × C(2)))) + C(C(2)))/6
62294 := (((4 + C((9 × C(2)))) + C(C(2)))/6)
62336 := (((-C(6)) + C(C(3))) + C((C(3) + C(2)))) - (6)
62343 := (C((C(3) + (4))) + (C(32) - C(6)))
62348 := (((8⁴) - C(C(3))) × (2 - 6))
62424 := ((C((C(4) + C(2)))/(4 + 2)) + C(6))
62426 := ((C(6) + 2) + (C((C(4) + C(2)))/6))
62452 := ((C(25) × 4) - (C(2) × 6))
62456 := (((6⁵) + 4) × C(2)) + C(6)
62458 := ((C(8) × ((C(5) - C(4)) × 2)) - (6))
62464 := (((C(4) - (6)) + C(4)) × C((2 + 6)))
62494 := ((4 × C(((9 - 4)²))) - (6))
62496 := (((C(6) + C((9 × 4))) × C(2))/6)
62521 := -(C((1 + C(2))) + (-C(5)) × (C(C(2)) - (6))))
62522 := (((C(C(2)) + 2) × C(5)) - C((2 × 6)))
62524 := ((-4) + C(2)) × (C((5²)) + (6))
62529 := (-((C(9) - C(2))) - (-C(5)) × (C(C(2)) - (6))))
62534 := (C(4) - (((3 - C(5)) × C(C(2))) - (6)))
62608 := ((80 + 6) × (C(C(2)) + C(6)))
62634 := ((C((-4) + C(3))) - (C((6 × 2)))) × 6
62693 := (-C(3)) - (((C(9) + (6)) × C(C(2)))/(-6))
62736 := (-6) × (((-C(3) - 7)) × C(C(2))) - C(6))
62767 := ((C(7) + C(6)) - (C(72)/(-6)))
62783 := -(((C(38) - C((7²))) - (6)))
62784 := ((C(4) + C(8)) - (C(72)/(-6)))
62792 := ((2⁹⁺⁷) - C((C(2) + (6))))
62875 := (C(5) × (((-7) + C(8)) - C(2)) + (6))
62892 := (((C(2) + C(9)) × C(8)) + C(2))/6
62929 := ((C(9) - C(2)) + (C((9 × C(2)))/6))
62964 := ((4 - C(6)) × (-((9²)) - C(6)))
63125 := (C(5) × (C(C(2)) - ((1³) + 6)))
63159 := (-C(9)) - (C((-5) + C((1 × 3))) × (-6))
63226 := (-C(((6²) + 2)) - (C(C(3)) × (-6)))
63261 := (((1 - C(6)) + C(C(2))) × (-3) + C(6))
63284 := (((-4) + C(8)) × C((2 + 3))) - C(6)
63288 := (((C(8) - C((8 - 2))) - 3) × C(6))
63293 := (((C(C(3)) + (C(9))) + C((C(2) + C(3)))) + (6))
63325 := (C((5 × C(2))) - (C(3) + (3 × C(6))))
63352 := (((C(2) × 5)³) - (3 × C(6)))
63358 := (-C(8)) - ((C((-5) + C(3))) - 3) × (-6))
63361 := (C(16) + ((3 × C(C(3))) + C(6)))
63364 := (4 × (C((-((6/3)) + C(3))) + C(6)))
63423 := -(C(C(3)) - ((C(24) + C(3)) × 6))
63424 := ((4^{C(2)}) - (C(4) × (C(3) + (6))))
63425 := (5 × ((C(C(2)) + C((-4) + C(3)))) + (6))
63484 := ((-4) - C(8)) + C((4 + 36))
63488 := (C(8) × (-8) - (-4) × (C(3) + (6)))
63504 := ((-C(4)) + C(((0 - 5) + C(3))) × 6)
63538 := (-C(8)) - ((C(3) + C((-5) + C(3))) × (-6))
63594 := ((-49) + C((-5) + C(3))) × 6
63625 := (C(5) × (C((2 + 6)) + ((3 - 6))))
63657 := -(C(7) - C((5 × ((6/3) + 6))))
63693 := (C(39) + (6 × (3⁶)))
63744 := (C(4) × (-4) + C(((7 - 3) + 6)))
63782 := (-2) + ((8 × C((-7) + C(3))) - C(6))
63784 := (C(-((4 - 8) × (7 + 3))) - C(6))
63822 := ((C(22) - (8 + 3)) × 6)
63824 := -(C(4) + (C((2 × (8 + 3))) × (-6)))
63838 := (C(((8 - 3) × 8)) - (C(3) × 6))
63841 := ((C((1 + 4)) × (C(8) - 3)) + C(6))
63855 := ((-5) × (C(5) - C(8))) × (C(3) + (6))
63875 := (C(5) × (-7 - ((8³) + 6)))
63881 := (((-1) + C(8)) × C((8 - 3))) + (6)
63884 := (-4) - ((-8) × C((8 + 3))) × 6
63888 := ((8 × C((-((8 + 8)) + C(3)))) × 6)
63928 := (-8) - ((C(C(2)) - (C((9 - 3)))) × (-C(6)))

- 63936 := ((C(C((6/3))) - C((9 - 3)))) × C(6))
63958 := (((C((8 × 5)) - 9) - C(3)) - (6))
63964 := (C((C(4) - (C(6)/9))) - 36)
63973 := -(C(3) - C((7 + ((9 × 3) + 6))))
63992 := (-C(2) + C(((9) + C(9))/(3 × 6)))
63995 := (-5) + C(((9) + C(9))/(3 × 6)))
64043 := ((-3) + C(40)) + 46)
64049 := (((-9) + C(40)) + C(4)) - (6))
64058 := ((C((8 × 5)) + C(04)) - (6))
64064 := (C(4) + C(((60 × 4)/6)))
64125 := (C(5) + C((2 × (14 + 6))))
64127 := ((C(7) + C((C(2) × (1 + 4)))) - C(6))
64128 := (((C(8) × (-21)) + C(4)) × (-6))
64152 := (((C((2 × 5)) - 1) × C(4)) + C(6))
64204 := (((C(40) - C(2)) - (4)) + C(6))
64216 := (C((((6 - 1) × 2) × 4)) + C(6))
64233 := ((3 × C(C(3))) + (24 × C(6)))
64243 := ((C(3) + C((C(4) - (24)))) + C(6))
64272 := ((C((C(2) + (7 × 2))) + C(4)) × 6)
64294 := (((C(C(4)) - C((9 × 2)))/4) + C(6))
64337 := ((C(7) + C(((3 - C(3)) + C(4)))) - (6))
64343 := (C((3 + 4)) + C((34 + 6)))
64347 := ((C(7) + (4)) + C((34 + 6)))
64357 := ((C(7) × (-5) - (-3) × C(4))) + C(6))
64384 := ((4⁸) + ((-3) × C(4)) × 6))
64385 := ((C(5) × (C(8) + 3)) + (4 + 6))
64448 := ((C(8) - C(4)) + C((4 × (4 + 6))))
64456 := ((C(6) × (-5)) + (4^{C(-4+6)}))
64457 := -(C(7) - (-5) × ((4 - C(4)) × C(6)))
64473 := ((C(37) - (4)) + C((4 × 6)))
64511 := (-1) + ((1 + C(5)) × C(C(-(4 - 6))))
64512 := (C(C(2)) × ((1 + (5 × 4)) × 6))
64518 := ((8 × ((1 + C(5)) × C(4))) + (6))
64522 := ((C(C(2)) + C((C(2) × 5))) + (4 + 6))
64524 := (((4 + C(C(2))) × C(5)) + (4 × 6))
64547 := ((C(7) × (C(4) + C(5))) - (C(4) + C(6)))
64568 := -(C(((8 - 6)⁵)) - C(46))
64582 := (C(C(2)) + (((C((8 × 5)) + C(4)) + (6))))
64624 := ((4^{C(2)}) - ((C(6) - C(4)) × 6))
64729 := (C(9) + C((C(2) × ((7 + 4) - 6)))
64773 := (C(3) × ((C(7) × 7) + ((4 - 6))))
64827 := (7 × C(((C(2) - C(8))/(-4 × 6))))
64857 := ((-7) + C((5 × 8))) - (-4) × C(6))
64864 := (C(4) - (((C(6) - C(8)) - (4)) × C(6)))
64872 := (((C(C(2)) - (7 - C(8))) × C(4)) - C(6))
64875 := (C(5) × (7 + C(((8/4) + 6))))
64954 := (((4⁵) - 9) × C(4)) - (6))
64977 := -(((C(7) - ((7 + 9)⁴)) + C(6)))
65119 := (((9 + C(C((1 + 1)))) × C(5)) - (6))
65125 := (((5^{C(2)}) × (-1)) - C(5))/(-6))
65178 := (((C(8) + (7)) × (1 + C(5))) - C(6))
65268 := (C(8) - (((6 + C(C(2))) × (-C(5))) - (6)))
65284 := (((4 + C(8)) + C(2)) × C(5)) - C(6))
65304 := ((C(40) - C(3)) + C((5 + 6)))
65331 := (C((13 + C(3))) + C((5 + 6)))
65344 := ((C(C(4))/4) - ((C(3) + (5)) × 6))
65358 := ((C((8 × 5)) + C(3)) + C((5 + 6)))
65384 := (C(4) + ((C(8) × (3 + C(5))) - C(6)))
65433 := (C(C(3)) - (((3 - C(4)) × C(5)) × 6))
65444 := (((4 - C(C(4)))/(-4)) + (C(5) - C(6)))
65445 := (C(5) - ((C(4) × (-4⁵)) + C(6)))
65469 := (((C(9) - C((6 × 4))) × (-5)) - (6))
65472 := (((2⁷) + C(4)) × (C(5) + C(6)))
65532 := ((2 × (C((C(3) + (5))) - (5))) + (6))
65583 := (C(3) × (((C(8) × 5) - C(5)) - (6)))
65694 := ((C((4 + 9)) × (6 × 5)) - C(6))
65728 := (8 × (C((C(2) + (7 + 5))) + C(6)))
65735 := (C(5) + (((3⁷) × 5) × 6))
65744 := ((C(C(4))/4) - ((C((7 - 5)) - C(6))))
65746 := (C(6) + ((4^{C(7-5)}) - (6)))
65752 := ((C((2⁵)) × (7 - 5)) + C(6))
65823 := (3 × (C(28) - (5 + 6)))
65869 := (((9 + 6) + C(8)) × C(5)) - (6))
65875 := (-5) × (7 + (C((8 + 5)) × (-6)))
65918 := -(C(8) - ((-1) - C(9)) × (C(5) - C(6)))
65924 := (((4^{C(2)}) + C(9)) - C(5)) - C(6))
65928 := (-82) × ((9 + C(5)) × (-6))
65946 := (-6) × ((C((4 + 9)) × (-5)) - (6))
65952 := -(C(C(2)) - (C(5) - (C(9) × (C(5) - C(6))))))
66093 := (-3) + ((90 + C(6)) × C(6))
66096 := ((C(6) × 90) + (6⁶))
66123 := (C(C(3)) - (((2 - 1) - C(6)) × C(6)))
66312 := (C(C((2 + 1))) - ((C(3) - (6⁶))))

$$\begin{aligned} 66313 &:= (C(C(3)) - ((-1) + C(3)) - (6^6)) \\ 66331 &:= -(((C(-((1-3))) - C(C(3))) - (6^6))) \\ 66333 &:= ((C((3^3)) + C(36)) - (6)) \\ 66336 &:= ((-6) + C(C(3))) + (3 + (6^6)) \\ 66343 &:= (C(C(3)) - (-4) - C((3 \times (6+6)))) \\ 66352 &:= (((C(2) + 5)) + C(C(3))) + (6^6) \\ 66373 &:= (C(C(3)) - ((-7) - C(3)) - (6^6)) \\ 66394 &:= (((C(4) - 9) + C(C(3))) + (6^6)) \\ 66403 &:= (C(C(3)) + (C(04) + (6^6))) \\ 66424 &:= ((4^{C(2)}) + (-4) \times (-6) - C(6))) \\ 66528 &:= ((-8) - C((2 \times 5))) \times (-66) \\ 66542 &:= (((C(C(2)) - 4) \times (C(5) + 6)) - (6)) \\ 66744 &:= (((44 \times 7) \times C(6)) + C(6)) \\ 66824 &:= (((4^{C(2)}) - 8) + (C(6) \times 6)) \\ 66856 &:= (((6 + C(5)) \times C(C(8-6))) - C(6)) \\ 66875 &:= (C(5) \times (7 + (8 \times 66))) \\ 67193 &:= (-C((3+9))) + C(-((1 - (7 \times 6)))) \\ 67229 &:= -((C(((9+2) + C(2))) - (C((7 \times 6)))) \\ 67239 &:= (93 \times (C((2+7)) - (6))) \\ 67266 &:= ((C(6) + 6) \times (C(C(2)) + (7 - C(6)))) \\ 67375 &:= (C(5) \times (((C(7) - C(3)) + 7) + C(6))) \\ 67544 &:= -((C(4) - (((C(4) \times 5) - 7) \times C(6)))) \\ 67582 &:= (-2) - (C(8) \times ((-5) - C(7)) + C(6))) \\ 67584 &:= ((C(4) \times 8) \times ((5 + C(7)) - C(6))) \\ 67585 &:= (-5) + ((C(8) \times (C(5) + 7)) + (6)) \\ 67593 &:= ((C(C(3)) + (9 \times C((5 \times 7))))/6) \\ 67594 &:= ((C(C(4))/9 - 5) + (C(7) \times 6)) \\ 67639 &:= (((C(9) - 3)/6) \times (C(7) + C(6))) \\ 67645 &:= (((C(5) - 4) \times (C(6) + C(7))) + (6)) \\ 67914 &:= ((C(4) - 1) \times ((C(9) + C(7)) + (6))) \\ 67995 &:= (-5) \times (9 - ((9 \times 7) \times C(6))) \\ 68125 &:= (C(5) \times ((C((2+1)) + C(8)) + (6))) \\ 68257 &:= (C(7) \times (-((5^2) - 8) + C(6))) \\ 68315 &:= (-5) \times (-1) - (C(3) \times (C(8) - (6)))) \\ 68392 &:= ((C(C(2)) \times (9 + C(-((3-8)))) - C(6)) \\ 68596 &:= (-6) + (((9 + C(5)) \times C(8)) - (6)) \\ 68599 &:= (-9) - ((-9) - C(5)) \times C(C((8-6)))) \\ 68634 &:= ((C((-4) + C(3))) - (C(6) + C(8))) \times 6) \\ 68698 &:= ((C((8+9)) - (6)) \times (8+6)) \\ 68782 &:= (C(((2+8) + 7)) \times (8+6)) \\ 68894 &:= ((C(-((4-9))) + 8) \times (C(8) + (6))) \\ 68914 &:= (C(41) - ((9-8) + 6)) \\ 68921 &:= C((((1+2) \times 9) + 8) + 6) \\ 68923 &:= (C((32+9)) + (8-6)) \\ 68927 &:= (C((7 + (2 \times (9+8)))) + (6)) \\ 68935 &:= (C(((5 + C(3)) + 9)) + (8+6)) \\ 68957 &:= (C(7) + (((C(5) + 9) \times C(8)) + (6))) \\ 68959 &:= (((95 \times C(9)) - C(8)) + C(6)) \\ 68968 &:= ((C(8) - C(6)) \times ((9+8) + C(6))) \\ 69137 &:= (C((((C(7) + C(3)) - 1)/9) + C(6)) \\ 69143 &:= (((-3) + C(41)) + 9) + C(6) \\ 69255 &:= ((5 \times C((5-2))) \times (C(9) - C(6))) \\ 69345 &:= ((-5) \times (C(4) + 3)) \times (9 - C(6)) \\ 69375 &:= (C(5) \times (((C(7) + C(3)) \times (-9))/(-6))) \\ 69434 &:= (C(((C(4) - C(3)) + 4)) + (C(9) - C(6))) \\ 69552 &:= ((2 - (-5) \times C(-((5-9)))) \times C(6)) \\ 69598 &:= (((C(8) + 9) \times (C(5) + 9)) - C(6)) \\ 69776 &:= ((C((6 \times 7)) - C((7+9))) - C(6)) \\ 69792 &:= ((2 - C(9)) \times (-((7+9) \times 6))) \\ 69848 &:= (((8^4) \times (8+9)) + C(6)) \\ 69875 &:= (C(5) \times ((-7) + C(8)) + ((9 \times 6))) \\ 69944 &:= (-4) \times (C((4+9)) - C(C((9-6)))) \\ 69952 &:= (-((2^5)) - (C(9) \times (-96))) \\ 69963 &:= -(((C(3) - 6) + (C(9) \times (-96)))) \\ 69969 &:= ((96 \times C(9)) - ((9+6))) \\ 69972 &:= ((-2) - (-((7+9) \times C(9))) \times 6) \\ 69977 &:= (-7) - (-((7+9) \times C(9)) \times 6) \\ 69978 &:= (((87+9) \times C(9)) - (6)) \\ 69982 &:= (-2) - (8 \times ((C(9) + C(9)) \times (-6))) \\ 69984 &:= (((4 \times 8) \times C(9)) \times (9-6)) \\ 69986 &:= (-((6-8)) - (C(9) \times (-96))) \\ 70333 &:= (C(C(3)) - (3 - C((30+7)))) \\ 70336 &:= (C(C((6-3))) + (C((30+7)))) \\ 70343 &:= ((C(C(3)) + C((C(4) - C(3)))) - (0-7)) \\ 70625 &:= (C(5) \times (C(C(2)) + (60-7))) \\ 70835 &:= (5 \times (C((3 \times 8)) + C(07))) \\ 70875 &:= (C(5) \times ((7 \times 80) + 7)) \\ 71136 &:= ((C(6)/3) \times (C(11) - C(7))) \\ 71168 &:= (C(8) \times (C(6) - ((11 \times 7)))) \\ 71328 &:= (8 \times (-2) + ((C(3) - 1) \times C(7))) \\ 71344 &:= ((4+4) \times ((C(3) - 1) \times C(7))) \\ 71362 &:= ((2 \times C((6 + C(3)))) - C((1+7))) \\ 71442 &:= ((-((2-4) \times C((C(4) - 1)))/7) \\ 71452 &:= (2 \times (5 - (C((C(4) - 1))/(-7)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}71494 &:= (((4 \times C(9)) + C(41)) - C(7)) \\71496 &:= (C(6) \times (-((9 + 4) - 1) + C(7))) \\71687 &:= (C(7) \times ((-8) + C(6)) + (1^7)) \\71928 &:= (C((8 - 2)) \times (-((9 + 1) + C(7))) \\72135 &:= ((C((-5) + C(3))) - C((-1) + C(2))) \times 7 \\72233 &:= (((C(33) + C(2)) \times 2) + C(7)) \\72235 &:= -((C(5) + (C((3 \times 2)) \times (C(2) - C(7)))))) \\72261 &:= ((1 + C(6)) \times ((-2) - C(2)) + C(7)) \\72333 &:= -((C(3) + (C((3 + 3)) \times (C(2) - C(7)))))) \\72373 &:= (((3 \times 73) - C(2)) \times C(7)) \\72424 &:= (C(4) - (C((2 + 4)) \times (C(2) - C(7)))) \\72568 &:= (-8) + (C(6) \times (C((5 + 2)) - (7))) \\72576 &:= (C(6) \times ((7^5 - 2) - 7)) \\72625 &:= (C(5) \times (C(C(2)) + (62 + 7))) \\72657 &:= (((C(7) - 5)) \times C(6)) - C(2) - C(7) \\72666 &:= (C(6) + ((6 - C(6)) \times (-2) - C(7))) \\72667 &:= (((C(7) - 6)) \times C(6)) - C(-((2 - 7))) \\72675 &:= (((-5) + C(7)) \times (C(6) - 2)) + C(7) \\72687 &:= (((C(7) - 8) \times (C(6) + 2)) - C(7)) \\72716 &:= ((C(6) - ((1 + 7)/2)) \times C(7)) \\72759 &:= (C(9) - ((C(5) - C(7)) + C(2)) \times C(7)) \\72873 &:= (((3^7) + C(8)) \times 27) \\72875 &:= (-C(5)) \times ((-78) - C(C(2))) + (7)) \\72949 &:= (((C(9) + C(4)) \times 92) - (7)) \\72966 &:= (-6) \times (6 - C((9 + (2 \times 7)))) \\73029 &:= (9 \times C(20)) + (3 \times C(7)) \\73138 &:= (((-8) - C(C(3))) \times (1 - C(3)))/7 \\73144 &:= (C(C(4)) + (C(((4 - 1) + C(3))) \times (-7))) \\73164 &:= (C(4) - ((C(6) - 1) \times (3 - C(7)))) \\73174 &:= ((C(((4 \times 7) + 1)) \times 3) + (7)) \\73261 &:= (C((-((1 - 6)) \times C(2))) + C((3 \times 7))) \\73269 &:= (((-96^2) + C(C(3))) \times 7) \\73359 &:= -((C(9) - C(((5 - 3) \times 3) \times 7))) \\73376 &:= ((C(6) \times (C(7) - 3)) - C(-((3 - 7))) \\73568 &:= (8 \times (-65) + C((3 \times 7))) \\73576 &:= (C((6 \times 7)) - C(((5 \times 3) - 7))) \\73604 &:= ((C(40) + C((-6) + C(3))) + C(7)) \\73612 &:= (C(C(2)) - ((1 - C(6)) \times (-3) + C(7))) \\73629 &:= (C(9) \times ((2^6) + 37)) \\73634 &:= -((C(4) - ((3 - C(6)) \times (-3) - C(7)))) \\73656 &:= (C(6) \times (-((5 - 6) + 3)) + C(7)) \\73683 &:= ((C((3 \times 8)) \times 6) - C((3 \times 7)))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}73724 &:= ((C(42) - C(7)) - ((3 \times 7))) \\73728 &:= (C(8) \times ((C(2) + C((7 + 3)))/7)) \\73736 &:= ((C(6) \times (3 + C(7))) - C((3 + 7))) \\73742 &:= ((C(((2 + 4) \times 7)) - 3) - C(7)) \\73745 &:= (((-5 - 47)^3) - C(7)) \\73766 &:= (((-6) + C((6 \times 7))) + C(3)) - C(7) \\73783 &:= (((C(3) \times 8) \times (C(7) - 3)) + C(7)) \\73866 &:= (((-6) - C(6)) - (-8 \times C((3 \times 7)))) \\73928 &:= (8 \times ((C(C(2)) + (C(9))) + C((C(3) - (7))))) \\73953 &:= ((C(3) \times (-5)) + C((9 - 3) \times 7)) \\73968 &:= (8 \times (-((6 + 9)) + C((3 \times 7))) \\73972 &:= (((2^7) \times C(9)) - C(C(3))) + C(7) \\73985 &:= (-5) \times (C(8) + (C(9) \times (-3 \times 7))) \\74024 &:= -((C(4) - C(((2 + 04) \times 7))) \\74079 &:= (-9) + C((70 - (4 \times 7))) \\74088 &:= C(((8 - (8/04)) \times 7)) \\74125 &:= (C(5) \times ((2 \times C((1 + 4))) + C(7))) \\74159 &:= (C(-((9 - 51))) + (C(4) + (7))) \\74169 &:= (C(9) - (C(6) \times (-((1 - 4)) - C(7)))) \\74262 &:= -((C(C(2)) - ((C(6) - ((2 - 4)) \times C(7)))) \\74277 &:= ((7 + C((7 \times 2))) \times C(-((4 - 7))) \\74367 &:= (((7 \times 6)^3) - C(4)) + C(7) \\74375 &:= (C(5) \times (((C(7) - 3)/(-4)) \times (-7))) \\74427 &:= ((C((7 \times (2 + 4))) - (4)) + C(7)) \\74431 &:= (C(((1 - 3) + 44)) + C(7)) \\74435 &:= (C(((5 - C(3)) + C(4))) - (-4) - C(7)) \\74522 &:= (((-2) + C((2 + (5 \times 4)))) \times 7) \\74528 &:= (-8) + (C((2 + (5 \times 4))) \times 7) \\74536 &:= (C(((6/3) + (5 \times 4))) \times 7) \\74563 &:= (C(C(3)) - (((6^5) + C(4)) \times (-7))) \\74644 &:= (C(4) + ((-4) - C(6)) \times (4 - C(7))) \\74657 &:= ((75 \times C((6 + 4))) - C(7)) \\74697 &:= (((C(7) + C(9)) \times (6 + C(4))) - C(7)) \\74736 &:= (C(6) \times (3 + ((7^4)/7))) \\74752 &:= (C(C(2)) \times (C(5) - (7 - (4 \times 7)))) \\74763 &:= (C(3) - (C(6) \times (-((7 - 4)) - C(7)))) \\74824 &:= (((C(C(4)) - (C(2) + C(8))) + C(C(4)))/7) \\74888 &:= (88 \times ((C(8) - (4)) + C(7))) \\74948 &:= -((C(8) - (((C(4) - 9) \times 4) \times C(7))) \\74952 &:= (C(((2 - 5) + 9)) \times (4 + C(7))) \\75117 &:= (((C(7) + 1) - C((1 \times 5))) \times C(7)) \\75159 &:= (-9) + (C((5 + 1)) \times (5 + C(7)))\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 75164 &:= (-4) + (C(6) \times ((1 \times 5) + C(7))) \\ 75175 &:= (((5 + C(7)) \times C((1 + 5))) + (7)) \\ 75223 &:= ((C(C(3)) \times (C(2) - 2)) - (C((5 \times 7)))) \\ 75245 &:= ((-5) \times (C(4) + C(C(2)))) + (5^7) \\ 75274 &:= (C(4) - ((C(7) + 2) \times (C(5) - C(7)))) \\ 75329 &:= ((C(9) + C(C(2))) + (C((35 + 7)))) \\ 75378 &:= ((-8) \times C(7)) - ((3 - (5^7))) \\ 75456 &:= ((6 + C(5)) \times (C(4) + C(C(-(5 - 7)))))) \\ 75516 &:= ((C(6) + (1^5)) \times (5 + C(7))) \\ 75558 &:= (((C(8) - C((5 \times 5))) \times (-5)) - (7)) \\ 75607 &:= (((70 \times C(6)) \times 5) + (7)) \\ 75625 &:= (C(5) \times ((2 \times (6 + C(5))) + C(7))) \\ 75643 &:= (C(((-3) \times C(4)) / (-6))) + (C((5 \times 7))) \\ 75676 &:= ((C(6) - C(7)) + ((C(6) + (5)) \times C(7))) \\ 75712 &:= ((C(2) + C(-(1 - 7))) \times (-5) + C(7)) \\ 75717 &:= (((C(7) + 1) \times (-7)) + (5^7)) \\ 75722 &:= (C(C(2)) + ((-2) - C(7)) \times (C(5) - C(7))) \\ 75735 &:= ((5 \times C(3)) \times ((C(7) - C(5)) + C(7))) \\ 75789 &:= (9 \times ((C(8) - (C(7) \times 5)) \times (-7))) \\ 75803 &:= (((C(3) \times 08) + (5)) \times C(7)) \\ 75816 &:= (C(-(6 \times (1 - 8)))) + (C((5 + 7))) \\ 75824 &:= ((C(42) + 8) + C((5 + 7))) \\ 75867 &:= ((7 - C(6)) \times (C(8) + (C(5) \times (-7)))) \\ 75928 &:= -((C(((8/2) + 9)) - (5^7))) \\ 75934 &:= (-4) + ((-3) \times C(9)) + (5^7) \\ 75939 &:= (((9 - C(C(3))) / 9) + (5^7)) \\ 75953 &:= ((3 \times (5 - C(9))) + (5^7)) \\ 76146 &:= (((6^{4-1}) + 6) \times C(7)) \\ 76173 &:= (C(3) + (((7 - 1) + C(6)) \times C(7))) \\ 76273 &:= (((3^7) - 2) + C((6 \times 7))) \\ 76285 &:= (C(((5 \times 8) + 2)) + C((6 + 7))) \\ 76288 &:= (C(8) \times (82 + 67)) \\ 76475 &:= (-5) \times (((7^4) - C(6)) \times (-7)) \\ 76489 &:= (((9 - (8/4)) + C(6)) \times C(7)) \\ 76492 &:= -((C(C(2)) - ((C(9) \times 4) + C((6 \times 7)))))) \\ 76584 &:= -((C(4) - ((C(8) \times 5) + C((6 \times 7)))))) \\ 76711 &:= (-1) + ((1 + C(7)) \times (C(6) + (7))) \\ 76712 &:= (((2 - 1) + C(7)) \times (C(6) + (7))) \\ 76822 &:= ((-2) - C(2)) + ((8 + C(6)) \times C(7)) \\ 76823 &:= (-((3^2)) + ((8 + C(6)) \times C(7))) \\ 76824 &:= (-((4 \times 2)) + ((8 + C(6)) \times C(7))) \\ 76825 &:= (-((5 + 2)) + ((8 + C(6)) \times C(7))) \\ 76827 &:= -((7 - 2)) + ((8 + C(6)) \times C(7)) \\ 76828 &:= -((8/2)) + ((8 + C(6)) \times C(7)) \\ 76831 &:= -((1^3)) + ((8 + C(6)) \times C(7)) \\ 76832 &:= (C(((2 \times 3) + 8)) + C((6 \times 7))) \\ 76833 &:= ((3/3) + ((8 + C(6)) \times C(7))) \\ 76836 &:= ((6 \times 38) \times (-6) + C(7)) \\ 76874 &:= ((((-4) \times C(7)) \times (-8)) + (6)) \times 7 \\ 76875 &:= (C(5) \times (((7 \times 8) + C(6)) + C(7))) \\ 76925 &:= ((C(5) \times (-2)) - ((-9) - C(6)) \times C(7)) \\ 76942 &:= (2 \times ((C(C(4)) - (9^6)) / (-7))) \\ 76957 &:= -(((C(7) - C(5)) + ((-9) - C(6)) \times C(7))) \\ 77168 &:= (((8 + C(6)) + 1) \times C(7)) - (7) \\ 77175 &:= (((C(5) - C(7)) \times (-1)) + (7)) \times C(7) \\ 77264 &:= -((C(4) - (C(6) \times ((C(2) + (7)) + C(7)))))) \\ 77324 &:= (-4) \times ((2 - C(C(3))) - (-7) - C(7)) \\ 77362 &:= (2 \times (C((6 + C(3))) + C((7 + 7)))) \\ 77364 &:= (-4) \times ((6 - C(C(3))) - (7 - C(7))) \\ 77374 &:= ((-4) \times (C(7) - C(C(3)))) + (7 + 7) \\ 77389 &:= -((C(9) - (((8 - 3)^7) - 7))) \\ 77437 &:= (((-C(7)) + C(C(3))) \times 4) + (77) \\ 77518 &:= (((8 - C((1 \times 5))) + C(7)) \times C(7)) \\ 77539 &:= (((-9) \times C(3)) + (5^7)) - C(7) \\ 77542 &:= -((C(C(2)) + (C(4) - ((5^7) - 7))) \\ 77563 &:= (((-3) - C(6)) + (5^7)) - C(7) \\ 77566 &:= (C(6) + ((C(6) + (5)) \times (C(7) + (7)))) \\ 77648 &:= ((C(8) \times 4) - (C(6) \times (-7) - C(7))) \\ 77672 &:= ((C(C(2)) - ((-7) \times C(6)) \times 7) \times 7) \\ 77673 &:= (((C(3) + C(7)) \times (C(6) - (7))) + C(7)) \\ 77679 &:= ((C(9) \times 7) - (C(6) \times (7 - C(7)))) \\ 77875 &:= (C(5) \times (7 + (8 \times 77))) \\ 77952 &:= ((2 \times (C(5) - 9)) \times (-7) + C(7)) \\ 78128 &:= (8 \times ((C(21) + C(8)) - (7))) \\ 78145 &:= (-5) \times (-4) - C((18 + 7)) \\ 78262 &:= ((-2) - C(6)) \times (-((2 \times 8)) - C(7)) \\ 78273 &:= ((C((C(3) + (7))) \times 2) + (8 - C(7))) \\ 78384 &:= -((4 - 8)) \times (C(C(3)) - 87) \\ 78445 &:= (5 \times (C(4) + C(((4 \times 8) - 7)))) \\ 78543 &:= ((C(C(3)) \times 4) - (C(-(5 - 8))) \times 7) \\ 78546 &:= (-6) \times ((C(45) + C(8)) / (-7)) \\ 78622 &:= (2 \times (C((26 + 8)) + (7))) \\ 78624 &:= (-((4 \times 2)) - C(6)) \times (-8) - C(7) \\ 78634 &:= ((4 \times C(C(3))) - ((6 + 8) \times 7)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 78652 &:= -(((C(C(2)) - C(-((5 - (6 \times 8)))))) + C(7))) \\ 78679 &:= (((-((9 \times 7)) + C(6)) \times C(8)) + C(7)) \\ 78733 &:= ((C(C(3)) \times (-3 - 7)) + (8 - 7)) \\ 78755 &:= (((C(5) + (5^7)) + C(8)) - (7)) \\ 78848 &:= ((C(8)/(-4)) \times (-88 \times 7)) \\ 78875 &:= (C(5) \times ((78 \times 8) + 7)) \\ 79164 &:= (C(((4 \times 6) + 19)) - C(7)) \\ 79233 &:= (-((33 \times (2 - 9))) \times C(7)) \\ 79236 &:= ((C(6) - 3) \times (29 + C(7))) \\ 79244 &:= (44 \times ((2 \times C(9)) + C(7))) \\ 79247 &:= (-7) \times ((-((4^2)) \times C(9)) + C(7)) \\ 79375 &:= (-((C(5) + (7))) + C((C(3) + ((9 + 7)))))) \\ 79424 &:= ((C(C(4)) + C((C(2) + C(4))))/C((9 - 7))) \\ 79454 &:= (((45 + C(4)) \times C(9)) - (7)) \\ 79456 &:= (C((6 + 5)) + (-((4 - 9))^7)) \\ 79473 &:= -(((C(3) + (7)) - C(((4 \times 9) + 7)))) \\ 79483 &:= (-((3 \times 8)) + C(((4 \times 9) + 7))) \\ 79494 &:= (-((4 + 9)) + C(((4 \times 9) + 7))) \\ 79507 &:= C((70 - C(((5 - 9) + 7))) \\ 79522 &:= ((C(2) + C(-((2 - (5 \times 9)))))) + (7)) \\ 79523 &:= (C((3 + (C(2) \times 5))) + (9 + 7)) \\ 79534 &:= (C(43) + C(((5 - 9) + 7))) \\ 79548 &:= (-84) \times ((C(5) - C(9)) - C(7)) \\ 79576 &:= (((6 \times (C(7) + (5)))/9) \times C(7)) \\ 79723 &:= (C((3 \times 2)) + C(-(((C(7) - C(9)) + C(7)))))) \\ 79725 &:= (((-C(5)) + C(((2 - 9) \times C(7)) + C(9)))) + C(7)) \\ 79872 &:= (C(C(2)) \times (78 \times (9 - 7))) \\ 80875 &:= (C(5) \times (7 + (80 \times 8))) \\ 81475 &:= (-5) \times (-((7^{4+1})) + C(8)) \\ 81648 &:= ((84/6) \times C(18)) \\ 81875 &:= (C(5) \times (7 + (81 \times 8))) \\ 82125 &:= (-C(5)) \times (C((C(2) - 1)) - (C((2 + 8)))) \\ 82432 &:= (23 \times (C((4^2)) - C(8))) \\ 82568 &:= (-C(8)) - ((C(6) \times (C(5) - C(C(2)))) + C(8)) \\ 82593 &:= (C((C(3) + 9)) + (C((5 + 28)))) \\ 82649 &:= (C(9) - (((C(4) - C(6)) - C(2)) \times C(8))) \\ 82693 &:= ((C(3) \times (-9) - (-6) \times C(C(2)))) - 8 \\ 82837 &:= ((C(7) \times (C(3) + C((8 - 2)))) - C(8)) \\ 82875 &:= (C(5) \times (7 + (82 \times 8))) \\ 82896 &:= ((C((C(6)/9)) - 8) \times (-2 - 8)) \\ 82936 &:= ((6 \times C(((3 + 9) \times 2))) - 8) \\ 82944 &:= ((C(4) + C(4)) \times ((9^2) \times 8)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 83166 &:= (C(6) + (-6) \times (-1) - C((3 \times 8))) \\ 83256 &:= (-6) \times (-52) - C((3 \times 8)) \\ 83267 &:= (((7 + (-6) \times C(C(2)))) \times (-C(3))) + C(8)) \\ 83287 &:= (C(7) + ((8 - 2) \times C((3 \times 8)))) \\ 83314 &:= ((C((C(4) - 1))/3) - (C(3) + 8)) \\ 83341 &:= ((((-1) + C(4))^3)/3) - 8 \\ 83346 &:= (6 \times ((C(4) + 3) + C((3 \times 8)))) \\ 83349 &:= (9 \times C((4 + ((3 \times 3) + 8)))) \\ 83368 &:= (-8) - ((C((-6) + C(3))) - C(C(3))) \times 8) \\ 83373 &:= (3 \times (((C(7) \times 3) \times C(3)) + 8)) \\ 83376 &:= (C(6) \times ((7 \times (C(3) + C(3))) + 8)) \\ 83528 &:= (8 \times (((C(C(2)) - (C(5))) \times C(3)) - 8)) \\ 83563 &:= (C(C(3)) + ((6 \times C((-5) + C(3)))) - 8) \\ 83564 &:= (((-4) \times ((C(6) \times (-5)) - C(C(3)))) + C(8)) \\ 83586 &:= (-6) + (((C(8) - C(5)) \times C(3)) \times 8) \\ 83592 &:= (((2^9) - C(5)) \times C(3)) \times 8 \\ 83618 &:= (((C(8) + 1) \times 6) \times C(3)) + C(8) \\ 83683 &:= (C(C(3)) + (C(((8 - 6) + 38)))) \\ 83685 &:= (((C((5 \times 8)) - (6)) + C(C(3))) + 8) \\ 83752 &:= ((C((C(2) + (5))) + (7)) \times 38) \\ 83789 &:= ((9 \times (-8) + C((7 \times 3))) + C(8)) \\ 83853 &:= ((C((C(3) - (5))) \times 8) - C((3 + 8))) \\ 83875 &:= (C(5) \times (7 + (83 \times 8))) \\ 83934 &:= (C((4 + C(3))) - ((C(9) - C(38)))) \\ 84125 &:= (C(5) \times (C((C(2) + 1)) - ((C(4) - 8)))) \\ 84132 &:= (((-C(2)) - C(C(3))) + C(-((1 - 48)))) \\ 84135 &:= (((-5) - C(C(3))) + C(-((1 - 48)))) \\ 84456 &:= -(((C(6) \times (C(5) - (4))) - C(48))) \\ 84463 &:= (((-3^6)) + C(44)) + 8 \\ 84469 &:= -(((C(9) - (6)) - C(44)) - 8) \\ 84472 &:= (((C(C(2)) \times (-C(7) + (4)))) + C(C(4))) - 8) \\ 84491 &:= -((C((-19) + C(4))) - C((C(4) - 8))) \\ 84495 &:= -((C((5 \times 9)) - (4))) + C((C(4) - 8)) \\ 84645 &:= ((C(5) + C((C(4) - (6)))) - C(48)) \\ 84666 &:= (-6) + (C(6) \times ((6 \times C(4)) + 8)) \\ 84668 &:= ((C((8 + (6 \times 6))) - (4)) - C(8)) \\ 84671 &:= (-1) + ((7 \times C(6)) \times (C(4) - 8)) \\ 84672 &:= ((C(2) \times 7) \times (C((6 + 4)) + C(8))) \\ 84683 &:= (C((C(3) - 8)) + (((C(6) - C(4)) \times C(8)))) \\ 84736 &:= ((C((-6) + C(3))) + C((7 + 4))) \times 8 \\ 84744 &:= (C(44) + ((-7) \times C(4)) + 8) \\ 84875 &:= (C(5) \times (7 + (84 \times 8))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 84928 &:= ((C(8)/(-2)) + C(((9 \times 4) + 8))) \\ 84964 &:= ((-4) - C(6)) + C(((9 \times 4) + 8)) \\ 84967 &:= (((C(7) - C(6)) \times (C(9) - C(4))) + C(8)) \\ 84992 &:= (((2 \times 9) \times 9) + 4) \times C(8) \\ 85136 &:= ((-6) + C((C(3) - (1 \times 5)))) \times 8 \\ 85144 &:= (C(44) - ((1 \times 5) \times 8)) \\ 85157 &:= (C(-((7 - 51))) - C(-((5 - 8)))) \\ 85176 &:= ((C(6) + C((7 + 1))) \times (C(5) - 8)) \\ 85177 &:= (-7) + (C((7 + 15)) \times 8) \\ 85182 &:= (-2) + C(-(((C((8 - 1)) + C(5)) - C(8)))) \\ 85184 &:= C((((4 \times 8) - 1) + 5) + 8) \\ 85186 &:= ((-6) + C((-81) + C(5))) + 8 \\ 85192 &:= (C((29 + 15)) + 8) \\ 85222 &:= (-2) - ((C(22) + 5) \times (-8)) \\ 85224 &:= (C((42 + 2)) + (5 \times 8)) \\ 85242 &:= (C((2 + 42)) + (58)) \\ 85244 &:= (C(44) + (2 + 58)) \\ 85248 &:= ((C((-8) + C(4)))/2) - (5 \times C(8)) \\ 85249 &:= -((((C(9) + 4) \times (C(2) - C(5))) + C(8))) \\ 85293 &:= (((C(3)/9)^{C(2)}) \times (5 + 8)) \\ 85312 &:= (((C(C(2)) - C((-1) + C(3)))) \times (-5)) - 8 \\ 85317 &:= (C((71 - C(3))) + ((C(5) + 8))) \\ 85325 &:= (C(5) - ((2 + C((C(3) - 5)))) \times (-8)) \\ 85339 &:= (C((-9) + C(3)) + C((35 + 8))) \\ 85344 &:= (((C(44) + C(3)) + C(5)) + 8) \\ 85373 &:= ((C(3) \times 7) - (C((C(3) - 5))) \times (-8)) \\ 85464 &:= ((C(4) + C(6)) + C((4 + (5 \times 8)))) \\ 85527 &:= (C(7) + C(-(((C((2 + 5)) + C(5)) - C(8)))) \\ 85568 &:= ((-8) - C(6)) \times ((5 + C(5)) - C(8)) \\ 85625 &:= (C(5) \times (((C(2) \times 6) + C(5)) + C(8))) \\ 85688 &:= (C(8) + ((C(8) + C(6)) \times (C(5) - 8))) \\ 85723 &:= ((C(3) + C(C(2))) + C(-(((C(7) + C(5)) - C(8)))) \\ 85727 &:= (-7) + (2 \times (C((7 \times 5)) - 8)) \\ 85742 &:= ((-((2 - 4)) \times C((7 \times 5))) - 8) \\ 85752 &:= ((2 \times (5 + C((7 \times 5)))) - 8) \\ 85772 &:= ((2 \times (7 + C((7 \times 5)))) + 8) \\ 85782 &:= (2 \times ((8 + C((7 \times 5))) + 8)) \\ 85875 &:= (C(5) \times (7 + (85 \times 8))) \\ 85944 &:= (C(44) + (95 \times 8)) \\ 85952 &:= (C((2 \times (5 + 9))) + C((5 \times 8))) \\ 86057 &:= -((C(7) - ((50 \times C(6)) \times 8)) \\ 86104 &:= ((401 \times C(6)) - C(8)) \\ 86203 &:= -((C((C(3) + 02)) - C((6 \times 8)))) \\ 86239 &:= ((C(9) \times (C((3 + 2)) - (6))) - C(8)) \\ 86344 &:= (C(44) + ((3 \times C(6)) + C(8))) \\ 86526 &:= ((6 - C(C(2))) \times ((C(5) + C(6)) - C(8))) \\ 86528 &:= (((C(8) - 2) - C(5)) - C(6)) \times C(8) \\ 86632 &:= ((C((2 + 3)) - (6)) \times (C(6) + C(8))) \\ 86813 &:= ((C(C(3)) \times (-1)) - ((8 - C(6)) \times C(8))) \\ 86875 &:= (C(5) \times (7 + (86 \times 8))) \\ 86932 &:= -((C((2 + C(3))) - (C(9) + C((6 \times 8)))) \\ 86967 &:= ((-7) \times C((6 + 9))) + C((6 \times 8)) \\ 87204 &:= ((4 + C(C(02))) \times (-C(7) - C(8))) \\ 87249 &:= ((C(9) + C(C(4))) - (C(2) + C((7 \times 8)))) \\ 87288 &:= (-8) - (((C(8)/(-2)) \times C(7)) + C(8)) \\ 87345 &:= (((-C(5)) - C(C(4)))/(-3)) - (78) \\ 87355 &:= -((C(5) - ((5 \times (3^7) \times 8)))) \\ 87384 &:= ((C(C(4)) + 8)/(-3 \times (7 - 8))) \\ 87424 &:= (C(4) \times (2 - ((-4) \times C(7)) + 8)) \\ 87464 &:= (C(4) + ((C(6) \times (C(4) + C(7))) - C(8))) \\ 87541 &:= (C((1 \times 45)) + (-7) \times C(8)) \\ 87552 &:= -(((2 - 5) \times 57) \times C(8)) \\ 87573 &:= (3 \times (7 - (-57) \times C(8))) \\ 87625 &:= -((C(5) + (-26) \times C((7 + 8)))) \\ 87711 &:= ((C(C((1 + 1))) + (7)) \times (-C(7) - C(8))) \\ 87723 &:= (C(3) \times ((C((2 \times 7)) - (7)) + C(8))) \\ 87744 &:= (C(4) \times ((4 \times C(7)) + ((7 - 8)))) \\ 87752 &:= (((2^5) \times C(7)) - (7)) \times 8 \\ 87864 &:= (((4 \times C((6 + 8))) + (7)) \times 8) \\ 87875 &:= (C(5) \times (7 + (87 \times 8))) \\ 87928 &:= (((8 \times C((2 + 9))) + C(7)) \times 8) \\ 87992 &:= (C(C(2)) + (C((9 + 9)) \times (7 + 8))) \\ 88387 &:= ((C(7) - C(8)) \times ((-3) - C(8)) - 8) \\ 88568 &:= (((8 \times 6) + C(5)) \times C(8)) - 8 \\ 88576 &:= ((C(6) - ((7 \times 5) + 8)) \times C(8)) \\ 88584 &:= (((48 + C(5)) \times C(8)) + 8) \\ 88725 &:= (C((5 + C(2))) - (((C(7) - C(8)) \times C(8)))) \\ 88726 &:= ((C(6) + 2) \times (C(7) + ((8 \times 8)))) \\ 88768 &:= ((-8) \times C((6 \times 7))) + C(88) \\ 88875 &:= (C(5) \times (7 + (8 \times 88))) \\ 89125 &:= (C(5) \times (((C(2) \times (-1)) + C(9)) - 8)) \\ 89344 &:= -((((C(4) + C(4)) \times (C(3) - C(9))) + C(8))) \\ 89352 &:= (((C(C(2)) + C((-5) + C(3))) + 9) \times 8) \\ 89373 &:= (3 \times C((C(7) - (39 \times 8)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 89549 &:= ((-9) \times C(4)) + (C(5) \times (C(9) - 8)) \\ 89625 &:= (C(5) \times (((-2) + C(6)) - 9) + C(8)) \\ 89738 &:= ((C((8 - 3)) \times (-7) + C(9))) - C(8) \\ 89765 &:= (C(5) + (C(6) \times (C(7) + (9 \times 8)))) \\ 89792 &:= ((C(C(2)) \times 9) + C(((C(7) + 9)/8))) \\ 89875 &:= (C(5) \times (7 + (89 \times 8))) \\ 89885 &:= ((C((5 + 88))/9) + C(8)) \\ 89928 &:= (((C(8) + C(2)) + C(9)) \times (9 \times 8)) \\ 90125 &:= (C(5) \times ((C(2) \times (-1)) + C(09))) \\ 90396 &:= (C(((6 + 9) \times 3)) - C(09)) \\ 90549 &:= ((-9) \times C(4)) + C((5 \times 09)) \\ 90625 &:= (C(5) \times ((2 - 6) + C(09))) \\ 90875 &:= (C(5) \times (7 + (80 \times 9))) \\ 91125 &:= C(((5 + 21) + 19)) \\ 91134 &:= (C(((43 + 1) + 1)) + 9) \\ 91144 &:= (C((4 + 41)) + (19)) \\ 91359 &:= (C((9 \times 5)) + ((C(3) - 1) \times 9)) \\ 91395 &:= (C((5 \times 9)) - (C(3) \times (-1 + 9))) \\ 91445 &:= ((5 \times C(4)) + C(((4 + 1) \times 9))) \\ 91512 &:= (C(C(2)) + ((-1) \times C(5)) \times (1 - C(9))) \\ 91525 &:= (5 \times (C((25 + 1)) + C(9))) \\ 91625 &:= (C(5) \times (-((2 - 6)) + C((1 \times 9)))) \\ 91657 &:= -((C(7) - (C(5) \times ((6 + 1) + C(9)))))) \\ 91729 &:= (C(9) + (C(-((2 - 7))) \times (-1) + C(9))) \\ 91852 &:= ((-2) + C((5 \times (8 + 1)))) + C(9) \\ 91854 &:= (C(45) + (81 \times 9)) \\ 91855 &:= ((C((5 + (5 \times 8))) + 1) + C(9)) \\ 92125 &:= (C(5) \times (C(2) + C(((1^2) \times 9)))) \\ 92288 &:= (-(((8 \times 8) \times 2)) \times (C(2) - C(9))) \\ 92296 &:= (((-((C(6) - 9)) + C(C(2))))^2) - (C(9))) \\ 92338 &:= ((-C(8)) + C(C(3))) - (-3) \times C(29) \\ 92344 &:= ((C(4) + (4)) \times (C(3) + C((2 + 9)))) \\ 92375 &:= (C(5) \times (((-7) + C(3))/2) + C(9)) \\ 92376 &:= (C(6) + (((-7) + C(3)) \times C(C(2))) \times 9) \\ 92475 &:= (-5) \times ((7 - (-4) \times C(C(2)))) \times (-9) \\ 92527 &:= ((-7) \times C(2)) + ((C(5) + 2) \times C(9)) \\ 92573 &:= (-((3 + 7)) + ((C(5) + 2) \times C(9))) \\ 92575 &:= -((C(-((5 - 7))) - ((C(5) + 2) \times C(9)))) \\ 92582 &:= ((C(2)/(-8)) + ((C(5) + 2) \times C(9))) \\ 92583 &:= (((C(3) \times (-8)) + C((5 + 2))) \times C(9)) \\ 92591 &:= (-((1 - 9)) + ((C(5) + 2) \times C(9))) \\ 92593 &:= (((C(C(3) + 9)) + (5)) \times 2) - (C(9)) \\ 92596 &:= (((6 + C(9)) \times C(5)) - C(2)) + C(9) \\ 92625 &:= (C(5) \times ((C(2) + (6 - 2)) + C(9))) \\ 92662 &:= ((2 - C(6)) \times ((-C(6)) + C(C(2))) - (C(9))) \\ 92672 &:= (C(C(2)) \times (7 + (6 \times 29))) \\ 92837 &:= ((C(7) + (C(3) \times (-8))) \times (2 + C(9))) \\ 92854 &:= ((C(45) + C((8 + 2))) + C(9)) \\ 93042 &:= ((C((2 + 40)) + C(C(3))) - (C(9))) \\ 93125 &:= (C(5) \times ((2^{1+3}) + C(9))) \\ 93238 &:= (-C(8)) - (C((C(3) - 2)) \times (3 - 9)) \\ 93244 &:= ((-4) - C(4)) - (-2) \times C((C(3) + 9)) \\ 93248 &:= (-C((8 - 4))) - (-2) \times C((C(3) + 9)) \\ 93285 &:= -((C(-((5 - 8))) + (-2) \times C((C(3) + 9)))) \\ 93294 &:= (((C((4 \times 9)) \times 2) - C(3)) + 9) \\ 93311 &:= (-1) + (-((1 - 3)) \times C((C(3) + 9))) \\ 93312 &:= (2 \times C((((1^3) + 3) \times 9)) \\ 93321 &:= ((C(12) \times (C(3) + C(3))) + 9) \\ 93322 &:= (2 \times ((2 + 3) + C((C(3) + 9)))) \\ 93339 &:= ((C((9 + C(3))) + C(3)) + C((C(3) + 9))) \\ 93375 &:= (C(5) \times (((7 \times 3) - 3) + C(9))) \\ 93382 &:= (2 \times ((8 + C(3)) + C((C(3) + 9)))) \\ 93384 &:= (((C(C(4)) + C(8))/3) + C((C(3) - 9))) \\ 93479 &:= ((C((9 + 7)) \times (-4) + C(3)) - C(9)) \\ 93526 &:= ((C(6) - 2) + ((C(5) + 3) \times C(9))) \\ 93528 &:= (C((8 - 2)) + ((C(5) + 3) \times C(9))) \\ 93529 &:= ((C(9) - C(C(2))) + ((C(5) + 3) \times C(9))) \\ 93548 &:= ((C(8) \times 4) - (C(5) \times (-3) - C(9))) \\ 93552 &:= (2 \times ((-5) + C(5)) + C((C(3) + 9))) \\ 93562 &:= ((C(2) - (6)) \times (C(5) + C((C(3) + 9)))) \\ 93625 &:= (C(5) \times ((2 + (6 \times 3)) + C(9))) \\ 93645 &:= ((-C(5)) - C(C(4))) - (-6) \times C(39) \\ 93654 &:= ((4 + C(5)) \times (-((6 - 3)) + C(9))) \\ 93685 &:= ((5 \times C(8)) + C((6 + 39))) \\ 93723 &:= (C(3) + ((2^7) \times (3 + C(9)))) \\ 93734 &:= (-C(4)) + ((C(C(3)) - C((7 \times 3))) \times 9) \\ 93761 &:= (((-1) + C((6 \times 7))) + C(C(3))) - 9 \\ 93771 &:= (C(-((1 - 7) \times 7)) + ((3^9))) \\ 93794 &:= (-4) + (((C(9) - C(7)) \times C(3)) \times 9) \\ 93875 &:= (5 \times (C(7) + (C(8) \times (C(3) + 9)))) \\ 94041 &:= (((1 + C(4)) + C(04)) \times C(9)) \\ 94125 &:= (C(5) \times ((C(2) \times (-1 - 4)) + C(9))) \\ 94157 &:= (-C(7)) - (-C(5)) \times (C(-((1 - 4))) + (C(9))) \\ 94262 &:= (C(C(2)) + (6 \times C(((2^4) + 9)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 94326 &:= ((6 \times C((-2) + C(3))) + (C(4) \times 9)) \\ 94427 &:= -((C(7) + (((-2) - C(4)) - C(4)) \times C(9))) \\ 94436 &:= (C((-6) + C(3)) + (C(44) - 9)) \\ 94438 &:= ((-C((8 + 3))) + C(C(4))) - C((C(4) - 9)) \\ 94462 &:= (-((2 - (6^4))) \times (C(4) + 9)) \\ 94553 &:= (C((3 + 5)) + ((C(5) + (4)) \times C(9))) \\ 94558 &:= ((C(8) + (5)) + ((C(5) + (4)) \times C(9))) \\ 94824 &:= (C((4 + 2)) \times ((C(8) - C(4)) - 9)) \\ 94848 &:= ((C(8)/(-4)) \times (-((8 + 4) - C(9))) \\ 94968 &:= (8 \times ((C(6) \times (-9) + C(4)) - 9)) \\ 95125 &:= (C(5) \times ((2 \times 1)^5 + C(9))) \\ 95221 &:= (C(((1 \times 2) \times C(2))) + (C((5 \times 9)))) \\ 95232 &:= ((C(C(2)) \times 3) \times (-2 + C(-(5 - 9)))) \\ 95247 &:= ((C(7) + ((-4) \times C(C(2))) \times (-5))) \times 9 \\ 95264 &:= ((C(C(4)) - (C(62))) \times (-5 - 9)) \\ 95297 &:= (((-7) + C(9)) \times (C(2) + C(5))) - C(9) \\ 95346 &:= (((C(6)/(-4)) + C((C(3) - (5)))) \times 9) \\ 95365 &:= (-5) \times ((6 - C(C(3))) - (C(5) - C(9))) \\ 95368 &:= ((C(8) + C(6)) \times ((-3) + C(5)) + 9) \\ 95375 &:= ((C(5) \times (7 + C(3))) + C((5 \times 9))) \\ 95384 &:= ((C(4) - C(8)) - (C((C(3) - (5))) \times (-9))) \\ 95395 &:= (5 \times ((C((9 \times 3)) + C(5)) - C(9))) \\ 95424 &:= (C(4) \times (((C(2) + (4)) \times C(5)) - 9)) \\ 95472 &:= (C(2) \times ((C((7 + 4)) - (5)) \times 9)) \\ 95499 &:= (C(9) - ((-((9 - 4)) - C(5)) \times C(9))) \\ 95697 &:= (C(7) \times ((9 \times 6) \times 5) + 9) \\ 95774 &:= (-((C(C(4)) - (7))) + C((7 + C(-(5 - 9)))))) \\ 95787 &:= ((C(((7 + 8) + 7)) - (5)) \times 9) \\ 95832 &:= (C(((-2) + C(3)) - (8 - 5)) \times 9) \\ 95835 &:= (5 \times (C(C(3)) - (C(8) - ((5 - 9)))))) \\ 95838 &:= (-8) - (((C(C(3)) - C(8)) \times (-5)) + 9) \\ 95877 &:= ((C(((7 + 7) + 8)) + (5)) \times 9) \\ 96125 &:= (C(5) \times ((C(2) \times (-1 - 6)) + C(9))) \\ 96159 &:= (((9 + C(5)) - 1) \times (-6 + C(9))) \\ 96224 &:= (-4) - (-((22 \times 6)) \times C(9)) \\ 96228 &:= ((-((82 + 2)) + C(6)) \times C(9)) \\ 96256 &:= ((C(6) \times (-5)) + C(-(C(2) - ((6 \times 9)))))) \\ 96285 &:= ((C(5) + (8 - 2)) \times (6 + C(9))) \\ 96354 &:= (((C(4) + C((-5) + C(3)))) - (6)) \times 9 \\ 96364 &:= (((C(46) - C(3)) - C(6)) - C(9)) \\ 96391 &:= (C((19 + C(3))) - (C(6) + C(9))) \\ 96435 &:= ((5 \times C(C(3))) + ((-4) - C(6)) \times 9) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 96472 &:= -((C(C(2)) + ((C(7) - C(46)) + 9))) \\ 96475 &:= -((((C(5) + (7)) - C(46)) + C(9))) \\ 96625 &:= (C(5) \times ((C(2) + (6 \times 6)) + C(9))) \\ 96634 &:= ((C(C(4)) + C(C(3))) - (C((66 - 9)))) \\ 96643 &:= (C((3 + C(4))) - (C(6) \times (C(6) + C(9)))) \\ 96677 &:= (-7) \times ((7 + 6) - C((C(6)/9))) \\ 96704 &:= (-C(4)) - ((0 - 7) \times C((C(6)/9))) \\ 96741 &:= -((C(-(1 - 4))) + (-7) \times C((C(6)/9)))) \\ 96747 &:= (-7) \times (-((4 - 7) - C((C(6)/9)))) \\ 96753 &:= (-((3 \times 5)) - (-7) \times C((C(6)/9))) \\ 96759 &:= (((C((9 - 5)) \times 7) \times C(6)) - 9) \\ 96761 &:= (-((1 + 6)) - (-7) \times C((C(6)/9))) \\ 96767 &:= (-((7 - 6)) - (-7) \times C((C(6)/9))) \\ 96768 &:= (((8 + 6) - 7) \times C((C(6)/9))) \\ 96783 &:= ((C((3 \times 8)) \times 7) + ((6 + 9))) \\ 96817 &:= (-7) \times ((1 - 8) - C((C(6)/9))) \\ 96822 &:= ((-2) - C(C(2))) + C(-(8 - (6 \times 9))) \\ 96823 &:= (C(((C(3) \times 2) - 8)) + ((C(6) - C(9)))) \\ 96824 &:= (-C((4 \times 2))) + C(-(8 - (6 \times 9))) \\ 96837 &:= ((7 \times C((3 \times 8))) + 69) \\ 96875 &:= (C(5) \times (C(7) + ((8 \times 6) \times 9))) \\ 96876 &:= ((6 \times 78) \times (C(6) - 9)) \\ 96957 &:= (((-7) + C(5)) + ((9 + 6)) \times C(9)) \\ 97125 &:= (C(5) \times ((C(2) \times (-1 - 7)) + C(9))) \\ 97152 &:= (((C(2) + C(5)) - 1) \times (7 + C(9))) \\ 97173 &:= (C(3) \times (C((7 + 1)) + (C(7) \times 9))) \\ 97273 &:= (C(-(3 - (7^2)))) - ((7 \times 9)) \\ 97324 &:= ((-4) - C(2)) + C((37 + 9)) \\ 97327 &:= (-((7 + 2)) + C((37 + 9))) \\ 97328 &:= (-8) + C(-(23 \times (7 - 9))) \\ 97329 &:= (-((9 - 2)) + C((37 + 9))) \\ 97333 &:= (-3) + C(-(33 - 79)) \\ 97334 &:= (C((43 + 3)) + ((7 - 9))) \\ 97335 &:= (-5) \times (C(3) - (C(3) \times (-7) + C(9))) \\ 97336 &:= C((((6 \times 3) + 37) - 9)) \\ 97338 &:= (C(((-8) + C(3)) + C(3))) - ((7 - 9)) \\ 97339 &:= ((9/3) + C((37 + 9))) \\ 97363 &:= (C(3) + C(((-6) - C(3)) + 79)) \\ 97364 &:= (C(46) + (37 - 9)) \\ 97416 &:= (C(6) \times ((1 + C(4)) - C(7)) + C(9)) \\ 97464 &:= (C(46) + (C(4) \times (-7 - 9))) \\ 97479 &:= (((-9) - C(7)) \times (C(4) - C(7))) - C(9) \\ 97524 &:= (-4) \times ((C(C(2)) - (C(5))) \times (-7 \times 9)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 97532 &:= (((C(C(2)) \times (-C(3))) - (5)) \times (-7)) + (C(9))) & 98425 &:= (-5) \times (-2) - C(C(((4+8) - 9)))) \\
 97534 &:= (C(4) + ((C(3) \times 5) \times (-7) + C(9))) & 98434 &:= -((C((-4) + C(3))) - ((C(48) + 9))) \\
 97572 &:= ((C(C(2)) + (7)) \times (C(5) + ((7 \times 9)))) & 98435 &:= (-5) \times ((C(C(3)) + (4)) \times (8 - 9)) \\
 97625 &:= (C(5) \times (-2) - ((C(6) \times (-7)) + C(9))) & 98496 &:= (((C(6) - C(9)) \times C((4+8)))/(-9)) \\
 97632 &:= (-2) \times (C(3) - (67 \times C(9))) & 98533 &:= (((-C(3)) - C(C(3))) \times (-5)) - (8+9)) \\
 97643 &:= -((((C(3) - C(46)) - C(7)) + 9)) & 98545 &:= (-5) \times (C(4) + (C((5+8)) \times (-9))) \\
 97664 &:= (((C(46) - (6)) + C(7)) - 9) & 98625 &:= -((C(5) \times ((C(2) - 68) - C(9)))) \\
 97672 &:= (2 \times (-7) + (67 \times C(9))) & 98632 &:= -((C(C(2)) - (C((3 \times 6)) \times (8+9)))) \\
 97678 &:= (-8) - (((-7) + C(6)) - C(7)) \times C(9)) & 98637 &:= -((7 \times 3) \times (C(6) - C((8+9)))) \\
 97686 &:= ((6 + ((8-6)^7)) \times C(9)) & 98784 &:= ((-((4-8)) \times C(7)) \times (8 \times 9)) \\
 97735 &:= ((5 \times C(C(3))) + ((7 \times 7) - C(9))) & 98793 &:= (((C(3) + 9) \times C(7)) \times 8) + 9 \\
 97746 &:= (((6 - C(4)) + C(7)) \times C(7)) - 9 & 98944 &:= -((C(C(4)) - (C(4) \times (C(9) + C((8+9))))) \\
 97764 &:= -((((C(4) - (6)) - C(7)) \times C(7)) - 9) & 98954 &:= (((4 + C(5)) \times C(9)) + C((8+9))) \\
 97848 &:= (C(8) + C((48+7) - 9)) & 99125 &:= (C(5) \times ((C(2) \times (-1-9)) + C(9))) \\
 97864 &:= ((C(46) + C(8)) + ((7+9))) & 99135 &:= (((5 \times C(3)) + 1) \times C(9)) - 9 \\
 98125 &:= (C(5) \times ((C(2) \times (-1-8)) + C(9))) & 99144 &:= (((4 \times 4) + 1) \times C((9+9))) \\
 98232 &:= (C(2) \times ((3 \times C((2 \times 8))) - 9)) & 99153 &:= (((C(3) \times 5) + 1) \times C(9)) + 9 \\
 98304 &:= (C(((4 \times 03) \times 8))/9) & 99328 &:= (C(8) \times (2 + (C((3+9))/9))) \\
 98313 &:= ((3 \times C(((1+3) \times 8))) + 9) & 99535 &:= (5 \times (C(C(3)) + (C(5) + 99))) \\
 98343 &:= (((C(C(3)) \times 4) + C(C(3))) - ((8 \times 9))) & 99549 &:= (9 \times (((4 \times C(5)) + C(9)) \times 9)) \\
 98345 &:= (((C(5) + C((-4) + C(3)))) \times 8) + 9 & 99584 &:= (C(4) \times (C(8) + ((C(5) - 9) \times 9))) \\
 98353 &:= ((C(C(3)) \times 5) + ((C(3) - (89)))) & 99594 &:= ((C((4+9)) \times (5 \times 9)) + C(9)) \\
 98355 &:= (-5) \times ((-5) - C(C(3))) + (8+9)) & 99864 &:= ((C(4) - C(6)) \times ((8 \times 9) - C(9))) \\
 98358 &:= (-8) + ((5 \times (C(C(3)) - 8)) - 9) & 99875 &:= (C(5) \times (7 + (8 \times 99))) \\
 98375 &:= (-5) \times ((7 - C(C(3))) - ((8-9))) & & \\
 98384 &:= (-((4-8)) \times (C(C(3)) + (C((8+9))))) & & \\
 \end{aligned}$$

4 Summary: Selfie Numbers

The author studied different ways of expressing numbers in such a way that both sides of the expressions are with same digits. One side is with number, and another side is an expression formed by same digits with some operations. These types of numbers we call **selfie numbers**. Some times they are called as **wild narcissistic numbers**. These numbers are represented by their own digits by use of certain operations. Subsections below give different ways of writing **selfie numbers**. Examples of selfie numbers with **Fibonacci sequence**, **Triangular numbers**, etc. In two variables, we obtained selfie numbers with **binomial coefficients**, **S-gonal numbers**, **centered polygonal numbers**, etc. The other way of writing **selfie numbers** is by use of permutable powers, where bases and exponents are of same digits. See the subsection below with some examples.

4.1 Permutable Powers

Below are some examples of **permutable power selfie numbers**. By **permutable powers**, we understand that bases and exponents are of same digits with different permutations. Some times we may call them as **flexible power selfie numbers**.

$$\begin{aligned}
 1 &:= 1^1 & 3529 &:= -3^3 + 5^5 + 2^9 - 9^2 \\
 23 &:= -2^2 + 3^3 & 4316 &:= 4^6 + 3^1 + 1^4 + 6^3 \\
 1239 &:= 1^2 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 9^3 & 4355 &:= 4^5 + 3^4 + 5^3 + 5^5 \\
 1364 &:= 1^6 + 3^1 + 6^4 + 4^3 & 39339 &:= -3^3 + 9^3 + 3^9 + 3^9 - 9^3 \\
 1654 &:= -1^6 + 6^1 + 5^4 + 4^5 & 46350 &:= -4^3 + 6^6 - 3^5 + 5^0 + 0^4 \\
 1837 &:= 1^8 - 8^1 + 3^7 - 7^3 & 46360 &:= 4^0 + 6^6 - 3^4 - 6^3 + 0^6 \\
 2137 &:= -2^1 + 1^3 + 3^7 - 7^2 & 397612 &:= 3^2 + 9^1 + 7^6 + 6^7 + 1^9 + 2^3 \\
 2173 &:= -2^3 + 1^2 - 7^1 + 3^7 & 423858 &:= 4^3 + 2^8 + 3^4 + 8^2 + 5^8 + 8^5 \\
 2537 &:= 2^5 - 5^2 + 3^7 + 7^3 & 637395 &:= 6^5 + 3^3 + 7^3 + 3^9 + 9^6 + 5^7 \\
 3125 &:= -3^2 + 1^1 + 2^3 + 5^5 & 758014 &:= 7^7 + 5^1 + 8^0 + 0^5 + 1^4 - 4^8 \\
 3275 &:= -3^3 + 2^7 + 7^2 + 5^5 & 778530 &:= 7^7 + 7^3 + 8^5 - 5^7 + 3^0 + 0^8 \\
 3435 &:= 3^3 + 4^4 + 3^3 + 5^5 & 804637 &:= 8^0 + 0^4 - 4^8 + 6^6 - 3^3 + 7^7
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 15647982 &:= 1^5 - 5^9 + 6^2 + 4^4 + 7^7 - 9^1 + 8^8 + 2^6 \\
 17946238 &:= 1^6 + 7^8 + 9^4 + 4^2 + 6^9 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 8^7 \\
 57396108 &:= -5^6 + 7^9 + 3^5 + 9^3 + 6^7 + 1^1 + 0^0 + 8^8 \\
 134287690 &:= 1^2 + 3^8 + 4^7 + 2^4 + 8^9 + 7^3 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 0^1 \\
 387945261 &:= 3^3 + 8^2 + 7^6 + 9^9 + 4^7 + 5^8 + 2^4 + 6^1 + 1^5 \\
 392876054 &:= 3^0 + 9^9 - 2^2 - 8^5 + 7^8 - 6^7 + 0^3 - 5^4 + 4^6 \\
 392876540 &:= -3^0 + 9^9 - 2^4 - 8^5 + 7^8 - 6^7 - 5^3 + 4^6 + 0^2
 \end{aligned}$$

More details can be seen in author's work [16].

4.2 Basic Operations

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** by use of **basic operations**. See below some examples in both orders:

$$\begin{aligned}
 13825 &:= 1 + (3 \times 8)^{-2+5} &= ((5 - 2) \times 8)^3 + 1 \\
 14641 &:= (1 + 4 + 6)^4 \times 1 &= (1 + 4 + 6)^4 \times 1 \\
 15552 &:= (1^5 + 5)^5 \times 2 &= 2 \times (6^5 + 5) \times 1 \\
 16377 &:= (1 + 6 - 3)^7 - 7 &= -7 + (7 - 3)^{6+1} \\
 23328 &:= (2 \times 3^3)^2 \times 8 &= (8 - 2)^{3+3} / 2 \\
 116565 &:= (-1 + 16) \times (-5 + 6^5) &= 5 \times (3 \times 6^{6-1} - 1) \\
 131072 &:= (1 + 3)^{1+0+7} \times 2 &= 2^{(7+0-1) \times 3-1} \\
 147419 &:= -1 + (4^7 - 4) \times 1 \times 9 &= 9 \times (1 \times 4^7 - 4) - 1 \\
 147429 &:= 1 + (4^7 - 4/2) \times 9 &= 9 \times (2 + 4^7 - 4 - 1) \\
 147491 &:= 1 \times (4^7 + 4) \times 9 - 1 &= 1 \times 9 \times (4^7 + 4) - 1 \\
 156252 &:= 1 \times 5^6 \times 2 \times 5 + 2 &= 2 \times (5^{2 \times 6-5} + 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

The above numbers are in **digit's order** and in **reverse order of digits**. Below are consecutive sequence values in both ways, i.e., in digit's order and in reverse order of digits:

$$\begin{aligned}
 656250 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 0 = 0 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656251 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 1 = 1 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656252 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 2 = 2 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656253 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 3 = 3 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656254 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 4 = 4 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656255 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 5 = 5 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656256 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 6 = 6 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656257 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 7 = 7 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656258 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 8 = 8 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\
 656259 &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 9 = 9 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6.
 \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [9, 10].

4.3 Factorial

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** with use of **factorial**. See below some examples:

$$\begin{aligned}
 145 &:= 1! + 4! + 5! & 361469 &:= 3! - 6! - 1! + 4! - 6! + 9! \\
 733 &:= 7 + 3!! + 3! & 363239 &:= 36 + 323 + 9! \\
 1463 &:= -1! + 4! + 6! + 3!! & 363269 &:= 363 + 26 + 9! \\
 5177 &:= 5! + 17 + 7! & 364292 &:= 3!! + 6! - 4! - 2! + 9! - 2! \\
 10077 &:= -1! - 0! - 0! + 7! + 7! & 397584 &:= -3!! + 9! - 7! + 5! + 8! + 4! \\
 40585 &:= 4! + 0! + 5! + 8! + 5! & 398173 &:= 3! + 9! + 8! + 1! - 7! + 3! \\
 80518 &:= 8! - 0! - 5! - 1! + 8! & 403199 &:= 40319 + 9! \\
 317489 &:= -3! - 1! - 7! - 4! - 8! + 9! & 408937 &:= -4! + 0! + 8! + 9! + 3!! + 7! \\
 352797 &:= -3! + 5 - 2! - 7! + 9! - 7! & 715799 &:= -7! - 1! + 5! - 7! + 9! + 9! \\
 357592 &:= -3! - 5! - 7! - 5! + 9! - 2! & 720599 &:= -7! - 2! + 0! - 5! + 9! + 9! \\
 357941 &:= 3! + 5! - 7! + 9! - 4! - 1!
 \end{aligned}$$

The above numbers are in **digit's order** and are only with positive and negative coefficients. Below are consecutive sequence values in both ways:

$$\begin{aligned}
 35280 &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 0 = 0 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35281 &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 1 = 1 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35282 &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 2 = 2 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35283 &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 3 = 3 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35284 &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 4 = 4 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35285 &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 5 = 5 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\
 35286 &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 6 = 6 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 35287 &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 7 = 7 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\ 35288 &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 8 = 8 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\ 35289 &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 9 = 9 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [22, 23].

4.4 Square-Root

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** with use of **square-root**. See below some examples in both orders, i.e., in **digit's order** and in **reverse order of digits**:

$1764 := 1 \times (7 \times 6)^{\sqrt{4}}$ $2378 := -23 + \sqrt{7^8}$ $19454 := 19 \times 4^5 - \sqrt{4}$ $19459 := 19 \times 4^5 + \sqrt{9}$ $19684 := 1 + \sqrt{9\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}/4}}$ $839793 := (-8 + (-3 + 9)^7 + \sqrt{9}) \times 3$ $839795 := -8 + (-3 + 9)^7 \times \sqrt{9} - 5$ $839804 := (-8 + (3 - 9)^8 + 0) / \sqrt{4}$ $839816 := (8 + (3 - 9)^8) / \sqrt{\sqrt{16}}$ $995544 := ((9 + \sqrt{9})^5 + 54) \times 4$ $999916 := -9 \times 9 - \sqrt{9} + (9 + 1)^6$ $999976 := -\sqrt{9} \times 9 + \sqrt{9} + (\sqrt{9} + 7)^6$	$64 := \sqrt{4^6}$ $1024 := \sqrt{\sqrt{4^{20}}} \times 1$ $1296 := 6^{\sqrt{9}+2-1}$ $2189 := \sqrt{9^{8-1}} + 2$ $3867 := (-7 + \sqrt{6^8}) \times 3$ $9375 := \sqrt{5^{7+3}} \times 9$ $12289 := \sqrt{9} \times 8^{2 \times 2} + 1$ $19693 := 3^9 + 6 + \sqrt{9} + 1$ $42436 := (6 \times 34 + 2)^{\sqrt{4}}$ $59051 := \sqrt{-1 + 5} + 0 + 9^5$ $999901 := (10^{9-\sqrt{9}}) - 99$ $999991 := (1^9 + 99)^{\sqrt{9}} - 9$
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First column numbers are in **digit's order** and second columns are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details refer author's work [9, 10].

4.5 Factorial and Square-Root

Below are some examples with **factorial** and **square-root** written in both ways, i.e., in **digit's order** and its reverse

$$\begin{aligned} 936 &:= (\sqrt{9})!^3 + 6! &= 6! + (3!)^{\sqrt{9}} \\ 1296 &:= \sqrt{(1 + 2)!^9 / 6} &= 6^{(\sqrt{9}+2-1)} \\ 2896 &:= 2 \times (8 + (\sqrt{9})!! + 6!) &= (6! + (\sqrt{9})!! + 8) \times 2 \\ 331779 &:= 3 + (31 - 7)^{\sqrt{7+9}} &= \sqrt{9} + (7 \times 7 - 1)^3 \times 3 \\ 342995 &:= (3^4 - 2 - 9)^{\sqrt{9}} - 5 &= -5 + (-9 + 9^2 - \sqrt{4})^3 \\ 759375 &:= (-7 + 59 - 37)^5 &= (5 + 7 + 3)^{\sqrt{9}-5+7} \\ 759381 &:= 7 + (5 \times \sqrt{9})^{-3+8} - 1 &= -1 + (8 \times 3 - 9)^5 + 7. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 5040 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 0 = 0 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 5041 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 1 = 1 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 5042 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 2 = 2 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 5043 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 3 = 3 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 5044 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 4 = 4 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 5045 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 5 = 5 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 5046 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 6 = 6 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 5047 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 7 = 7 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 5048 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 8 = 8 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)! \\
 5049 &:= (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 9 = 9 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!
 \end{aligned}$$

The following examples are in **digit's order** and its **reverse** separately:

$120 := ((1 + 2)! - 0)! $	$25 := 5^2 $
$127 := -1 + 2^7 $	$64 := \sqrt{4^6} $
$1673 := -1 - 6 + 7!/3 $	$289 := (9 + 8)^2 $
$1679 := 1 + (-6 + 7!)/\sqrt{9} $	$3894 := (\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{(\sqrt{9})!^8}) \times 3 $
$1680 := (1 + 6)!/\sqrt{8 + 0!} $	$4957 := 7! - 59 - 4! $
$38970 := -3!! + 8! - 9 \times 70 $	$6992 := 2^9 + 9 \times 6! $
$38986 := -3 + 8! - \sqrt{(\sqrt{9} + 8)^6} $	$26493 := (2 + 6)! - 4!^{\sqrt{9}} - 3 $
$40310 := (\sqrt{4^{03}})! - 10 $	$30792 := 3! \times ((0 + 7)! + 92) $
$90894 := -(\sqrt{9})! + ((0! + 8)! + (\sqrt{9})!!)/4 $	$54476 := (5! + 4!^4 - 7!)/6 $
$91560 := ((\sqrt{9})! + 1)! + 5! \times (6! + 0!) $	$75989 := \sqrt{9} \times (8 - (\sqrt{9})!!) + 5^7 $

First column numbers are in **digit's order** and second columns are in **reverse order of digits**. For details refer author's work [9, 10, 11].

4.6 Fibonacci Sequence

Fibonacci sequence numbers are well known in literature. This sequence is defined as

$$F(0) = 0, \quad F(1) = 1, \quad F(n + 1) = F(n) + F(n - 1), \quad n \geq 1.$$

Below are examples of **selfie numbers** by use of **Fibonacci sequence values**. This we have done in different situations, such as using $F(\cdot)$ and $F(F(\cdot))$ in separate works. See below examples:

$$\begin{aligned}
 143 &:= -1 + F(4 \times 3) &= F(3 \times 4) - 1 \\
 986 &:= F(9) \times (F(8) + F(6)) &= (F(6) + F(8)) \times F(9) \\
 1178 &:= F(11) \times F(7) + F(8) &= F(8) + F(7) \times F(11)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 2585 &:= F(2) + F(5 + 8 + 5) &= F(5 + 8 + 5) + F(2) \\
 12819 &:= 1 + F(2 \times (8 - 1)) \times F(9) &= F(9) \times F((-1 + 8) \times 2) + 1 \\
 24297 &:= F(2 \times 4) \times F(2 + 9) \times F(7) &= F(7) \times F(9 + 2) \times F(4 \times 2) \\
 39394 &:= -3 + 93 + F(9)^{F(4)} &= (-4 + F(9)) \times 3 + F(9)^3 \\
 74997 &:= -7 \times 4 + F(9 + 9 + 7) &= F(7 + 9 + 9) - 4 \times 7 \\
 87937 &:= -8 + F(7) \times F(9 \times 3 - 7) &= F(7) \times F(3 \times 9 - 7) - 8 \\
 98703 &:= 9 \times (F(8) + F(7 \times 03)) &= (F(3 \times 07) + F(8)) \times 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$34 := F(3 \times F(4))$	$36 := 6^{F(3)}$
$233 := F(F(-2 + 3 \times 3))$	$143 := F(3 \times 4) - 1$
$630 := F(F(6)) \times 30$	$231 := F(13) - 2$
$1178 := F(11) \times F(7) + F(8)$	$377 := F(-7 + 7 \times 3)$
$2079 := (-2 + F(F(07))) \times 9$	$986 := (F(6) + F(8)) \times F(9)$
$4864 := F(F(4))^8 \times (F(F(6)) - F(F(4)))$	$1165 := 5 \times F(F(6 \times 1 + 1))$
$8759 := -F(9 - 5)^7 + F(F(8))$	$1596 := F(F(6) + 9) - F(F(F(5 - 1)))$
$8849 := -9 \times F(F(F(F(F(4)))) - 8) + F(F(8))$	$2592 := F(2 \times 9) + F(5 + F(2))$
$9349 := -F(F(9)/F(F(4))) + F(F(F(-3 + 9)))$	$9756 := F(F(F(6))) - 5 \times 7 \times F(9)$

$$\begin{aligned}
 834660 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 0 = 0 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834661 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 1 = 1 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834662 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 2 = 2 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834663 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 3 = 3 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834664 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 4 = 4 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834665 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 5 = 5 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834666 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 6 = 6 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834667 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 7 = 7 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834668 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 8 = 8 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 834669 &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 9 = 9 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)).
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 21960 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21961 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21962 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21963 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21964 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21965 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21966 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21967 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21968 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 21969 &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2.
 \end{aligned}$$

First three blocks are in both ways. In the last block the first column values are in **digit's order** and the second columns values are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details see author's [19, 20].

4.7 Triangular Numbers

Triangular numbers are very much famous in the literature of mathematics. The general formula to write these numbers is given by

$$T(n) = 1 + 2 + 3 + \dots = \frac{n+1}{2} = C(n+1, 2).$$

The examples given in above subsections are with **factorial**, **square-root**, **Fibonacci sequence** numbers, etc. Still, one can have similar kind of results using **Triangular numbers**. See below some examples:

$1069 := T(10) - T(6) + T(T(9))$ $1081 := T(1 + T(08 + 1))$ $2887 := T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(8) + T(8)) + T(7)$ $4965 := T(-4 + 9) + T(-T(6) + T(T(5)))$ $4999 := 49 + T(99)$ $99545 := T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 5$ $99546 := T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 6.$	$874 := T(T(T(4))) - T(T(7) + 8)$ $0105 := 50 + T(10)$ $1155 := -T(T(5)) + T(51 - 1)$ $1224 := T(T(T(4)) - T(T(2))) - 2 + 1$ $2418 := T(81) - T(42)$ $99632 := 2 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9)$ $99633 := 3 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9).$
--	---

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second column values are in **reverse order of digits**. In consecutive sequential values we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
 2210 &:= T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 0 = 0 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 2211 &:= T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 1 = 1 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 2212 &:= T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 2 = 2 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 2213 &:= T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 3 = 3 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 2214 &:= T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 4 = 4 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 2215 &:= T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 5 = 5 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 2216 &:= T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 6 = 6 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 2217 &:= T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 7 = 7 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 2218 &:= T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 8 = 8 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) \\
 2219 &:= T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 9 = 9 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))).
 \end{aligned}$$

For more details see author's work [17].

4.8 Binomial Coefficients

Binomial coefficients are well known in literature. They are given by

$$C(m, r) = \frac{m!}{r! \times (m-r)!}, \quad m \geq r \geq 0, \quad m, r \in \mathbf{N}.$$

In above subsections, we gave examples of selfie numbers with **Fibonacci sequence**, **Triangular numbers**, etc. Still, one can have similar kind results using **binomial coefficients**. See below some examples written in **both ways**, **digit's order** and **reverse order of digits**:

$$\begin{aligned} 6435 &:= C(C(6, 4), 3 + 5) = C(5 \times 3, \sqrt{4} + 6) \\ 15504 &:= C(15 + 5, 0! + 4) = C(4 \times 05, 5 \times 1) \\ 42504 &:= C(4!, \sqrt{2 \times 50/4}) = C(4!, -05 + 24) \\ 54264 &:= C(5 + 4^2, C(6, 4)) = C(4! - 6/2, (\sqrt{4 + 5})!) \\ 74613 &:= C(7 \times 4 - 6, 1 \times 3!) = C(3! + 16, (-4 + 7)!). \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 12650 &:= C(-1 + 26, 5 - 0!) & 28 &:= C(8, 2) \\ 12870 &:= C(1 \times 2 \times 8, 7 + 0!) & 792 &:= C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7) \\ 14950 &:= C(-1 + 4! + \sqrt{9}, 5 - 0!) & 924 &:= C(4!/2, (\sqrt{9})!) \\ 18564 &:= C(18, (5 - 6 + 4)!) & 2024 &:= C(4!, 2 + (0 \times 2)!) \\ 19448 &:= C(19 - \sqrt{4}, \sqrt{4} + 8) & 4845 &:= C(5 \times 4, 8 - 4) \\ 26334 &:= C(2 + C(6, 3), 3 + \sqrt{4}) & 00378 &:= C(C(8, \sqrt{7-3}), 0! + 0!) \\ 43758 &:= C(4! - 3!, 7 - 5 + 8) & 00792 &:= C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7 - 0! - 0!) \\ 53130 &:= C(5^{3-1}, 3! - 0!). & 00924 &:= C(4!/2, \sqrt{9} \times (0! + 0!)). \end{aligned}$$

Consecutive sequential representations:

$$\begin{aligned} 25920 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 0 & 98280 &:= 0 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 25921 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 1 & 98281 &:= 1 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 25922 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 2 & 98282 &:= 2 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 25923 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 3 & 98283 &:= 3 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 25924 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 4 & 98284 &:= 4 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 25925 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 5 & 98285 &:= 5 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 25926 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 6 & 98286 &:= 6 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 25927 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 7 & 98287 &:= 7 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 25928 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 8 & 98288 &:= 8 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 25929 &:= (-2 + 5)!! \times C(9, 2) + 9. & 98289 &:= 9 + C(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}). \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [18].

4.9 S-gonal numbers

The formula for **S-gonal numbers** is given by

$$P(n, s) := \frac{n(n-1)(s-2)}{2} + n, \quad s > 2.$$

This subsection brings some examples of selfie numbrs using **S-gonal numbers**. These examples are in **digit's order** and in **reverse order of digits**:

$$\begin{aligned}
 4992 &:= P(4!, 9 + 9 + 2) & 8967 &:= 7 \times P(P(6, \sqrt{9}), 8) \\
 7744 &:= (P(7, 7) - 4!)^{\sqrt{4}} & 9504 &:= 4! \times P(\sqrt{0! + 5!}, 9) \\
 7896 &:= 7 \times P(8 \times \sqrt{9}, 6) & 9744 &:= 4! \times P(4 \times 7, \sqrt{9}) \\
 65485 &:= -P(6, 5) + \sqrt{4} \times 8^5 & 49281 &:= 1 \times 8! + P(29, 4!) \\
 65943 &:= P(6, 5) \times ((\sqrt{9})!^4 - 3) & 49548 &:= -8! - P(4!, 5) + 9!/4 \\
 67977 &:= (6 + 7) \times (P(9, 7) + 7!) & 50424 &:= 4! \times P(-2 + 4!, \sqrt{0! + 5!}) \\
 72495 &:= -P(7 + 2, 4) + 9!/5 & 52895 &:= (5 + P(9, 8))^2 - 5 \\
 83544 &:= \sqrt{P(8, 3)} \times (5! - \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{4}}. & 53995 &:= (5! - P(9, \sqrt{9})) \times 3!! - 5.
 \end{aligned}$$

The consecutive sequential examples are given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 86640 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 0 & 5640 &:= 0 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86641 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 1 & 5641 &:= 1 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86642 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 2 & 5642 &:= 2 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86643 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 3 & 5643 &:= 3 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86644 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 4 & 5644 &:= 4 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86645 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 5 & 5645 &:= 5 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86646 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 6 & 5646 &:= 6 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86647 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 7 & 5647 &:= 7 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86648 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 8 & 5648 &:= 8 + P(4!, 6) \times 5 \\
 86649 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 9. & 5649 &:= 9 + P(4!, 6) \times 5.
 \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [12].

4.10 Centered Polygonal Numbers

The formula for **centered polygonal numbers** is given by

$$K(n, t) := \frac{tn(n-1)}{2} + 1, \quad t > 2.$$

Below are some examples of selfie numbers with **centered polygonal numbers**. These are in **digit's order** and **inreverse order of digits**:

$$\begin{aligned}
 2883 &:= K(2 \times 8, 8) \times 3 & 00938 &:= K(\sqrt{K(8, 3!)}, (\sqrt{9})!) \times (0! + 0!) \\
 2888 &:= K(2 + 8, 8) \times 8 & 01051 &:= K(15, 010) \\
 3640 &:= K(3!, 6) \times 40 & 01199 &:= K(9, \sqrt{9}) \times (1 + 10) \\
 14939 &:= -1 + (K(4!, (\sqrt{9})!) + 3) \times 9 & 59938 &:= K(8, 3!) + (\sqrt{9})!! + 9^5 \\
 14959 &:= (-1 + K(4!, (\sqrt{9})!) + 5) \times 9 & 62424 &:= 4! \times K(2 + 4!, 2 + 6) \\
 15144 &:= K(15, (-1 + 4)!) \times 4! & 63384 &:= 4! + (K(8, 3) + 3) \times 6! \\
 15347 &:= (-1 + 5)! \times 3!! - K(4!, 7) & 63744 &:= 4! \times (K(4!, 7) + 3 + 6!) \\
 15399 &:= K(1 \times 5!/3!, 9) \times 9 & 63973 &:= K(3! + 7, 9) \times K(3!, 6).
 \end{aligned}$$

The consecutive sequential examples are given by

$$\begin{aligned}
 99360 &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 0 = 0 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 99361 &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 1 = 1 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 99362 &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 2 = 2 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 99363 &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 3 = 3 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 99364 &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 4 = 4 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 99365 &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 5 = 5 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 99366 &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 6 = 6 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 99367 &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 7 = 7 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 99368 &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 8 = 8 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} \\
 99369 &:= K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 9 = 9 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}.
 \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [12].

4.11 Quadratic-Type Selfies

The formula for **quadratic numbers** is given by

$$Q(n) := n^2, \quad n > 0, n \in \mathbb{N}.$$

Below are some examples of selfie numbers with **quadratic-type selfie numbers**. These are in **digit's order** and **inreverse order of digits**:

$48 := -Q(4) + Q(8)$	$49 := Q((-9) + Q(4))$
$81 := Q(8 + 1)$	$89 := Q(9) + 8$
$128 := 1 \times 2 \times Q(8)$	$224 := ((Q(4) - 2) \times Q(Q(2)))$
$292 := Q(Q(Q(2))) + 9 \times Q(2)$	$275 := Q(5) \times (7 + Q(2))$
$322 := Q(Q(3) \times 2) - 2$	$736 := (Q((Q(6) - Q(3))) + (7))$
$1036 := 10^3 + Q(6)$	$0107 := 7 + Q(010)$
$1125 := Q(11 + Q(2)) \times 5$	$0231 := -((Q(13) - Q(20)))$
$1729 := 1 \times 7 \times (Q(Q(Q(2))) - 9)$	$1257 := 7 + Q(Q(5)) \times 2 \times 1$
$9843 := ((Q((-9) + Q(8))) + Q(Q(4))) \times 3$	$2239 := ((-Q(9) + Q((3 \times Q(Q(2)))))) + (Q(Q(2)))$
$10025 := ((100^2) + Q(5))$	$08136 := (Q(6) + Q((Q(3) + ((1 + 80))))$
$10384 := (((-1) - ((0 - Q(Q(3))) \times (-8))) \times (-Q(4)))$	$15323 := (Q(Q(Q(3))) + ((Q(Q(Q(2))) + (Q(Q(3)))) \times (Q(5) + 1)))$
$99378 := (9 \times ((Q(93) + Q(Q(7))) - 8))$	$37293 := (-3) + (((Q(Q(9)) - Q(Q(2))) - Q(Q(7))) \times Q(3))$

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second column values are in **reverse order of digits**. In consecutive sequential values we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
 12680 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 0 = 0 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12681 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 1 = 1 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12682 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 2 = 2 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12683 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 3 = 3 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12684 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 4 = 4 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12685 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 5 = 5 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12686 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 6 = 6 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12687 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 7 = 7 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12688 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 8 = 8 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1)) \\
 12689 &:= (Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [21].

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